

**Neural Connectivity of the Rat: Theory, Methods and
Applications**

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Declaration

All data collation, programming and data analysis reported in this thesis were performed by me, except for the MBOLTZMANN optimisation program that was developed by Dr Mark O'Neill.

No part of this thesis has been accepted or is currently being submitted for any degree or diploma or other qualification in this University or elsewhere.

Newcastle, 31st July 1997.

It is easy to impose
a pattern
less easy to make it
stick
less still
to discover one there

‘Building a Snowman’

Richard Burns.

“One must think like a hero to behave like a merely decent human being.”

Mary Sarton.

“Neuroanatomy is dull and usually correct, whereas neurophysiology is exciting and usually wrong.”

Attributed to David Hubel by Semir

Zeki.

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Abstract

Objective analysis of the network of connections between brain areas and nuclei can provide insight into the organisation of neural systems. The rat brain can be parcellated into hundreds of different regions, areas and nuclei at a variety of scales. Current knowledge of the connections between these brain regions is distributed throughout the literature in thousands of papers.

I describe a computational database that can accurately represent this large and complex data set in a mathematically tractable form. I entered over ten thousand separate data entries to provide a detailed description of the connectivity of the early visual and limbic systems of the rat, as well as a coarse description of the connections across the whole brain. I devised and applied a novel method to estimate weights for neural connections in these systems.

Previous analyses typically use two dimensional nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) to visualise brain connection data. I developed an approach to the study of neural systems that uses NMDS in coordinate spaces with more than three dimensions. I analysed the connectivity of all retinal efferent pathways to describe the organisation of the rat's early visual system in terms of purely neuroanatomical information. Two and five dimensional NMDS were combined with nonparametric cluster analysis to group together brain structures with similar connectivity. I also used this methodology to analyse the connectivity of a set of limbic brain structures,

putatively involved in spatial navigation in the rat. The schemes that these analyses produced, corroborate known organisational features of the systems in question.

Contents

1. A Theoretical Approach To Systems Level Neuroanatomy.....	2
1.1. Introduction.....	2
1.2. Parcellation schemes: the grey box doctrine.....	5
1.3. Theoretical framework of neuroanatomical connectivity.....	9
1.3.1. Basic ideas.....	9
1.3.2. Definitions of connection strength.....	10
1.3.3. Substructure and subnodes.....	13
1.3.4. Issues not covered by this model.....	14
1.4. Neuroanatomical tract-tracing experiments.....	14
1.4.1. The basic design of tract-tracing experiments.....	15
1.4.2. Problems arising from the methodology.....	16
1.4.3. Dynamics of chemical tracer methods.....	19
1.5. The proximity model of neural connectivity.....	24
1.5.1. Connections are directional, distances are not.....	27
1.5.2. How are nonconnections represented?.....	28
1.5.3. How can we represent non-Euclidean connection matrices?.....	31
1.5.4. High dimensionality.....	32
1.5.5. Conclusions.....	33

1.6. Thesis plan.	35
2. Methods.....	37
2.1. Neurobase: a neuroanatomical connection databasing system.	37
2.1.1. Parcellation table.....	37
2.1.2. Connection tables.....	38
2.1.3. Data matrices and summary tables.	44
2.2. Methods of analysis of neuroanatomical data.....	44
2.2.1. Pathway tracing analyses.	45
2.2.2. Calculating ordinal connection weights for neural connections from noncomparable neuroanatomical studies.	46
2.2.3. NMDS analyses	54
2.2.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis.....	65
3. Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling in High-Dimensional Euclidean Space and its Relevance To Neural Connectivity Data.....	74
3.1. Introduction.....	74
3.2. Objectives of chapter.	77
3.3. Methods.....	78
3.3.1. Configuration generation	78
3.3.2. NMDS, procrustes and stress.....	83
3.3.3. Methods of each section.	83

3.4. Results.....	85
3.4.1. High-dimensional, high-ordinal data.	85
3.4.2. High-dimensionality, low-ordinality data.....	88
3.4.3. Decreased-dimensionality, low-ordinality data.	93
3.4.4. Other methods of dimensional reduction.....	97
3.4.5. The effect of different cost functions.....	100
3.5. Discussion.....	104
4. The Connectivity of the Rat’s Visual System.	108
4.1. Introduction.....	108
4.2. Basic pathway analysis	113
4.2.1. How many ‘retinal pathways’ are there?	113
4.2.2. Discussion	122
4.3. NMDS analysis of first stage retinal efferents.....	122
4.3.1. Introduction.....	122
4.3.2. Methods	124
4.3.3. Results.....	126
4.3.4. Discussion.....	137
4.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from the retinal efferent connection matrix.	139
4.4.1. Introduction.....	139

4.4.2. Methods.....	140
4.4.3. Results.....	140
4.4.4. Discussion.....	161
4.5. Subparcellation analysis	162
4.6. Connection strength estimation.....	166
4.6.1. Pathway analysis.....	167
4.6.2. Connection weight estimation for the retinal efferent matrix.....	172
4.7. NMDS analysis based on a connection weight estimates for a matrix.....	175
4.7.1. Methods	175
4.7.2. Results.....	176
4.7.3. Discussion.....	178
4.8. Extension of the NMDS proximity method to the next stage of the visual system.....	179
4.8.1. Introduction.....	179
4.8.2. Methods	180
4.8.3. Results.....	182
4.8.4. Control analyses.....	186
4.8.5. Discussion.....	190
4.9. Discussion.....	192

5. Proximity Analysis of the Connectional Organisation of Central Systems Involved in Spatial Memory in Rats.....	198
5.1. Introduction.....	198
5.2. Neuroanatomical data	200
5.2.1. Similarity matrices.....	201
5.3. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling results.....	201
5.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis	209
5.4.1. A comparison between cluster analyses taken from NMDS analyses of different similarity matrices.....	214
5.4.2. Differences between cluster schemes of NMDS configurations with different numbers of dimensions.....	223
5.4.3. Summary of results	227
5.5. Connection weight estimates for this system.....	230
5.5.1. Introduction.....	230
5.5.2. Analysis of the whole connection matrix.	231
5.6. Discussion.....	238
6. General Discussion.....	245
6.1. Summary.....	245
6.2. What can be deduced from these studies?	247
6.2.1. The definition of neural systems.....	248

6.2.2. The need for quantitative data.	249
6.2.3. The relationship between structure and function.....	252
6.3. Future ideas: A unified mathematical framework for neuroanatomical, neurophysiological and connectional data	253
References.....	259
Appendix A : Parcellation Scheme.....	288
Appendix B : Reference Scheme.....	295
Appendix C : Connection Tables.....	301
First stage retinal connection table.	301
Second Stage Retinal Connection Matrix.	349
Limbic System Matrix.	414
Appendix D : A Comparison Table For Retinal Efferents.	474
Appendix E : Stress Values.	483

Figures and Tables

Figures

Figure 1-1: An example of a graph describing the connectivity of a neural circuit. ...	10
Figure 1-2: Definitions of ‘neuronal connection strength’ for AB.....	10
Figure 1-3: Two equivalent ‘grey box’ connections where each dot might represent 10 neurons.....	13
Figure 1-4: Dendritic connections. Despite the fact that Area C projects to A but not to B, some neurons in B receive direct synaptic input from C because their dendrites extend into A.	14
Figure 1-5: Conceptual diagram showing the basic design of a tract-tracing experiment with typical retrograde and anterograde labelling. Red arrows with solid arrowheads illustrate zones of potential uptake on cells. Red arrows with open arrowheads illustrate the retrograde and anterograde transport that gives rise to labelling in the cells shown.....	16
Figure 1-6: A tract-tracing experiment with several possible types of nonideal labelling.	17
Figure 1-7: If area A receives connections from areas B and C, the injection site shown will only label cells in area C.	19
Figure 1-8: ‘A proposed neural circuit for emotion’, from figure 47.2 of Kandel, Schwarz and Jessel 1991.....	25
Figure 1-9: An example of a set of distances that satisfy the metric inequality but which have no Euclidean representation (Not to scale; from Gower and Legendre 1986)	31
Figure 2-1: The tree structure of the CA1 field of the hippocampus.....	38

Figure 2-2: Excerpt from Neurobase connection database. The two connections are from Sesack et al. 1989, Journal of Comparative Neurology 290:213-242. The use of abbreviations to describe features was necessary since the length of data fields in Microsoft Excel is restricted to 255 characters..... 40

Figure 2-3: The subparcellation problem..... 46

Figure 2-4: Idealised diagram of subparcellated connection data. 49

Figure 2-5: An observation matrix, C^{eg} . The matrix contains 15 separate data entries. I have only considered the lower triangle since the data is symmetrical. 55

Figure 2-6: Dissimilarity matrix, Δ^{eg} . This is a measure of the level of ‘noninteraction’ between objects 1 to 6..... 55

Figure 2-7: Examples of ordinal dissimilarity matrices..... 56

Figure 2-8: Initial configuration of six points for test data..... 60

Figure 2-9: Graph of disparity and distance, displaying concept of monotone regression.. The graph displays the distance and disparity values for a ‘high stress’ initial configuration prior to optimisation. 60

Figure 2-10: Graph of disparity and distance, displaying effect of monotone regression optimisation. 61

Figure 2-11: This figure illustrates the interactions between objects 1 to 6 in a two-dimensional configuration of points calculated by MDS in the SAS statistical package. 61

Figure 2-12: Illustration of the pathlength transform. AB and AC are both ‘0’ values but under the pth1 transform we recognize the ADB path as shorter than the ADC path, because the sum of the intermediate nonzero observations along the ADB path is greater than that of those along the ADC path..... 62

Figure 3-1: Different shapes of configurations of 1000 points..... 79

Figure 3-2: Representations of the frequency distributions of the distances of each of the four shapes described above. This is a global, graphical representation of proximity(distances) in configurations, and illustrates the differences between ‘filled’ and ‘empty’ configurations in terms of the shape of the frequency distribution of distances. 81

Figure 3-3: The relationship between Procrustes R^2 values and number of dimensions for comparisons between configurations, and reconstructed NMDS configurations calculated from high-dimensional, maximally ordinal distance matrices. This graph also illustrates the effect of having a larger number of constraints in the original matrix. Error bars were calculated as standard errors calculated with $n=11$ 86

Figure 3-4: Graph of stress values plotted against number of dimensions in the final configuration of NMDS solutions from maximally ordinal dissimilarities with no dimensional reduction. The number of objects in each configuration was either equal to the number of dimensions plus one (denoted by ‘ $N=M+1$ ’) or twice this value (denoted by ‘ $N=2[M+1]$ ’)..... 87

Figure 3-5: Procrustes R^2 values for NMDS solutions with a reduced total number of ranks. Error bars were calculated as standard errors. 89

Figure 3-6: Procrustes R^2 values for NMDS solutions with a reduced total number of ranks. The number of points in each configuration, N , was equal to $N=2(M+1)$ where M is the number of dimensions in the original configuration 90

Figure 3-7: Stress values for the degraded ordinal matrices representing configurations where $N=M+1$ 91

Figure 3-8: Stress Values for the degraded ordinal matrices representing configurations where $N=2[M+1]$ 92

Figure 3-9: This figure shows how the actual fit between the original configuration and dimensionally reduced NMDS solutions is dependent upon the number of points and dimensions in the original configuration and NMDS solution. This data was obtained from five filled hyperspherical configuration, where the number of points in the configuration was equal to the number of dimensions plus one. 94

Figure 3-10: This figure shows how the actual fit between the original configuration and dimensionally reduced NMDS solutions is dependent on the number of points and dimensions in the original configuration and NMDS solution. This data was obtained from five filled hyperspherical configurations, where the number of points in the configuration was equal $2(M+1)$ where M is the number of dimensions. 95

Figure 3-11: Stress values for NMDS solutions calculated at intermediate dimensionalities where the number of ranks is diminished. 96

Figure 3-12: Procrustes R^2 values for comparisons of the principal components of NMDS solutions and the original configurations. Only results for the 16 point, 15-dimensional configurations are presented here. 98

Figure 3-13: Procrustes R^2 values for comparisons of the principal components of NMDS solutions and the original configurations. Only results for the 32 point, 15-dimensional configurations are presented here. 99

Figure 3-14: Figure to illustrate similarities between the performance of different cost functions. The configurations used in this section had 16 points, and 15 dimensions. 101

Figure 3-15: Figure to illustrate similarities between the performance of different cost functions. The configurations used in this section had 32 points, and 15 dimensions. 102

Figure 3-16: Figure to illustrate the differences between stress values of NMDS solutions calculated under different cost functions..... 103

Figure 4-1: A schematic of the whole brain redrawn with permission from figure 8 of Swanson’s rat brain atlas (Swanson 1992). Each dot represents a named nucleus or area (refer to Appendix A: Parcellation Database, for meanings of label abbreviations). There are two hundred and fifty dots on this figure..... 115

Figure 4-2: Pathway tree illustrating divergent dense connections from the retina. Abstract reports have been included in this figure and are shown in red. 117

Figure 4-3: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two-, and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of densely labelled connection or abstract reports..... 119

Figure 4-4: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two- and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of densely and moderately labelled connection reports or abstract reports. 120

Figure 4-5: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two- and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of any labelled connection reports (i.e. belonging to the ‘3’, ‘2’, ‘1’ or ‘c’ categories, see Chapter 2) or abstract reports. 121

Figure 4-6: Connection matrix for first-stage retinal connections. Codes have standard meanings as defined in Table 2-2. 125

Figure 4-7: The NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of \hat{N}_1 . See Appendix A for abbreviations. Thick arrows correspond

to Neurobase codes of '3', medium arrows to codes of '2' and thin arrows to '1', 'c' or 'x'. See Table 2-2 for explanation of Neurobase codes.	128
Figure 4-8: The NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of \hat{T}_1	129
Figure 4-9: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{N}_1 and \hat{T}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.....	131
Figure 4-10: The configuration generated by NMDS analysis of the matrix shown in \hat{P}_1	133
Figure 4-11: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{P}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.....	134
Figure 4-12: The configuration generated by NMDS analysis of \hat{W}_1	136
Figure 4-13: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{W}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.....	137
Figure 4-14: An example of fixed kernel (kernel radius: 0.45) nonparametric cluster analysis based on the two-dimensional NMDS configuration derived from \hat{N}_1 under the $S^{(1)}$ cost function with the tied condition.	141
Figure 4-15: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with R=0.45 and active JOIN option. The input datum for this analysis was the NMDS configuration (Fit=1, tied) of the asymmetrical similarity matrix shown in Figure 4-6.	143
Figure 4-16: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with R=0.65 and active JOIN option.	144

Figure 4-17: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with DR=1.8 and CK=3 and active JOIN option. 145

Figure 4-18: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . The MODECLUS analyses used paradigms based on fixed-radius clustering kernels (paradigms 1-4). 147

Figure 4-19: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . The MODECLUS analyses used paradigms based on nearest-neighbour clustering kernels (paradigms 5-10). 149

Figure 4-20: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 151

Figure 4-21: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . 1210 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure. 152

Figure 4-22: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{T}_1 . 1168 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure. 153

Figure 4-23: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{P}_1 . 1123 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure. 155

Figure 4-24: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{W}_1 . 1219 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure..... 157

Figure 4-25: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from $\hat{N}_1, \hat{T}_1, \hat{P}_1$ and \hat{W}_1 . 4720 separate cluster schemes from 480 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure..... 159

Figure 4-26: Cartoon of the NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of \hat{N}_1 with a Venn diagram showing the major groupings suggested by interpreting the cluster-count matrix in Figure 4-25. 161

Figure 4-27: Cluster-count matrix derived from a connection matrix of all retinal efferents with small-scale structures removed. The counts in this figure are based on 2956 cluster schemes from 480 cluster trees. 163

Figure 4-28: Venn diagram showing clustering in large-scale connectivity matrix.. 164

Figure 4-29: Cluster-count matrix derived from a connection matrix of all retinal efferents with large-scale structures removed. The counts in this figure are based on 3838 cluster schemes from 480 cluster trees. 165

Figure 4-30: Venn diagram showing clustering in small-scale connectivity matrix. 166

Figure 4-31: Connection strength frequency functions calculated from 1064 26-level retinal efferent connection strength hierarchies using the MBOLTZMANN classifier. 169

Figure 4-32: Two stage tree of connection weight estimates from the retina involving the recipients of the twelve strongest connections of the retina. The weight of the lines indicates connection weight estimate values. The areas were sorted vertically according to the estimated strength of the strongest afferent connection, so that areas receiving the strongest connections lie at the top. 171

Figure 4-33: The matrix of connection weight estimates used as the asymmetric similarity matrix in these NMDS analyses of connective organisation of the visual system. 176

Figure 4-34: Procrustes rotation of two-dimensional NMDS configurations from the six different NMDS analyses of the matrix of connection weight estimates. 177

Figure 4-35: Two-dimensional NMDS plot representing the connective organisation of the early visual system in the rat with lines representing interarea connections. The weight of the lines represents the strength of the connection as shown in the similarity matrix in Figure 4-33. The configuration was calculated under the $S^{(1)}$ cost function using the tied approach. 178

Figure 4-36: The connection matrix for second stage analyses of the visual system. The constituent areas were the retina, the retina's major targets (defined according to the analyses reported in section 4.6) and their five major outputs. See text above for comments. 181

Figure 4-37: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the matrix shown in Figure 4-36. The cluster-counts were derived from 4471 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees. 185

Figure 4-38: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from Figure 4-38. 186

Figure 4-39: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the subparcellated structures removed. The cluster-counts were derived from 3162 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees. 187

Figure 4-40: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the connection matrix shown in figure 4-36 with the subparcellated structures removed, with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from figure 4-39. 188

Figure 4-41: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the connection matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the large-scale structures removed. The cluster-counts were derived from 4105 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees. 189

Figure 4-42: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the large-scale structures removed with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from Figure 4-44. 190

Figure 5-1: Connection matrix for central systems involved in spatial memory, (see Appendix C for each individual connection report, and Table 2-2 for the meanings of matrix entries). 201

Figure 5-2: NMDS output configuration produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ (bottom), under the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function.....	203
Figure 5-3: NMDS output configuration produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ (bottom) under the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function	204
Figure 5-4: Six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ (bottom), under all cost functions.	205
Figure 5-5: Six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ (bottom) under all cost functions	206
Figure 5-6: Cluster-count matrix derived from all 480 cluster trees from $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3, \hat{\mathbf{T}}_3, \hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ involving 2607 cluster schemes.	210
Figure 5-7: Venn diagram illustrating cluster-count data from Figure 5-6 superimposed onto the NMDS configuration derived from $S^{(1)}$ tied analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$	211
Figure 5-8 : Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$	215
Figure 5-9: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-8 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$	215
Figure 5-10: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$	216
Figure 5-11: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-10 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$	216

Figure 5-12: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ 218

Figure 5-13: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ 218

Figure 5-14: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-13 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ 219

Figure 5-15: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ 221

Figure 5-16: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-15 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ 221

Figure 5-17: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ 223

Figure 5-18: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-17 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ 224

Figure 5-19: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ 226

Figure 5-20: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-19 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ 225

Figure 5-21: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of the binarised forms of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ 229

Tables

Table 2-1: Table of codes used to denote different tracer techniques. 41

Table 2-2: The categories of connection report used while extracting matrices and summary tables.	44
Table 2-3: Priority of different comparison conditions in the GTLT algorithm	50
Table 2-4: Calculated size of search space used by MBOLTZMANN in calculating optimal hierarchies for sets of connections with 1 to 20 elements.	53
Table 4-1: The connection data underlying this section.	114
Table 4-2: The translation between Neurobase codes and the similarity values required to generate a proximity matrix. All other Neurobase codes were assigned a similarity value of 0.	126
Table 4-3: Connection matrix with normalised ordinal probabilistic connection weights and an unbiased estimate of standard deviation calculated from the probability distribution function generated by MBOLTZMANN. Bold alphanumeric codes: Neurobase connection codes (see Chapter 2), Bold italic values: normalised ordinal probabilistic connection strength values, Italic values: unbiased estimate of standard deviation from connection strength frequency functions.	174
Table 5-1: Mean Procrustes R^2 statistics for the NMDS configurations. Each mean value is calculated from 36 individual Procrustes rotations between configurations generated with different combinations of cost function and tied or untied approaches. The mean values along the leading diagonal were calculated from 30 separate R^2 values since configurations were not rotated against themselves.	201

Table 5-2: Matrix of mean normalised connection strengths for the whole connection matrix. See text for description.....	233
Table 5-3: Numbers of hierarchies in efferent and afferent connection weight analyses.....	235
Table 5-4: Afferent connection weight matrix. Connection hierarchies are arranged vertically.	236
Table 5-5: Efferent connection weight matrix. Connection hierarchies are arranged horizontally.	237

Chapter 1

A Theoretical Approach To Systems Level

Neuroanatomy.

1. A Theoretical Approach To Systems Level Neuroanatomy.

1.1. Introduction

Neuroscience studies the brain at many scales, ranging from the molecular level to descriptions of circuits involving hundreds of millions of cells. Systems-level neuroscience is the subject at its grossest level, one step down from studying the brain as a whole. In mammals, the number of individual neurons responsible for phenomena at this level is literally astronomical: the number of cells in the human brain is of the same order of magnitude as the number of stars in our galaxy (Murdin 1989; Schuz 1995). This presents a fundamental problem of complexity, and means that it is necessary to describe structures and phenomena in terms of large-scale functional units within a simplified theoretical framework (Shepherd 1994). These functional units are the nuclei and areas that are delineated in brain atlases, and their interactions are determined by the axonal projections between them.

This use of a simplified description ensures that our understanding of the mechanisms underlying phenomena at this level is formally qualitative (Perkel 1990). For this reason, it is often more worthwhile to attempt to describe how neural systems are organised as the first step towards a description of how they work (Young *et al.* 1995a). A brain structure's connectivity (that is, the axonal connections that the neurons of that structure make throughout the brain) determines its place in the organisation of the whole system (Zeki and Shipp 1988; Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Young 1992).

Young has proposed that objective analysis should be employed to constrain descriptions of connectional organisation, and that neural connection data should be treated with the same rigour that is applied to other neurobiological data (Young 1992; Young 1993). This

insistence on rigour in the analysis and interpretation of neuroanatomical connectivity can be distilled into the following principles:

- 1) As far as possible, all connections in the system under study should be represented in the connection scheme.
- 2) Connection schemes should be species specific. For example, data from a macaque monkey are not equivalent to data from an owl monkey. I have interpreted this to mean that connections identified in other species of rodent such as hamsters or mice cannot be used in the analysis of rat connectivity. For example, there are differences in connectivity between the hooded and albino strains, in the crossed and uncrossed retinogeniculate projections (Hickey and Spear 1976), but I judge this variability to be acceptable for the purpose of this thesis.
- 3) The data underlying the representation of a connection in the analysis should be taken from the results sections of published (and hence peer-reviewed) neuroanatomical papers.
- 4) Interpretations of the data should be made by objective mathematical or statistical methods which take only the connection data into account.

The methods that Young and co-workers have employed to investigate the connectional organisation of neural systems have included nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) (Young 1992; Scannell and Young 1993; Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b), hierarchical analysis (Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Hilgetag *et al.* 1996a), seriation (Simmen *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b), and optimal set-analysis (Hilgetag *et al.* 1996b).

The aim of this thesis is to describe the connectional organisation of neural systems in the rat brain using objective analyses (Young *et al.* 1995a). This project was broad in its scope, and

had several subsidiary aspects which needed to be investigated before progress could be made on the global issues. These were:

- 1) At present, the majority of neuroanatomical connection data are qualitative, and are reported in published journals in a nonstandard format with a nomenclature that is evolving (Swanson 1992). I needed to represent these data in a unified format that represents the neuroanatomists' original interpretations, but also permits computational analysis. I have designed a neuroanatomical connection database to solve this problem (see Section 2.1).
- 2) The variable that was used in all of the analyses in this thesis, was the connection strength of neural projections (see Section 1.3.2). I have devised a method that can estimate ordinal probabilistic connection weights by analysing simple interpretations of labelling-density in published papers. This method will be described in Chapter 2, and then it will be applied to components of the rat's visual system in Chapter 4, and then the limbic system in Chapter 5.
- 3) The NMDS analysis of neural connectivity data has been criticised by other workers, who claim that annular structure in the configurations is due to artefact generated by the analysis method (Goodhill *et al.* 1995). However, this annular structure reflects a *bone fide* aspect of the data under study: that of connectional sparsity. This can be removed by the use of mathematical transforms (Young *et al.* 1995b). Prompted by these methodological issues, I re-examined the NMDS methodology with different cost functions in different dimensionalities. I will present simulation studies of the NMDS method in Chapter 3.
- 4) NMDS is principally a tool for visualisation. Cox and Cox use the term 'multidimensional scaling' to refer to any technique which produces a graphical representation of objects from multivariate data (Cox and Cox 1995). Since it is impossible to visualise more than three dimensions at once, I have devised a way of visualising the relationships present in a high-

dimensional NMDS configuration, with nonparametric cluster analysis. This method will be described in Chapter 2 and applied to neural connection data in Chapters 4 and 5.

The remainder of this chapter is concerned with the conceptual background underlying the analyses described in this thesis. In the first section, I will consider the criteria used to delineate the functional unit of systems-level neuroscience: the brain area or nucleus (Shepherd 1994). In the following section, I will describe the ‘grey box’ model. This is a set of assumptions that allows brain areas and nuclei to be represented in simple mathematical terms. The third section of the chapter will be concerned with the characteristics of tract-tracing experimental data. In the final section of this chapter, I will discuss some in-depth issues concerning the model that I employ to elucidate the connectional organisation of the rat brain: the proximity model of neural connectivity.

1.2. Parcellation schemes: the grey box doctrine.

In a review paper, Douglas and Martin coined the phrase ‘the grey box’ to describe a representation of cortical areas, where macroscopic descriptions of cortical circuitry ignore the internal organisation of areas (Douglas and Martin 1991). This expression denotes the neuroanatomical model that I use in this thesis, and this section will describe how brain areas are defined from experimental data.

Brain tissue is regionally organised. Brain areas can be delineated by microscopically inspecting sections of brain which have been treated with the Nissl technique which stains every cell, and by placing boundaries, based on changes in the cellular density (Swanson 1992). This cellular architecture provided the basis for the earliest cortical maps (Creutzfeldt 1995), and is the simplest basis for any extant parcellation scheme.

The properties that can be used as a basis for a parcellation scheme are as numerous as there are experimental protocols. Van Essen describes broad sets of criteria which are used to define

cortical visual areas, and some of these are appropriate for a general treatment of brain parcellation (Van Essen 1985). If these criteria are used to define separate 'classes' of cells, a single brain area may contain many intermingled cells of different classes. The borders of an area can be delineated either by the spatial distribution of a combination of cell classes, or by a change in the distribution of cells of a single class. The exact definition depends on the area.

The criteria Van Essen describes are architectonics, connectivity, electrophysiological properties, and classifications based on behavioural deficits caused by lesions or the inactivation of areas. I will discuss the process of defining brain areas in terms of only the first three of these criteria, since the interpretation of data obtained by the behavioural method is complicated, and not widely used in this context (Grobstein 1990).

Architectonics includes any structural feature of brain tissue which can be stained and mapped. These include histological stains for neurotransmitters, their related enzymes and other cellular constituents. Immunohistological techniques provide a way of staining that is specific to a type of molecule (if antibodies can be raised to the molecule in question). It is remarkable that early cytoarchitectonic parcellation schemes (devised at the beginning of this century) are still largely valid, and that the histological techniques which were used in their production are still used today (Swanson 1992; Geyer *et al.* 1996).

Cell classes can be defined by either the presence of specific neurotransmitters, receptors or other molecules, or on the basis of morphology. A cell type can be defined on the basis of its connectivity (Swanson 1992). For example, one definition of 'prefrontal cortex' in the rat presents it as the recipient zone of efferents from the mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (Leonard 1969).

The electrophysiological properties of cells in different regions can provide persuasive evidence of the parcellation of a given region. Experiments describing the topography of

visual field representations in the extrastriate cortex of rats, for example, suggest that this region is made up of several 'visual areas' (Espinoza and Thomas 1983; Thomas and Espinoza 1987), even though it is considered to be a single region when defined by cytoarchitectonic criteria (Zilles 1985). Electrophysiological recording can be used in both awake, behaving animals (Mizumori and Williams 1993), and anaesthetised preparations (Hubel and Wiesel 1962). Imaging techniques such as positron emission tomography, functional nuclear magnetic resonance imaging, and optical imaging do not describe cell types as such, since it is impossible to resolve individual cells of mammalian brains at the appropriate time scale. These methods present images that show how functional properties are distributed over regions of the brain, usually the cerebral cortex, and so can show whether architectonic boundaries correspond to functional ones. It is possible to use positron emission tomography and functional magnetic resonance imaging on humans (PET: Geyer *et al.* 1996, fMRI: Ogawa *et al.* 1990, but also see Baraniga 1997, optical imaging: Blasdel 1992).

The ways in which brain areas are delineated in tract-tracing experiments is of particular interest here, since tract-tracing literature provides the data for analysis in this thesis. Most of the studies that were used in my analyses had performed extensive, qualitative examination of the stained tissue, and localised the cells by referring to a standard atlas of the rat brain (*e.g.* Paxinos and Watson 1986).

Such atlases are generated by performing extensive image analysis on a small number of brains which have been stained using a single method; Nissl stain in the case of Swanson (1992), and acetylcholinesterase staining in the case of Paxinos and Watson (1986). Image analysis is performed by the atlas' author in order to place structural borders, by using their own extensive knowledge of the literature, and the cytoarchitectural features of their

preparation. For example, Zilles published an atlas based on the laminar patterns of an automated grey-scaled image of cortex (Zilles 1985).

The impact of these atlases on neuroscience is very large. For example, Paxinos and Watson's atlas (first published in 1982 and the second edition published in 1986) has a citation index of 3900 on the Bath Information Data Services on-line literature database. In contrast, Hubel and Wiesel's Nobel Prize winning paper from 1962 has a much smaller citation index of 1416. Atlases are central to the work in this thesis.

The qualitative nature of the data that atlases summarise means that the only way to corroborate the parcellation scheme they propose is to re-read the original papers and produce another atlas. These atlases are extremely impressive in their scholastic depth and breadth, but are still based purely on the subjective intuition of their authors. Consequently, all work based upon them is also affected by their subjectivity (Roland and Zilles 1994). Moreover, the locations of borders tend to be fuzzily defined, since the presence of abrupt transitions between cell types as you move from one structure to its neighbours is relatively rare (Swanson 1992). The exact criteria which determine the presence of a border depend on the history of the research of the area in question. As a result the criteria used to delineate areas vary. Obtaining quantitative neuroanatomical data is therefore very important. Unfortunately, it is often too time-consuming and expensive to perform, and automated approaches to procedures like cell-counting are unreliable (Warren 1992). Rigorous comparisons between parcellation schemes require analysis in their own right (K. E. Stephan 1997, personal communication): quantitative measures and multivariate statistics have been used by Geyer and co-workers to distinguish two brain areas within the human primary motor cortex (Geyer *et al.* 1996), indicating that the potential of analytical approaches in this context is beginning to be realised.

In summary, the definition of brain areas and nuclei is properly a problem in multivariate statistics when provided with appropriate quantitative data, but in lieu of these treatments, neuroscientists must trust the schemes provided for them in brain atlases, which implicitly define the ‘grey box’ model that is widely used in systems-level neuroscience. The parcellation scheme used in this thesis is based on Swanson’s atlas (Swanson 1992).

1.3. Theoretical framework of neuroanatomical connectivity.

1.3.1. Basic ideas.

In general, illustrative figures describing the organisation of macroscopic circuits in the brain are box-and-line diagrams (*e.g.* Felleman and Van Essen 1991), which employ the same assumptions as the ‘grey box’ model which I have described. In this section, I will discuss certain mathematical concepts which I will use to illustrate quantitative aspects of neuroanatomical connectivity data.

My work uses a graph of interconnected nodes as a representation of the brain. Each node represents a given brain structure, and each edge connecting a pair of nodes represents an extrinsic projection between two areas. Each edge has a variable ‘weight’ or ‘strength’, and is strictly unidirectional. An illustrative example of a macroscopic neural circuit is presented in Figure 1-1. The brain areas (A, B, C, and D) represented in the graph are shown as circles, and the connections between them are shown as arrows. Arrows of different weights correspond to connections of different strengths. The experimental basis for the numerical values of each edge in the graph, denoted by ‘ c_{ij} ’, will be discussed in the next section.

Figure 1-1: An example of a graph describing the connectivity of a neural circuit.

1.3.2. Definitions of connection strength.

Consider the schematic connection from area A to area B shown in Figure 1-2. Area A contains N_A neurons in total, N_A^{PR} neurons that project to neurons outside of area A, and $(N_A^{PR})_B$ neurons that project to B. Area B contains N_B neurons in total, N_B^{PO} neurons that receive projections from other areas, and $(N_B^{PO})_A$ neurons that receive projections from area A. In this situation, what would be a suitable definition of the connection strength, c_{AB} ?

Figure 1-2: Definitions of ‘neuronal connection strength’ for AB.

At this abstract level, I consider two alternative preliminary definitions of connection strength: the ‘absolute connection strength’, which would be a straightforward count of the number of presynaptic and postsynaptic cells involved in the connections; and the ‘relative connection strength’, where the projection cell-counts would be normalised by dividing the absolute connection strengths by the total number of neurons in the whole area. Further and more

formally, the ‘absolute neuronal presynaptic connection weight’, $AW_N^{PR}(AB)$, and the ‘absolute neuronal postsynaptic connection weight’, $AW_N^{PO}(AB)$, can be defined as:

$$AW_N^{PR}(AB) = \left(N_A^{PR}\right)_B \quad \text{Equation 1-1}$$

$$AW_N^{PO}(AB) = \left(N_B^{PO}\right)_A \quad \text{Equation 1-2}$$

The ‘relative neuronal presynaptic connection weight’, $RW_N^{PR}(AB)$, and the ‘relative neuronal postsynaptic connection weight’, $RW_N^{PO}(AB)$, are defined according to the following two equations:

$$RW_N^{PR}(AB) = \frac{\left(N_A^{PR}\right)_B}{N_A^{PR}} \quad \text{Equation 1-3}$$

$$RW_N^{PO}(AB) = \frac{\left(N_B^{PO}\right)_A}{N_B^{PO}} \quad \text{Equation 1-4}$$

A definition of c_{AB} as a simple variable should take pre- and postsynaptic connection strengths into account and could be defined as the product of pre- and postsynaptic relative connection strengths, that is:

$$c_{AB} = RW_N^{PR}(AB) \cdot RW_N^{PO}(AB) = \frac{\left(N_A^{PR}\right)_B}{N_A^{PR}} \cdot \frac{\left(N_B^{PO}\right)_A}{N_B^{PO}} \quad \text{Equation 1-5}$$

The anatomical strengths of connections are rarely measured quantitatively in tract-tracing studies (Linden and Perry 1983; Martin 1986). Postsynaptic cell-counts are only possible indirectly by measuring the density of neurons over a termination region and inferring the likely termination patterns of cells in the desired region. Measuring the number of cells which are involved presynaptically in a connection requires that each one be labelled retrogradely and counted. It is possible to achieve this in well-studied systems. In 1995, Patton and MacNaughton published an extensive collation of data describing a quantitative connection matrix for the dentate gyrus. They presented absolute anatomical connection weights (as defined above) and also made estimations of the number of dendritic spines and synapses

involved in connections, which they described as ‘poorly known’ (Patton and McNaughton 1995). This can be attributed to the qualitative nature of experimental neuroanatomical data (see later).

Shepherd claims that synapses are the ‘fundamental unit of nervous function’ (Shepherd 1990). Therefore, a theoretical definition of the strength of a connection between two brain structures may be best expressed in terms of the total number of synapses involved in the connection; (Braitenburg and Schuz 1991; Bernard and Wheal 1994; Patton and McNaughton 1995). However, the relative functional importance of a synapse is relative to its position on the dendritic tree, soma, or even axon, and the nature of the processes that it triggers on activation. A simple count of synapses would also miss important information about the functional characteristics of a given connection, since different neurotransmitter systems have different effects on the postsynaptic cell, depending on the receptors to which they bind (Llinas 1988; Nicoll *et al.* 1990).

Abeles defines a connection weight indirectly, by calculating the probability of synaptic contact between pairs of neurons from different areas, where the extent and geometry of terminal arbours and dendritic trees are known variables (Abeles 1991). This is not the case for the majority of the data I describe. Characterising a neuronal connection involving tens of thousands of individual cells with a single scalar is a great simplification. It has strong implications for the power of the description that can be achieved. Consider two areas A and C which both project to area B, with the organisations shown in Figure 1-3. Under the definitions of connection strength described above, the two connections are equivalent, despite having very different organisations.

Figure 1-3: Two equivalent ‘grey box’ connections where each dot might represent 10 neurons.

The ‘functional connectivity’ between two brain structures can be defined as the influence that activity in a presynaptic region has on activity in a postsynaptic region (Finnerty and Jefferys 1993). Within the model of macrocircuitry used here, this is not, in general, the same as anatomical connectivity. The physiological effects of a volley of action potentials fired along an anatomically defined projection depend on many factors. Functional connectivity can be measured experimentally by a variety of methods, including cross-correlation analysis (Perkel *et al.* 1967). These methods involve recording the electrophysiological activity in the presynaptic and postsynaptic regions and mathematically comparing the signals to infer that the one region sends a signal to the other.

1.3.3. Substructure and subnodes.

It is not always clear which scale of description is the most appropriate to use when dividing brain tissue into areas and nuclei, because many putative areas or nuclei contain smaller structures. The most appropriate way of representing the data would allow structures to be defined over multiple scales of description. Within the graph-theoretical framework, I allow the nodes in the graph to contain ‘subnodes’, which represent the substructure of a given brain area. This is unlike most mathematical graphs, but is a necessary level of complication to include when dealing with neuroanatomical data.

1.3.4. Issues not covered by this model.

This model does not account for a ‘connection’ where the dendrites of cells in a given area extend into a neighbouring area, and make synaptic contact with axons which terminate there. It would be possible to represent dendritic connections by approaching the literature describing dendritic morphology in the same way as I have approached the problem of representing axonal connections. However, the implementation of this idea would be a large-scale project in its own right, and will therefore not be covered here.

Figure 1-4: Dendritic connections. Despite the fact that Area C projects to A but not to B, some neurons in B receive direct synaptic input from C because their dendrites extend into A.

1.4. Neuroanatomical tract-tracing experiments.

In this section, I will explore how well real data fit into the theoretical framework outlined in the previous section. I will describe the basic concepts underlying modern neuroanatomical techniques; the pitfalls of an over-simplistic interpretation of neuroanatomical data; the rudiments of some of the cell biology underlying the methodology and how this real data can be used to obtain quantitative estimates of connection strength which are appropriate for the ‘grey box’ model.

Tract-tracing neuroanatomical studies label a subpopulation of the neurons involved in a connection. I call this the ‘labelling density’, which probably correlates very strongly with the aforementioned ‘connection strength’, but varies according to the sensitivity of the method used.

1.4.1. The basic design of tract-tracing experiments.

My analyses have been based entirely on the results of neuroanatomical tract-tracing experiments, which are the standard methods for studying connections between populations of neurons in the brain. In this section I will review the most widely-used methods, emphasising how I have interpreted the data in terms of the graph-theoretical model described above.

All tract-tracing experiments are based on the same basic design. An experimental animal is anaesthetised and small amounts of tracer chemicals are injected into the region of the brain under investigation. The tracer is taken up by the parts of neurons which extend into the injection site, typically at axonal terminals or dendritic arbours. Then the tracer is transported along the cell's axon by intracellular transport mechanisms, either anterogradely from the cell body to the axonal terminals, or retrogradely, in the opposite direction, or both. Finally, the animal is killed, and its brain sectioned and stained to reveal a pattern that shows the distribution of transported label (Blackstad *et al.* 1981).

The end product of a given tract-tracing experiment is a three-dimensional map of tracer concentration at the time of the animal's death. Since tracer is originally applied in a localised injection to a small region of the brain, labelled regions of the brain must be connected to the injection site. The data are usually presented as photographs or *camera lucida* drawings of sections which show the distribution of label throughout the brain (for example, see figure 4 of Sesack *et al.* 1989)

Studies are classified into 'retrograde' and 'anterograde', based on the type of axonal transport mechanism mediating the tracer's movement (Vallee and Bloom 1991). Tracers which have been classified as 'retrograde' are assumed to be taken up by axon terminals, and then transported along the axons to the soma of neurons projecting to the injection site. In contrast, tracers that have been classified as 'anterograde' are assumed to be taken up by the

soma and dendrites of neurons, and then transported to label the axonal terminals of that cell (Figure 1-5).

Figure 1-5: Conceptual diagram showing the basic design of a tract-tracing experiment with typical retrograde and anterograde labelling. Red arrows with solid arrowheads illustrate zones of potential uptake on cells. Red arrows with open arrowheads illustrate the retrograde and anterograde transport that gives rise to labelling in the cells shown.

Retrograde data can be considered numerically equivalent to the 'presynaptic connection strength' described in the previous section, since it is possible to count the number of cells labelled in a given injection. In anterograde studies, only ordinal level estimates of 'postsynaptic connection strength' are possible, such as 'strong', 'moderate' or 'weak' (e.g. Figure 14 in Coogan and Burkhalter 1993). This is because the best data available using this technique are qualitative estimates of the number of cells contacted postsynaptically, based on the extent of the axonal terminal arbour labelled by the tracing method.

1.4.2. Problems arising from the methodology.

Unfortunately, interpreting labelling patterns is not as simple as described above. In this section, I will describe some of the common problems facing researchers when performing this sort of work. The categorisation of tract-tracing techniques as 'anterograde' and 'retrograde' is a simplification. In reality, the uptake and transport processes of the cells can give rise to different patterns of labelling in different circumstances. Some conceptual examples are presented in Figure 1-6.

Figure 1-6: A tract-tracing experiment with several possible types of nonideal labelling.

The sensitivity of the tracer can be described as the ratio of the amount injected, to the amount transported. This property determines how much tracer is used in a given injection and therefore, the size of a given injection site. Tracer sensitivity and other tracer properties are largely determined by the uptake and transport of tracer by dendrites, soma, axons, or terminals of cells at the injection site.

This often gives rise to 'fibres of passage' labelling, where axons passing through the injection site have taken up tracer and transported it to terminals or soma. Some tracer chemicals can be transported transynaptically, and so it cannot be assumed that neuroanatomical tracers only label cells which are directly connected to the injection site (Sawchenko and Swanson 1981; Cliffer and Giesler 1988; Dado *et al.* 1990). If tracer can be taken up by the dendrites of cells that lie on the periphery of the injection site, it may be possible for anterograde label to be transported to the terminals of cells whose soma lie outside the injection site. Transport of some tracers can also occur in both anterograde and retrograde directions. In some cases, tracer could conceivably be taken up by axonal terminals, transported retrogradely, and then transported anterogradely down a collateral branch of the neuron (See Figure 3 of Warr *et al.* 1981).

When attempting to minimise spurious results and uninterpretable labelling patterns, neuroanatomists cross-reference their descriptions to corroborate the presence of connections between structures. Comparing results between experiments is complicated, especially when researchers from different laboratories use different protocols.

Readers of neuroanatomical papers have to trust the papers' descriptions of injection sites and the absence of transynaptic labelling or labelling from damaged and undamaged fibres of passage. Some methods are more prone to error than others and may be treated with some element of suspicion (Sawchenko and Swanson 1981).

If the injection site's boundaries do not coincide exactly with those of the nucleus or area being studied, the labelling produced in a single experiment can only be regarded as a sub-sample of the total population of cells involved. This situation is illustrated in Figure 1-7, and is sometimes addressed by performing the experiment many times, so that the entire volume of area A has been sampled (*e.g.* Coogan and Burkhalter 1993). It would be necessary to take this sub-sampling factor into account when calculating the number of cells projecting to or from any one region. The opposite problem is evident when attempting to label the connections of a small, focal structure. If the technique being used produces large injection sites, then the zone of active uptake will extend beyond the boundaries of the nucleus under study and produce false-positive labelling from neighbouring regions.

Figure 1-7: If area A receives connections from areas B and C, the injection site shown will only label cells in area C.

Some techniques are more sensitive than others, labelling cells that others miss (Wan *et al.* 1982). This may imply that the cells labelled in these experiments are usually an underestimation of the total population of cells with active uptake zones in the injection site. One would normally assume that this sub-sampling does not suffer from systematic errors, but it is possible that some classes of cells may be more strongly labelled than others: for example, cells with very extensive terminal arbours might tend to take up more retrograde tracer than neurons with small trees.

Consequently, when basing our descriptions of ‘connection strength’ on data from tract-tracing studies, I cannot defensibly estimate the connection strength without first examining the functional dynamics of these tract-tracing methods.

1.4.3. Dynamics of chemical tracer methods

In this section I will describe the mechanisms of tracer uptake and transport for a number of experimental methods. There are many different tract-tracing techniques available to the experimental neuroanatomist, but they do not, in general, produce results that conform simply to the ideal model described in Section 1.4.1. The most commonly used methods include the autoradiographic technique using tritiated amino acids, horseradish peroxidase, horseradish peroxidase conjugated to wheat germ agglutinin, the most common fluorescent dyes, and *Phaseolus vulgaris* leuco-agglutinin. These methods have been extensively studied and

reviewed (Heimer and Robards 1981; Heimer and Zaborszky 1989; Bolam 1992), and will only be briefly described here, with reference to their sensitivity and departure from the behaviour of ideal retrograde and anterograde tracers.

Tritiated amino acids were first used in the late 1960s (*e.g.* Lasek *et al.* 1968). They involve injections of radioactive amino acids into a given brain area. These molecules are taken up by neuronal cell bodies, where they are incorporated into proteins which are then transported along the axon to cell terminals. Uptake occurs within the first one-and-a-half hours in cell bodies at the injection site (Cowan *et al.* 1972). This method can label neurons transynaptically (Fallon *et al.* 1984), but this can be controlled by careful consideration of the post-injection survival time. This, coupled with the fact that label is gradually cleared from the injection site, means that the timing of these experiments is important. The time delay employed depends on the connections being studied. Autoradiographic studies use sensitive photographic film which is laid over histological sections, and produces opaque grains when ionised by the radiation. Regions where the grain-density is high, indicate regions with a high concentration of radioactive tracer. This labelling process actually measures the radioactivity across the slide, and so the presence of a small amount of label may reflect small random levels of background radiation, rather than the presence of transported tracer (*e.g.* see Figure 1 of Ter Horst *et al.* 1984).

Retrograde transport along axons was first demonstrated *in vivo* in 1971 using the protein horseradish peroxidase or 'HRP' (Kristensson and Olsson 1971). After injection, tracer is taken up by fluid-phase endocytosis at the surface of the plasma membrane, which occurs at dendrites and perikarya of neurons, as well as at presynaptic terminals (Turner and Harris 1974). Undamaged fibres of passage also can take up HRP (Herkenham and Nauta 1977). HRP is not transported transynaptically (LaVail and LaVail 1974), and is transported

anterogradely as well as retrogradely (Hansson 1973). It is cleared relatively rapidly from the injection site, with the result that if the animal is not killed at the point in time when the size of the injection site is at its greatest, the size of the injection site may be underestimated. Fahrbach and co-workers demonstrated that the time of greatest spread of iontophoretic injections of HRP into the ventromedial nucleus of the hypothalamus in the rat, is one hour after the injections were made (Fahrbach *et al.* 1984) .

The sensitivity of the HRP approach can be significantly increased through the conjugation of either cholera toxin (CT) or wheat germ agglutinin (WGA) onto HRP (Schwab *et al.* 1978). This is due to the increased binding affinity of these molecules to sites on the plasma membrane, which greatly increases the uptake of tracer into the cell. *In vitro* experiments with neuroblastoma show that 100-200 times less tracer is required to produce the same amount of cellular uptake when ricin-conjugated HRP deposits are compared with free HRP (Gonatas *et al.* 1980). *In vivo* tracer experiments with WGA-HRP and CT-HRP show that the conjugated molecules have sensitivities greater than forty times that of free HRP (Gonatas *et al.* 1979; Trojanowski *et al.* 1982; Wan *et al.* 1982). This increased sensitivity means that these tracers are suitable for labelling connections involving fewer cells. Transsynaptic transport of tracer can occur in CT-HRP and WGA-HRP studies (Wan *et al.* 1982), as does the anterograde transport of tracer from cell bodies to terminals (Levine *et al.* 1991; Akaike 1992).

A wide variety of fluorescent dyes and labelled microspheres can also be used in tract-tracing experiments. The principal advantage of using fluorescent dyes is that they require much less tissue-processing than other histological techniques to visualise the tracer. More than one fluorescent tracer can be used in the same material to double-label cells which connect to different regions of brain, revealing divergent collateral connections from a single cell (Kuypers *et al.* 1980). They can also be used in conjunction with other techniques which do

involve staining, such as immunohistochemistry (Sawchenko and Swanson 1981). Many of the early fluorescent compounds are as sensitive as HRP (Aschoff and Hollander 1982), but they can be taken up by fibres of passage and cause transneuronal labelling (Sawchenko and Swanson 1981). These compounds include Fast Blue, which is still used extensively in tract-tracing experiments (Montero 1993).

Recently, techniques have been developed that have more favourable properties such as small, well-confined injection sites, lack of transneuronal labelling, and clear transport in either retrograde or anterograde directions. These compounds such as SITS (Schmued and Swanson 1982), Fluoro-Gold (Schmued and Fallon 1986), and rhodamine-labelled microspheres (Katz *et al.* 1984), were initially reported not to exhibit uptake by undamaged fibres of passage or transneuronal labelling, but Dado and co-workers have reported that this is not always the case with Fluoro-Gold (Dado *et al.* 1990). If the mechanisms of transport and uptake of these tracers were better understood, the process of quantifying the data that they describe would be made much more straightforward. For example, the mechanism that is responsible for the properties of uptake in Fluoro-Gold might consist of the diffusion, and subsequent sequestration of its active group (hydroxystilbamidine) within the cell by the presence of a favourable pH gradient (Wessendorf 1991).

The final method described here is *Phaseolus vulgaris* leucoagglutinin (PHA-L). This was invented in 1984 by Gerfen and Sawchenko and is used as an anterograde tract-tracing method. It uses an immunohistochemical approach to label a transported lectin and fills cells to the same morphological level of detail as Golgi stains. This delineates neuronal pathways more clearly than the autoradiographic method of anterograde tracing with tritiated amino acids (Ter Horst *et al.* 1984), because labelled cells are clearly delineated at the injection site, and the cells themselves are stained. The processes underlying uptake are not fully

understood, although an optimal method of anterograde labelling has been described (Gerfen and Sawchenko 1984). The original paper reporting the technique reported that PHA-L is not taken up by undamaged fibres of passage, but more recent reports claim otherwise (Cliffer and Giesler 1988). This method does not appear to give rise to transneuronal labelling.

Many of the methods described above have been shown to give rise to labelling caused by endocytosis of tracer into undamaged axons (Sawchenko and Swanson 1981; Cliffer and Giesler 1988; Dado *et al.* 1990). None of the postulated mechanisms of tracer uptake are specific to terminal, dendritic or perikaryal zones (Wan *et al.* 1982; Wessendorf 1991). If endocytosis of tracer can occur over any exposed part of the neuronal plasma membrane, then the uptake of tracer into a cell will depend on the surface area of the cell that lies in the injection site. The surface area of a smooth axon is much smaller than either that of a terminal arbour with boutons, or that of the dendritic tree of a cell. If uptake cannot occur at myelinated portions of an axon, the surface available for axonal uptake will be lessened still. Therefore, even if it is possible for uptake to occur at axonal sites, the geometrical arrangement of cells at the injection site will mean that the uptake of tracer is more likely to occur in unmyelinated terminal zones or over the surface of the dendritic tree or the soma. The degree of error involved in these experiments is difficult to estimate quantitatively in the absence of clear biophysical models of the actions of tracers.

Two exceptions to the general design described in the previous section are lesion studies and electrical stimulation studies, since neither method involves injection of an actively transported substance. The earliest techniques were based on introducing damage to the brain structures under study. Damaged axons and terminals are identifiable by the Fink-Heimer silver staining procedure, and indicate the course of projections from the damaged area (see description in Blackstad *et al.* 1981). However, the nature of the lesion can affect the data

results. Aspiration and radiofrequency lesions suffer from the problem that fibres passing through the area where the lesion is delivered also degenerate. Cytochemical lesions avoid this problem by selectively damaging cell bodies and leaving fibres of passage unaffected.

Electrical stimulation experiments involve placing a stimulating electrode in one area and a recording electrode in another, and then measuring responses at the recording site after passing current through the stimulating electrode. This technique is used relatively rarely and will not be covered further (but see Finnerty and Jefferys 1993).

1.5. The proximity model of neural connectivity.

The basic premise of this thesis is that analysis is required to interpret neuroanatomical connection data. At present, it is common to find box-and-line figures of the kind shown in Figure 1-8, where the arrangement of boxes and lines represents beliefs about the organisation of the system (e.g. Kolb 1990; Lopes da Silva *et al.* 1990; Kandel *et al.* 1991). Figures such as these are of limited value to the task of interpreting the organisation of most systems, except perhaps as a convenient summary of the connectional data. This point of view was stated explicitly by Young (1995a):

“In all other disciplines in which complex numerous data are derived from experiments, conclusions drawn from data without any supporting analysis are not considered reliable.”

Other direct criticisms of the representation in Figure 1-8 are that each of the boxes in the figure are made up of several brain areas, but the figure does not show this. The relative sizes of the different areas are not indicated, and the strength of connections is not represented. Moreover, it is not clear what the layout of the figure actually represents, and no attempt is made to represent any aspects of the actual experimental data. The figure is taken from a textbook, in which a simplified conceptual framework is being used. Nonetheless, these faults are repeated in the majority of organisational schemes of this kind.

Figure 1-8: 'A proposed neural circuit for emotion', from figure 47.2 of Kandel, Schwarz and Jessel 1991.

If figures of this kind are produced by considering neuroanatomical connection data in conjunction with neurophysiological or behavioural data, a different situation arises (e.g. Gray 1982; Redish and Touretzky 1997). These schemes are generally not directly concerned with the connectional organisation of the system, but instead propose a functional model of the macrocircuitry underlying a specific behaviour or physiological phenomenon. The neuroanatomical and neurophysiological data are interpreted in parallel, using intuition rather than rigorous analysis. The relationship between structure and function in systems-level neuroscience is difficult to define, and such models cannot often be regarded as predictive in anything other than a very loosely-defined sense (Perkel 1990). In many models, some connections are omitted (see Figure 3 of Redish and Touretzky 1997).

The nonmetric multidimensional scaling technique (Shepard 1962; Kruskal 1964; Takane *et al.* 1977; Cox and Cox 1995) has been used by Young and co-workers to analyse the organisation of systems in the monkey (Young 1992; Young 1993), cat (Scannell and Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995) and rat (This thesis). This methodology is based on the idea of

representing a system of brain structures as a configuration of points embedded in a multidimensional Euclidean coordinate space. If the distances between points are monotonically related to the inverse of the strength of the connection between the areas that the points represent, the configuration can be treated as a representation of the connective organisation of the system. I call this ‘the proximity model of neural connectivity’, and it forms the basis for most of the analyses described in this thesis. An introduction to the mathematics underlying the calculation of coordinates in the configuration, and the comparison and analysis of configurations will be described in Chapter 2. In the remainder of this section, I will describe the simple conceptual framework of the proximity model, and discuss some of the theoretical problems underlying its use to describe connectivity data.

As I described earlier in this chapter, quantitative connection weights are rarely measured or even defined in neuroanatomical tract-tracing studies. This is due to inherent methodological problems (Warren 1992). Consequently, all previous connectivity analyses have been based on nonmetric data, defined at the ordinal level of measurement (that is, it is possible to say that one datum is greater than another, but not by how much; Coombs 1964).

It is informative to consider how the multidimensional scaling procedure would behave if more precisely-defined data were available. The proximity model requires that the distances between points are related mathematically to the connection density between the brain areas that the points represent. I would define connection strength according to Equation 1-5 taking values from 0 to 1. This would define a connection matrix (\mathbf{C} , with elements c_{ij} , where $i, j = 1 \dots N$). I would then calculate a matrix of dissimilarities (\mathbf{A} , with elements δ_{ij}) where the relationship between connection strength and dissimilarity could be defined by Equation 1-6. In the terminology of the NMDS method, the term ‘similarity’ refers to the closeness of the

areas in the representation, and can be defined mathematically as $\delta_{max} - \delta_{ij}$, where δ_{max} is equal to the maximum dissimilarity.

$$\delta_{ij} = 1 - \frac{1}{2}(c_{ij} + c_{ji}) \quad (\text{where the object variables } i, j \text{ refer to brain areas } A, B) \quad \text{Equation 1-6}$$

In this hypothetical model, each distance is defined to be equal to the equivalent dissimilarity.

$$d_{ij} = \delta_{ij} \quad (\text{where the object variables } i, j \text{ refer to brain areas } A, B) \quad \text{Equation 1-7}$$

The dissimilarity variable is said to be ‘metric’ if the triangle inequality ($\delta_{ij} + \delta_{jk} \geq \delta_{ik}$) holds for all triplets (i, j, k). This variable can be considered ‘Euclidean’ if the N points can be embedded in a Euclidean space, so that the Euclidean distance between the i^{th} and j^{th} point is δ_{ij} (Gower and Legendre 1986). These conditions are not necessarily true for every connection matrix. This ‘metric’ condition should not be confused with ‘nonmetric’ descriptions of data, which are data defined at the nominal or ordinal levels of measurement (See Chapter 2).

In this section, I consider a hypothetical situation where the connection strength matrix has ratio values according to Equation 1-5. In a situation such as this, there are four issues which may cause problems in a proximity model representation: the connections are directional but the distances are not; the way that nonconnections are represented is significant; the data may be non-Euclidean; and high-dimensional coordinate spaces may be required.

1.5.1. Connections are directional, distances are not.

In general, connections are directional (*i.e.* $c_{AB} \neq c_{BA}$) but their correspondent distances are not (*i.e.* $d_{AB} = d_{BA}$). Equation 1-6 defines a proximity variable that does not take the direction of connections into account. This means that a very strong unidirectional connection (*i.e.* $c_{AB} = 1, c_{BA} = 0$) would be represented by the same distance as a pair of reciprocal connections of intermediate strength (*i.e.* $c_{AB} = 0.5, c_{BA} = 0.5$). This is an intrinsic limitation of the proximity model, and cannot be addressed by simply changing the way the distance matrix is defined. It

is possible in principle to use multidimensional scaling to model asymmetric data (Cox and Cox 1995), but I have not applied these somewhat undeveloped methods in this thesis.

1.5.2. How are nonconnections represented?

Since connection strength is a continuous variable, modelling nonconnections (*i.e.* $c_{ij} = 0$) as distances is a natural extension of modelling very sparse connections (*i.e.* $c_{ij} \approx 0$). This model sets the distance between points of all nonconnected structures to 1, irrespective of the number of intermediate steps in a pathway linking the two structures. This is an example of a ‘topological’ model, that represents the connections between structures strictly as proximity values. For example, the retina is neither connected to the visual cortex nor to the hippocampus. Under such a model the retina should lie equally distant from both of them.

This seems counter-intuitive, since a two-stage pathway exists between the retina and the visual cortex (via the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus), and the number of intermediate steps from the retina to the hippocampus is at least three (for a weak anatomically-defined pathway that is not supported physiologically; see Chapter 4). The activity of neurons in primary visual cortex is directly influenced by the retina even under general anaesthesia (Wiesenfeld and Kornel 1975), whereas physiological activity of hippocampal cells may occur in the absence of visual input (Quirk *et al.* 1990). A model based on pathway information would be an example of a ‘hodological’ model, and data-conditioning methods have been described which implement this approach (see Chapter 2, Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b). It should be emphasised that the presence of a neuroanatomically defined pathway does not necessarily imply a causal link between the neurons of all the areas in the pathway, and so caution should be used when employing a hodological approach.

The most appropriate way of representing nonconnections in the proximity model has been a source of controversy (Simmen *et al.* 1994; Goodhill *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young

et al. 1995b). This has been concerned with whether the tied or untied approach is the most appropriate with regard to nonconnections. Young and co-workers propose that a hybrid methodology involving a tied approach to nonconnections and an untied approach to connections would be the most mathematically appropriate for a topological analysis, since nonconnections should all be considered to be ‘as absent’ as each other (Young *et al.* 1995b). The opposite approach has been described in the literature where an untied approach to nonconnections is combined with a tied approach to connections. This ‘tertiary approach to ties’ was devised for the study of adjacency matrices (Kendall 1977), rather than connection matrices, and can be regarded as a hodological method, with the same basis and pitfalls as the hodological methods mentioned above.

The way in which nonconnections are treated is important with regard to the overall structure of the model, since nonconnections are usually the most common entries in a connection matrix of quantitative data (*e.g.*, Young *et al.* 1995b). This ‘sparsity’ of connection matrices is a respectable feature of connection data and can in itself be informative; but it can obscure features of connectional organisation within the proximity model.

One hodological method which circumvents the effects of sparsity is to base the definition of proximity on the densest pathway between areas. If areas X and Y are not connected, and the densest pathway from X to Y involves one intermediary area, J, the ‘pathway connection distance’ (p_{XY}) can be expressed according to Equation 1-8.

$$p_{XY} = (1 - c_{XJ}) + (1 - c_{JY}) \quad \text{Equation 1-8}$$

This leads to an alternative definition of dissimilarity, where nonconnections are constrained to different distances depending on the relative strength of the connecting pathway.

$$\delta_{AB} = \frac{1}{2}(p_{AB} + p_{BA}) \quad \text{Equation 1-9}$$

This may require ‘pathway information’ to take precedence over the presence of nonconnections and weak connections (since very weak connections may be less influential on an area’s activity than input from a strong pathway). Proximity models based on quantitative connection strengths would be likely to contravene the triangle inequality (which is a requirement for the model to be ‘metric’, see page 27) in many instances. In these cases the ‘pathway connection distance’ may be a more appropriate variable to use in a proximity model.

For example, consider the pathway from the retina to the primary visual cortex in the rat. Roughly 4×10^4 retinal ganglion cells project to the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (Linden and Perry 1983, Martin 1986). When WGA-HRP is injected into the primary visual cortex, over 90% of labelled cells lie in the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, suggesting that there is a dense pathway leading from the retina to the primary visual cortex (Sanderson *et al.* 1991). In the proximity model, the distances representing the connection from the retina to the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus and the connection from there to the primary visual cortex, would both be very small. In order for the triangle inequality to be valid, the distance representing the nonconnection must be shorter than the sum of the distances representing the two dense connections.

Unless the relationship between connection strength and proximity is carefully defined to take this into account, the triangle inequality will almost certainly be violated. Therefore, the standard approach to nonconnections would encounter conceptual problems when applied to ratio-level data, but these problems could be avoided by the careful definition of an appropriate dissimilarity coefficient.

1.5.3. How can we represent non-Euclidean connection matrices?

Connection matrices which are not positive semi-definite, that is, those that have negative eigenvalues (Gower and Legendre 1986), cannot be represented by proximities in Euclidean space of any dimensionality. Gower and Legendre describe an example of a set of four points with no Euclidean representation, that I will describe here (Gower and Legendre 1986). Consider the metric dissimilarity matrix below:

$$\begin{matrix}
 A & \begin{bmatrix} 0 & & & \\ & 2 & 0 & \\ & 2 & 2 & 0 \\ & 1.1 & 1.1 & 1.1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \\
 B \\
 C \\
 D
 \end{matrix}
 \qquad \text{Equation 1-10}$$

A, B and C form an equilateral triangle of side 2, and D is equidistant from A, B and C. The smallest possible distance that DA, DB or DC could have in a Euclidean representation is $2\sqrt{3}/2 = 1.15$. The geometry of this situation is illustrated in Figure 1-9.

Figure 1-9: An example of a set of distances that satisfy the metric inequality but which have no Euclidean representation (Not to scale; from Gower and Legendre 1986)

Given a non-Euclidean metric dissimilarity variable (δ_{ij} for $i, j = 1$ to N), the most common practice is to transform it to ε_{ij} by adding a constant value to all dissimilarities (Cailliez 1983).

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon_{ij} &= \sqrt{\delta_{ij}^2 + k} && \text{if } i \neq j \\
 &= 0 && \text{if } i = j
 \end{aligned}
 \qquad \text{Equation 1-11}$$

The smallest number k^* such that ε_{ij} has a Euclidean representation for all $k \geq k^*$ is $-2\lambda_n$, where λ_n is the smallest eigenvalue of W_d .

$$W_d = -\frac{1}{2}A\Delta^2A \quad \text{Equation 1-12}$$

with Δ^2 is an $N \times N$ matrix with elements $(\delta_{ij})^2$.

$$A = I - \frac{1}{N}\mathbf{j}\mathbf{j}'; \quad I = N^{\text{th}} \text{ order identity matrix.},$$

\mathbf{j} = N-dimensional vector with all coordinates equal to 1.

This shows that non-Euclidean connection data can be represented in a Euclidean proximity model at the cost of the ratio properties of the data.

1.5.4. High dimensionality.

In a general case, where the positions of points are not linearly related, the number of dimensions required in the analysis increases as the number of points increases. This is relevant in attempts to analyse very large networks, such as those over the whole brain, since the dimensionality of the required solution is likely to be higher the more structures are involved. High-dimensional representations are problematic because their geometry has properties which appear counterintuitive when compared to more commonplace two- and three-dimensional coordinate spaces. These properties will only be described briefly here, in order to give an impression of the problems inherent in using high-dimensional representations. See Scott (1992) for a description of the geometry of high-dimensional Euclidean coordinate spaces.

The volume occupied by the central portion of the space surrounding the origin is much less in high-dimensional space. For example, the ratio of the area of a two-dimensional circle of unit radius to the area of a square that encloses it is 0.793. In contrast, the ratio of the volume of a

seven-dimensional unit hypersphere to that of its enclosing hypercube is 0.037 (Scott 1992). In a similar way, the tails of high-dimensional multivariate normal distributions contain increasingly more of the probability mass of the distribution as the dimensionality increases. This has been called the ‘empty space phenomenon’ (Scott 1992).

Proximity analyses embedded into high-dimensional space are difficult to interpret for two reasons. Straightforward visualisation is not possible in spaces with more than three dimensions. Attempting to analyse the configuration’s properties by density estimation is often impossible in spaces with more than five dimensions, since accurately estimating the density of points in high-dimensional spaces requires very large sample sizes (Epanechnikov 1969; Silvermann 1986).

Approaches that involve high-dimensional configurations require some form of dimensional reduction, such as principal component analysis, to represent the most important features of the data. Multidimensional scaling is itself considered a technique of dimensional reduction (Kendall 1975).

1.5.5. Conclusions.

This section has explored possible sources of difficulty in the analysis method used in this thesis. The proximity model has shortcomings: the directions of connections are not represented, the definition of dissimilarity depends upon the interpretation of nonconnections, and the Euclidean properties and possible high-dimensionality of the data should be represented in as few dimensions as possible to be interpretable. The NMDS approach used here and elsewhere (Young 1992; Scannell and Young 1993; Young 1993; Simmen *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1994; Goodhill *et al.* 1995; Scannell *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b) is essentially an approximation of the ratio-level proximity model using ordinal data. NMDS relies on the properties of the coordinate space in which the output is to

be plotted to constrain the data, and therefore judging the dimensionality of ordinal data is important.

If a MDS program is presented with non-Euclidean data, it will attempt to fit that data into the coordinate space required. The degree of fit of NMDS configurations to the input data is measured as the 'stress' of the configuration, where high stress values denote a very poor fit (see Chapter 2). In a non-Euclidean example, the stress of the output configuration will always be greater than zero, although Euclidean data will also have nonzero stress in the presence of measurement error (*e.g.*, Stenson and Knoll 1969). A distance matrix must be positive semi-definite (that is, it must have zero or positive eigenvalues) to be Euclidean, and there is no *a priori* reason why a connection matrix that is based on experimental measurements should meet this criterion. Some measures of proximity (such as the Jaccard or Czekowski coefficients) can be shown to give rise to Euclidean representations in all cases (Gower and Legendre 1986), but these tend to be based on binary variables and analyses of connectivity are based on ordinal connection weights.

It may be that the majority of connection matrices are either not metric (that is, they do not satisfy the triangle inequality), non-Euclidean, or of high dimensionality. If this is the case then the low-dimensional proximity model would be inappropriate to represent neural systems except in special cases.

If ordinal dissimilarity data are analysed with NMDS, the interpoint distances in the configuration would be defined by inequalities between distances. Hence the positions of brain structures in connectivity space would be less well defined and would be denoted by regions rather than points. Configurations made up of these regions are referred to as 'wobblegons' (Best *et al.* 1979). This would mean that NMDS configurations derived from ordinal data are degenerate, that is, there is not only one ideal solution but many. If the data

were Euclidean and without measurement error, real valued cost functions could be used to map this degeneracy. If the underlying dissimilarities are non-Euclidean, are being calculated in an inappropriate number of dimensions, or possess measurement error, a real valued stress function would be nonzero and could be minimised to give an apparently unique solution. Repeating the analysis with a different cost function would probably give produce a different configuration, where each analysis would fit different aspects of the data more accurately. The degeneracy of non-Euclidean solutions may be estimated tentatively by the use of more than one stress function.

The use of this model for low-level ordinal connection data is justifiable because the objective of this work is not to obtain a mathematically perfect representation of the connectivity data. Rather, the aims underlying this method are to understand the organisation of a system in broad terms, establishing the main organisational features of the macrocircuitry in order to use the neuroanatomical data in the literature as a predictive tool (Scannell *et al.* 1996). The limitations described in this section suggest that the proximity model would probably not be capable of providing more than a general description of the organisation of neural systems, even if perfect data describing connection strength were available.

1.6. Thesis plan.

The remainder of this thesis is concerned with the use of the proximity model in investigating the connectional organisation of the rat brain. I will outline my methods of data collation and analysis in Chapter 2. In Chapter 3, I will describe some simulations of NMDS analysis on test data to establish the characteristics of NMDS when reconstructing high-dimensional configurations. Chapter 4 will describe analyses of the connectional organisation of the visual system in the rat. Chapter 5 will be concerned with the connectional organisation of the putative limbic system in the rat. I will present my conclusions in Chapter 6.

Chapter 2

Methods

2. Methods

The first half of this chapter concerns the databasing system that I have used to represent neuroanatomical connection data taken from the literature accurately. In the second half of the chapter I will describe the methods of analysis I have implemented. These methods include optimisation techniques for extracting connection strength information from the database; graph-theoretical programmes to trace pathways through the connection network; and nonmetric multidimensional scaling and nonparametric cluster analysis as methods for analysing the multivariate structure of configurations produced by NMDS.

2.1. Neurobase: a neuroanatomical connection databasing system.

As the first stage of my investigations of connectional organisation in the rat, I designed a neuroanatomical connection database using Microsoft Access 7.0. I then used Microsoft Query to provide an interface between this database and the Microsoft Excel 7.0 spreadsheet environment. This software provided a convenient way of entering, processing and presenting the data, using programs written in Microsoft Excel Visual Basic. I will refer to this database system as ‘Neurobase’ throughout the rest of this thesis. Neurobase was implemented on a 200MHz Pentium PC with 32MB memory and a 2GB hard disk.

Neurobase is organised into three interlinked tables: a parcellation table, a reference table and a connection report table. The parcellation table contains an entry for each neural structure in the parcellation scheme. The connection report table describes the connectivity data, and the reference table contains bibliographic descriptions of the papers in the connection report table.

2.1.1. Parcellation table.

I compiled a table of all the structures in the rat brain. Each area was assigned a unique alphanumeric abbreviation, a ‘tree’ that describes in which other structures it is contained, and a full name. The abbreviations were taken from Swanson’s comprehensive rat brain atlas,

which provides a unified and up-to-date nomenclature (Swanson 1992). An area's tree is a list of all the larger structures that contain the area, with each abbreviation separated by a period. The tree of the CA1 region of the hippocampus is shown as an example in Figure 2-1 below.

Figure 2-1: The tree structure of the CA1 field of the hippocampus.

Entries for alternative Latin and English synonyms were all included in the database as additional entries.

2.1.2. Connection tables.

Each entry in the connection table is a separate report of an axonal connection between two brain areas. A typical neuroanatomical study may contain reports from several different experiments describing the same connection, with the result that a single paper can give rise to several database entries for a single connection.

In general, anatomical papers contain several different types of information concerning connections. A paper usually mentions its most interesting results in its abstract, and cites reports of related connections from other papers in its introduction and discussion. It presents experimental evidence for its findings in the results section and this may consist of reports from several experiments. When I collated data into Neurobase, I included connection reports

from all sections, but concentrated on data from the results section. Each separate connection data entry was classified as either an abstract report, citation or result.

The data-entry strategy I employed covers as much of the published literature as possible. I entered abstract reports from the MEDLINE and B.I.D.S. (Bath Information and Data Services) literature databases, and citations from published reviews (Kolb and Tees 1990; Paxinos 1995).

Connection reports found in the results sections of papers form the bulk of the data in my analyses. I relied on authors' descriptions of connections as the core of each database entry wherever possible, so that every report of experimental evidence supporting the presence of a connection was included. Evidence of a connection from figures and tabulated results was also considered admissible, and was included in the database entry as an annotation.

An example of typical data entries appear in Figure 2-2. This database excerpt has thirteen columns; each one is a separate field containing specific information describing a connection report in the literature.

Reference	Case	IC	rd	λ	Soma_Tree	Soma_Notes	Terminal_Tree	Terminal_Notes	Type
Se89	pg218-219, fig4	P364	P	i>c	0.5 PL	FB.ISO.PL. Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	MDc	Both medial & lateral divisions of rostral MD contained high density of PHA-L fibres which exhibited ... terminal specializations. At midthal lvls, terminal axons persisted in dorlat MD but appeared sparse in medial & central divisions. Few PHA-L in cau MD.	a
Se89	pg218-219, fig4	P364	P	i>c	3 PL	FB.ISO.PL. Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	MDI	Both medial & lateral divisions of rostral MD contained high density of PHA-L fibres which exhibited ... terminal specializations. At midthal lvls, terminal axons persisted in dorlat MD but appeared sparse in medial & central divisions. Few PHA-L in cau MD.	a

Figure 2-2: Excerpt from Neurobase connection database. The two connections are from Sesack *et al.* 1989, *Journal of Comparative Neurology* 290:213-242. The use of abbreviations to describe features was necessary since the length of data fields in Microsoft Excel is restricted to 255 characters.

The ‘Reference’ field holds an abbreviation of the reference of the document containing the report. Each abbreviation is unique, and generally uses the first letters of the authors’ names and the year of publication. A complete list of these abbreviations is contained in the reference table (See Appendix B).

The ‘Case’ field contains the exact page number of the connection report, and the numbers of relevant figures, *e.g.* “pg227, fig1,2, table2”. This is to provide clear directions to the location of the data to allow easy confirmation of the validity of the report. The classification of each report as an abstract, a citation or result is based on the contents of this field: citations are represented by square brackets enclosing the abbreviation of the paper cited, *e.g.*: “pg227: [Se89]”. Abstract reports contain the string ‘abstr’.

The 'I' data field contains a label denoting a specific experiment. It is often the code used by a paper's authors to denote a specific tracer injection or experiment. The role of the entry in this field is to denote which connection densities can be compared directly (see Section 2.2.2).

The 'M' field contains a code to denote the type of tracer method used. The abbreviations used to represent the different methods are listed in Table 2-1:

Code	Method
H	Horseradish Peroxidase
A	Autoradiographic studies
W	Horseradish Peroxidase conjugated with Wheatgerm Agglutinin.
F	Fluorescent Dyes or Beads
L	Lesion Studies
C	Cholera Toxin conjugated to Horseradish Peroxidase
P	<i>Phaseolus vulgaris</i> Leuco-Agglutinin
E	Electrophysiological stimulation
D	D-[3H] Aspartate labeling

Table 2-1: Table of codes used to denote different tracer techniques.

The entry in the 'IC' field denotes whether a connection is wholly ipsilateral, contralateral or a combination of the two: 'i' denotes a totally ipsilateral connection; 'c' a wholly contralateral connection; 'ic' refers to bilateral connections where both sides are equally labelled, 'i>c' or 'c>i' refer to cases where the ipsilateral component is more heavily-labelled than the contralateral, and *vice versa*.

The value in the 'λ' field is the labelling density of the connection report. It can take values from -2 to 3. An entry of '-2' indicates that the experimental labelling may not have been caused by a valid axonal connection, such as for 'fibres of passage'. A connection denoted by '-1' represents a connection of unspecified density. An entry of '0' indicates that a connection had been looked for and found absent. An entry of '1' indicates a sparse connection; '2' indicates a connection of moderate density, and '3' indicates a dense connection. Noninteger values in this field represent intermediate labelling densities, for example, an entry of 1.5 would represent a sparse to moderate labelling density.

Two connection reports often belong to the same labelling density category even though one is demonstrably stronger than the other. I represented this situation by giving the connection reports noninteger ' λ ' values which differ by less than 0.09, *e.g.* the connection from the retina to the superior colliculus was assigned the value 3.02 and the connection from the retina to the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, a value of 3.01. This indicated that both connections could be thought of as dense, but that the connection to the superior colliculus was denser.

The abbreviation in the 'Soma' field denotes the position of the cell bodies involved in the connection. In some anterograde experiments, the injection site spreads over two or more areas, implicating them in the connection report. In these cases, abbreviations representing each of the areas implicated were included in the database entry and separated by slashes. These are referred to as 'mixed connections'. If there was only a minimal spread of tracer into neighbouring areas, the main injection site was written twice, separated by slashes, for example, "SC/SC/PAG" would denote an injection into the superior colliculus (SC) with minimal spread into the periaqueductal grey (PAG). See Appendix A for a key to the abbreviations

The 'Soma Tree' field is the tree of the abbreviation in the 'Soma' field. If the soma field contained a mixed connection, then the soma tree field was organised in an exactly analogous way. Accordingly, the example given above with a 'Soma' entry of "SC/SC/PAG" would have the entry ".BS.SENS.VISBS.SC. / .BS.SENS.VISBS.SC. / .BS.RETIC.CGB.PAG".

The 'Soma Notes' field contains an abbreviated version of a paper's description of the position of the cells involved in a specific connection. This is where the main body of the text describing the connection was entered, and should be considered as the raw connection data of these studies. The contents of this field and the 'Terminal Notes' field provide as much information describing the connection as possible, including the exact phrasing of the

descriptions of labelling densities and injection sites, observations taken from diagrams, and disagreements between the paper itself and others. The number of characters in this field was restricted to a maximum of 255, with the result that words often had to be abbreviated or omitted. This involved substituting ‘inj.’ for ‘injection’, ‘connx.’ for connection, and ‘med.’, ‘lat.’, ‘ven.’, ‘dor.’, ‘cau.’ and ‘ros.’ for ‘medial’, ‘lateral’, ‘ventral’, ‘dorsal’, ‘caudal’ and ‘rostral’; and so on.

For anterograde studies, this field contains a description of the injection site, and in retrograde studies it contained a description of the pattern of retrograde labelling. Annotations are enclosed in ‘<’ and ‘>’ characters, and are written in italics (<fig 4: dense label>). These have been included explicitly so that readers can follow the logic behind a particular interpretation of a given report. This is especially important where database entries are based on evidence presented in figures, since there is no other way of representing this information in the database.

The ‘Terminal’, ‘Terminal Tree’ and ‘Terminal Notes’ fields are exactly analogous to the ‘Soma’, ‘Soma Tree’, and ‘Soma Notes’ fields, describing the positions of terminals associated with a given connection. If the report used an anterograde method, the ‘Terminal Notes’ field contains a description of the terminal labelling; if retrograde methods were used, it contains a description of the injection site. The ‘Type’ field contained ‘r’ if the connection was a retrograde report, and ‘a’ if it was anterograde.

Some comments on data entry

The most important aspect of data entry in Neurobase is that it is easy to corroborate the data through the use of the ‘Case’ data field. The inclusion of page and figure numbers allowed me to reconfirm connection reports when checking the integrity of the data. Previous literature-based databases cite the paper where the neuroanatomical information resides, but do not

represent the original authors' report or indicate the position of this description in the text (*e.g.* Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Young 1992; Scannell *et al.* 1995).

2.1.3. Data matrices and summary tables.

Each connection was classified as one of thirteen categories according to the quality of the report and the experimental labelling density. These categories are listed in Table 2-2.

Category	Category Number	Description of Connection
3	1	Dense connection.
2	2	Moderate connection.
1	3	Sparse connection.
C	4	Connection of unspecified strength.
x	5	Connection appears in an abstract report, and is not reported as mixed.
0	6	Connection has been looked for and found absent
z	7	Connection is reported in an abstract as having been looked for and found absent
u	8	Spurious evidence suggests that the connection could exist, <i>e.g.</i> : fibres of passage
m	9	Mixed Connection: injection or lesion site of experiment involves more than one structure.
G	10	Connection report is citation to another paper
a	11	Mixed connection from an abstract report
d	12	Connection only exists in a report concerning a different animal from a rat.
X	13	Connection is referring to an area connecting with itself or with a part of itself

Table 2-2: The categories of connection report used while extracting matrices and summary tables..

Excel Macros written in Visual Basic were used to prepare matrices and summary tables of data pertaining to a selected sets of connections. The data entries for a given connection were sorted in ascending order of category number, and the value of the 'λ' field of the report with the lowest category number was used in subsequent analysis (See Appendix C).

2.2. Methods of analysis of neuroanatomical data

In this section, I will describe the theory and implementation of the methods of analysis which I have employed to investigate the connectional organisation of brain systems in the rat. It is divided into four parts: the use of a rudimentary form of graph theory (called 'pathway tracing analysis'); a novel method of calculating probabilistic connection weights from the literature

described in Neurobase; the use of NMDS analysis to examine neural connectivity data; and the use of nonparametric cluster analysis in interpreting NMDS output.

2.2.1. Pathway tracing analyses.

I have employed a form of graph theory in order to search for ‘pathways’ between specified structures in the connection database. Each connection reported in Neurobase was weighted in a rudimentary sense. I used these weights to prioritise the pathways: pathways involving stronger individual connections were considered more important. However, this is only a simplified view of the organisation of neural systems, since it is possible for ‘weak’ neuromodulatory connections to have profound effects on the physiological activity of a structure (Foote and Morrison 1987). I used a Microsoft Excel Visual Basic macro to compile lists of all possible efferent pathways from the brain area at the origin of the pathway (*e.g.* $B \rightarrow E \rightarrow D$). Such lists were typically many thousands of lines long.

The subparcellation problem

Descriptions of pathways which are based on connections between structures defined at multiple levels may not take important intra-area or ‘intrinsic’ connections into account. This situation is illustrated in Figure 2-3. From the organisation of the left-hand diagram, the pathway $B \rightarrow E \rightarrow D$ appears to be the most important pathway; but when the underlying organisation of the connections of the system is actually shown, as in the right-hand diagram, the weight of the $B \rightarrow E_a \rightarrow E_b \rightarrow D$ pathway depends upon the intra-area connection $E_a \rightarrow E_b$. At the present time, it is extremely difficult to measure the ‘density’ or ‘strength’ of intrinsic connections. If the subparcellation of area E contains populations of cells which do not interact strongly, it may be difficult to define clearly which pathways exist.

Figure 2-3: The subparcellation problem.

2.2.2. Calculating ordinal connection weights for neural connections from noncomparable neuroanatomical studies.

Attempting to extract quantitative connection weights from the neuroanatomical literature is a very difficult task. The data are almost universally qualitative; the nomenclature is disparate and nonstandardised; different papers use a variety of techniques and approaches and also describe their data with parcellation schemes at different scales. The strategy of my work relies upon the supposition that it is possible to compare tracer labelling patterns of connections in certain circumstances. If two connections were labelled in the same experiment and one labelling pattern was significantly denser, then the more densely labelled connection could be said to be stronger than the other. Such comparisons will be referred to as ‘reliable’. But, if two connections were labelled in different experiments with the same technique and one connection was very much more densely labelled, it was likely that that this connection was stronger than the other. These comparisons will be referred to as ‘tentative’. I have made a list of comparisons by searching through all the data in Neurobase concerning the connections under study. I have analysed these comparisons using MBOLTZMANN, a hierarchical optimisation programme (Hilgetag *et al.* 1996a), to produce ordinal connection weights estimates for a given system. This was accomplished by building an intermediate database of all possible comparisons in a given connection system from the data available. I will describe how the ‘reliable’ and ‘tentative’ comparisons were made below.

Reliable comparisons

I sorted all connection data concerning the system under study into groups of connection reports which had identical entries in their 'Reference' and 'Label' data fields. This indicated that the separate connection reports originated from the same paper and experiment or were directly comparable by virtue of being semi-quantitative. Some papers stated that a given connection was denser than another, even though the data that indicated this came from separate experiments. I chose to regard these observations as evidence for the comparison to be represented in the database.

Consider two connections: the first from area A to area B the second from area A to area C. If two connection reports from a single experiment had different ' λ ' values then conclusions about their relative strength were made based on this difference. This can be expressed mathematically as follows: if ' λ_{AB} ' and ' λ_{AC} ' denote the labelling density of connections from A to B and from A to C, and $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)}$ is defined as $\lambda_{AB} - \lambda_{AC}$ (where λ_{AB} and λ_{AC} are equal to or greater than zero) then deductions concerning the actual connection strengths ' c_{AB} ' and ' c_{AC} ' can be based on values of $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)}$. The example described here is of an 'efferent comparison'. An equivalent 'afferent comparison' might compare the connections from A to C, and from B to C, through the use of the variable $\partial\lambda_{(AB)C} = \lambda_{AC} - \lambda_{BC}$. The possible conclusions will be described in the following sections and are identified by the symbols '>', '<', '>=', '<=' and '=' and their opposites. I will use efferent comparisons as examples.

One connection is stronger than another: '>' ('<')

This condition indicates that the comparison between λ_{AB} and λ_{AC} suggests that c_{AB} is unequivocally greater than c_{AC} . It occurs in three circumstances:

- 1) When $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)}$ is greater than 0.5. This means that the connection $A \rightarrow B$ is in a denser category than the connection $A \rightarrow C$.

- 2) When $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)}$ is greater than zero but less than 0.09. This means that the two connection reports belong to the same labelling density category, but one is demonstrably denser than the other.
- 3) When λ_{AB} is equal to -1, and λ_{AC} is equal to 0. This means that a connection of unknown density is denser than an absent connection. Connections of unknown density (*i.e.* ‘ λ ’ values of -1) were only evaluated by this sort of comparison.

One connection is stronger than or of equal strength to another: ‘>=’ (‘<=’)

This condition indicates that the comparison between λ_{AB} and λ_{AC} shows that c_{AB} is either greater than, or equal to c_{AC} . It occurs when $0.09 < \partial\lambda_{A(BC)} \leq 0.5$. For example, where one connection is described as “moderate/dense”, and another connection is described as moderate (*i.e.* $\lambda_{AB} = 2.5$, $\lambda_{AC} = 2$ and $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)} = 0.5$).

The connections are of indistinguishable strength: ‘=’

This condition indicates that there were connection reports where λ_{AB} is equal to λ_{AC} . It is not interpreted to mean that c_{AB} and c_{AC} are precisely equal.

Tentative comparisons

I sorted the connection database into groups with identical entries in both the ‘M’ and the ‘Type’ data fields, so that the connections within a single group were labelled by a given experimental technique in a given transport direction. The different conditions that these comparisons produced were labelled ‘<?’, ‘>?’, ‘<=?’, ‘>=?’ and ‘=?’. These categories were assigned in an identical manner as the reliable comparisons, except that the ‘>?’ condition requires $\partial\lambda_{A(BC)}$ to be greater than 1.5, if c_{AB} was to be considered greater than c_{AC} . This required a substantial difference in labelling density between studies to support the claim. No other situations can give rise to a ‘>?’ condition.

Subparcelled data

The problem presented by incorporating data from subparcelled data is illustrated in Figure 2-4.

Figure 2-4: Idealised diagram of subparcelled connection data.

This illustrates a typical comparison between two connections $A \rightarrow B$ and $A \rightarrow C$. Unfortunately, in this case, there are no connections reported from A to C, (only those from A to Ca and Cb, where Ca and Cb are both subareas that lie within C). I have defined a new category of comparisons called ‘subparcelled comparisons’, which can be either ‘reliable’ or ‘tentative’ as described in the previous section. They are denoted ‘>s’, ‘<s’, ‘>=s’, ‘<=s’, ‘=s’, ‘>?s’, ‘<?s’, ‘>=?s’, ‘<=?s’, and ‘=?s’. Subparcelled connection comparisons are comparisons between $A \rightarrow B$ and $A \rightarrow C$, which are supported by information concerning connections to a subparcelled region within one of the areas such as $A \rightarrow Ca$. This presented me with a problem. How can I compare the connections $A \rightarrow C$ and $A \rightarrow B$ if $A \rightarrow Ca$ has one value and $A \rightarrow Cb$ has another? My approach was to prioritise different connection comparisons and to only accept the evidence from comparisons with the highest priority. If comparisons with the highest priority contradicted each other then the entire comparison was disregarded. The priority of the different comparisons is defined in Table 2-3.

Priority	Conditions	Comparison Type
11	<, >	Reliable
10	<=, >=	Reliable
9	=	Reliable
8	<s, >s, =s	Reliable, Subparcellated
7	<=s, >=s	Reliable, Subparcellated
6	<?, >?	Tentative
5	<=? , >=?	Tentative
4	=?	Tentative
3	<s?, >s?, =s?	Tentative, Subparcellated
2	<=s?, >=s?	Tentative, Subparcellated
1	C	Contradiction

Table 2-3: Priority of different comparison conditions in the GTLT algorithm

In the example above, if $\lambda_{AB} = 1$ and $\lambda_{ACa} = 2$ in two reports from the same paper and experiment, the data comparison condition will be ‘<s’. If another comparison condition exists which has a higher priority, then the condition just described will be ignored in favour of the new comparison. This would require the presence of a ‘nonsubparcellated reliable comparison’. If there is data supporting two different comparison codes of the same priority, then the data is judged to be contradictory and all conditions will then be ignored.

MBOLTZMANN.

The problem facing this analysis is to construct a hierarchy of connection strengths, by bringing together all of the individual comparisons between connections without violating more than a minimum of the comparison constraints. Fortunately, this problem has already been solved by MBOLTZMANN, a computer classifier that can evaluate exactly these sort of hierarchical constraints to produce a set of optimally organised hierarchies. This is ideal, since the output set can provide statistics which show how well a given data set is constrained. The MBOLTZMANN algorithm has been described elsewhere (Hilgetag *et al.* 1995; Hilgetag *et al.* 1996a), but a short explanatory example will be presented here. Consider a system of the four efferent connections of area A to areas B, C, D and E. These connections are denoted AB, AC, AD and AE. A constraint table is extracted from the literature to indicate how the strength of each connection compares with every other connection in the analysis, i.e. ‘AB is

stronger than AC, AD is weaker than or equivalent to AE'. In order to construct an optimised hierarchy, MBOLTZMANN generates a randomised list of connections where connections in a higher position in the list are presupposed to be stronger than connections lower in the list. MBOLTZMANN counts the number of constraints that are violated in this list (i.e. 'AB is stronger than AC but occupies a lower position in the list') and generates new lists by swapping connections' positions in order to minimise the number of violations.

Processing information: memory & storage requirements.

I ran the MBOLTZMANN programme on a DEC Alpha 3000 machine with 256 MB of main memory and a 10 GB hard disk. As is the case with most optimisation algorithms, this method was computationally intensive. MBOLTZMANN has been designed to be able to resume a run if the programme terminates prematurely, so it was possible to perform very long runs to search for as many solutions as possible.

Output data and statistics

The output data of MBOLTZMANN is presented in a 'best structure file' and a 'log file'. The best structure file is a list of the best hierarchies generated. This file also describes the constraints that were violated for each hierarchy and the output statistics of the positions of connections within hierarchies. The log file describes the progress of the run.

The series of connection hierarchies in the best structure file have different numbers of levels for each comparison matrix. These hierarchies are ordered lists of connections in ascending order of connection strength. Given a count of N_c connections, the total number of possible hierarchies ϖ is given by Equation 2-1.

$$\varpi = \sum_{m=1}^{N_c} \mathbf{s}_{N_c}^{(m)} (m!) = \sum_{m=1}^{N_c} \sum_{k=0}^m (-1)^{m-k} \binom{m}{k} k^{N_c} \quad \text{Equation 2-1}$$

Where $\mathcal{S}_{N_c}^{(m)}$ is a Stirling number of the second kind describing all possible ways of partitioning a set of N_c elements into m empty subsets (Abramowitz and Stegun 1972; Hilgetag *et al.* 1995). Some values of ϖ for given values of N_c have been tabulated in Table 2-4. The possible number of solution hierarchies becomes extremely large very quickly with increasing N_c .

Number of Connections	Maximum Number of Solutions
1	1
2	3
3	13
4	75
5	541
6	4683
7	47293
8	545835
9	7087261
10	102247600
11	1622633000
12	28091570000
13	5.26858E+11
14	1.06413E+13
15	2.30283E+14
16	5.31566E+15
17	1.30371E+17
18	3.38554E+18
19	9.28016E+19
20	2.67769E+21

Table 2-4: Calculated size of search space used by MBOLTZMANN in calculating optimal hierarchies for sets of connections with 1 to 20 elements.

I compared connection weights from hierarchies with different numbers of levels to give a normalised connection strength with values from 0 to 1. In a hierarchy with L levels, a connection that occupies the l^{th} level is assigned a normalised connection strength of $\frac{l}{L}$. The connection strength estimate is the mean of the distribution across all hierarchies, (See Figure 2-2).

$$\bar{C}_{AB} = \frac{1}{N_c} \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \frac{l_i^{AB}}{L_i} \quad \text{Equation 2-2}$$

\bar{C}_{AB} is the connection strength estimate of the connection from A to B, l_i^{AB} is the rank of the connection from A to B in the i^{th} hierarchy, L_i is the total number of levels in the i^{th} hierarchy and N_c is the total number of connections.

The statistical variation in this value can be calculated as the standard deviation of this sample calculated in the following formula

$$S_{AB} = \sqrt{\frac{N_c \sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \left(\frac{I_i^{AB}}{L_i} \right)^2 - \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_c} \frac{I_i^{AB}}{L_i} \right)^2}{N_c (N_c - 1)}} \quad \text{Equation 2-3}$$

This gives a scaled connection weight (\bar{C}_{AB}) between 0 and 1 and a scaled indication of how well this value is constrained by the connection data.

2.2.3. NMDS analyses

Nonmetric multidimensional scaling is the principal method of analysis used in this thesis. It is for this reason that I include a thorough description of the mathematical formulation of the technique here.

Basic concepts

In a set of N interacting objects, where the degree of interaction between every pair of objects (i, j) can be numerically measured as a variable c_{ij} , NMDS can summarise the matrix of interactions, \mathbf{C} , in a single illustrative representation. The technique was originally devised for psychometric data, but has been used in a wide variety of applications (Cox and Cox 1995).

Consider an $N \times N$ matrix of observations, \mathbf{C} , with elements c_{ij} , such that a high value of c_{ij} represents a high degree of interaction, or ‘similarity’ between objects i and j . We can also define a measure of ‘dissimilarity’: an $N \times N$ matrix, \mathbf{A} , with elements, ∂_{ij} , that are calculated according to Equation 2-4. High ‘similarity’ values of c_{ij} correspond to low ‘dissimilarity’ values of ∂_{ij} .

$$\partial_{ij} = c_{\max} - c_{ij} \quad \text{where } c_{\max} \text{ is the largest matrix element } c_{ij} \text{ in } \mathbf{C} \quad \text{Equation 2-4}$$

I will describe how NMDS works with a simple numerical example: consider a symmetrical numerical matrix \mathbf{C}^{eg} , denoting interactions or similarities between six numbered objects.

C^{es}	1	2	3	4	5	6
1						
2	32.9					
3	15.7	27.4				
4	38.0	21.7	28.2			
5	23.0	28.5	24.4	16.0		
6	14.5	2.6	19.9	11.8	20.5	

Figure 2-5: An observation matrix, C^{es} . The matrix contains 15 separate data entries. I have only considered the lower triangle since the data is symmetrical.

The corresponding dissimilarity matrix is shown in Figure 2-6.

Δ^{es}	1	2	3	4	5	6
1						
2	5.1					
3	22.3	10.6				
4	0.0	16.3	9.8			
5	15.0	9.5	13.6	22.0		
6	23.5	35.4	18.1	26.2	17.5	

Figure 2-6: Dissimilarity matrix, Δ^{es} . This is a measure of the level of ‘noninteraction’ between objects 1 to 6.

Within an NMDS model, the N objects are represented as points embedded in a Euclidean coordinate space of M dimensions, represented by an $N \times M$ matrix of coordinates, \mathbf{X} , with elements x_{ij} , corresponding to the j^{th} ordinate of the i^{th} point. The distance between the i^{th} and j^{th} points is denoted d_{ij} and is calculated according to the Pythagoras theorem (Equation 2-5) to give an $N \times N$ matrix \mathbf{D} , with elements d_{ij} .

$$d_{ij} = \sqrt{\sum_{k=1}^M (x_{ik} - x_{jk})^2} \quad \text{Equation 2-5}$$

Each distance, d_{ij} , in the model has a corresponding ‘proximity’, p_{ij} , defined according to Equation 2-6 where d_{max} is the maximum distance in the configuration.

$$p_{ij} = d_{max} - d_{ij} \quad \text{Equation 2-6}$$

MDS analyses fit the coordinates of points in the configuration so that every distance between points, d_{ij} , is fitted to the corresponding dissimilarity value δ_{ij} . The exact way in which this is accomplished depends heavily upon the type of data under study and will be explored more completely in the next section.

Types of data

One of the principal reasons why NMDS is a useful tool in analysing neural connectivity data is its capability to analyse qualitative data in an objective and quantitative way. I shall follow the classification scheme most commonly used in the MDS literature, by describing the various different scales of measurement as ‘nominal’, ‘ordinal’, ‘interval’ and ‘ratio’ (Stevens 1951; Coombs 1964; Takane *et al.* 1977; Cox and Cox 1995). These scales denote qualitative differences between types of measurement.

Nominal measurements are not numerical but descriptive. Different values of such a measure refer to different categories. Eye colour is a typical nominal measurement variable. Ordinal measurements are numerical and can be ordered so that one measurement can be ‘greater than’ or ‘less than’ another but it is impossible to say by how much.

Figure 2-7 shows ordinal versions of the dissimilarity matrix in the numerical example. The left-hand data matrix is called Δ^{*best} , because every interaction has been allocated a unique rank giving the maximum number of ranks. The right-hand ordinal matrix, Δ^{deg} , is more representative of the kind of data available to studies of neural connectivity with many tied ranks.

Δ^{*best}	1	2	3	4	5	6
1						
2	1					
3	11	4				
4	0	7	3			
5	6	2	5	10		
6	12	14	9	13	8	

Δ^{deg}	1	2	3	4	5	6
1						
2	0					
3	2	1				
4	0	1	0			
5	1	0	1	2		
6	2	2	2	2	1	

Figure 2-7: Examples of ordinal dissimilarity matrices.

The relative sizes of values in interval and ratio measurements are meaningful. They differ only in that the ratio measurements have a well defined zero point. This means that the absolute value of ratio measurements carry meaning, whereas only the relative values of interval values can be interpreted. The Kelvin temperature scale is a ratio measure; a

temperature scale with an undefined zero point would be an interval measure. Neural connectivity data are typically defined at the ordinal level.

How the algorithm works.

Nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) can be used to produce configurations from qualitative ordinal and nominal data. In this section, I will describe a typical algorithmic method for calculating the cost function to be reduced in an ordinal NMDS calculation (Kruskal 1964; Takane *et al.* 1977).

Consider an $N \times N$ ordinal observation matrix, \mathbf{C} , with elements, c_{ij} , and a corresponding dissimilarity matrix, \mathbf{A} , with elements, ∂_{ij} . In this worked example, I constrain these matrices to be symmetrical about the leading diagonal of \mathbf{C} . The central principle of ordinal NMDS is that the following conditions be met.

$$\text{If } c_{ij} < c_{kl} \text{ then } \partial_{ij} > \partial_{kl} \text{ and } d_{ij} > d_{kl}$$

$$\text{If } c_{ij} > c_{kl} \text{ then } \partial_{ij} < \partial_{kl} \text{ and } d_{ij} < d_{kl} \qquad \text{Equation 2-7}$$

When two values in the observation matrix are equal, one of two approaches can be used. In the ‘untied’ approach, no judgement is made concerning the relative values of the corresponding distances. In the ‘tied’ approach, two equal observations require that the two distances are equal as well (as shown in Equation 2-8).

$$\text{If } c_{ij} = c_{kl} \text{ then } d_{ij} = d_{kl} \qquad \text{Equation 2-8}$$

The key to finding a configuration where the constraints from Equation 2-7 are met, lies in the definition of an appropriate ‘stress’ function that describes how poorly the distances in the configuration fit the ordinal characteristics of the observation matrix. A preliminary stage of the definition of stress, is to define ‘disparity’ (a variable that relates the distances in the configuration to the observation matrix). I define disparity as an $N \times N$ matrix, \mathbf{D}^* , with elements, d_{ij}^* . \mathbf{D}^* can be thought of as a transformed version of \mathbf{D} that satisfies all of the

constraints imposed by Equations 2-7 and 2-8. The stress function is based on the difference between disparity and distance, and can be thought of as a measure of how much the distances would have to be modified in order to have them satisfy the ordinal conditions of the original data.

Given a configuration of points described by a matrix of coordinates, \mathbf{X} , and a dissimilarity matrix, \mathbf{A} , the algorithm calculates the distance matrix, \mathbf{D} , and compares the data structure of \mathbf{A} and \mathbf{D} . This is achieved by arranging each element of the two matrices, d_{ij} and ∂_{ij} , in two ordered one-dimensional lists where the k^{th} entries are denoted by $(d_{ij})^k$ and $(\partial_{ij})^k$, and equivalent matrix entries occupy the same position in the list. The values of elements of this list are arranged in ascending order of $(\partial_{ij})^k$ so that the condition $(\partial_{ij})^k \leq (\partial_{ij})^{k+1}$ is always maintained. Values of the distance matrix that violate the ordinal constraints will satisfy the condition $(d_{ij})^k > (d_{ij})^{k+1}$.

An equivalent ordered list of disparity values is calculated so that its value always increases or remains constant as k increases, *i.e.* $(d_{ij}^*)^k \leq (d_{ij}^*)^{k+1}$. This can be achieved with the iterative procedure described below.

1) Each disparity value is set to be equal to each corresponding distance value, *i.e.* $(d_{ij}^*)^k = (d_{ij})^k$. Each disparity value is assigned to a separate ‘partition’, where all disparity values in the same partition have equal $(d_{ij}^*)^k$ values.

2) Loop through the list of $(d_{ij}^*)^k$ varying k from 1 to $\frac{1}{2}N(N-1)$. On each iteration of the loop, if $(d_{ij}^*)^k > (d_{ij}^*)^{k+1}$ or $(d_{ij}^*)^k < (d_{ij}^*)^{k-1}$ then join the two partitions containing both values, and set all disparity values of each in the partition to the mean partition disparity value. See Figure 2-9 for an example.

The stress of the configuration, $S^{(1)}$, is simply the normalised sum of the differences between the distances and the disparities.

$$S^{(1)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (d_{ij} - d_{ij}^*)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (d_{ij}^*)^2}} \quad \text{Equation 2-9}$$

The $S^{(1)}$ notation indicates that this stress function is based on the first powers of d_{ij} and d_{ij}^* .

However, $S^{(1)}$ is not the only stress function available, and there follows a brief description of other stress functions. In all cases, disparity is defined in the same way.

$$S^{(2)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (d_{ij}^2 - d_{ij}^{*2})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (d_{ij}^{*2})^2}} \quad \text{Equation 2-10}$$

The $S^{(2)}$ cost function is the equivalent to ‘SSTRESS’, which is defined in the ‘alternating least squares method’ of NMDS (ALSCAL, Kruskal 1964; Takane *et al.* 1977). It means that larger distances tend to contribute more to stress than small distances. Within NMDS, this means that the algorithm will place greater emphasis on accurately modelling small observation values with large distances. The reverse is true of $S^{(0.5)}$, where smaller distances are better fitted in the output configurations because they contribute more to the overall stress value.

$$S^{(0.5)} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (\sqrt{d_{ij}} - \sqrt{d_{ij}^*})^2}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{j=1}^N (\sqrt{d_{ij}^*})^2}} \quad \text{Equation 2-11}$$

Hence, the problem of finding the optimum configuration simplifies to the task of minimising the chosen stress function with respect to \mathbf{X} under a specified approach to ties, as illustrated in the following example.

The initial configuration, X^{init} , is a randomly generated two dimensional configuration made up of six points. Its coordinates are shown in Figure 2-8, and its distance and disparity values are plotted in Figure 2-9. The length of the vertical lines correspond to each distance's contribution to the overall stress of the system. The equivalent distance and disparity graph has been plotted in Figure 2-10 after the configuration's stress had been minimised. The vertical lines are much shorter, and so the ordinal level of fit was much better. The output configuration is shown in Figure 2-11.

X^{init}		
1	0.13	0.85
2	0.13	-0.19
3	0.18	0.39
4	-0.31	0.90
5	-0.28	-0.97
6	-0.56	0.04

Figure 2-8: Initial configuration of six points for test data, the coordinates were generated randomly..

Figure 2-9: Graph of disparity and distance, displaying concept of monotone regression.. The graph displays the distance and disparity values for a 'high stress' initial configuration prior to optimisation.

Distance & Disparity for Optimised Configuration of Test Data

Figure 2-10: Graph of disparity and distance, displaying effect of monotone regression optimisation.

Figure 2-11: This figure illustrates the interactions between objects 1 to 6 in a two-dimensional configuration of points calculated by MDS in the SAS statistical package.

An interpretation of Figure 2-11 immediately suggests organisational properties of the six objects. Object 6 appears to be an outlier. Objects 2 and 5 are closely related, as are objects 3 and 4. Object 1 seems to be intermediate between objects 2, 3, 4, and 5 but a long way from object 6. This is typical of the output of an NMDS analysis.

Similarity transforms

I have used data conditioning methods to avoid the effects of sparsity (see Section 1.5.2). Here, I will describe two methods, which I will call the ‘pathlength’ (*pthl*) and the ‘weighted dissimilarity’ (*wdsm*) transform methods.

Pathlength transform (*pth1*)

Consider an observation matrix, C , containing many zero values, $(c_{ij})^0$. In an NMDS model, they would correspond to a set of large distances, $(d_{ij})^0$. If these distances are not constrained to be equal, it would be possible to distinguish between different observations, $(c_{ij})^0$, by searching for routes involving nonzero observations throughout the data. This idea is illustrated in Figure 2-12.

Figure 2-12: Illustration of the pathlength transform. AB and AC are both '0' values but under the *pth1* transform we recognize the ADB path as shorter than the ADC path, because the sum of the intermediate nonzero observations along the ADB path is greater than that of those along the ADC path.

The *pth1* transform can be used to increase the ordinality of observation matrices (that is, the number of ranks present in the ordinal matrix). It is not always completely reliable and can misassign ordinal levels. This data method is most effective on observation matrices where a large number of intermediate steps are required to reconstruct the longest distances used (Young *et al.* 1995b).

Weighted dissimilarity transform (*wdsm*)

The *wdsm* transform derives a secondary similarity matrix W with elements w_{ij} based on observation matrix elements, c_{ij} , which is based on the following formula.

$$w_{ij} = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^N |c_{ik} - c_{jk}|}{\sum_{k=1}^N |c_{ik} + c_{jk}|}$$

Equation 2-12

This transform has proved most efficient at reconstructing the data structure of degraded test data in two dimensions (Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b). It is not, strictly speaking, a method which is specifically designed for reconstructing ordinal data.

The *wdsm* transform is based on the same equations as the Czekowski coefficient, (a standard method of extracting dissimilarities from binary data) (Gower and Legendre 1986; Cox and Cox 1995). The Czekowski similarity coefficient can be shown to produce Euclidean output proximities under all conditions, whereas this has not been shown for *wdsm* (Gower and Legendre 1986).

***The 'shape' of neural systems and problems associated with choice of
parcellation schemes.***

The shape of configurations can be represented mathematically by the frequency histogram of the distances between points in the configuration. If the composition of the connection matrix is changed, by adding areas that strongly connect to every other structure, this will change the overall shape of the output configuration.

This issue is significant when considering the composition of a matrix containing nuclei which can be subdivided. Three options exist in such cases. The analyses could be performed on a matrix that includes both the nuclei and subnuclei (*i.e.* a matrix might contain the pretectum, and two of its constituent nuclei: the nucleus of the optic tract, and the optic nucleus, see Section 4.3). The analysis would treat the relationship between an area and its subareas as a strong connection in NMDS analyses. This approach has the advantages of using all the connection data available, but has a tendency to produce clusters made up of structures and their subnuclei.

Alternatively, the substructure of nuclei could be dropped, and only the parent structure included in the analysis. No connection data is lost, since all connections to and from subnuclei are included in the connections of the higher level structure.

A third possibility would be to include only sub-nuclei in the analysis. This would mean that connections reported to terminate or originate in the higher level structure would be ignored. Connection studies involving smaller, more finely delineated areas tend to be more recent and rarer, so this approach has a tendency to ignore data from older papers and to generate sparse connectivity matrices. If two brain nuclei were included in the same structure as part of a parcellation scheme, there should, in theory, be no bias to associate them in an NMDS model unless they were interconnected or had similar patterns of connectivity. In addition to these constraints, the shape of proximity representations of neural systems will be greatly influenced by the use of similarity transforms, and the way the similarity variable is defined.

Procrustes analysis

Procrustes rotation fits one configuration of N points in M dimensions (called the ‘fitted’ configuration) to another equivalent configuration (called the ‘fixed’ configuration) by applying the isotropic dilation, rigid translation, rotation and reflection that most closely match the two configurations (Cox and Cox 1995). I use Procrustes analysis to test the validity of the NMDS method, as well allowing the quantitative comparison of configurations.

The output of Procrustes analysis is the rotated coordinates of two configurations and a measure of the fit between them: the Procrustes R^2 value. This is the measure I use to judge the quality of fit between the two configurations. This is defined in equation 2-13.

$$R^2 = 1 - \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\sum_{j=1}^M (x_{ij}^{Fix} - x_{ij}^{Fit})^2 \right) \quad \text{Equation 2-13}$$

where x_{ij}^{Fix} is the j^{th} ordinate of the i^{th} point in the ‘fixed’ configuration and x_{ij}^{Fit} is the j^{th} ordinate of the i^{th} point in the ‘fitted’ configuration.

Both sets of coordinates have their centroids positioned at the origin and the variance of all points in each dimension set to unity during the course of this procedure.

Technical details of analysis method.

I used the MDS procedure in the SAS 6.09 statistics software (SAS Technical Report P-229 SAS/STAT Software: Changes and Enhancements. Chapter 15. The MDS procedure, pp 249-286) on a Sun SPARC Center 2000 with 10 processors and 768Mb RAM, or on a G6-200 Pentium PC with 32 Mb RAM. I used a combination of C programmes, UNIX C shell scripts and Perl 5 programmes to generate the code automatically and commands for the analyses.

2.2.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis.

All published studies of neural connectivity that use NMDS have presented only two-dimensional plots (Young 1992; Young 1993; Simmen *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1994; Goodhill *et al.* 1995; Scannell *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b). Two- and three-dimensional representations may misrepresent data by using too low a dimensionality, but NMDS configurations in higher dimensions cannot be interpreted by visual inspection. This misrepresentation is visible in two dimensional configurations where lines are added to represent connections, since long lines on this configuration represent poorly fitted connections (See Young 1992). Here, I describe how nonparametric cluster analysis can be used to interpret configurations of low to intermediate dimensionality.

Cluster analysis is a method of classification (Gordon 1981). Given a set of N objects, cluster analysis seeks to partition the set into clusters, so that members of the same cluster have similar properties. The NMDS method naturally lends itself to this approach, since the criteria used to group objects together can be represented by the distances between the objects' points in the configuration. Within this framework, a cluster can be loosely defined as a local maximum of the point density in the space inhabited by the configuration.

Nonparametric density estimation provides a means of modelling the density function as a random variable without making assumptions concerning the form of the true density function. Methods of cluster analysis based on nonparametric density estimation can detect clusters of unequal size and dispersion or with highly irregular shapes. The MODECLUS function in the SAS/STAT statistical analysis package was used, since it could perform nonparametric cluster analysis with significance testing.

Density estimation.

Probability density functions are an important conceptual tool in statistical analyses. If a random variable X has a probability density function f , the probability that a sampled value, x , has a value lying between the limits, a and b , is denoted by Equation 2-14.

$$P(a < x < b) = \int_a^b f(y)dy \quad \text{for all } a < b \quad \text{Equation 2-14}$$

Given a set of data points sampled from an unknown probability density function, the process of nonparametric density estimation seeks to construct the probability density function from the observed data. The most widely used method of density estimation for multivariate data is the kernel method. Given a sample of N observations of M variables, (represented as N points in a coordinate space of M dimensions, where the j^{th} coordinate of the i^{th} point is denoted by x_{ij}), the estimated density at a position y (with coordinates $y_1, y_2 \dots, y_M$) can be written according to Equation 2-15.

$$\hat{f}(y_1, y_2, \dots, y_M) = \sum_{j=1}^M \sum_{i=1}^N k(|y_j - x_{ij}|, l) \quad \text{Equation 2-15}$$

The function $k(|y_i - x_{ij}|, l)$ is the ‘kernel function’, which determines each point’s contribution to the density at y . In general, kernel functions are symmetrical, and bell-shaped so that they decline to zero with increasing distance. This ensures that only the local points surrounding a

given position will contribute to the density function at that position. In a general sense, the kernel parameter, l , is the maximum distance a single point must be from a given position to affect the density at that position. The choice of l mostly determines the ‘smoothness’ of the density function. Since cluster analysis attempts to detect the local maxima of the density function, a suitable choice of l is essential. The reader is referred to Silvermann (1986) or Scott (1992) for an introduction to density estimation.

For my analyses of neural connectivity, the probability density functions were estimated for NMDS configurations. Connectionally defined groups of areas or nuclei which correspond to the organisational framework of the system appear as local maxima of this density function.

The MODECLUS procedure uses uniform, spherical kernels of a fixed, or variable radius to estimate density at each point in the NMDS configuration. I define the ‘neighbourhood’ of the i^{th} point, X^i , to be a hypersphere of radius l , centred at $\mathbf{x}_i=(x_{i1}, x_{i2}, \dots, x_{iM})$, so that any observation with a point lying within the neighbourhood of X^i is a ‘neighbour’ of X^i . Many aspects of the MODECLUS procedure revolve around the definition of neighbourhoods.

If the volume of the neighbourhood of X^i is denoted as V^i , and X^i has η^i neighbours, the estimated density at X^i is given by Equation 2-16.

$$\hat{f}^i = \frac{\eta^i}{NV^i} \quad \text{Equation 2-16}$$

The MODECLUS procedure uses two alternative definitions of the neighbourhood to calculate density. One is fixed, so that all points have identical kernel radii. The other is based on the ‘ k^{th} nearest-neighbour’ approach where the neighbourhood-radius of X^i is defined as the minimum distance required to include the closest $k-1$ points in X^i ’s neighbourhood.

Clustering algorithm.

Once the density function has been estimated for a given set of points, the MODECLUS procedure detects the local maxima of the density function to define the cluster structure of the data. The clustering method variable was set to the METHOD=1 option for this purpose.

Algorithmically, this method can be described in the following steps:

1. Assign each observation to a separate cluster.
2. For each observation, find the nearest-neighbour with a greater estimated density. If such a neighbour exists, join the observation and neighbour's clusters together.
3. Define a set of observations where the estimated density is equal to that at one or more neighbours, but not less than the estimate at any neighbour.
4. For each member of this set of observations, join the cluster containing the observation with every cluster containing a neighbour of the observation where the cluster's maximum density estimate is equal to that of the observation.
5. For each member of this set of observations, join the cluster containing the observation with the cluster containing the nearest-neighbour of the observation where that clusters' maximum estimated density is greater than the estimated density at the observation.

MODECLUS allows the use of fixed or variable radius neighbourhoods of different sizes to perform the density estimation and clustering separately. This feature was used with a nearest-neighbour clustering paradigm combined with the JOIN option.

Significance testing.

The MODECLUS procedure can test the significance of clusters by comparing the maximum estimated density at points within the cluster to the maximum estimated density at the cluster's boundary. Points are considered to be at the boundary if they have neighbours

outside of the current cluster. This process yields an approximate significance ‘ p value’ (see SAS/STAT Users Guide Chapter 19, The MODECLUS procedure). Fixed-radius density estimation radius kernels are required for this process.

Under the JOIN option, MODECLUS produces a hierarchical scheme (called a ‘cluster tree’) where clusters are sequentially dissolved in ascending order of significance. The points of a dissolved cluster are left unassigned if there are no points from neighbouring clusters within a single kernel radius. If the clusters are sequentially joined to provide a tree, this can give an indication of the relative proximity of separate clusters. I will clarify these issues in Chapter 4 where I present a worked example of this methodology (see Section 4.1.4).

Computational implementation.

Given a connection matrix, I generated two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations using the $S^{(1)}$, $S^{(2)}$ and $S^{(0.5)}$ cost functions under the tied and untied approaches in the SAS/STAT MDS procedure. This produced twelve output configurations per input matrix. I used five dimensions because the accuracy of density estimation falls with increased dimensionality, requiring very large numbers of observations at high dimensions (Epanechnikov 1969; Silvermann 1986). Five-dimensional space was selected because of good performance in preliminary trials of this method in comparison to analyses with higher dimensionality.

Cluster analysis imposes a classification onto a dataset based on the cluster parameters chosen for the analysis. It is often possible to find class structure in data even if no class structure exists (Gordon 1996). In order to examine the class structure in a way that was as unbiased as possible, I ran many analyses with a wide variety of different clustering parameters, and reported the most consistent features that occurred in the output clustering schemes.

Ten separate MODECLUS analyses were run on each configuration according to four different types of paradigm. The first paradigm simply ran 30 separate cluster analyses with increasing fixed-radius density estimation and clustering kernels. The radius of this kernel ranged from the minimum interpoint distance to the mean interpoint distance in the configuration.

The next three paradigms used a fixed-radius kernel that was calculated from the cluster analysis under the first paradigm. The kernel radius was chosen to produce an initial number of clusters which was equal to the total number of points in the analysis divided by two, four, and eight, respectively. A hierarchical cluster tree was obtained for each scheme by testing the significance of these clusters with the JOIN option. This procedure compared the maximum estimated density of points within a cluster to the maximum around the cluster's border (referred to here as the 'saddle point') in order to estimate the cluster's significance. On successive iterations the least significant cluster was dissolved, or their members assigned to a neighbouring cluster if it was close enough.

The next three paradigms were based on nearest-neighbour kernels with $K=$ values set to 2, 3, and 4 (*i.e.* the density estimation and clustering kernels were set to the value so that the number of neighbours of each point was a minimum of 1, 2 and 3).

The final three paradigms used nearest-neighbour clustering methods with the JOIN option to give hierarchically organised schemes. This involved the use of fixed-radius density estimation kernels (with the radius set to the configuration's mean distance), and clustering kernels with nearest-neighbour $CK=$ values set to 2, 3 and 4.

Sixty cluster trees were generated for each connection matrix at each dimensionality. Seven out of every ten of these trees were hierarchically organised, and were made up of several individual cluster schemes. In a given cluster scheme, each area would either be assigned to

one and only one cluster, or be unassigned. I defined an $N \times N$ 'cluster-count' matrix, \mathbf{K} for each cluster tree. Each matrix element, κ_{ij} , denoted the number of times the i^{th} and j^{th} areas were assigned to the same cluster in the cluster tree, divided by the total number of different cluster schemes in the cluster tree.

All cluster-counts of a given configuration were averaged to give an overall cluster-count value that indicated the most consistent features of the cluster analyses. Cluster-counts were averaged over configurations that had been derived from specified transforms, or from a specified dimensionality, to give transform-specific, and dimension-specific cluster-counts. Within these averaging processes, the cluster-counts of each cluster tree were weighted equally so each paradigm contributed equally to the overall cluster-count score. The cluster-count took the significance of clusters into account. If a brain area was in a cluster, that was subsequently dissolved under the JOIN= option, the brain area would not contribute further to the cluster-count, (that is, it would not be counted as being in the same cluster as any other structures, including itself). This explains how some analyses describe cluster-counts between an area and itself of less than 100%.

The order of structures within each cluster-count matrix was selected so that a given brain area in the matrix would be followed by that brain area that, when paired with the first area, had the largest cluster-count out of those remaining. This procedure allowed easier interpretation of the cluster-count matrices, by grouping areas with high cluster-counts together.

In order to facilitate the interpretation of these cluster-count figures, cluster-count values over two thresholds were coloured blue and red respectively. The way these thresholds were selected were consistent. I used 20 grey levels to shade individual cells in the matrix where the lightest shade was set to the minimum cluster-count value and the darkest shade was set to

the maximum cluster-count value. These values were never 0 or 1. The largest eleven categories were coloured red, the next two or three blue, and the remaining values grey.

As a final step, I superimposed the set structure of each summary cluster-count matrix onto a two-dimensional NMDS configuration (that was derived with the $S^{(1)}$ cost function and tied approach) as a Venn-diagram consisting of blue and red sets. These sets were representations of the sets of brain areas in cluster-count matrices which were either all coloured blue, or red. They provided a way of combining the structure derived in the cluster analysis with configurations produced in NMDS studies.

Chapter 3

Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling in High-Dimensional Euclidean Space and its Relevance To Neural Connectivity Data.

3. Nonmetric Multidimensional Scaling in High-Dimensional Euclidean Space and its Relevance To Neural Connectivity Data.

3.1. Introduction.

The majority of work testing the validity of the NMDS method comes from Monte Carlo analyses of either apparent or actual measures of the ‘goodness of fit’. Apparent measures of fit (such as stress) are available to workers using NMDS, but actual measures (such as Procrustes R^2 values) are not. Therefore, it can be difficult to interpret the stress values of different NMDS configurations to judge which configurations best represent the data. Neural connectivity data are ordinal, and may require NMDS representations in high-dimensional Euclidean space. In this chapter, I use Monte Carlo methods to examine the apparent and actual measures of fit of NMDS configurations derived from high-dimensional proximity data defined at a low-level of measurement.

Kruskal devised the first scheme where the quality of fit was described in terms of stress values (Kruskal 1964). Stress percentage values of 20%, 10%, 5%, 2.5% or 0% were claimed to give rise to a goodness of fit that was ‘poor’, ‘fair’, ‘good’, ‘excellent’ or ‘perfect’ respectively. However, this contained no reference to the behaviour of stress with respect to the numbers of points in the configuration, the number of dimensions of the coordinate space, or the amount of measurement error present in the data. Subsequent papers have attempted to make the interpretation of stress more straightforward by tabulating the expected stress of random configurations (Klahr 1969; Stenson and Knoll 1969; Wagenaar and Padmos 1971; Spence and Ogilvie 1973; Levine 1978; Levine 1981). Stress values were calculated for a large number of pairs of random configurations and dissimilarity matrices (see

Section 2.2.3). These analyses define the probability distributions of stress for random configurations with a given number of points, in a given dimensionality and, with a specified level of random noise. These papers allowed researchers to see if the stress values of configurations derived from their data were significantly better than chance.

Other Monte Carlo studies describe the statistics of stress variability with respect to the dimensionality of both the original configuration and the NMDS solutions (Wagenaar and Padmos 1971; Isaac and Poor 1974); the Minkowski metric constant, used to define the distance function in the NMDS procedure (Sherman 1972); and the number of points in the configuration; as well as the level of random noise added to the data (Young 1970; Spence and Graef 1974; Cox and Cox 1990; Cox and Cox 1992).

Many of these papers characterise the performance of the NMDS procedure by measuring the level of fit between the final output and the original configuration. Early studies used ‘metric determinacy’ to measure the correspondence between the NMDS solution and the original configuration (Young 1970; Wagenaar and Padmos 1971; Sherman 1972; Isaac and Poor 1974). This is the correlation coefficient between the distances in the original configuration and those in the NMDS solution. As an objective measure of fit between configurations, metric determinacy has several drawbacks: it does not illustrate how well the individual components of a solution are fitted, and is vulnerable to distortion from one or two badly-fitted points (Cohen and Jones 1974). A far more appropriate measure of actual fit is the Procrustes R^2 variable (see Chapter 2; Gower 1975; Sibson 1979).

Much of the work that describes the original characteristics of NMDS was performed over twenty years ago, using computational methodologies that have since been

superseded, both in terms of the sophistication of their algorithms, and in terms of their raw computational power. Not only that, but these studies were concerned with the use of NMDS as a tool for investigating psychometric data, rather than neural connection data. Analysis of connectivity is a relatively new field, and therefore requires an approach that is tailored to the eccentricities of the data under investigation.

Research on NMDS in psychometrics has emphasised careful experimental design to minimise the number of dimensions in output configurations to two or three dimensions (Shepard 1974). Low-dimensional output may not be appropriate for connection data. Whilst cortical studies have yielded interpretable two-dimensional configurations (Young 1992; Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a), my work on the rat suggests that a general, high-dimensional approach may be required when subcortical data are included.

Neural connectivity data are concerned with interconnections between physical objects, rather than judged similarities between psychological stimuli. The dimensionality of the underlying ‘connectivity space’ is influenced by a prudent choice of structures and careful definition of the dissimilarity coefficient. However, in analyses of neural connectivity, the dissimilarity coefficient is only defined at the ordinal level, and the structures are usually pre-selected. This important difference between the original design of NMDS and its usage here, prompted me to examine the performance of NMDS in reconstructing high-dimensional data in a low number of dimensions and at a low level of measurement.

3.2. Objectives of chapter.

I have generated low level ordinal proximity matrices from known random configurations of points and compared the NMDS solutions of these matrices to the configurations they were derived from. I altered the parameters of both the input data and the NMDS procedures, in order to address the following issues:

- 1) The most general Euclidean model available for N -dimensional data is $(N-1)$ -dimensional space. For example: if three points are embedded in two-dimensional space, and a fourth point is added to the configuration, another dimension will generally be required to accommodate it, and so on for higher dimensions. Using $N-1$ dimensions is the ‘worst case scenario’, because the configuration occupies the maximum number of dimensions available. If N points are embedded in a Euclidean space with $N-1$ dimensions and the dissimilarity is defined at a high-ordinal level of measurement, how well can NMDS recover the original data? Similarly, how well can NMDS recover configurations of N points in $\binom{N}{2}-1$ -dimensional space?
- 2) How well can NMDS reconstruct high-dimensional dissimilarity data at a low-ordinal level of measurement?
- 3) Most of the published work concerning neural connection data use two- or three-dimensional configurations with no attempt to estimate the dimensionality of the data structure (Young 1992; Scannell *et al.* 1995). How much distortion is produced when NMDS is used to obtain solutions with an under- or over-estimated dimensionality?
- 4) Principal component analysis can find a configuration of points from a distance matrix. The n^{th} principal component is a list of all the different n^{th} -dimensional

ordinates of points in the configuration. A principal component analysis of an $N \times N$ distance matrix, \mathbf{D} , of rank M , produces an $N \times M$ configuration matrix \mathbf{X} , so that the i^{th} principal component is the vector, $(x_{1i}, x_{2i}, x_{3i}, \dots, x_{Ni})^T$. The principal axes of the configuration are arranged so that the variance is maximised for the first principal component and then falls for subsequent principal components. This provides a way of estimating the amount of structure of the configuration contained in each successive principal component, indicating the ‘dimensionality’ of the solution.

- 5) Is there any significant variation in performance where the stress function being minimised is changed in the MDS procedure in SAS 6.09? Which stress function is more accurate or more appropriate, and does the choice of either the ‘primary’ or ‘secondary’ (‘untied’ or ‘tied’) approach to ties make any difference?

3.3. Methods

3.3.1. Configuration generation

The issue of ‘shape’ is extremely important in these analyses (Young *et al.* 1995a). When interpreting the distribution of points in NMDS output configurations, the most immediate feature is the overall shape of the configuration. I have used four different types of shape as input data for these analyses which I refer to as ‘filled’ or ‘hollow’; ‘cubic’ or ‘spherical’ configurations. Two-dimensional examples of these shapes are illustrated below in Figure 3-1.

Figure 3-1: Different shapes of configurations of 1000 points.

The distance characteristics of these data are illustrated as distance frequency histograms below in Figure 3-2. Data of this type constitute the Euclidean test data that I used to test the performance of the MDS procedure in SAS 6.09.

Distance frequency histogram for hollow hypercubic configurations

Distance frequency histogram for filled hypercubic configurations

See over for caption

Distance frequency for hollow hyperspherical configurations

Distance frequency histogram for filled hyperspherical configurations

Figure 3-2: Representations of the frequency distributions of the distances of each of the four shapes described above. This is a global, graphical representation of proximity (distances) in configurations, and illustrates the differences between 'filled' and 'empty' configurations in terms of the shape of the frequency distribution of distances.

I generated eleven random configurations for each of the four shapes consisting of N points in $(N-1)$ -dimensional space, where N took values of 3, 6, 11, 16, 21, 26 and 29.

In addition to this, I generated 11 random configurations of each shape, where N took

values of 6, 12, 22 and 32 in two-, five-, ten-, and fifteen-dimensional spaces respectively.

I generated an ‘envelope’ in multidimensional space, such that the points in the configuration would either lie on the surface of this envelope or be scattered throughout its interior, depending on whether the data was ‘hollow’ or ‘filled’. The cubic multidimensional envelopes were generated so that x_{ij} , (the j^{th} ordinate of the i^{th} point) was either distributed uniformly within the interval (-1.0,1.0) for filled data or one randomly-chosen ordinate of each point would be set to either 1.0 or -1.0 for hollow data. The positions of points in hollow spherical configurations were defined by calculating the positions of points in a hypercubic envelope as described above, and then these points were projected onto the surface of a hypersphere of unit radius centred at the origin. The positions of points in filled spherical configurations were calculated by setting the radius of points in hollow spherical configurations to a uniformly-distributed random value between 0 and 1.

A note concerning ‘spherical configurations’.

The method I used to generate hollow and filled hyperspherical configurations gave a greater point density along the diagonals linking the origin to the corners of the sphere’s enclosing hypercube. This can be seen in Figure 3-1 as an ‘X’-like cluster around the origin of the two-dimensional filled hypersphere. This means that the probability density function of the hyperspherical envelopes were not uniform. Since the analyses of this chapter place no special relevance on the exact shape of test data, this feature was judged not to be severe enough to warrant repeating the entire analysis.

3.3.2. NMDS, procrustes and stress.

I used the MDS procedure in the SAS 6.09 statistics software (SAS Technical Report P-229 SAS/STAT Software: Changes and Enhancements. 'Chapter 15, The MDS procedure', pp 249-286) on a Sun SPARC Center 2000 with 10 processors and 768Mb RAM. I used the $S^{(1)}$ cost function in these analyses under the tied approach, except for analyses concerned with issue (5).

Each of the following sections describes a different set NMDS analyses, where the input dissimilarity matrices were derived from the distances of a random configuration by ranking the distances. The output of each NMDS analysis was compared to the original configuration with Procrustes rotations.

3.3.3. Methods of each section.

1) In order to study how well NMDS can reconstruct high-dimensional configurations, I generated random configurations of points where, N , the number of points, was equal to $M+1$, the number of dimensions of the configuration plus one. These configurations had 3, 6, 11, 16, 21, 26, and 29 points in coordinate spaces with 2, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, and 28 dimensions, respectively. I repeated this analysis where N was set to $2(M+1)$ with configurations of 6, 12, 22 and 32 points in 2, 5, 10 and 15 dimensions, respectively. The number of ranks, o , (also referred to as 'partitions') in this matrix was the maximum possible (See Equation 3-1).

$$o = \frac{1}{2} N(N - 1) \qquad \text{Equation 3-}$$

1

Later in this chapter I will consider NMDS studies of matrices with fewer ranks.

I used SAS to calculate the coordinates of NMDS solutions for these matrices. I matched these configurations to the original configuration with Procrustes

analysis in GENSTAT to obtain R^2 values for each NMDS configuration. I calculated stress statistics for each reconstructed configuration.

- 2) In the second part of the study, I reduced the number of ordinal ranks in the ordinal dissimilarity matrix by halving each dissimilarity matrix entry, and then rounding it down to the nearest integer. I repeated this process several times to give a series of matrices for each configuration. The ordinality of each matrix decreased by a factor of two at each step through the series. These data were analysed with SAS to give high-dimensional configurations which were compared with the original configuration with Procrustes rotations. Matrices with 2 ranks, matrices with 3 or 4 ranks, and matrices with 5 to 8 ranks, were analysed.
- 3) I analysed the same data from parts (1) and (2), by finding NMDS solutions in intermediate dimensions from 2 to M . In the case of data with $N=2(M+1)$, I also overestimated the dimensionality by calculating NMDS solutions with $N-1$ dimensions. Data from 'filled hyperspheres' are presented as an example of the worst case available, since their R^2 values were generally smaller than for other shapes.
- 4) I wrote a small C program which used the principal component analysis algorithms 'tred2.c' and 'tqli.c' in the Numerical Recipes in C programme library (Press *et al.* 1988) to analyse the principal components of high-dimensional solutions obtained in (1) & (2). In order to see how the R^2 values of low-dimensional configurations related to the statistics obtained from the PCA analyses.
- 5) I repeated the analyses in (1), (2) and (3) using the $S^{(2)}$, $S^{(0.5)}$, and $S^{(1)}$ cost functions with the untied approach, by using different values for the FIT option in

the MDS procedure (SAS Technical Report P-229 SAS/STAT Software: Changes and Enhancements. 'Chapter 15, The MDS procedure', pp. 249-286).

3.4. Results

I calculated Procrustes R^2 statistics describing the fit between the NMDS solutions and the original configuration and the 'apparent fit' of the configuration measured by stress. This section is divided into five parts corresponding to the five issues put forward in the introduction.

3.4.1. High-dimensional, high-ordinal data.

When the ordinal distance matrix under study contained ordinal data with no tied ranks, and the dimensionality of the NMDS output configuration was the same as the original configuration, Procrustes comparisons between the two configurations yielded R^2 values that were consistently greater than 0.9 and did not show any particular tendency to decrease as the number of dimensions and points increased (See Figure 3-3). The R^2 values were higher still when the same calculation was performed with twice as many points in the configuration.

The one anomalous case was the filled hypersphere data, that had consistently smaller R^2 values than other configurations. The R^2 values were smaller at high dimensions, but were still in the region of 0.9. In general, the MDS programme in SAS performed well at reconstructing high-dimensional configurations from maximally ordinal proximities (that is, proximities with the maximum number of ordinal ranks).

Figure 3-3: The relationship between Procrustes R^2 values and number of dimensions for comparisons between configurations, and reconstructed NMDS configurations calculated from high-dimensional, maximally ordinal distance matrices. This graph also illustrates the effect of having a larger number of constraints in the original matrix. Error bars were calculated as standard errors calculated with $n=11$.

Figure 3-4 illustrates stress values for configurations with the minimum number of points in high dimensions and twice the minimum number of points. Both sets of stress values are extremely small, corresponding to situations of (almost) perfect monotone regression. Interestingly, the configurations where the number of points is equal to $2(M+1)$ have higher stress values, and therefore a slightly worse ‘apparent fit’, even though they have marginally higher R^2 values. Stress functions are dependent on the number of points in the configuration, since doubling the number of values actually quadruples the number of elements to be summed over when calculating stress.

Figure 3-4: Graph of stress values plotted against number of dimensions in the final configuration of NMDS solutions from maximally ordinal dissimilarities with no dimensional reduction. The number of objects in each configuration was either equal to the number of dimensions plus one (denoted by ‘ $N=M+1$ ’) or twice this value (denoted by ‘ $N=2[M+1]$ ’).

3.4.2. High-dimensionality, low-ordinality data.

The number of different ranks in the similarity matrix was reduced, with the result that some of the matrix elements were tied. Procrustes comparisons between NMDS reconstructions of these degraded ordinal matrices and the original configurations are illustrated in Figures 3-5 and 3-6. These graphs illustrate how well NMDS can cope with low-ordinality data. In general, the fit of solutions with the maximum number of ranks possible, and the solutions with 5-8 ranks were roughly equal. All graphs showed that R^2 was usually greater than 0.8, irrespective of the number of dimensions in the solution. NMDS performed less well at reconstructing configurations with $2(M+1)$ points rather than $M+1$. The largest deficit occurred with filled hyperspheres, which displayed characteristics slightly different from the other types of configuration under study. Therefore, reducing the ordinality of Euclidean data does not prevent NMDS from reconstructing the structure of high-dimensional configurations.

Figure 3-5: Procrustes R^2 values for NMDS solutions with a reduced total number of ranks. Error bars were calculated as standard errors.

Figure 3-6: Procrustes R^2 values for NMDS solutions with a reduced total number of ranks. The number of points in each configuration, N , was equal to $N=2(M+1)$ where M is the number of dimensions in the original configuration.

The stress values calculated for these configurations are shown in Figures 3-7 and 3-8. In all analyses, the stress was very small, even for data with only two ranks. The stress of configurations of different dimensionalities was of the same magnitude and was usually below 0.01. The filled sphere configurations tended to have higher stress values than other configurations.

Figure 3-7: Stress values for the degraded ordinal matrices representing configurations where $N=M+1$.

Figure 3-8: Stress Values for the degraded ordinal matrices representing configurations where $N=2[M+1]$.

3.4.3. Decreased-dimensionality, low-ordinality data.

The fit between the NMDS solutions and the original configuration was most greatly diminished if the dimensionalities of the original configuration and the NMDS solution were different. Procrustes R^2 statistics for comparisons between low-dimensional NMDS configurations and the original high-dimensional configurations are plotted in Figures 3-9 and 3-10. The values of the actual fit of configurations calculated at half their original dimensionalities are often of the same magnitude as those of the high-dimensional solution. Therefore, these intermediate-dimensional solutions capture as almost much data structure as high-dimensional solutions. These low values of R^2 for low-dimensional reconstructions of high-dimensional data were not functions of the number of points in the configuration, since two-dimensional reconstructions of two-dimensional configurations with thirty points can have R^2 values in excess of 0.95 (Young *et al.* 1995b).

Figure 3-10 illustrates the effect of overestimating the dimensionality of solutions. In most cases, the degree of fit between NMDS solutions with too many dimensions and the original configuration was similar (if not marginally lower) than R^2 values obtained at the same dimensionality as the original configuration. The only exceptions to this rule were configurations derived from a matrix with only two ranks where the fit increased when the dimensionality was overestimated.

Figure 3-9: This figure shows how the actual fit between the original configuration and dimensionally reduced NMDS solutions is dependent upon the number of points and dimensions in the original configuration and NMDS solution. This data was obtained from five filled hyperspherical configuration, where the number of points in the configuration was equal to the number of dimensions plus one.

Figure 3-10: This figure shows how the actual fit between the original configuration and dimensionally reduced NMDS solutions is dependent on the number of points and dimensions in the original configuration and NMDS solution. This data was obtained from five filled hyperspherical configurations, where the number of points in the configuration was equal $2(M+1)$ where M is the number of dimensions.

Stress and its derivatives, not Procrustes R^2 statistics, are the only measures of ‘fit’ accessible to workers using NMDS. It is important to evaluate how this variable is affected by dimensional reduction and overestimation. In Figure 3-11, stress values are plotted against NMDS solution dimensionality for fifteen-dimensional configurations involving 16 and 32 points.

The stress values of configurations calculated at the correct dimensionality are almost zero, and the stress values of the NMDS configurations in lower-dimensional spaces is much higher. The stress of NMDS solutions with overestimated dimensionality is

marginally higher than that of the solutions at the true dimensionality. These sharply defined 'elbows' of stress at the correct dimensionality vanish when noise are added to the data to simulate measurement error (Isaac and Poor 1974).

Figure 3-11: Stress values for NMDS solutions calculated at intermediate dimensionalities where the number of ranks is diminished.

3.4.4. Other methods of dimensional reduction.

Principal component analysis was applied to the original configurations and to NMDS solutions. This was used as a form of dimensional reduction on configurations to investigate their dimensionality more closely.

Figures 3-12 and 3-13 show R^2 values from Procrustes rotations between the principal components of fifteen-dimensional NMDS solutions and the original configurations. This illustrates how the coordinates of each dimension contribute to the R^2 value. The maximum number of principal components were often not required to produce partial solutions with R^2 values over 0.9, suggesting that variability of the output solutions could be adequately represented by the low-order principal components. This is because the number of points is small relative to the number of dimensions.

These comparisons show that the principal components of high-dimensional NMDS solutions have similar properties to the NMDS solutions, in terms of the actual fit of representations of intermediate-dimensionality to the original configuration. Principal component analysis may be useful in investigating the true dimensionality of data in NMDS studies.

Figure 3-12: Procrustes R^2 values for comparisons of the principal components of NMDS solutions and the original configurations. Only results for the 16 point, 15-dimensional configurations are presented here.

Figure 3-13: Procrustes R^2 values for comparisons of the principal components of NMDS solutions and the original configurations. Only results for the 32 point, 15-dimensional configurations are presented here.

3.4.5. The effect of different cost functions.

The choice of cost function does not substantially change the actual fit of the NMDS solution as shown in Figures 3-14 and 3-15. As before, the filled sphere data exhibited the poorest fit in high dimensions. In some cases, the tied approach yielded structures with marginally better fit at low dimensions and marginally worse fit at high dimensions, but these variations were very small. Increasing the number of points in the configuration made the level of fit marginally worse, independent of the cost function used.

The optimal values of stress functions for NMDS solutions are shown in Figure 3-16. This shows how the apparent fit is extremely dependent on the stress function used to calculate the configuration, even though the actual fit is not.

Procrustes comparison between original configuration and NMDS solutions calculated with $S^{(0.5)}$, $S^{(1)}$ and $S^{(2)}$ stress functions and both the 'tied' and the 'untied' approach to ties

Figure 3-14: Figure to illustrate similarities between the performance of different cost functions. The configurations used in this section had 16 points, and 15 dimensions.

Procrustes comparison between original configuration and NMDS solutions calculated with $S^{(0.5)}$, $S^{(1)}$ and $S^{(2)}$ stress functions and both the 'tied' and the 'untied' approach to ties

Figure 3-15: Figure to illustrate similarities between the performance of different cost functions. The configurations used in this section had 32 points, and 15 dimensions.

Stress values for NMDS solutions calculated with $S^{(0.5)}$, $S^{(1)}$, and $S^{(2)}$ stress functions using 'untied' and 'tied' approaches

Figure 3-16: Figure to illustrate the differences between stress values of NMDS solutions calculated under different cost functions.

3.5. Discussion

The approach used in this chapter may seem to be at odds to the original purpose of NMDS, that is, to produce a visually interpretable two- or three-dimensional configuration to illustrate the organisation of the system under study. Instead, I have examined the ability of the MDS procedure in SAS/STAT to analyse data in the maximum number of dimensions possible. This was prompted by the consideration that low-dimensional solutions may not provide the best fit for neural connectivity data in the proximity model. In fact all NMDS work which has used neural connection data has only presented configurations in two dimensions, including previous Monte Carlo studies (Young 1992; Young 1993; Scannell and Young 1993; Simmen *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b; Goodhill *et al.* 1995; Scannell *et al.* 1995). Three-dimensional analyses have been performed on monkey and cat cortical data (M. P. Young and J. W. Scannell, Personal Communication), and Scannell and co-workers have recently (1997) used three-dimensional analysis to visualise thalamocortical connections in the cat (Scannell J. W., Personal Communication).

I have shown that the MDS procedure in the SAS statistical software package can recover a high degree of metric information from Euclidean ordinal data. Unfortunately, it seems likely that neural connection strength data is non-Euclidean when measured at a ratio level (see Section 1.5).

Sibson and co-workers (1981) wrote that 'stress is a measure of the Euclidean-ness of a set of ordinal data'. This has been confirmed by the work described in this chapter: stress vanishes when NMDS recovers the original configuration in the correct number of dimensions when there are no tied ranks in the ordinal matrix of distances, and no

error in the data (Sibson *et al.* 1981). If this is the case, why was the stress of NMDS solutions of matrices with reduced ordinality nonzero under the tied approach? Under the tied approach, the configuration corresponding to the zero-cost, high-ordinality NMDS solution, no longer carries a minimum cost since the tied ranks are constrained to correspond to tied distances.

The problem of coping with data of a low ordinality has been approached in several ways. The use of dissimilarity coefficients which are derived from binary data could have an application in these studies (reviewed in Cox and Cox 1995; Simmen 1996), and the *pthl* and *wdsm* transforms described in the previous chapter are similar to these coefficients. Previous Monte Carlo studies show that these transformations are very effective at improving the level of fit for two-dimensional solutions, but have yet to be tested with more complex high-dimensional Euclidean data (Young *et al.* 1995b).

But what of non-Euclidean data? The method normally used to model a connection matrix's departure from Euclidean characteristics is to add random noise to the Euclidean test data. The stress values of NMDS of Euclidean configurations are strongly dependent on the amount of noise added to the distance matrix elements before calculating the ordinal dissimilarity matrix. (Stenson and Knoll 1969; Wagenaar and Padmos 1971; Isaac and Poor 1974; Cox and Cox 1990; Cox and Cox 1992; Cox and Cox 1995). The effect of noise was not modelled in this study, since the primary aim was to compare the effects of reduced ordinality and dimensional reduction on high-dimensional Euclidean data. Young *et al.* (1995b) generated test data with 30 points in 2 dimensions with added noise which produced the same level of stress as NMDS analyses of monkey cortical data. They showed that the ALSCAL

programme (from the SPSS statistical package) is capable of producing hollow circular configurations that have average Procrustes R^2 values in the range of 0.90-0.96, and filled circular configurations with average R^2 values in the range 0.84-0.90. This suggests that, even with added noise, the NMDS approach can reconstruct test data very well, as long as the NMDS programme is reconstructing the test data in an appropriate number of dimensions (Young *et al.* 1995b).

The Euclidean model is only one of many possible metrics that can be used (see Table 1.1 in Cox and Cox 1995). It is the most convenient, but it may not be the most appropriate. At present, no work has investigated neural connectivity data in coordinate spaces with other metrics. It is not clear whether using other models would be useful, since NMDS is primarily a visualisation method, and secondary analysis would need to be used to interpret the structure of these models. I would expect this approach to be justifiable in terms of the increased insight into the system's organisation only if the connectivity data was of a much higher level of precision than is available at the present time. Methods of analysis which do not use the proximity model may be more appropriate for neural connectivity data.

The analyses in this chapter have been concerned with the special case where dimensionality of test configurations is maximised relative to the number of points. I have shown that NMDS can reconstruct high-dimensional Euclidean configurations even when the ordinality of the input matrix is low. The use of very high-dimensional spaces is rare due to their counter-intuitive geometry (Scott 1992). Nonetheless, this study shows that the MDS procedure in the SAS/STAT statistical software package is perfectly capable of calculating intermediate-dimensional and even high-dimensional representations of Euclidean data.

Chapter 4

The Connectivity of the Rat's Visual System.

4. The Connectivity of the Rat's Visual System.

4.1. Introduction.

At first glance, my studies of the connectional organisation of the rat's visual system bear little resemblance to previous analyses of connectivity, or to previous organisational schemes based on combined neurophysiological and neuroanatomical studies. The reason for this is that my studies are based purely on anatomical connection data. My decision to do this was determined by the fact that several slight contradictory trends exist between the published analyses based on monkey and cat data, and the literature describing the visual system in the rat; combined with the need for a rigorous approach to the analysis of neuroanatomical data.

Firstly, all published analyses of connectivity have been concerned mainly with corticocortical systems, and only include specific subcortical systems, such as connections to and from the hippocampus and amygdala (*e.g.* Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995). The omission of subcortical structures from these studies has arisen from the absence of computational databases describing the connectivity of these systems (*e.g.* Felleman and Van Essen 1991), and the prominence of the cerebral cortex as a subject of study in the monkey and cat. By contrast, descriptions of the possible mechanisms underlying vision in the rat often involve subcortical structures (see Figure 2 in Dean and Redgrave 1984, and Figure 13.1. in Goodale and Carey 1990). The relative connection strength of the retinal projection to the superior colliculus is much greater than to the dorsal part of the lateral geniculate nucleus in rats (Linden and Perry 1983; Martin 1986), a situation which is reversed in primates (Perry and Cowey 1984; Perry *et al.* 1984), suggesting that subcortical pathways may play a greater role in mediating visual behaviour in rats than in primates. In addition to this,

rats without visuotopically organised cortex retain some capability of discriminating patterns (Goldstein and Oakley 1987). Hence, my studies of the visual system in rats requires detailed consideration of subcortical visual pathways.

Secondly, the number of structures that are included in a single connectivity analysis range from roughly 30 to 80 (Young 1992; Young 1993). Whereas the number of structures involved in descriptions of the organisation of visual processing in the rat is usually less than ten (Dean 1990; Goodale and Carey 1990; Sefton and Dreher 1995). Organisational schemes of this sort typically describe the neuroanatomical connections between structures thought to be involved in vision. They incorporate neurophysiological information by the choice of structures that are included in the scheme, as well as by requiring some idea of each structure's relative importance to the physiological phenomenon under study.

For example, in a review published in 1984, Dean and Redgrave describe some possible mechanisms underlying visual neglect following lesions of the superior colliculus in rats and hamsters (Dean and Redgrave 1984). They present an organisational scheme that is based on the retinal pathways leading to cortex via the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, the superior colliculus, and (implicitly) the lateral posterior nucleus. They omit several structures which receive input from the retina (the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, the pretectum, and the accessory optic nuclei) arguing that the visual capabilities of the rat are so greatly limited by the destruction of both the superior colliculus and visual cortex, that other structures are unlikely to play any major role in the visual tasks they study.

However, the interpretation of lesion experiments can be difficult and counterintuitive. In 1966, Sprague demonstrated that cats with large lesions over

visually responsive cortex failed to respond to stimuli presented in the contralateral visual hemifield, but regained this ability after lesions were placed in the contralateral superior colliculus (Sprague 1966). This phenomenon (combined with others) led Grobstein to state that “*one cannot conclude from the absence of a piece of behaviour that the structure is essential for the behaviour*” (Grobstein 1990). The finding that extensive bilateral lesions to both the superior colliculus and posterior cortex strongly disrupts vision in the rat cannot therefore be used to support assumptions concerning the relative importance of other retinal pathways, without behavioural data from similar experiments with lesions to these other structures. In fact, lesions to the pretectum, the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, or the accessory optic nuclei, do not seem to produce the same levels of deficit as with lesions to the superior colliculus and visual cortex (Legg and Turkish 1983; Tischler and Davis 1983). Nonetheless, visual deficits have been described where lesions have been made in subcortical systems other than the traditional geniculostriate and tectocortical pathways (Legg 1979a), and a description of the organisation of the visual system that excludes these pathways should be considered incomplete.

Churchland, Ramachandran and Sejnowski (1993) addressed this issue by challenging a set of broadly-shared assumptions in vision research, which they called ‘the theory of pure vision’ (Churchland *et al.* 1993). They argue that vision is not a strictly hierarchically-organised, isolated, perceptual process with the purpose of building a unified percept of the visual world. Instead they cite psychophysical, physiological and anatomical evidence to assert that vision is exploratory and predictive. Rather, it intimately involves nonperceptual processes such as memory, attention and movement, and serves to produce behaviour which permits the animal to thrive within its ecological niche. This description of the nature of vision suggests to me that there

is a need for descriptions of the organisation of the system over a large number of structures, including those that fall outside the set of components commonly perceived to comprise the visual system. One passage is of particular significance to the work presented here.

“What is frustrating about this assembly of data, as with Neuroanatomy generally, is that we don’t really know what it all means. The number of neurons and number of connections is bewildering & the significance of projections to one place or another of distinct cell populations, and so on, is typically puzzling. Neuroanatomy is, nonetheless, the observational hardpan of neuroscience and the data can be provocative even when they are not self-explanatory.” (Churchland *et al.* 1993).

This quotation goes to the heart of the subject of this thesis: the interpretation of neuroanatomical data. In all previous work, organisational schemes have been determined largely by physiological criteria, and have understandably limited the number of structures involved.

I have based the criteria for selecting which areas to include in the analysis solely on neuroanatomical connection data, rather than analysing the connections between a subset of brain structures, such as the different regions of the cortex (Young 1993, Scannell & Young 1994). Since the source of all visual information in the brain is the retina, brain structures were included in the analysis on the basis of that structure’s involvement in retinal pathways. I therefore performed an open-ended exploratory analysis of connectivity to examine the predictive power of such an approach.

Section two of this chapter is concerned with all possible retinal pathways, simply by tracing every one-, two- and three-stage pathway from the retina to the rest of the brain using the data in Neurobase. By performing this analysis, I intended to examine

the possibility of using neuroanatomically defined retinal pathways as selection criteria for the analysis of the rat's visual system.

Section three describes analyses performed on the areas that receive efferents from the retina using NMDS. These analyses were performed on all interconnections between selected structures rather than parallel pathways from the retina. Section four involves the use of nonparametric cluster analysis to interpret groupings within the configurations produced in section 3.

Sections three and four incorporate subparcellated areas in the same analysis as their parent areas, (that is, the connections of both the optic nucleus of the pretectum, and of the pretectum itself were considered in a single analysis). Section five described control analyses where subparcellated and parent structures are analysed separately.

Section six describes the use of a novel method of deriving connection weight estimates from connection reports of retinal efferents and the efferents of areas receiving the densest projections from the retina (see Section 2.2.2). A connection matrix for the thirteen strongest retinal efferents was derived and used as the input data for the NMDS analyses described in Section seven. The strongest efferents of areas receiving strong retinal input were obtained from connection strength estimation analyses and the further analysis of this data using NMDS and nonparametric cluster analysis is described in Section eight.

The primary objective of the work in this chapter is to describe the connectional organisation of the rat's early visual system from first principles, using only neuroanatomical data.

4.2. *Basic pathway analysis*

In one of the more recent reviews of the neuroanatomical organisation of the rat's visual system, Sefton and Dreher (1995) describe many visual brain structures which receive retinal projections, and subsequent areas which receive projections from these first stage structures (Sefton and Dreher 1995). All visual structures must receive information from pathways which originate from the retina. A description of the total extent and divergence of retinal pathways would be a useful first step in defining the visual system in terms of neuroanatomical connectivity.

The connection data underlying this analysis were spread over a large number of papers. Entering all the relevant data from these papers' results sections would have been too time-consuming a project to finish in the time allotted, and so I chose to allow abstract reports to be treated as 'valid data' for these initial open-ended pathway analyses. I expect also that the connections reported here may be an underestimation of the total number of connections in the system, since I did not manage to include every datum from every neuroanatomical tract-tracing experiment performed on the rat. I have nevertheless endeavoured to strike a balance between representing as much of the literature as possible and at sufficient depth to be interpretable.

4.2.1. How many 'retinal pathways' are there?

The number of pathways from the retina to the rest of the brain is, not surprisingly, large. How large depends primarily on the criteria used to decide which connections should constitute part of a pathway. I looked at pathways based on three different sets of connection data: (1) connections belonging to the 'dense labelling' and 'abstract' categories; (2) connections belonging to the 'dense labelling', 'moderate labelling' and 'abstract' categories; (3) connections belonging to the 'dense labelling',

‘moderate labelling’, ‘sparse labelling’, ‘unspecified labelling density’ and ‘abstract’ categories (See Chapter 2).

Table 4-1 displays the number of separate connection reports involved in one-, two- and three-stage pathways, and which categories of connection reports contributed the most to these analyses. It is clear that abstract reports played an influential role in these analyses, especially for the three-stage pathways.

<i>Densely labelled connection reports</i>		Number of stages in pathway			Totals
		1	2	3	
type of connx report	Densely labelled connection reports	17	50	131	198
	Abstract reports	0	13	279	292
Totals		17	63	410	490

<i>Densely and moderately labelled connection reports</i>		Number of stages in pathway			Totals
		1	2	3	
type of connx report	Densely labelled connection reports	17	83	376	476
	Moderately labelled connection reports	8	105	726	839
	Abstract reports	0	80	1346	1426
Totals		25	268	2448	2741

<i>All connection reports</i>		Number of stages in pathway			Totals
		1	2	3	
type of connx report	Densely labelled connection reports	17	146	567	730
	Moderately labelled connection reports	8	185	1021	1214
	Sparsely labelled connection reports	11	160	806	977
	Connections of unspecified density	8	116	676	800
	Abstract reports	0	167	1996	2163
Totals		44	774	5066	5884

Table 4-1: The connection data underlying this section.

Figure 4-1 is a schematic diagram of the whole rat brain (redrawn with permission from Figure 8 of Swanson 1992), where each coloured dot represents a brain structure. This represents only one of many possible parcellation schemes but was selected as an illustrative case to show how retinal pathways diverge.

Figure 4-1: A schematic of the whole brain redrawn with permission from figure 8 of Swanson's rat brain atlas (Swanson 1992). Each dot represents a named nucleus or area (refer to Appendix A: Parcellation Database, for meanings of label abbreviations). There are two hundred and fifty dots on this figure.

Densest connections (3, x).

The organisation of dense efferent pathways from the retina to the rest of the brain is illustrated as a 'pathway tree', in Figure 4-2. Several issues are evident in this figure. Firstly, the connectivity trees, when considered in this way, are highly divergent. Secondly, the data are scale-dependent: both large- and small-scale structures, (that is, regions, their constituent nuclei and their constituent subnuclei) contribute to the overall connection tree. Clearly, an approach that permits neuroanatomical information to be represented at multiple levels is required.

In all of the results reported in this section, specific abbreviations are only included once; if an area is involved in a three-stage connection as well as a two-stage connection it would only be counted as part of the two-stage connection tree.

Figure 4-2: Pathway tree illustrating divergent dense connections from the retina. Abstract reports have been included in this figure and are shown in red.

The trees of the densest connections are the least widespread. When Figure 4-2 was expanded to incorporate the next layer of efferent connections, the number of areas involved in the tree became very large (17 separate named structures in level one, 34 in level 2 and 148 in level three). These data are represented in Figure 4-3.

The separate structures named in connection reports did not necessarily exactly correspond to the areas represented by individual dots in Figure 4-1. A given dot was filled if either the brain region it represented or that region's constituent subnuclei were implicated in the pathway under study. If a larger-scale structure that included the region, was involved in a pathway, the dot was filled in with a checked pattern. This is why the number of separate named structures described in Table 4-1 does not correspond to the number of dots filled in.

Retinal pathways involving densely labelled connections and abstracts.

Figure 4-3: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two-, and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of densely labelled connection or abstract reports.

Moderate connections (3, 2, x).

The trees that include moderately-labelled connection reports are more widespread than those taken only from dense connection reports. There are 25 separate named targets in the first level of the retinal pathways tree, 126 in the second level, and 212 in the third (See Figure 4-4). Three-stage pathways involve the majority of brain areas.

Retinal pathways involving densely and moderately labelled connections and abstracts.

Figure 4-4: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two- and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of densely and moderately labelled connection reports or abstract reports.

All connections (3, 2, 1, c, x).

Figure 4-5 shows that if all types of connection report are used to define the retinal efferent pathway, the trees become extremely divergent. This is to the extent that almost every structure in the rat brain is implicated in three-stage retinal pathways at the scale of parcellation chosen for Figure 4-1. There are 44 separate named targets in the first level of the retinal pathways tree, 216 in the second level and 170 in the third.

Figure 4-5: Schematic diagram of the whole rat brain illustrating which areas are implicated in one-, two- and three-stage retinal efferent pathways consisting of any labelled connection reports (i.e. belonging to the '3', '2', '1' or 'c' categories, see Chapter 2) or abstract reports.

4.2.2. Discussion

This section confronts a problem facing objective studies of neuroanatomical organisation in the rat: the conventional definition of ‘a pathway’ as a set of serially connected brain structures, produces a prohibitively large number of pathways when the literature is searched almost exhaustively.

The existence of a chain of connections linking a given structure in the rat brain to the retina, cannot be considered a reliable criterion for the inclusion of that structure in the visual system. If rats have atypically divergent retinal connections, then it may be appropriate to apply neuroanatomical criteria in this way to define systems in other animals. In the absence of a sufficiently broad survey of the literature, however, it would be prudent to treat organisational schemes defined in this way with suspicion.

4.3. NMDS analysis of first stage retinal efferents.

4.3.1. Introduction

This section is concerned with investigating the organisation of interconnections between nuclei receiving direct retinal input. With this objective in mind, I have adopted and developed the approach used by Young and Scannell in their analyses of the connectivity of cortical areas in the cat and monkey (Young 1992, Scannell *et al.* 1995).

These analyses use the ALSCAL routine in the SPSS statistical package, and generally present one single configuration for each connection matrix. The ALSCAL algorithm utilises a cost function, that is equivalent to the $S^{(2)}$ variable described in Chapter 2. This cost function has advantages over others, largely because of its mathematical convenience (Takane *et al.* 1977), but tends to fit longer distances in the configuration more accurately than short distances (Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b).

Changing the order of the rows and columns of asymmetric input data in neural connection matrices sometimes dramatically alters the positions of points in the output configuration with ALSCAL in the SPSS package, which suggests that this method might suffer from problems with local minima with certain asymmetrical connection matrices. In this analysis, I used the MDS procedure from the SAS statistics package. Repeated informal testing of inconsistencies in the output configurations of shuffled matrices revealed that MDS provided consistent results, even with matrices which produced inconsistent output with ALSCAL.

In response to criticisms of the methodology, similarity transforms were developed to remove the effects of sparsity in the NMDS solutions (Simmen *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1994; Young *et al.* 1995b). Monte Carlo methods were used to test the standard NMDS procedure and the data-conditioning transforms, to see how well they could reconstruct two-dimensional configurations from degraded matrices of their distances. They performed very well, producing an average Procrustes R^2 statistic that describes the fit between the reconstructed and original configuration as greater than 0.95 (Young *et al.* 1995b).

I applied NMDS analysis to four matrices representing the connections between areas which receive direct input from the retina, and the retina itself. The four ordinal observation matrices were a raw connection matrix, a symmetrised matrix, and two matrices where the raw connection matrix had been transformed under *pth1* and *wdsm*.

4.3.2. Methods

Computational implementation

I implemented the MDS function on a G6-200 MHz, Pentium Pro PC with 32 Mb RAM by using the PERL programming language to generate the SAS code and run the analyses as a single batch run.

Input matrices and data transforms.

The matrix of connections between the areas that receive input from the retina is shown in Figure 4-6. There are forty-five brain areas which receive a connection from the retina. Only connections denoted by a Neurobase code with a category number equal to or less than that of an abstract report (i.e. code 'x', with category number 5, see Table 2-2). All other connection reports (such as 'mixed connections', see Table 2-2) were disregarded. In situations where Neurobase contains more than one connection report with a different code, I have simply used the connection report with the lowest category number.

	ICe	AOS	DT	LT	MT	PRT	NOT	OP	PPT	SC	SCI	SCg	SCs	SCop	SCsg	MEA	MA	LHA	SOperi	LPO	AHA	AHNa	AVP	MPO	MPN	RCH	SBPV	SCH	PV	PVH	SO	OT	R	BST	NDB-h	AD	AV	LD	LG	LGd	LP	IGL	LGv	LGvl	LGvm										
ICe	X																																																						
AOS	X	X	X	X	X	3	3	0	0	0																																													
DT	X	X	X	0																																																			
LT	X	X	X																																																				
MT	X	3	2		X	3	3	0	0	1																																													
PRT	X	X	X	X	X	X	X	2	2																																														
NOT	c				e	X	X	c																																															
OP						X	X	X		1																																													
PPT						X	X	X		X																																													
SC	2					3	c	1	c	X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
SCI						3				X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
SCg										X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
SCs						3	c	e	e	X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
SCop										X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
SCsg										X	X	X	X	X	X																																								
MEA																X		x						2	2																														
MA																	X		x					0	0																														
LHA																		X	X	3	2			3	3																														
SOperi																		X	X																																				
LPO						1													X					c	c																														
AHA																			X	X	X	X		1	1	1																													
AHNa																			X	X	X																																		
AVP																				X	X	X		2	2																														
MPO						1															X	X		X	X																														
MPN																					X	X		X	X																														
RCH																																																							
SBPV																																																							
SCH						1																																																	
PV																																																							
PVH																																																							
SO						1																																																	
OT																																																							
R	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	3	3	3	1	c	e	c	2	1	c	1	1	2	2	3	1	2	1	c	X	1	e	1	1	c	3	3	2	3	3	3	3	1										
BST																																																							
NDB-h																																																							
AD																																																							
AV																																																							
LD											2																																												
LG											0																																												
LGd											0																																												
LP											2																																												
IGL											2																																												
LGv											2																																												
LGvl											3																																												
LGvm											3																																												

Figure 4-6: Connection matrix for first-stage retinal connections. Codes have standard meanings as defined in Table 2-2.

Four input matrices were calculated from this connection matrix. The first was obtained by replacing the Neurobase codes with similarity values according to the scheme described in Table 4-2, to give an asymmetric similarity matrix, (referred to hereafter as \hat{N}_1). This matrix was ‘symmetrised’ (that is, it was transposed and added to itself) to give the matrix \hat{T}_1 , according to Equation 4-1.

$$\hat{T}_1 = \hat{N}_1^T + \hat{N}_1 \tag{Equation 4-1}$$

The third matrix was obtained by acting on \hat{N}_1 with the *pthl* transform to obtain the matrix \hat{P}_1 . The fourth matrix was obtained by acting on \hat{N}_1 with the *wdsm* transform to give a matrix \hat{W}_1 .

Each similarity matrix was analysed separately with NMDS, using both tied and untied approaches under the $S^{(0.5)}$, $S^{(1)}$ and $S^{(2)}$ cost functions described in Section

2.2.3. This procedure generated six configurations which were compared by performing a Procrustes rotation to fit each of them to the first configuration generated.

Neurobase Code	Similarity Value
X	3
3	3
2	2
1	1
c	1
x	1
g	0
0	0

Table 4-2: The translation between Neurobase codes and the similarity values required to generate a proximity matrix. All other Neurobase codes were assigned a similarity value of 0.

4.3.3. Results

Analysis of nontransformed connection matrices.

NMDS solutions for the $S^{(1)}$ cost function under the tied approach, acting on the basic asymmetric similarity matrix (\hat{N}_1), and the nontransformed symmetric similarity matrix (\hat{T}_1), are shown with connections included in Figure 4-7 and Figure 4-8.

In this analysis, the retina sits at the centre of the configuration and radiates connections to each and every area. This is not unexpected, since the criterion for selecting an area to be included in this analysis was that it receive input from the retina.

The most interconnected structures in this configuration are the brain structures that are often considered to be the early visual system (Sefton and Dreher 1995), lying along the right-hand side of the configuration. There are roughly three groups within this sector of the figure. The superior colliculus and its subnuclei (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop) lie close to the dorsal part of the lateral geniculate nucleus and the lateral posterior nucleus, at the top of the figure. Approximately midway down the side of the figure are the ventral part of the lateral geniculate nucleus and its lateral

subnucleus (LGv, LGvl), the pretectum, the optic pretectal nucleus, the posterior pretectal nucleus (PRT, OP, PPT) and the laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (LD). At the bottom of the figure lies a group made up of the parts of the accessory optic system (AOS, DT, LT, MT), and the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT).

The top left-hand corner holds an interconnected set of structures made up of the lateral and medial preoptic nuclei (LPO, MPN), the medial preoptic area (MPO), the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVH), the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BST), the medial nucleus of the amygdala (MEA), the anterior hypothalamic area (AHA), and the anteroventral preoptic nucleus (AVP).

Several structures lie at positions in between these two major groups. The intergeniculate leaflet (IGL), the external nucleus of the inferior colliculus (ICe) and the ventromedial part of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGvm) lie to either side of the retina, equidistant from both groups. The suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), the retrochiasmatic nucleus (RCH), the subparaventricular zone (SBPV) and the olfactory tubercle (OT) lie between the retina and the group of structures containing the preoptic nuclei.

Areas at the bottom of the figure (AHNa, NDBh, AV, AD, PV, SO, Soperi, MA) have very sparse connectivity with the other structures in the system, and are constrained to lie close together in order to be as far from the other structures as possible.

The configuration derived from $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_1$ using the $S^{(1)}$ tied approach appears almost identical to that obtained from $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_1$, the only significant difference being that the positions of the ICe and LGvl change between the two analyses.

Figure 4-7: The NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of \hat{N}_1 . See Appendix A for abbreviations. Thick arrows correspond to Neurobase codes of '3', medium arrows to codes of '2' and thin arrows to '1', 'c' or 'x'. See Table 2-2 for explanation of Neurobase codes.

Figure 4-8: The NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_1$.

The output configurations of the six separate NMDS analyses for each input matrix produced Figure 4-9 when mapped onto a single figure with Procrustes rotation. The coloured lines denote the different positions of points representing the same brain structure in different configurations. The points correspond to the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied, and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied analyses, moving from the labelled to the unlabelled end of the line.

Many of the lines in this figure overlap considerably and suggest that the positions of points in Figures 4-7 and 4-8 should be considered to be variable within the range of lines shown in Figure 4-9. In as much as the interpretation of these figures is performed by eye, there does not seem to be any significant difference between the output configurations produced by analyses of \hat{T}_1 and \hat{N}_1 (a Procrustes rotation between the configurations shown in Figure 4-7 and 4-8 had an R^2 value of 0.92; the average R^2 for Procrustes rotations between \hat{T}_1 and \hat{N}_1 output configurations derived from the same cost function has an mean value of 0.95).

Figure 4-9: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{N}_1 and \hat{T}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.

Analysis of transformed connection matrices.

The *pth1* and *wdsm* transforms were used on the basic asymmetric connection matrix to produce two similarity matrices: $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_1$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_1$ respectively. The configurations produced by analyses which involved the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function are presented below in Figures 4-10 and 4-12.

The overall distribution of points in both output configurations is much less homogenous than in the nontransformed data. The interconnected areas form tightly-bound clumps, rather than the even distribution that is present in Figures 4-7 and 4-8. The two configurations have significantly different overall shapes, but the composition of their constituent clumps is similar (a Procrustes rotation between the two configurations in Figures 4-10 and 4-12 produced an R^2 value of 0.59).

The configuration produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_1$ has the retina lying centrally, the main connections from the retina terminating within two clusters, and sparsely-connected nuclei which have no involvement in pathways to other structures occupying the left-hand side of the figure in a radial pattern. One of the main clusters contains the parts of the accessory optic system (AOS, DT, LT, MT), the pretectum (PRT, NOT, PPT, OP), the superior colliculus (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop), the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd, LGv, LGvl, LGvm, IGL), the lateral posterior and laterodorsal nuclei of the thalamus (LP, LD), and the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH). The second cluster is made up of the lateral and medial preoptic nuclei (LPO, MPN), the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis (BST), the peri-supraoptic retinal terminal field (SOperi), the medial preoptic area (MPO), the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVH), the medial nucleus of the amygdala (MEA), the anterior hypothalamic area (AHA), the anterior part of the

anterior hypothalamic nucleus (AHNa), and the olfactory tubercle. The anteroventral preoptic nucleus (AVP) and the retrochiasmatic nucleus (RCH) lie between the retina and the two interconnected clusters.

Figure 4-10: The configuration generated by NMSD analysis of the matrix shown in \hat{P}_1 .

This configuration is very strongly constrained by the inclusion in the analysis of many objects which are very dissimilar to all others. An interesting feature of the substructure of the main visual cluster is that the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd) is separated from the superior colliculus (SC), but otherwise the fine structure of the collection of nuclei resembles the grouping of visual nuclei in the previous section's description of analyses of \hat{T}_1 and \hat{N}_1 .

The differences between cost functions in this system are dramatic, as shown in Figure 4-11. The overall shape of the configuration is extremely dependent upon the cost function used in the analysis, and the positions of all points change significantly under the $S^{(2)}$ cost function. The four nuclei that only receive a sparse input from the retina (AV, NDBh, PV, AD) collapsed into a single point under the $S^{(2)}$ cost function with the tied condition. Nonetheless, there is no overlap between the clusters described above, with the exception that the retrochiasmatic nucleus (RCH) lies in the visual system cluster under analyses using the $S^{(2)}$ tied condition.

Figure 4-11: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{P}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.

The main organisational feature emphasised by the analysis of \hat{W}_1 is the extreme separation of sparsely-connected structures in the top left-hand corner from the clusters in rest of the figure. The retina is less central in this figure, occupying a roughly central position at the bottom. Two sets of connections extend from the retina to either side of it, and appear very separate from one another. The cluster to the right of the retina is almost identical in composition to the top cluster in the configuration generated from \hat{P}_1 , with the exception that the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), lies closer to the cluster on the left of the retina which contains the preoptic nuclei. The intergeniculate leaflet lies very close to the retina in an intermediate position between the two clusters. The peri-supraoptic retinal terminal field (SOperi), the olfactory tubercle (OT), and the anterior part of the anterior hypothalamic nucleus (AHNa), appear as a separate cluster in this analysis.

One interesting feature is the separation of the pretectum (PRT) from three of its six constituent nuclei (PPT, NOT, OP) in this figure. The *wdsm* transform emphasises the overall connectivity of a structure in NMDS analyses. The connectivity of parts of the pretectum that do not receive input from the retina (APN, MPT, NPC), may have affected its position in the configuration. The rudimentary interpretation of labelling density that I used in the definition of the connection matrix may be dependent on scale. Denser labelling is considered to be indicative of stronger connections and large-scale injections would tend to produce denser labelling.

Figure 4-12: The configuration generated by NMDS analysis of \hat{W}_1 .

The amount of overlap between lines joining equivalent points in the scatter-plot of the six solution configurations is very small in comparison to previous analyses (see Figure 4-13). There is some overlap between structures within a given subgroup, such as the parts of the accessory optic system, but in general, the length of the lines is much shorter, suggesting that the positions of points are much more tightly constrained in this analysis. In fact, this is an example of an NMDS analysis that cannot be more tightly constrained with this number of objects in two dimensions, since every entry in \hat{W}_1 is unique.

Figure 4-13: The six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{W}_1 with the $S^{(1)}$ tied, $S^{(1)}$ untied, $S^{(2)}$ tied, $S^{(2)}$ untied, $S^{(0.5)}$ tied and $S^{(0.5)}$ untied cost functions.

4.3.4. Discussion

The analyses presented in this section advance the description of the early visual system in the rat by presenting in single diagrams organisational schemes for rat retinal efferents, based on objective analysis. From a methodological viewpoint, it builds on previous analyses of the connectional organisation of connection data using NMDS in cats and monkeys by presenting more than one possible solution at a time,

thus providing an estimate of the likely variability or uncertainty of the position of each point in the configuration.

According to these analyses, the retinal efferents of the rat fell into three broad categories: the nuclei of the classical early visual system; a group dominated by the presence of many hypothalamic nuclei; and sparsely-connected nuclei that are not interconnected at all.

The group consisting of the nuclei of the early visual system included the superior colliculus and its constituent parts (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop); the pretectum as a whole, as well as three of its six subnuclei (PRT, NOT, OP, PPT); the nuclei of the lateral thalamus and some of the lateral geniculate nuclei (LP, LD, LGv, LGvl, LGvm, LGd); and the parts of the accessory optic system (AOS, DT, LT, MT). Within this group there seemed to be three subgroups. The nuclei of the accessory optic system, (with occasional inclusion of the nucleus of the optic tract, NOT) formed one subgroup; the other pretectal nuclei which receive retinal input (PRT, OP, PPT) and the ventral part of the lateral geniculate nucleus formed a second; and the superior colliculus (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop), the lateral posterior nucleus (LP) and dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd) formed a third.

Other efferent connections of the retina include hypothalamic, septal and amygdaloid nuclei (PVH, LHA, AVP, LPO, MPO, MPN, BST, MEA) that are not usually associated with the visual system. Nonetheless they appeared to form a second cluster consistently in the four analyses presented here. Other nuclei were associated with these two groups: the intergeniculate leaflet (IGL), and suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), which were consistently found in an intermediate position.

The final group were the sparsely-connected nuclei (SO, NDBh, AD, AV, PV, SBPV, OT, MA, AHNa, and SOperi). Their relative proximity in these analyses was caused by their separation from other nuclei, rather than any association caused by interconnections between them. Therefore, this grouping of brain regions is not regarded to be functionally significant.

4.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from the retinal efferent connection matrix.

4.4.1. Introduction

The NMDS plots presented in Section 4.3 are all two-dimensional representations of the data. In Chapter 3, I showed that two-dimensional NMDS representations of high-dimensional Euclidean proximity data captured little of the underlying organisation, producing Procrustes R^2 values of less than 0.5. This may mean that low-dimensional NMDS is of limited utility for the analysis of neural connectivity, and that higher-dimensional solutions may capture details of the data that are obscured in two-dimensional analyses.

In this section, I will describe results from nonparametric cluster analyses of the proximity data of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from the retinal efferent connectivity matrix in Figure 4-6. The objective of this exercise was to compare cluster analyses of high-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from the retinal efferent connection matrix with cluster analyses taken from two-dimensional NMDS configurations. If the problems concerning the reconstruction of high-dimensional configurations in a low dimensionality were present, then nonparametric cluster analysis can be used to interpret the structure of high-dimensional configurations.

4.4.2. Methods.

I applied cluster analysis using the MODECLUS function from the SAS/STAT statistical computing package to the configurations described in Section 4.3. I derived ten different hierarchically organised cluster schemes for each configuration, by analysing the data under the different clustering paradigms described in detail in Chapter 2.

Sixty cluster trees were generated for each connection matrix at each dimensionality. Seven out of every ten of these schemes were hierarchically organised and were made up of several individual cluster schemes. The data presented below are the averaged cluster-count matrices for all trees, derived using either a fixed-radius or nearest-neighbour paradigm (see Section 2.2.4 for a definition of cluster-count matrices).

4.4.3. Results.

Cluster analysis of two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N} : an example.

In this section, I will use illustrative examples to show the form of output from the cluster analyses. I will start at a low level, describing the output of a relatively small number of analyses; and then generalise from this restricted dataset. The two-dimensional configurations in Figure 4-14 show how the cluster analysis produces clusters of variable size and shape for the configuration that was presented in Figure 4-7. MODECLUS found thirteen clusters in the configuration illustrated below. Broadly speaking, the nature of the clusters is quite similar to the groupings described in Section 4.3, but with some exceptions. The groupings that are described in the conclusions of the previous section are based on an interpretation by eye of the relative proximities and connections between objects, whereas the cluster analysis in this section only acts on the proximities; and unconnected brain structures, (such as

the AD, AV, NDBh and PV), appear in a single cluster in this analysis. The main features of the previous analysis are also preserved here, with a large cluster to the bottom left, made up of parts of the visual brainstem and visual thalamus; a second cluster containing the constituent parts of the accessory optic system and the nucleus of the optic tract; and another cluster appearing at the bottom left made up of parts of the hypothalamus and the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis, as well as the medial nucleus of the amygdala.

Figure 4-14: An example of fixed kernel (kernel radius: 0.45) nonparametric cluster analysis based on the two-dimensional NMDS configuration derived from \hat{N}_1 under the $S^{(1)}$ cost function with the tied condition.

If we were presented with this classification without knowledge of the connectivity or proximities upon which it is based, the degree to which organisational properties of the system could be inferred would be quite limited. The clustering information

presented by this analysis does not convey any indication concerning the layout of each cluster without reference to the coordinate data on which it was based.

Using the JOIN option in MODECLUS produces a hierarchical scheme, where clusters are sequentially dissolved in ascending order of significance. If the clusters were sequentially joined to provide a tree, the branching of the tree would indicate the relative proximity of separate clusters. A hierarchical scheme for the same configuration and initial cluster conditions shown in Figure 4-14, is presented in Figure 4-15. Dissolved clusters do not join in a sequential way at all, because the kernel radius is not large enough. If the kernel radius is increased (see Figure 4-16), a hierarchical tree is obtained, but the original cluster structure of the tree changed. Happily, this scheme coincides with the interpretations of the same configuration from the previous section, but this may not have been the case with all input variables. The final tree in Figure 4-17 employs the nearest-neighbour clustering methodology with the K= variable set to 3. The initial cluster structure of this solution is similar to that of the solution presented in Figure 4-15, but the hierarchical tree is fully joined, providing an indication of inter-cluster proximities.

Figure 4-15: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with $R=0.45$ and active JOIN option. The input datum for this analysis was the NMDS configuration ($Fit=1$, tied) of the asymmetrical similarity matrix shown in Figure 4-6.

Figure 4-16: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with $R=0.65$ and active JOIN option.

Figure 4-17: Hierarchical tree of MODECLUS analysis with $DR=1.8$ and $CK=3$ and active JOIN option.

It seems clear after having presented three examples of quite varied cluster schemes produced by this analysis that the exact specifications of the input parameters strongly influence the nature of the output. The remainder of this section describes a large number of separate analyses that use a wide variety of input variables. The most consistent features in the output cluster schemes from different analyses were described in cluster-count matrices (see Section 2.2.4).

The cluster-count matrix in Figure 4-18 is the average of the different fixed-radius kernel cluster analyses (paradigms 1, 2, 3, and 4; see Section 2.2.4). The overall distribution of areas corresponded well to the descriptions derived by eye from the NMDS configurations in the last section.

The first group includes the ventrolateral and ventral nuclei of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGvl, LGv), the pretectum, the optic pretectal nucleus and the posterior pretectal nucleus (PRT, OP, PPT), and the retina (R). The second group contains the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd), the lateral posterior nucleus (LP), the superior colliculus, and its constituent nuclei (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop). The third group was made up of the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), and the accessory optic nuclei (AOS, MT, DT, LT). I will refer to these groupings as the 'early visual system'.

The last, well-defined group is made up of the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the lateral and medial preoptic nuclei (LPO, MPN), the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVH), the medial nucleus of the amygdala (MEA), the medial preoptic area (MPO), the bed nuclei of the stria terminalis (BST), the anterior hypothalamic area (AHA), the anteroventral nucleus of the hypothalamus (AVP), the perisupraoptic retinal terminal field (SOperi), and the anterior part of the anterior

hypothalamic nucleus (AHNa). This group will be referred to as the ‘hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal group’ for the remainder of this section.

The remaining structures (ICe, SO, LGvm, AD, NDBh, AV, SBPV, MA, RCH, SCH, OT) are grouped together, but rarely with any other structure more than 60% of the time. These will be referred to as ‘intermediate’ or ‘sparsely-connected’ structures in the remainder of this section.

Figure 4-18: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . The MODECLUS analyses used paradigms based on fixed-radius clustering kernels (paradigms 1-4).

The overall appearance of the cluster-count matrix derived from the nearest-neighbour clustering paradigms (see Figure 4-19) is patchy in comparison with the fixed-radius kernel analyses; and some groupings that are weak in the fixed kernel analysis appear strong here. For example, the grouping of AD, NDBh, AV and PV is as strong as the grouping between the accessory optic nuclei (AOS, DT, LT, MT). The organisation of the cluster-count matrix is less interpretable from a hierarchical point of view, since its patchiness obscures the substructure of the larger scale groups. However, the groupings in the matrix corresponds well to those from the fixed-radius analysis described above. The one anomalous set of areas is the sparsely-connected nuclei (LGvm, SO, PV, AV, AD, NDBh, SBPV, MA, OT, AHN_a) which forms a strongly-associated group amongst themselves, and groups together with nuclei that lie in the intermediate positions of the two-dimensional configuration (RCH, SCH).

Figure 4-19: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . The MODECLUS analyses used paradigms based on nearest-neighbour clustering kernels (paradigms 5-10).

Rather than restrict my attention to one class of analysis, I used as many methods as possible, and reported features that were common in all cases. The final matrix of this section is shown in Figure 4-20, presenting the average cluster-counts of all cluster analyses based on two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . This matrix is the mean of the two matrices in Figures 4-18 and 4-19.

There are six overlapping groups. The first two are made up of early visual system structures (ICe, IGL, SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop, LGd, LP, LGv, LGvl, PRT, PPT, OP, R), and are associated with each other. The third group is made up of the accessory optic nuclei (AOS, DT, LT, MT), and the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT). The remaining three groups overlap. They contain the hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal regions which formed a separate group previously (AVP, PVH, MEA, MPN, BST, MPO, AHA, LPO, LHA, SOperi); and the remaining sparsely-connected and intermediate areas (LGvm, SO, PV, AD, NDBh, AV, SBPV, MA, RCH, OT, AHN_a).

Figure 4-20: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 .

Comparison between nonparametric cluster analysis of two and five-dimensional NMDS configurations.

An average cluster-count matrix from cluster analysis of both two- and five-dimensional configurations is presented in Figure 4-21. The composition of the clusters in this figure tallies very well with that of the two-dimensional cluster-count matrix shown above. There appears to be a clearer separation between the visual-system groupings and the other groups of structures (the hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal group, and the intermediate and sparsely-connected nuclei) than with two-dimensional data alone. There was less grouping amongst the intermediate and sparsely-connected nuclei.

Figure 4-21: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . 1210 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure.

Comparison between nonparametric cluster analyses of different similarity matrices based on the same connectivity data.

All of the analyses described in the previous section were derived from NMDS analyses of a single similarity matrix, \hat{N}_1 . The analysis was repeated on each of the three remaining similarity matrices for this connection matrix (\hat{T}_1 , \hat{P}_1 and \hat{W}_1). The composition of groups formed over all the cluster analyses is quite consistent with previous results, with the following exceptions: the clusters produced by analysis of the \hat{T}_1 similarity matrix have a very similar cluster-count matrix to that of \hat{N}_1 ; the groupings of intermediate and sparsely-connected nuclei are associated with the hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal nuclei; and there is a clear separation between the groups which contain early visual system nuclei and those which do not.

Figure 4-22: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{T}_1 . 1168 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure.

The three groups of structures from the early visual system form a single large-scale group in the cluster-count matrix derived from NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_1$ (see Figure 4-23). Two sub-clusters are present. One is made up of the external nucleus of the inferior colliculus (ICe), the parts of the superior colliculus (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop); and the lateral posterior nucleus and laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (LP, LD). The other holds the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), and the nuclei of the accessory optic system (AOS, DT, LT, MT). The intergeniculate nucleus appears as a member of this group.

The remaining structures of the hypothalamic, amygdaloid, septal group and the sparsely-connected or intermediate group form two very distinct sets. The structures which possess only one afferent connection from the retina are in one group (AD, AV, PV and NDBh), whilst the remaining structures comprise the other (AVP, AHNa, AHA, MPO, MPN, BST, LPO, MEA, PVH, SOperi, LHA, OT and MA).

Figure 4-23: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{P}_1 . 1123 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure.

The cluster-count matrix derived from analysis of \hat{W}_1 is the least like the cluster-count matrix derived from \hat{N}_1 (See Figure 4-24). One large-scale group contains early visual system structures as well as some of the intermediate structures, such as IGL and SCH. A second group corresponds well to the hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal group; and the remaining sparsely-connected nuclei form two other groups.

Sub-groups within the early visual system group appear quite different from those shown in analyses of \hat{N}_1 : the intermediate and superficial parts of the superior colliculus appear in different sub-groups; and the pretectum (PRT) appears in a different directory from two of its subnuclei (PPT, OP). This lends weight to the argument that NMDS representations of connectivity data transformed under *wdsm* emphasise different characteristics from those described by studies of untransformed data (Young *et al.* 1995b).

Figure 4-24: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{W}_1 . 1219 separate cluster schemes from 120 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure.

Summary of all cluster analyses

When compiled into a single matrix, the cluster-count data is similar to the interpretation taken from the two-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 . The cluster-count matrix of this data is presented in Figure 4-25.

There are five groups. The first two are parts of a larger group. The first group consists of the lateral posterior nucleus (LP), the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd), and the various parts of the superior colliculus (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop). The second group is made up of the lateral dorsal nucleus (LD), the ventrolateral and ventral parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGvl, LGv), the pretectum, posterior pretectal nucleus, and optic pretectal nucleus (PRT, PPT, OP). The third group is close to, but separate from, the first two, and is made up of the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), and the accessory optic nuclei (AOS, DT, LT, MT).

Several stray nuclei are associated with these groups but do not seem to form a distinctive group of their own. These are the external nucleus of the inferior colliculus (ICe), the intergeniculate nucleus (IGL), the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), the retina (R), the retrochiasmatic nucleus (RCH), the subparaventricular zone, the ventromedial part of the lateral geniculate (LGvm), and the supraoptic nucleus (SO).

The fourth group is made up of nuclei that receive very sparse input from the retina and project to no other retinal targets (AV, NDBh, PV, AD). The last group is made up of the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the lateral and medial preoptic nuclei (LPO, MPN), the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVH), the medial nucleus of the amygdala (MEA), the medial preoptic area (MPO), the bed nuclei of the stria terminalis (BST), the anterior hypothalamic area (AHA), the anteroventral

nucleus of the hypothalamus (AVP), the peri-supraoptic retinal terminal field (SOperi) and the anterior part of the anterior hypothalamic nucleus (AHNa).

Figure 4-25: Cluster-count matrix of MODECLUS analyses from all two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations derived from \hat{N}_1 , \hat{T}_1 , \hat{P}_1 and \hat{W}_1 . 4720 separate cluster schemes from 480 different cluster trees make up the data underlying this figure.

The general conclusions drawn from the two-dimensional NMDS scatterplots with lines, are supported by the information in this section. To illustrate this, I have drawn a Venn diagram of the cluster structure from the global cluster-count matrix onto the two-dimensional NMDS configuration taken from \hat{N}_1 (Figure 4-26). The sets delineated by thick red lines correspond roughly to groups of areas which share the same cluster, on average, in more than approximately 70% of cluster trees. The sets delineated by thin red lines contain structures that share the same cluster, on average, in at least approximately 40% of cases. The blue lines delineate structures that share the same cluster tree, on average, in at least approximately 30% of cases.

This shows that the features of the various different clustering methodologies support the organisational principles described in the previous section; namely that the dorsal part of the lateral geniculate body (LGd), the superior colliculus and its constituents (SC, SCi, SCig, SCs, SCsg, SCop), and the lateral posterior nucleus (LP) form a well defined group. A second group is made up of the pretectum (PRT), the optic pretectal nucleus (OP), the posterior pretectal nucleus (PPT), and the ventrolateral and ventral parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGv, LGvl). A third tightly-bound group is made up of the parts of the accessory optic nuclei (AOS, DT, LT, MT).

The first two tightly-bound groups are part of a larger group which also contains the third tightly-bound group, and other retino-recipient nuclei (IGL, ICe, SCH). These structures form the basis of ‘second stage’ analyses which will be reported later in this chapter. The ICe is not included in subsequent analysis, due to the weakness of its input from the retina, which was only evident after analysis of connection strength (see Section 4.6).

Other nuclei featured in this section, (those contained in the so-called hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal cluster and the sparsely-connected nuclei), were dropped from further analyses, unless they satisfied selection criteria for the ‘second stage analysis’ (see Section 4.8).

Figure 4-26: Cartoon of the NMDS configuration obtained with the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function from analyses of \hat{N}_1 with a Venn diagram showing the major groupings suggested by interpreting the cluster-count matrix in Figure 4-25.

4.4.4. Discussion

The results of this section suggest that the two-dimensional representations of $\hat{N}_1, \hat{T}_1, \hat{P}_1$ and \hat{W}_1 are not contradicted by NMDS configurations derived in five dimensions. Of the various methodologies presented here, the one that produced the most consistent and interpretable results were the fixed-radius kernels cluster methods. The nearest-neighbour kernels tended to form clusters made up of very sparsely-connected nuclei which it would have been more desirable to leave unclustered.

4.5. Subparcellation analysis

The matrices analysis in the two preceding sections treat both nuclei and their subnuclei (SC, SCs, and SCsg, for example) in the same analysis, in order to maximise the usage of the available data. In Section 4.4, I ran analyses based on all available data. In connection matrices such as Figure 4-6, matrix entries between a nucleus and a constituent subnucleus were denoted with an 'X' Neurobase code. This was then replaced by a similarity value equivalent to a strong connection. This means that the constituent subnuclei in the NMDS analyses of the previous section are 'bound' to their parent nuclei. However, this may present a problem, because the subnuclei of a given structure may then cluster around that structure and each other as a result of the parcellation scheme's organisation rather than the system's connectivity.

Older studies tend to emphasise larger parcellation schemes, whereas more recent studies tend to emphasise subparcellation. This section is therefore concerned to compare NMDS and cluster analyses of connection matrices using either the large-scale parcellation scheme or the smaller subparcellated delineation of brain nuclei. To do this, I repeated the NMDS and nonparametric cluster analysis using two connection matrices derived from Figure 4-6; in the first, the subparcellated areas were removed, so that only the largest scale structures were present. In the second, I removed the large-scale structures and left the smaller parcellation scheme intact. In both cases the connection matrix only had 'X' symbols along the leading diagonal.

Two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations were calculated for each matrix under all transforms and cost function conditions. Nonparametric cluster analysis was applied to every NMDS output configuration under all ten clustering paradigms. The

global cluster-count matrices are shown in Figures 4-28 and 4-30, and the cluster structure is superimposed onto NMDS configurations in Figures 4-29 and 4-31.

The analysis of the large-scale parcellated connection matrix produced three main groups: a group of unconnected nuclei (AD, PV, NDBh, AV); the group of hypothalamic, amygdaloid and septal nuclei that was described in the previous section (AVP, MPO, LPO, MEA, BST, AHA, PVH, LHA, OT, MA); and the assembled early visual system structures (ICe, AOS, LGv, SC, PRT, LGd, LP, LD, IGL, SCH, R, SO), of which a subset appears to form a tightly-bound group within the larger scale group (LGv, SC, PRT, LGd, LP, LD).

It is interesting to note that AOS did not form part of the tightly-bound group; thus supporting the results of the previous section, where the accessory optic system lies apart from the other structures in the early visual system, (namely the LGd, the LGv, and the SC).

Figure 4-27: Cluster-count matrix derived from a connection matrix of all retinal efferents with small-scale structures removed. The counts in this figure are based on 2956 cluster schemes from 480 cluster trees.

This information was summarised as a Venn diagram superimposed onto the two-dimensional NMDS solution derived using the $S^{(1)}$ cost function under the tied condition (see Figure 4-28). The figure shows how the cluster analysis taken from NMDS configurations in high-dimensional spaces under different cost functions compares to that shown in the simple two-dimensional configuration.

Figure 4-28: Venn diagram showing clustering in large-scale connectivity matrix.

This consistency is not the case for the cluster analysis performed on the similarity matrices taken from the small-scale connectivity data. The cluster-count matrix presents a cluster scheme which, when superimposed onto a two-dimensional NMDS configuration, has one elongated snaking group involving sparsely-connected nuclei

(ICe, SOperi, AHNa, PV, SO, NDBh, AV, AD). This grouping suggests that the two-dimensional cluster structure produced in these configurations is not reliable, since the cluster structure of higher-dimensional solutions suggest associations between structures which appear widely separated when plotted in a two-dimensional configuration.

Removing the large-scale structures effectively drops much of the older connectivity data from the analysis, since older papers tend to involve larger scale parcellation schemes. This showed itself in the two-dimensional NMDS plot in Figure 4-30, since there are a large number of very sparsely-connected structures present.

Figure 4-29: Cluster-count matrix derived from a connection matrix of all retinal efferents with large-scale structures removed. The counts in this figure are based on 3838 cluster schemes from 480 cluster trees.

Figure 4-30: Venn diagram showing clustering in small-scale connectivity matrix.

The other features of the cluster structure seem to confirm the overall conclusions of the previous sections: that the nuclei of the early visual system (SC, AOS, NOT, PRT, PPT, OP, LGd, LGv, LP, LD) are identifiable as a separate system on the basis of the connections between them.

4.6. Connection strength estimation.

The objective of this section is to re-examine the raw data and obtain quantitative estimates of the connection weights in order to attempt to prioritise the connections. Most neuroanatomical papers offer qualitative descriptions of connection strength rather than quantitative measurements. In the rat, quantitative data does exist for a

limited number of connections that have been particularly well studied (Martin 1986; Linden and Perry 1983), but does not exist for the vast majority of connection reports. For example: the number of retinal ganglion cells that project to the superior colliculus is of the order 10^5 (Linden and Perry 1983), and the weakest retinal efferents may only involve a few fibres, such as the retinal projection to the inferior colliculus (see Figure 5 in Itaya and Van Hoesen 1982). In addition to this, the sensitivity of different neuroanatomical methods varies over at least two orders of magnitude (Wan *et al.* 1982; Trojanowski *et al.* 1982; Ter Horst *et al.* 1984). Furthermore, the density of label produced in any neuroanatomical experiment is dependent on the concentration and volume of tracer injected (Behzadi *et al.* 1990).

In previous studies of systems-level organisation, little or no explicit attempt was made to address this problem quantitatively. Scannell and co-workers categorised connections into one of four classifications: ‘dense’, ‘moderate’, ‘sparse’ or ‘nonexistent’, based on their interpretation of the literature, and assigned ordinal connection weights of 3, 2, 1 and 0 respectively (Scannell *et al.* 1995). In other studies of neural connectivity, connections were not differentiated on the basis of their strength, but on the basis of whether they were reciprocal (Young 1992; Young 1993), or on the basis of their laminar pattern of origin and termination (Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Hilgetag *et al.* 1996a).

The analysis presented here describes how the data in Neurobase was analysed objectively to give ordinal connection weight estimates between brain structures.

4.6.1. Pathway analysis.

The basic structure of the method for calculating connection weight estimates was described in detail in Chapter 2. The strength both of the output connections of the

retina and of those of structures which receive relatively strong inputs from the retina were analysed. These retino-recipient areas of the brain are the lateral and medial terminal nuclei of the accessory optic system (LT, MT), the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), the optic nucleus of the pretectum (OP), the posterior pretectal nucleus (PPT), the superior colliculus (SC), the suprachiasmatic nucleus of the hypothalamus (SCH), the dorsal and ventral parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd, LGv), and the intergeniculate nucleus (IGL) (Sefton and Dreher 1995).

Methods

I analysed the output connectivity of the retina in the rat using data taken from 23 separate papers yielding 821 comparisons between 87 connections.

Results

MBOLTZMANN found 4852 connection strength hierarchies in which the number of levels varies between 21 and 32. In of these hierarchies, none of the comparison constraints are violated. The most frequent number of levels is 26, present in 1064 hierarchies. The frequencies of connection strength hierarchies are plotted in Figure 4-31 below. In subsequent analyses this information was interpreted by calculating the mean and variance of each connection strength frequency function. This provides both a derived value for the connection strength (referred to here as the ‘connection strength estimate’ or \bar{C}_{AB} ; see Section 2.2.2), and a measure of how well-defined this value is (that is, the standard deviation of the connection strength frequency function, S_{AB}).

Probability density functions of 26 level connection weight hierarchies for retinal efferents.

Figure 4-31: Connection strength frequency functions calculated from 1064 26-level retinal efferent connection strength hierarchies using the MBOLTZMANN classifier.

The procedure was repeated for areas receiving the twelve strongest connections from the retina. The connection strength hierarchies generated were summarised by plotting the mean connection strengths in Figure 4-32 where the weight of each of the lines is an indication of their \bar{C}_{AB} value.

The following figure only describes the simplest kind of systems-level descriptions of connectivity: a feed-forward 'tree' with no consideration of the interaction between branches, and no consideration of reciprocal connections or feedback loops. It does serve to illustrate the simple utility of this approach, by showing how this analysis can describe connections in a semi-numerical framework suitable for analysis. The figure does not, however, show the variability in the definition of the connection strength.

Figure 4-32: Two stage tree of connection weight estimates from the retina involving the recipients of the twelve strongest connections of the retina. The weight of the lines indicates connection weight estimate values. The areas were sorted vertically according to the estimated strength of the strongest afferent connection, so that areas receiving the strongest connections lie at the top.

Discussion

The mathematical discipline of Graph Theory involves the analysis of networks made up of nodes and edges. Such a formulation appears ideal for the analysis of ‘grey box’ connectivity data. However, the development of graph-theoretical approaches to studying neural connectivity has been hampered by the absence of clearly-defined connection weights in the raw data. Despite being merely a probabilistic ordinal estimate, the end-product of this method may aid the development of graph-theoretical approaches.

A great wealth of neuroanatomical data exists in the literature, but it cannot properly be interpreted reliably without analysis. Connection strength estimation analysis is time consuming and computationally intensive. It does, however, describe the ‘raw data’ of large-scale connectivity in more objective detail than previous connectivity analyses.

4.6.2. Connection weight estimation for the retinal efferent matrix.

The analyses in the previous section calculated weights for efferent projections from the retina and from first-stage retino-recipient areas in separate analyses. In this section, I will describe how I have used this approach to describe the connectivity of a whole connection matrix, representing the network of interconnections between the areas that were studied in the previous section.

Method

The connections between the retina and retino-recipient areas that appeared in Figure 4-32 were analysed using the method described in the previous section. The analysis used 135 connection reports, taken from 42 papers, and produced 481 comparisons.

Results

Table 4-3 shows the numerical data which was produced by analysis of the early visual system matrix. Each cell of the matrix is divided into 3 rows. The first row represents the highest priority labelling density found in Neurobase. These values are referred to here as 'Neurobase codes'. The mean values of the connection strength distributions are located in the second row of each cell and the final row of each cell contains the standard deviation from with the same distributions.

Some of the connections in Table 4-3 are only denoted by valid Neurobase codes (that is, c, 1, 2 or 3), and do not have mean or standard deviation values. This means that despite the presence of valid data in the database, no comparisons could be made to constrain these connections' values. All other Neurobase codes, such as '0', 'u', 'm', 'g', and 'X' were ignored.

	AOS	LT	MT	PRT	NOT	OP	PPT	SC	SCH	R	LGd	IGL	LGv
AOS	X	X	X	3 <i>0.58</i> <i>0.24</i>	3 <i>0.73</i> <i>0.18</i>	0 <i>0.33</i> <i>0.22</i>	0	0 <i>0.23</i> <i>0.17</i>			0		1 <i>0.56</i> <i>0.20</i>
LT	X	X	g	m	3 <i>0.60</i> <i>0.26</i>	m	m	0 <i>0.14</i> <i>0.13</i>			m		1 <i>0.56</i> <i>0.21</i>
MT	X	2 <i>0.29</i> <i>0.10</i>	X	3 <i>0.58</i> <i>0.26</i>	3 <i>0.70</i> <i>0.17</i>	0 <i>0.10</i> <i>0.09</i>	0	1 <i>0.31</i> <i>0.10</i>			0 <i>0.09</i> <i>0.08</i>		0 <i>0.11</i> <i>0.09</i>
PRT	m	g	m	X	X	X	X	m			1 <i>0.92</i> <i>0.08</i>		2 <i>0.58</i> <i>0.25</i>
NOT	c	g	c	X	X	c		1 <i>0.46</i> <i>0.11</i>			1 <i>0.33</i> <i>0.18</i>		1 <i>0.55</i> <i>0.21</i>
OP	m		m	X	m	X		1 <i>0.37</i> <i>0.10</i>			1 <i>0.31</i> <i>0.16</i>		2 <i>0.64</i> <i>0.17</i>
PPT	m		m	X	m	m	X	m			1 <i>0.51</i> <i>0.32</i>		2 <i>0.27</i> <i>0.15</i>
SC				3 <i>0.36</i> <i>0.15</i>	c	1	c	X			3 <i>0.64</i> <i>0.14</i>	2	3 <i>0.92</i> <i>0.09</i>
SCH				1 <i>0.15</i> <i>0.10</i>					X		0 <i>0.06</i> <i>0.07</i>	1	2 <i>0.85</i> <i>0.12</i>
R	3 <i>0.35</i> <i>0.22</i>	3 <i>0.48</i> <i>0.11</i>	3 <i>0.61</i> <i>0.10</i>	3 <i>0.49</i> <i>0.15</i>	3 <i>0.82</i> <i>0.15</i>	3 <i>0.88</i> <i>0.10</i>	3 <i>0.22</i> <i>0.16</i>	3 <i>0.94</i> <i>0.07</i>	3 <i>0.20</i> <i>0.14</i>	X	3 <i>0.78</i> <i>0.09</i>	3	3 <i>0.67</i> <i>0.15</i>
LGd	m	m		m	m	m		0 <i>0.19</i> <i>0.13</i>	m		X	m	0 <i>0.09</i> <i>0.09</i>
IGL				2 <i>0.72</i> <i>0.20</i>				2 <i>0.80</i> <i>0.14</i>	3 <i>0.73</i> <i>0.21</i>		1 <i>0.21</i> <i>0.19</i>	X	2 <i>0.45</i> <i>0.20</i>
LGv	2 <i>0.34</i> <i>0.24</i>	2 <i>0.38</i> <i>0.12</i>	c	3 <i>0.57</i> <i>0.25</i>	2 <i>0.21</i> <i>0.17</i>	3 <i>0.73</i> <i>0.15</i>	u	3 <i>0.64</i> <i>0.10</i>	2 <i>0.45</i> <i>0.19</i>		2 <i>0.65</i> <i>0.10</i>	m	X

Table 4-3: Connection matrix with normalised ordinal probabilistic connection weights and an unbiased estimate of standard deviation calculated from the probability distribution function generated by MBOLTZMANN. Bold alphanumeric codes: Neurobase connection codes (see Chapter 2), Bold italic values: normalised ordinal probabilistic connection strength values, Italic values: unbiased estimate of standard deviation from connection strength frequency functions.

Discussion

It is interesting to note that some of the mean connection strength values shown in Table 4-3 did not have the same ordinal characteristics as the Neurobase codes: 0, 1, 2, and 3. This confirms that objective analysis of the connection data from the literature was necessary to estimate the connection strength.

4.7. *NMDS analysis based on a connection weight estimates for a matrix.*

This section describes NMDS analysis of the matrix of connection weight estimates described in Section 4.6.

4.7.1. Methods

The asymmetric matrix of mean values of the connection strength frequency functions were used as proximity data, which were then analysed with NMDS. The matrix is shown in Figure 4-33. Where the connection was known to exist but no ordinal probabilistic connection strength values had been calculated, the value of 0.5 was given. When the original matrix entry had a ‘X’ Neurobase code the value of 1.0 was assigned to the connection (see Table 4-3 for the output of the analysis of the matrix of connection weight estimates). This ensured that subnuclei were treated as if they were ‘very strongly connected’ to the nuclei that contained them.

	AOS	LT	MT	PRT	NOT	OP	PPT	SC	SCH	R	LGd	IGL	LGv
AOS	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.58	0.73	0.33	0.00	0.23	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56
LT	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.60	0.00	0.00	0.14	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.56
MT	1.00	0.29	1.00	0.58	0.70	0.10	0.00	0.31	0.00	0.00	0.09	0.00	0.11
PRT	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.92	0.00	0.58
NOT	0.50	0.00	0.50	1.00	1.00	0.50	0.00	0.46	0.00	0.00	0.33	0.00	0.55
OP	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.37	0.00	0.00	0.31	0.00	0.64
PPT	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.51	0.00	0.27
SC	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.36	0.50	0.50	0.50	1.00	0.00	0.00	0.64	0.50	0.92
SCH	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.15	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.06	0.50	0.85
R	0.35	0.48	0.61	0.49	0.82	0.88	0.22	0.94	0.20	1.00	0.78	0.50	0.67
LGd	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.19	0.00	0.00	1.00	0.00	0.09
IGL	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.72	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.80	0.73	0.00	0.21	1.00	0.45
LGv	0.34	0.38	0.50	0.57	0.21	0.73	0.00	0.64	0.45	0.00	0.65	0.00	1.00

Figure 4-33: The matrix of connection weight estimates used as the asymmetric similarity matrix in these NMDS analyses of connectional organisation of the visual system.

The computational implementation of the NMDS analysis was identical to that used in Section 4.3, with six separate configurations produced, with three cost functions under two different conditions for tied similarities. Procrustes rotations were used to map the configurations into a single configuration.

4.7.2. Results

The six NMDS configurations are shown rotated onto each other using Procrustes rotations in Figure 4-34. The spread of the points is relatively small and the positions of points relative to each other does not change between different cost functions. The retina appears in the centre, the retino-recipient parts of the pretectum (PRT, NOT, OP, PPT) at the top of the figure, and the accessory optic system nuclei (AOS, MT, LT) on the right-hand side. The superior colliculus (SC) appears to the left of, but relatively close to, the retina, and the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH) appears at the bottom of the figure. One interesting feature of this figure is that the three constituent parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus appear in widely separated parts of the figure. The ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (LGv) lies close to the retina, on the opposite side from the superior colliculus so that it is on the same side as the accessory optic system nuclei. The intergeniculate leaflet (IGL) appears at the extreme bottom left-hand corner of the figure, and the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus lies on the far right of the figure.

NMDS solutions of finely-graded retinal efferent matrix

Figure 4-34: Procrustes rotation of two-dimensional NMDS configurations from the six different NMDS analyses of the matrix of connection weight estimates.

Figure 4-35 shows the configuration calculated with the $S^{(1)}$ cost function under the tied condition, and includes the connections as lines between the points to show the association between nuclei more explicitly. There are a large number of interconnections between these brain structures, and the relative complexity of the system is illustrated here. No obvious pathways or routes stand out from this figure.

Figure 4-35: Two-dimensional NMDS plot representing the connective organization of the early visual system in the rat with lines representing interarea connections. The weight of the lines represents the strength of the connection as shown in the similarity matrix in Figure 4-33. The configuration was calculated under the $S^{(1)}$ cost function using the tied approach.

4.7.3. Discussion

The configurations in this section show a distribution of points which seems to confirm that all the nuclei included in the analysis are part of the same system, since there does not appear to be any strong clustering that to suggest that some areas are segregated from the others. The different parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus lie in completely different parts of the figure. The ventral part is closer to the accessory optic nuclei; the intergeniculate leaflet is close to the suprachiasmatic nucleus; and

the dorsal part is close to the superior colliculus, but remote from all other parts of the system.

The results of these analyses should be treated with caution since they only made use of a limited number of connections. The effect of including the other areas with which these nuclei interconnect cannot be estimated, and might transform the relative positions of the points in these figures. The connection strengths (asymmetric similarity values) represented in the configurations were more carefully estimated than any others presented here or elsewhere, but were nonetheless only mean values of ordinal probability distributions. Work in the future may involve coupling NMDS directly to an MBOLTZMANN-like engine to calculate proximity models directly from the connection data in the literature.

4.8. Extension of the NMDS proximity method to the next stage of the visual system.

4.8.1. Introduction

In my opinion, establishing which areas to include in a connectivity analysis is the most important single factor determining the interpretability of the results. As I have shown, it is a relatively straightforward matter to repeat NMDS analyses in coordinate spaces with different numbers of dimensions and under different minimisation paradigms; but repeating analyses for different connection matrices may be an impractical approach to such a large-scale problem. The visual system is an ideal vehicle for addressing the issue of how one can select a subset of areas for analysis based on connectivity data, because it has a clearly definable starting point.

Once the first stage of retinal output has been analysed, what criteria should be used to study the next stage? It would seem appropriate to repeat the NMDS analysis using brain areas which receive input from the main output stations of the retina.

In Section 4.6, I derived connection weight estimates for retinal efferents and the efferents of the areas that received the strongest input from the retina. In this section, I will describe NMDS and nonparametric cluster analysis of the connection matrix made up of these structures and their principle efferents.

These structures do not comprise the entire ‘visual system’. It is also to be expected that the divergent connectivity of the nuclei involved will implicate many nonvisual structures, or structures which have minimal visual function. The analyses presented here are intended to be an exploratory description of the organisation of the strongest two stage pathways from the retina.

The structures in this analysis were selected purely on connectional grounds. Areas which receive input from retinal recipient nuclei are not necessarily involved in vision, and so the term ‘visual system’ must be used with caution in this context. The collation of connection data was as exhaustive as was permitted by the time-frame of this project, and it was almost certainly incomplete.

4.8.2. Methods

The connection matrix that acted as input data for these analyses is shown in Figure 4-36. The constituent areas of this matrix are the retina, the twelve areas that receive the strongest connections from the retina, and the structures that receive the five strongest connections from each first stage retinal efferent. The superior colliculus and pretectum were large-scale structures that contained nuclei and laminae which do not receive strong retinal input. In order to ensure that the first-stage retinal efferent subnuclei were represented, the ten strongest outputs of these large-scale structures were included. This involved extra areas in the analysis, and three nuclei, (the subparaventricular zone, the parataenial thalamic nucleus, and the pineal) were removed

asymmetric similarity matrix to give two other similarity matrices (which are referred to as $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_2$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_2$ respectively).

NMDS analyses using the $S^{(1)}$, $S^{(2)}$ and $S^{(0.5)}$ cost functions under both tied and untied conditions were used to generate configurations in two- and five-dimensional coordinate spaces. These configurations were then analysed with nonparametric cluster analysis. The ten clustering paradigms that were described in Section 2.2.4 were used to analyse every separate configuration, and the data was compiled into cluster-count matrices as before.

4.8.3. Results

In this section, I will describe the overall characteristics of the summary cluster-counts and Venn diagrams superimposed onto NMDS plots, calculated with the $S^{(1)}$ cost function under the tied condition.

The general structure of the positions of the points from the first-stage analysis is similar to the output configurations reported in Section 4.3. There are roughly three subsystems; one contains the nuclei of the accessory optic system, the second the suprachiasmatic nucleus, and the third the superior colliculus and visual thalamus. The second-stage nuclei and areas fit quite well into this scheme.

The vestibular nuclei (VNC) and the inferior olive (IO) associate themselves with the nuclei of the accessory optic system. Hypothalamic structures lie close to the suprachiasmatic nucleus. The pretectal nuclei occupy an intermediate position between the accessory optic nuclei and the superior colliculus. The additional structures contained in the main lateral thalamus/superior colliculus group, seem to include the zona incerta (ZI), the anterior pretectal area (APN), and the areas of the visual cortex (VISp, VISL, VISM).

I have superimposed red and blue thresholds at roughly 40% and 30% in the cluster-count matrix shown in Figure 4-37. These thresholds were applied (as accurately as it is possible to manage by eye) to determine the set borders on the Venn diagram superimposed onto the NMDS configuration in Figure 4-38. The cluster structure broadly suggests that the second-stage structures in this analysis could be subdivided into four broad groups.

The largest group includes the retina, the pretectum, superior colliculus, visual cortex (VISp, VISL, VISM), and other mesencephalic and diencephalic structures (ZI, PO, PBG). There are two subgroups within this large-scale group. The first includes the pretectum (PRT), the ventral part of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGv), the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), the retina (R), the posterior pretectal nucleus (PPT), the superficial layer of superior colliculus (SCs, SCsg, SCop), the optic pretectal nucleus (OP), the parabigeminal nucleus (PBG), the superior colliculus as a whole (SC), the intermediate layers of the superior colliculus (SCi), the zona incerta (ZI) and the posterior thalamic nucleus (PO). The second subgroup includes the striate and extrastriate cortex (VISp, VISL, VISM), the dorsal part of the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd), the lateral posterior nucleus (LP), and to a lesser extent, the lateral dorsal nucleus of the thalamus (LD) and the anterior thalamic nuclei as a whole (ATN).

The next major group of structures that are implicated in visual function, appears at the top of Figure 4-38 and includes the nuclei of the accessory optic system (AOS, DT, LT, MT), the nucleus of the optic tract (NOT), the inferior olive (IO), the vestibular nuclei (VNC), the pontine grey (PG), the prepositus nucleus hypoglossi (PRP) and the tegmental reticular nucleus (TRN).

The third group of structures includes the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), the intergeniculate leaflet (IGL), the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the tuberal hypothalamic area (TUA), the paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus (PVT), and the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus (PVH). The final category of structures in this analysis is made up of outliers: brain structures which are not included in any large-scale groups, despite having been grouped to a proportion of some members of a large-scale group (POm, CL, MD, RT, PF, MRN). It should be mentioned that some of these structures were not strictly outliers in all of the analyses since they were often included in different groupings, but did not fall into a specific grouping consistently. So, rather than consider the outliers as 'outside' the classification scheme, it may be more appropriate to consider them as falling 'between' different groups.

Figure 4-37: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the matrix shown in Figure 4-36. The cluster-counts were derived from 4471 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees.

Figure 4-38: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from Figure 4-38.

4.8.4. Control analyses.

The matrices under analysis in this section (and in Sections 4.3 and 4.4) all contain nuclei and their subnuclei in the same analysis (that is, SC, SCs, and SCsg all appear in the same analysis). I trimmed the connection matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the same procedures as were used in the control analysis in Section 4.5. Two matrices were used, one with all substructures removed, and the second with all large-scale structures omitted.

Figure 4-39: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the subparcellated structures removed. The cluster-counts were derived from 3162 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees.

The cluster-count matrix of the large-scale analysis is presented in Figure 4-39 and the Venn diagram illustrates the cluster-counts in Figure 4-40. These analyses present a more interpretable large-scale organisation of the system than the mixed parcellation analysis. There were four groups of brain structures. The visual cortex (VISp, VISL, VISM), dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (LGd), lateral posterior thalamic nucleus (LP), and laterodorsal thalamic nucleus (LD) are very strongly grouped together. The accessory optic nuclei (AOS), vestibular nuclei (VNC), inferior olive (IO), prepositus nucleus hypoglossi (PRP), mesencephalic reticular nucleus (MRN), and pontine grey (PG) form another distinct group.

One difference between this and the global analysis is the presence of a set of areas in between these two groups. The posterior nucleus of the thalamus (PO), the zona incerta (ZI), the superior colliculus (SC), the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (LGv), and the parabigeminal nucleus (PBG) all lie in a band separating the two groups on

the NMDS configuration in Figure 4-40 and share clusters with structures from both groups in more than roughly 30% of the different cluster trees in this analysis.

The retina lies apart from these groups in the final large-scale set, which also contains the intergeniculate leaflet (IGL), the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), the lateral hypothalamic area (LHA), the tuberal area of the hypothalamus (TUA), and the periventricular nucleus of the thalamus (PVT).

Figure 4-40: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the connection matrix shown in figure 4-36 with the subparcellated structures removed, with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from figure 4-39.

The structure of the small-scale analysis was less clear than the large-scale. This is evident in the patchy appearance of the cluster-count matrix shown in Figure 4-41. The large-scale groups shown in Figure 4-42 correspond to the four groups of the large-scale analysis. One group contains the parts of the visual cortex (VISp, VISL, VISM), and the nuclei of the lateral thalamus (LD, LP, LGd). A second group containing the inferior olive (IO), the vestibular nuclei (VNC), and the accessory optic nuclei lies on the opposite side of the configuration from the first group; and an intermediate group of areas which contains some pretectal nuclei (PPT, OP, APN), the zona incerta (ZI) and the superior colliculus (SC) lies between them. A final group lies to one side, containing the suprachiasmatic nucleus (SCH), and other hypothalamic nuclei (PVH, PVT, TUA, LHA).

Figure 4-41: Cluster-count matrix from nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from two- and five-dimensional configurations calculated from four similarity matrices derived from the connection matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the large-scale structures removed. The cluster-counts were derived from 4105 cluster schemes taken from 480 cluster trees.

Figure 4-42: The NMDS configuration produced by the $S^{(1)}$ fit function under the tied condition for the matrix shown in Figure 4-36 with the large-scale structures removed with Venn diagrams illustrating the overall cluster structure read from Figure 4-44.

4.8.5. Discussion

In this section, I examine the connective organisation of the second stage of retinal efferents in the rat. Since connection weight estimates have not been derived for the matrix due to insufficient data, and time constraints, the analyses in this section should be viewed as exploratory.

Including the second-stage structures does not appear significantly to disrupt the relative positions of the brain areas from the first stage of the analysis. The main difference is that the retina is consistently situated at one edge of the configuration whereas in previous analyses it has lain at the centre. The three main sub-groups of

areas as identified in Sections 4.3, 4.4 and 4.7 were retained in the analyses of this section: the accessory optic nuclei (AOS) consistently appears in a separate cluster, the superior colliculus and lateral thalamic nuclei in another (SC, LP, LGd, LGv, LP, LD), and the regions of the hypothalamus appear in a third (*e.g.* SCH).

The apparent association between the superior colliculus and dorsal part of the lateral geniculate nucleus from the first-stage analysis was not preserved. The LGd was much more strongly associated with the visual cortex, and the superior colliculus is consistently associated with other parts of the visual midbrain and diencephalon.

The physiological properties of the nuclei in this analysis are consistent with the large-scale structure scheme presented here. The members of the first large-scale cluster (that is, AOS, IO, and VNC) and areas which appear proximal to the core areas of the cluster (MRN, PG, TRN, PRP), are all implicated either in optokinetic, or optovestibular systems (King and Fuchs 1979; Horn *et al.* 1983; Cazin *et al.* 1984; Lannou *et al.* 1984; Torigoe *et al.* 1986; Schmidt *et al.* 1993); or are precerebellar nuclei (Wiesendanger and Wiesendanger 1982; Azizi and Woodward 1987).

The members of the second large-scale group (SC, LGd, LP, VISp, VISL and VISM) are all members of the classical visual pathway implicated in pattern recognition and the perceptual process of vision (Hughes 1977; Dean 1978; Dean 1981; Goodale and Carey 1990).

The members of the third large-scale group (SCH, TUA, PVH) are hypothalamic nuclei. SCH is known to mediate diurnal rhythms, and the nuclei that it is most closely associated with are likely to be involved in the homeostatic aspects of diurnal rhythms (Levine *et al.* 1991; Moore and Card 1994). The presence of the IGL in this

group corroborates the fact that it is functionally distinct from the other the parts of the lateral geniculate nucleus (Moore and Card 1994).

Even though the cluster analyses in this section are influenced by the number of structures and the presence of subparcellated regions, the general features of the analysis appear consistent when either the subparcellated regions are removed or considered without their 'parent' regions.

Next stage

The next stage in the examination of the visual pathway would be to collate enough connection data concerning the connections described in the connection matrix in Figure 4-37, to be able to reliably define connection weight estimates for this system and then to run more detailed NMDS and MODECLUS analyses. Then connection weight estimates would also be derived for all efferents of the nuclei involved. These efferents would be ranked and the strongest connections included in the next stage of analysis.

4.9. Discussion.

This chapter describes the first systematic analyses of the connectional organisation of the visual system in the rat. The principles I have set out could equally be applied to any sensory system which has a definite starting point: the trigeminal somatosensory pathway, for example. I began by tracing all connections from the starting point to 'first-stage' structures. Then, the connections were prioritised in terms of their connection strength, and the interconnections between the first-stage structures which received the strongest input were examined. This process was repeated, so that the output connections of the first-stage structures to second-stage

structures were found, prioritised and analysed. Subsequent stages might conceivably be analysed in the same way, given sufficient time and computational resources.

The principal drawback of this methodology is that it is extremely time consuming. The rate-limiting step of the process was data entry (reading and collating neuroanatomical papers into Neurobase). The criteria for the selection of areas (and consequently the papers that described the connections of those areas) were previous analyses. This meant that the whole process involved several stages of data entry, interspersed with preliminary analysis.

The advantages of this method are that it is objective treatment of the neuroanatomical data; it presents an original view of the organisation of neural systems in general, and is informative concerning the organisation of the visual system in the rat.

One of the largest scales of neuroscience is the 'systems level' (see Chapter 1, Perkel 1990; Shepherd 1994). The definition of a 'system' and the neuroanatomical basis of interactions between systems is of vital importance to the theoretical basis of the subject, and neuroanatomical information is often used to define the major pathways that carry information.

The existence of a neuroanatomical pathway as a serially-linked chain of brain structures is not sufficient evidence to support the definition of a system or a functional pathway under the 'grey box' model, since a description of all possible 'pathways' can connect the retina to the majority of structures in the entire brain in the same number of stages required to reach the primary visual cortex. If neurophysiological evidence (or perhaps more quantitative neuroanatomical

descriptions) is used to demonstrate a functional connection, then the concept of a pathway may be more usefully employed.

Studying the network of axonal projections between brain areas is a more useful method to describe the organisation of the system (Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Young 1992; Van Essen and Deyoe 1995). NMDS analysis was combined with nonparametric cluster analysis to provide a representation of the connective organisation of the early visual system in the rat, based on global connection matrices which incorporated all of the connections between areas in the analysis. This representation broadly divides the early visual system in the rat into three subsystems: optokinetic and optovestibular areas; areas that are classically associated with the visual system and hypothalamic areas likely involved in circadian rhythms.

Some areas were included that are not normally associated with vision. For example, the zona incerta appeared in the second-stage analysis of retinal output connectivity by virtue of the strength of its connections with the pretectum (see Section 4.8). In 1979, Legg showed that lesions of the zona incerta impair black-white visual discrimination tasks, but show no impairment of tasks requiring discrimination between sets of lines at different orientations. He selected ZI as a candidate region for his experiments on the basis of its afferent connections from the LGv (Legg 1979a).

This suggests that visual processing in the rat may involve components which are not considered part of the classically-defined visual system. One possible definition of 'a system' within the grey box model could be 'a set of brain structures that have more connections inside the set than outside, and more nonconnections with structures outside the set than inside' (M. P. Young, Personal Communication). A definition on these terms would depend on the definition of 'a connection', and 'a brain structure',

but would require a global treatment of connection data across many structures. This issue will be discussed in Chapter 6.

This approach may have relevance to the study of the phenomenon of ‘blindsight’. Human subjects with damaged visual cortices will deny that they can see stimuli presented in the affected portion of the visual field. Under ‘forced choice’ behavioural paradigms, they can correctly report which visual stimuli are presented to them (Covey and Stoerig 1993). Work in animal models has demonstrated analogous phenomena in gerbils and monkeys (Carey *et al.* 1990; Covey and Stoerig 1995). The underlying anatomical substrate that permits this form of residual vision usually cites subcortical pathways, involving the superior colliculus, the pulvinar, and extrastriate projections of the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, but not other retinal efferents such as the accessory optic system and the pretectum (See figure 1 of Covey and Stoerig 1993). The analyses of two stage retinal projections is in agreement with these intuitive interpretations, since the set that contains the striate and extrastriate cortex also contains LP and LGd but not SC, PRT or AOS (See Figure 4-39, 4-41 and 4-45).

Interpretation of the substructure of clusters was not attempted, partially because the positions of points within a given configuration are quite mobile (*e.g.*, see Figure 4-9). Additionally, it becomes harder to interpret the results of NMDS analyses in the absence of clear trends of receptive field properties, such as those that can be identified in the monkey and cat cortices (Young 1992; Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995).

Within the framework of the proximity model described in Chapter 1, the analysis described in this chapter can be described as a detailed exploration of the region of connectivity space surrounding the retina. Since I included every structure which is

connected to the retina (as far as possible), and therefore the points which represented those structures in the proximity model, populated the region of connectivity space surrounding the retina.

It is interesting to consider how a global analysis of the whole brain might appear under the proximity model with a topological, or a hodological definition of dissimilarity. Such an analysis would involve several hundred areas. Furthermore, in a topological analysis, the maximum distance between two points would be the nonconnection distance; and under a hodological approach, the divergence of the pathways from the retina suggests that the maximum number of 'steps' required to step from a given structure to any other structure is three or four. This would mean that even in this situation, the maximum distance between any two structures would be relatively small. This would suggest that whole brain analyses of connectivity would require high-dimensional proximity representations, a nonspatial analysis, or a more refined relationship between connection strength and proximity (see Chapter 1). Alternatively, the definition of brain systems mentioned above could be used to partition the set of all brain structures into more manageable subsets that could be investigated with proximity models. Computational methods have been devised which could conceivably implement this (Hilgetag *et al.* 1996b).

In order to map the connectivity of the data, it may be necessary to screen connections for strength and only accept connections which are stronger than a predetermined threshold value (see Section 4.6). Even in the absence of quantitative connection strengths, this model could be used to describe the connectional organisation of any neural system in a rigorous and exploratory manner.

Chapter 5

Proximity Analysis of the Connectional Organisation of Central Systems Involved in Spatial Memory in Rats

5. Proximity Analysis of the Connectional Organisation of Central Systems Involved in Spatial Memory in Rats

5.1. Introduction

In the last chapter, I applied an open-ended approach to connectional data, by basing my analyses on pathways originating from the most peripheral component of the visual system. In this chapter, I will consider the connections between a restricted set of structures involved in a form of central processing: that of spatial learning and memory.

The hippocampus of the rat is a prominent field of research in the study of both memory and spatial information processing. Individual neurons within the CA3 and CA1 regions of Ammon's Horn fire preferentially when the rat is in a specific region of space (the so-called 'place cells' firing within their 'place fields'; O'Keefe and Dostrovsky 1971), even when the animal navigates there in darkness (Quirk *et al.* 1990). Destruction of the hippocampus also impairs the ability of rats to navigate to an invisible submerged platform (Morris *et al.* 1982). As a result, the hippocampal formation has been the focus of much theoretical work concerning a variety of different descriptions of central processing. These theories involve such disparate topics as the mechanisms of depression (Gray 1982), memory trace formation (Buzsaki 1989), cognitive mapping and systems of path integration (O'Keefe and Nadel 1978; McNaughton *et al.* 1996), and declarative memory (Eichenbaum *et al.* 1992). Although there are differences in interpretation between authors concerning the precise nature of the information processing being executed in the hippocampus (compare Cohen and Eichenbaum 1991, and Rawlins *et al.* 1991 for two contrasting points of view), it would appear that the hippocampus and other neural systems

involved in spatial processing would provide an ideal test for the analysis methods described in this thesis.

Existing organisation schemes were derived principally from neurophysiological data, but they also incorporated constraints imposed by the neuroanatomical connections. If there are clear differences between the output schemes of the analyses in this chapter and existing schemes, then either the methods described in this thesis produce misleading results and need to be refined or redesigned, or the standard intuitive method of generating organisational schemes is unsatisfactory.

As was emphasised in the previous chapter, the choice of which nuclei to include in an analysis of connectivity is important. The anatomical circuitry of the hippocampal formation has been well studied and comprehensively reviewed (Amaral and Witter 1989; Amaral and Witter 1995); as has that of the limbic cortex, which includes the hippocampal formation and limbic areas of the periarthocortex, such as the prelimbic, infralimbic, cingulate, retrosplenial, perirhinal, entorhinal and subicular cortices (Lopes da Silva *et al.* 1990). The connectivity of this system provides the framework within which the hippocampus lies (see Figure 3 of Lopes da Silva *et al.* 1990).

I have included other structures which are implicated in theories involving the hippocampus. The anterior nuclei of the thalamus contain cells which fire preferentially when the animal's head is pointing in a specific direction. These are also known as 'head direction cells' (Blair and Sharp 1995; Taube 1995; Mizumori and Williams 1993). Part of the subcortical system described by Gray (1982) include the mamillary bodies that receive input from the subiculum (Shibata 1989). The mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus was included on the basis of its strong interconnections with parts of the limbic cortex (Groenewegen 1988).

No septal nuclei were included in this analysis despite their involvement in the organisational schemes described by Gray (Gray 1982), and their possible role in the formation of theta rhythms (Buszaki *et al.* 1994). The septum receives a strong input from the hippocampal formation (Meibach and Siegel 1977d; Swanson and Cowan 1977) and Jakab and Leranth describe it as ‘*a conspicuous, integrated part of the limbic system*’ (Jakab and Leranth 1995). However, it does not appear in descriptions of systems concerned with spatial navigation (Redish and Touretzky 1997; Neave *et al.* 1996), and so it was omitted from these analyses.

5.2. Neuroanatomical data

As much connection data as possible was compiled using Neurobase, and is summarised in a Neurobase connection matrix in Figure 5-1. I analysed this matrix with NMDS, and nonparametric cluster analysis, and then derived connection weight estimates for it using the MBOLTZMANN optimisation program. These data were derived from 89 papers, and 933 separate connection reports.

	CA1	CA3	DG	ENT	PAR	POST	PRE	SUB	LM	MM	SUM	TM	ACA	ILA	PL	PRh	RSP	AD	AM	AV	IAM	LD	MD	
CA1	X		c	3	2	2	c	3					0	c	3	1	1							
CA3	3	X	c	1	1		c	c					0		0	0	x							
DG	c	c	X				c	c					0		0									
ENT	3		3	X	2	1	c	c	0	2			1		1	2	1							1
PAR	1	0	1	3	X	2	3	1	3	0	0		0				3	3			1		0	
POST				2	2	X	2		1				0			3	3	3			1		3	
PRE	0	0	1	3	3	2	X	2	3	2	0	0				0	2	2			2		3	
SUB	2	2	2	3	2	c	3	X	2	3	1	2	1	1	3	1	3			2	c	1		
LM									X									3	0					
MM										X						c		2	3	3	3		0	
SUM	2	3	3	3	1	c	1	2	2	1	X				1	1		1						
TM								1	1			X				2								
ACA				1	0	2	2		2	2			X	c	c	2	3	0	3	1		2	3	
ILA				0			0	2	3	3	3	3	1	X	c	2	2	0	2	2	2		2	
PL				2			1		2	2	1	1	3	2	X	2	2		2	2	2	1	3	
PRh	c	0	0		c	2		c							2	X	1							
RSP				2	2	3	2	0		2			3	0	0	x	X	2	3	3			3	
AD	c	c		2	2	3	3				c		3	0	0	c	3	X						
AM		c		3	2		1	2					3	2	2	2	3		X					
AV	c	c		1	2	2	3	2			c		3	0	0	1	3			X				
IAM				2									2			3	2				X			
LD	c	c		1	3	3	3						3		2		3					X		
MD				3			0						3	3	3	1	1							X

Figure 5-1: Connection matrix for central systems involved in spatial memory, (see Appendix C for each individual connection report, and Table 2-2 for the meanings of matrix entries).

5.2.1. Similarity matrices.

I translated the connection values in Figure 5-1 to give an asymmetric similarity matrix \hat{N}_3 . This matrix was transposed and added to itself (see Equation 4-2) to give a symmetrical similarity matrix \hat{T}_3 . Finally, the *pthl* and *wdsm* transforms (see Section 2.2.3) were applied to the matrix to give two similarity matrices \hat{P}_3 and \hat{W}_3 . I analysed these matrices with nonmetric multidimensional scaling, using the $S^{(1)}$, $S^{(2)}$, and $S^{(0.5)}$ cost functions under tied and untied approaches, to produce two- and five-dimensional configurations. I analysed the organisation of these configurations with nonparametric cluster analysis, and generated cluster-count matrices and Venn diagrams to aid the interpretation of the configurations produced by NMDS.

5.3. Nonmetric multidimensional scaling results.

The Procrustes R^2 values describing the similarities between configurations are shown in Table 5-1.

		2 dimensional configurations					5 dimensional configurations				
		N_3	T_3	P_3	W_3	Total	N_3	T_3	P_3	W_3	Total
2 dimensional configurations	N_3	0.79	0.80	0.53	0.81	0.73	0.40	0.42	0.37	0.60	0.45
	T_3	0.80	0.87	0.57	0.81	0.76	0.39	0.41	0.39	0.60	0.45
	P_3	0.53	0.57	0.82	0.60	0.62	0.32	0.30	0.37	0.42	0.35
	W_3	0.81	0.81	0.60	0.99	0.79	0.39	0.40	0.36	0.66	0.45
	Total	0.73	0.76	0.62	0.79	0.72	0.38	0.38	0.37	0.57	0.43
5 dimensional configurations	N_3	0.40	0.39	0.32	0.39	0.38	0.86	0.86	0.68	0.63	0.75
	T_3	0.42	0.41	0.30	0.40	0.38	0.86	0.94	0.67	0.67	0.78
	P_3	0.37	0.39	0.37	0.36	0.37	0.68	0.67	0.87	0.55	0.68
	W_3	0.60	0.60	0.42	0.66	0.57	0.63	0.67	0.55	0.98	0.69
	Total	0.45	0.45	0.35	0.45	0.43	0.75	0.78	0.68	0.69	0.73

Table 5-1: Mean Procrustes R^2 statistics for the NMDS configurations. Each mean value is calculated from 36 individual Procrustes rotations between configurations generated with different combinations of cost function and tied or untied approaches. The mean values along the leading diagonal were calculated from 30 separate R^2 values since configurations were not rotated against themselves.

The low overall mean Procrustes R^2 score of 0.43 between the two- and five-dimensional configurations, suggests that there are substantial differences between them. This apparent difference is reinforced by the observation that the ratio between the stress values of two- and five-dimensional configurations (under the same conditions of cost function and approach to ties) is 1 to 0.4, when averaged over all configurations. Two-dimensional configurations derived from the $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS analyses of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ (with connections represented as lines) are shown in Figures 5-2 and 5-3. Configurations under each combination of cost function and tied or untied conditions are shown in Figures 5-4 and 5-5.

Figure 5-2: NMDS output configuration produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ (bottom), under the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function

Figure 5-3: NMDS output configuration produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ (top) and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ (bottom) under the $S^{(1)}$ tied cost function

Figure 5-4: Six output configurations produced by NMDS analysis of \hat{N}_3 (top) and \hat{T}_3 (bottom), under all cost functions.

Figure 5-5: Six output configurations produced by NMSD analysis of \hat{P}_3 (top) and \hat{W}_3 (bottom) under all cost functions

The two-dimensional configurations representing this system have a consistent structure between different similarity matrices, and under different stress

minimisation paradigms, although the configurations produced by analysis of the transformed matrices $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ are less consistent than the configurations produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$. Some organisational features are immediately apparent from an inspection of Figures 5-2, 5-3, 5-4 and 5-5.

I will describe the some of Figure 5-2 as an example. The parts of the hippocampus (CA1, CA3 and DG) lie at the edge of the figure with CA1 lying closer to the main body of the configuration than the other two points. Their immediate neighbours to the bottom right are the parts of the retrohippocampal region (ENT, SUB, PAR, POST, PRE), and their neighbours to the top left are the supramamillary and lateral mamillary nuclei (SUM, LM). The retrohippocampal areas form a tight clump that includes the anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus.

The variability of the position of LM between cost functions is the most pronounced feature of the structures in the figure, suggesting that its position is less constrained in these two-dimensional configurations than its neighbours. In fact, the position of LM is the most variable in every case except for configurations calculated from $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$, where it is the second most variable. Other areas which shift under different combinations of cost function and tied condition are CA3, IAM, MM, and MD. In the configurations generated by $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, and $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$, the positions of individual areas overlap somewhat with their nearest-neighbours, but generally do not exceed this limit. The configurations produced by NMDS analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$ have no overlap at all.

The tuberomamillary nucleus lies on the edge of the configuration to the top left-hand corner of the figure. The connection matrix in Figure 5-1 shows TM to have three efferent and three afferent connections suggesting that the separation in the figure is

due to the differences in its pattern of connections to other areas in the structure, rather than 'popout' due to sparseness (see Chapter 4). This separation of TM is strongly emphasised in the configuration derived from \hat{W}_3 .

The mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus is situated on the edge of the configuration to the mid-to-bottom left. Just to the right of this lie the infralimbic, prelimbic and perirhinal cortices (ILA, PL, PRh), quite closely together, roughly halfway up the figure to the left-hand side. Slightly below them, the anterior cingulate (ACA) and retrosplenial cortex (RSP) appear, and between them the medial mamillary (MM) nucleus lies separately from the other mamillary nuclei.

The anterior nuclei of the thalamus (AD, AM, AV, IAM, LD) are scattered over the bottom half of the configuration; AM and AV are close to ACA, and RSP; AD is strongly associated with the retrohippocampal regions; LD lies slightly separated to the bottom of the figure; and the interanteromedial nucleus of the thalamus (IAM) lies close to the medial dorsal nucleus (MD) on the left-hand side of the configuration

The configurations produced by NMDS analysis of the \hat{P}_3 similarity matrix appear qualitatively different from configurations derived from the other matrices. The main differences are that CA1 appears separate from CA3 and DG; and that the position of ENT shifts from halfway up on the right-hand side, (close to SUB and PAR) to midway across the bottom half of the configuration (close to ACA and RSP). Other features consistent in other configurations also changed. For example, the tight grouping of PAR, PRE, POST and AD has become a line of points separating CA1 from CA3 and DG.

5.4. Nonparametric cluster analysis.

I submitted the output configurations of the NMDS analyses to the same barrage of cluster analyses that I used on the retinal efferent data in Chapter 4. I used ten cluster analysis paradigms, with both fixed-radius and nearest-neighbour clustering kernels and a variety of different parameter values to ensure that clustering structure at different scales could be examined.

Forty-eight different configurations were produced in the previous section (four matrices, three cost functions, two conditions to tied data, in two- and five-dimensional space), which when analysed produced four hundred and eighty separate cluster trees. The number of separate schemes in a given cluster tree depends on the parameters of the analysis but is typically less than 10.

The results of this chapter are presented as cluster-count matrices. I will describe the most general results first, and then describe the way in which individual analyses differ from them. Figure 5-6 shows the cluster-count matrix taken for all cluster analyses using $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$. I will describe each matrix individually in a later section.

Figure 5-6: Cluster-count matrix derived from all 480 cluster trees from \hat{N}_3 , \hat{T}_3 , \hat{P}_3 and \hat{W}_3 involving 2607 cluster schemes.

I superimposed the cluster structure from Figure 5-6 onto the two-dimensional NMDS configuration of \hat{N}_3 under the $S^{(1)}$ tied condition as a Venn diagram cartoon in Figure 5-7. The Venn diagrams delineate sets of nuclei which share the same cluster in a proportion of cluster trees corresponding to groups of cluster-count cells which are coloured red in Figure 5-6. The sets delineated by thick red lines represent very consistent clusters (>70%), whereas those delineated by thin red lines contain areas which shared the same cluster in 39% to 67% of cluster trees. Those surrounded by blue lines contain structures which share the same cluster in 27% to 39% of cluster trees. These sets will be referred to here as ‘strongly-clustered sets’, ‘red’ sets and ‘blue’ sets. The use of dotted lines to delineate sets does not signify anything, but is to help differentiate between the sets when they overlap. These sets correspond to groupings derived from the cluster analysis, but the thresholds that determined the inclusion of areas into clusters were set arbitrarily.

Figure 5-7: Venn diagram illustrating cluster-count data from Figure 5-6 superimposed onto the NMDS configuration derived from $S^{(1)}$ tied analysis of \hat{N}_3 .

At the broadest level, there are three overlapping blue sets. Two of these sets are distinct from each other, and the third overlaps both of them. Between them, the two nonoverlapping sets involved most of the nuclei and areas involved in the study. One of these sets includes most of the nuclei and areas in the top half of the cluster-count matrix in Figure 5-6 and is situated on the right-hand side of Figure 5-7. This blue set contains one red set and a strongly-clustered set. The red set contains the parts of the hippocampus (CA1, CA3 and DG), the subiculum (SUB), the entorhinal cortex (ENT) and the supramamillary nucleus (SUM). The strongly-clustered set contains the presubiculum, the parasubiculum, the postsubiculum and the anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (PRE, PAR, POST and AD). This strongly-clustered set is one of the

most persistent features throughout these analyses. In the analysis of \hat{N}_3 , the lateral mamillary nucleus (LM) is also part of this red set.

The second blue set that overlaps the other two, contains all the members of the first blue set, except the parts of the hippocampus (CA1, CA3 and DG) and the supramamillary nucleus (SUM). The nuclei involved in the strongly-clustered set from the first cluster (PRE, PAR, POST and AD), are part of a red set that also includes the lateral mamillary nucleus (LM), and the anteroventral nucleus of the thalamus (AV).

The two-dimensional structure of the NMDS configuration of \hat{N}_3 in Figure 5-2 appears quite consistent with the cluster-count sets that are superimposed onto it. There are relatively few sets with components which are widely separated. The one notable exception is the inclusion of the lateral mamillary nucleus (LM) into the red set containing PAR, PRE, AD, POST and AV described above. This may indicate that some two-dimensional configurations placed LM in a less peripheral position (see Figures 5-4 and 5-5) and this feature is preserved in the five-dimensional configurations.

There are a series of partially overlapping red sets at the bottom of the figure. The second red set contains the strongly-clustered set from the first blue set (PRE, PAR, POST and AD), the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus (LD), the anteroventral thalamic nucleus (AV), the retrosplenial cortex (RSP), and the anterior cingulate cortex.

The third red set contains the anteroventral nucleus of the thalamus (AV), the retrosplenial cortex (RSP), the anterior cingulate cortex (ACA), the laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (LD), the anteromedial nucleus of the thalamus (AM), and the

medial mamillary nucleus (MM). In order to make the Venn diagrams interpretable, I reduced the number of overlapping lines. In this case I included both LD and MM in this set despite the fact that they were only included in the same cluster less than 39% of the time. A strongly-clustered set contained AV and RSP.

The third blue set contains all of the areas and nuclei in the last set described, except for LD (RSP, AV, ACA, AM, MM), as well as the mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (MD), the infralimbic and prelimbic cortices (ILA and PL), the perirhinal cortex (PRh), and the interanteromedial nucleus of the thalamus (IAM). There are two overlapping red sets that which are wholly contained within this blue set. They both contain AM, MM, MD, ILA, PL and IAM, and only differ in that one contains PRh and not ACA, and the other contains ACA and not PRh. The tuberomamillary nucleus is the only structure that does not lie within one of the blue sets, but is contained in a red set with the PRh, ILA and PL.

There are several interesting features of this analysis which merit further description. The perirhinal cortex and the entorhinal cortex are associated with completely different structures even though they neighbour each other and appear relatively close on many of the NMDS configurations. Lesion studies which affect this area often damage both the entorhinal and perirhinal cortices simultaneously (Rothblat *et al.* 1993). If these two areas are involved in different connectional systems, then these lesions may affect a wider range of information processing. Other similar features include the separation between the medial mamillary nucleus (MM), the lateral mamillary nucleus (LM), and the supramamillary nucleus (SUM). Although the anterior nuclei of the thalamus (AD, AV, AM, LD, IAM) appear to be very spread out in the NMDS configurations, they appear in the same cluster more than 39% of the

time on average, for all cluster trees, except for AD and AM. IAM is the one exception to this but this nucleus still shares the same red set as AM.

5.4.1. A comparison between cluster analyses taken from NMDS analyses of different similarity matrices.

The results in the previous section describe cluster-counts which were derived from averages over all analyses of all the different similarity matrices. This section considers cluster-count matrices which represent all the cluster analyses derived for each similarity matrix in turn. Given that the Procrustes R^2 value falls to very low values for comparisons between certain configurations, it is important to see if NMDS configurations from different matrices have consistent cluster structures.

The lowest value of R^2 for two configurations of the same dimensionality is 0.41 which occurred between two-dimensional NMDS solutions of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ under the $S^{(2)}$ tied cost function condition and those of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ with the $S^{(1)}$ untied condition. The lowest overall value of R^2 was 0.26 which occurred between five-dimensional NMDS solutions of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ using the $S^{(0.5)}$ cost function and tied condition, and two-dimensional solutions of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ using the $S^{(0.5)}$ cost function under untied condition.

Figures 5-8 and 5-9 illustrate the cluster-count matrices and Venn diagrams of the cluster counts, averaged over all solutions of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$. Figures 5-10 and 5-11 describe the cluster-counts of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$. The overall appearance of these figures is extremely similar to those of the global analyses, in terms of the number and general shape of the sets. This is partially because these Venn diagrams were all plotted on very similar configurations, but this only serves to emphasise the similarities between the set schemes.

Figure 5-8 : Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of \hat{N}_3 .

Figure 5-9: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-8 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of \hat{N}_3 .

Figure 5-10: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$.

Figure 5-11: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-10 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$.

The most consistent features of these analyses are that the parts of the hippocampus (CA1, CA3 and DG), the subiculum (SUB), the supramamillary nucleus (SUM) and

the entorhinal cortex (ENT) are separate from other structures; either in a single red set or in overlapping red sets.

The anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (AD), the postsubiculum (POST), the presubiculum (PRE), and the parasubiculum (PAR) consistently inhabit a strongly-clustered set, and share a red set with the lateral mamillary nucleus (LM). The remaining nuclei and areas in the study are involved in a series of overlapping red sets, although the sets are more discrete in the $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ cluster-counts than those from the $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$ analysis. One possible interpretation of these overlapping clusters is that their sequential sets form an anatomically definable pathway. As I will argue later, this interpretation, although attractive, has problems when the two- and five-dimensional results are considered separately.

Cluster analysis of the configurations generated from $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ resulted in a cluster-count matrix with many off-diagonal red patches which I could not transfer to a Venn diagram (Figure 5-10). This was caused by differences between the two- and five-dimensional configurations and are illustrated by superimposing the cluster structure of the five-dimensional cluster-count matrix (Figure 5-13) onto the two-dimensional NMDS solution as a Venn diagram (Figure 5-14).

Figure 5-12: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$.

Figure 5-13: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of five-dimensional NMDS configurations of $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$.

Figure 5-14: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-13 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$

The set structure shown in Figure 5-14 illustrates how the five-dimensional cluster sets derived from $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ differ markedly from the two-dimensional configurations they have been drawn on to. This can be seen in the way in which the sets are elongated and have to cross over one another without including the same nuclei. Despite this, some of the features which were mentioned before were clearly conserved. AD, PAR, PRE and POST formed a strongly-clustered set. The subiculum (SUB) and the parts of the hippocampus (CA1, CA3 and DG) form a red set. The exception to this is the entorhinal cortex which forms a strongly-clustered set with the dentate gyrus, and is only part of a blue set with the remaining areas of the hippocampus. The perirhinal, infralimbic and prelimbic cortices (PRh, ILA, PL) form a strongly-clustered set with

the mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (MD). The association of AD, PAR, POST, PRE, RSP, ACA, AM and LD in a red set that traverses the entire configuration was consistent with the series of overlapping red sets at the bottom right-hand corner of Figures 5-9 and 5-11, but the inclusion of LM and MM in the same set, despite being on completely different sides of the NMDS configuration; differs from analyses of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$.

Figure 5-15: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of \hat{W}_3 .

Figure 5-16: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-15 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of \hat{W}_3 .

Cluster analyses of the configuration produced by the NMDS analysis of \hat{W}_3 are very consistent, producing clear well-defined sets which rarely overlap. This is probably

due to the high ordinality of the similarity matrix. In these analyses, there are five distinct strongly-clustered sets which appeared separate from each other, but are grouped together in overlapping red sets. The CA3 area of the hippocampus and dentate gyrus (DG), occupy a strongly-clustered set, as did the supramamillary nucleus (SUM), the subiculum (SUB), the entorhinal cortex (ENT), and the CA1 area of the hippocampus. These two strongly-clustered sets are associated in a red set, which is strongly similar to the situation that is described in analyses of \hat{N}_3 and \hat{T}_3 .

The third strongly-clustered set occupies a central position in the two-dimensional configuration, and contains the retrosplenial and anterior cingulate cortices (RSP, ACA), and the anteromedial and anteroventral nuclei of the thalamus (AM, AV). This set is either wholly or partially involved in four red sets, indicating that the *wdsm* transform designates this set of nuclei and areas to be a central set within this particular collection of brain structures. AV and RSP are involved in a red set together with the structures of the second strongly-clustered set (SUM, CA1, SUB, ENT). All four structures in the third strongly-clustered set are involved with the infralimbic and prelimbic cortices (ILA, PL); and are involved in a red set that includes LM, MD and LD.

As before, AD, POST, PRE and PAR are involved in a strongly-clustered set, but LD is also included. A red set associates these structures with ACA, AV and RSP. The last strongly-clustered set involves IAM, ILA, PL, PRh and MM. These structures form a red set together with the tuberomamillary nucleus (TM).

Although some features of the connectional organisation shown in previous analyses are preserved in this figure, some differences are also apparent: there are no series of partially overlapping clusters to suggest a sequential processing hierarchy of any

kind; and the strongly-clustered set containing PAR, POST, PRE, AD and LD is not strongly affiliated with the other parts of the hippocampus in these analyses.

5.4.2. Differences between cluster schemes of NMDS configurations with different numbers of dimensions.

In the previous section, I was concerned with the differences between cluster-count matrices derived from different similarity matrices. In this section, I will consider cluster analyses derived from configurations in either two or five dimensions. Figures 5-17 and 5-18 show the cluster-count matrix and associated Venn diagram derived from all two-dimensional NMDS configurations for this set of areas and nuclei.

Figure 5-17: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two-dimensional NMDS configurations of \hat{N}_3 , \hat{T}_3 , \hat{P}_3 and \hat{W}_3 .

Figure 5-18: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-17 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of \hat{N}_3 .

The two-dimensional structure of the configuration has been preserved in the set structure of this figure; that is, there are no long sinuous pockets where one set includes structures which appear in completely different regions of the configuration (see Figure 5-12). At the large-scale, the set structure in this case is similar to that of the global cluster-count matrix described at the beginning of the chapter (Figure 5-6). There are roughly four blue sets where the constituent nuclei all share the same cluster in at least 27% of the separate cluster trees (on average). The first of these blue sets contains the parts of the hippocampal formation that were closely associated in previous analyses (CA3, DG, CA1, ENT, SUB and SUM), but unlike other analyses LM is also included in this set. The second group of areas in this set includes a

strongly-clustered set which is consistently found across all analyses and includes PAR, PRE, POST and AD. This strongly-clustered set also formed a red set with LD.

The second blue set is completely distinct from the first, with no overlap. It contains several overlapping red sets, and three distinct strongly-clustered sets. The first strongly-clustered set contains PRh, PL, ILA and MM, and the second, MM, AM, and ACA. Both of these sets are included in a red set that also contains MD and IAM. The third strongly-clustered set contains AV and RSP and is also included in a red set that also includes the second strongly-clustered set described above.

The third and fourth blue sets overlap the first and second, with a degree of overlap between themselves. The set structure of the two-dimensional solutions differs from the global and transform-specific cluster-count matrices at the broadest level. The red sets overlap in a way similar to that described previously, but not to an extent that would strongly reinforce the interpretation of a pathway of areas in this system.

The set structure of the cluster-count summary matrix of all the cluster analyses derived from five-dimensional configurations differs from that derived from two-dimensional structures (compare Figures 5-18 and 5-20). The principal difference is the large-scale (blue set) structure.

Figure 5-19: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of five-dimensional NMDS configurations of \hat{N}_3 , \hat{T}_3 , \hat{P}_3 and \hat{W}_3 .

Figure 5-20: Venn diagram of cluster-counts from Figure 5-19 superimposed onto $S^{(1)}$ tied NMDS configuration produced by analysis of \hat{N}_3

The parts of the hippocampus (CA3, CA1 and DG), the supramamillary nucleus (SUM), the entorhinal cortex (ENT), and the subiculum, once again form a red set

that appears separately from other structures, except for the inclusion of the medial mamillary nucleus in a blue set that involves all six members of this red set. A second blue set involves SUB and ENT; and is associated with all of other parts of the retrohippocampal region (PAR, PRE, POST), and the anterodorsal thalamic nucleus (AD). As was the case in almost all the other analyses, AD, PRE, POST and PAR formed a strongly-clustered set.

AV, LD, RSP and ACA also form a nearby strongly-clustered set that is included in two red sets which both, include PAR, PRE, POST, AD, and AM. One of these sets includes LM, and the other MM. This reinforces the connectional difference between MM and LM that has been a feature throughout these analyses. Most nuclei of the anterior thalamus appear in the same red set, rather than being spread out over many structures. IAM and PRh form a strongly-clustered set that also is contained within a red set with MM and PL. ILA, PL and MD form a strongly-clustered set that also is contained a red set with TM and PRh.

5.4.3. Summary of results

The majority of the cluster-count matrices averaged across all data for a given similarity matrix (that is, $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ or $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$), produced broadly similar results across all the data, with respect to the composition of the main sets of clusters. Some features of the summary cluster-count matrix are specific to a subset of cluster analyses, whereas other features are specific to a different subset, for example: the association of LM to the strongly-clustered set of POST, PRE, PAR and AD consistently occurs in five-dimensional and global cluster-count analyses but does not in two-dimensional summaries.

The main differences between analyses derived from different similarity matrices are the medium- and large-scale groupings of areas. The strongly-clustered structure was consistent throughout, but the different methods of analysis emphasise different aspects of the data at medium- and large-scales. The interpretation of the set structure in terms of organisational schemes which might correspond to physiological properties of individual cells in the different areas, appears speculative at best.

In brief, these analyses seem to indicate the existence of four main 'connectional groups'. The first is made up of SUM, SUB, ENT, CA1, CA3 and DG. These areas are the parts of the hippocampus proper and the retrohippocampal areas most usually associated with it (see Figure 3 in Redish and Touretzky 1997). The inclusion of the SUM in this group is unlike most other organisational schemes (*e.g.* Lopes da Silva *et al.* 1990) and is a product of its efferent connections to the hippocampus; especially to the dentate gyrus (Haglund *et al.* 1984). This nucleus contains cells that fire in phase with the theta rhythm of the hippocampus (Kirk 1997).

The second group is made up of PRE, POST, PAR and AD. These structures are probably the most tightly-associated structures in the entire analysis. This reflects particularly the difference in connection patterns between the various anterior thalamic nuclei (Shibata 1993c).

The third and fourth groups are less clearly defined. The third group seemed to consist of LM, RSP, AV, ACA, AM, LD and MM, and this group has quite a heterogeneous structure. It is rare for MM and LM to be categorised in the same group. The lateral mamillary nucleus tends to be more frequently closely affiliated to the second group; whereas the medial mamillary nucleus tended to be more frequently associated with the fourth group. The fourth group consists of IAM, ILA, PL and MD.

The one outlying area in these analyses is TM, which is only ever affiliated to this group out of from those available.

I will discuss some cautionary notes concerning the methodology here. The interactions between these groups are not entirely obvious from the analysis I have used (which was always intended to be exploratory). The exact groupings depend on the choice of transformation applied to the similarity data, and the dimensionality of the coordinate space selected to represent it. Given that two- and five-dimensional configurations present different cluster-count sets, I would prefer to trust the five-dimensional sets since the apparent fit of the NMDS configurations is better (that is, the interpoint distances represent the ordinal properties of the similarity values better in five dimensions than in two).

The choice of colour thresholds for the cluster-counts was made to facilitate the interpretation of the associations between areas in the analysis, and no special relevance should be attached to the values of cluster-counts except in comparison with each other.

The organisational scheme is dependent upon the connection weights used in the analysis. Figure 5-21 shows a cluster-count matrix derived from cluster analyses of NMDS configurations derived in turn from the binary form of the matrix shown in Figure 5-1 (that is, all connections were given the value 1, all nonconnections were given the value zero). This illustrates the importance of connection weights in these analyses.

Figure 5-21: Cluster-count matrix calculated from nonparametric cluster analysis of two- and five-dimensional NMDS configurations of the binarised forms of $\hat{\mathbf{N}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{T}}_3$, $\hat{\mathbf{P}}_3$ and $\hat{\mathbf{W}}_3$.

The parcellation scheme used in the analysis has a strong effect on the interpretation of the connectional groups produced. For example, these analyses have described the various parts of the mamillary bodies (SUM, TM, LM and MM) as belonging to different connectional groups, which would clearly be impossible if the mamillary bodies were considered to be a single entity (Redish and Touretzky 1997; Gray 1982). This is an important point to make concerning the future of this approach (see Chapter 6), since there is no reason why individual nuclei and areas should not be further subdivided if different parts of a given structure have different connectivities.

5.5. Connection weight estimates for this system

5.5.1. Introduction

Part of the reason for studying the connections of a restricted set of brain structures, rather than attempting the open-ended approach used in the previous chapter, was to compile enough connection data from the literature to allow the use of the optimisation method of deriving estimates for the weights for the connections. I compiled a large-scale comparison matrix for the whole connection matrix. I also compiled separate comparison matrices for each row and column in the connection

matrix shown in Figure 5-1. Then I analysed these comparison matrices with the MBOLTZMANN optimiser. I will refer to these studies as ‘whole connection matrix’, ‘efferent’, and ‘afferent’ analyses respectively.

5.5.2. Analysis of the whole connection matrix.

I extracted a single comparison table and matrix for the connection matrix shown in Figure 5-1, and ran MBOLTZMANN on it. The MBOLTZMANN routine was run over 1000 epochs, generating 100 structures per epoch, and produced connection strength hierarchies consisting of 187 separate connections. The best connection strength hierarchy produced in this analysis has a cost of 7220 and 24 hierarchies were computed which had costs of less than 7581 ($7220 + 5\%$ of 7220). The cost function was defined so that a violated strict constraint carried a cost of 2, and a violated tentative constraint carried a cost of 1. The best solutions generated by MBOLTZMANN for this data had a great many violations, but still had a much lower cost than hierarchies generated by chance at the start of each epoch, which was 13769 on average.

It is somewhat surprising that such high costs should be encountered since the connection matrix has only twenty-three entries, compared to the thirteen entries of the whole-matrix analysis reported in Chapter 4. It is possible that the original data taken from Neurobase contained contradictions which gave rise to the extremely high costs.

Connection weight estimates are displayed in Table 5-2, where each connection has three data values on successive rows. The first entry is the Neurobase code attributed to that connection (Table 5-1). The second row contains the value of the mean

normalised connection strength, as defined by Equation 2-2. The third row shows the standard deviation of each normalised connection weight, as defined by Equation 2-3.

There is a low correlation between the codes used in the previous sections and the calculated mean normalised connection strength. This indicates that either this method for calculating connection weight estimates for moderately sized matrices cannot predict connection weights particularly accurately, or that the weights derived from Neurobase codes may not represent the ordinal connection strengths accurately.

	CA1	CA3	DG	ENT	PAR	POST	PRE	SUB	LM	MM	SUM	TM	ACA	ILA	PL	PRh	RSP	AD	AM	AV	IAM	LD	MD	
CA1	X			3 0.51 0.09	2 0.68 0.16	2 0.40 0.13	c 0.78 0.23	3					0	c	3 0.43 0.14	1 0.43 0.22	1 0.60 0.36							
CA3	3 0.56 0.17	X c	c	1 0.24 0.26	1 0.16 0.13		c 0.57 0.35	c 0.50 0.15					0		0	0	x							
DG	c	c	X			c	c	c					0		0									
ENT	3 0.19 0.22	3 0.25 0.19	X	2 0.35 0.13	1 0.25 0.09	c	c	0 0.45 0.19	2 0.57 0.16				1 0.37 0.05	c	1 0.66 0.25	2 0.68 0.09	1 0.20 0.09						1 0.26 0.19	
PAR	1 0.29 0.24	0 0.33 0.22	1 0.71 0.03	3 0.85 0.08	X 0.30 0.14	2 0.85 0.23	3 0.33 0.12	1 0.80 0.39	0 0.34 0.12	0 0.34 0.26			0				3 0.84 0.19	3 0.55 0.11		1 0.35 0.10		0 0.13 0.16		
POST				2 0.45 0.09	2 0.38 0.32	X 0.23 0.14	2 0.23 0.14	1 0.51 0.26					0				3 0.63 0.17	3 0.49 0.16	3 0.47 0.11		1 0.45 0.01		3 0.51 0.21	
PRE	0 0.45 0.29	0 0.88 0.10	1 0.48 0.18	3 0.20 0.10	3 0.20 0.10	X 0.33 0.19	2 0.84 0.11	3 0.32 0.08	2 0.32 0.28	0 0.32 0.28		0				0 0.43 0.18	2 0.22 0.12	2 0.64 0.39		2 0.28 0.17		3 0.71 0.09		
SUB	2 0.75 0.14	2 0.68 0.08	2 0.27 0.19	3 0.15 0.10	2 0.30 0.09	c 0.55 0.06	3 0.55 0.06	X 0.39 0.12	2 0.87 0.01	3 0.45 0.21	1 0.25 0.11	2 0.40 0.04	1 0.80 0.14	1 0.18 0.16	3 0.55 0.21	1 0.33 0.15	3 0.49 0.15				c	2 0.47 0.20	1	
LM								X									3 0.48 0.21	0						
MM									X								c	2 0.62 0.28	3 0.37 0.25	3 0.36 0.14	3		0	
SUM	2 0.74 0.24	3 0.74 0.13	3 0.80 0.33	3 0.36 0.16	1 0.47 0.43	c 0.41 0.19	1 0.78 0.11	2 0.81 0.25	2 0.30 0.28	1 0.30	X				1 0.41 0.37	1 0.50 0.13								
TM								1 0.47 0.24	1 0.38 0.13			X					2							
ACA				1 0.14 0.23	0 0.33 0.26	2 0.83 0.11	2 0.35 0.16	2 0.60 0.32	2 0.73 0.08				X	c	c	2 0.51 0.10	3 0.83 0.22	0 0.33 0.09	3 0.68 0.07	1 0.10 0.06		2 0.38 0.04	3 0.63 0.02	
ILA				0 0.66 0.30			0 0.29 0.09	2 0.58 0.04	3 0.29 0.17	3 0.68 0.07	3 0.35 0.17	1 0.27 0.08	X	c	c	2 0.24 0.35	2 0.40 0.00	0 0.14 0.15	2 0.77 0.19	2 0.96 0.01	2 0.34 0.07	2 0.21 0.14		
PL				2 0.35 0.08			1 0.32 0.15	2 0.75 0.18	2 0.34 0.15	1 0.44 0.14	1 0.81 0.27	3 0.46 0.08	2 0.79 0.04	X	2 0.18 0.05	2 0.16 0.15			2 0.29 0.06	2 0.41 0.20	2 0.59 0.18	1 0.32 0.06	3 0.38 0.30	
PRh	c	0	0	c	2 0.48 0.29		c								2 0.63 0.23	X 0.23 0.11	1							
RSP				2 0.61 0.27	2 0.58 0.33	3 0.38 0.26	2 0.27 0.38	0 0.10 0.06	2 0.54 0.31				3 0.37 0.05	0	0	x	X 0.34 0.26	2 0.83 0.16	3 0.77 0.06		3 0.65 0.12			
AD	c	c		2 0.44 0.17	2 0.34 0.18	3 0.89 0.01	3 0.87 0.08			c			3 0.41 0.11	0	0	c	3 0.93 0.04	X						
AM		c		3 0.40 0.14	2 0.82 0.15		1 0.51 0.19	2 0.17 0.24					3 0.62 0.10	2 0.19 0.09	2 0.59 0.14	2 0.66 0.20	3 0.56 0.09		X					
AV	c	c		1 0.11 0.12	2 0.44 0.38	2 0.32 0.16	3 0.32 0.08	2 0.49 0.17		c			3 0.13 0.02	0	1 0.18 0.02	1 0.07 0.06	3 0.50 0.14			X				
IAM				2 0.37 0.04									2 0.73 0.10			3 0.65 0.31	2 0.56 0.14				X			
LD	c	c		1 0.35 0.22	3 0.58 0.17	3 0.47 0.07	3 0.49 0.15						3 0.66 0.25	2 0.51 0.07		3 0.58 0.15						X		
MD				3 0.63 0.06			0						3 0.46 0.05	3 0.37 0.08	3 0.82 0.07	1 0.40 0.20	1 0.29 0.13						X	

Table 5-2: Matrix of mean normalised connection strengths for the whole connection matrix. See text for description.

Afferent and efferent connectional analysis.

I extracted separate comparison tables for each row and column of the matrix shown in Figure 5-1, and ran MBOLTZMANN separately on each matrix. This provided a separate connection weight hierarchy for the efferent and afferent connections of each brain structure in the matrix.

The MBOLTZMANN routine was run over 50 epochs, generating 25 structures per epoch (except in the case of the MM afferent hierarchy where 100 structures per epoch were calculated). The statistics of the analysis for each row and column are presented in Table 5-3. In some cases, there was insufficient data in the matrix to construct a comparison table, and these are denoted by a dash. None of the output hierarchies had any violations. Cases were observed where the number of hierarchies was relatively small. This usually occurred when the number of areas involved in the hierarchy was small; however the number of hierarchies calculated was also affected by the number of comparisons in the analysis.

With respect to the cases where the total number of hierarchies was close to the maximum calculable under these input parameters, it may be argued that the analysis had not sufficiently explored the search space of all possible hierarchies. The size of the search space of all possible hierarchies becomes prohibitively large with relatively small values of N_{areas} (see Table 2-4).

The data from these analyses are interpretable, and could be used in subsequent NMDS analysis. Similarity matrices derived from this data would be considered 'row conditional' (that is, only the ordinal properties of similarities in the same row would be considered in the calculation, see Takane *et al.* 1977), but this method has not been tested with neural connection data.

Brain Structure	Afferent Hierarchies		Efferent Hierarchies	
	N_{areas}	$N_{hierarchies}$	N_{areas}	$N_{hierarchies}$
CA1	3	4	7	1177
DG	5	54	-	-
ENT	16	1177	10	1201
PAR	13	1177	11	1201
POST	10	1201	8	232
PRE	12	1201	12	520
SUB	4	8	17	1153
LM	9	1201	2	-
MM	11	5000	2	1
SUM	-	-	10	1201
TM	2	1	-	-
ACA	10	619	11	1153
ILA	4	18	11	1201
PL	10	1201	15	1201
PRh	13	1201	2	2
RSP	16	1201	11	1201
AD	9	1201	7	48
AM	5	12	7	1081
AV	6	368	9	1201
IAM	2	2	2	1
LD	6	116	7	321
MD	3	3	6	95

Table 5-3: Numbers of hierarchies in efferent and afferent connection weight analyses.

	CA1	CA3	DG	ENT	PAR	POST	PRE	SUB	LM	MM	SUM	TM	ACA	ILA	PL	PRh	RSP	AD	AM	AV	IAM	LD	MD	
CA1	X		c	3 0.93 0.10	2 0.78 0.18	2 0.35 0.24	c 0.71	3 0.26					0	c	3 0.55 0.15	1 0.12 0.13	1 0.14 0.15							
CA3	3	X	c	1 0.08 0.10	1 0.21 0.18		c 0.20 0.20	c 0.10					0		0 0.13 0.13	0 0.13 0.13	x							
DG	c	c	X			c	c	c					0		0									
ENT	3 0.88 0.25	3 0.85 0.19	X	2 0.79 0.19	1 0.00	c 0.00	c 0.00	0 0.82 0.17	2 0.00				1 0.35 0.10	1 0.20 0.14	2 0.71 0.21	1 0.27 0.10							1 0.17 0.29	
PAR	1 0.00 0.00	0 0.19 0.22	1 0.73 0.16	3 0.33 0.24	X 0.86 0.16	2 0.91 0.07	3 0.04	1 0.07	3 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.06 0.08	1 0.27 0.10	3 0.95 0.25	1 0.25 0.66	3 0.66 0.13	3 0.61 0.23	1 0.20 0.22	1 0.22	0 0.06 0.12	0 0.06 0.12		
POST				2 0.63 0.19	2 0.79 0.19	X 0.50 0.25	2 0.65	1 0.29					0		3 0.96 0.07	3 0.66 0.13	3 0.61 0.23	3 0.23	1 0.20 0.22	1 0.22	3 0.82 0.19	3 0.82 0.19		
PRE	0 0.19 0.22	0 0.58 0.09	1 0.71 0.18	3 0.33 0.24	2 0.86 0.16	X 0.00 0.13	2 0.91 0.07	3 0.04	2 0.07	2 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.00	0 0.06 0.08	1 0.27 0.10	3 0.95 0.25	1 0.25 0.66	3 0.66 0.13	3 0.61 0.23	2 0.20 0.17	2 0.73 0.26	2 0.26	3 0.82 0.19		
SUB	2 0.63 0.48	2 0.38 0.34	2 0.76 0.09	3 0.31 0.22	2 0.88 0.15	c 0.00	3 0.91 0.07	X 0.20 0.05	2 0.98 0.14	3 0.48 0.20	1 0.20	2 0.00	1 0.06 0.08	1 0.27 0.35	3 0.95 0.11	1 0.25 0.13	3 0.66 0.11	3 0.61 0.13	2 0.12 0.18	c 0.25 0.35	1 0.25 0.35	1 0.17 0.29		
LM								X										3 0.94 0.10	0					
MM									X							c		2 0.57 0.17	3 0.00	3 0.25	3 0.25	3 0.25	0	
SUM	2 0.90 0.15	3 0.34 0.11	3 0.17 0.15	1 0.22 0.21	c 0.00	1 0.22 0.21	2 0.55 0.14	2 0.48 0.20	1 0.20	X					1 0.19 0.14	1 0.20 0.14	1 0.14	1 0.14						
TM								1 0.04 0.10	1 0.48 0.20			X				2								
ACA				1 0.07 0.10	0 0.08 0.11	2 0.68 0.10	2 0.68 0.24	2 0.32 0.21	2 0.40 0.15				X	c 0.00	c 0.00	2 0.46 0.10	3 0.53 0.11	0 0.05 0.09	3 1.00 0.00	1 0.26 0.25	2 0.20 0.25	2 0.20 0.25	3 1.00 0.00	
ILA				0 0.30 0.21		0 0.72 0.12	2 0.33 0.22	3 0.72 0.12	3 1.00 0.24	3 0.33 0.12	3 1.00 0.24	1 0.33 0.24	X 0.00	c 0.00	2 0.82 0.14	2 0.56 0.11	0 0.05 0.09	2 0.12 0.18	2 0.73 0.26	2 0.75 0.35	2 0.75 0.35	2 0.75 0.35		
PL				2 0.31 0.12		1 0.60 0.28	2 0.32 0.22	2 0.34 0.13	1 0.22	1 0.22	3 0.73 0.35	3 0.73 0.35	2 0.73 0.35	X 0.00	2 0.66 0.10	2 0.10 0.10	2 0.10 0.10	2 0.57 0.20	2 0.57 0.20	2 0.57 0.20	2 0.57 0.20	1 0.25 0.18	3 0.82 0.19	
PRh	c	0	0		c	2 0.68 0.10		c							2 0.48 0.17	X 0.14 0.10	1 0.14 0.10							
RSP				2 0.31 0.12	2 0.33 0.11	3 0.30 0.23	2 0.31 0.24	0 0.66 0.15	2 0.66 0.15				3 0.57 0.11	0 0.00 0.11	0 0.00 0.11	x 0.00 0.11	X 0.00 0.11	2 0.51 0.18	3 0.40 0.22	3 0.84 0.19	3 0.84 0.19	3 0.84 0.19		
AD	c	c		2 0.22 0.17	2 0.30 0.15	3 1.00 0.00	3 0.88 0.14						3 0.19 0.10	0 0.05 0.09	0 0.05 0.09	c 0.95 0.08	3 0.95 0.08	X						
AM		c		3 0.81 0.17	2 0.84 0.16	1 0.09 0.12	2 0.12						3 0.82 0.06	2 0.16 0.24	2 0.71 0.24	2 0.81 0.14	3 0.34 0.10		X					
AV	c	c		1 0.24 0.16	2 0.18 0.15	2 0.34 0.25	3 0.42 0.16	2 0.25 0.28					3 0.06 0.08	0 0.04 0.09	0 0.27 0.21	1 0.96 0.07	3 0.96 0.07			X				
IAM				2 0.24 0.15									2 0.79 0.08		3 0.94 0.09	2 0.82 0.16					X			
LD	c	c		1 0.22 0.16	3 0.81 0.19	3 0.33 0.24	3 0.42 0.16							3 0.55 0.10	2 0.68 0.25	3 0.62 0.14						X		
MD				3 0.95 0.08			0						3 1.00 0.00	3 0.84 0.24	3 0.84 0.14	1 0.35 0.24	1 0.04 0.07						X	

Table 5-4: Afferent connection weight matrix. Connection hierarchies are arranged vertically.

	CA1	CA3	DG	ENT	PAR	POST	PRE	SUB	LM	MM	SUM	TM	ACA	ILA	PL	PRh	RSP	AD	AM	AV	IAM	LD	MD
CA1	X			3	2	2	c	e					0										
				0.86	0.43	0.21		0.86								0.74	0.32	0.11					
				0.17	0.24	0.20		0.17								0.23	0.27	0.15					
CA3	3	X	c	1	1		c	c					0		0	0	x						
DG	c	c	X				c	c	c				0		0								
ENT	3		3	X	2	1	c	c	0	2			1		1	2	1						1
				0.71	0.84	0.38			0.16	0.77			0.34		0.41	0.76	0.36						0.38
				0.24	0.20	0.29			0.20	0.24			0.27		0.32	0.26	0.29						0.30
PAR	1	0	1	3	X	2	3	1	3	0	0		0				3	3		1		0	
	0.33	0.29	0.97		0.33	0.87	0.33		0.14								0.56	0.93		0.46		0.04	
	0.22	0.21	0.08		0.23	0.14	0.23		0.16								0.14	0.11		0.16		0.09	
POST				2	2	X	2		1				0			3	3	3		1		3	
				0.50		0.50		0.07								0.93	0.28	0.72		0.07		0.93	
				0.14		0.14		0.10								0.10	0.14	0.14		0.10		0.10	
PRE	0	0	1	3	3	2	X	2	3	2	0	0				0	2	2		2		3	
				0.15	0.92	0.66	0.48		0.48	0.70	0.06					0.15	0.32	0.48		0.66		0.92	
				0.14	0.10	0.10	0.10		0.10	0.25	0.10					0.14	0.12	0.10		0.10		0.10	
SUB	2	2	2	3	2	c	3	X	2	3	1	2	1	1	3	1	3		2	c	1		
	0.66	0.69	0.32	0.52	0.33		0.97		0.54	0.80	0.25	0.33	0.13	0.27	0.90	0.28	0.41		0.68		0.27		
	0.13	0.13	0.23	0.17	0.23		0.06		0.27	0.15	0.19	0.23	0.14	0.21	0.11	0.20	0.18		0.19		0.18		
LM									X									3	0				
MM										X						c		2	3	3	3	0	
																		1.00	0.00				
SUM	2	3	3	3	1	c	1	2	2	1	X				1	1	1						
	0.53	0.91	0.91	0.39	0.26		0.26	0.53	0.71	0.35					0.06								
	0.15	0.13	0.13	0.16	0.20		0.21	0.15	0.27	0.31					0.12								
TM									1	1		X				2							
ACA				1	0	2	2		2	2			X	c	c	2	3	0	3	1		2	3
				0.32	0.21	0.21	0.60									0.22	0.82	0.02	1.00	0.42		0.78	0.45
				0.22	0.16	0.16	0.08									0.07	0.04	0.06	0.00	0.08		0.07	0.28
ILA				0				0	2	3	3	3	1	X	c	2	2	0	2	2	2	2	
									0.12	0.30	0.21	1.00	0.21			0.79	0.20		0.78	0.78	0.79	0.81	
									0.16	0.18	0.20	0.00	0.20			0.18	0.18		0.18	0.18	0.17	0.17	
PL				2	2	1		2	2	1	1	3	2	X	2	2	2		2	2	2	1	3
				0.55		0.18		0.82	0.13	0.44	0.46	0.88	0.93			0.13	0.46		0.28	0.72	0.71	0.14	0.64
				0.13		0.16		0.18	0.14	0.30	0.29	0.14	0.11			0.15	0.20		0.15	0.17	0.17	0.15	0.23
PRh	c	0	0		c	2		c							2	X	1						
						0.75											0.25						
						0.35											0.35						
RSP				2	2	3	2	0	2				3	0	0	x	X	2	3	3		3	
				0.32	0.54	0.64	0.51	0.03	0.37				0.71					0.09	0.95	0.64		0.79	
				0.12	0.19	0.24	0.19	0.08	0.28				0.25					0.12	0.10	0.14		0.18	
AD	c	c		2	2	3	3				c		3	0	0	c	3	X					
				0.07	0.25	0.94	0.86						0.49		0.07		0.78						
				0.11	0.14	0.10	0.15						0.12		0.11		0.15						
AM		c		3	2	1	2						3	2	2	2	3		X				
				0.69	0.60		0.28	0.08					0.88	0.41		0.59							
				0.27	0.33		0.25	0.15					0.18	0.32		0.33							
AV	c	c		1	2	2	3	2			c		3	0	0	1	3			X			
				0.14	0.62	0.67	0.91	0.47					0.37		0.09	0.19	0.96						
				0.16	0.14	0.14	0.11	0.16					0.15		0.13	0.17	0.08						
IAM				2									2			3	2				X		
				0.00												1.00							
LD	c	c		1	3	3	3						3		2		3					X	
				0.00	0.46	0.93	0.46						0.40		0.88		0.44						
				0.00	0.21	0.11	0.21						0.18		0.15		0.20						
MD				3			0						3	3	3	1	1					X	
				0.83									0.86	0.73	0.40	0.07	0.19						
				0.18									0.16	0.25	0.15	0.12	0.21						

Table 5-5: Efferent connection weight matrix. Connection hierarchies are arranged horizontally.

These analyses demonstrate that my method of obtaining connection weight estimates from the literature, is not particularly feasible on larger but still relatively medium sized connection matrices. Some of the published studies describe connections between as many as 73 separate brain structures (Young 1993), and estimation the connection weights of such a large connection matrix is patently impossible at the present time, even if the data existed in a computationally tractable form.

5.6. Discussion.

This study concerned a number of brain structures which are often referred to as ‘the limbic system’. Kötter and Meyer (1992) suggested that this term has no empirical foundation, despite being commonly used (Kotter and Meyer 1992). They examined the use of the phrase in standard neuroscientific textbooks, as well as, the way in which it was used in the current literature, by examining the mode of its use in different articles that had included it as a keyword in the MEDLINE literature database. They also questioned authors concerning their use of this phrase, and their perception of which areas constituted the limbic system. They found not only that there was there a large amount of variability in the reported functional properties of the limbic system (“affects/emotions, memory, sensory processing, time perception, attention, consciousness, instincts, autonomic/vegetative control, actions/motor behaviour”), but also that all the interviewees reported different combinations of 60 different structures that had been presented as the limbic system’s constituents. There was however a general consensus concerning the involvement of the hippocampus and gyrus cinguli in the limbic system. In addition, there was a consensus that the limbic system was anatomically defined. Although Kotter and Meyer were primarily concerned with the limbic system in a medical context (that is, the human limbic

system), many of the texts referred to were concerned with studies of the rat, including Gray (1982).

The network of connections that I have analysed in this chapter could be considered to be part of the so-called 'limbic system' (Kandel *et al.* 1991; Lopes da Silva *et al.* 1990). They include many areas which are implicated in functional models such as those concerning spatial memory and navigation (O'Keefe and Nadel 1978; Buszaki *et al.* 1994; McNaughton *et al.* 1996; Redish and Touretzky 1997), anxiety (Gray 1982), and declarative memory (Eichenbaum *et al.* 1992). Most of the areas display functional properties other than those involved in spatial processing and include the hippocampus (Bunsey and Eichenbaum 1996).

This chapter is not aimed at describing the anatomical circuitry responsible for a specific behaviour or function. Rather, it is an examination of the global anatomical constraints of the system. Naturally, theoreticians already take anatomical constraints into account when designing their models, but they rarely use the anatomy as a starting point. Instead, the functional properties of the system are probed, and the anatomy is used, as a way of substantiating models of physiological or computational mechanisms. Unless the anatomy is considered objectively and comprehensively, there is a danger that only neuroanatomical information that conforms to the theory is used.

Redish and Touretzky's (1997) model is inspired by earlier theoretical work, and driven by neurophysiological and behavioural results (Touretzky and Redish 1996). Their organisational scheme does not incorporate every connection which I have described in this system (see their Figure 3). This may be a result of the way in which I have represented the labelling density of individual connection reports from tract-

tracing studies, and have incorporated every occurrence of reported labelling into my connection database. I would contend that Touretsky and Redish did not consider ‘anomalous’ connections in their organisation scheme. I cite four randomly selected examples which were omitted from their Figure 3: the efferent connections of SUM to the hippocampus (Haglund *et al.* 1984); the projection from PRE to LD (van Groen and Wyss 1990c); the projection from RSP to LD (Seki and Zyo 1984); and the projection from AM to ENT (Shibata 1993c).

The plan they present is similar in many ways to that described earlier in this chapter. For example, the hippocampus, the entorhinal cortex and the subiculum appear closely associated; the the postsubiculum, the presubiculum, the parasubiculum are associated with the anterior thalamic nuclei and the retrosplenial cortex. However, the role given to the mamillary bodies conflicts with that put forward in this thesis, since the only projections they consider are the mamillary bodies’ inputs from the subiculum. SUM, MM and LM possess other connections within this system (see Figure 5-1; Shibata 1992; Shibata 1989; Shibata 1988; Haglund *et al.* 1984).

It may be that this purely anatomical approach is of limited use from a functional point of view, since the fact that a connection exists does not mean that it is involved in a given function. Predictions of physiological phenomena at the system level from the analysis of neuroanatomical data have either been based on analysis of connectivity, (Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Young 1992; Young 1993). The end product of such analyses are clues to the trends of receptive-field characteristics and other possible physiological properties of the cells in the areas under study.

If enough is known about the physiological properties of a system, then the kinds of analysis described in this thesis can ‘fill in gaps’ to make predictions of physiological

properties in specific regions. Such a process allowed Scannell et al (1995) to predict plaid-pattern selective cells in the anterior ectosylvian sulcus of the cat cerebral cortex (Scannell *et al.* 1995; Scannell *et al.* 1996). The hippocampus and other parts of the limbic system in the rat have been extremely well studied, and a similar approach may be applied here. In order to be able to perform this type of deductive reasoning, it would be necessary to identify a neurophysiological property (such as visual stimuli for cells in the cat visual cortex) that varies in its characteristics across brain structures in the nuclei involved in the study.

The electrophysiological properties of place cells in the hippocampus (that is, cells that fire preferentially when the whole animal occupies a certain position in space), have been extensively studied over the last twenty-five years (O'Keefe and Dostrovsky 1971; Muller 1996). Cells that exhibit these and similar selective firing properties have been found in several parts of the rat brain, namely the CA3 and CA1 fields of the hippocampus (O'Keefe and Dostrovsky 1971; O'Keefe and Nadel 1978), the subiculum (Sharp and Green 1994; Sharp 1997), the entorhinal cortex (Quirk *et al.* 1992), and the parasubiculum (Taube 1995).

A second classification of neurophysiological properties discriminates a further type of cell in parts of the system I have studied in this chapter. These cells fire preferentially when the head of the animal is pointing in a specific direction. These are referred to as 'head direction' cells and can be found in the postsubiculum (Taube *et al.* 1990), anterodorsal nucleus of thalamus (Blair and Sharp 1995, Taube 1995), laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (Mizumori and Williams 1993), and the posterior parietal (also referred to as the anterior part of the medial extrastriate cortex) and retrosplenial cortices (Chen *et al.* 1994).

This distribution of electrophysiological properties across limbic structures is consistent with the classification of brain structures presented here. One of the cluster-count sets that was quite clearly delineated in the analyses contained in this chapter, was comprised of CA1, CA3 DG, SUM, SUB, and ENT. Four of these are structures that contain place cells.

The closest neighbouring sets which occasionally overlap with this set contain AD, POST, PRE and LD, which have all been reported to contain head-direction cells. This separation between clusters is not complete, since single units have been recorded in the parasubiculum which correspond to the spatial position of the animal, rather than the direction in which it faces (Taube 1995). In the two-dimensional NMDS plots shown earlier in the chapter, PAR lies closer to the structures in the set containing the hippocampus than the other parts of the second set.

Studies which have attempted to find either head-direction or place cells in the prelimbic cortex of the rat, report a null result, even though PL receives a direct connection from CA1 (Poucet 1997). In the analyses of this chapter, PL was consistently in a different cluster from CA1. This shows that the analysis of neuroanatomical connection data described in this chapter is in agreement with neurophysiological data, although at quite a crude level of description.

If physiological properties are consistent with these analyses, then the method may have predictive power. In the Venn diagrams of this chapter, SUM appears in the same set as several other brain areas which contain place cells, possibly suggesting that SUM may contain place cells. Applying the same logic to another part of the system may suggest that ACA and AV might contain head-direction cells.

The apparently tenuous causal link between neuroanatomy and neurophysiology becomes more concrete as you descend into more-detailed descriptions of the tissue. A model proposed by Bernard and Wheal (1994) incorporates both highly-descriptive neuroanatomical and neurophysiological data in order to describe interactions between the CA3 and CA1 region in a slice preparation (Bernard and Wheal 1994). The importance of incorporating more-detailed aspects of neuroanatomy which go beyond the constraints of the 'grey box' model will be considered in the next chapter.

Chapter 6

General Discussion

6. General Discussion

6.1. Summary.

My D.Phil. research has produced several new methods which have advanced the field of the mathematical analysis of neuroanatomical connection data.

Firstly, I have designed a large-scale, open-ended literature databasing system, called 'Neurobase', which can be applied to collating neuroanatomical literature in any species. This database effectively solves one of the problems facing studies of connectivity which are based on data from the literature, as any global treatment of connectivity would have to be. All previous studies have been based on compilations of connection reports from neuroanatomical papers without explicitly describing the experiments that produced them. This included the most influential papers in the field when I started this project (Felleman and Van Essen 1991; Young 1992). Neurobase contains abbreviated versions of the experimenters' own descriptions of the original data. The database's design can be expanded to accommodate changes in nomenclature and neuroanatomical parcellation of the areas.

Secondly, I have devised a method of calculating probabilistic ordinal connection weight estimates for large-scale networks of brain areas. This was achieved by making a large number of restricted comparisons between subsections of the database, and then cross-referencing them with a powerful computational classifier.

Thirdly, I have developed new methods for analysing neuroanatomical connection data with nonmetric multidimensional scaling (NMDS). NMDS illustrates the organisation of neural systems by characterising different brain areas as points in a mathematically defined coordinate space. The proximity between points represents the similarity between the brain structures' connectivity patterns. I have devised and

applied a mathematical transform of proximity data that reduces the effects of connectional sparsity in NMDS configurations by finding the shortest pathways between nonadjacent data points (Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b).

Lastly, I have extended the use of proximity-based representations of neural connectivity by using cluster analysis to interpret multidimensional data. Previous studies have presented descriptions of neuroanatomical organisation as two-dimensional configurations of points, and the deduction of the organisation of the system was accomplished by eye, or by Procrustes rotation of other models (Young 1992; Young *et al.* 1995b). I have examined how high-dimensional configurations become distorted when they are fitted into a small number of dimensions by NMDS, and how NMDS studies may be combined with nonparametric cluster analysis to interpret configurations in more than three dimensions.

An immense amount of connection data exists in the literature. At present, Neurobase contains over 10,000 separate connection reports taken from over 1000 papers, and represents a valuable data resource in its own right. These data describe in detail only a limited subset of the whole literature, but they do provide a coarse description of connectivity over the whole rat brain.

I have studied the connectivity of the putative visual and limbic systems of the rat in detail; and compiled an extensive description of the literature concerning the connectivity of these systems. I then analysed the connectivity of each system with the methods described above. I have applied a rigorous approach to the neuroanatomical connectivity of efferents of the retina in order to investigate the connectional organisation of the rat's visual system. The results produced by these

analyses appear to be in accordance with known physiological properties of the systems described.

The connectional organisation of the early visual system in the rat is divided into three large-scale groups: the hypothalamic areas associated with the suprachiasmatic nucleus, the accessory optic nuclei and other structures involved in optovestibular processing, and the parts of the visual brainstem, thalamus and cortex which are involved in vision. This latter set appears to have some degree of interpretable substructure: visual brainstem structures such as the superior colliculus and pretectal nuclei, lie between the retina and the visual cortex, which is heavily associated with the lateral thalamic nuclei (the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus and the lateral posterior nucleus), in a position that is distant from the retina.

Two of the groups defined by the analysis of connections in the hippocampus correspond to areas containing cells which fire selectively when the rat is located in a specific position (so called 'place cells') and a neighbouring set of brain areas and nuclei include areas containing cells which fire selectively when the rat faces in a particular direction (so-called 'head direction cells'). I have predicted where these physiological features might be found elsewhere, on the basis of my analyses of connectivity.

6.2. What can be deduced from these studies?

The principal implication of this work is that, despite its obvious simplifications, analyses based on the 'grey box' model of neuroanatomical connectivity can be informative in revealing the organisation of any neural system where a parcellation scheme has been defined, and the major connections between structures have been described. These studies have implications for the way in which neural systems can

be defined on the basis of their connectivity; the importance and use of quantitative connection strengths, and the way in which structure and function are related.

6.2.1. The definition of neural systems.

A system can be mathematically defined as a set of brain structures that are more connected with each other than with structures that are outside the set and more disconnected outside the set than within (M. P. Young, Personal Communication). The analysis of Chapter 4 is consistent with this, since the descriptions of parts of the visual system in the rat are most clearly elucidated by nonparametric cluster analysis of NMDS configurations derived from the network of connections between all structures studied.

If this is the case, then patterns of connections across the whole brain should be considered when defining neural systems. Some structures, in particular the cerebral cortex, are thought to have elevated ethological importance in animals such as humans and monkeys (Shepherd 1994), although there is no *a priori* reason why the neurons of the cerebral cortex should be considered in a separate context from the many subcortical cells with which they share interconnections. The prominence of the cerebral cortex in cats and monkeys explains why previous studies of connectivity mainly considered corticocortical connections (Young 1992; Young 1993; Scannell *et al.* 1995; Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b). However, a more general treatment of connectional data is currently being applied to monkey, cat and rat connectional data (Hilgetag *et al.* 1996a; Scannell, J. W., Personal Communication).

Any study of connectivity faces an obvious and immediate obstacle: published neuroanatomical data is presented as written prose, combined with occasional *camera lucida* drawings of the distribution of tracer labelling or histological photographs. The

first stage of every project of this type is to read and interpret the published papers and convert the data into a format that can be analysed. Not only is this process time-consuming, it suffers from the lack of a unified nomenclature, and cannot be truly objective since it is based on the data collator's subjective interpretations of written papers.

In order for mathematical analysis of connectivity to exploit its full potential, there is a need for the existing connectional data to be placed into a single database. This database would need a unified nomenclature, or at least a nomenclature where the various synonyms and abbreviations which are commonly used in the study of different areas are explained. For an example of this, see the index of Swanson (1993) where the previous nomenclatures have been referred to the corresponding region in the atlas. Given a database of this scope, it would then be possible to describe the organisation of the whole brain in a single representation. Such a description would provide an insight into the global organisation of the brain that could not be derived from piecemeal descriptions of the system. Neurobase is a prototype for such a database.

6.2.2. The need for quantitative data.

In order to remove the problems inherent in basing analyses on subjective interpretations of qualitative data, connection strength should ideally be measured quantitatively. In order to obtain accurate measurements of connection strength, a quantitative description of the brain region in question must first be made. For example, Equations 1-1 and 1-2 are absolute counts of projection neurons. It is difficult to conceive how one could calculate or measure this variable without some sort of quantitative estimation of the total number of neurons in the area, the relative density of projection neurons to interneurons, and so on (Abeles 1991).

Previous theoretical models of specific systems have represented these systems in an idealised geometrical form as two-dimensional sheets, where the number of neurons in given areas is estimated (*e.g.* Patton and McNaughton 1995). This is an essential simplification, given the way in which neuroanatomical data is reported, since the three-dimensional structure is usually represented as a series of two-dimensional sections. Reconstructing this three-dimensional structure requires mathematical manipulation and a more sophisticated representation of the three-dimensional structure of the brain than is commonly available.

The number of quantitative papers within the connectivity literature of the rat visual and limbic systems is relatively small (for example, Sanderson *et al.* 1991) although the rat hippocampus has been very well described (see Bernard and Wheal 1994; Patton and McNaughton 1995 for reviews). Global studies such as this one, require that this kind of quantitative data be comparable with conventional ordinal descriptions of connection strength.

The method of calculating connection weight estimates can use qualitative differences in labelling density to estimate ordinal characteristics of the strength of connections (see Section 2.2.2), but this is computationally intensive and cannot yet be used on even medium-sized connection matrices (see Chapter 5). Although this analysis can only produce probabilistic ordinal connection weights, it is an objective method that can be applied to both quantitative and ordinal data.

Analyses such as this could be used to incorporate quantitative and qualitative neuroanatomical connection data into a single representation. Eventually, the global database described above would need to represent the geometry of tissue in a statistically realistic way, in order to make the model as realistic as possible. Some

issues underlying this kind of neuroanatomical representation are considered later in this chapter.

NMDS studies can reconstruct test configurations very accurately even when the input data has been degraded to the same level of measurement as the neuroanatomical connection data (Young *et al.* 1995a; Young *et al.* 1995b). In these studies, random noise was added to the dissimilarities to simulate measurement error, which may alternatively be thought of as simulating the non-Euclidean characteristics of the data. As a cautionary note, the type of noise (Gaussian, uniform, *etc.*) used in this kind of NMDS Monte Carlo reconstruction study, can affect the stress of reconstructed configurations (Cox and Cox 1990; Cox and Cox 1992; Cox and Cox 1995) and so the appropriate level of noise to be added would depend on the choice of noise type.

The output configurations produced have high Procrustes R^2 values (>0.95) when compared with the original configurations. This suggests that the non-Euclidean characteristics of the input data are relatively insignificant in analyses at this level of measurement, and that quantitative connection weights are not required to be able to capture the essential features of the connectional organisation of neural systems in NMDS representations.

This interpretation is based upon the assumption that the configuration generated in an analysis with ratio-level connection data would be Euclidean. There is no *a priori* reason why a ratio-level connection matrix should either be Euclidean (where the connection matrix must be positive semi definite), or even metric (where it must satisfy the triangle inequality). A measure of the 'Euclidean-ness' of a set of ratio data is required. The stress of an NMDS solution has been described as the a measure of

the ‘Euclidean-ness’ of a set of ordinal data (Sibson *et al.* 1981), but it is affected by dimensionality, number of points, measurement error, as well as non-Euclidean characteristics.

In order to confirm how well NMDS can recapture the data structure of a generalised connection matrix, it may be more appropriate to test the ability of NMDS to reconstruct random ratio-level connection matrices from low level data, and employ a method other than Procrustes rotations to compare the distances of the output configuration with the connection matrix entries. In Chapter 1, I described how the proximity model has several drawbacks that become evident when the data in question become more quantitative. It is likely that that the non-Euclidean properties of connection matrices will become more influential when the data is defined at a higher level of measurement. It is impossible to estimate whether a representation based on connection strength could be accurately represented in a Euclidean model in the absence of quantitative data. Thus, although the proximity model adequately describes the structure of Euclidean test data when degraded to the same level of measurement as neural connectivity data, this does not detract from the likely importance of quantitative data in studies of connectivity.

6.2.3. The relationship between structure and function

It is likely that this purely anatomical description omits details which can only be elucidated by physiologically defined variables, such as ‘functional connectivity’ (Finnerty and Jefferys 1993). As a general rule, physiological descriptions of the importance of a given connection are far more complex than their anatomical counterparts. I would claim that a quantitative description of the structural constraints of a neural projection system are vital prerequisites for a realistic modelling study of the physiology of that same system. However, neuroanatomical connection data can

only describe the general organisation of the system and must be used in conjunction with physiological data to describe functional characteristics of the components of neural systems. For example, NMDS analysis has been used with physiological data to predict physiological properties of neurons in the anterior ectosylvian sulcus in cats (Scannell *et al.* 1996).

6.3. *Future ideas: A unified mathematical framework for neuroanatomical, neurophysiological and connectional data .*

Models of neural systems which are based on quantitative descriptions of the connections between brain areas are rare (but see Bernard and Wheal 1994; Patton and McNaughton 1995). This is due to the scarcity of quantitative data which exists outside of well-studied systems such as the hippocampus. Part of the reason why systems such as the hippocampus have attracted attention as possible candidates for a modelling approach, is the regularity of its neuroanatomical structure. This section is concerned with the development of a computational framework that would be capable of studying connectivity without the simplifications imposed by the 'grey box' model.

This framework is currently under development as part of the structure of three-dimensional brain atlases, which could be linked to databases containing anatomical information and physiological data (Roland and Zilles 1994; L Swanson, Personal Communication). The coregistration of different datasets into three-dimensional atlases would be based on the assumption that reproducible internal landmarks, such as the physiologically- or cytoarchitectonically-defined borders between areas, could be regarded as stationary surfaces which are equivalent.

The importance of brain atlases was discussed in Chapter 1. These are two-dimensional representations of histological sections in which the borders of nuclei

and areas are drawn as lines. In computerised atlases, this structure can be represented as a three-dimensional spatial template upon which anatomical and physiological properties can be mapped. Such anatomical properties include cell density, (measured by grey level index calculated from Nissl stained sections; Geyer *et al.* 1996), the distribution of types of receptor, (measured by quantitative autoradiography; Roland and Zilles 1994), or any other suitably quantitative anatomical variable. The range of physiological variables that can be measured in neural tissue is very large, but two broad classes of experiment will be mentioned here. One physiological variable can be described by the stimuli that evoke electrophysiological activity in the cells in a given region of brain tissue (for example, the receptive fields of visually responsive neurons in the extrastriate cortex; Espinoza and Thomas 1983). A second can be described by the spontaneous electrophysiological activity of neurons in a certain region when the animal is in a specific physiological state, such as anaesthetised, sleeping or exploring (McNaughton 1980). Mathematically, neuroanatomical properties can be represented as scalar fields, and the spatial distribution of the firing properties of neurons as multidimensional vector fields (See Obermayer *et al.* 1992 for an example).

The geometry of every individual's brain is different. Consequently, these spatially-distributed variables ought to be mapped onto a suitable template with mathematical transformations. This problem is likely to be mathematically nontrivial, and would probably require that certain points be considered homologous between brains ('stationary points'). Morphometric studies of brain images are defined on the basis of gross morphology (Bookstein 1996), but these may not always be considered reliable as stationary points: Van Essen (1985) reported that the positions of cytoarchitecturally-defined borders can vary by several millimetres relative to

morphological landmarks between individuals (Van Essen 1985). Other internal landmarks such as physiologically-defined borders, histological landmarks or specific connectivity patterns may be more appropriate for this purpose. Physiological landmarks are often used by experimental researchers to navigate in brain tissue (McNaughton 1980; R. Mason, Personal Communication).

The spatial distribution of physiological properties can be very complicated. For example, the apparent regularity of the cytoarchitecture of the primate primary visual cortex obscures the complexity of physiological maps of orientation-preference and ocular-dominance (Blasdel 1992). The two-dimensional spatial distribution of these properties across the surface of the cortex contains a variety of complex spatial patterns, such as regions of linear change, singularities, saddle points, and fractures (Obermayer and Blasdel 1993). A curvilinear map of these properties would have a complicated swirling organisation that is unlike any neuroanatomical property which is currently measurable. The visuotopic representation of the visual field has a similar distorted appearance (Das and Gilbert 1997). The presence of cells encoding other information, such as colour, suggest that many maps are superimposed over the same tissue (Ts'o and Gilbert 1988). These maps are complex, and are likely to differ between individuals. They are also likely to vary with time if they are affected by processes involving neural plasticity.

The link between structure and function is a fundamental principle in neuroscience (Duus 1989). Complex neurophysiological properties are almost certainly caused in part by the interactions between neurons, defined by their connections. An accurate description of connectivity in a computational framework would require a volumetric estimation of the size of the dendritic and terminal arbours of different cell types,

based on morphological and tract-tracing studies (Abeles 1991), and quantitative descriptions of synaptic density (Braitenburg and Schuz 1991). The interactions of neurons clearly occur via chemical synapses, but they may also occur by other mechanisms which studies of connectivity ignore, such as through gap junctions in dendrites (Peinado *et al.* 1993) or other as yet undiscovered, methods of electrical or chemical coupling which could involve information transfer between neurons.

A representation of this organisation may seem impossible due to the staggeringly large number of individual cells and synapses (Young *et al.* 1995a), but without this, the task of understanding the causal processes that give rise to the functional properties of neural systems will never be understood to a level that would allow the brain to be modelled realistically. In fact, the existence of the aforementioned quantitative descriptions of connectivity in the rat hippocampus, suggest that such an objective may not be as far-fetched as previously thought (Bernard and Wheal 1994; Patton and McNaughton 1995).

In order for this long term goal to be realised, much technological and theoretical progress is needed: a spatial representation of the morphology of brain tissue that can accommodate interindividual variability (Roland and Zilles 1994); methodological advances to aid the acquisition of quantitative neuroanatomical data (Warren 1992); and computational advances to assimilate large amounts of spatially-mapped anatomical and physiological data into a single unified framework. In neuroscience, many different methodologies and approaches are used to study a single object: the brain. At some stage, it may be feasible and rewarding to synthesise the data from these different disciplines into the single representation I have described. Within this

representation, the structure of the brain's anatomical circuitry will have an important part to play.

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Appendix A : Parcellation Scheme.

Each area is listed, with its abbreviation and tree (See Section 2.1.1). This table was adapted from Table A of Swanson (1993): 'Basic Cell Groups of the Rat Brain'.

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
AAA	.FB.AMY.AAA.	Anterior Amygdaloid Area
ACA	.FB.ISO.ACA.	Anterior Cingulate Area
ACAd	.FB.ISO.ACA.ACAd.	Anterior Cingulate Area, dorsal part
ACAv	.FB.ISO.ACA.ACAv.	Anterior Cingulate Area, ventral part
ACB	.FB.CSTR.STR.ACB.	Nucleus Accumbens
ACVI	.BS.MOTBS.Eye.VI.ACVI.	Accessory Abducens Nucleus
ACVII	.BS.MOTBS.Face.VII.ACVII.	Accessory Facial Nucleus
AD	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.AD.	Anterodorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus
ADP	.FB.HY.MEZ.ADP.	Anterodorsal Preoptic Nucleus
AHA	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.	Anterior Hypothalamic Area
AHN	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.AHN.	Anterior Hypothalamic Nucleus
AHNa	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.AHN.AHNa.	Anterior Hypothalamic Nucleus, anterior part
AHNc	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.AHN.AHNc.	Anterior Hypothalamic Nucleus, central part
AHNd	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.AHN.AHNd.	Anterior Hypothalamic Nucleus, dorsal part
AHNp	.FB.HY.MEZ.AHA.AHN.AHNp.	Anterior Hypothalamic Nucleus, posterior part
AI	.FB.ISO.INS.AI.	Agranular Insular area
AId	.FB.ISO.INS.AId.	Agranular Insular area, dorsal part
AIp	.FB.ISO.INS.AI.AIp.	Agranular Insular area, posterior part
AIv	.FB.ISO.INS.AI.AIv.	Agranular Insular area, ventral part
AM	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.AM.	Anteromedial Nucleus of the Thalamus
AMBd	.BS.MOTBS.PhLa.AMBd.	Nucleus Ambiguus, dorsal division
AMBv	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.AMBv.	Nucleus Ambiguus, ventral division
AMY	.FB.AMY.	Amygdala
AN	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.AN.	Ansiform Lobule
AOB	.FB.OLF.AOB.	Accessory Olfactory Bulb
AON	.FB.OLF.AON.	Anterior Olfactory Nucleus
AOS	.BS.SENS.VISBS.AOS.	Accessory Optic System
AP	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.AP.	Area Postrema
APN	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.APN.	Anterior Pretectal Nucleus
ARH	.FB.HY.PVZ.ARH.	Arcuate Nucleus of the Hypothalamus
ASO	.FB.HY.PVZ.SO.ASO.	Supraoptic Nucleus, Accessory Supraoptic group
AT	.BS.RETIC.CGB.AT.	Anterior Tegmental Nucleus
ATN	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.	Anterior Group of the Dorsal Thalamus
AUD	.FB.ISO.AUD.	Auditory Cortical Areas
AUDb	.FB.ISO.AUD.AUDb.	Auditory Belt Cortex
AUDBS	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.	Auditory Sensory Brainstem
AUDd	.FB.ISO.AUD.AUDb.AUDd.	Ventral Auditory belt Cortex
AUDp	.FB.ISO.AUD.AUDp.	Primary Auditory Cortex
AUDv	.FB.ISO.AUD.AUDb.AUDv.	Dorsal Auditory belt Cortex
AV	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.AV.	Anteroventral Nucleus of the Thalamus
AVP	.FB.HY.MEZ.AVP.	Anteroventral Preoptic Nucleus
AVPV	.FB.HY.PVZ.AVPV.	Anteroventral Periventricular Hypothalamic Nucleus
B	.BS.RETIC.CGB.B.	Barrington's Nucleus
BA	.FB.AMY.BA.	Bed Nucleus of the Accessory Olfactory Tract
BAC	.FB.SEP.BAC.	Bed Nucleus of the Anterior Commissure
BLA	.FB.AMY.BLA.	Basolateral Nucleus of the Amygdala
BMA	.FB.AMY.BMA.	Basomedial Nucleus of the Amygdala
BS	.BS.	Brainstem
BST	.FB.SEP.BST.	Bed Nucleus of the Stria Terminalis
CA	.FB.HPF.HIP.CA.	Ammon's Horn
CA1	.FB.HPF.HIP.CA.CA1.	Ammon's Horn, field CA1
CA2	.FB.HPF.HIP.CA.CA2.	Ammon's Horn, field CA2
CA3	.FB.HPF.HIP.CA.CA3.	Ammon's Horn, field CA3
CB	.BS.CB.	Cerebellum
CBX	.BS.CB.CBX.	Cerebellar Cortex
CEA	.FB.AMY.CEA.	Central Nucleus of the Amygdala
CENT	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.CENT.	Central Lobule
CGB	.BS.RETIC.CGB.	Central Grey of the brain
CL	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.CL.	Central Lateral Nucleus of the Thalamus
CLA	.FB.ISO.CLA.	Clastrum
CLI	.BS.RETIC.RA.CLI.	Central Linear Raphe Nucleus

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
CM	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.CM.	Central Medial Nucleus of the Thalamus
CN	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.CN.	Cochlear Nuclei
COA	.FB.AMY.COA.	Cortical Nucleus of the Amygdala
COPY	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.COPY.	Copula Pyramidis
CP	.FB.CSTR.STR.CP.	Caudoputamen
CS	.BS.RETIC.RA.CS.	Superior Central Raphe Nucleus
CSTR	.FB.CSTR.	Corpus Striatum
CU	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.CU.	Cuneate Nucleus
CUL	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.CUL.	Culmen
CUN	.BS.RETIC.RET.CUN.	Cunieforn Nucleus
DCN	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.	Dorsal Column Nuclei
DCO	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.CN.DCO.	Dorsal Cochlear Nucleus
DEC	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.DEC.	Declive (VI)
DG	.FB.HPF.HIP.DG.	Dentate Gyrus
DMH	.FB.HY.MEZ.TUA.DMH.	Dorsomedial Nucleus of the Hypothalamus
DMX	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.DMX.	Dorsal Motor Nucleus of the Vagus Nerve
DN	.BS.CB.DNC.DN.	Dentate Nucleus
DNC	.BS.CB.DNC.	Deep Cerebellar Nuclei
DOR	.FB.TH.DOR.	Dorsal Thalamus
DPC	.FB.ISO.ILA.DPC.	Dorsal Peduncular Cortex
DR	.BS.RETIC.RA.DR.	Dorsal Raphe Nucleus
DT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.AOS.DT.	Dorsal Terminal of the Accessory Optic Tract
DTN	.BS.RETIC.CGB.DTN.	Dorsal Tegmental Nucleus
ECO	.BS.MOTBS.Laby.ECO.	Efferent Cochlear Group
ECT	.FB.ISO.PRh.ECT.	Ectorhinal Area
ECU	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.ECU.	External Cuneate Nucleus
ENT	.FB.HPF.RHP.ENT.	Entorhinal Area
ENTl	.FB.HPF.RHP.ENT.ENTl.	Entorhinal Area, lateral part
ENTm	.FB.HPF.RHP.ENT.ENTm.	Entorhinal Area, medial part, dorsal zone
EP	.FB.OLF.EP.	Endopiriform Nucleus
EPI	.FB.TH.EPI.	Epithalamus
EV	.BS.MOTBS.Laby.EV.	Efferent Vestibular Nucleus
EW	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.EW.	Edinger-Westphal Nucleus
ExPyr	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.	Extrapyramidal Motor Brainstem Nuclei
Eye	.BS.MOTBS.Eye.	Eye Motor Brainstem Nuclei
Face	.BS.MOTBS.Face.	Face Motor Brainstem Nuclei
FB	.FB.	Forebrain
FC	.FB.HPF.HIP.FC.	Fasciola Cinera
FF	.FB.TH.VNT.ZI.FF.	Fields of Forel
FL	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.FL.	Flocculus
FN	.BS.CB.DNC.FN.	Fastigial Nucleus
FOTU	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.FOTU.	Folium-Tuber Vermis (VII)
FS	.FB.CSTR.STR.FS.	Fundus of the Striatum
GEN	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.	Geniculate group of the Dorsal Thalamus
GP	.FB.CSTR.PAL.GP.	Globus Pallidus
GPI	.FB.CSTR.PAL.GP.GPI.	Globus Pallidus, lateral segment
GPm	.FB.CSTR.PAL.GP.GPm.	Globus Pallidus, medial segment
GR	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.GR.	Gracile Nucleus
GRN	.BS.RETIC.RET.GRN.	Gigantocellular Reticular Nucleus
GU	.FB.ISO.INS.GU.	Gustatory area
GUSBS	.BS.SENS.GUSBS.	Gustatory Sensory Brainstem
GV	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.GV.	Trigeminal Ganglion
HEM	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.	Hemispheric Region
HIP	.FB.HPF.HIP.	Hippocampal Region
HPF	.FB.HPF.	Hippocampal Formation
HY	.FB.HY.	Hypothalamus
IA	.FB.AMY.IA.	Intercalated Nuclei of the Amygdala
IAD	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.IAD.	Interanterodorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus
IAM	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.IAM.	Interoanteromedial Nucleus of the Thalamus
IAN	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.CN.IAN.	Interstitial Nucleus of the Auditory Nucleus
IC	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.IC.	Inferior Colliculus
ICB	.BS.SENS.VESBS.ICB.	Infracerbellar Nucleus
ICc	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.IC.ICc.	Inferior Colliculus, Central Nucleus
ICd	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.IC.ICd.	Inferior Colliculus, Dorsal Nucleus
ICe	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.IC.ICe.	Inferior Colliculus, External Nucleus
IF	.BS.RETIC.RA.IF.	Interfascicular Raphe Nucleus
IG	.FB.HPF.HIP.IG.	Induseum Griseum
IGL	.FB.TH.VNT.LG.IGL.	Intergeniculate Leaflet of the Lateral Geniculate Complex
III	.BS.MOTBS.Eye.III.	Oculomotor Nucleus
ILA	.FB.ISO.ILA.	Infralimbic Area
ILC	.FB.ISO.ILA.ILC.	InfraLimbic Cortex
ILM	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.	Intralaminar Nuclei of the Thalamus

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
IMA	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.IMA.	Intermedullary Area
IMD	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.MD.IMD.	Interomedial Nucleus of the Thalamus
INC	.BS.RETIC.CGB.INC.	Interstitial Nucleus of Cajal
INS	.FB.ISO.INS.	Insular Cortex
INV	.BS.SENS.VESBS.INV.	Interstitial Nucleus of the Vestibular Nerve
IO	.BS.PrCB.IO.	Inferior Olivary Complex
IP	.BS.CB.DNC.IP.	Interposed Nucleus
IPN	.BS.RETIC.IPN.	Interpeduncular Nucleus
ISN	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.ISN.	Inferior Salivatory Nucleus
ISO	.FB.ISO.	Isocortex
IV	.BS.MOTBS.Eye.IV.	Trochlear Nucleus
Jaw	.BS.MOTBS.Jaw.	Jaw Motor Brainstem Nuclei
KF	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.PB.KF.	Parabrachial Nucleus, Kolliker-Fuse Subnucleus
LA	.FB.AMY.LA.	Lateral Nucleus of the Amygdala
Laby	.BS.MOTBS.Laby.	Labyrinth Motor Brainstem Nuclei
LAT	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.	Lateral Group of the dorsal Thalamus
LAV	.BS.SENS.VESBS.VNC.LAV.	Lateral Vestibular Nucleus
LC	.BS.RETIC.CGB.LC.	Locus Coeruleus
LCN	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.LCN.	Lateral Cervical Nucleus
LD	.FB.TH.DOR.ATN.LD.	Lateral Dorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus
LDT	.BS.RETIC.CGB.LDT.	Laterodorsal Tegmental Nucleus
LG	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.LG.	Lateral Geniculate Complex
LG	.FB.TH.VNT.LG.	Lateral Geniculate Complex
LGd	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.LG.LGd.	Lateral Geniculate Complex, dorsal part
LGv	.FB.TH.VNT.LG.LGv.	Ventral Part of the Lateral Geniculate Complex
LGvl	.FB.TH.VNT.LG.LGv.LGvl.	Ventral Part of the Lateral Geniculate Complex, lateral zone
LGvm	.FB.TH.VNT.LG.LGv.LGvm.	Ventral Part of the Lateral Geniculate Complex, medial zone
LH	.FB.TH.EPI.LH.	Lateral Habenula
LHA	.FB.HY.LZ.LHA.	Lateral Hypothalamic Area
LIN	.BS.PrCB.LIN.	Linear Nucleus of the Medulla
LING	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.LING.	Lingula
LM	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.LM.	Lateral Mammillary Nucleus
LP	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.LP.	Lateral Posterior Nucleus of the Thalamus
LPO	.FB.HY.LZ.LPO.	Lateral Preoptic Area
LRN	.BS.PrCB.LRN.	Lateral Reticular Nucleus
LS	.FB.SEP.LS.	Lateral Septal Nucleus
LSd	.FB.SEP.LS.LSd.	Lateral Septal Nucleus, dorsal part
LSi	.FB.SEP.LS.LSi.	Lateral Septal Nucleus, intermediate part
LSv	.FB.SEP.LS.LSv.	Lateral Septal Nucleus, ventral part
LT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.AOS.LT.	Lateral Terminal of the Accessory Optic Tract
LZ	.FB.HY.LZ.	Lateral Zone of the Hypothalamus
MA	.FB.CSTR.PAL.SI.MA.	Magnocellular Preoptic Nucleus
MARN	.BS.RETIC.RET.MARN.	Magnocellular Reticular Nucleus
MBO	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.	Mammillary Body
MD	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.MD.	Mediodorsal Dorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus
MDc	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.MD.MDc.	Mediodorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus, central part
MDl	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.MD.MDl.	Mediodorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus, lateral part
MDm	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.MD.MDm.	Mediodorsal Nucleus of the Thalamus, medial part
MDRN	.BS.RETIC.RET.MDRN.	Medullary Reticular Nucleus
ME	.FB.HY.PVZ.ME.	Median Eminence
MEA	.FB.AMY.MEA.	Medial Nucleus of the amygdala
MED	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.	Medial Group of the Dorsal Thalamus
MEDUL	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.	Medullary Nuclei
MEPO	.FB.HY.PVZ.MEPO.	Median Preoptic Nucleus
MEV	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.MEV.	Mesencephalic Nucleus of the Trigeminal
MEZ	.FB.HY.MEZ.	Medial Zone of the Hypothalamus
MG	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.MG.	Medial Geniculate Complex
MGd	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.MG.MGd.	Medial Geniculate Complex, dorsal part
MGm	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.MG.MGm.	Medial Geniculate Complex, medial part
MGv	.FB.TH.DOR.GEN.MG.MGv.	Medial Geniculate Complex, ventral part
MH	.FB.TH.EPI.MH.	Medial Habenula
MID	.FB.TH.DOR.MID.	Midline Group of the Dorsal Thalamus
MM	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.MM.	Medial Mammillary Nucleus
MO	.FB.ISO.MO.	Motor Areas
MOB	.FB.OLF.MOB.	Main Olfactory Bulb
MOp	.FB.ISO.MO.MOp.	Primary Motor Area
MOs	.FB.ISO.MO.MOs.	Secondary Motor Areas
MOTBS	.BS.MOTBS.	Motor Brainstem
MPN	.FB.HY.MEZ.MPO.MPN.	Medial Preoptic Nucleus
MPO	.FB.HY.MEZ.MPO.	Medial Preoptic Area
MPT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.MPT.	Medial Pretectal Area
MRN	.BS.RETIC.RET.MRN.	Mesencephalic Reticular Nucleus

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
MS	.FB.SEP.MSC.MS.	Medial Septal Nucleus
MSC	.FB.SEP.MSC.	Medial Septal Complex
MT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.AOS.MT.	Medial Terminal of the Accessory Optic Tract
MV	.BS.SENS.VESBS.VNC.MV.	Medial Vestibular Nucleus
NB	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.NB.	Nucleus of the Brachium of the Inferior colliculus
ND	.BS.RETIC.CGB.ND.	Nucleus of Darkschewitsch
NDB	.FB.SEP.MSC.NDB.	Nucleus of the Diagonal Band
NDB-h	.FB.SEP.MSC.NDB.NDB-h.	Nucleus of the Diagonal Band, horizontal limb
NDB-v	.FB.SEP.MSC.NDB.NDB-v.	Nucleus of the Diagonal Band, vertical limb
Neck	.BS.MOTBS.Neck.	Neck Motor Brainstem Nuclei
NI	.BS.RETIC.RA.NI.	Nucleus Incertus
NIS	.BS.SENS.VESBS.PHY.NIS.	Nucleus Intercalatus
NLL	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.NLL.	Nucleus of the Lateral Lemniscus
NLOT	.FB.AMY.NLOT.	Nucleus of the lateral olfactory tract
NOD	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.NOD.	Nodulus (X)
NOT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.NOT.	Nucleus of the Optic Tract
NPC	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.NPC.	Nucleus of the Posterior Commissure
NR	.BS.SENS.VESBS.PHY.NR.	Nucleus of Roller
NTB	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.NTB.	Nucleus of the Trapezoid Body
NTS	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.NTS.	Nucleus of the Solitary Tract
NTSm-r	.BS.SENS.GUSBS.NTSm-r.	Nucleus of the Solitary Tract, rostral zone of medial part
OLF	.FB.OLF.	Olfactory Cortex
OP	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.OP.	Olivary Pretectal Nucleus
ORB	.FB.ISO.ORB.	Orbital Area
ORB1	.FB.ISO.ORB.ORB1.	Orbital Area, lateral part
ORBm	.FB.ISO.ORB.ORBm.	Orbital Area, medial part
ORBv	.FB.ISO.ORB.ORBv.	Orbital Area, ventral part
ORBvl	.FB.ISO.ORB.ORBvl.	Orbital Area, ventrolateral part
OT	.FB.OLF.OT.	Olfactory Tubercle
OV	.FB.HY.PVZ.OV.	Vascular Organ of the Lamina Terminalis
PA	.FB.AMY.PA.	Posterior Nucleus of the Amygdala
PAA	.FB.OLF.PAA.	Piriform-Amygdaloid Area
PAG	.BS.RETIC.CGB.PAG.	Periaqueductal Grey
PAL	.FB.CSTR.PAL.	Pallidum
PAR	.FB.HPF.RHP.PAR.	Parasubiculum
PARN	.BS.RETIC.RET.PARN.	Parvicellular Reticular Nucleus
PAS	.BS.PrCB.PAS.	Parasolitary Nucleus
PAT	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.PAT.	Paratrigeminal Nucleus
PB	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.PB.	Parabrachial Nucleus
PBG	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PBG.	Parabigeminal Nucleus
PBI	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.PB.PBI.	Parabrachial Nucleus, lateral division
PBm	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.PB.PBm.	Parabrachial Nucleus, medial division
PCG	.BS.RETIC.CGB.PCG.	Pontine central Grey
PCN	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.PCN.	Paracentral Nucleus of the Thalamus
PD	.FB.HY.MEZ.PD.	Posterodorsal Preoptic Nucleus
PERI	.FB.ISO.PRh.PERI.	Perirhinal Area
PF	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.PF.	Parafascicular Nucleus
PFL	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.PFL.	Paraflocculus
PFor	.FB.HY.LZ.LHA.PFor.	Periformical Nucleus
PG	.BS.PrCB.PG.	Pontine Gray
PGRN	.BS.RETIC.RET.PGRN.	Paragigantocellular Reticular Nucleus
PH	.FB.HY.MEZ.PH.	Posterior Hypothalamic Nucleus
PhLa	.BS.MOTBS.PhLa.	Pharynx/Larynx/Esophagus Motor Brainstem Nuclei
PHY	.BS.SENS.VESBS.PHY.	Perihypoglossal Nuclei
PI	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.PI.	Posterior Intralaminar Nucleus of the Thalamus
PIN	.FB.PIN.	Pineal Gland
PIR	.FB.OLF.PIR.	Piriform Area
PIT	.FB.PIT.	Pituitary gland
PL	.FB.ISO.PL.	Prelimbic Area
PMd	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.PMd.	Dorsal Premammillary Nucleus
PMR	.BS.PrCB.PMR.	Paramedian Reticular Nucleus
PMv	.FB.HY.MEZ.TUA.PMv.	Ventral Premammillary Nucleus
PO	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.PO.	Posterior Complex of the Thalamus
POL	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.POL.	Posterior Limiting Nucleus of the Thalamus
POm	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.PO.POm.	Posterior Complex of the Thalamus, medial part
POR	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.SOC.POR.	Superior Olivary Complex, periolivary region
POST	.FB.HPF.RHP.POST.	Postsubiculum
PP	.FB.TH.VNT.PP.	Peripeduncular Nucleus
PPN	.BS.RETIC.RET.PPN.	Peduncularpontine Nucleus
PPT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.PPT.	Posterior Pretectal Nucleus
PR	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.PR.	Perireuniens Nucleus
PrCB	.BS.PrCB.	Pre- and Post- Cerebellar Nuclei

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
PRE	.FB.HPF.RHP.PRE.	Presubiculum
PRh	.FB.ISO.PRh.	Perirhinal Region
PRM	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.PRM.	Paramedian Lobule
PRN	.BS.RETIC.RET.PRN.	Pontine Reticular Nucleus
PRP	.BS.SENS.VESBS.PHY.PRP.	Nucleus Prepositus
PRT	.BS.SENS.VISBS.PRT.	Pretectal Region
PS	.FB.HY.MEZ.PS.	Parastrial Nucleus
PSC	.FB.SEP.PSC.	Posterior Septal Complex
PSCH	.FB.HY.PVZ.PSCH.	Suprachiasmatic Preoptic Nucleus
PSV	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.PSV.	Principal Sensory Nucleus of the Trigeminal
PT	.FB.TH.DOR.MID.PT.	Parataenial Nucleus
PTLp	.FB.ISO.VISA.	Posterior Parietal Association areas
PV	.FB.HY.PVZ.PV.	Periventricular Nuclei of the Hypothalamus
PVH	.FB.HY.PVZ.PVH.	Paraventricular Nucleus of the Hypothalamus
PVT	.FB.TH.DOR.MID.PVT.	Paraventricular Nucleus of the Thalamus
PVZ	.FB.HY.PVZ.	Periventricular Zone of the Hypothalamus
PYR	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.PYR.	Pyramus (VIII)
R	.FB.R.	Retina
RA	.BS.RETIC.RA.	Raphe Nuclei
RCH	.FB.HY.MEZ.RCH.	Retrochiasmatic Area
RE	.FB.TH.DOR.MID.RE.	Nucleus Reuniens
RET	.BS.RETIC.RET.	Reticular Formation
RETIC	.BS.RETIC.	Reticular Core
RH	.FB.TH.DOR.ILM.RH.	Rhomboid Nucleus
RHP	.FB.HPF.RHP.	Retrohippocampal Region
RL	.BS.RETIC.RA.RL.	Rostral Linear Raphe Nucleus
RM	.BS.RETIC.RA.RM.	Nucleus Raphe Magnus
RN	.BS.PrCB.RN.	Red Nucleus
RO	.BS.RETIC.RA.RO.	Nucleus Raphe Obscurus
RPA	.BS.RETIC.RA.RPA.	Nucleus Raphe Pallidus
RPO	.BS.RETIC.RA.RPO.	Nucleus Raphe Pontis
RR	.BS.RETIC.RET.MRN.RR.	Mesencephalic Reticular Nucleus, Retrobulbar Area
RSP	.FB.ISO.RSP.	Retrosplenial Area
RSPd	.FB.ISO.RSP.RSPd.	Retrosplenial Area, dorsal part
RSPv	.FB.ISO.RSP.RSPv.	Retrosplenial Area, ventral part
RT	.FB.TH.VNT.RT.	Reticular Nucleus of the Thalamus
SAG	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.SAG.	Nucleus Sagulum
SBPV	.FB.HY.MEZ.SBPV.	Subparaventricular Zone
SC	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.	Superior Colliculus
SCd	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCd.	Superior Colliculus, deep layers
SCdg	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCd.SCdg.	Superior Colliculus, deep grey layer
SCdw	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCd.SCdw.	Superior Colliculus, deep white layer
SCH	.FB.HY.MEZ.SCH.	Suprachiasmatic Nucleus
SCi	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCi.	Superior Colliculus, intermediate layers
SCig	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCi.SCig.	Superior Colliculus, intermediate grey layer
SCiw	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCi.SCiw.	Superior Colliculus, intermediate white layer
SCO	.BS.RETIC.CGB.SCO.	Subcommisural Organ
SCop	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCs.SCop.	Superior Colliculus, optic layer
SCs	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCs.	Superior Colliculus, superficial layers
SCsg	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCs.SCsg.	Superior Colliculus, superficial grey layer
SCzo	.BS.SENS.VISBS.SC.SCs.SCzo.	Superior Colliculus, zonal layer
SENS	.BS.SENS.	Sensory Brainstem
SEP	.FB.SEP.	Septal Region
SF	.FB.SEP.PSC.SF.	Septofimbrial Nucleus
SFO	.FB.SEP.SFO.	Subfornical Organ
SG	.BS.RETIC.CGB.SG.	Supragenual Nucleus
SGN	.FB.TH.DOR.LAT.SGN.	Supragenulate Nucleus
SH	.FB.SEP.SH.	Septohippocampal Nucleus
SI	.FB.CSTR.PAL.SI.	Substantia Innominata
SIM	.BS.CB.CBX.HEM.SIM.	Simple Lobule
SLC	.BS.RETIC.CGB.LC.SLC.	Subcoeruleus Nucleus
SLD	.BS.RETIC.CGB.LDT.SLD.	Sublaterodorsal Tegmental Nucleus
SMT	.FB.TH.DOR.MED.SMT.	Submedial Nucleus of the Thalamus
SN	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.SN.	Substantia Nigra
SNC	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.SN.SNC.	Substantia Nigra, compact part
SNr	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.SN.SNr.	Substantia Nigra, reticular part
SO	.FB.HY.PVZ.SO.	Supraoptic Nucleus
SOC	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.SOC.	Superior Olivary Complex
SOCI	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.SOC.SOCI.	Superior Olivary Complex, lateral part
SOCm	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.SOC.SOCm.	Superior Olivary Complex, medial part
SOM	.BS.RETIC.CGB.PAG.SOM.	Supraoculomotor Periaqueductal Grey
SOMBS	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.	Somatosensory Sensory Brainstem

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
SOperi	.FB.HY.LZ.LHA.SOperi.	Peri Supraoptic-Nucleus Retinal Terminal Field
SP	.SP.	Spinal Cord
SPF	.FB.TH.VNT.SPF.	Subparafascicular Nucleus
SPIV	.BS.SENS.VESBS.VNC.SPIV.	Spinal Vestibular Nucleus
SPV	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.SPV.	Spinal Nucleus of the Trigeminal
SPVC	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.SPV.SPVC.	Spinal Nucleus of the Trigeminal, caudal part
SPVI	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.SPV.SPVI.	Spinal Nucleus of the Trigeminal, interpolar part
SPVO	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.SPV.SPVO.	Spinal Nucleus of the Trigeminal, oral part
SS	.FB.ISO.SS.	Somatosensory Areas
SSN	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.SSN.	Superior Salivatory Nucleus
SSp	.FB.ISO.SS.SSp.	Primary Somatosensory Area
SSs	.FB.ISO.SS.SSs.	Supplemental Somatosensory Areas
STN	.FB.TH.VNT.STN.	Subthalamic Nucleus
STR	.FB.CSTR.STR.	Striatum
SUB	.FB.HPF.RHP.SUB.	Subiculum
SUM	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.SUM.	Supramammillary Nucleus
SUT	.BS.RETIC.RET.SUT.	Supratrigeminal Nucleus
SUV	.BS.SENS.VESBS.VNC.SUV.	Superior Vestibular Nucleus
TEv	.FB.ISO.TEv.	Ventral Temporal Association Areas
TH	.FB.TH.	Thalamus
TM	.FB.HY.MEZ.MBO.TM.	Tuberomammillary Nucleus
Tong	.BS.MOTBS.Tong.	Tongue Motor Brainstem Nuclei
TR	.FB.OLF.TR.	Postpiriform Transition Area
TRIG	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.TRIG.	Sensory Trigeminal Nuclei
TRN	.BS.PrCB.PG.TRN.	Tegmental Reticular Nucleus
TRS	.FB.SEP.PSC.TRS.	Triangular Nucleus of the Septum
TT	.FB.OLF.TT.	Tenia Tecta
TUA	.FB.HY.MEZ.TUA.	Tuberal Area of the Hypothalamus
UVU	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.UVU.	Uvula (IX)
V	.BS.MOTBS.Jaw.V.	Motor Nucleus of the Trigeminal
VAL	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VAL.	Ventral Anterior-Lateral Complex of the Thalamus
VCO	.BS.SENS.AUDBS.CN.VCO.	Ventral Cochlear Nucleus
VENT	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.	Ventral Group of the Dorsal Thalamus
VERM	.BS.CB.CBX.VERM.	Vermal Regions
VESBS	.BS.SENS.VESBS.	Vestibular Sensory Brainstem
VI	.BS.MOTBS.Eye.VI.	Abducens Nucleus
VII	.BS.MOTBS.Face.VII.	Facial Nucleus
VIS	.FB.ISO.VIS.	Cortical Visual Areas
VISA	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISA.	Anterior Extrastriate Cortex
VISal	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-r.VISal.	Anterolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISam	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISM.VISam.	Anteromedial Cortical Visual Area
VISBS	.BS.SENS.VISBS.	Visual Sensory Brainstem
VISC	.FB.ISO.INS.VISC.	Visceral Area
VISCBS	.BS.SENS.VISCBS.	Visceral Sensory Brainstem
Viscera	.BS.MOTBS.Viscera.	Viscera Motor Brainstem Nuclei
VISFL	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISFL.	Far Lateral Extrastriate Cortex
VISL	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.	Lateral Extrastriate Cortex
VISL-c	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.	Caudal Lateral Extrastriate Cortex
VISL-r	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-r.	Rostral Lateral Extrastriate Cortex
VISli	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISFL.VISli.	Intermediolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISll	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISFL.VISll.	Laterolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISlla	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISFL.VISlla.	Anterior Laterolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISlm	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISlm.	Mediolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISM	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISM.	Medial Extrastriate Cortex
VISp	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISp.	Primary Visual Cortex
VISpl	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISPX.VISpl.	Posterolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISpm	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISM.VISpm.	Posterolateral Cortical Visual Area
VISpos	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISPX.VISpos.	Posterior Cortical Visual Area
VISPX	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-c.VISPX.	Posterior Lateral Extrastriate Cortex
VISrl	.FB.ISO.VIS.VISL.VISL-r.VISrl.	Rostralateral Cortical Visual Area
VM	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VM.	Ventral Medial Nucleus of the Thalamus
VMH	.FB.HY.MEZ.TUA.VMH.	Ventromedial Nucleus of the Hypothalamus
VNC	.BS.SENS.VESBS.VNC.	Vestibular Nuclei
VNT	.FB.TH.VNT.	Ventral Thalamus
VP	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VP.	Ventral Posterior Complex of the Thalamus
VPL	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VP.VPL.	Ventral Posterolateral Nucleus of the Thalamus
VPLpc	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VP.VPL.VPLpc.	Ventral Posterolateral Nucleus of the Thalamus, parvicellular part
VPM	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VP.VPM.	Ventral Posteromedial Nucleus of the Thalamus
VPMpc	.FB.TH.DOR.VENT.VP.VPM.VPMpc.	Ventral Posteromedial Nucleus of the Thalamus, parvicellular part
VTA	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.VTA.	Ventral Tegmental Area
VTN	.BS.RETIC.CGB.VTN.	Ventral Tegmental Nucleus

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Complete Tree</i>	<i>Area</i>
VTRZ	.BS.MOTBS.ExPyr.VTA.VTRZ.	Visual Tegmental Relay Zone
x	.BS.SENS.VESBS.x.	Nucleus x
XI	.BS.MOTBS.Neck.XI.	Nucleus of the Accesory Spinal Nerve
XII	.BS.MOTBS.Tong.XII.	Hypoglossal Nucleus
y	.BS.SENS.VESBS.y.	Nucleus y
z	.BS.SENS.SOMBS.DCN.MEDUL.z.	Nucleus z
ZI	.FB.TH.VNT.ZI.	Zona Incerta

Appendix B : Reference Scheme.

The following table contains abbreviations used in the connection tables of Appendix C to denote the citation of different papers. The table involves 256 papers.

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Akaik92	Akaike 1992
All&Hop89	Allen and Hopkins 1989
All&Cech93	Allen and Cechetto 1993
Amaral91	Amaral <i>et al.</i> 1991
Araki84	Araki <i>et al.</i> 1984
Barm93	Barmack <i>et al.</i> 1993
BarrWard&Kilp84	Barrington-Ward <i>et al.</i> 1984
Be78	Beckstead 1978
Be79	Beckstead 1979
Be83	Beckstead and Frankfurter 1983
Benz83	Benzinger and Massopust 1983
Beren&Groen91	Berendse and Groenewegen 1991
Berry86	Berry <i>et al.</i> 1986
Bina93	Bina <i>et al.</i> 1993
Blan82	Blanks <i>et al.</i> 1982
Bons83	Bons <i>et al.</i> 1983
Border86	Border <i>et al.</i> 1986
Bra82	Brauer and Schober 1982
Brau84	Brauer <i>et al.</i> 1984b
Brau84b	Brauer <i>et al.</i> 1984a
Burn81	Burne <i>et al.</i> 1981
CallBled&Witt93	Caballero-Bleda and Witter 1993
Cad85	Cadusseau and Roger 1985
Cad&Rog90	Cadusseau and Roger 1990
Caduss91	Cadusseau and Roger 1991
Cant92	Canteras <i>et al.</i> 1992a
Cant&Swa92c	Canteras and Swanson 1992
Cant&Swa92b	Canteras <i>et al.</i> 1992b
Car&Rie87	Carey and Rieck 1987
Carst90	Carstens <i>et al.</i> 1990
Cesaro85	Cesaro <i>et al.</i> 1985
Ch92	Chandler <i>et al.</i> 1992
Chev&Deni84	Chevalier and Deniau 1984
Chib&Mura85	Chiba and Murata 1985
Clarke89	Clarke <i>et al.</i> 1989
Cole80	Coleman and Clerici 1980
Cole&Cler87	Coleman and Clerici 1987
Conde90	Conde <i>et al.</i> 1990
Coog90	Coogan and Burkhalter 1990
Coog&Burk93	Coogan and Burkhalter 1993

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Corn&Phil88	Cornwall and Phillipson 1988a
Corn&Phil88b	Cornwall and Phillipson 1988b
Corn90b	Cornwall <i>et al.</i> 1990
Cosen&Moor84	Cosenza and Moore 1984
Cow&Per79	Cowey and Perry 1979
Cullin93	Cullinan <i>et al.</i> 1993
Dann87	Dann and Buhl 1987
deVries93	de Vries <i>et al.</i> 1993
DeZee93	De Zeeuw <i>et al.</i> 1993
De83	Deacon <i>et al.</i> 1983
DeZeeuw93	De Zeeuw <i>et al.</i> 1993
Dome69	Domesick 1969
Donnelly83	Donnelly <i>et al.</i> 1983
Donovan&Wyss83	Donovan and Wyss 1983
Dori92	Dori <i>et al.</i> 1992
Dre85	Dreher <i>et al.</i> 1985
Dreh90	Dreher <i>et al.</i> 1990
Drug&Syk84	Druga and Syka 1984
Eric91	Ericson <i>et al.</i> 1991
Fall83b	Fallon 1983
Fall84	Fallon <i>et al.</i> 1984
Fe87	Ferino <i>et al.</i> 1987
Fin84	Finch <i>et al.</i> 1984
Finn&Jeff93	Finnerty and Jefferys 1993
Foster89	Foster <i>et al.</i> 1989
Fred&Mug91	Fredette and Mugnaini 1991
Freed91	Freedman and Cassell 1991
Gay&Fau88	Gayer and Faull 1988
Gerf82	Gerfen <i>et al.</i> 1982
Giol84b	Giolli <i>et al.</i> 1984
Giol85d	Giolli <i>et al.</i> 1985d
Giol85c	Giolli <i>et al.</i> 1985c
Giol88b	Giolli <i>et al.</i> 1988
Giol92	Giolli <i>et al.</i> 1992
Gonz92	Gonzalo-Ruiz <i>et al.</i> 1992
Gray74	Graybiel 1974
Groene87	Groenewegen <i>et al.</i> 1987
Groene88	Groenewegen 1988
Groen90	Groenewegen and Berendse 1990
Grove88b	Grove 1988
Haglund84	Haglund <i>et al.</i> 1984
Harv90	Harvey and Worthington 1990
Haya93	Hayakawa <i>et al.</i> 1993
Hay62	Hayhow 1962
Hick76	Hickey and Spear 1976
Hoogland85	Hoogland <i>et al.</i> 1985
Horikawa88	Horikawa <i>et al.</i> 1988

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Hug77a	Hughes 1977
Hu91	Hurley <i>et al.</i> 1991
Ibat89	Ibata <i>et al.</i> 1989
Ita81	Itaya <i>et al.</i> 1981
It82a	Itaya and Van Hoesen 1982
Ja89	Jay <i>et al.</i> 1989
Ja91	Jay and Witter 1991
Johnson88	Johnson <i>et al.</i> 1988
John&Burk92	Johnson and Burkhalter 1992
John&Burk94	Johnson and Burkhalter 1994
Kawan&Masuk92	Kawano and Masuko 1992
Kawa&Masu93	Kawano and Masuko 1993
Kim92	Kim <i>et al.</i> 1992
Kohler84	Kohler 1984
Koh85	Kohler 1985a
Kohler85b	Kohler 1985b
Koh86	Kohler 1986
Kohler88	Kohler 1988
Korp89	Korp <i>et al.</i> 1989
Kos83	Kosel <i>et al.</i> 1983
Kos71	Kostovic 1971
Kunz&Schnyd84	Kunzle and Schnyder 1984
Legg79	[Legg, 1979b #104]
Leo69	[Leonard, 1969 #105]
Levine91	Levine <i>et al.</i> 1991
Levine94	Levine <i>et al.</i> 1994
Lieber85	Lieberman <i>et al.</i> 1985
Lind83a	Linden and Perry 1983
MS83	Mackay-Sim <i>et al.</i> 1983
Mai79b	Mai 1979
Marani87	Marani <i>et al.</i> 1987
Mart86	Martin 1986
Mas81	Mason and Groos 1981
Matsuy&Kawa85	Matsuyama and Kawamura 1985
McDon&Jack87	McDonald and Jackson 1987
McDon87	McDonald 1987
Mei77b	Meibach and Siegel 1977b
Mei77d	Meibach and Siegel 1977d
Mei&Sie77	Meibach and Siegel 1977
Mihail89	Mihailoff <i>et al.</i> 1989
Mikk90	Mikkelsen and Moller 1990
Mikk92	Mikkelsen 1992
Mi84	Miller and Vogt 1984
Mo93	Montero 1993
Moo72	Moore and Lenn 1972
Moore&Card94	Moore and Card 1994
Murabe83	Murabe <i>et al.</i> 1983
Nagata86	Nagata 1986

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Nicollelis92	Nicolelis <i>et al.</i> 1992
OHearn84	O'Hearn and Molliver 1984
OgMeg92	Ogawa-Meguro <i>et al.</i> 1992
OHar85	Ohara and Lieberman 1985
Oht92	Ohtsuki <i>et al.</i> 1992
Olav79	Olavarria 1979
Olav82	Olavarria and Van Sluyters 1982
Pakhomova&Akopian85	Pakhomova and Akopian 1985
Pak&Akop86	Pakhomova and Akopian 1986
Pa91	Paperna and Malach 1991
Pas82c	Pasquier and Villar 1982
Perr79	Perry and Cowey 1979
Perr80	Perry 1980
Perr82	Perry and Cowey 1982
Petro83	Petrovicky 1983
Price&Slot83	Price and Stern 1983
Price91	Price <i>et al.</i> 1991
Quim91	Quimet 1991
Raos&Bent93	Raos and Bentivoglio 1993
Ray92	Ray and Price 1992
Red87	Redgrave <i>et al.</i> 1987a
Redgr87	Redgrave <i>et al.</i> 1987b
Redgr92b	Redgrave <i>et al.</i> 1992
Re90	Reep <i>et al.</i> 1990
Rees&Cow83	Reese and Cowey 1983
Rees84	Reese 1984
Reese&Cowey87	Reese and Cowey 1987
Rees88	Reese 1988
Reperant87	Reperant <i>et al.</i> 1987
Rib75	Ribak and Peters 1975
Roberts84	Roberts <i>et al.</i> 1984
Robson83	Robertson 1983
Rog&Cad84	Roger and Cadusseau 1984
Rog&Cad85	Roger and Cadusseau 1985
Roman85	Romanowski <i>et al.</i> 1985
Ru88	Ruth <i>et al.</i> 1988
Ruth84	Rutherford <i>et al.</i> 1984
Ruther84	Rutherford <i>et al.</i> 1984
Sa91	Sanderson <i>et al.</i> 1991
Sar83	Sarter and Markowitsch 1983
Sar84	Sarter and Markowitsch 1984
Scal&Aran79	Scalia and Arango 1979
Schmidt93	Schmidt <i>et al.</i> 1993
Schnyd84	Schnyder and Kunzle 1984
Schulz83	Schulz <i>et al.</i> 1983
Schum87	Schumann 1987
Sef81	Sefton <i>et al.</i> 1981
Sef84	Sefton and Martin 1984

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Sek&Zyo84	Seki and Zyo 1984
Serf&Lind91	Serfaty and Linden 1991
Se89	Sesack <i>et al.</i> 1989
Sh-Lag83	Shammah-Lagnado <i>et al.</i> 1983
Sh-Lag85	Shammah-Lagnado <i>et al.</i> 1985
Shib88	Shibata 1988
Shib89	Shibata 1989
Shib92	Shibata 1992
Shibita93c	Shibata 1993c
Shibita93b	Shibata 1993b
Sik&Vog87	Sikes and Vogt 1987
Sikes&Vogt87	Sikes and Vogt 1987
Sim&Swa86	Simerly and Swanson 1986
Sim&Swa88	Simerly and Swanson 1988
Solo&Nomo84	Sologub and Nomokonova 1984
Sri&Wys86	Sripanidkulchai and Wyss 1986
Sri87	Sripanidkulchai and Wyss 1987
Steinin92	Steininger <i>et al.</i> 1992
Ste&Sco76	Steward and Scoville 1976
Sug83	Sugita <i>et al.</i> 1983
Sug&Otan86	Sugita and Otani 1986
Sugita89	Sugita <i>et al.</i> 1989
Swa74	Swanson <i>et al.</i> 1974
Swa&Cow75b	Swanson and Cowan 1975
Sw77	Swanson and Cowan 1977
Swa78	Swanson <i>et al.</i> 1978
Sw81	Swanson 1981
Swa.et.al81	Swanson <i>et al.</i> 1981
Swa82	Swanson 1982
Swe&Cas83b	Swenson and Castro 1983b
Swe&Cas83a	Swenson and Castro 1983a
Swe84	Swenson <i>et al.</i> 1984
Ta91	Takagishi and Chiba 1991
Tak85	Takahashi 1985
Tanaka85	Tanaka <i>et al.</i> 1985
Taylor86	Taylor <i>et al.</i> 1986
TerHorst&Luiten86	Ter Horst and Luiten 1986
TerHor&Luit87	Ter Horst and Luiten 1987
Tera79	Terasawa <i>et al.</i> 1979
Teru84	Terubayashi and Fujisawa 1984
Thier83	Thierry <i>et al.</i> 1983
Thomas84	Thomas <i>et al.</i> 1984
Thomp&Robert87b	Thompson and Robertson 1987b
Thomp87	Thompson and Robertson 1987a
Tori86	Torigoe <i>et al.</i> 1986
To84	Torrealba <i>et al.</i> 1984
Turl93	Turlejski <i>et al.</i> 1993
Ullan85	Ullan 1985

<i>Abbreviation</i>	<i>Reference</i>
Urush88	Urushibata <i>et al.</i> 1988
vdT&vdW92	van der Togt and van der Want 1992
VdWant92	van der Want <i>et al.</i> 1992
vGr90a	van Groen and Wyss 1990a
vGr90b	van Groen and Wyss 1990b
vGr90c	van Groen and Wyss 1990c
vGr90d	van Groen and Wyss 1990d
vGr92	van Groen and Wyss 1992a
vGr92b	van Groen and Wyss 1992b
Ver&Mar88	Vertes and Martin 1988
Villalo&Ferssi87	Villalobos and Ferssiwi 1987
Vo83	Vogt <i>et al.</i> 1981
Vo81	Vogt and Miller 1983
Wat79	Watanabe and Kawana 1979
Watts&Swans87	Watts and Swanson 1987b
Watts87	Watts <i>et al.</i> 1987a
Wayn83	Wayner <i>et al.</i> 1983
Wies82a	Wiesendanger and Wiesendanger 1982
Wi88	Witter <i>et al.</i> 1988
Woolf84	Woolf <i>et al.</i> 1984
Wree83	Wree and Zilles 1983
Wys81	Wyss 1981
Wyss&vGr92a	Wyss and Van Groen 1992
Yama83	Yamasaki <i>et al.</i> 1986
Yamas86	Yamauchi <i>et al.</i> 1983
Zen91	Zeng and Stuesse 1991

Appendix C : Connection Tables

The three connection matrices in Figures 4-6, 4-36 and 5-1 are large scale summaries of connection data that are summarised in the following three tables. The first stage retinal connection table lists the connection data underlying Figure 4-6; the second stage retinal connection table lists the data summarised in Figure 4-36 and the connection matrix in Figure 5-1 is based on the limbic system connection table.

First stage retinal connection table.

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
ICe	PRT	1	1	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	1	ICe	several weak cells were also visible ... ipsilaterally in the brachium and external cortex of the inferior colliculus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
ICe	SC	2	2	1	Drug&Syk84	a	pg248, fig1	H	2	ICe		SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r
AOS	PRT	3	3	7	Clarke89	a	pg270-1, fig1.2, table1	F	3	MT	... label large numbers of neurons that are evenly distributed throughout the ipsilateral dorsal (MTNd) & ventral (MTNv) subdivs of the MTN & portion of VTRZ lying adj to MTNd (figs1b&c), table1, fig2: ~70% of labeled neurons in expt in MT	PRT/PRT/N OT	pg270: 32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: IOdc(i), PAG/MRN, LAV/SUV, VTRZ, PG <Ignore this inj>... 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT. pg271: injections of FG into pretectum, centred in NOT ...	r
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	3	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	NOT	Heavy terminal labeling within 2 comps of the pretectal comp: NOT and DTN. Axonal terminal fields covered superficial portions of most of the rostral 3/4 of the NOT, overlapping R->NOT projection. Most caudal parts lightly/not labelled.	a
					Giol84b	a	pg231,232-3, fig2.4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	NOT	pretectum receives the largest, most specific terminal of the rabbit & rat MTN. Moderate/heavy term field dist to sup. part of most of ipsi NOT, except for small venomed seg of its ros 2/3 & a larger med seg of its cau 1/3.	a
					Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	LT	Labeling in the LTN & inSfp is bilateral: heavy ipsilaterally & sparse contralaterally	NOT/NOT/ OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
					Giol92	a	pg351	F	3	LT	Lateral Terminal nucleus: A exceedingly high density of neurons target the ipsi NOT/DT (204neurons/mm3) none of these cells are GABAergic.	NOT/DT/S C/PRT/MG	Fluoro-gold was injected into a total of 18 rats. Of these 11 with less extensive spread of tracer beyond NOT & neighbouring DTN were used. Injs into lateral pretectum while centred in NOT/DTN spread over areas that include PRT(lat), MG, SC	r
					Giol92	a	pg351	F	3	MT	Medial Terminal nucleus: high densities of neurons in MTNd,v that are single labeled with FG & are non GABAergic (30-120neurons/mm3). A 2nd pop of nerve cells are GABA immunoreactive. (MTNd: 78cells/mm3, MTNv: 33cells/mm3)	NOT/DT/S C/PRT/MG	Fluoro-gold was injected into a total of 18 rats. Of these 11 with less extensive spread of tracer beyond NOT & neighbouring DTN were used. Injs into lateral pretectum while centred in NOT/DTN spread over areas that include PRT(lat), MG, SC	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	DT	Neuronal labeling in ipsi DTN is of high density but is lacking within contra DTN	NOT/NOT/OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
			2	1	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	2	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NOT	These injections resulted in anterograde labeling of terminals in the NOT, the DTN & the VTRZ. The area of termination of MTN afferents in the NOT were found to coincide with the areas occupied by retro labeled neurons. Heavier clustering centrally.	a
			0	7	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	OP	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	OP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	MPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	APN	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NPC	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	APN	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	PPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
AOS	NOT	3	3	4	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	3	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	NOT	Heavy terminal labeling within 2 comps of the pretectal comp: NOT and DTN. Axonal terminal fields covered superficial portions of most of the rostral 3/4 of the NOT, overlapping R->NOT projection. Most caudal parts lightly/not labelled.	a
					Giol84b	a	pg231,232-3, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	NOT	pretectum receives the largest, most specific terminal of the rabbit & rat MTN. Moderate/heavy term field dist to sup. part of most of ipsi NOT, except for small venmed seg of its ros 2/3 & a larger med seg of its cau 1/3.	a
					Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	LT	Labeling in the LTN & inSFP is bilateral; heavy ipsilaterally & sparse contralaterally	NOT/NOT/OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
					Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	DT	Neuronal labeling in ipsi DTN is of high density but is lacking within contra DTN	NOT/NOT/OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
			2	1	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	2	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NOT	These injections resulted in anterograde labeling of terminals in the NOT, the DTN & the VTRZ. The area of termination of MTN afferents in the NOT were found to coincide with the areas occupied by retro labeled neurons. Heavier clustering centrally.	a
AOS	OP	0	0	2	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	OP	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	OP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
AOS	PPT	0	0	1	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	PPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
AOS	SC	1	1	2	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SC	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
			0	3	Giol88b	b	pg610	H	0	LT	... never produced labeled neurons in the DTN, LTN or inSFp	SC	Injections (HRP) into the superior colliculus ...	r
					Giol88b	b	pg610	H	0	DT	... never produced labeled neurons in the DTN, LTN or inSFp	SC	Injections (HRP) into the superior colliculus ...	r
					Giol85d	b	pg104-5, table1, fig1,6	H	0	MT	injections into the superior colliculus of the rabbit & rat fail to label ventral tegmental neurons in nuclei other than the ipsilateral reticular division of the substantia nigra.	SC	3 rats received inj (HRP) into the superior colliculus	r
AOS	SCs	1	1	1	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
AOS	SCop	1	1	1	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
AOS	LGd	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LGd	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
AOS	LP	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
AOS	LGv	1	1	1	MS83	C	pg29	W	1	LT	In the contralateral terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system there was a small number of labelled cells, these cells lay in clearly defined line just caudal and medial to LGNv and ventral to the medial geniculate nucleus, (ips cells inj site?)	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
			0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LGv	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
DT	LT	0	0	1	Yama83	a	pg217	L	0	DT/???	In the first group of 5 rats, dorsal terminal nucleus or the area including a part of the brachium colliculi superioris was injured on the right side by electrical coagulation technique. <Not really tracer expt, conclusions based on small Ncase>	LT/???	In 1st group... degenerating nerve fibres seen in dorsal fasciculus & could be followed to medial terminal nucleus on the same side. No degenerating nerve fibre observed in lateral terminal nucleus. i.e. LT not innervated by dorsal fasciculus	a
DT	PRT	3	3	1	Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	DT	Neuronal labeling in ipsi DTN is of high density but is lacking within contra DTN	NOT/NOT/ OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
DT	NOT	3	3	1	Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	DT	Neuronal labeling in ipsi DTN is of high density but is lacking within contra DTN	NOT/NOT/ OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
DT	SC	0	0	1	Giol88b	b	pg610	H	0	DT	... never produced labeled neurons in the DTN, LTN or inSFp	SC	Injections (HRP) into the superior colliculus ...	r
LT	PRT	3	3	2	Giol92	a	pg351	F	3	LT	Lateral Terminal nucleus: A exceedingly high density of neurons target the ipsi NOT/DT (204neurons/mm3) none of these cells are GABAergic.	NOT/DT/S C/PRT/MG	Fluoro-gold was injected into a total of 18 rats. Of these 11 with less extensive spread of tracer beyond NOT & neighbouring DTN were used. Injs into lateral pretectum while centred in NOT/DTN spread over areas that include PRT(lat), MG, SC	r
					Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	LT	Labeling in the LTN & inSFp is bilateral: heavy ipsilaterally & sparse contralaterally	NOT/NOT/ OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
LT	NOT	3	3	1	Giol88b	a	pg610, table1	H	3	LT	Labeling in the LTN & inSfp is bilateral: heavy ipsilaterally & sparse contralaterally	NOT/NOT/OP/PPT/SC	large HRP injns into the pretectal complex of 12 rabbits and 5 ratshave involved substantial portions of PRT. Small injections in 2 rabbits & 1 rat confined almost entirely to NOT with minimal dye spread med into the PPT & olivary OP & dor into the SC	r
LT	SC	0	0	1	Giol88b	b	pg610	H	0	LT	... never produced labeled neurons in the DTN, LTN or inSfp	SC	Injections (HRP) into the superior colliculus ...	r
LT	LGv	1	1	1	MS83	C	pg29	W	1	LT	In the contralateral terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system there was a small number of labelled cells, these cells lay in clearly defined line just caudal and medial to LGNv and ventral to the medial geniculate nucleus, (ips cells inj site?)	LGv/LGv/LGd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
MT	DT	3	3	2	Giol84b	a	pg231,232-3, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	DT	same pattern of input from MTN to nucleus of the optic tract in rabbit as it rat... compare figs2AB,5A with 4A-C. In addition a dense terminal field of axons covers nearly all of the ipsilateral DTN.	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	3	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	DT	Heavy terminal labeling within 2 comps of the pretectal comp: NOT and DTN... The DTN is uniformly covered by a highly dense zone of silver grains.	a
MT	LT	2	2	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,233, fig2,4	A	2	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	LT	MTN neurons terminate on cells of the LTN & interstitial nucleus of the superior fasciculus, posterior fibres. The terminal axon fields in the LTN and the interstitial population are of sparse to moderate density in both species	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig2	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LT	A few axons (superficial mesencephalic bundle) gave rise to a sparse terminal field within the lateral terminal nucleus	a
MT	PRT	3	3	4	Clarke89	a	pg270-1, fig1.2, table1	F	3	MT	... label large numbers of neurons that are evenly distributed throughout the ipsilateral dorsal (MTNd) & ventral (MTNv) subdivs of the MTN & portion of VTRZ lying adj to MTNd (figs1b&c), table1, fig2: ~70% of labeled neurons in expt in MT	PRT/PRT/N OT	pg270: 32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: IOdc(i), PAG/MRN, LAV/SUV, VTRZ, PG <Ignore this inj>... 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT. pg271: injections of FG into pretectum, centred in NOT ...	r
					Giol84b	a	pg231,232-3, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	NOT	pretectum receives the largest, most specific terminal of the rabbit & rat MTN. Moderate/heavy term field dist to sup. part of most of ipsi NOT, except for small venomed seg of its ros 2/3 & a larger med seg of its cau 1/3.	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	3	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	NOT	Heavy terminal labeling within 2 comps of the pretectal comp: NOT and DTN. Axonal terminal fields covered superficial portions of most of the rostral 3/4 of the NOT, overlapping R->NOT projection. Most caudal parts lightly/not labelled.	a
					Giol92	a	pg351	F	3	MT	Medial Terminal nucleus: high densities of neurons in MTNd,v that are single labeled with FG & are non GABAergic (30-120neurons/mm3). A 2nd pop of nerve cells are GABA immunoreactive. (MTNd: 78cells/mm3, MTNv: 33cells/mm3)	NOT/DT/S C/PRT/MG	Fluoro-gold was injected into a total of 18 rats, Of these 11 with less extensive spread of tracer beyond NOT & neighbouring DTN were used. Injs into lateral pretectum while centred in NOT/DTN spread over areas that include PRT(lat), MG, SC	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	2	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NOT	These injections resulted in anterograde labeling of terminals in the NOT, the DTN & the VTRZ. The area of termination of MTN afferents in the NOT were found to coincide with the areas occupied by retro labeled neurons. Heavier clustering centrally.	a
					Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	OP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	PPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a					
Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	APN	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a					

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	APN	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	MPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NPC	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	OP	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
MT	NOT	3	3	2	Giol84b	a	pg231,232-3, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	NOT	pretectum receives the largest, most specific terminal of the rabbit & rat MTN. Moderate/heavy term field dist to sup. part of most of ipsi NOT, except for small venomed seg of its ros 2/3 & a larger med seg of its cau 1/3.	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	3	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	NOT	Heavy terminal labeling within 2 comps of the pretectal comp: NOT and DTN. Axonal terminal fields covered superficial portions of most of the rostral 3/4 of the NOT, overlapping R->NOT projection. Most caudal parts lightly/not labelled.	a
			2	1	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	2	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	NOT	These injections resulted in anterograde labeling of terminals in the NOT, the DTN & the VTRZ. The area of termination of MTN afferents in the NOT were found to coincide with the areas occupied by retro labeled neurons. Heavier clustering centrally.	a
MT	OP	0	0	2	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	OP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	OP	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
MT	PPT	0	0	1	vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	PPT	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
MT	SC	1	1	2	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SC	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
					Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
			0	1	Giol85d	b	pg104-5, table1, fig1,6	H	0	MT	injections into the superior colliculus of the rabbit & rat fail to label ventral tegmental neurons in nuclei other than the ipsilateral reticular division of the substantia nigra.	SC	3 rats received inj (HRP) into the superior colliculus	r
MT	SCs	1	1	1	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
MT	SCop	1	1	1	Blan82	a	pg229, fig1	A	1	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	SCop	In figs 1C & 2C the field of labeled terminals are seen to continue into the extension of the NOT within the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	a
MT	LGd	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LGd	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
MT	LP	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LP	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
MT	LGv	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	LGv	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PRT	ICe	1	1	1	Red87	2302	pg155, fig2	W	1	SC/SC/PPT/NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	ICe	Some fibres run to the cunieforn nucleus and surrounding areas. These include... the external nucleus of the inferior colliculus, Label was weak	a
PRT	AOS	c	c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	MT	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system...	a
PRT	MT	c	c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	MT	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system...	a
PRT	SC	2	2	5	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	2	NPC	most labelled cells (in pretectum) were confined to the nucleus of the posterior commissure and nucleus of the optic tract	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCi	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
					Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCs	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	NPC	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... nucleus of the posterior commissure... Fewer cells < than PBG/ZI > were seen in nucleus of posterior commissure ipsilaterally	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
					Wat79	R95	pg3, fig4	H	2	NPC	neurons were found	SC/SC/AC A	HRP injections, small leakage into ACA along needle track	r
			1	6	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	APN	case RC14 also exhibited some cell labelling in the olivary pretectal and anterior pretectal nuclei	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	NOT	most labelled cells (in pretectum) were confined to the nucleus of the posterior commissure and nucleus of the optic tract	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	OP	case RC14 also exhibited some cell labelling in the olivary pretectal and anterior pretectal nuclei	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Drug&Syk8 4	a	pg251	H	1	PRT	HRP +ve cells	SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	OP	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... olivary pretectal nucleus, contained a small number of widely dispersed labelled cells	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	NOT	retrogradely labelled cells were seen bilaterally in: the nucleus of the optic tract... The nucleus of the optic tract both ipsilaterally and contralaterally to the injected colliculus contained a small number of widely dispersed labelled cells.	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
			c	1	Wat79	R95	pg3, fig4	H	-1	NOT/OP/APN	obs from fig 4, mentioned in text: PRT including NOT	SC/SC/ACA	HRP injections, small leakage into ACA along needle track	r
			0	1	Wat79	R95	pg5, fig4	H	0	MPT	obs no labelling in MPT region on figure	SC/SC/ACA	HRP injections, small leakage into ACA along needle track	r
			x	1	VdWant92		abstract, [VdWant91]		-1	PRT		SC		
PRT	SCi	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCi	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
PRT	SCs	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCs	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
PRT	R	0	0	2	Hoogland85		p326	x	0	PRT	In our experiments the oculomotor nucleus is the only area in the brain which shows retrograde labelling	R	intravitreal injections of NY.	r
					Schnyd84		pg504,505	W	0	PRT	WGA cases also did not show any labeled neurons in the pretectum, neither in albino or pigmented rats	R	In 12 animals the tracer (injected into the vitreous body of one eye) 3-5µl of [125I] wheat germ agglutinin	r
PRT	LD	3	3	8	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	MPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	APN	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	APN	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	PPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	PPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	OP	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	NOT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	MPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	17	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	APN	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	MPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... medial pretectal region... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	OP	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... olivary pretectal nucleus... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	NOT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	MPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM. Many cells were seen in the contralateral hemisphere including PM	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	x	2	PRT	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the pretectal nuclei ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralamina complex	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	NPC	Many cells were seen in the contralateral hemisphere including ... nucleus of the posterior commissure	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	OP	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	PPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	PPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	APN	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	MPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	OP	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r	
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r	
			1	1	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	1	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LD	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle... occasional labelling also appeared in the lateral dorsal and ventral lateral thalamic nuclei	a	
			0	2	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	OP	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r	
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	NOT	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r	
PRT	LGd		3	3	1	Pas82c	D	pg412, fig3	H	3	PRT	the rat PT projects to the LGBd and LGBv. Both projections were bilateral and abundant, dorsal being more numerous than the ventral.	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
						Pas82c	D	pg413, fig3	H	2	NPC	a specific projection from the nucleus of the posterior commissure to the LGBd	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
			1	6	MS83	A	pg27,29	W	1	OP	In pretectum, a few cells <lt.20> were usually labelled in the ipsilateral olivary nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract close to the brachium of the superior colliculus	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r	
					MS83	A	pg27,29	W	1	NOT	In pretectum, a few cells <lt.20> were usually labelled in the ipsilateral olivary nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract close to the brachium of the superior colliculus	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r	
					Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	APN	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, about 200-250 cells of the dorsal part of the non-retino-recipient anterior pretectal nucleus formed a predominantly ipsilateral projection to the DLG	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r	
					Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	PPT	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r	
					Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	NOT	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r	
					Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	OP	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r	
PRT	LP		3	3	1	Solo&Nomo 84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	3	PRT	one of most powerful ips sources of inputs in lateral part of PRT	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r
			2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LP	dorsal bunch of the ascending bundle proceeds dorsally in a rostral direction and distributes terminals in the rostral part of the lateral posterior thalamic nucleus	a	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	Solo&Nomo 84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	-1	PRT	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA)	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
			0	1	Mas81	b	pg108	F	0	NOT	a projection not apparant	LP	EB/HRP injections restricted to rostral LTP	r
PRT	LGv	3	3	2	Caduss91	control 4r	pg93	W	3	APN	a dense pattern of both retrograde and anterograde labeling occure in the APc	LGv	bilateral applications of WGA-HRP in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus	r
					Pas82c	V	pg412, fig4	H	3	PRT	the rat PT projects to the LGBd and LGBv. Both projections were bilateral and abundant, dorsal being more numerous than the ventral.	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
			2	5	Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	APN	Some neurons in other subcortical structures was also labeled (bilaterally with ips dominance): anterior pretectal nucleus	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Cosen&Mo or84	a	pg368	H	2	PPT	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					Cosen&Mo or84	a	pg368	H	2	OP	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					Cosen&Mo or84	a	pg368	H	2	APN	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LGv	dorsal bunch of the ascending bundle: ... some fibres continue laterally in the thalamic radiation, passing through the dorsal lateral geniculate before terminating in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, densest in medial(parvocellular) div.	a
			1	4	MS83	C	pg32	W	1	OP	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were ... bilaterally in the olivary pretectal nucleus, ipsilateral projections dominated	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
					MS83	C	pg32	W	1	PPT	A few very lightly labelled cells were also seen bilaterally in the posterior pretectal nuclei	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
					MS83	C	pg32	W	1	NOT	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were ... bilaterally in the nucleus of the optic tract, ipsilateral projections dominated	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
					MS83	C	pg32	W	1	APN	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were in the ipsilateral anterior pretectal nucleus	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
			c	2	Brau84b	a	pg212-3, fig4	L	-1	PRT	lesions?	LGv	some fibre bundles descending from the pretectal region vai the nucleus ventralis thalami to the zona project to the vLGN. Using the HRP method it was possible to find out that all pretectal nuclei except for OP project to LGv	a
					Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	LGv	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... ventral portion of the lateral geniculate nucleus ...	a
			0	1	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4	H	0	NPC	None of the LGBv cases showed it <projection from nulceus of hte posterior commissure.>	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
NOT	AOS	c	c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	MT	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system...	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
NOT	MT	c	c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	MT	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system...	a
NOT	OP	c	c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	OP	Labeling in contralateral PON and EW accounted for by involvement of PON	a
NOT	SC	1	1	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	NOT	most labelled cells (in pretectum) were confined to the nucleus of the posterior commissure and nucleus of the optic tract	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	NOT	retrogradely labelled cells were seen bilaterally in: the nucleus of the optic tract... The nucleus of the optic tract both ipsilaterally and contralaterally to the injected colliculus contained a small number of widely dispersed labelled cells.	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
NOT	LD	3	3	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	NOT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	NOT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	NOT	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
NOT	LGd	1	1	2	Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	NOT	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
					MS83	A	pg27,29	W	1	NOT	In pretectum, a few cells <lt.20> were usually labelled in the ipsilateral olivary nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract close to the brachium of the superior colliculus	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r
NOT	LP	0	0	1	Mas81	b	pg108	F	0	NOT	a projection not apparant	LP	EB/HRP injections restricted to rostral LTP	r
NOT	LGv	1	1	1	MS83	C	pg32	W	1	NOT	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were ... bilaterally in the nucleus of the optic tract, ipsilateral projections dominated	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
			c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	LGv	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... ventral portion of the lateral geniculate nucleus ...	a
OP	SC	1	1	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	OP	case RC14 also exhibited some cell labelling in the olivary pretectal and anterior pretectal nuclei	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	OP	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... olivary pretectal nucleus, contained a small number of widely dispersed labelled cells	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
OP	LD	3	3	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	OP	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	OP	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... olivary pretectal nucleus... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	OP	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	OP	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	OP	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
OP	LGd	1	1	2	MS83	A	pg27,29	W	1	OP	In pretectum, a few cells <lt.20> were usually labelled in the ipsilateral olivary nucelus and nucleus of the optic tract close to the brachium of the superior colliculus	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r
					Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	OP	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
OP	LGv	2	2	1	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368	H	2	OP	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
			1	1	MS83	C	pg32	W	1	OP	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were ... bilaterally in the olivary pretectal nucleus, ipsilateral projections dominated	LGv/LGv/L Gd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
PPT	LD	3	3	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	PPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	PPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	PPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	PPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PPT	LGd	1	1	1	Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	PPT	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, in all three retino-recipient pretectal nuclei there were small numbers (cell numbers: 700-1000) of retrogradely labelled neurons...	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
PPT	LGv	2	2	1	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368	H	2	PPT	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
			1	1	MS83	C	pg32	W	1	PPT	A few very lightly labelled cells were also seen bilaterally in the posterior pretectal nuclei	LGv/LGv/LGd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
SC	ICe	2	2	1	Cole&Cler87	ICe	pg218, fig1	H	2	SCd	Other labeled neurons in the brainstem are seen in the ... deep superior colliculus ...	ICe	Injection of the external cortex (of the IC) with HRP results in retrolabeled cells in an array of neural sites. The illustrated injection which covers the upper two laminae and part of the third lamina...	r
			1	1	Red87	2302	pg155, fig2	W	1	SC/SC/PPT/NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of interned blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	ICe	Some fibres run to the cunieforn nucleus and surrounding areas. These include... the external nucleus of the inferior colliculus, Label was weak	a
SC	PRT	3	3	3	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCs	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCi	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	SCs	the largest mesencephalic input to the APc arises from the superior colliculus. In all cases numerous labeled cells were located in the superficial layers, especially in the optic layer. +ve neurons were ... distributed over entire mediolateral extent	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injns. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Lieber85	a	pg237, (n=3)	H	1	SC	6 HRP injns (which included virtually the entire extent of the stratum griseum superficiale, most of the intermediate collicular layer and the central portion of the deeper layers but did not encroach upon adjacent regions) in 3 different animals	OP	labelled terminals, recognized by their content of electron dense reaction product, were found in OPN. They were scattered sparsely in within OPN and occurred singly, rather than in clusters.	a
c		10			Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	OP/OP/???	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: a region between the npa & nto. <Corresponds to either OP or PPT, & PPT is denoted 'ppn' in paper. Assume connection is referring to OP>	a
					Foster89		pg691	W	-1	SC	anterograde transport of WGA-HRP following injection into the superior colliculus	APN	a labelling of varicose fibres in the ipsilateral APTA	a
					Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	PRT	label present in ... pretectal region	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	OP	Labelled terminals in the olivary pretectal nucleus were concentrated in the region of the peripheral 'shell' and were more difficult to detect in the central core of the nucleus	a
Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	NPC	labelled terminals were distributed uniformly throughout the ...nucleus of the posterior commissure	a					

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	APN	terminal label found in the anterior pretectal nucleus	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	NOT	labelled terminals were distributed uniformly throughout the ... nucleus of the optic tract	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	PPT/PPT/?? ?	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: npp, , (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	NOT	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: nucleus of the optic tract	a
					Perr80	R11	pg916,921, fig1	A	-1	SC	an injection of 0.5µl of [3H]leucine into the lateral and caudal part of the superior colliculus. The injection involved superficial and deep layers	PRT	Rostral to the injection site, efferent pathways were found passing directly rostral into the pretectal region	a
SC	NOT	c	c	2	Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	NOT	labelled terminals were distributed uniformly throughout the ... nucleus of the optic tract	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	NOT	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: nucleus of the optic tract	a
SC	OP	1	1	1	Lieber85	a	pg237, (n=3)	H	1	SC	6 HRP injns (which included virtually the entire extent of the stratum griseum superficiale, most of the intermediate collicular layer and the central portion of the deeper layers but did not encroach upon adjacent regions) in 3 different animals	OP	labelled terminals, recognized by their content of electron dense reaction product, were found in OPN. They were scattered sparsely in within OPN and occurred singly, rather than in clusters.	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	OP/OP/???	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: a region between the npa & nto. <Corresponds to either OP or PPT, & PPT is denoted 'ppn' in paper. Assume connection is referring to OP>	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	OP	Labelled terminals in the olivary pretectal nucleus were concentrated in the region of the peripheral 'shell' and were more difficult to detect in the central core of the nucleus	a
SC	PPT	c	c	1	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	PPT/PPT/?? ?	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: npp, , (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
SC	LD	2	2	4	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	SC	Labelled cells were also observed bilaterally in {4,5} and ipsilaterally in {6} of the superior colliculus	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	SC	Retrogradely labeled cells in the superior colliculus were found in the rostral portions of laminae 4,5,6	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCdg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SC	LGd	3	3	3	Pas82c	D	pg413, fig3, table1	H	3	SCsg	Neuronal HRP labelling was found along the rostrocaudal axis of the superior colliculus in LGBd cases, arising entirely from ipsilateral superficial grey layer with a notable absence of labelling in its caudal part	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
					Chev&Deni 84	A	pg428, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	LGd	a particularly dense fibre bunch enters brachium of SC and to follow a dorsal and ventral course to innervate the dorsal and ventral aspects of the lateral geniculate nuclei.	a
					Tur193	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	SCsg	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (iii) the superficial grey layer (SuG) and to a lesser extent of the stratum zonale (Zo) of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			2	8	Rees84	a	pg163-5, fig2,3	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. Only injections which included the stratum griseum superficiale produced terminal label within the dLGN	LGd	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the dLGN. Terminal label appeared as a single dense focus of silver grains just beneath the optic tract in 1 or 2 sections. Obvious topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
					MS83	A	pg27,29, fig1F	W	2	SC	Many small cells (8.1±1.1µm, n=68) were labelled in the superior colliculus	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r
					OgMeg92	b	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	LGd	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the lateral part of the LGNd, the LGd region containing terminal labelling was small-celled and constituted a lamina covering the outer surface of the LGNd dorsolaterally and caudally beneath the optic tract	a
					OgMeg92	c	pg61	W	2	SCop	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
					OgMeg92	d	pg61	W	2	SCsg	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
					Perr80	R11	pg916,921, fig1	A	2	SC	an injection of 0.5µl of [3H]leucine into the lateral and caudal part of the superior colliculus. The injection involved superficial and deep layers	LGd	In the thalamus ipsilaterally to the injection site, terminal label was found in the ... dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus (dLGN) ...	a
					Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	2	SCsg	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%97% neurons in SGS)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Yamas86	b	pg226	W	2	SCsg	labelled cells formed a continuous band in the lower portion of the stratum griseum superficiale. Majority of cells located in ventral 1/2 of SGS in cts mediat band	LGd	labelled superficial layer tectal cells which projected to another thalamic nucleus: the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus... WGA-HRP deposit placed within the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	r
			1	3	Tur193	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	1	SCzo	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (iii) the superficial grey layer (SuG) and to a lesser extent of the stratum zonale (Zo) of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	1	SCop	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%3% neurons in SO)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Perr80	SCd	pg916, fig4	A	1	SCig/SCdg	In three animals with injections ([3H]leucine) confined to the layers below the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	LGd	the label in LP nucleus, the dLGN, and vLGN was much reduced if not absent	a
			c	4	Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	LGd	label present in ... dLGN	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGd	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: lgd	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3,5	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	LGd	In the LGd the terminal label was restricted to one small region along the lateral margin, immediately medial to the optic tract at mid-rostrocaudal level.	a
					Rees88		conclusions page 129		-1	SC		LGd	outer shell, adjacent to optic tract & extending rostrally into nucleus, retinotopic mapping preserved btwn SC & LGd	
SC	LP	3	3	5	Solo&Nomo84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	3	SC	one of most powerful ips sources of inputs in SC{2}. ips: 50-94 cells per section, con: 4-5 cells per section	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r
					Perr80	R11	pg916, fig1	A	3	SC	an injection of 0.5µl of [3H]leucine into the lateral and caudal part of the superior colliculus. The injection involved superficial and deep layers	LP	In ipsi thalamus, terminal label was found in the ... lateral posterior (LP) nucleus ... Terminal label was dense in caudal portion (evenly distributed). Anteriorly, medial/ventral parts remain dense, lateral patchy.	a
					Tanaka85	a	pg82-3, fig1	H	3	SC	20 male rats injected with HRP into the SC under visual guidance after aspirating the overlying cerebral cortex... injns were made at various depths.	LP	Other labeled fibres were also observed in the LP. These fibres arose from the superficial layers and ran laterally in the SCop & brachium of the SC & terminated in the LP. Labeled terminals were densely distributed in the caudal half of the LP.	a
					Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	3	SCop	most of the labelled neurons found in SO, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r
					Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	3	SCop	most of the cells %76% were found in the stratum opticum, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
			2	6	Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. collico-LP axons arise from the lower half of the stratum griseum superficiale	LP	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... lateral posterior nucleus. LP also displayed broader patches of diffuse label usually separate from the discrete patches.	a
					Mas81	f	pg109, fig2	F	2	SC	labelled cells were found bilaterally in the superior colliculus	LP	EB/HRP injections made into (or encroached on) the caudal pole of LTP	r
					Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	2	SCsg	a smaller proportion of the cells (%19%) were foundd in SGS, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r
					Chev&Deni84	A	pg428, fig1,2	W	2	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	LP	dorsal to the lateral geniculate, terminal labelling was evident in the nucleus lateral posterior	a
					Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	2	SCsg	fewer cells (%24%) were found in the stratum griseum superficiale, tended to be in its deeper portion, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
					Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	2	SCop	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%92% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SO, 87ips 5con)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
			1	3	Mas81	d	pg108, fig2	F	1	SCsg	a restricted population of labelled cells in the superior colliculus which was confined ipsilaterally to the deep superficial gray layer	LP	EB/HRP injections restricted to rostral LTP	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	1	SCsg	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%8% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SGS)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Perr80	SCd	pg916, fig4	A	1	SCig/SCdg	In three animals with injections ([3H]leucine) confined to the layers below the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	LP	the label in LP nucleus, the dLGN, and vLGN was much reduced if not absent	a
		c		6	Solo&Nomo 84	b	pg141, fig1.2	H	-1	SC	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA). {2}	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
					Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	LP	label present in LP	a
					Groene88	rp8449	pg409, fig27,28,29	P	-1	SC	Three injections of WGA-HRP and three PHA-L injections were placed in the superior colliculus. in rat RP-8449 PHA-L inj site shows a number of darkly stained neurons, mainly located in the intermediate and deep layers of the SC	LP	Anterogradely labeled fibres in the dorsal thalamus are present in the lateral posterior, the mediodorsal, the central lateral, the paracentral, and the central medial nuclei	a
					Tak85	sc	pg284-295, fig5	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LPcm	nucleus lateralis posterior pars caudomedialis of both sides was labelled in every rat receiving injections into the superior colliculus. SC(med/lat)->LPcm(dor/ven.lat), SC(ant or pos/middle)->LP(med/lat)	a
					Tak85	sc	pg295, fig5	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LPic	the caudal part of the ipsilateral lpl was labeled in all rats receiving an injection of the superior colliculus (even when inj restricted to most superficial levels), contra nuc. never labeled.	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of the midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	LP	In the lateral posterior-pulvinar complex they were seen in greatest concentration in its more dorsolateral aspect	a
		0		1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SC	IGL	2	2	1	OgMeg92	a	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	IGL	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the intergeniculate nucleus	a
SC	LGv	3	3	2	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4,7a-b, table1	H	3	SCsg	HRP in the LGv labelled the CS with peculiarities: (1) consistent contra labelling observed, less than ipsi; (2) labelling found in superficial grey layer, and a few cell bodies were also found scattered in the intermediate layer	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
					Chev&Deni 84	A	pg428, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	LGv	a particularly dense fibre bunch enters brachium of SC and to follow a dorsal and ventral course to innervate the dorsal and ventral aspects of the lateral geniculate nuclei.	a
				2	Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCs	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC	LGvl	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... ventral lateral geniculate nucleus. projection to the external division of the vLGN. topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
					OgMeg92	e	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	LGv	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, ipsilaterally to inj	a
					Perr80	R11	pg916,921, fig1	A	2	SC	an injection of 0.5µl of [3H]leucine into the lateral and caudal part of the superior colliculus. The injection involved superficial and deep layers	LGv	In the thalamus ipsilaterally to the injection site, terminal label was found in the ... ventral lateral geniculate nucleus.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	SCs	... labeled neurons were found in the superficial layers of the SC. A large number of labeled neurons were distributed through the upper part of the SCop & lower SCsg in ipsilateral SC. A few labeled neurons were detected in contralateral SC in 2 cases	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368, fig2A	H	2	SCs	Superior colliculus: labeled neurons are present in the ventral portion of the ipsilateral stratum griseum superficiale	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					MS83	C	pg32	W	2	SC	In the optic stratum and deeply in the superficial gray stratum of the ipsilateral superior colliculus were labelled large multipolar cells	LGv/LGv/LGd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
		1	2		Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4,7a-b, table1	H	1	SCi	HRP in the LGv labelled the CS with peculiarities: (1) consistent contra labelling observed, less than ipsi; (2) labelling found in superficial grey layer, and a few cell bodies were also found scattered in the intermediate layer	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
					Perr80	SCd	pg916, fig4	A	1	SCig/SCdg	In three animals with injections ([3H]leucine) confined to the layers below the stratum opticum of the superior colliculus	LGv	the label in LP nucelus, the dLGN, and vLGN was much reduced if not absent	a
		c	4		Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	-1	SC	lesions ?	LGvl	Termination degeneration of fibres originating in the superior colliculus can regularly be observed in the lateral part of the LGv, bilateral projection from SC to vLGN	a
					Perr80 Taylor86	R7 1st	pg916, fig4 pg137, fig3	A H	-1	SCs/SC/PAG/MRN	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	LGv LGv	label present in ... vLGN In the LGv, labelled terminals were identified throughout the lateral sector at all rostrocaudal levels. However they were more concentrated in the ventral part around the region containing the retrogradely labelled cells	a a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGvl	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (lgv) pars externa	a
SC	LGvl	2	2	1	Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCs	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC	LGvl	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... ventral lateral geniculate nucleus. projection to the external division of the vLGN. topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
		c	2		Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	-1	SC	lesions ?	LGvl	Termination degeneration of fibres originating in the superior colliculus can regularly be observed in the lateral part of the LGv, bilateral projection from SC to vLGN	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGvl	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (lgv) pars externa	a
SCi	PRT	3	3	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCi	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
SCi	LD	2	2	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCi	LGv	1	1	1	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4,7a-b, table1	H	1	SCi	HRP in the LGv labelled the CS with peculiarities: (1) consistent contra labelling observed, less than ipsi; (2) labelling found in superficial grey layer, and a few cell bodies were also found scattered in the intermediate layer	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
SCig	LD	2	2	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCs	PRT	3	3	2	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCs	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	SCs	the largest mesencephalic input to the APc arises from the superior colliculus. In all cases numerous labeled cells were located in the superficial layers, especially in the optic layer. +ve neurons were ... distributed over entire mediolateral extent	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injns. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	PPT/PPT/???	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: npp, , (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
					Perr80 Tak85	R7 sc	pg916, fig4 pg305	A A	-1 -1	SCs SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	PRT OP/OP/???	label present in ... pretectal region The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: a region between the npa & nto. <Corresponds to either OP or PPT, & PPT is denoted 'ppn' in paper. Assume connection is referring to OP>	a a
			c	4	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	NOT	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: nucleus of the optic tract	a
SCs	NOT	c	c	1	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	NOT	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: nucleus of the optic tract	a
SCs	OP	c	c	1	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	OP/OP/???	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: a region between the npa & nto. <Corresponds to either OP or PPT, & PPT is denoted 'ppn' in paper. Assume connection is referring to OP>	a
SCs	PPT	c	c	1	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	PPT/PPT/???	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: npp, , (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
SCs	LD	0	0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCs	LGd	3	3	2	Pas82c	D	pg413, fig3, table1	H	3	SCsg	Neuronal HRP labelling was found along the rostrocaudal axis of the superior colliculus in LGBd cases, arising entirely from ipsilateral superficial grey layer with a notable absence of labelling in its caudal part	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
					Tur193	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	SCsg	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (iii) the superficial grey layer (SuG) and to a lesser extent of the stratum zonale (Zo) of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	6	OgMeg92	c	pg61	W	2	SCop	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
					OgMeg92	d	pg61	W	2	SCsg	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
					OgMeg92	b	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	LGd	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the lateral part of the LGNd, the LGd region containing terminal labelling was small-celled and constituted a lamina covering the outer surface of the LGNd dorsolaterally and caudally beneath the optic tract	a
					Yamas86	b	pg226	W	2	SCsg	labelled cells formed a continuous band in the lower portion of the stratum griseum superficiale. Majority of cells located in ventral 1/2 of SGS in cts mediat band	LGd	labelled superficial layer tectal cells which projected to another thalamic nucleus: the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus... WGA-HRP deposit placed within the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	r
					Rees84	a	pg163-5, fig2,3	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. Only injections which included the stratum griseum superficiale produced terminal label within the dLGN	LGd	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the dLGN. Terminal label appeared as a single dense focus of silver grains just beneath the optic tract in 1 or 2 sections. Obvious topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
					Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	2	SCsg	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%97% neurons in SGS)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
			1	2	Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	1	SCop	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%3% neurons in SO)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Tur93	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	1	SCzo	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (iii) the superficial grey layer (SuG) and to a lesser extent of the stratum zonale (Zo) of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			c	2	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGd	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: lgd	a
					Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	LGd	label present in ... dLGN	a
SCs	LP	3	3	2	Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	3	SCop	most of the cells %76% were found in the stratum opticum, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
					Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	3	SCop	most of the labelled neurons found in SO, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r
			2	4	Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	2	SCsg	fewer cells (%24%) were found in the stratum griseum superficiale, tended to be in its deeper portion, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
					Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	2	SCsg	a smaller proportion of the cells (%19%) were found in SGS, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r
					Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	2	SCop	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%92% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SO, 87ips 5con)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. colliculo-LP axons arise from the lower half of the stratum griseum superficiale	LP	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... lateral posterior nucleus. LP also displayed broader patches of diffuse label usually separate from the discrete patches.	a
			1	2	Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	1	SCsg	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%8% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SGS)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Mas81	d	pg108, fig2	F	1	SCsg	a restricted population of labelled cells in the superior colliculus which was confined ipsilaterally to the deep superficial gray layer	LP	EB/HRP injections restricted to rostral LTP	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	3	Tak85	sc	pg284-295, fig5	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LPcm	nucleus lateralis posterior pars caudomedialis of both sides was labelled in every rat receiving injections into the superior colliculus. SC(med/lat)->LPcm(dor/ven.lat), SC(ant or pos/middle)->LP(med/lat)	a
					Tak85	sc	pg295, fig5	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LPic	the caudal part of the ipsilateral lpl was labeled in all rats receiving an injection of the superior colliculus (even when inj restricted to most superficial levels), contra nuc. never labeled.	a
					Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	LP	label present in LP	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCs	IGL	2	2	1	OgMeg92	a	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	IGL	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the intergeniculate nucleus	a
SCs	LGv	3	3	1	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4,7a-b, table1	H	3	SCsg	HRP in the LGv labelled the CS with peculiarities: (1) consistent contra labelling observed, less than ipsi; (2) labelling found in superficial grey layer, and a few cell bodies were also found scattered in the intermediate layer	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
			2	4	OgMeg92	e	pg60	W	2	SCs	In 5 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the superficial layers of the SC	LGv	marked anterograde labelling was produced in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, ipsilaterally to inj	a
					Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCs	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC	LGvl	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, projection to the external division of the vLGN. topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
					Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	SCs	... labeled neurons were found in the superficial layers of the SC. A large number of labeled neurons were distributed through the upper part of the SCop & lower SCsg in ipsilateral SC. A few labeled neurons were detected in contralateral SC in 2 cases	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368, fig2A	H	2	SCs	Superior colliculus: labeled neurons are present in the ventral portion of the ipsilateral stratum griseum superficiale	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
			c	2	Perr80	R7	pg916, fig4	A	-1	SCs	small injection (of [3H]leucine) to superficial layers of SC	LGv	label present in ... vLGN	a
					Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGvl	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (gv) pars externa	a
SCs	LGvl	2	2	1	Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCs	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC	LGvl	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, projection to the external division of the vLGN. topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
			c	1	Tak85	sc	pg305	A	-1	SCs	collicular injections (n=6, [3H]leucine) were stereotaxically placed btwn 0.4-0.7 mm beneath pial surface, all injections involved stratum zonale, stratum griseum superficiale and the upper one-half of stratum opticum	LGvl	The following areas were labeled in all rats receiving an injection into the superior colliculus: ventral lateral geniculate nucleus (gv) pars externa	a
SCop	LGd	2	2	1	OgMeg92	c	pg61	W	2	SCop	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
			1	1	Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	1	SCop	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%3% neurons in SO)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
SCop	LP	3	3	2	Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	3	SCop	most of the labelled neurons found in SO, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	3	SCop	most of the cells %76% were found in the stratum opticum, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
			2	1	Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	2	SCop	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%92% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SO, 87ips 5con)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
SCsg	LD	0	0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCsg	LGd	3	3	2	Turl93	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	SCsg	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (iii) the superficial grey layer (SuG) and to a lesser extent of the stratum zonale (Zo) of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
					Pas82c	D	pg413, fig3, table1	H	3	SCsg	Neuronal HRP labelling was found along the rostrocaudal axis of the superior colliculus in LGBd cases, arising entirely from ipsilateral superficial grey layer with a notable absence of labelling in its caudal part	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
			2	4	Yamas86	b	pg226	W	2	SCsg	labelled cells formed a continuous band in the lower portion of the stratum griseum superficiale. Majority of cells located in ventral 1/2 of SGS in cts medlat band	LGd	labelled superficial layer tectal cells which projected to another thalamic nucleus: the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus... WGA-HRP deposit placed within the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	r
					Sug83	b	pg144, fig2B,E	H	2	SCsg	resulted in labelling of neurons in the SGS and SO ipsilaterally, no cells contralaterally. (%97% neurons in SGS)	LGd	unilateral intra-LGNd injection (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Rees84	a	pg163-5, fig2,3	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. Only injections which included the stratum griseum superficiale produced terminal label within the dLGN	LGd	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the dLGN. Terminal label appeared as a single dense focus of silver grains just beneath the optic tract in 1 or 2 sections. Obvious topography: lat/med->caud/rost	a
					OgMeg92	d	pg61	W	2	SCsg	retrogradely labelled cell bodies were seen in the SC; mainly in the stratum griseum superficiale and additionally in the stratum opticum	LGd	3 rats injected with WGA-HRP into the LGNd	r
SCsg	LP	2	2	3	Rees84	a	pg163-4	A	2	SCsg	Injections of [3H]proline into superficial layers of SC. collico-LP axons arise from the lower half of the stratum griseum superficiale	LP	highly discrete regions of densely packed silver grains were observed in the ... lateral posterior nucleus. LP also displayed broader patches of diffuse label usually separate from the discrete patches.	a
					Donnelly83	f2	pg317, fig2	H	2	SCsg	a smaller proportion of the cells (%19%) were found in SGS, also show band like topographic organization	LP	HRP injection into the ventral half of LP	r
					Donnelly83	f1	pg316, fig1	H	2	SCsg	fewer cells (%24%) were found in the stratum griseum superficiale, tended to be in its deeper portion, also show band like topographic organization	LP	injection of HRP into the dorsal part of LP	r
			1	2	Sug83	a	pg144, fig2A	H	1	SCsg	labeled neurons in the SGS ipsilaterally and in the optic lamina of the SC bilaterally (%8% of total of SC labelled neurons were found in SGS)	LP	unilateral injection of tracers (HRP or WGA-HRP)	r
					Mas81	d	pg108, fig2	F	1	SCsg	a restricted population of labelled cells in the superior colliculus which was confined ipsilaterally to the deep superficial gray layer	LP	EB/HRP injections restricted to rostral LTP	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCsg	LGv	3	3	1	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4,7a-b, table1	H	3	SCsg	HRP in the LGv labelled the CS with peculiarities: (1) consistent contra labelling observed, less than ipsi; (2) labelling found in superficial grey layer, and a few cell bodies were also found scattered in the intermediate layer	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
MEA	MPO	2	2	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	2	MEA		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg263		-1	MEA	afferent connections observed	MPN		
			x	1	McDon87		abstract		-1	MEA	double label BST	MPO	WGA-HRP injections	r
MEA	MPN	2	2	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	2	MEA		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg263		-1	MEA	afferent connections observed	MPN		
MEA	BST	x	x	1	McDon87		abstract	-1	MEA	double label MPO		BST	WGA-HRP injections	r
MA	LPO	x	x	1	Wayn83		abstract	-1	MA			LPO	HRP injections	r
MA	MPO	0	0	1	Sim&Swa86	a	pg322, fig2	F	0	MA	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.	MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
MA	MPN	0	0	1	Sim&Swa86	a	pg322, fig2	F	0	MA	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.	MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
LHA	PRT	c	c	1	Villalo&Fer ssi87		pg96, R714	-1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAc		PRT/APN	anterior pretecal area	a
LHA	SC	c	c	1	Villalo&Fer ssi87	R725	pg98, R725, fig2	A	-1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAp	SC	internal layers	a
			0	1	Cad85	Lrge	table1	H	0	LHA	no labelled cells in table	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
LHA	LPO	3	3	1	All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	3	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	LPO		a
			c	1	Grove88b		pg329-30, fig10,12, RPLH5	-1	LHA	PHA-L inj into lateral hypothalamus	LPO		a	
			x	1	Wayn83		abstract	-1	LHA	??? perifornical area	LPO	HRP injections	r	
LHA	AHA	2	2	2	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	2	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	AHN		a
					All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	AHN	parvocellular portions	a
LHA	MPO	3	3	2	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	MPN		a
					All&Cech93	f7	pg430, fig7C	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, dense group of filled cells dorsal, medial and ventral to fornix	MPO	lateral portion	a
			1	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	1	LHA	lateral hypothalamic nucleus	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264	-1	LHA	afferent connx observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r	
LHA	MPN	3	3	1	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	MPN		a
			1	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	1	LHA	lateral hypothalamic nucleus	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264	-1	LHA	afferent connx observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r	
LHA	PVH	3	3	2	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	PVH		a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					All&Cech93	f7	pg428, fig7D,3A	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, dense group of filled cells dorsal, medial and ventral to fornix	PVH	parvocellular	a
				2	All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	PVH	parvocellular portions	a
				c	Grove88b		pg329-30, fig10,12, RPLH5	-1		LHA	PHA-L inj into lateral hypothalamus	PVH		a
				x	TerHor&Lui	t87	abstract	-1		LHA		PVH	magno & parvo	
LHA	OT	c	c	1	Fall83b	f3ret	pg781, fig3	H	-1	LHA		isl	HRP inj	r
LHA	BST	3	3	1	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	3	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	BST		a
				2	All&Cech93	f7	pg430, fig7C	P	2	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, dense group of filled cells dorsal, medial and ventral to fornix	BST		a
					Grove88b		pg329-30, fig10,12, RPLH5	2		LHA	PHA-L inj into lateral hypothalamus	BST		a
				1	All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	1	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	BST	light terminal labelling	a
LHA	LD	2	2	2	Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	W	2	LHA	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the ... lateral hypothalamus ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralamina complex	r
					All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	LD		a
LHA	LGd	1	1	1	Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	LHA	in both strains <pigmented and albinos> a very small number (80-130) of neurones retrogradely labelled from injections restricted to DLG was observed in the caudal part of the lateral hypothalamic nucleus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
LPO	PRT	1	1	1	Foster89	f3	pg686, fig3	F	1	LPO	a few weakly labelled neurons were visible in the ipsilateral medial and preoptic areas	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
LPO	MEA	1	1	1	Sim&Swa88	e	pg233-4	P	1	LPO	PHA-L inj	MEA		a
LPO	MPO	c	c	1	Chib&Mura	85	pg264	-1		LPO	afferent connections observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
				0	Chib&Mura	85	table1	W	0	LPO		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
LPO	MPN	c	c	1	Chib&Mura	85	pg264	-1		LPO	afferent connections observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
				0	Chib&Mura	85	table1	W	0	LPO		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
LPO	BST	1	1	1	Sim&Swa88	e	pg233-4	P	1	LPO	PHA-L inj	BST	a few fibres in lateral	a
AHA	MEA	1	1	1	Sim&Swa88	f	pg233-4	P	1	AHA	PHA-L inj	MEA	very few	a
AHA	LPO	x	x	1	Wayn83		abstract	-1		AHA	??? anterior hypothalamic nuclei	LPO	HRP injections	r
AHA	MPO	1	1	1	Chib&Mura	85	table1	W	1	AHN		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
				c	Sim&Swa88	f	pg233-4	P	-1	AHA	PHA-L inj	MPN	mostly in MPNI	a
					Chib&Mura	85	pg264	-1		AHN	afferent conenctions observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
AHA	MPN	1	1	1	Chib&Mura	85	table1	W	1	AHN		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
				c	Sim&Swa88	f	pg233-4	P	-1	AHA	PHA-L inj	MPN	mostly in MPNI	a
					Chib&Mura	85	pg264	-1		AHN	afferent conenctions observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
AHA	PVH	2	2	1	Sim&Swa88	f	pg233-4	P	2	AHA	PHA-L inj	PVH		a
AHA	BST	2	2	1	Sim&Swa88	f	pg233-4	P	2	AHA	PHA-L inj	BST		a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
AHA	IGL	c	c	1	Moore&Car d94	b	pg404, 407, fig5	F	-1	AHA	following injections of Fluoro-Gold into IGL, there are labeled neurons in contralateral IGL, caudal thalamic reticular nucleus, SCN, & adjacent anterior hypothalamic area & retrochiasmatic area where relatively large numbers of neurons are present...	IGL/IGL/LG d/LGv	Injecting fluorescent tracer into either SCN (bilaterally) or IGL. 50-100nl of fluoro-gold injected stereotaxically (n=10)	r
AVP	MEA	1	1	1	Sim&Swa88	c	pg233	P	1	AVP	PHA-L inj	MEA		a
AVP	MPO	2	2	1	Sim&Swa88	c	pg233	P	2	AVP	PHA-L inj	MPNI		a
AVP	MPN	2	2	1	Sim&Swa88	c	pg233	P	2	AVP	PHA-L inj	MPNI		a
AVP	BST	1	1	1	Sim&Swa88	c	pg233	P	1	AVP	PHA-L inj	BST		a
MPO	PRT	1	1	1	Foster89	f3	pg686, fig3	F	1	MPO	a few weakly labelled neurons were visible in the ipsilateral medial and preoptic areas	APN	Injectons of FB into the APTN	r
MPO	MEA	2	2	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	2	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	MEA		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg263 fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	MEA	reciprocated connections	a	
MPO	LHA	2	2	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	2	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	LHA	lateral hypothalamic nucleus	a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264, fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	LHA	reciprocated connection		
			x	1	Sim&Swa88		abstract	-1	MPO		LHA			
MPO	LPO	1	1	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj		LPO		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264, fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	LPO	reciprocated projection	a	
			x	1	Wayn83		abstract	-1	MPO		LPO	HRP injections	r	
MPO	AHA	3	3	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	3	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	AHN		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264, fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	AHN	reciprocated connections	a	
MPO	PV	0	0	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	0	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	PV		a
			x	1	Sim&Swa88		abstract	-1	MPO		PVa			
MPO	PVH	c	c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg264, fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj		PVH	efferent connections	a
			0	2	Chib&Mura 85	22	table1	W	0	MPO/PV/S CH	WGA-HRP inj	PVH		a
					Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	0	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	PVH		a
			x	3	Sim&Swa88 Kawa&Mas u93 Kawan&Ma suk92		abstract abstract abstract	-1 -1 -1	MPO MPO MPO		PVH PVH PVH			
MPO	BST	3	3	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	3	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	BST		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg263, fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	BST	reciprocated connections	a	
			x	1	Sim&Swa88		abstract	-1	MPO		BST			
MPN	MEA	2	2	1	Chib&Mura 85	23	table1	W	2	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	MEA		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85		pg263 fig3	-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	MEA	reciprocated connections	a	
MPN	LHA	2	2	1	Chib&Mura	23	table1	W	2	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	LHA	lateral hypothalamic nucleus	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	λ	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					85									
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85	pg264, fig3		-1	MPN	WGA-HRP injns		LHA	reciprocated connection	
MPN	LPO	1	1	1	Chib&Mura 85	23 table1		1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj		LPO		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85	pg264, fig3		-1	MPN	WGA-HRP injns		LPO	reciprocated projection	a
MPN	AHA	3	3	1	Chib&Mura 85	23 table1		W	3 MPN	WGA-HRP inj		AHN		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85	pg264, fig3		-1	MPN	WGA-HRP injns		AHN	reciprocated connections	a
MPN	PV	0	0	1	Chib&Mura 85	23 table1		W	0 MPN	WGA-HRP inj		PV		a
MPN	PVH	c	c	1	Chib&Mura 85	pg264, fig3		-1	MPN	WGA-HRP inj		PVH	efferent connections	a
			0	1	Chib&Mura 85	23 table1		W	0 MPN	WGA-HRP inj		PVH		a
MPN	BST	3	3	1	Chib&Mura 85	23 table1		W	3 MPN	WGA-HRP inj		BST		a
			c	1	Chib&Mura 85	pg263, fig3		-1	MPN	WGA-HRP injns		BST	reciprocated connections	a
RCH	SCH	x	x	1	Marani87	abstract		-1	RCH			SCH		
RCH	IGL	c	c	1	Moore&Car d94	b pg404, 407, fig5		F	-1 RCH	following injections of Fluoro-Gold into IGL, there are labeled neurons in contralateral IGL, caudal thalamic reticular nucleus, SCN, & adjacent anterior hypothalamic area & retrochiasmatic area where relatively large numbers of neurons are present...	IGL/IGL/LG d/LGv	Injecting fluorescent tracer into either SCN (bilaterally) or IGL. 50-100nl of fluoro-gold injected stereotaxically (n=10)	r	
SCH	PRT	1	1	1	Foster89	f3 pg686, fig3		F	1 SCH	occasionally cells were visible in the suprachiasmatic and supraoptic nucleus on the same side as the dye injection		APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
SCH	MEA	c	c	1	Bons83	pg349, fig1		-1	SCH	electrolytic lesion		MEA		a
SCH	AHA	1	1	1	Watts87	A54 pg208,213, fig3H		P	1 SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally		AHA	6th Pway. A relatively small group of fibres appears to course posteriorly & laterally from Sch through retrochiasmatic & anterior hypothalamic areas to end in ventral & ventrolateral parts of cell-sparse zone surrounding VMH. Thin, small varicosities.	a
SCH	AVP	1	1	1	Watts87	A54 pg208, fig3B		P	1 SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally		AVP	1st Pway. Some of most ros fibres enter anteroventral preoptic & anteroventral periventricular nucleus... Thick convoluted fibres (narrowly spaced varic.) & thinner linear fibres (widely spaced varic). V few fibres branch/give rise to terminal boutons.	a
SCH	MPO	1	1	1	Watts87	A54 pg208, fig3D-G		P	1 SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally		MPN	2nd Pway. A relatively sparse projection to the septal region was detected: fibres course rostrally & dorsally through the lateral part of the medial preoptic nucleus ... Few clear terminal boutons were associated with this pathway.	a
			0	1	Sim&Swa86	a pg322, fig2		F	0 SCH	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.		MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
SCH	MPN	1	1	1	Watts87	A54 pg208, fig3D-G		P	1 SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally		MPN	2nd Pway. A relatively sparse projection to the septal region was detected: fibres course rostrally & dorsally through the lateral part of the medial preoptic nucleus ... Few clear terminal boutons were associated with this pathway.	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			0	1	Sim&Swa86	a	pg322, fig2	F	0	SCH	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.	MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
SCH	RCH	1	1	1	Watts87	A54	pg208,213, fig3I	P	1	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	RCH	6th Pway. A relatively small group of fibres appears to course posteriorly & laterally from Sch through retrochiasmatic & anterior hypothalamic areas to end in ventral & ventrolateral parts of cell-sparse zone surrounding VMH. Thin, small varicosities.	a
SCH	SBPV	3	3	1	Watts87	A54	pg208,212,221, fig3G-L7	P	3	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	SBPV	5th Pway, densest fibre plexus begins just dor & cau to SCH, in relatively cell sparse zone btwn the PV & AHA & continues dorsally to just ventral to PV(post. magno.) <SBPV>. Many terminal boutons. Predominantly ipsi, sparse contra.	a
SCH	PVH	2	2	1	Watts87	A54	pg208-11, fig3J-L	P	2	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	PVH	3rd Pway, pathway courses ventrally through ... anterior parts of the PVH. Fibres in the anterior parvicellular & periventricular parts of the PVH thicker, have large varicosities and display some clear terminal boutons.	a
					Bons83		pg349, fig1		-1	SCH	electrolytic lesion	PVH	a	
					Chib&Mura85	22	table1		W	0	MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	PVH	a
SCH	OT	c	c	1	Bons83		pg348, fig1		-1	SCH	electrolytic lesion	OT		a
SCH	BST	2	2	1	Watts87	A54	pg208,211, fig3G-I	P	2	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	BST	3rd Pway, pathway courses ventrally to innervate the preoptic continuation of the bed nucleus as well as parataenia & paraventricular nuc of thalamus. In PT & PVT fibres are thin, widely spaced small varicosities and give rise to many terminal boutons.	a
					Watts87	A54	pg208, fig3G-I	P	1	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	BST	2nd Pway. A small number of fibres were also observed in the ventral lateral septal nucleus, medial septal nucleus and caudal parts of the bed nucleus of the stria terminalis. Strictly ipsi. Few clear terminal boutons were associated with this pathway.	a
SCH	LGd	0	0	1	Watts&Swans87	E3	pg240	F	0	SCH	No labeled neurons were seen in region of Sch in expts E3	LGd	TB Inj in E3 was centred in dorsal lateral geniculate.	r
SCH	IGL	1	1	1	Watts87	A54	pg208,212, fig4	P	1	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	IGL	4th Pway. Relatively small number of labeled fibres ... can be traced to a term field in ventral geniculate nucleus (including the IGL). Proximal to lateral geniculate nucleus these fibres are generally V thin with small varicos & few terminal boutons	a
					Moore&Card94	b	pg404, 407, fig5	F	-1	SCH	following injections of Fluoro-Gold into IGL, there are labeled neurons in contralateral IGL, caudal thalamic reticular nucleus, SCN, & adjacent anterior hypothalamic area & retrochiasmatic area where relatively large numbers of neurons are present...	IGL/IGL/LGd/LGv	Injecting fluorescent tracer into either SCN (bilaterally) or IGL. 50-100nl of fluoro-gold injected stereotaxically (n=10)	r
SCH	LGv	2	2	1	Watts&Swans87	D2	pg240	F	2	SCH	D2 & E8 yielded greatest number of retrogradely labeled neurons in the region of the Sch. Labeled neurons in dorsolateral & perinuclear regions of the Sch	LGvm	4 animals receive injections of SITS (D2, D7, D8, D10) & 2 received implants of true-blue centred in the lateral geniculate nucleus. D2 & E3 centered in medial ventral LG, whereas D7, D8 & D10 labeled LGv/IGL/LGd.	r
					Watts87	A54	pg208,212, fig4	P	1	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	LGv	4th Pway. Relatively small number of labeled fibres ... can be traced to a term field in ventral geniculate nucleus (including the IGL). Proximal to lateral geniculate nucleus these fibres are generally V thin with small varicos & few terminal boutons	a
SCH	LGvm	2	2	1	Watts&Swans87	D2	pg240	F	2	SCH	D2 & E8 yielded greatest number of retrogradely labeled neurons in the region of the Sch. Labeled neurons in dorsolateral & perinuclear regions of the Sch	LGvm	4 animals receive injections of SITS (D2, D7, D8, D10) & 2 received implants of true-blue centred in the lateral geniculate nucleus. D2 & E3 centered in medial ventral LG, whereas D7, D8 & D10 labeled LGv/IGL/LGd.	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
PV	ICe	c	c	1	Cole&Cler87	pg218, fig1		-1		PVi/PVp/PVa	& surrounding region of HY	ICe	WGA-HRP inj	r
PV	MPO	0	0	2	Chib&Mura85	23	table1	W	0	PV		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PV		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
PV	MPN	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	23	table1	W	0	PV		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
PV	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PV		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
PV	PVH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	PVH		a
PVH	LHA	x	x	1	TerHor&Lui87	abstract		-1		PVH		LHA		
PVH	LPO	x	x	1	Wayn83	abstract		-1		PVH	(stellato-cellular)	LPO	HRP injections	r
PVH	MPO	0	0	2	Chib&Mura85	23	table1	W	0	PVH		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PVH		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Chib&Mura85	abstract		-1	PVH	periventricular area at the caudal hypothalamic level	MPN			
PVH	MPN	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	23	table1	W	0	PVH		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Chib&Mura85	abstract		-1	PVH	periventricular area at the caudal hypothalamic level	MPN			
PVH	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PVH		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
PVH	PV	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PVH		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
SO	PRT	1	1	1	Foster89	f3	pg686, fig3	F	1	SO	occasionally cells were visible in the suprachiasmatic and supraoptic nucleus on the same side as the dye injection	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
SO	MPO	0	0	1	Sim&Swa86	a	pg322, fig2	F	0	SO	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.	MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
SO	MPN	0	0	1	Sim&Swa86	a	pg322, fig2	F	0	SO	each major nucleus or area of hypothalamus reliably contained at least a few retrogradely labeled cells, with the exception of the median & magnocellular preoptic nuclei, supraoptic nucleus & suprachiasmatic nucleus.	MPN	9 implants of true blue were centred in the MPN... tracer dep more discrete & concentrated than those from pressure inj of TB suspensions; each implant involved majority of MPN & rarely adjacent structures. Could have uptake by Fibres of Pass.	r
OT	LHA	c	c	3	Fall83b	gpBret	pg781, 7C,7D,8c,10F	H	-1	isl		LHA	HRP inj	r
					Fall83b	f3ant	pg781, fig3	H	-1	isl		LHA		a
					Price91		pg449-52, fig2	H	-1	OT	deep polymorphic zone	LHA	WGA-HRP inj	r
R	ICe	1	1	1	It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	17 adult Sprague-Dawley rats were used. 3 rats received bilateral injections. Intraocular injections consisted of 1-10 microlitres of 33% HRP. In 1 case 4 microl of 1% WGA-HRP conjugat in saline was injected.	ICe	In 17 rat injections, retinal axons were traced to the contralateral pericentral nucleus of the inferior colliculus. Fibres sweep caud & lat forming a thin layer throughout much of dor pericentral IC. Smaller contingent in small area near SC.	a
R	AOS	3	3	8	Wree83	a	pg23, fig1b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250µCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5µl Ringer solution)	MT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsla terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					Giol85c	a	pg3,5	A	3	R	in each of 16 adult Sprague-Dawley rats, 80-240µCi of [3H]adenosine were injected into the vitreous of the right eye, and rat sacrificed after 4-14 days	MT	4-14 days following injections of [3H]adenosine into an eye, a dense field of silvergrains covers the neuronal population of the contralateral MTN. Labeled MTN cells on the side ipsilateral to eye inj are seldom seen.	a	
					Gully94	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3	R	1.5% of all RGcl cells, (40-49 cells/mm2)	MT	Fast Blue injections (followed by Lucifer Yellow visualization of dendrites), <LGd. <SC.	r	
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	In the group C animals, 1µl of [3H] adenosine was injected into the vitreous chamber of the left eye.	MT	Silver grains were located over cells and neuropil in the medial terminal nucleus, as well as numerous cells in the VTA. These results suggest that VTA neurons may receive retinal input, may reach VTA neurons via dendrites located within MTN	a	
					Kos71	a	pg202,4, fig4	L	3	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	MT	p204: terminal degeneration on MT very extensive & involves whole nucleus. After partial lesion of retina, degeneration in MT always diffuse & showed no signs of localization. <fig4: schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contra>	a	
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250µCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5µl Ringer solution)	DT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsla terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a	
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250µCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5µl Ringer solution)	LT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsla terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a	
					Dann87	a	pg145, fig3,4	H	3	R	F	Cells labeled with HRP evenly distributed throughout the whole retina... density of distribution highest in central retina and attenuated peripherally... highest temp-nasal axis. btwn retina... total number of MTN cells from 1703-1784 (1.5% of all Rgcls)	MT	Examination of retinae after HRP injection into the MTN (also injections of FB into MTN)	r
		2		3	Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	DT	p206: terminal distribution of fibre bundles... greater sparseness of retinal output to dorsal & lateral terminal nuclei. <fig4: schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contralateral >	a	
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	LT	p206: terminal distribution of fibre bundles... greater sparseness of retinal output to dorsal & lateral terminal nuclei. <fig4: schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contralateral >	a	
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	MT	A partially quantitative estimate of the size of these projections can be obtained from table 1: right MT - 39.2±3.1, left MT - 295.2±22.4 DPM/mg dry weight tissue. (background - ie level in VIS, MOs/ACA, HY, SEP = 30-60)	a	
		c		12	Yama83	b	pg218	H	-1	R	In the second group of 7 rats, right dorsal terminal nucleus and/or lateral terminal nucleus were injured by an electrical coagulation. After 1/2 weeks 3microl of 20% HRP soln in saline was injected into vitreous body of left eye.	DT	In 2 cases which received injection of HRP in left eye & lesion in area including lateral terminal nucleus and dorsal fasciculus on right side, DT & dors fasc dorsal to injured site showed almost same amount of HP reaction product as control.	a	
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	MT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C,) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a	
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	LT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C,) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a	
					Yama83	b	pg218, fig1D	H	-1	R	In the second group of 7 rats, right dorsal terminal nucleus and/or lateral terminal nucleus were injured by an electrical coagulation. After 1/2 weeks 3microl of 20% HRP soln in saline was injected into vitreous body of left eye.	LT/DT/???	In 3 cases received HRP inj in left vitreous body 1/2 wks after DT(r) lesion, no HRP reaction product seen in dors fasc of RHS. LT seemed to contain HRP r.p. & to be connected with MT by lat fasc (fig1D) <Not clear, lesions affect f.o.p. & HRP trans>	a	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Reperant87	pg601, fig1		A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	DT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal dorsal	a
					Reperant87	pg601, fig1		A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal latéral	a
					Reperant87	pg601, fig1		A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	MT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal médian	a
					Schnyd84	pg505		W	-1	R	the tracer (injected into the vitreous body of one eye) 3-5μl of [125I] wheat germ agglutinin, [3H] proline	MT	All intraocular injections showed anterograde transport of label to ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system	a
					Teru84	pg288, fig1			-1	R	Whole Mount	LT		
					Teru84	pg288, fig1			-1	R	Whole Mount	MT		
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	DT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C.) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a
					Murabe83	pg152, fig1		L	-1	R	Enucleated left eyes on first postnatal day, & HRP soln injection into right eyeball and pathways illustrated with TMB method.	AOS	the pathways of the accessory including its terminal nuclei were visualized	a
R	DT	3	3	1	Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250μCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5μl Ringer solution)	DT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsal terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	DT	p206: terminal distribution of fibre bundles... greater sparseness of retinal output to dorsal & lateral terminal nuclei. <fig4: schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contralateral >	a
					Yama83	b	pg218	H	-1	R	In the second group of 7 rats, right dorsal terminal nucleus and/or lateral terminal nucleus were injured by an electrical coagulation. After 1/2 weeks 3microl of 20% HRP soln in saline was injected into vitreous body of left eye.	DT	In 2 cases which received injection of HRP in left eye & lesion in area including lateral terminal nucleus and dorsal fasciculus on right side, DT & dors fasc dorsal to injured site showed almost same amount of HP reaction product as control.	a
					Reperant87	pg601, fig1		A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	DT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal dorsal	a
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	DT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C.) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a
R	LT	3	3	1	Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250μCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5μl Ringer solution)	LT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsal terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	LT	p206: terminal distribution of fibre bundles... greater sparseness of retinal output to dorsal & lateral terminal nuclei. <fig4: schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contralateral >	a
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	LT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C.) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a
					Reperant87	pg601, fig1		A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal latéral	a
					Teru84	pg288, fig1			-1	R	Whole Mount	LT		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
R	MT	3	3	6	Wree83	a	pg23, fig1b	A	3	R	After unilateral intravitreal injection... (250µCi L-[4,5-3H] leucine in 5µl Ringer solution)	MT	one can that the fasciculi of the accessory optic tract reach the contralateral medial lateral and dorsla terminal nuclei which are heavily labelled	a
					Giol85c	a	pg3,5	A	3	R	in each of 16 adult Sprague-Dawley rats, 80-240µCi of [3H]adenosine were injected into the vitreous of the right eye, and rat sacrificed after 4-14 days	MT	4-14 days following injections of [3H]adenosine into an eye, a dense field of silvergrains covers the neuronal population of the contralateral MTN. Labeled MTN cells on the side ipsilateral to eye inj are seldom seen.	a
					Gully94	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3	R	1.5% of all RGcl cells, (40-49 cells/mm2)	MT	Fast Blue injections (followed by Lucifer Yellow visualization of dendrites), <LGd. <SC.	r
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	In the group C animals, 1µl of [3H] adenosine was injected into the vitreous chamber of the left eye.	MT	Silver grains were located over cells and neuropil in the medial terminal nucleus, as well as numerous cells in the VTA. These results suggest that VTA neurons may receive retinal input, may reach VTA neurons via dendrites located within MTN	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,4, fig4	L	3	R	p202: in 15 animals lesions of various sectors of retina were made with a heated needle. In 20 animals one eye was enucleated.	MT	p204: terminal degeneration on MT very extensive & involves whole nucleus. After partial lesion of retina, degeneration in MT always diffuse & showed no signs of localization. <fig4- schematic suggest degree of degen in MT greater than DT & LT, contra>	a
					Dann87	a	pg145, fig3,4	H F	3	R	Cells labeled with HRP evenly distributed throughout the whole retina... density of distribution highest in central retina and attenuated peripherally... highest temp-nasal axis. btwn retina... total number of MTN cells from 1703-1784 (1.5% of all Rgcls)	MT	Examination of retinae after HRP injection into the MTN (also injections of FB into MTN)	r
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	MT	A partially quantitative estimate of the size of these projections can be obtained from table 1: right MT - 39.2±3.1, left MT - 295.2±22.4 DPM/mg dry weight tissue. (background - ie level in VIS, MOs/ACA, HY, SEP = 30-60)	a
					Yama83	c	pg217,219	H	-1	R	In the third group of 5 rats the same amount of HRP was injected into the vitreous body of one eye.	MT	In third group, HRP reaction product was seen in fibers of anterior, dorsal (fig 1C.) and lateral (fig2D) as well as in their relevant terminal nuclei	a
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A H F	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	MT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralemet (avec une prédominace controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... terminal médian	a
					Schnyd84		pg505	W	-1	R	the tracer (injected into the vitreous body of one eye) 3-5µl of [125I] wheat germ agglutinin, [3H] proline	MT	All intraocular injections showed anterograde transportof label to ... medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic system	a
Teru84		pg288, fig1		-1	R	Whole Mount	MT							
R	PRT	3	3	6	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	NOT	The label was densely distributed over NOT but with less clearly defined borders than in the geniculate nucleus or PO <OP>. No label was found ipsilaterally	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	OP	In the autoradiographs the whole contralateral olivary nucleus is densely labelled and can be seen to have a leaflet slightly separate from the main body of the nucleus in a more medial and ventral position. There is a small ipsi projection to core of PO.	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	PRT	The label in the dorsal geniculate, pretectal area, & superior colliculus is so intense that we were unable to resolve whether these fibres come from the retino-geniculate path, the retino-tectal path or both.	a
					Scal&Aran7 9	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	NOT	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as ... NTO. derived exclusively from the contralateral eye	a
					Scal&Aran7 9	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	PPT	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as ... PP. ... contain both crossed and uncrossed components, i>c.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	OP	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as PO ... contain both crossed and uncrossed components. ipsi: two parallel subfields: lat & med; contra: main bulk ros, with 2 tails: med & lat	a
			2	1	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	PRT	Medium labeling overlies pretectal area, lateral posterior nucleus and an area rostral to these nuclei (???)	a
			1	1	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	PPT	Label was found in the most dorsal part of PP sometimes as a single focus but occasionally as two or more small foci. There was also a small ipsilateral projection to the dorsal part of PP. <q.v. fig1 label appears sparse>	a
			c	4	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	NOT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette controlatéralement sur les noyaux du tractus optique ...	a
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	OP	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... olivaire prétectal	a
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	PPT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette controlatéralement sur les noyaux du ... et prétectal postérieur	a
					Murabe83		pg152-6, fig1	L	-1	R	Enucleated left eyes on first postnatal day, & HRP soln injection into right eyeball and pathways illustrated with TMB method.	PRT	As shown in fig1 ... the pretectal area ... on the side contralateral to the intraocular injection were identified as blue reaction products. On ips. side, sparse fibres in optic tract terminated at ros of PRT	a
			x	1	Urush88		abstract		-1	R		NOT		
R	NOT	3	3	2	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	NOT	The label was densely distributed over NOT but with less clearly defined borders than in the geniculate nucleus or PO <OP>. No label was found ipsilaterally	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	NOT	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as ... NTO. derived exclusively from the contralateral eye	a
			c	1	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	NOT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette controlatéralement sur les noyaux du tractus optique ...	a
			x	1	Urush88		abstract		-1	R		NOT		
R	OP	3	3	2	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	OP	In the autoradiographs the whole contralateral olivary nucleus is densely labelled and can be seen to have a leaflet slightly separate from the main body of the nucleus in a more medial and ventral position. There is a small ipsi projection to core of PO.	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	OP	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as PO ... contain both crossed and uncrossed components. ipsi: two parallel subfields: lat & med; contra: main bulk ros, with 2 tails: med & lat	a
			c	1	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	OP	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... olivaire prétectal	a
R	PPT	3	3	1	Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	PPT	dense aggregates of silver grains were located over the cell masses previously identified as ... PP. ... contain both crossed and uncrossed components, i>c.	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			1	1	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	PPT	Label was found in the most dorsal part of PP sometimes as a single focus but occasionally as two or more small foci. There was also a small ipsilateral projection to the dorsal part of PP, <q.v. fig1 label appears sparse>	a
			c	1	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	PPT	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette controlatéralement sur les noyaux du ... et prétectal postérieur	a
R	SC	3	3	11	Gully94	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3	R	In the con. retinae a roughly circular region had labelled cells... Nearly all neurons with cell bodis larger than 7-8µm were labelled... 47% of all neurons in labelled patch were labelled, 50% of cells in Rgcl project to brain (>90%) [Perry81, Nsci6:931]	SCs	small deposits off HRP confined to the tectum of one side... a region of the of the superficial layers of the superior colliculus was filled with a dark-brown reaction product with variable extension to deep layers... no sign of spread to pretectum or others...	r
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	SC	The label in the dorsal geniculate, pretectal area, & superior colliculus is so intense that we were unable to resolve whether these fibres come from the retino-geniculate path, the retino-tectal path or both.	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	SCs	contra projection to superior colliculus showed even distribution of label throughout SCsg & deeper two-thirds of SCzo. SCop was also labelled but probably FoP. small ipsi proj to anterlat. part of SCop.	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 53% HRP in 0.9% saline	SC	heaviest labeling located in primary optic pathway: dorsal & ventral lateral geniculate nuclei, Brachium of superior colliculus & SC.	a
					Lind83a	a	pg146-147	H	3	R	In the contralateral retinae a roughly circular region had labelled cells... Nearly all neurons with cell bodis larger than 7-8µm were labelled... 47% of all neurons in labelled patch were labelled, 50% of cells in Rgcl project to brain. [Perry81, Nsci6:931]	SC	small deposits off HRP confined to the tectum of one side... a region of the of the superficial layers of the superior colliculus was filled with a dark-brown reaction product with variable extension to deep layers... no sign of spread to pretectum or others...	r
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	3	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	SC	A partially quantitative estimate of the size of these projections can be obtained from table 1: right SC - 140.1±16.3, left SC - 5878±8.7 DPM/mg dry weight tissue. (background - ie level in VIS, MOs/ACA, HY, SEP = 30-60)	a
					Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	intraocular HRP (in DMSO) injections into two rats (DN1, DN3)	SCs	ips: clusters of terminal label across mediolateral extent of rostral 1/3 of SC, across SCop/SCsg border. Small clusters along roscau axis close to med. border of SC (crescent fig4). con: homogeneous label through sup. layers <f3: extension into ig??>	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCop	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCsg	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg277, fig1,3,4	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	SCs	distribution of label in stratum griseum superficiale of contra superior colliculus examined for uniformity (used as indication of absence of R or op damage). <in fig 1 label is very dense. fig3/4 label seems to be conc in SGs, dSCs=3, dSCi=?, dSCd=0.>	a
					Dre85	a	pg30, fig9C	H	3	R	1195 cells labelled in 0.46 mm2 patch	SC	HRP inj	r
			2	2	Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCi	significant amount of linear & punctate axon labeling below SCop on either side... several labeled axons could be traced out of brachium of SC & SCop into intermediate gray layer. In many places, axons extend through SCig to upper margin of SCiw	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCig	8 rat cases... In contra SC, amount of axon labeling in intermediate gray layer relative to that in superficial layers sig. greater than in monkey or cat... densest rostrally, persists throughout SCig to caudal pole. Very few, if any, fibres on ipsi	a
			c	5	Cow&Per79		pg463, fig3	H	-1	R	small area of temporal R, very sparse, ipsilateral projection to SC smaller than ips projection to LG	SC	3 rats with (HRP) injections aimed at the superior colliculus of one hemisphere, only small region of ipsilateral SC contains label. <No mention of contralateral R-SC connection>	r
					Reese&Cowey87		pg954-6, fig4	L	-1	R	7 rats with retinal lesions in one eye, intraocular injections of [3H] proline & retrograde labelling from LGd to mark temporal crescent	SC	figure 4 shows locus of anterograde labelling in superior colliculus contralateral to the lesion. degeneration confined to rostral border of the SC (ros.med. for lesions in ven part of crescent and ros.lat. for more dorsal lesions)	a
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	SCs	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilatéralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les couches superficielle de colliculus supérieur	a
					Rees&Cow83		pg1235-6, fig4	L	-1	R	retinal lesions produced with a laser ophthalmoscope	SC	... gave degeneration of variable extent within the ... superior colliculus. <Do not understand discrepancies btwn this and HRP inj>	a
					Murabe83		pg152-6, fig1	L	-1	R	Enucleated left eyes on first postnatal day, & HRP soln injection into right eyeball and pathways illustrated with TMB method.	SC	As shown in fig1 ... the superior colliculus on the side contralateral to the intraocular injection were identified as blue reaction products. Most of surface of ips colliculus was filled with HRP	a
			0	2	Scal&Aran79	a	pg277, fig1,3,4	A	0	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	SCd	<in fig 1 label is very dense. fig3/4 label seems to be conc in SGs, dSCs=3, dSCi=?, dSCd=0.>	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	eye injections of 25μCi of [3H]leucine	SCi	<Very little labeling in sgi (SCig) shown in fig1. No description in text so assume little/or no connection>	a
R	SCi	2	2	2	Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCi	significant amount of linear & punctate axon labeling below SCop on either side... several labeled axons could be traced out of brachium of SC & SCop into intermediate gray layer. In many places, axons extend through SCig to upper margin of SCiw	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCig	8 rat cases... In contra SC, amount of axon labeling in intermediate gray layer relative to that in superficial layers sig. greater than in monkey or cat... densest rostrally, persists throughout SCig to caudal pole. Very few, if any, fibres on ipsi	a
			0	1	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	eye injections of 25μCi of [3H]leucine	SCi	<Very little labeling in sgi (SCig) shown in fig1. No description in text so assume little/or no connection>	a
R	SCig	2	2	1	Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCig	8 rat cases... In contra SC, amount of axon labeling in intermediate gray layer relative to that in superficial layers sig. greater than in monkey or cat... densest rostrally, persists throughout SCig to caudal pole. Very few, if any, fibres on ipsi	a
R	SCs	3	3	6	Gully94	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3	R	In the con. retinae a roughly circular region had labelled cells... Nearly all neurons with cell bodis larger than 7-8μm were labelled... 47% of all neurons in labelled patch were labelled, 50% of cells in Rgcl project to brain (>90%) [Perry81, Nsci6:931]	SCs	small deposits off HRP confined to the tectum of one side... a region of the of the superficial layers of the superior colliculus was filled with a dark-brown reaction product with variable extension to deep layers... no sign of spread to pretectum or others...	r
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25μCi of [3H]leucine	SCs	contra projection to superior colliculus showed even distribution of label throughout SCsg & deeper two-thirds of SCzo. SCop was also labelled but probably FoP. small ipsi proj to anterlat. part of SCop.	a
					Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	intraocular HRP (in DMSO) injections into two rats (DN1, DN3)	SCs	ips: clusters of terminal label across mediolateral extent of rostral 1/3 of SC, across SCop/SCsg border. Small clusters along roscau axis close to med. border of SC (crescent fig4). con: homogeneous label through sup. layers <f3: extension into ig??>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCop	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCsg	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg277, fig1,3,4	A	3	R	Eye injection of [3H]proline into 17 Rats (albinos and pigmented)	SCs	distribution of label in stratum griseum superficiale of contra superior colliculus examined for uniformity (used as indication of absence of R or op damage). <in fig 1 label is very dense. fig3/4 label seems to be conc in SGs, dSCs=3, dSCi=?, dSCd=0.>	a
			c	1	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine B isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	SCs	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les couches superficielle de colliculus supérieur	a
R	SCop	3	3	1	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCop	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
R	SCsg	3	3	1	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	retinotectal projection investigated in 8 hooded rats... received an injection of 50% aqueous solution of HRP in vitreal chamber of the eye... single 4microl inj of HRP	SCsg	<label very dense & homogeneous in figure 4>	a
R	MEA	1	1	1	Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MEA	Still more caudally, at the level of the supraoptic decussation and the retrochiasmatic SON, a sparse innervation of the medial and medial posteroventral amygdaloid nuclei could be observed. terminals along the perimetre & within nuclei.	a
R	MA	c	c	1	Levine91	a	pg352	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MA	terminal label at these more caudal levels continued to be evident in ... the magnocellular preoptic nucleus as well.	a
R	LHA	2	2	1	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	LHA	retinohypothalamic tract 3 components: 3)fairly dense terminal plexus in the LHA. (extends from the lateral border of the optic tract over the supraoptic nucleus)	a
			1	1	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	LHA	The lateral component of the RHT consisted mainly of a scattered projection in the lateral hypothalamus... As noted above, diffuse labeling in the lateral hypothalamic area ... was evident.	a
			c	1	Lenine94	a	pg216,7, fig4B	C	-1	R	34 rats (remainder after preliminary studies) used. injections of cholera toxin conjugated to horseradish peroxidase (CT-HRP) into left eye, then given one of following treatments: PRV(Be) in left eye (11); PRV(Ba) into right eye, 5: Ba in PITpos	SOperi	In brightfield peri-SON terminal field, defined by CT-HRP occurs solely on contralateral side. Black finely distributed reaction product over dorsal border of SON caudal to optic chiasm where of begin to ascend sides of diencephalon	a
			0	3	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	LHA	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	10 albino rats... unilateral enucleation was performed in either newborn animals or 5 days after birth. 3 until 7 months later between 50 & 150 micro Ci of 3H leucine or 3H proline have been injected into the remaining eye.	LHA	In all autoradiographs from enucleated animals an increased number of silver grains was found within a localised area of the AHL. crest-like shape & was restricted dorsally to the contralateral SON. <Only present in enucleated animals.>	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	65 animals (albino rats) which had been injected uni or bilaterally with various amounts of tritiated leucine between 2 to 20 days prior to killing.	LHA	Analysis of autoradiographs of unoperated animals revealed labelling of the area in question on only 3 brain series.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
R	SOperi	c	c	1	Lenine94	a	pg216,7, fig4B	C	-1	R	34 rats (remainder after preliminary studies) used. injections of cholera toxin conjugated to horseradish peroxidase (CT-HRP) into left eye, then given one of following treatments: PRV(Be) in left eye (11); PRV(Ba) into right eye, 5: Ba in PITpos	SOperi	In brightfield peri-SON terminal field, defined by CT-HRP occurs solely on a contralateral side. Black finely distributed reaction product over dorsal border of SON caudal to optic chiasm where it begins to ascend sides of diencephalon	a
R	LPO	c	c	1	Levine91	a	pg351, fig5a-f	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	LPO	In addition label evident in ventral part of the lateral preoptic area	a
R	AHA	2	2	2	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	AHA	retinohypothalamic tract 3 components: 2) extension of SCN axonal plexus into the AHA and the RCA. this is sparse rostrally and grows increasingly dense caudally, where it extends to a wide zone caudal to the SCN including AHA & RCA	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	2	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AHA	Medial component of the RHT... swept dorsally through the central part of the anterior hypothalamic area where it began to disperse. terminals evident in med. anterior and central anterior hypothalamic areas.	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AHNa	Med. component of the RHT... in addition, labeled fibres & terms were found lateral to the lateral boundary of the SCN, in the lateroanterior hypothalamic nucleus. Lat component diffuse labeling ... in the lateroanterior hypothalamic nucleus ... was evident	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	AHA	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
R	AHNa	1	1	1	Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AHNa	Med. component of the RHT... in addition, labeled fibres & terms were found lateral to the lateral boundary of the SCN, in the lateroanterior hypothalamic nucleus. Lat component diffuse labeling ... in the lateroanterior hypothalamic nucleus ... was evident	a
R	AVP	c	c	1	Levine91	a	pg351, fig5a-e	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AVP	Terminal label evident ... throughout the anteroventral preoptic nucleus.	a
R	MPO	1	1	2	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MPO	Medial component of the RHT included labeled fibres and terminals found near the midline... involved the medial half of the medial preoptic area... terminals evident in the anterior medial preoptic area <Paper describes a.m.p.a. as separate region>	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MPN	Medial component of the RHT included labeled fibres and terminals found near the midline... involved the medial half of the medial preoptic area... terminals evident in the ventral part of the medial preoptic nucleus	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352, fig5a-f	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MPO	in preoptic region ros. to SCN. lat. component of RHT labeled terminals & fibres within or lateral to the lateral half of the medial preoptic area... Terminal label evident in ven. 1/2 of the lateral part of the medial preoptic area	a
R	MPN	1	1	1	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	MPN	Medial component of the RHT included labeled fibres and terminals found near the midline... involved the medial half of the medial preoptic area... terminals evident in the ventral part of the medial preoptic nucleus	a
R	RCH	2	2	2	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	RCH	retinohypothalamic tract 3 components: 2) extension of SCN axonal plexus into the AHA and the RCA. this is sparse rostrally and grows increasingly dense caudally, where it extends to a wide zone caudal to the SCN including AHA & RCA	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	RCH	Medial component of the RHT included labeled fibres and terminals found near the midline... entered the retrochiasmatic area ... Along this path (extension of the medial component of the RHT) terminals were evident in the retrochiasmatic area	a
			0	1	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	RCH	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
R	SBPV	2	2	1	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	SBPV	Medial component of the RHT included labeled fibres and terminals found near the midline... finally disappearing in the subparaventricular zone	a
			0	1	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	SBPV	Plexus does not extend into the subparaventricular zone, nor laterally as far as the fornix	a
R	SCH	3	3	3	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	SCH	retinohypothalamic tract 3 components: 1) largest is innervation of SCN. Rostral SCN: a very dense band of terminals at border of SCN and optic chiasm, Mid SCN: most of ven.lat. component of nuc filled with dense terminal plexus, remainder less dense	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	SCH	Medial component of the RHT ... a) inbtwn 2 SCNs under v3, b) ven. lat. to SCN, appear to cradle it ... high density of terminal labeling in & around SCN. (ven.lat. parts of ros. SCN, venlat. dorlat. parts of cau. SCN.) dormed. subncl of SCN largely spared.	a
					deVries93	a	pg235, fig3	C	3	R	4 male brown Norweg. rats were bilaterally injected in the vitreous of the eyes with 8µl of 0.1% HRP conjugated ti cholera toxin, B subunit. also use glutamate immunoreactivity	SCH	In rostral SCN, labelling found in in the ventral part of the nucleus lining the optic chiasm. In the middle and caudal SCN dense labeling was also present along the ventrolateral and dorsolateral side of the nucleus, almost no lab in dor.med. part of SCN	a
			2	1	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	SCH	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
			c	2	Ibat89		pg3	L	-1	R	8 rats were bilaterally eye enucleated under Nembutal anaesthesia	SCH	degenerating myelinated axons were also found within the ventral part of the SCN of the enucleated animals... degenerating axon terminals formed synapses with VIP-like immunoreactive neuronal elements: denrites, perikarya, and axons	a
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	SCH	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux suprachiasmaticque, ...	a
R	PV	1	1	1	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3c	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	PV	Along this path (extension of the medial component of the RHT) terminals were evident in the periventricular nucleus	a
R	PVH	2	2	1	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	PVH	Medial component of the RHT: a few fibres were seen in the PVN in some rats but this label was not consistently evident	a
			0	1	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	PVH	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
R	SO	1	1	2	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	2 adult male hooded rats and 5 adult male albino rats were used. each received an injection of CT-HRP into the posterior chamber of the eye.	SO	There are scattered terminals within the supraoptic nucleus	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Levine91	a	pg351, fig6b	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	SO	The lateral component of the RHT consisted mainly of a scattered projection in the ... supraoptic nucleus. a low density of terminals was evident within the SON itself along its entire rostrocaudal extent.	a
			0	2	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	SO	There is no labelling in the supraoptic nucleus immediately adjacent to the heavily labeled contralateral optic tract	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	SO	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
			x	1	Levine94		abstract			R		SO		
R	OT	c	c	1	Levine91	a	pg351	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	OT	In addition label evident in ... along the base of the brain in the olfactory tubercle	a
R	BST	1	1	2	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	BST	Medial component of RHT: The ventral portion of the medial posterolateral bed nucleus of the stria terminalis was also involved in this projection	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	BST	HRP labeled retinal fibres & terminals found in the contra BNST... HRP granules formed a dense cluster, reminiscent of the terminal labeling in LGd and SC. Most of HRP label traced to med. area of pos. tail of BNST. <dots in fig2: lightest labelling>	a
			c	3	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	BST	quelques axones optiques courent à travers la strie terminale pour s'arboriser dans la portion postérieure du noyau prethalamique (ou noyau du lit de la strie terminale BNST)	a
					Levine91	a	pg353-4	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	BST	fibres can be seen in stria terminalis coursing rostrally from these more caudal levels. This pathway gives rise to the thalamic label reported earlier (anterior dorsal, anterior ventral thalamic nuc. & bed nuc. of the stria terminalis.)	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	BST	The dorsal extent of the diffuse terminal fields extended to the level of the medial posterolateral bed nucleus of the stria terminalis ventral to the fornix	a
R	NDB-h	c	c	1	Levine91	a	pg351, fig5	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	NDB-h	Finally, the medial aspect of the preoptic horizontal limb of the diagonal band also received a projection... terminal label at these more caudal levels continued to be evident in the nuc of the hor. limb of the diagonal band of Broca	a
R	AD	1	1	1	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	AD	HRP labeled retinal fibres and terminals were found in the ... contralateral anterodorsal thalamic nucleus. <dots in fig2: lightest labelling>	a
			c	2	Reperant87		pg602, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	AD	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent successivement sur les noyaux ... antérodorsal (AD)	a
					Levine91	a	pg353-4	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AD	fibres can be seen in stria terminalis coursing rostrally from these more caudal levels. This pathway gives rise to the thalamic label reported earlier (anterior dorsal, anterior ventral thalamic nuc. & bed nuc. of the stria terminalis.)	a
R	AV	1	1	1	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	AV	HRP labeled retinal fibres and terminals were found in the ... contralateral anteroventral thalamic nucleus. <dots in fig2: lightest labelling>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	2	Levine91	a	pg353-4	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AV	fibres can be seen in stria terminalis coursing rostrally from these more caudal levels. This pathway gives rise to the thalamic label reported earlier (anterior dorsal, anterior ventral thalamic nuc. & bed nuc. of the stria terminalis.)	a
					Reperant87		pg602, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	AV	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent successivement sur les noyaux ... antéro ventral (AV)	a
R	LD	c	c	1	Reperant87		pg601-2, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LD	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent successivement sur les noyaux latéral antérieur(LA) ...	a
R	LGd	3	3	13	Rees88	a	Fig2A,B; pg121-3	H	3	R	HRP injection	LGd	con: covers most of nucleus except for small patch corresponding to ipsilateral connection, ips: irregular shape, tends to be segregated from region of contralateral input, medial position	a
					Rees&Cow8 3	a	pg1235, figs1,2,3	H	3	R	Anterograde transport of horseradish peroxidase from the eye	LGd	Ipsi: medial region in dLGN along greater rostrocaudal length viewed in X-section, throughout rostral 3/4. Contra: only a small region devoid of HRP filled terminals, ipsi. label covers region medial to island overlapping contra. label.	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	LGd	In both the albino and hooded rats, contralateral DGL receives an extensive retinal projection. ...projections to the ipsilateral DGL appear to be more extensive in hooded rats.	a
					Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	LGd	proj. from contralateral eye to the dLGN was dense except for a small region situated dorsomedially in the central half of the nucleus, which has a sparse if not absent con proj and ... is the region receiving part of the ips proj. ips/con overlap exists	a
					Gully94	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (173cells/.25mm)=1092 cells/mm2 labelled (36%)	LGd	HRP injection into LGd (large injection)	r
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	LGd	The label in the dorsal geniculate, pretectal area, & superior colliculus is so intense that we were unable to resolve whether these fibres come from the retino-geniculate path, the retino-tectal path or both.	a
					Mart86	a	table 1: AD1	H	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (277cells/.25mm) = 1108 cells/mm2 labelled (labelled/estimated total = %37%). MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 14.4 um. cells smaller than AV injections. 5-10% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP + 5% DMSO injection into Anterodorsal LGd, (and encroached on optic tract neurons...)	r
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	LGd	heaviest labeling located in primary optic pathway: dorsal & ventral lateral geniculate nuclei, Brachium of superior colliculus & SC.	a
					Mart86		table 1: PD2	H	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (88cells/.21mm) = 415 cells/mm2 labelled (14%). MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 12.3um. cells smaller than AV injections. 5-10% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP injection into anteroventral LGd	r
					Mart86		table 1: PD1	H	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (87cells/.16mm) = 543 cells/mm2 labelled (labelled/estimated total=18-14%) MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 11.5 um. cells smaller than AV injections. 5-10% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP injection into anteroventral LGd, injection 2 wks after lesion of SC	r
					Mart86		table 1: DLG2	H	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (61cells/.16mm) = 381 cells/mm2 labelled (19-13%)	LGd	HRP injection into LGd (large injection)	r
					Mart86		table 1: DLG1	H	3	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (173cells/.25mm)=1092 cells/mm2 labelled (36%)	LGd	HRP injection into LGd (large injection)	r
					Dre85	a	pg30, fig9D	H	3	R	344 cells labelled in 0.46 mm2 patch	LGd	HRP inj	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T			
			2	2	Mart86		table 1: AV3	H	2	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (40cells/59mm) = 67 cells/mm2 labelled (labelled/estimated total=2%). MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 17.7 um. cells larger than AD/PD injections. >50% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP + 5% DMSO injection into anteroventral (inner core?) LGd	r			
					Mart86		table 1: AV1	H	2	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. CELL NUMBERS: (32 cells/80mm) = 40 cells/mm2 labelled (labelled/estimated total = 2%). MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 15.8 um. cells larger than AD/PD injections. >50% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP injection into anteroventral (inner core?) LGd, injection 2 wks after lesion of SC	r			
			1	1	Mart86		table 1: AV2	H	1	R	labelled cells outside area centralis. (24cells/4.6mm) = 5 cells/mm2 labelled (labelled/estimated total<1%). MEAN SOMAL SIZE = 16.4 um. cells larger than AD/PD injections. >50% of cells were type I.	LGd	HRP + 5% DMSO injection into anteroventral (inner core?) LGd	r			
			c	6	Rees&Cow83		pg1235-6, fig4	L	-1	R	retinal lesions produced with a laser ophthalmoscope	LGd	... gave degeneration of variable extent within the dLGN. Correlation between rostrocaudal extent of the lesion and the location of the ipsilateral degeneration. <Do not understand discrepancies btwn this and HRP inj>	a			
					Rees88		conclusions, page 129.		-1	R	smaller type II & III cells [Mart86] with thinner, slower axons [Fuku80, Gab85], recives W cell input from whole of R(c)	LGd	outer shell or outer caudodorsal lamina. Smaller smaller relay neurons [Gabb86] conducting more slowly to VIS [Fuku74, Fuku79, Hale79], can see shell/core border on myeloarchitecture of nucleus (see fig1D,F)				
					Reese&Cowey87		pg956-958, fig5,6	L	-1	R	7 rats with retinal lesions in one eye, intraocular injections of [3H] proline & retrograde labelling from LGd to mark temporal crescent	LGd	fig5 shows sections through the dLGN. In every case the region and the amount of degeneration was very small	a			
					Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LGd	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... genouillé latéral dorsal (GLd)	a			
					Rees88		conclusions, page 129.		-1	R	type III cells & large type I Rgcl [Mart86], I cells with thick rapidly conducting axons [Fuku80, Gab85] that give rise to coarse, sparse arborizations [Braun79]	LGd	inner core or inner rostroventral lamina. Large cells [Gabb86] probably conduct rapidly to VIS [Fuku74, Fuku79, Hale79], can see shell/core border on myeloarchitecture of nucleus (see fig1D,F)				
					MS83	A	pg27		-1	R	labelled cells in retina ...	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r			
R	LP	2	2	1	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10μl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	LP	Medium labeling overlies pretectal area, lateral posterior nucleus and an area rostral to these nuclei (???)	a			
					1	2	Perr82			H	1	R	pg587, fig2	eye injections of HRP.	LP	In the normal rat a small projection is found from the retina to the LP. This projection is most readily observed in HRP material and clumps of terminals are found in the lateral part of LP. the distribution of the clumps varies somewhat btwn animals.	a
					Gully94	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	HRP injection, small projection.	LP	clumps of terminals	a			
			c	1	Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LP	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilateralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... latéral postérieur (LP)	a			
			0	1	Hay62	a	text	L	0	R	lesion study	LP	no terminal degeneration, only labelled by damaged axons of passage.	a			
R	IGL	3	3	1	Hick76	a	pg527-8, fig1,2	A	3	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	IGL	... separate retinal projection to a group of cells lying btwn DGL & VGL rostrally... Cells (small, oval) receive a clear bilateral projection... contra somewhat larger than ipsi proj. Great deal of variability in size & loc of proj btwn animals. i/c overlaps.	a			
			c	2	Moore&Card94	a	pg404,6-7, fig1	C	-1	R	anterograde transport of cholera toxin, conjugated to horseradish peroxidase ... injected into vitreous of deeply anesthetised rats either unilaterally (n=2) or bilaterally (n=1).	IGL	projections to IGL characterised by 3 features: (1) they are distributed throughout IGL bilaterally; (2) projections to contralateral IGL are approx twice as dense as those to ipsi IGL; (3) morphology of terminal plexus is distinct from DLG/VLG.	a			
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	-1	R	eye injections of 25μCi of [3H]leucine	IGL	We found a bilateral projection to the I.G.L.	a			

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
R	LGv	3	3	3	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	LGvl	Lateral portion of vLGN receives a dense projection from the contralateral eye. There are areas of the contralateral vLGN which are less heavily labelled, corresponding to the region of the ipsilateral projection.	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	LGvl	heavy contralateral retinal projection to the VGL in both hooded and albinos... confined primarily to external division of the nucleus... An ipsilateral projection to ext. division found in both (strains)	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	LGv	heaviest labeling located in primary optic pathway: dorsal & ventral lateral geniculate nuclei, Brachium of superior colliculus & SC.	a
		1	2	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	LGvm	Medial division of vLGN has a small amount of labelling in the caudal part of the medial vLGN	a	
				Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	LGvm	The projection to the internal division of the VGL is comparatively sparse... we have also found that an ipsilateral retinal projection is present in the VGL in the albino rat as well as the hooded rat	a	
		c	3	Brau84b	a	pg212, fig4	L	-1	R	lesions?	LGvl	Visual information from the retina reaches the contralateral vLGN mainly directly via the primary optic pathway. The terminal area of retinal efferents covers only the lateral subnucleus of the LGv. Only a few degenerating retinal axons reach the LGv	a	
				Reperant87		pg601, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiniennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LGv	chez le Rat, la rétine se projette bilatéralement (avec une prédominance controlatérale) sur les noyaux ... genouillé latéral ventral (GLv)	a	
				Swa74	a	pg148, fig4	A	-1	R	intraocular injection of a small amount of [3H]proline	LGvl	Numerous silver grains can be seen in autoradiographs of the lateral magnocellular subdivision of LGNv	a	
		0	1	Watts&Swans87	D2	pg240	F	0	R	Flat mounted whole retinae were taken from the animals injected with SITS, no retrogradely labeled neurons were found in retinae of expt D2	LGvm	4 animals receive injections of SITS (D2, D7, D8, D10) & 2 received implants of true-blue centred in the lateral geniculate nucleus. D2 & E3 centered in medial ventral LG, whereas D7, D8 & D10 labeled LGv/IGL/LGd.	r	
		R	LGvl	3	3	2	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	LGvl
Hick76	a						pg524, fig1	A	3	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	LGvl	heavy contralateral retinal projection to the VGL in both hooded and albinos... confined primarily to external division of the nucleus... An ipsilateral projection to ext. division found in both (strains)	a
c	2			Brau84b	a	pg212, fig4	L	-1	R	lesions?	LGvl	Visual information from the retina reaches the contralateral vLGN mainly directly via the primary optic pathway. The terminal area of retinal efferents covers only the lateral subnucleus of the LGv. Only a few degenerating retinal axons reach the LGv	a	
				Swa74	a	pg148, fig4	A	-1	R	intraocular injection of a small amount of [3H]proline	LGvl	Numerous silver grains can be seen in autoradiographs of the lateral magnocellular subdivision of LGNv	a	
R	LGvm	1	1	2	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	eye injections of 25µCi of [3H]leucine	LGvm	Medial division of vLGN has a small amount of labelling in the caudal part of the medial vLGN	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	6 rats (3 albino and 3 hooded) were used. Intraocular injection of [3H]leucine	LGvm	The projection to the internal division of the VGL is comparatively sparse... we have also found that an ipsilateral retinal projection is present in the VGL in the albino rat as well as the hooded rat	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T	
			0	1	Watts&Swans87	D2	pg240	F	0	R	Flat mounted whole retinae were taken from the animals injected with SITS, no retrogradely labeled neurons were found in retinae of expt D2	LGvm	4 animals receive injections of SITS (D2, D7, D8, D10) & 2 received implants of true-blue centred in the lateral geniculate nucleus. D2 & E3 centered in medial ventral LG, whereas D7, D8 & D10 labeled LGv/IGL/LGd.	r	
BST	MEA	3	3	1	Grove88b		pg325, fig8	3	BST	PHA-L inj into most lateral part		MEA	rostral 2/3	a	
BST	LHA	c	c	1	Grove88b		pg325, fig8	-1	BST	PHA-L inj into most lateral part		PFor		a	
BST	LPO	3	3	1	Grove88b		pg325, fig8	3	BST	PHA-L inj into most lateral part		LPO	dense	a	
BST	MPO	3	3	1	Chib&Mura85	23	table1		W	3	BST		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Grove88b		pg325, fig8	2	BST	PHA-L inj into most lateral part	MPO		a		
					Chib&Mura85		pg263	-1	BST	afferent connections observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r		
					McDon87 Sim&Swa86		abstract abstract	-1 -1	BST BST	intra-amygdaloid portions of BST	MPO MPO	WGA-HRP injections	r		
BST	MPN	3	3	1	Chib&Mura85	23	table1		W	3	BST		MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r
					Chib&Mura85		pg263	-1	BST	afferent connections observed	MPN	WGA-HRP inj	r		
BST	PVH	3	3	1	Grove88b		pg325, fig8	3	BST	PHA-L inj into most lateral part		PVH	many fibres	a	
					Cullin93		pg10	-1	BST		PVH	FG inj	r		
AD	LHA	0	0	1	Petro83		pg292, fig9,10	0	AD			VTA/LHA/PH/???	HRP inj, VTA with a small extension into the posterior parts of the lateral hypothalamus	r	
AV	LHA	0	0	1	Petro83		pg292, fig9,10	0	AV			VTA/LHA/PH/???	HRP inj, VTA with a small extension into the posterior parts of the lateral hypothalamus	r	
LD	SC	2	2	1	Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	LD	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... lateral thalamic nucleus, <obs from fig2a> A small number of labelled cells was seen concentrated in ... the dorsal part of the lateral nucleus of the thalamus	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r	
LGd	SC	0	0	1	Hug77a	x	pg322	A	0	LGd	[3H]leucine injections	SC	no subcortical efferents of NLP or LGNd were observed despite an extensive search which focussed of the di-mesencephalic juncture and the tectum	a	
LGd	LP	2	2	1	Solo&Nomo84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	2	LGd	far fewer cells <than in SC or PRT> were tagged in the medial part of the dorsal region LGB	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r	
					Solo&Nomo84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	-1	LGd	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA)	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r	
LGd	LGv	0	0	2	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368	H	0	LGd	No labeled neurons were observed in the DLGN after VLGN injections confined to that nucleus	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r	
					Pas82c	V	pg412, fig4	H	0	LGd	Contrary to our expectations, none of the LGBv cases labelled cell bodies in the LGBd, while labeled fibres were labelled.	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r	
LP	PRT	1	1	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	1	LP	In two cases (HP25 and HP26) a very small number of positive cells was observed in the caudal pole of the lateral posterior thalamic nucleus	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r	
LP	SC	2	2	1	Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	LP	cells seen bilaterally in the dorsal part of the lateral posterior/pulvinar complex... A small number of labelled cells was seen concentrated in the dorsal part of the lateral posterior/pulvinar complex just deep to the brachium of the SC	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			0	1	Hug77a	y	pg322	A	0	LP	[3H]leucine injections	SC	no subcortical efferents of NLP or LGNd were observed despite an extensive search which focussed of the di-mesencephalic juncture and the tectum	a
IGL	PRT	2	2	1	Mikk92	a	pg958	P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	APN	2 routes from inj site: 1) medial: largest output proj to con hemisphere, projected under caudal op through LD & APN into pc. Presumably, many fibres terminate in the LD and the APN of ips hemisphere, No. of fibres much lower on con side.	a
IGL	SC	2	2	1	Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	IGL	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... intergeniculate leaflet of the lateral geniculate body...	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
IGL	LHA	2	2	1	Mikk90	a	pg59	P	2	IGL	PHA-L was injected iontophoretically into 35 adult male Wistar rats	LHA	Injections involving the intergeniculate leaflet gave rise to a substantial number of fibres to the hypothalamus. In the LHA, innervation was mostly concentrated in the rostral and ventromedial parts. Small number of contra LHA	a
IGL	LPO	1	1	1	Mikk90	a	pg60	P	1	IGL	PHA-L was injected iontophoretically into 35 adult male Wistar rats	LPO	Injections involving the intergeniculate leaflet gave rise to a substantial number of fibres to the hypothalamus. A few fibres were observed in the adjacent lateral preoptic area and the tuber cinerum	a
IGL	SCH	3	3	1	Mikk90	a	pg59	P	3	IGL	PHA-L was injected iontophoretically into 35 adult male Wistar rats	SCH	Injections involving the intergeniculate leaflet gave rise to a substantial number of fibres to the hypothalamus. The fibres terminated primarily in the suprachiasmatic nuclei, mostly in the ipsilateral site	a
			2	3	Card89		pg141, fig3		2	IGL	large numbers of small bipolar neurons, separate into 2 groups: 1 immunoreactive to NeuroPep Y, the other not, ips > con	SCH	RD/FG injections	r
					Card89		pg141, fig3		2	IGL		SCH		
					Mikk92	a	pg958	P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	SCH	2 routes from inj site: 2) other group of fibres passing into op was followed in tract to optic chiasm... numerous fibers penetrated dorsally into the hypothalamus, in particular the SCN, but several fibres appear to LGN(c)	
			c	1	Moore&Card94	b	pg404, 407	F	-1	IGL	neurons retrogradely labeled in IGL following FG inj into either SCN or contralateral IGL are distributed in a pattern essentially identical to retinal afferents or distribution of NPY+ neurons	SCH	Injecting fluorescent tracer into either SCN (bilaterally) or IGL. 50-100nl of fluoro-gold injected stereotaxically (n=10)	r
IGL	LD	2	2	1	Mikk92	a	pg958	P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	LD	2 routes from inj site: 1) medial: largest output proj to con hemisphere, projected under caudal op through LD & APN into pc. Presumably, many fibres terminate in the LD and the APN of ips hemisphere, No. of fibres much lower on con side.	a
IGL	LGd	1	1	1	Mikk92	a	pg958, fig2,5	P	1	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	LGd	fibres heterogeneously distributed (Fg2,5). Fibre bundle not in optic tract but ros and ven to it. Single axons arborized within the DLG, mostly in that part adjacent to the IGL. Densest region of termination not confined to IGL but spread to ... ven DLG	a
IGL	LGv	2	2	1	Mikk92	a	pg958, fig2,5	P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	LGv	fibres hetero' distributed (Fg2,5). Fibre bundle ros & ven to optic tract. In the VLG the number of PHA-L +ve fibres was low-moderate and distributed heterogeneously but in all parts of the nuc. Ros more dense than cau. (Limited subpop of innerv cells)	a
LGv	AOS	2	2	1	Swa74	c	pg150	A	2	LGv/LGv/LGd/CA3	Of 16 injns in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	LT	Medial pathway followed to the contralateral ... LTN. Ventral pathway descends towards the ipsi LTN which is overlain by a large number of silver grains	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	2	Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	-1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	MT	Ventrally, silver deposits appear over the subthalamic region and perirubral fields, medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic tract (MTN, not illustrated)	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5	A	-1	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	DT	The last ven.med. proj was the longest ... in the op... termination of this tract was in the contralateral vLGN and the lateral terminal nucleus of the accessory optic tract	a
LGv	DT	c	c	1	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5	A	-1	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	DT	The last ven.med. proj was the longest ... in the op... termination of this tract was in the contralateral vLGN and the lateral terminal nucleus of the accessory optic tract	a
LGv	LT	2	2	1	Swa74	c	pg150	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	LT	Medial pathway followed to the contralateral ... LTN, Ventral pathway descends towards the ipsi LTN which is overlain by a large number of silver grains	a
LGv	MT	c	c	1	Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	-1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	MT	Ventrally, silver deposits appear over the subthalamic region and perirubral fields, medial terminal nucleus of the accessory optic tract (MTN, not illustrated)	a
LGv	PRT	3	3	4	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	3	LGv	bilateral applications of WGA-HRP in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus	APN	a dense pattern of both retrograde and anterograde labeling occur in the APc	a
					Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	LGv	a very dense population of cells projecting to the APTA was found in the ipsilateral ventrolateral geniculate nucleus, (fewer number of neurons on contralateral side)	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	LGv	The labelled cells were distributed essentially between two structures: the ventral lateral geniculate body and the zona incerta. In all cases, neurons were located laterally in the magnocellular part of the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injs, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Swa74	c	pg150, fig9	A	3	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	OP	Medially directed pathway to ... a well defined termination within the olivary pretectal nucleus. Of the pretectal nucleus only the olivary nucleus was heavily labeled... fibres easily traced to the contralateral OP	a
			2	5	Legg79		pg350		2	LGv	3H A,A, injections	APN	LGv->OP projection spills into APN	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5CD	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	APN	Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract.	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5CD	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	OP	Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract. Con: labeling terminals in PRT limited to ... pars oralis & reticularis of OP	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5CD	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	NOT	Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract. Con: labeling terminals in PRT limited to NOT & ... OP	a
					Swa74	c	pg150	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	NOT	fibres easily traced to the anterior half of the contralateral nucleus of the optic tract where label suggests a terminal field	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	3	Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGv	Lesions of LGv only in contralaterally enucleated animals	PRT	Degenerating fibres reach the nucleus olivaris and the nucleus tractus opticus of the pretectal region of the opposite side via the posterior commissure	a
					Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	-1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	PRT	Dorsally labeled fibres can be traced from the LGv to restricted subdivisions of the dorsal Pt (nucleus of the optic tract, olivary nucleus, and part of the pretectal nucleus)	a
					Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGvl	we can observe large labelled cells in the dorsolateral part of vLGN. Some labelled cells can also be found in the ventrolateral direction	PRT	after application of HRP in the pretectal region	r
LGv	NOT	2	2	2	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5CD	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	NOT	Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract. Con: labeling terminals in PRT limited to NOT & ... OP	a
					Swa74	c	pg150	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	NOT	fibres easily traced to the anterior half of the contralateral nucleus of the optic tract where label suggests a terminal field	a
LGv	OP	3	3	1	Swa74	c	pg150, fig9	A	3	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	OP	Medially directed pathway to ... a well defined termination within the olivary pretectal nucleus. Of the pretectal nucleus only the olivary nucleus was heavily labeled... fibres easily traced to the contralateral OP	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5CD	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	OP	Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract. Con: labeling terminals in PRT limited to ... pars oralis & reticularis of OP	a
LGv	SC	3	3	2	Bra82	a	pg84, fig1	H	3	LGvl	Many neurons in the rat's vLGN are labelled in HRP preparations. The labelled cells are localized in the lateral subnucleus of vLGN	SC	Small injections of HRP were made stereotaxically by pressure into the right SC of five adult albino rats	r
					Swa74	c	pg150, fig6	A	3	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCi	the medial pathway gives off a distinct caudally directed component which can be traced posteriorly into the superior colliculus. Silver grains found in large numbers over all layers except SCzo. SCig particularly heavily labeled. No con. label	a
					Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	2	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	SCi	Dorsally labeled fibres can be traced from the LGv to (2) the optic and intermediate layers of the SC and, in smaller numbers, its superficial gray layer.	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCsg	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCop	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. Most strongly labeled was SCop (not homogeneous, since the medial 1/3 highest density), no contra.	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCig	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a
					Swa74	c	pg150, fig6	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCd	the medial pathway gives off a distinct caudally directed component which can be traced posteriorly into the superior colliculus. Silver grains found in large numbers over all layers except SCzo. SCig particularly heavily labeled. No con. label	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					Swaw74	c	pg150, fig6	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCs	the medial pathway gives off a distinct caudally directed component which can be traced posteriorly into the superior colliculus. Silver grains found in large numbers over all layers except SCzo. SCig particularly heavily labeled. No con. label	a	
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	LGv1	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... the LGv pars lateralis... most caudal part of LGv was free of labelled cells, but throughout the rostral two thirds of the nucleus many close packed cells were found.	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r	
			1	3	Drug&Syk8 4	a	pg251	H	1	LGv	HRP +ve cells	SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r	
					Araki84	a	pg438, fig3	H	1	LGv	distinct neurons labelled by retrograde transport were seen in the ...ventral lateral geniculate nucleus. A few neurons in the ventral lateral geniculate were also labelled for HRP,	SC	HRP injections were restricted to the SC and did not involve adjacent cell groups such as the pretectal nuclei or the dorsolateral part of the central grey. They occupied all layers of the SC	r	
					Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	SCs	Dorsally labeled fibres can be traced from the LGv to (2) the optic and intermediate layers of the SC and, in smaller numbers, its superficial gray layer.	a	
			c	3	Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGv1	labelled projection cells can be found in the vLGN lateral subnucleus	SC	HRP application in the superior colliculus	r	
					Bra82	b	pg86, fig6	L	-1	LGv	To study the degeneration patterns of the vLGN efferents, electrolytic lesions of the right vLGN were made stereotaxically in five albino rats which had been enucleated contralaterally eight months before.	SC	We found ipsilateral fibre degeneration in the SC. Grains characteristic of terminal degeneration were observed in lower SCsg, SCig, SCiw	a	
					Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGv	Lesions of LGv only in contralaterally enucleated animals	SC	The majority of degenerating fibres reaching the superior colliculus concentrated on the SCop and SCiw. degenerating fibres could be also be observed in the medial part of the SC	a	
			x	1	Sug&Otan8 6		abstract [Hereditary Microphthalmic rat]		-1	LGv		SC			
LGv	SCi		3	3	1	Swaw74	c	pg150, fig6	A	3	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCi	the medial pathway gives off a distinct caudally directed component which can be traced posteriorly into the superior colliculus. Silver grains found in large numbers over all layers except SCzo. SCig particularly heavily labeled. No con. label	a
					Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	2	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	SCi	Dorsally labeled fibres can be traced from the LGv to (2) the optic and intermediate layers of the SC and, in smaller numbers, its superficial gray layer.	a	
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCig	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a	
LGv	SCig		2	2	1	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCig	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a
LGv	SCs		2	2	3	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCsg	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a
					Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCop	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. Most strongly labeled was SCop (not homogeneous, since the medial 1/3 highest density). no contra.	a	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Swa74	c	pg150, fig6	A	2	LGv/LGv/LGd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCs	the medial pathway gives off a distinct caudally directed component which can be traced posteriorly into the superior colliculus. Silver grains found in large numbers over all layers except SCzco. SCig particularly heavily labeled. No con. label	a
			1	1	Gray74	F1	pg303, fig1A	A	1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	SCs	Dorsally labeled fibres can be traced from the LGv to (2) the optic and intermediate layers of the SC and, in smaller numbers, its superficial gray layer.	a
LGv	SCop	2	2	1	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (FigID) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCop	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. Most strongly labeled was SCop (not homogeneous, since the medial 1/3 highest density). no contra.	a
LGv	SCsg	2	2	1	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5ABC	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (FigID) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCsg	One dorsomedial projection coursed caudally from the vLGN through the brachium of the superior colliculus to terminate in the ipsilateral SC. The SCsg and SCig were also labeled at levels above background	a
LGv	SCH	2	2	2	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (FigID) had injections confined to the vLGN	SCH	The last ven.med. proj was the longest ... in the op... label appeared in the ventral regions of the suprachiasmatic nuclei on both sides of the brain stem. It appeared that label was ~twice as dense over ipsilateral than over contra portion of HY nuc	a
					Swa74	c	pg150, fig8	A	2	LGv/LGv/LGd/CA3	Of 16 injs in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	SCH	Ventral pathway ... terminates bilaterally within the suprachiasmatic nuclei of the hypothalamus... grains confined to ventral halves but ipsi SCH contains twice as many grains as contra	a
LGv	LD	2	2	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	LGv	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	LGv	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus,	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	LGv	No labeled cells were found in the vLG, ZI or mammillary bodies	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
LGv	LGd	2	2	1	Pas82c	D	pg411, fig3	H	2	LGv	Labeled medium sized cell bodies were found ipsi- and contralaterally (fig3a) and mostly placed at the mediadorsal portion of the LGBv (fig5b).	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
LGv	LP	c	c	1	Solo&Nomo84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	-1	LGv	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA)	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
LGvl	PRT	c	c	1	Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGvl	we can observe large labelled cells in the dorsolateral part of vLGN. Some labelled cells can also be found in the ventrolateral direction	PRT	after application of HRP in the pretectal region	r
LGvl	SC	3	3	1	Bra82	a	pg84, fig1	H	3	LGvl	Many neurons in the rat's vLGN are labelled in HRP preparations. The labelled cells are localized in the lateral subnucleus of vLGN	SC	Small injections of HRP were made stereotaxically by pressure into the right SC of five adult albino rats	r
			2	1	Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	LGvl	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... the LGv pars lateralis... most caudal part of LGv was free of labelled cells, but throughout the rostral two thirds of the nucleus many close packed cells were found.	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	Brau84b	a	pg213, fig5	L	-1	LGVl	labelled projection cells can be found in the vLGN lateral subnucleus	SC	HRP application in the superior colliculus	r

Second Stage Retinal Connection Matrix.

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PG	PRP	1	1	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	1	TRN	Within the pontine tegmentum, small numbers of HRP-labeled neurons are found bilaterally in central and pericentral subdivisions of NRTP.	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
PG	VISp	1	1	1	OHearn84	V	pg716, fig7,8	F	1	TRN	analysis of differential B9 labeling limited by smaller cell numbers & greater variation from each inj than obs for DR & CS. Average number of cells labeled: V=28.2 S.E=±12. Ratio i/c = 2.3±0.6	VISp	All 15 injns confined to cerebral cortex & TB did not extend into underlying structures. Occipital injns in area 17	r
TRN	PRP	1	1	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	1	TRN	Within the pontine tegmentum, small numbers of HRP-labeled neurons are found bilaterally in central and pericentral subdivisions of NRTP.	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
TRN	VISp	1	1	1	OHearn84	V	pg716, fig7,8	F	1	TRN	analysis of differential B9 labeling limited by smaller cell numbers & greater variation from each inj than obs for DR & CS. Average number of cells labeled: V=28.2 S.E=±12. Ratio i/c = 2.3±0.6	VISp	All 15 injns confined to cerebral cortex & TB did not extend into underlying structures. Occipital injns in area 17	r
MRN	IO	2	2	3	Ruth84		pg291-295, fig6, eg case DR545 (n=20)	2	MRN	mesencephalic ret form		IO	HRP inj	r
					Ruth84		pg295-298, fig9 (n=9)	2	MRN	mesencephalic ret form		IO	FB inj	r
					Swe&Cas83 a		pg335, fig3C	2	MRN	medial & lateral		IO	large HRP inj	r
					Swe&Cas83 b		pg262, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a	-1	MRN	lateral deep mesencephalic nucleus		IO	HRP inj	r
					Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	RR			IO		
					Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	MRN	deep mesencephalic nucleus		IO		
MRN	PG	2	2	2	Tori86		pg98, fig1, table1	2	RR	perirubral/perilemniscal area		TRN	HRP injection	r
					Tori86		pg98, fig1, table1	2	MRN			TRN	HRP injection	r
					Border86		pg175, fig2,5A-C	-1	MRN/RR	perirubral area		PG	WGA-HRP inj {& GAD immuno}	r
					Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	0	MRN	3H Leucine inj		PG		a
MRN	TRN	2	2	2	Tori86		pg98, fig1, table1	2	RR	perirubral/perilemniscal area		TRN	HRP injection	r
					Tori86		pg98, fig1, table1	2	MRN			TRN	HRP injection	r
MRN	PRT	3	3	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	MRN	a very dense collection of strongly labelled cells was visualized in the deep mesencephalic nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	2	MRN	3H Leucine inj		APN		a
					Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	1	MRN	3H Leucine inj		MPT		a
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	1	RR	some positive neurons also appeared in the ... retrorubral field, ...	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	1	MRN	some positive neurons also appeared in the deep mesencephalic nucleus, just dorsolateral to the lateral horn of the red nucleus.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
MRN	APN	3	3	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	MRN	a very dense collection of strongly labelled cells was visualized in the deep mesencephalic nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
			2	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		2	MRN	3H Leucine inj	APN		a
			1	2	Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	1	RR	some positive neurons also appeared in the ... retrorubral field, ...	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	1	MRN	some positive neurons also appeared in the deep mesencephalic nucleus, just dorsolateral to the lateral horn of the red nucleus.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
MRN	SC	3	3	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		3	MRN	3H Leucine inj	SC		a
			2	1	Araki84	a	pg438, fig3	H	2	MRN	distinct neurons labelled by retrograde transport were seen in the ...reticular formation of the midbrain, mainly located in the central portion of the RF	SC	HRP injections were restricted to the SC and did not involve adjacent cell groups such as the pretectal nuclei or the dorsolateral part of the central grey. They occupied all layers of the SC	r
			1	1	Drug&Syk8 4	a	pg251	H	1	MRN	HRP +ve cells	SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r
			c	1	Giol85d	b	pg104-5, table1, fig1,6	H	-1	RR	labeled cells are also found in retrorubral field after superior collicular injections	SC	3 rats received injns (HRP) into the superior colliculus	r
MRN	SCH	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		0	MRN	3H Leucine inj	SCH		a
MRN	PVH	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		0	MRN	3H Leucine inj	PVH		a
MRN	ATN	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		0	MRN	3H Leucine inj	LD		a
MRN	LD	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		0	MRN	3H Leucine inj	LD		a
MRN	CL	3	3	2	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		3	MRN	3H Leucine inj	CL		a
					Carst90	f1	pg616, fig1	W	3	MRN	A very large number of retrogradely labeled neurons was observed throughout the ros.cau. extent of the midbrain PAG and adjacent reticular formation, including the region of the dorsal raphe nucleus... bilateral with ips preponderance	CL/CL/CM/ MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r
			c	1	Carst90	f4	pg619, fig4	W	-1	MRN	labelled a relatively smaller <Than CM injections> but in a distribution similar to that seen in following the CM injection	CL	A gold (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) microinjection restricted largely to CL	r
MRN	PF	3	3	2	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		3	MRN	3H Leucine inj	PF		a
					Corn&Phil8 8b	f3	pg142, fig3,6d	W	3	MRN	In the midbrain there was a large group of well stained cells consistently observed in mesencephalic reticular formation just caudal to the posterior commissure.	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
MRN	LP	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)		0	MRN	3H Leucine inj	LP		a
MRN	PO	c	c	2	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	-1	MRN	cell labelling was evident in the mesencephalic reticular formation	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	-1	RR	cell labelling was evident in the perirubral field	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
MRN	MD	0	0	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	0	MRN		3H Leucine inj	MD		a
MRN	PVT	2	2	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	2	MRN		3H Leucine inj	PVT		a
MRN	LGv	2	2	1	Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	MRN	Some neurons in other subcortical structures was also labeled (bilaterally with ips dominance): ... mesencephalic reticular formation	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
			c	1	MS83	C	pg29	W	-1	MRN	labelled cells were found in the same nonvisual centres which project to LGNd. <MRN,DR,PAG,DTN,LC>, there were also a few cells ...in the reticular formation lateral to the red nucleus	LGv/LGv/LGd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r
			x	1	Brau84b		abstract		-1	MRN		LGv		
MRN	RT	3	3	1	Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	3	MRN		3H Leucine inj	RT		a
			2	1	MS83	B	pg27,29, fig2FH,3	W	2	MRN	cells were labelled in mesencephalic reticular formation, ... moderate <20-100 cells> projection	RT	In three animals injections of WGA-HRP were made into visual RNT	r
			x	1	Com90b		abstract		-1	MRN		RT		
MRN	ZI	3	3	3	Carst90	f5	pg619, fig5	W	3	MRN	A very large number of retrogradely labeled neurons (i.e. over 1600 in section shown in fig5C) was observed bilaterally in the midbrain PAG and reticular formation, with a preponderance ipsilateral to the injection	ZI	In one case we successfully injected ZI with little involvement of the ventrobasal complex (with WGA-HRP / colloidal gold)	r
					Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	3	MRN	3H Leucine inj	FF		a	
					Ver&Mar88		table1, (parcellation ???)	3	MRN	3H Leucine inj	ZI		a	
			x	1	Rog&Cad85		abstract	2	MRN	deep mesencephalic ret form	ZI			
PRP	IO	2	2	1	Swe&Cas83	a	pg335, (case923), fig3B	2	PRP			IO	large HRP inj	r
			c	1	Swe&Cas83	b	pg261, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a	-1	PRP		IO	HRP inj	r	
			x	4	DeZee93		abstract	-1	PRP		IO			
					DeZeeuw93		abstract	-1	PRP		IO	dorsal cap		
Barm93		abstract []	-1	PRP		IO	dorsal cap							
Swe&Cas83	b	abstract	-2	PRP		IO								
PRP	MRN	1	1	Stein92		pg530, fig9E	1	PRP			MRN	WGA-HRP inj, fig3, MEA	r	
PRP	PRT	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2	PRP	contralateral to the side of the injection was a population of cells ... in the prepositus hypoglossal nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
			x	1	Oht92		abstract	-1	PRP		PRT	WGA-HRP injections, including NOT	r	
PRP	APN	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2	PRP	contralateral to the side of the injection was a population of cells ... in the prepositus hypoglossal nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
PRP	SC	x	x	2	Oht92		abstract	-1	PRP			SC	WGA-HRP injections	r
					Redgr92b		abstract	-1	PRP		SC			
VNC	IO	3	3	1	Swe&Cas83	a	pg335, (case923), fig3B	3	SPIV		inferior vest nuc	IO	large HRP inj	r
			1	1	Swe&Cas83	a	pg335, (case923), fig3B	1	MV		IO	large HRP inj	r	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	4	Barm93		pg273, fig4ABCE	-1	PRP/MV/SP IV	PHA-L inj		IO	dorsal cap & Beta nucleus	a
					Swe&Cas83 b		pg262, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a	-1	SPIV	inferior vestibular nucleus		IO	HRP inj	r
					Swe&Cas83 b		pg262, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a	-1	MV			IO	HRP inj	r
					Barm93		pg273, fig5	-1	MV/SPIV	PHA-L inj		IO	Beta nucleus	a
			x	7	Barm93		abstract []	-1	VNC	descending & medial vestibular nuclei, PHA-L injections		IO	beta subnucleus	a
					Barm93		abstract []	-1	SPIV	PHA-L injections		IO	dorsal cap & beta subnucleus	a
					Fred&Mug9 l		abstract	-1	LAV	dorsal part		IO		
					Barm93		abstract []	-1	MV	PHA-L injections		IO	dorsal cap & beta subnucleus	a
					Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	MV			IO		
					Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	SPIV			IO		
					Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	VNC	inferior ???		IO		
VNC	PG	3	3	1	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	3	SUV			TRN	HRP injection	r
			2	1	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	2	LAV			TRN	HRP injection	r
			1	2	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	1	MV			TRN	HRP injection	r
					Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	1	SPIV			TRN	HRP injection	r
			x	1	Swe84		abstract	-1	SPIV			PG		
VNC	TRN	3	3	1	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	3	SUV			TRN	HRP injection	r
			2	1	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	2	LAV			TRN	HRP injection	r
			1	2	Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	1	MV			TRN	HRP injection	r
					Tori86		pg90, table1, fig1,2	1	SPIV			TRN	HRP injection	r
VNC	PRT	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2 MV	a large collection of moderately labelled neurons in the ipsilateral medial vestibular nucleus was apparent, (smaller weaker stained group in contralateral group.)		APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
VNC	APN	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2 MV	a large collection of moderately labelled neurons in the ipsilateral medial vestibular nucleus was apparent, (smaller weaker stained group in contralateral group.)		APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
VNC	SC	c	c	1	Gay&Fau88	b	pg361-2, fig4	W	-1 SPIV	Retrograde labelled neurons are found in deep cerebellar nuclei, substantia nigra, parabrachial nucleus, visual cortex, external cuneate nucleus & nucleus of the spinal tract of trigeminal nerve		SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	r
VNC	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0 VNC			MPO/PV/SC	WGA-HRP inj	r
VNC	CL	x	x	2	Nagata86		abstract	-1	SUV			CL		
					Nagata86		abstract	-1	MV			CL		
VNC	PF	x	x	1	Corn&Phil88b		abstract	-1	VNC			PF		
VNC	PO	2	2	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	2 SPIV	more systematic labelling was observed in the sensitive nucleus of the trigeminal nerve and in the nucleus of the spinal tract of the trigeminal nerve		PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
			1	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1 SUV	few positive cells (1-2 per animal) were detected in the superior vestibular nucleus and in the dentate nucleus of the cerebellum		PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
VNC	LGv	2	2	1	Pas82c	V	pg414, fig4	H	2 VNC	a direct vestibular connection to the LGV is reported in rats. It seems to be fully ipsilateral and very specific		LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>		
AOS	IO	3	3	3	Giol88b	c	pg611, table1	H	3	DT	With injns into both ros/cau IOdc, there is moderate/heavy conc of labeled somata in the ipsi DTN, LTN & inSFp(dor). Injs into IOdc(cau) only has sparse label in LTN, but heavy in other nuclei. DTN, LTN label bilateral.	IO	Injs (HRP) completely unilateral & centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olivary complex in 3 rabbit & 2 rat cases. Either injns involve both ros & cau portions of the dorsal cap (2rab/1rat) or caudal portion of the dorsal cap (1rab/1rat)	r		
					Giol88b	c	pg611, table1	H	3	LT	With injns into both ros/cau IOdc, there is moderate/heavy conc of labeled somata in the ipsi DTN, LTN & inSFp(dor). Injs into IOdc(cau) only has sparse label in LTN, but heavy in other nuclei. DTN, LTN label bilateral.	IO	Injs (HRP) completely unilateral & centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olivary complex in 3 rabbit & 2 rat cases. Either injns involve both ros & cau portions of the dorsal cap (2rab/1rat) or caudal portion of the dorsal cap (1rab/1rat)	r		
					Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	IO	At lvl of IO axons spread ventrally to enter inferior olive. In rat MTN-olivary proj only involves the rostral 1/3 of the dorsal cap. In addition, a few axons innervate the contra dorsal cap. Mostly contralateral. high density.	a		
		2	1	Swe&Cas83 a	A923	pg331,335, fig2	H	2	MT	Labeled neurons of the rostral brainstem were predominantly ipsilateral to the inj site but had a relatively small contralateral repr as well. Nuclei with this general pattern included the ... especially the medial terminal nucleus of the acc optic tract	IO	Stereotaxic injns of HRP were made into the inferior olive complex of 52 Long-Evans black-hooded rats following both dorsal(n=19) and ventral(n=33) approaches to BS. Results from animal 923 repr of several animals. limited spread to RF.	r			
		1	2	Fall84	b	pg335, fig2	F	1	MT	... Several neurons were also labeled in the medial terminal nucleus.	IO	In cases where injections (fluorescent dyes) were restricted mainly around the dorsal cap region of the inferior olive...	r			
				Giol85d	k	pg109, table1, fig1	H	1	MT	A few labeled neurons are consistently found in the MTNd, primarily in the ipsilateral nucleus.	IO	Injections (HRP) are centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olive in 5 rabbits & 7 rats. In 5 cases (3 rabbits & 2 rats) the injns are entirely unilateral & largely confined to rostral parts of the dorsal cap.	r			
				vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	-1	DT	retrogradely labeled cells were found in the DTN, MTN & the ventral tegmental relay zone	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injns into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r			
		vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	-1	MT	retrogradely labeled cells were found in the DTN, MTN & the ventral tegmental relay zone	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injns into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r					
AOS	PG	3	3	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	PG	The axons give off branches that innervate the dorsolateral division of the contralateral basilar pontine complex... limited to its dorlat division. Term field is of high density & involves a small part of this division. 1/2 patches.	a		
					2	3	Mihail89 Giol85d	j	pg632, fig14CD pg109, table1, fig1,5		2	LT	...produce moderate numbers of labeled somata in the contralateral MTNv, MTNd & the VTRZ	PG PG	WGA-HRP inj (HRP) injections into the dorsolateral division of the basal pons in 3 rat cases. injns mainly involve dorsolat div of the basal pontine complex	r r
							Clarke89	f	pg270-1, fig1,2, table1	F	2	MT	p271: additionally, labeled neurons have been seen within MTd, MTv & VTRZ after injections of ... dorsolateral pons. Table1, fig2: 9-10% of labeled neurons in expt found in MT	PG	32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: dorsolateral nucleus of basilar pons. 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT	r
					0	4	Giol88b	i	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	PG	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
		Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r					

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Giol88b	i	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	PG	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
					Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
AOS	TRN	0	0	2	Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
					Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
AOS	MRN	3	3	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,238-9, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	MRN	These axons provide a moderate to heavy terminal in a portion of the midbrain reticular formation that corresponds to the deep mesencephalic nucleus, pars medialis (qv: Veazey & Severin '80, JCN190:231)	a
					Giol85d	f	pg109, table1, fig1	H	2	MT	Labeled perikarya in low to moderate density are found in the ipsilateral MTNd, VTRZ, nucleus paranigralis & compact & reticular portions of substantia nigra	MRN	The portion of an injection site which would retrogradely transport HRP from the pars medialis of the deep mesencephalic nucleus is illustrated in fig1B	r
					Giol88b	g	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	MRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
					Giol88b	g	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	MRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorlat div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
AOS	PRP	0	0	1	Giol85d	i	pg109	H	0	MT	... & in each of these instances found no HRP-filled neurons in the MTN of either the rabbit or rat.	PRP	we have made restricted HRP injections into the medial vestibular nucleus or into the nucleus praepositus hypoglossi which spare the superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ...	r
AOS	VNC	2	2	5	Giol85d	g	pg109, table1, fig1	H	2	MT	There is no indication of an ipsilateral MTN-vestibular projection in the rat. Table1: MTNd: c,d/v+2 (ie moderate label)	VNC	vestibular inj sites include the target zones for MTN neurons in the rostradorsal parts of the superior vestibular nucleus. These injns also involve portions of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei in both rabbits & rats. In 3 rats included PRP.	r
					Giol88b	d	pg611-2, table1	H	2	MT	Labeled neurons are found in moderate numbers within the MTN.	VNC	Injs of HRP involve the vestibular nuclei n 4 rabbits & 20 rat. In all cases inj includes portion of SUV. Injs also usually include a portion of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei & in 3 rat cases the PRP.	r
					Clarke89	e	pg270-1, fig1,2, table1	F	2	MT	p271: additionally, labeled neurons have been seen within MTd, MTv & VTRZ after injections of contralateral superior/lateral vestibular nuclei. Table1, fig2: 6% of labeled neurons in expt found in MT	VNC/VNC/ SUV/LAV	32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: ... contralateral superior/lateral vestibular nuclei... 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT	r
					Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	2	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	SUV	The axons distribute to the contralateral superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ... The MTN-vestibular projection is of moderate density and involves distinct zones in each nucleus. No ipsi projection found in the rat.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	2	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	LAV	The axons distribute to the contralateral superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ... The MTN-vestibular projection is of moderate density and involves distinct zones in each nucleus. No ipsi projection found in the rat.	a	
				1	1	Giol88b	d	pg611-2, table1	H	1	LT	Labeled neurons are seen only contralateral to injections & then in small numbers within the DTN	VNC	Injs of HRP involve the vestibular nuclei n 4 rabbits & 20 rat. In all cases inj includes portion of SUV. Injs also usually include a portion of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei & in 3 rat cases the PRP.	r
				0	1	Giol85d	h	pg109	H	0	MT	... & in each of these instances found no HRP-filled neurons in the MTN of either the rabbit or rat.	MV	we have made restricted HRP injections into the medial vestibular nucleus or into the nucleus praepositus hypoglossi which spare the superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ...	r
AOS	APN	0	0	2	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	APN	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a	
					vdT&vdW9 2	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	APN	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a	
AOS	ZI	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/ VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	ZI	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a	
DT	IO	3	3	1	Giol88b	c	pg611, table1	H	3	DT	With injs into both ros/cau IOdc, there is moderate/heavy conc of labeled somata in the ipsi DTN, LTN & inSFp(dor). Injs into IOdc(cau) only has sparse label in LTN, but heavy in other nuclei. DTN, LTN label bilateral.	IO	Injs (HRP) completely unilateral & centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olivary complex in 3 rabbit & 2 rat cases. Either injs involve both ros & cau portions of the dorsal cap (2rab/1rat) or caudal portion of the dorsal cap (1rab/1rat)	r	
				c	1	vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	-1	DT	retrogradely labeled cells were found in the DTN, MTN & the ventral tegmental relay zone	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injs into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
DT	PG	0	0	2	Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injs into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r	
					Giol88b	i	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	PG	HRP injs into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r	
DT	TRN	0	0	1	Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injs into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r	
DT	MRN	0	0	1	Giol88b	g	pg612-5, table1	H	0	DT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	MRN	HRP injs into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r	
LT	IO	3	3	1	Giol88b	c	pg611, table1	H	3	LT	With injs into both ros/cau IOdc, there is moderate/heavy conc of labeled somata in the ipsi DTN, LTN & inSFp(dor). Injs into IOdc(cau) only has sparse label in LTN, but heavy in other nuclei. DTN, LTN label bilateral.	IO	Injs (HRP) completely unilateral & centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olivary complex in 3 rabbit & 2 rat cases. Either injs involve both ros & cau portions of the dorsal cap (2rab/1rat) or caudal portion of the dorsal cap (1rab/1rat)	r	
LT	PG	2	2	1	Mihail89		pg632, fig14CD		2	LT		PG	WGA-HRP inj	r	
				0	2	Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injs into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Giol88b	i	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	PG	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
LT	TRN	0	0	1	Giol88b	k	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	TRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
LT	MRN	0	0	1	Giol88b	g	pg612-5, table1	H	0	LT	... all fail to show HRP-labeled neurons within the DTN, LTN or inSFp	MRN	HRP injns into accessory oculomotor nuclei, supraoculomotor - periaqueductal gray, the mesencephalic & pontine reticular formations, the dorsal div of basilar pontine complex, nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis & the cerebellar flocculus	r
LT	VNC	1	1	1	Giol88b	d	pg611-2, table1	H	1	LT	Labeled neurons are seen only contralateral to injections & then in small numbers within the DTN	VNC	Injs of HRP involve the vestibular nuclei n 4 rabbits & 20 rat. In all cases inj includes portion of SUV. Injs also usually include a portion of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei & in 3 rat cases the PRP.	r
MT	IO	3	3	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	IO	At lvl of IO axons spread ventrally to enter inferior olive. In rat MTN-olivary proj only involves the rostral 1/3 of the dorsal cap. In addition, a few axons innervate the contra dorsal cap. Mostly contralateral. high density.	a
					Swe&Cas83a	A923	pg331,335, fig2	H	2	MT	Labeled neurons of the rostral brainstem were predominantly ipsilateral to the inj site but had a relatively small contralateral repr as well. Nuclei with this general pattern included the ... especially the medial terminal nucleus of the acc optic tract	IO	Stereotaxic injns of HRP were made into the inferior olive complex of 52 Long-Evans black-hooded rats following both dorsal(n=19) and ventral(n=33) approaches to BS. Results from animal 923 repr of several animals. limited spread to RF.	r
					Fall84	b	pg335, fig2	F	1	MT	... Several neurons were also labeled in the medial terminal nucleus.	IO	In cases where injections (fluorescent dyes) were restricted mainly around the dorsal cap region of the inferior olive...	r
					Giol85d	k	pg109, table1, fig1	H	1	MT	A few labeled neurons are consistently found in the MTNd, primarily in the ipsilateral nucleus.	IO	Injections (HRP) are centred in the dorsal cap of the inferior olive in 5 rabbits & 7 rats. In 5 cases (3 rabbits & 2 rats) the injns are entirely unilateral & largely confined to rostral parts of the dorsal cap.	r
					vdT&vdW92	a	pg449	C	-1	MT	retrogradely labeled cells were found in the DTN, MTN & the ventral tegmental relay zone	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injns into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
MT	PG	3	3	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	PG	The axons give off branches that innervate the dorsolateral division of the contralateral basilar pontine complex... limited to its dorsal division. Term field is of high density & involves a small part of this division. 1/2 patches.	a
					Clarke89	f	pg270-1, fig1.2, table1	F	2	MT	p271: additionally, labeled neurons have been seen within MTd, MTv & VTRZ after injections of ... dorsolateral pons. Table1, fig2: 9-10% of labeled neurons in expt found in MT	PG	32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: dorsolateral nucleus of basilar pons. 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT	r
					Giol85d	j	pg109, table1, fig1,5	H	2	MT	...produce moderate numbers of labeled somata in the contralateral MTNv, MTNd & the VTRZ	PG	(HRP) injections into the dorsolateral division of the basal pons in 3 rat cases. injns mainly involve dorsolateral div of the basal pontine complex	r
MT	MRN	3	3	1	Giol84b	a	pg231,238-9, fig2,4	A	3	MT/MT/VT A/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	MRN	These axons provide a moderate to heavy terminal in a portion of the midbrain reticular formation that corresponds to the deep mesencephalic nucleus, pars medialis (qv: Veazey & Severin '80, JCN190:231)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	1	Giol85d	f	pg109, table1, fig1	H	2	MT	Labeled perikarya in low to moderate density are found in the ipsilateral MTNd, VTRZ, nucleus paranigralis & compact & reticular portions of substantia nigra	MRN	The portion of an injection site which would retrogradely transport HRP from the pars medialis of the deep mesencephalic nucleus is illustrated in fig1B	r
MT	PRP	0	0	1	Giol85d	i	pg109	H	0	MT	... & in each of these instances found no HRP-filled neurons in the MTN of either the rabbit or rat.	PRP	we have made restricted HRP injections into the medial vestibular nucleus or into the nucleus praepositus hypoglossi which spare the superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ...	r
MT	VNC	2	2	5	Giol85d	g	pg109, table1, fig1	H	2	MT	There is no indication of an ipsilateral MTN-vestibular projection in the rat. Table1: MTNd: c,d/v+2 (ie moderate label)	VNC	vestibular inj sites include the target zones for MTN neurons in the rostradorsal parts of the superior vestibular nucleus. These inj also involve portions of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei in both rabbits & rats. In 3 rats included PRP.	r
					Giol88b	d	pg611-2, table1	H	2	MT	Labeled neurons are found in moderate numbers within the MTN.	VNC	Injs of HRP involve the vestibular nuclei n 4 rabbits & 20 rat. In all cases inj includes portion of SUV. Injs also usually include a portion of the lateral & medial vestibular nuclei & in 3 rat cases the PRP.	r
					Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2.4	A	2	MT/MT/VTA/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	LAV	The axons distribute to the contralateral superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ... The MTN-vestibular projection is of moderate density and involves distinct zones in each nucleus. No ipsi projection found in the rat.	a
					Giol84b	a	pg231,239, fig2.4	A	2	MT/MT/VTA/SN	Typical [3H]A.A. inj site in 4 rats in fig2, invs a substantial portion of the MTN & a minimal amount of adjacent brain tissue... unavoidable spread of isotope to portions of the tegmental area of Tsai & SN. Label also transported from VTA cells.	SUV	The axons distribute to the contralateral superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ... The MTN-vestibular projection is of moderate density and involves distinct zones in each nucleus. No ipsi projection found in the rat.	a
					Clarke89	e	pg270-1, fig1.2, table1	F	2	MT	p271: additionally, labeled neurons have been seen within MTd, MTv & VTRZ after injections of contralateral superior/lateral vestibular nuclei. Table1, fig2: 6% of labeled neurons in expt found in MT	VNC/VNC/SUV/LAV	32 rats (Long-Evans & Sprague Dawley). FB injected into one of the following targets of MT: ... contralateral superior/lateral vestibular nuclei... 2nd tracer (FG) injected into NOT	r
			0	1	Giol85d	h	pg109	H	0	MT	... & in each of these instances found no HRP-filled neurons in the MTN of either the rabbit or rat.	MV	we have made restricted HRP injections into the medial vestibular nucleus or into the nucleus praepositus hypoglossi which spare the superior & lateral vestibular nuclei ...	r
MT	APN	0	0	2	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	APN	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
					vdT&vdW92	b	pg449	P	0	MT	Iontophoretic injections of PHA-L or biocytin were invariably small & restricted to the MTN.	APN	No anterograde labeling of terminals was found in the other pretectal sites surrounding the NOT.	a
MT	ZI	0	0	1	Blan82	a	fig2	A	0	MT/MT/SN/VTA	The MTN was successfully injected in 7 animals. ([3H]leucine). <No description of size of injection site>	ZI	<see fig2, no labelling shown>	a
PBG	PRT	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2	PBG	contralaterally, but not ipsilaterally to the injection site was a closely packed group of intensely labelled FB neurons in the parabigeminal nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
			0	1	Sef84	c	pg146	H	0	PBG	No labeled cells were ever found in PBG following injections into pretectal nuclei just rostral to SC (olivary pretectal nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract)	PRT/NOT/OP	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)	r
PBG	APN	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2	PBG	contralaterally, but not ipsilaterally to the injection site was a closely packed group of intensely labelled FB neurons in the parabigeminal nucleus	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
PBG	NOT	0	0	1	Sef84	c	pg146	H	0	PBG	No labeled cells were ever found in PBG following injections into pretectal nuclei just rostral to SC (olivary pretectal nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract)	PRT/NOT/OP	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)	r
PBG	OP	0	0	1	Sef84	c	pg146	H	0	PBG	No labeled cells were ever found in PBG following injections into pretectal nuclei just rostral to SC (olivary pretectal nucleus and nucleus of the optic tract)	PRT/NOT/OP	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PBG	SC	3	3	3	Sef84	g	pg147	F	3	PBG	confirmed results found with HRP, number of cells labelled in SC injection was always greater than into DLG, and labeled cells were always distributed more widely. Some cells in medial division contained both labels.	SC	Injections of fluorescent tracer into the SC or DLG	r
					Sef84	a	pg145, fig1B	H	3	PBG	Many labelled cells were always found in the med. division of the contra. PBg. A few labelled cells sometimes extended to the ven. division. Only rarely observed labelled cells in PBg ipsi. to inj site.	SC	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)... When small injections were made into the superficial layers of the SC...	r
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	3	PBG	retrogradely labelled cells were seen bilaterally in: parabigeminal nucleus. Greatest numbers of labelled cells seen ipsilaterally in dorsal and ventral subdivisions of the parabigeminal nucleus and the zona incerta.	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
					Wat79	R95	pg3, fig3	H	2	PBG	contra=mostly in throughout PGm (PGd/PGv free from labelling)	SC/SC/AC A	HRP injections, small leakage into ACA along needle track	r
					Wat79	R95	pg3, fig3	H	2	PBG	ipsi=mostly in middle PGd & PGv (not PGm)	SC/SC/AC A	HRP injections, small leakage into ACA along needle track	r
					Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	PBG	The ipsilateral parabigeminal nucleus contained a small number of labelled cells in case RC15	SC	RC15, HRP deposited in the medioposterior portion of the SC	r
					Drug&Syk84	a	pg251	H	1	PBG	HRP +ve cells	SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r
					Gay&Fau88	b	pg361-2, fig4	W	-1	PBG	Retrograde labelled neurons are found in deep cerebellar nuclei, substantia nigra, parabigeminal nucleus, visual cortex, external cuneate nucleus & nucleus of the spinal tract of trigeminal nerve	SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	r
					Kunz&Schnyd84	a	pg517, fig5	W	-1	PBG	cells labeled by retrograde transport were found in dorsal & ventral portions of ipsilateral n. parabigeminalis and in middle portion of contralateral Pbg.	SC	estimated uptake area within superior colliculus following injections of WGA or WGA-HRP was unilateral and involved superficial, intermediate and to some extent deep collicular layers.	r
					Schum87	a	pg587, fig3.5	H	-1	PBG	localization of HRP +ve neurons in both pbgn changed dependent on the site of the inj in ros cau extent of SC. Rostral inj: great number of labelled neurons found in contra med pbgn. Caudal inj: labelling of neurons in ipsi dorsal & ventral divs of pbgn.	SC	13 juvenile albino rats btwn 30-50 days (used in total)... micropipette localization adjusted by recording multiunit activities from ipsi SC after stimulation in inj site. 3 rats inj in SC. HRP was deposited in superficial as well as deep layers of SC.	r
PBG	SCH	x	x	1	Bina93	abstract	-1	PBG		SCH	ACh innervation, FG injections (confirmed by ant. biocytin expts.)	r		
PBG	LGd	3	3	1	Sef84	d	pg146, fig2	H	3	PBG	... cells were always found to be labelled in the medial division of the contralateral PBg	LGd	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)... After injections of HRP into DLG or DLG & VLG ...	r
					Turl93	A	pg226-30, fig1,2	F	2	PBG	... in pigmented rats the projection of this ... nucleus to the DLG is overwhelmingly contralateral and the labelled cells were distributed throughout the entire medio-lateral extent of the nucleus, cell numbers: 1700-2700)	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
					Sef84	h	pg147	F	2	PBG	confirmed results found with HRP, number of cells labelled in SC injection was always greater than into DLG, and labeled cells were always distributed more widely. Some cells in medial division contained both labels	LGd	Injections of fluorescent tracer into the SC or DLG	r
					MS83	A	pg27,29, fig1D	W	2	PBG	A moderate <20-100> number of cells was labelled in contralateral parabigeminal nucleus (medial division), (n=69)	LGd	Injection of WGA-HRP into LGNd in two animals, ... and injections of unconjugated HRP in 12 others revealed same results	r
					Pas82c	D	pg414, fig3	H	0	PBG	An NPB-LGBd connection seems unlikely in the rat due to negative findings in the numerous LGBd cases	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PBG	LP	c	c	1	Schum87	a	pg587, fig3,5	H	-1	PBG	only large cells were seen in contralateral medial nucleus. Significantly larger than HRP labeled neurons after HRP inj into LGNd.	LP	13 juvenile albino rats btwn 30-50 days (used in total)... micropipette localization adjusted by recording multiunit activities from ipsi SC after stimulation in inj site. 1 rats inj in LP... HRP inj into LP	r
PBG	LGv	2	2	2	Pas82c	V	pg414, fig4,8a	H	2	PBG	well-labelled cell bodies of the parabigeminal nucleus after HRP deposits in the contralateral LGBv. They were found medially and laterally within the NPB, displaying dorsoventral or mediolateral orientation	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
					Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	PBG	Some neurons in other subcortical structures was also labeled (contralaterally): ... parabigeminal nucleus	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Sef84	e	pg146	H	0	PBG	... no labelled cells were observed in PBg.	LGv	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5). When injections were centred in VLG with little apparent leakage into DLG.	r
PBG	RT	0	0	1	MS83	B	pg27,29, fig2FH,3	W	0	PBG	No labelled cells were found in ... parabigeminal nucleus	RT	In three animals injections of WGA-HRP were made into visual RNT	r
PRT	IO	2	2	7	Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the ... posterior and anterior pretectal nuclei. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					Swe&Cas83 a	A923	pg331,335, fig2	H	2	NOT	Labeled neurons of the rostral brainstem were predominantly ipsilateral to the inj site but had a relatively small contralateral repr as well. Nuclei with this general pattern included the ... nucleus of the optic tract.	IO	Stereotaxic injns of HRP were made into the inferior olive complex of 52 Long-Evans black-hooded rats following both dorsal(n=19) and ventral(n=33) approaches to BS. Results from animal 923 repr of several animals. limited spread to RF.	r
					Swe&Cas83 b	a16	pg264, fig 1,5,16,6H	A	2	NOT	More rostral pretectal injections (fig1, inj16) which included most of the rostral part of the nucleus of the optic tract...	IO	Heavy label ing was observed in the ipsilateral dorsal cap	a
					Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the ... posterior and anterior pretectal nuclei. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449, fig1	C	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled neurons were found in the superficial & deep layers of the NOT, Neurons randomly dispersed in the NOT, with some clustering of their cell bodies,	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injns into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
					Red87	2302	pg159, fig2	W	2	SC/PPT/NO T/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	IO	There was a well defined area of moderate intensity label in the caudomedial part of the inferior olive, centered on the dorsal cap of Kooy, thought to be due to PRT involvement in inj site]	a
								1	1	Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	1
			c	3	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	IO	Fibres branch. One branch ... proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 2nd: descends within the pyramidal tract and ... terminates within the posterior one-half of the dorsal cap of Kooy	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Swe&Cas83 b		pg262, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a	-1	PRT	caudal		IO	HRP inj	r
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	IO	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
			0	6	vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	0	NPC	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	0	OP	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	0	MPT	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	0	APN	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
					Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	0	OP	Blue labeled cells were not seen in the pretectal olivary nucleus. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449	C	0	PPT	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
			x	1	Swe&Cas83 b		abstract	-2	PRT	caudal		IO		
PRT	PG		3	3	1	Red87	2302 pg159, fig2	W	3	SC/SC/PPT/ NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small inj	PG	Some fibres continue ventrally until they reach the pons where dense terminal label can be seen at the dor.lat. margin of the pyramidal tract, and in puffs in the lateral pontine nuclei. Puffs not observed after injections more medial than 2302.	a
			2	5	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	TRN	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, ... and in the dorsal aspect of the reticular nucleus of the tegmentum	a
					Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	PG	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres proceed ventrocaudally through the oral part of the pontine reticular nucleus and terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, lateral and medial divisions of the pontine grey	a
					Caduss91	control	pg93	W	2	OP	numerous labelled cells occurred in the olivary pretectal nucleus	PG	following tracer deposits in the basal pontine gray (WGA-HRP)	r
					Korp89	a	pg278	H	2	NOT	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
					Tori86		pg94, table1, fig1K-M,5E			2	NPC		HRP injection	r
			1	2	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	APN	only a few cells in APc	PG	following tracer deposits in the basal pontine gray (WGA-HRP)	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1L,	H	1	NOT	small number of labeled neurons found within the nucleus of the optic tract. In 3 of the 6 medial & intermediate NRTP inj sites cases, label is ipsi In one case, label is bilat due to spread of inj into contra NRTP. input from NOT surprisingly small.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
			c	5	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	PG	Fibres branch. One branch targets the dor.lat. and lat. pontine nuclei, other proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 1st : terminates throughout the ros. cau. extent of dor.med. pontine nucleus	a
					Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	TRN	Pretectal axons enter the NRTP and continue caudally in both portions of the NRTP, the central and pericentral subdivisions. Projections are strictly ipsilateral. Terminal fields: ros. 2/3 of NRTPc and ros. & mid. levels of NRTPp	a
					Red87	2302	pg154, fig2	W	-1	SC/SC/PPT/NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	PG	ipsilaterally descending pathway: mass of intensely labelled fibres ... travel ventrally to innervate dor.lat. pontine nuclei	a
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	PG	HRP injection into the pontine nuclei (mainly the lateral part of the nuclei) <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	TRN	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
			0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
			x	1	Burn81		abstract		-1	PRT	3H AA injections	PG	med, & lat, nuc, in rostral & middle PG	a
PRT	TRN	2	2	3	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	TRN	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, ... and in the dorsal aspect of the reticular nucleus of the tegmentum	a
					Korp89	a	pg278	H	2	NOT	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
					Tori86		pg94, table1, fig1K-M,5E		2	NPC		TRN	HRP injection	r
			1	1	Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1L,	H	1	NOT	small number of labeled neurons found within the nucleus of the optic tract. In 3 of the 6 medial & intermediate NRTP inj sites cases, label is ipsi In one case, label is bilat due to spread of inj into contra NRTP. input from NOT surprisingly small.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
			c	2	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	TRN	Pretectal axons enter the NRTP and continue caudally in both portions of the NRTP, the central and pericentral subdivisions. Projections are strictly ipsilateral. Terminal fields: ros. 2/3 of NRTPc and ros. & mid. levels of NRTPp	a
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	TRN	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
			0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PRT	PRP	3	3	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	3	NOT	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
			2	3	Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	APN	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
					Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	PPT	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
					Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	OP	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
			c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	PRP	Fibres branch. One branch ... proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 2nd: ultimately targets the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus>. Entirely ipsi.	a
PRT	ATN	3	3	8	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	MPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	APN	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	APN	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	PPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	PPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	OP	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	NOT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	MPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	17	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	APN	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	MPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... medial pretectal region... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	OP	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... olivary pretectal nucleus... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	NOT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	MPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM. Many cells were seen in the contralateral hemisphere including PM	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	x	2	PRT	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the pretectal nuclei ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralamina complex	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	NPC	Many cells were seen in the contralateral hemisphere including ... nucleus of the posterior commissure	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	OP	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	PPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	PPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	APN	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	MPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	OP	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
		1	1		Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	1	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LD	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle... occasional labelling also appeared in the lateral dorsal and ventral lateral thalamic nuclei	a
		0	2		Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	OP	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	NOT	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
		x	4		Sikes&Vogt 87		abstract	-1		MPT		ATN		
					Sik&Vog87		abstract	-1		MPT	main PRT-ATN projection	ATN		
					Sikes&Vogt 87		abstract	-1		PPT		ATN		
					Sik&Vog87		abstract	-1		PPT	minor PRT-ATN projection	ATN		
PRT	CL	3	3	1	Carst90	fl	pg616, fig1	W	3	APN	Many labeled neurons were also observed in ... caudal part of the anterior pretectal nucleus	CL/CL/CM/MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r
PRT	PF	2	2	2	Corn&Phil8 8b	f3	pg142, fig3	W	2	PRT/PRT/PT	In further caudal midbrain sections, small clusters of well stained neurones appeared just ventral to the brachium of the superior colliculus in the region of the pretectal nuclei. cells either in ... posterior pretectal nucleus	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
					Corn&Phil8 8b	f3	pg142, fig3	W	2	PRT/PRT/APN	In further caudal midbrain sections, small clusters of well stained neurones appeared just ventral to the brachium of the superior colliculus in the region of the pretectal nuclei. cells either in dor.lat. wing of the anterior pretectal	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
PRT	PO	3	3	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	3	APN	the anterior pretectal nucleus was the most heavily labelled	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
		2	1		Rog&Cad84	a	pg479	H	2	PRT	following HRP deposits into ... pt	PO	anterograde transport of the enzyme resulted in axon-terminal labeling within tp	a
		1	2		Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	OP	a few cells could be detected in the olivary pretectal nucleus	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	NPC	on occasion, cell labelling was evident in the nucleus of the posterior commissure	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
PRT	MD	2	2	1	Gerf82		pg295		2	NPC		MD	WGA-HRP inj	r
PRT	RT	2	2	1	MS83	B	pg27,29, fig2FH,3	W	2	APN	labelled cells located in ... ipsilateral anterior pretectal nucleus	RT	In three animals injections of WGA-HRP were made into visual RNT	r
		c	1		Corn90b		pg163, fig9a,b	-1		MPT	PHA-L inj	RT	WGA-HRP inj	ar
PRT	ZI	2	2	4	Rog&Cad85	a	pg483, fig3D	H	2	APN	small number of labeled cells was consistently observed within anterior pretectal nucleus, except when HRP deposited in rostralmost sector of ZI (case ZI 11), characteristic light labeling in PRT.	ZI	Horseshoe peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sh-Lag85	a	pg119, fig2LJ	W	2	APN	Relatively numerous marked perikarya were consistently found in ipsi anterior pretectal nucleus, mainly in pars reticularis, whereas occasional labeled neurons appeared contralaterally in same nuc.	ZI	In 21 animals (8 WGA-HRP, 13 HRP cases) injection sites were found to be almost entirely confined to the subthalamic region. In 15 expts the injs were centred in different regions of the ZI	r
					Carst90	f5	pg619, fig5	W	2	NOT	labeled neurons were also seen in ... Sol (NOT)	ZI	In one case we successfully injected ZI with little involvement of the ventrobasal complex (with WGA-HRP / colloidal gold)	r
					Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	ZI	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle runs across the lateral part of the ventrobasal complex and distributes terminals into the zona incerta, especially in its pars caudalis and pars ventralis	a
			1	2	Rog&Cad85	a	pg482	H	1	NPC	Only exceptionally was cell labeling noted in nucleus of posterior commissure, characteristic light labeling in PRT.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
					Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	APN	induced sparse cellular and terminal labeling in the lateral part of the caudal APc	ZI	a tracer deposit (WGA?) restricted to the zona incerta	r
			c	2	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	FF	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to ... H1 & H2 fields of Forel	a
					Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	ZI	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... zona incerta	a
APN	IO	2	2	1	Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the ... posterior and anterior pretectal nuclei. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
			0	1	vdT&vdW9	a	pg449	C	0	APN	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injs into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
APN	PG	2	2	2	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	PG	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres proceed ventrocaudally through the oral part of the pontine reticular nucleus and terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, lateral and medial divisions of the pontine grey	a
					Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	TRN	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, ... and in the dorsal aspect of the reticular nucleus of the tegmentum	a
			1	1	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	APN	only a few cells in APc	PG	following tracer deposits in the basal pontine gray (WGA-HRP)	r
			0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
APN	TRN	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	TRN	ventral bunch of descending bundle: ... fibres terminate in the basilar pontine nuclei-dorsal peduncular area, ... and in the dorsal aspect of the reticular nucleus of the tegmentum	a
			0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r

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APN	PRP	2	2	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	APN	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
APN	OP	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	OP	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: emerges medially from the APc and gives terminals to the posterior (except case PP4) and olivary pretectal nuclei	a
APN	PPT	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	PPT	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: emerges medially from the APc and gives terminals to the posterior (except case PP4) and olivary pretectal nuclei	a
APN	SC	2	2	2	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCi	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
												SCs	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
					1	1	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	APN	case RC14 also exhibited some cell labelling in the olivary pretectal and anterior pretectal nuclei	SC
APN	SCi	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCi	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
APN	SCs	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg90, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	SCs	dorsal bunch of the descending bundle: ... enters the stratum album intermediale of the superior colliculus, fibres terminate essentially in the superficial layers: stratum opticum and stratum griseum superficiale. some terminals found in deep layers	a
APN	ATN	3	3	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	APN	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	APN	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	APN	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	APN	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r					

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			1	1	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	1	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LD	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle... occasional labelling also appeared in the lateral dorsal and ventral lateral thalamic nuclei	a
APN	LD	3	3	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	APN	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	APN	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
			2	3	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	APN	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	APN	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	APN	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			1	1	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	1	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LD	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle... occasional labelling also appeared in the lateral dorsal and ventral lateral thalamic nuclei	a
APN	LGd	1	1	1	Turl93	A	pg230, fig2	F	1	APN	in both strains <pigmented and albinos>, about 200-250 cells of the dorsal part of the non-retino-recipient anterior pretectal nucleus formed a predominantly ipsilateral projection to the DLG	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
APN	CL	3	3	1	Carst90	f1	pg616, fig1	W	3	APN	Many labeled neurons were also observed in ... caudal part of the anterior pretectal nucleus	CL/CL/CM/MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r
APN	LP	2	2	1	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LP	dorsal bunch of the ascending bundle proceeds dorsally in a rostral direction and distributes terminals in the rostral part of the lateral posterior thalamic nucleus	a
APN	PO	3	3	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	3	APN	the anterior pretectal nucleus was the most heavily labelled	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
APN	LGv	3	3	1	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	3	APN	a dense pattern of both retrograde and anterograde labeling occurs in the APc	LGv	bilateral applications of WGA-HRP in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus	r
			2	3	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368	H	2	APN	Pretectal area: Scattered labeled neurons are found in the olivary, anterior, and posterior pretectal nuclei.	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	APN	Some neurons in other subcortical structures was also labeled (bilaterally with ips dominance): anterior pretectal nucleus	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	LGv	dorsal bunch of the ascending bundle: ... some fibres continue laterally in the thalamic radiation, passing through the dorsal lateral geniculate before terminating in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, densest in medial(parvocellular) div.	a
			1	1	MS83	C	pg32	W	1	APN	In pretectum, a few labelled cells were in the ipsilateral anterior pretectal nucleus	LGv/LGv/LGd	one injection of WGA-HRP and three injections of unconjugated HRP were centred in LGNv, a small amount of HRP leaked dorsally	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
APN	RT	2	2	1	MS83	B	pg27,29, fig2FH,3	W	2	APN	labelled cells located in ... ipsilateral anterior pretectal nucleus	RT	In three animals injections of WGA-HRP were made into visual RNT	r
APN	ZI	2	2	3	Caduss91	ant	pg91, fig5,6	P	2	APN	PHA-L injections. In all 3 cases examined, the efferent projections displayed the same basic pattern. Two bundles originate from the APc and course ipsilaterally in the descending and ascending directions, each being made of a dorsal and a ventral bunch	ZI	ventral bunch of the ascending bundle runs across the lateral part of the ventrobasal complex and distributes terminals into the zona incerta, especially in its pars caudalis and pars ventralis	a
					Sh-Lag85	a	pg119, fig2I,J	W	2	APN	Relatively numerous marked perikarya were consistently found in ipsi anterior pretectal nucleus, mainly in pars reticularis, whereas occasional labeled neurons appeared contralaterally in same nuc.	ZI	In 21 animals (8 WGA-HRP, 13 HRP cases) injection sites were found to be almost entirely confined to the subthalamic region. In 15 expts the injs were centred in different regions of the ZI	r
					Rog&Cad85	a	pg483, fig3D	H	2	APN	small number of labeled cells was consistently observed within anterior pretectal nucleus, except when HRP deposited in rostralmost sector of ZI (case ZI 11), characteristic light labeling in PRT.	ZI	Horseshoe peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
			1	1	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	APN	induced sparse cellular and terminal labeling in the lateral part of the caudal APc	ZI	a tracer deposit (WGA?) restricted to the zona incerta	r
NOT	IO	2	2	4	Swe&Cas83 b	a16	pg264, fig 1,5,16,6H	A	2	NOT	More rostral pretectal injections (fig1, inj16) which included most of the rostral part of the nucleus of the optic tract...	IO	Heavy labeling was observed in the ipsilateral dorsal cap	a
					Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					Swe&Cas83 a	A923	pg331,335, fig2	H	2	NOT	Labeled neurons of the rostral brainstem were predominantly ipsilateral to the inj site but had a relatively small contralateral repr as well. Nuclei with this general pattern included the ... nucleus of the optic tract.	IO	Stereotaxic injs of HRP were made into the inferior olive complex of 52 Long-Evans black-hooded rats following both dorsal(n=19) and ventral(n=33) approaches to BS. Results from animal 923 repr of several animals. limited spread to RF.	r
					vdT&vdW9 2	a	pg449, fig1	C	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled neurons were found in the superficial & deep layers of the NOT. Neurons randomly dispersed in the NOT, with some clustering of their cell bodies,	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP injs into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
			c	2	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	IO	Fibres branch. One branch ... proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 2nd: descends within the pyramidal tract and ... terminates within the posterior one-half of the dorsal cap of Kooy	a
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	IO	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
NOT	PG	2	2	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	2	NOT	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
			1	1	Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1L,	H	1	NOT	small number of labeled neurons found within the nucleus of the optic tract. In 3 of the 6 medial & intermediate NRTP inj sites cases, label is ipsi In one case, label is bilat due to spread of inj into contra NRTP. input from NOT surprisingly small.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
			c	4	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	PG	Fibres branch. One branch targets the dor.lat. and lat. pontine nuclei, other proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 1st : terminates throughout the ros. cau. extent of dor.med. pontine nucleus	a
					Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	TRN	Pretectal axons enter the NRTP and continue caudally in both portions of the NRTP, the central and pericentral subdivisions. Projections are strictly ipsilateral. Terminal fields: ros. 2/3 of NRTPc and ros. & mid. levels of NRTPp	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	PG	HRP injection into the pontine nuclei (mainly the lateral part of the nuclei) <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	TRN	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
NOT	TRN	2	2	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	2	NOT	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
			1	1	Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1L,	H	1	NOT	small number of labeled neurons found within the nucleus of the optic tract. In 3 of the 6 medial & intermediate NRTP inj sites cases, label is ipsi In one case, label is bilat due to spread of inj into contra NRTP. input from NOT surprisingly small.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
			c	2	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	TRN	Pretectal axons enter the NRTP and continue caudally in both portions of the NRTP, the central and pericentral subdivisions. Projections are strictly ipsilateral. Terminal fields: ros. 2/3 of NRTPc and ros. & mid. levels of NRTPp	a
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	NOT	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral NOT	TRN	HRP injection into nucleus tegmenti pontis or the inferior olive nucleus <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
NOT	PRP	3	3	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	3	NOT	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
			c	1	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/ APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	PRP	Fibres branch. One branch ... proceeds medially and enters the rostral NRTP. Traverses NRTP & divides into 3 bundles. 2nd: ultimately targets the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus>. Entirely ipsi.	a
NOT	ATN	3	3	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	NOT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	NOT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	NOT	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
NOT	LD	3	3	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	NOT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	NOT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the nucleus of the optic tract. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	NOT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	NOT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	NOT	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
NOT	ZI	2	2	1	Carst90	f5	pg619, fig5	W	2	NOT	labeled neurons were also seen in ... Sol (NOT)	ZI	In one case we successfully injected ZI with little involvement of the ventrobasal complex (with WGA-HRP / colloidal gold)	r
			c	2	Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	ZI	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to the ipsilateral ... zona incerta	a
					Korp89	c	pg278, fig1	A	-1	NOT/NOT/APN/PPT/O P/LP	PRT injected with [3H]leucine in 5 animals. Case V-378 is representative ... inj site involved the NOT, as well as adjacent portions of the APN, PPN and PON. <fig 1 shows inclusion of LP in inj site>	FF	In confirmation of previous studies, the pretectum projects to ... H1 & H2 fields of Forel	a
OP	IO	0	0	2	Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	0	OP	Blue labeled cells were not seen in the pretectal olivary nucleus. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
					vdT&vdW92	a	pg449	C	0	OP	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
OP	PG	2	2	1	Caduss91	control 7	pg93	W	2	OP	numerous labelled cells occurred in the olivary pretectal nucleus	PG	following tracer deposits in the basal pontine gray (WGA-HRP)	r
			0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
OP	TRN	0	0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
OP	PRP	2	2	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	OP	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
OP	ATN	3	3	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	OP	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	OP	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... olivary pretectal nucleus... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	2	OP	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	OP	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	OP	No cells were seen in TO or OL	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
OP	PO	1	1	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	OP	a few cells could be detected in the olivary pretectal nucleus	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
PPT	IO	2	2	1	Robson83	io	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons that were clearly labeled with cytoplasmic blue granules were found prominently in the ... posterior and anterior pretectal nuclei. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	IO	An injection of 75nl true blue and granular blue was placed in the inferior olive complex, inj involved several parts of the olivary complex, including the dorsal cap, the medial accessory olive and the principal olive.	r
			0	1	vdT&vdW9	a	pg449	C	0	PPT	No labeled neurons were found in the other pretectal nuclei	IO	Inj sites after CTB-HRP inj into the brain stem always included at least one side of the inferior olive. In 1 case, both sides of IO & the medial longitudinal fasciculus, paramedian retic nuc, & pyramidal tract.	r
PPT	PG	0	0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
PPT	TRN	0	0	1	Korp89	a	pg278	H	0	OP/NPC/PP T/MPT/AP N	HRP labeled neurons were only observed in dorsal parts of the rostromedial NOT	TRN	Cases in which HRP was placed into the NTRP of 7 animals, minimal spread to adjacent reticular nuclei, and injections were all unilateral	r
PPT	PRP	2	2	1	Korp89	b	pg278	H	2	PPT	A majority of HRP-labeled neurons are present in the rostral portions of the ipsilateral NOT and a lesser number of labeled neurons are present within the PON, APN, and PPN	PRP/PRP/M V	HRP was injected into the ph <prepositus hypoglossi nucleus> of 11 animals. Injection sites were largely confined to ph, although some spread to the medial vestibular nucleus occurred, some spillage to contralateral ph	r
PPT	APN	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	2	PPT	short projections arising bilaterally in the posterior pretectal nucleus, contralateral neurons were more strongly fluorescent	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
			1	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	1	PPT	some positive neurons also appeared in the ... posterior pretectal nucleus, ...	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
PPT	ATN	3	3	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	3	PPT	Heaviest retrograde labeling occurred in the ipsilateral pretectal complex, especially the pretectal nuclei that receive direct retical projections. i.e: OL, PP & OT. Labeled cells were also found in PA and PM	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f2	pg191-2, fig2	H	3	PPT	Retrogradely labeled neuron somata in all major divisions of the pretectal complex, q.v. fig2: intense labeling in PA, PM, and PP & moderate labeling of cells in TO & OL	LD	Relatively large injections of HRP in LD	r
			2	3	Robson83	ld	pg94, fig1,2	F	2	PPT	Neurons with a nucleus clearly labeled with nuclear yellow were found in all pretectal nuclei, including the ... anterior and posterior pretectal nuclei... most prominent labelling. NO double PRT->IO/LD cells	LD	An injection of 50nl nuclear yellow was placed in the thalamic lateral dorsal nucleus... Injection did not involve the central lateral or lateral posterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	PPT	Pretectal labeling in this case was found only in PA, PP & PM.	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r

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					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	PPT	retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in the pretectal complex, including TO, PP, PA, especially in its pars compacta, OL and PM.	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
				x	2	Sikes&Vogt87	abstract		-1	PPT		ATN		
						Sik&Vog87	abstract		-1	PPT	minor PRT-ATN projection	ATN		
SC	IO	3	3	1	Red87	2482	pg162, fig5,6	W	3	SC	Injection site <WGA-HRP> centred on the lateral part of the intermediate white layer. Intermediate blue-white zone extended across all collicular layers and encroached slightly onto underlying tegmentum	IO	Fibres leave the predorsal bundle ventrally to enter the inferior olive where there is a patch of intense terminal label in its caudal part, probably corresponding to the caudal part of the medial accessory olive contra.	a
				2	2	Gay&Fau88	a pg260, fig6	W	2	SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	IOma	Anterograde label is present in the subnucleus C of the caudal 1/2 of the contralateral MAO. At caud lvls, terminals are seen ventrally & at more rosl lvls terminals shift to venmed & med margins of the MAO	a
						Swe&Cas83b	a7 pg264, fig 1,5,7	A	2	SCd	6 injections of the stratum profundum (fig1, inj7) displayed a labeling pattern similar to that after caudal pretectum injns <Which were into the NB> ...	IO	... i.e. contralateral subnuc c of the Mao and the medial part of the ipsilateral Pod.	a
				1	2	Red87	xxx pg159	F	1	SC	very few labeled cells in ipsilateral superior colliculus	IO	Separate experiments ... using retrograde transport of fluorescent dyes ... caudo-medial olivary injections	r
						Swe&Cas83a	A923 pg331,335, fig2	H	1	SCd	The caudal portions of the pretectum and the small cells of the stratum profundum of the superior colliculus were labeled mainly on the side contralateral to the inj.	IO	Stereotaxic injns of HRP were made into the inferior olive complex of 52 Long-Evans black-hooded rats following both dorsal(n=19) and ventral(n=33) approaches to BS. Results from animal 923 repr of several animals. limited spread to RF.	r
				c	1	Akaik92	a pg401, fig8	W	-1	SC	20 rats ... glass pipettes filled with WGA-HRP soln were placed in the SC stereotaxically. Tracer ejected electrophoretically... injected into rostralateral region,	IOma	one case, with representative anterograde labeling of terminals of tecto-olivary fibres in the IO nucleus... 4 of 10 coronal sections which contain labeled areas in contralateral MAO illustrated in A-D	a
SC	PG	3	3	4	Red87	2482	pg162, fig5,6	W	3	SC	Injection site <WGA-HRP> centred on the lateral part of the intermediate white layer. Intermediate blue-white zone extended across all collicular layers and encroached slightly onto underlying tegmentum	TRN	Fibres turn ventrally from the predorsal bundle to reach the nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis. Intense terminal label appears to be mainly in the central division of this nucleus. contra.	a
						Kunz&Schnyd84	a pg517, fig5AC, fig6B	W	3	SC	Anterograde transport after collicular injections of Met, WGA, WGA-HRP, and Gly.	PG	We were unable to identify a terminal pattern of labeling within the lateral tegmentum because of the densely labeled fibres passing to the Pbg and the pontine gray.	a
						Chev&Deni84	A pg433, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	PG	Figs 1 and 2 illustrate the dense innervation by the lateral SC onto the dorsolateral wing of the ipsilateral pontine nuclei	a
						Red87	2302 pg159, fig2	W	3	SC/SC/PPT/NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	PG	Some fibres continue ventrally until they reach the pons where dense terminal label can be seen at the dor.lat. margin of the pyramidal tract, and in puffs in the lateral pontine nuclei. Puffs not observed after injections more medial than 2302.	a
				2	4	Gay&Fau88	a pg258-260, fig5	W	2	SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	TRN	ant label present in the contra Rtp and inferior olive. dense in med.margin of Rtp & sparse in lat. margin	a
						Gay&Fau88	a pg258-260, fig5	W	2	SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	PG	ant. label bilat. in the pontine nuclei. 2 groups of descending fibres: ipsi mainly terminate in the dorlat, peduncular & lat nuclear groups of caudal pons. Others cross & terminate in dorlat PG, dense in med.margin of Rtp & sparse in lat. margin	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCi	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injns showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
					Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCd	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injns showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
		1		1	Red87	2482	pg162, fig5,6	W	1	SC	Injection site <WGA-HRP> centred on the lateral part of the intermediate white layer. Intermediate blue-white zone extended across all collicular layers and encroached slightly onto underlying tegmentum	PG	Small amount of lighter label in medial pontine nucleus, contra.	a
		c		4	Burn81	a	pg292, fig4	A	-1	SC/SC/PAG	orthograde transport of labeled amino acids. Case89: med. 1/2 of SC; 1.3mm roscau.; 1.6mm medlat.; 1.2mm dorven. focus of autoradiographic label over ventral layers of SC (SCig->SCdw) with slight encroachment on dorsal edge of central gray	PG	label localized to caudal 1/2 of pons... over peduncular and dorsomedial subdivisions of the basilar ponine nuclei & NRTP. In summary neurons of SCmedial give rise to terminal field over ipsi lateral peduncular regions & conta dormed NRTP	a
					Burn81	a	pg292, fig4	A	-1	SC/SC/PAG	orthograde transport of labeled amino acids. Case89: med. 1/2 of SC; 1.3mm roscau.; 1.6mm medlat.; 1.2mm dorven. focus of autoradiographic label over ventral layers of SC (SCig->SCdw) with slight encroachment on dorsal edge of central gray	TRN	label localized to caudal 1/2 of pons... over ... NRTP. In summary neurons of SCmedial give rise to terminal field over ... conta dormed NRTP. Clusters of silver grains (axons of psg?) & accumulations (terms?) obs over dormed NRTP, not far dormed/far cau pole	a
					Red87	2302	pg154, fig2	W	-1	SC/SC/PPT/NOT/PAG	A large centrally-located (WGA-HRP) inj with a central zone that extended across all collicular lvls. Slight invasion of intermed blue/white zone of ... PPT, NOT & dorlat PAG. Same main features in 5 other large & some similarities with small injns	PG	ipsilaterally descending pathway: mass of intensely labelled fibres ... travel ventrally to innervate dor.lat. pontine nuclei	a
					Tera79	a	pg412, fig7	H	-1	SC	labelled cells found in the ipsilateral superior colliculus	PG	HRP injection into the pontine nuclei (mainly the lateral part of the nuclei) <no figures or description of the extent of the injection site.>	r
		x		1	Redgr87		abstract		-1	SC		PG	dorsolateral basilar pons	
SC	TRN	3		3	Red87	2482	pg162, fig5,6	W	3	SC	Injection site <WGA-HRP> centred on the lateral part of the intermediate white layer. Intermediate blue-white zone extended across all collicular layers and encroached slightly onto underlying tegmentum	TRN	Fibres turn ventrally from the predorsal bundle to reach the nucleus reticularis tegmenti pontis. Intense terminal label appears to be mainly in the central division of this nucleus, contra.	a
		2		3	Gay&Fau88	a	pg258-260, fig5	W	2	SC	Fig4 shows a typical injection site in SC <central WGA-HRP inj, all layers> & the resultant retrograde & anterograde labelling in the various cerebellar & precerebellar nuclei.	TRN	ant label present in the contra Rtp and inferior olive. dense in med.margin of Rtp & sparse in lat. margin	a
					Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCi	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injns showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
					Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCd	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injns showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
		c		1	Burn81	a	pg292, fig4	A	-1	SC/SC/PAG	orthograde transport of labeled amino acids. Case89: med. 1/2 of SC; 1.3mm roscau.; 1.6mm medlat.; 1.2mm dorven. focus of autoradiographic label over ventral layers of SC (SCig->SCdw) with slight encroachment on dorsal edge of central gray	TRN	label localized to caudal 1/2 of pons... over ... NRTP. In summary neurons of SCmedial give rise to terminal field over ... conta dormed NRTP. Clusters of silver grains (axons of psg?) & accumulations (terms?) obs over dormed NRTP, not far dormed/far cau pole	a

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SC	MRN	1	1	1	Red87	2482	pg162, fig5,6	W	1	SC	Injection site <WGA-HRP> centred on the lateral part of the intermediate white layer. Intermediate blue-white zone extended across all collicular layers and encroached slightly onto underlying tegmentum	MRN	Fibres from the predorsal bundle can be seen entering areas of weak terminal label in the mesencephalic reticular formation underlying the sup coll. contra.	a
SC	PBG	3	3	1	Kunz&Schnyd84	a	pg517, fig5AC, fig6B	W	3	SC	Anterograde transport after collicular injections of Met, WGA, WGA-HRP, and Gly.	PBG	resulted in labeling within the ipsi Pbg. In the Gly & Met cases there were also faint silver grain accumulations over the contra Pbg... densely labeled fibres passing to the Pbg and the pontine gray.	a
					Sef84	b	pg145-6, fig1C	H	2	SCs	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)... When small injections were made into the superficial layers of the SC...	PBG	We always found HRP-filled terminals, indicative of anterograde transport in both dorsal and ventral divisions.	a
					Tanaka85	b	pg82, fig1	H	-1	SC	20 male rats injected with HRP into the SC under visual guidance after aspirating the overlying cerebral cortex... injns were made at various depths.	PBG	one bundle of fibres were traced lateroventrally into the reticular formation and the parabigeminal nucleus where it terminated.	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	PBG	labelled terminals were distributed uniformly throughout the parabigeminal nuclei	a
SC	APN	3	3	3	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCs	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCi	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	SCs	the largest mesencephalic input to the APc arises from the superior colliculus. In all cases numerous labeled cells were located in the superficial layers, especially in the optic layer. +ve neurons were ... distributed over entire mediolateral extent	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injns. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Foster89		pg691	W	-1	SC	anterograde transport of WGA-HRP following injection into the superior colliculus	APN	a labelling of varicose fibres in the ipsilateral APTA	a
					Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	APN	terminal label found in the anterior pretectal nucleus	a
SC	VISp	0	0	1	Sef81	e	pg8	H	0	SC	there were no labelled cells in SC	VISp	single of multiple injections into cortical area 17	r
SC	ATN	2	2	4	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	SC	Labeled cells were also observed bilaterally in {4,5} and ipsilaterally in {6} of the superior colliculus	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	SC	Retrogradely labeled cells in the superior colliculus were found in the rostral portions of laminae 4,5,6	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCdg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

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					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SC	CL	3	3	4	Chev&Deni84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	CL	fibres ... projected densely to the central-medial, paracentral, central-lateral and the neighbouring lateral part of the mediadorsal nucleus	a
					Yamas86	c	pg230, fig5	A	3	SC	rats were injected with 3H-leucine, <where? assume SC>	CL	SC projected heavily to Pf, CL and o adjacent, medial portion of PO	a
					Carst90	fl	pg616, fig1	W	3	SCi	Many labeled neurons were also observed in the intermediate to deep layers of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	CL/CL/CM/MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r
					Carst90	fl	pg616, fig1	W	3	SCd	Many labeled neurons were also observed in the intermediate to deep layers of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	CL/CL/CM/MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r
			c	2	Carst90	f4	pg619, fig4	W	-1	SC	labelled a relatively smaller <Than CM injections> but in a distribution similar to that seen in following the CM injection	CL	A gold (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) microinjection restricted largely to CL	r
					Groene88	rp8449	pg409, fig27,28,29	P	-1	SC	Three injections of WGA-HRP and three PHA-L injections were placed in the superior colliculus. in rat RP-8449 PHA-L inj site shows a number of darkly stained neurons, mainly located in the intermediate and deep layers of the SC	CL	Anterogradely labeled fibres in the dorsal thalamus are present in the lateral posterior, the mediadorsal, the central lateral, the paracentral, and the central medial nuclei	a
SC	PF	3	3	2	Chev&Deni84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	PF	rostral to the pretectal nuclei a large number of thick labelled fibres coursed medially and passed through parafascicular nucleus... These fibres provided a substantial innervation to the parafascicular and the adjoining posterior thalamic nuclear group.	a
					Yamas86	c	pg230, fig5	A	3	SC	rats were injected with 3H-leucine, <where? assume SC>	PF	SC projected heavily to Pf, CL and o adjacent, medial portion of PO	a
			1	1	Corn&Phil88b	f3	pg142, fig3	W	1	SCd	Very occasional lightly stained single cells were also found further medial in the deep layers of the superior colliculus	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
			c	2	Gerf82	pf_inj_r	pg292	W	-1	SC	Labeled perikarya were found bilaterally in the ... superior colliculus	PF	<WGA-HRP> injections into the parafascicular nucleus	r
					Gerf82	sca	pg298	W	-1	SC	Injections <WGA-HRP> into the rostral superior colliculus	PF	resulted in terminal labeling in the paramellar mediadorsal, parafascicular and ventromedial thalamic nuclei	a
SC	PO	3	3	2	Chev&Deni84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	PO	rostral to the pretectal nuclei a large number of thick labelled fibres coursed medially and passed through parafascicular nucleus... These fibres provided a substantial innervation to the parafascicular and the adjoining posterior thalamic nuclear group	a
					Yamas86	c	pg230, fig5	A	3	SC	rats were injected with 3H-leucine, <where? assume SC>	POm	SC projected heavily to Pf, CL and o adjacent, medial portion of PO	a
			2	2	Rog&Cad84	b	pg479	H	2	SCd	following HRP deposits into ... deep layers of the lateral sc	PO	anterograde transport of the enzyme resulted in axon-terminal labeling within tp	a
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	2	SCiw	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r

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			1	3	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	SCdw	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	SCdg	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	SCig	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
			0	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478	H	0	SCop/SCsg/ SCzo	no cells found in superficial layers of sup. coll.	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
SC	POm	3	3	1	Yamas86	c	pg230, fig5	A	3	SC	rats were injected with 3H-leucine, <where? assume SC>	POm	SC projected heavily to Pf, CL and o adjacent, medial portion of PO	a
SC	MD	3	3	2	Groene88	rp8449	pg409, fig27,28,29	P	3	SC	Three injections of WGA-HRP and three PHA-L injections were placed in the superior colliculus. in rat RP-8449 PHA-L inj site shows a number of darkly stained neurons, mainly located in the intermediate and deep layers of the SC	MD	Anterogradely labeled fibres in the dorsal thalamus are present in ... the mediodorsal ... nuclei. In MD label mainly in lat segment with a few fibres in ven and lat parts. med zone of lat MD segment remains free of label. dense patch in caud 1/2 of MD	a
					Chev&Deni 84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	3	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	MDI	fibres ... projected densely to the central-medial, paracentral, central-lateral and the neighbouring lateral part of the mediodorsal nucleus	a
			2	2	Matsuy&Ka wa85	a	pg343, fig6,7	W	2	SCd	These injections produced retrograde labeling of cells in the PRT and SC. Pattern of labeled cells similar to that of orthograde labels after injection into the prefrontal cortex. Cells in deep layers (IV,V & VI) with ventral extension into dorsal PAG	MD	In 3 rats the injection sites were placed in the MD. <WGA-HRP>	r
					Gerf82	md	pg292-5, fig10	W	2	SC	In excess of 80 labeled perikarya were observed in each of the following brain areas: ... (7) the superior colliculus bilaterally. <Obs from fig 10: labeled cells appear in deeper layers laterally>	MD	Iontophoretic injections of WGA-HRP were made into the mediodorsal thalamic nucleus and included the central lateral intralaminar nucleus. There was little detectable spread of the tracer into the intralaminar nuclei.	r
			c	1	Gerf82	sca	pg298	W	-1	SC	Injections <WGA-HRP> into the rostral superior colliculus	MD	resulted in terminal labeling in the paralamellar mediodorsal, parafascicular and ventromedial thalamic nuclei	a
			x	1	Ray92	abstract			-1	SC		MD		
SC	PVT	0	0	1	Groene88	rp8449	pg409, fig27,28,29	P	0	SC	Three injections of WGA-HRP and three PHA-L injections were placed in the superior colliculus. in rat RP-8449 PHA-L inj site shows a number of darkly stained neurons, mainly located in the intermediate and deep layers of the SC	PVT	In none of the experiments is anterograde labelling observed in the paraventricular or the lateral habenula	a
SC	ZI	3	3	1	Kim92	a	pg564, fig10	P	3	SCig	figure18 summarizes the results of a case in which PHA-L was injected into the superior colliculus... The inj site involved primarily the lateral 1/3 of the intermediate gray layer...	ZI	Fig18B&C illustrates the distribution of labeled terminals in the zona incerta. The projection is topographic and dense in the ventral subdivision.	a
			2	8	Rog&Cad85	a	pgg482, fig3.5, table1	H	2	SCd	Labeled neurons in the SC equally distributed btwn the intermediate and deep layers (table1: from 0-44 cells, all but 1 cell in 1 case purely ipsi), no cells identified in superficial layers. SCdp whole medlat ext. SCint more lateral.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
					Rog&Cad85	a	pgg482, fig3.5, table1	H	2	SCi	Labeled neurons in the SC equally distributed btwn the intermediate and deep layers (table1: from 0-44 cells, all but 1 cell in 1 case purely ipsi), no cells identified in superficial layers. SCdp whole medlat ext. SCint more lateral.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r

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					Perr80	R11	pg921-2	A	2	SC	an injection of 0.5µl of [3H]leucine into the lateral and caudal part of the superior colliculus. The injection involved superficial and deep layers	ZI	the collicular injections led to labelling ... into the zona incerta	a
					Chev&Deni84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	2	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	ZI	the ventral contingent (of fibres running through parafascicular nucleus) innervated the subthalamic field (zona incerta, Forel field.)	a
					Carst90	f5	pg619, fig5	W	2	SC	Neurons in the SC and SN were labeled predominantly ipsilaterally	ZI	In one case we successfully injected ZI with little involvement of the ventrobasal complex (with WGA-HRP / colloidal gold)	r
					Sh-Lag85	a	pg119-20, fig2	W	2	SCi	Relatively numerous ipsi & a few contra marked perikarya appeared in the superior colliculus, mainly in the lateral 2/3 of the intermediate and deep layers. Table1: ipsi:++(moderate), cont:+(sparse)	ZI	In 21 animals (8 WGA-HRP, 13 HRP cases) injection sites were found to be almost entirely confined to the subthalamic region. In 15 expts the injs were centred in different regions of the ZI	r
					Sh-Lag85	a	pg119-20, fig2	W	2	SCd	Relatively numerous ipsi & a few contra marked perikarya appeared in the superior colliculus, mainly in the lateral 2/3 of the intermediate and deep layers. Table1: ipsi:++(moderate), cont:+(sparse)	ZI	In 21 animals (8 WGA-HRP, 13 HRP cases) injection sites were found to be almost entirely confined to the subthalamic region. In 15 expts the injs were centred in different regions of the ZI	r
					Chev&Deni84	A	pg433, fig1,2	W	2	SC	a unilateral deposit (20-30 nl) of a 4% WGA-HRP solution in the lateral portion of the SC intermediate strata, the enzyme spread throughout the lateral SC... spread remained confined within rostro-caudal and dorsoventral boundaries of the nucleus	FF	the ventral contingent (of fibres running through parafascicular nucleus) innervated the subthalamic field (zona incerta, Forel field.)	a
			c	1	Taylor86	1st	pg137, fig3	H	-1	SC/SC/PAG/MRN	in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of the midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	ZI	A concentration of labelled terminals around retrogradely labelled cells was seen in the zona incerta	a
			0	1	Rog&Cad85	a	pgg482, fig3.5, table1	H	0	SCs	Labeled neurons in the SC equally distributed btwn the intermediate and deep layers (table1: from 0-44 cells, all but 1 cell in 1 case purely ipsi), no cells identified in superficial layers. SCdp whole medlat ext. SCint more lateral.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
SCi	PG	2	2	1	Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCi	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injs showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
SCi	TRN	2	2	1	Tori86	A	pg94, table1, fig1J	H	2	SCi	Labeling in superior colliculus is entirely contra in the small inj site cases. All labeled neurons are located within or below the stratum opticum in the intermediate & deep layers. Lrge injs showed abundant labeling in all layers except SCsg	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
SCi	APN	3	3	1	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCi	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
SCi	ATN	2	2	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCi	CL	3	3	1	Carst90	f1	pg616, fig1	W	3	SCi	Many labeled neurons were also observed in the intermediate to deep layers of the ipsilateral superior colliculus	CL/CL/CM/MDm	An (WGA-HRP / colloidal gold) injection which involved CL, medial MD and part of CM.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
SCi	PO	2	2	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	2	SCiw	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	SCig	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
SCi	ZI	3	3	1	Kim92	a	pg564, fig10	P	3	SCig	figure18 summarizes the results of a case in which PHA-L was injected into the superior colliculus.... The inj site involved primarily the lateral 1/3 of the intermediate gray layer...	ZI	Fig18B&C illustrates the distribution of labeled terminals in the zona incerta. The projection is topographic and dense in the ventral subdivision.	a
					Sh-Lag85	a	pg119-20, fig2	W	2	SCi	Relatively numerous ipsi & a few contra marked perikarya appeared in the superior colliculus, mainly in the lateral 2/3 of the intermediate and deep layers. Table1: ipsi:++(moderate), cont:+(sparse)	ZI	In 21 animals (8 WGA-HRP, 13 HRP cases) injection sites were found to be almost entirely confined to the subthalamic region. In 15 expts the injs were centred in different regions of the ZI	r
					Rog&Cad85	a	pgg482, fig3.5, table1	H	2	SCi	Labeled neurons in the SC equally distributed btwn the intermediate and deep layers (table1: from 0-44 cells, all but 1 cell in 1 case purely ipsi), no cells identified in superficial layers. SCdp whole medlat ext. SCint more lateral.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
SCig	ATN	2	2	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	SCig	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCig	PO	1	1	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	SCig	labelled neurons could also be found in the medial and deep layers of the superior colliculus, mainly in stratum album mediale, some in stratum griseum profundum and stratum album profundum on few occasions in stratum griseum mediale	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
SCig	ZI	3	3	1	Kim92	a	pg564, fig10	P	3	SCig	figure18 summarizes the results of a case in which PHA-L was injected into the superior colliculus.... The inj site involved primarily the lateral 1/3 of the intermediate gray layer...	ZI	Fig18B&C illustrates the distribution of labeled terminals in the zona incerta. The projection is topographic and dense in the ventral subdivision.	a
SCs	PBG	2	2	1	Sef84	b	pg145-6, fig1C	H	2	SCs	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5)... When small injections were made into the superficial layers of the SC...	PBG	We always found HRP-filled terminals, indicative of anterograde transport in both dorsal and ventral divisions.	a
SCs	APN	3	3	2	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	SCs	a major innervation of the APTA arose in the ipsilateral superior colliculus, neurons occurred in all laminae but the bulk were found in medial zones of the superficial grey, optic nerve and intermediate grey layer	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	SCs	the largest mesencephalic input to the APc arises from the superior colliculus. In all cases numerous labeled cells were located in the superficial layers, especially in the optic layer. +ve neurons were ... distributed over entire mediolateral extent	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injs, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
SCs	ATN	0	0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCs	PO	0	0	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478	H	0	SCop/SCsg/SCzo	no cells found in superficial layers of sup. coll.	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
SCs	ZI	0	0	1	Rog&Cad85	a	pgg482, fig3,5, table1	H	0	SCs	Labeled neurons in the SC equally distributed btwn the intermediate and deep layers (table1: from 0-44 cells, all but 1 cell in 1 case purely ipsi). no cells identified in superficial layers. SCdp whole medlat ext. SCint more lateral.	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
SCop	PO	0	0	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478	H	0	SCop/SCsg/SCzo	no cells found in superficial layers of sup. coll.	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
SCsg	ATN	0	0	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	0	SCsg	Labeled neurons were also seen in the intermediate and deep gray layers of the superior colliculus, and were restricted to the anterior portions of these layers. No labeled cells were seen in the superficial gray layers of the colliculus	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
SCsg	PO	0	0	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478	H	0	SCop/SCsg/SCzo	no cells found in superficial layers of sup. coll.	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
LHA	IO	1	1	1	Villalo&Ferssi87	R725	pg98, R725, fig2	A	1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAp	IO		a
LHA	MRN	3	3	1	Steinin92		pg527, fig8DE		3	LHA		MRN	WGA-HRP inj, fig3, MEA	r
					Villalo&Ferssi87		pg96, R714		-1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAc	MRN	central tegmental field	a
					Steinin92		abstract		-1	LHA	& perifornical HY	MRN	midbrain extrapyramidal area, medially adjacent to PPN	
LHA	PRP	1	1	1	Villalo&Ferssi87		pg96, R714		1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAc	PRP		a
					Villalo&Ferssi87	R725	pg98, R725, fig2	A	-1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAp	PRP		a
LHA	PRT	c	c	1	Villalo&Ferssi87		pg96, R714		-1	LHA	3H A.A. inj into LHAc	PRT/APN	anterior pretectal area	a
LHA	TUA	c	c	1	Grove88b		pg329-30, fig10,12, RPLH5		-1	LHA	PHA-L inj into lateral hypothalamus	DMH		a
					TerHor&Lui t87		abstract		1	LHA		VMH		
					TerHor&Lui t87		abstract		-1	LHA		DMH		
LHA	VISL	2	2	1	Car&Rie87	R129	pg207, fig2	W	2	LHA	neurons scattered in lateral hypothalamus	VISL	21 WGA-HRP inj into 18a, lack of labelling in LGd, extensive labelling in LP	r
LHA	VISp	2	2	2	Car&Rie87	R125	pg209, fig6	W	2	LHA	neurons labelled in lateral hypothalamus	VISp	15 WGA-HRP inj into VISp, we consider those in lateral aspect	r
					Car&Rie87	R104	pg209, fig6	W	2	LHA	neurons labelled in lateral hypothalamus	VISp	15 WGA-HRP inj into VISp, we consider those in medial aspect	r
LHA	ATN	2	2	2	Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	W	2	LHA	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the ... lateral hypothalamus ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralaminar complex	r
LHA	PO	2	2	1	All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	LD		a
					All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	PO		a
LHA	MD	2	2	3	Gerf82		pg295, fig10		2	LHA	>80 cells, posterior, same area that projects to SN	MD	WGA-HRP inj	r
					All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9		2	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	MD		a
					All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2		2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	MD		a
					Corn&Phil88		abstract		-1	LHA	lateral hypothalamus	MD	all	
					Groene88		abstract		-1	LHA	lateral hypothalamus	MD		
LHA	PVT	2	2	2	All&Cech93	f9	pg431, fig9	P	2	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, POSTERIOR PFA, mainly ventral to the fornix and extended medial and dorsal to fornix	PVT		a
					All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	2	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	PVT		a
					All&Cech93	f7	pg428, fig7D	P	1	LHA	PHA-L pressor site inj, dense group of filled cells dorsal, medial and ventral to fornix	PVT	anterior and posterior regions	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
LHA	ZI	c	c	1	All&Cech93	f2	pg424, fig2	P	-1	LHA	PHA-L inj into depressor sites	ZI		a
			x	1	Rog&Cad85		abstract		2	LHA		ZI		
SCH	VNC	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	VNC		a
SCH	TUA	2	2	1	Watts87	A54	pg208,213,221, fig3NO	P	2	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	DMH	5th Pway. Fibres form a moderately dense plexus within dorsomedial nucleus of hypothalamus & in relatively cell sparse zone dorsal & medial to the ventromedial nucleus. Fibres tend to be thick/vaicosse, often branched & display terminal boutons.	a
			1	1	Watts&Swans87	E38	pg238, fig6	F	1	SCH	Within Sch, retrogradely labeled cells were more sparse & tended to be concentrated ventrally.	VMH	Two crystal were placed in the area of the ventromedial nucleus. The inj in expt E38 was centred dorsolaterally in VMH, tracer spread to fill nucleus & caudal parts of anterior hypothalamic area as well. Dye did not extend rostrally into SBPV / ARH / ME.	r
			0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	PMv		a
SCH	PVT	3	3	1	Watts&Swans87	E33	pg237, fig6,7	F	3	SCH	Both these expts (E30 & E33) produced heavy retrograde labeling in the region of the Sch.	PVT	Expt E33 involved a smaller liquid injection (than E30) in the paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus	r
			2	2	Watts87	A54	pg208,211, fig3H-N	P	2	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	PVT	3rd Pway. pathway courses ventrally to innervate the preoptic continuation of the bed nucleus as well as parataenia & paraventricular nuc of thalamus. In PT & PVT fibres are thin, widely spaced small varicosities and give rise to many terminal boutons.	a
					Watts87	A54	pg208,212, fig3I-Q	P	2	SCH	3 PHA-L injns were virtually limited to the Sch, with less than 5% of labeled neurons outside boundaries of nucleus itself. Injs A7 & A54 tended to label cells in ventral part of nucleus, while inj A25 extended more dorsally	PVT	5th Pway. Many fibres from PVH appear to continue dorsally through midline thalamic nuclei (reuniens, rhomboid & central medial) to end in more caudal parts of the PVT. Some branching/terminal boutons seen in PVT, much less freq in RE & RH.	a
SCH	ZI	1	1	1	Watts&Swans87	E48	pg240	F	1	SCH	In both expts (E50 & E48), many true blue labeled cells were seen in the vicinity of the Sch, although density was not as great as that following injections in PVH. Density greater in perinuclear regions. Only a very few cellss lay within nucleus itself.	ZI	Implant in E48 situated immediately dorsal to dorsomedial nucleus, but it did not appear to spread into the nucleus, being centred in zona incerta.	r
TUA	PRT	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg686, fig3	F	2	VMH	a relatively large projection from the hypothalamus to the APTA arose in its ventromedial part, principally on the ipsilateral side	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
TUA	APN	2	2	1	Foster89	f3	pg686, fig3	F	2	VMH	a relatively large projection from the hypothalamus to the APTA arose in its ventromedial part, principally on the ipsilateral side	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
TUA	SC	1	1	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	VMH	in the hypothalamic region there was a small number of of labelled cells mainly distributed in the nucleus ventromedialis	SC	In three cases (RC14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	VMH	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... ventromedial hypothalamic area, contained only a very few labelled cells	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
TUA	LHA	x	x	4	Cant&Swa92c		abstract		-1	PMv		LHA		
					TerHor&Luit87		abstract		1	DMH		LHA		
					TerHor&Luit87		abstract		1	VMH		LHA	ventromedial part of the tuberal LHA	
					Cant92		abstract		-1	PMv		LHA		
TUA	SCH	x	x	1	Marani87		abstract		-1	VMH		SCH		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
TUA	PVH	3	3	1	All&Cech93	f10	pg431, fig10	W	3	LHA/DMH/ PMv/PMd/P H/SUM	WGA-HRP inj	PVH	parvocellular	a	
			x	3	TerHor&Lui t87		abstract		3	DMH		PVH	parvocellular		
					TerHorst&L uiten86		abstract		-1	DMH		PVH	parvocellular		
					Cant92		abstract		-1	PMv		PVH	except SCH & MEPO		
TUA	MD	x	x	2	Cant&Swa9 2c		abstract		1	PMv		MD			
					Cant92		abstract		-1	PMv		MD			
TUA	PVT	1	1	1	All&Cech93	f10	pg431, fig10	W	1	LHA/DMH/ PMv/PMd/P H/SUM	WGA-HRP inj	PVT		a	
			x	2	Cant&Swa9 2c		abstract		1	PMv		PVT			
					Cant92		abstract		-1	PMv		PVT			
TUA	ZI	x	x	1	Rog&Cad85		abstract		3	VMH		ZI			
PVH	TUA	x	x	2	TerHor&Lui t87		abstract		-1	PVH		DMH			
					TerHor&Lui t87		abstract		-1	PVH		VMH			
PVH	PVT	1	1	1	Watts&Sw ns87	E33	pg237, fig6,7	F	1	PVH	True blue labeled cells completely surrounded the region of the paraventricular nucleus of the hypothalamus in E30. The number of true blue-labeled cells lower in E33, but such cells seen in AHA & strikingly in periventricular part of PVH	PVT	Expt E33 involved a smaller liquid injection (than E30) in the paraventricular nucleus of the thalamus	r	
VISL	PG	2	2	1	Wies82a	f6	pg221, fig6	H	2	VISL	Numerous labeled cells, most of them arranged in clusters of 0.5-1mm diameter. They were found in visual cortex (occipital areas Oc1, Oc2)... In decreasing order, density of labeled corticopontine cells was 1) Sml, 2) Motor Ctx, 3) SMII, 4) Visual areas ...	PG	case 79-196, 81-2: areas of HRP uptake relatively large in these cases & enzyme spread over ventral & lateral surface of nucleus. Fig6 illustrates case 79-196	r	
			c	1	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	PG	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a	
VISL	PRT	3	3	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISL	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cels were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r	
				2	1	Caduss91	control 3	pg93	W	2	VISL	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	Finally, deposits in area 17 produced relatively dense terminal labelling in the central part of the APc	a
				1	1	Caduss91	control 2	pg93	W	1	VISL	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	deposits in area 18a also included sparse terminal labelling in the APc but limited to a small portion of the nucleus	a
			c	6	Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	APN	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... dorsal portion of the anterior pretectal nucleus. ventral part only labelled by AL injections	a	
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	OP	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	NOT	an injection confined to area 18a labeled the retinal terminal zone of nto	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	APN	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	fig9A4	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L inj	NOT	<Obs from fig9A4>	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	APN	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... dorsal portion of the anterior pretectal nucleus. ventral part only labelled by AL injections	a
VISL	APN	3	3	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISL	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cels were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
					Caduss91	control 3	pg93	W	2	VISL	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	Finally, deposits in area 17 produced relatively dense terminal labelling in the central part of the APc	a
					Caduss91	control 2	pg93	W	1	VISL	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	deposits in area 18a also included sparse terminal labelling in the APc but limited to a small portion of the nucleus	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	APN	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... dorsal portion of the anterior pretectal nucleus. ventral part only labelled by AL injections	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	APN	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	APN	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... dorsal portion of the anterior pretectal nucleus. ventral part only labelled by AL injections	a
VISL	NOT	c	c	2	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	NOT	an injection confined to area 18a labeled the retinal terminal zone of nto	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	fig9A4	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L inj	NOT	<Obs from fig9A4>	a
VISL	OP	c	c	1	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	OP	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	SC	3	3	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	3	VISL	In all three cases the visual cortical areas were labelled, but to varying degrees: area 17 most densely, area 18a less so and area 18 least of all	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGL, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Olav82	f2	pg335, fig2	H	3	VISlm/VISa 1/VISFL/VI SPX	clusters of labeled pyramidal cells are observed in {5} of ... several regions of the cortex adjoining the lateral and anteromedial borders of V1. several fields arranged along an anteroposterior axis in the cortex adjacent to V1 and in fields more lateral	SC	The SC of nine adult gray rats was injected stereotaxically with 0.01-0.02µl of 30% HRP in saline	r
					Sef81	a	pg5, fig1G	H	2	VISL	There were smaller numbers (than in area17) in area 18 and fewer still in area 18a. In all 4 cases labelled cells in areas 17, 18 and 18a were confined to {5}	SC	injection of HRP into SC	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	4	Harv90	a	pg287, fig5H	W	1	VISal	(WGA-HRP) injection placed more rostrally in area 18a, probably in the AL region	SCig	anterograde label in the SC Although the density of terminals is not very high, label was clearly distributed in a lattice like arrangement with a prominent dorsal tier at the SGI/SO border and puffs joining to lighter tier at SGI/SAI.	a
					Harv90	a	pg287, fig4	W	1	VISlm	The (WGA-HRP) injection site was close to the lateral border of area 17 and was probably in area LM	SCop	Only light terminal labelling was seen in the SC ipsilateral to the injection site. Sparse label was scarred through the SO, but there seemed to be patches of more dense label	a
					Harv90	a	pg287, fig4,5	W	1	VISFL	The (WGA-HRP) injection was placed slightly more laterally in 18a, probably in area LI, or LL	SCi	In medial SC scattered terminals were found in SGI and SO. The label was not uniform within the SGI since there were areas devoid of corticotectal label. ...light labelling also extended into the SGS, particularly into its ventral half	a
					Harv90	a	pg287, fig4,5	W	1	VISFL	The (WGA-HRP) injection was placed slightly more laterally in 18a, probably in area LI, or LL	SCs	In medial SC scattered terminals were found in SGI and SO. The label was not uniform within the SGI since there were areas devoid of corticotectal label. ...light labelling also extended into the SGS, particularly into its ventral half	a
			c	2	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCsg	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCop	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	SCi	1	1	2	Harv90	a	pg287, fig5H	W	1	VISal	(WGA-HRP) injection placed more rostrally in area 18a, probably in the AL region	SCig	anterograde label in the SC Although the density of terminals is not very high, label was clearly distributed in a lattice like arrangement with a prominent dorsal tier at the SGI/SO border and puffs joining to lighter tier at SGI/SAI.	a
					Harv90	a	pg287, fig4,5	W	1	VISFL	The (WGA-HRP) injection was placed slightly more laterally in 18a, probably in area LI, or LL	SCi	In medial SC scattered terminals were found in SGI and SO. The label was not uniform within the SGI since there were areas devoid of corticotectal label. ...light labelling also extended into the SGS, particularly into its ventral half	a
VISL	SCig	1	1	1	Harv90	a	pg287, fig5H	W	1	VISal	(WGA-HRP) injection placed more rostrally in area 18a, probably in the AL region	SCig	anterograde label in the SC Although the density of terminals is not very high, label was clearly distributed in a lattice like arrangement with a prominent dorsal tier at the SGI/SO border and puffs joining to lighter tier at SGI/SAI.	a
VISL	SCs	1	1	2	Harv90	a	pg287, fig4	W	1	VISlm	The (WGA-HRP) injection site was close to the lateral border of area 17 and was probably in area LM	SCop	Only light terminal labelling was seen in the SC ipsilateral to the injection site. Sparse label was scarred through the SO, but there seemed to be patches of more dense label	a
					Harv90	a	pg287, fig4,5	W	1	VISFL	The (WGA-HRP) injection was placed slightly more laterally in 18a, probably in area LI, or LL	SCs	In medial SC scattered terminals were found in SGI and SO. The label was not uniform within the SGI since there were areas devoid of corticotectal label. ...light labelling also extended into the SGS, particularly into its ventral half	a
			c	2	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCsg	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCop	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	SCop	1	1	1	Harv90	a	pg287, fig4	W	1	VISlm	The (WGA-HRP) injection site was close to the lateral border of area 17 and was probably in area LM	SCop	Only light terminal labelling was seen in the SC ipsilateral to the injection site. Sparse label was scarred through the SO, but there seemed to be patches of more dense label	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCop	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	SCsg	c	c	1	Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	SCsg	p305: inj confined to 18a labeled ... all targets of area 17 except SCzo. <i.e.PG, APN, NOT, OP, PPT, SCop, SCsg, LGvl, RT, slightly spurious>. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	VISM	3	3	4	Sa91	f4A	pg326, fig4A	W	3	VISL-r	rostral 18b receives its major associational input from area 18a	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18b	r
					Sa91	f4B	pg326,329, fig4B	W	3	VISL-c	caudal 18b receives major assoc input from caudal 18a	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into caudal 18b	r
					Coog&Burk 93	f5	pg3755-9, fig5	P	3	VISlm	PHA-L inj fell into the posterior part of the callosal free oval in the lateral extrastriate cortex that contains LM	VISM	Without exception , injections resulted in labelling of dense projections to ... MX ... in medial extrastriate cortex, main projection column was surrounded by sparser and more diffuse projections, indicating that MX contains multiple projection sites	a
					Sa91	f4A	pg326, fig4A	W	3	VISL-c	rostral 18b receives its major associational input from area 18a	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18b	r
			2	6	To84	EM2	pg544,546, fig2	H	2	VISL	HRP labelled fields: ... several moderate to weakly labeled fields along an anteroposterior axis in area 18a	VISam	HRP injection into area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r
					Mi84	f8	pg190, fig6,8	A	2	VISL	a small injection into area 18a. Conservative interpretation of this injection site includes some of the adjacent area 41, since no label is in the medial geniculate nucleus, the limits of the active injection site can be considered to be confined to 18a	VISM	silver grains are seen over ... patches in anterior 18b	a
					Mi84	f10	pg190, fig10	W	2	VISL	HRP positive neurons are in {2,3,5} ... of the central strip of area 18a	VISM	A small injection of WGA-HRP into area 18b.	r
					Sa91	f3c	fig3,%	W	2	VISL-c	%39% labelling in ISO(ips), major associational input	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18b	r
					Sa91	f3c	fig3,%	W	2	VISL-r	%32-54% labelling in ISO(ips), major associational input, 54% in {1,2,3}	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18b	r
					Sa91	f3d	fig3,%	W	2	VISL-c	%47-65% labelling in ISO(ips), 67% cells in {1,2,3}	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into caudal 18b	r
			1	1	Coog&Burk 93	f10	pg3763, fig10H2,L2	P	1	VISFL	In a single case, PHA-L injection made 7mm lateral to lamda point. Transcallosal labeling incomplete, PHA-L labeled projts to ctx medial to inj site & immediately lateral to area 17 strongly indicate that this represents an FLX inj.	VISM	Compared to rest of projections, inputs to MX were extremely weak & mainly confined to layer 2/3	a
			c	3	Coog&Burk 93	f8	pg3759-61, fig8L9	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injections ... were recovered in the anterior portion of the callosal free oval in lateral extrastriate cortex. In the case shown in fig 8 , injection centred in anterior AL where the upper visual field is represented	VISM	In addition AL was also connected to ... MX, columnar pattern of termination {1,2,3,4,5,6}	a
					Coog&Burk 93	b	pg3759, fig8L3,L4	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L inj into ant VISal (upper vis fd)	VISam	AL was also connected to PX, FLX, MX, AX, RL, anterior & posterior sites in PR, second somatosensory cortex, RS & PS. Layers 1-6, columnar pattern.	a
					Coog90	18a	pg50, fig 1	P	-1	VISL	3 cases of PHA-L injections into area 18a ...	VISM	...each revealed 1-2 projections to cytoarchitectonic area 18b, similar to 17-18a pattern. Column of labeled fibres with main terminations in layers 2/3-5, but substantial input also to deep layer 1	a
VISL	VISp	3	3	4	Sa91	V1	pg326	W	3	VISL-r	V1 receives major associational input from LM (caudal 18a),d:{5,6}, m:{2,3}	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into V1	r
					Sa91	f3e	fig3,%	W	3	VISL-c	%83-87% labelling in ISO(ips), major associational input; 65% of neurons in {5,6}, remainder in {2,3}	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into V1	r
					Coog&Burk 93	f5	pg3755-9, fig5	P	3	VISlm	PHA-L inj fell into the posterior part of the callosal free oval in the lateral extrastriate cortex that contains LM	VISp	Without exception , injections resulted in labelling of dense projections to striate cortex	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Mi84	f2	pg186, fig2	W	3	VISL	most afferent projections arose from parts of primary and secondary visual cortices. In area 18a, HRP positive neurons are distributed throughout the central strip spanning the anteroposterior extent of area 18a... labeled neurons concentrated in patches	VISp	Two WGA-HRP injections placed in area 17.	r
2	1				Coog&Burk 93	f10	pg3763, fig10H4,L2-L4	P	2	VISFL	In a single case, PHA-L injection made 7mm lateral to lamda point. Transcallosal labeling incomplete, PHA-L labeled proj to ctx medial to inj site & immediately lateral to area 17 strongly indicate that this represents an FLX inj.	VISp	not surprising to see reciprocal connection from FLX to area 17. laminar pattern stratified, terminating principally in layers 1, 2/3 & 5; did not involve layer 4	a
1	1				Mi84	f8	pg190, fig6,8	A	1	VISL	a small injection into area 18a. Conservative interpretation of this injection site includes some of the adjacent area 41, since no label is in the medial geniculate nucleus, the limits of the active injection site can be considered to be confined to 18a	VISp	silver grains are seen over lateral area 17	a
c	44				Mo93 Coog&Burk 93	R59b f8	pg2,3, fig2A(blue) pg3759-61, fig8L9	F P	-1 -1	VISpos VISal	boundary between areas PL & P is filled with FB proj PHA-L injections ... were recovered in the anterior portion of the callosal free oval in lateral extrastriate cortex. In the case shown in fig 8 , injection centred in anterior AL where the upper visual field is represented	VISp VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant It resulted in multiple projections to topographically corresponding points in posterior striate cortex, projection spared layer 4 {1,2,3,5,6}	r a
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISpl	RB projections to area PL distributed medially to R21y	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISpl	similar distribution to AL, LM, LI, LL, PL to R38y	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R59y	pg2,3, fig2A(yellow)	F	-1	VISpl	FG projection occupies an interediate position <btwn R59r/R59b >	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R38b	pg5, fig3A(blue)	F	-1	VISli	in LI, lower visual field (RD) is rostralateral	VISp	FB injection more rostral (lower in visual field)	r
					Mo93	R76b	pg5, fig2B(blue)	F	-1	VISli	lower visual field FB projection is lateral, more rostral and medial than case R59b	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant, more rostrally placed injection than R59b	r
					Mo93	R76b	pg5, fig2B(blue)	F	-1	VISpl	upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated rostrocaudally	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant, more rostrally placed injection than R59b	r
					Mo93	R76y	pg5, fig2B(yellow)	F	-1	VISpl	upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated rostrocaudally	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg5, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISli	in LI, upper visual field (RD) is caudal	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Coog&Burk 93	b	pg3759, fig8H9	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injns aimed 2.5 mm anterior to lamdha-point & 6mm lateral to midline recovered in anterior portion of callosal-free oval in lateral extrastriate cortex. In case in fig8 inj centred in anterior AL (upper visual field)	VISp VISp	multiple projections to topographically corresponding points in posterior striate cortex (fig8H9) & to LM in posterolateral extrastriate cortex. Layer 4 input missing in area 17 proj	a
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISli	similar distribution to AL, LM, LI, LL, PL to R38y	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R59y	pg2,3, fig2A(yellow)	F	-1	VISpos	more caudally <than FB injection> in area P is the relatively higher visual field FG proj	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R76b	pg5, fig2B(blue)	F	-1	VISpos	upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated caudorostrally, nasotemporal axis given by FB/RD axis orientated mediolaterally	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant, more rostrally placed injection than R59b	r
					Mo93	R76y	pg5, fig2B(yellow)	F	-1	VISpos	upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated caudorostrally	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R59b	pg2,3, fig2A(blue)	F	-1	VISlm	FB lies rostrally and medially, at the boundary with AL	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R59y	pg2,3, fig2A(yellow)	F	-1	VISli	FG projection occupies an interediate position <btwn R59r/R59b >	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg5, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISlm	in LM, upper visual field (FG) is caudal	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISli	similar distribution to AL, LM, LI, LL, PL to R38y	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg5, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISli	upper-lower (FB-FG) axis orientated caudorostrally	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38b	pg5, fig3A(blue)	F	-1	VISli	low visual field projection merges with proj to LM and LL	VISp	FB injection more rostral (lower in visual field)	r
					Mo93	R59y	pg2,3, fig2A(yellow)	F	-1	VISlm	FG projection occupies an interediate position <btwn R59r/R59b >	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R76b	pg5, fig2B(blue)	F	-1	VISlm	high to low visual field axis is caudorostral, (FB rostral, boundary region with AL	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant, more rostrally placed injection than R59b	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Mo93	R76y	pg5, fig2B(yellow)	F	-1	VISlm	high to low visual field axis is caudorostral, (FG caudal)	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R59b	pg2,3, fig2A(blue)	F	-1	VISpl	the lower-nasal FB projection is caudal and medial, boundary between areas PL & P is filled with FB proj	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R76y	pg5, fig2B(yellow)	F	-1	VISll	upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated rostrocaudally	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R59b	pg2,3, fig2A(blue)	F	-1	VISal	connections from the FB project medially	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R76b	pg5, fig2B(blue)	F	-1	VISll	Nasotemporal axis given by RD-FB is orientated mediolaterally. upper-lower axis given by FB/FG axis orientated rostrocaudally	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant, more rostrally placed injection than R59b	r
					Mo93	R59y	pg2,3, fig2A(yellow)	F	-1	VISll	in LL, FG projection is caudolateral	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISlm	RB projections to area LM distributed medially to R21y	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R59b	pg2,3, fig2A(blue)	F	-1	VISll	in LL, FG <typo! FB> projection is rostro-medial	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISli/VISll/VISpl	RB projection at confluence of LI, LL, PL	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISlm	similar distribution to AL, LM, LI, LL, PL to R38y	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38b	pg5, fig3A(blue)	F	-1	VISlm	in LM, lower visual field (FB) is rostral	VISp	FB injection more rostral (lower in visual field)	r
					Coog90	18a	pg50, fig 1	P	-1	VISL	each of 3 area 18a (PHA-L) injections ...	VISp	... laminar pattern in area 17 independent of rostrocaudal position of inj site. Projection from 18a to 17 stratified with strong input to layer 1 & weaker inputs to layers 2/3 & 5 while input to layer 4 & lower 2/3 extremely sparse.	a
					Mo93	R38y	pg5, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISrl	lower visual field(FG) is caudal	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38b	pg5, fig3A(blue)	F	-1	VISrl	upper visual field(FG) is rostral	VISp	FB injection more rostral (lower in visual field)	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISal	similar distribution to AL, LM, LI, LL, PL to R38y	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISal	RB projections to area AL distributed rostro-medially to R21y	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISpos	RB projection to area P caudally	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R59b	pg2,3, fig2A(blue)	F	-1	VISli	FB projection lateral	VISp	FB injection was placed in lower nasal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg5, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISal	in AL upper visual field (FG) lies between R38b and R38r	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R38b	pg5, fig3A(blue)	F	-1	VISal	in AL nasal FB is medial	VISp	FB injection more rostral (lower in visual field)	r
					Mo93	R76y	pg5, fig2B(yellow)	F	-1	VISal	FG is intermediate <inbetween RD and FB>	VISp	FG injection was placed more caudally <Than R59b> at about the horizontal meridian	r
VISL	ATN	1	1	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	VISL	A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	VISL	A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex. <From diagram in fig3>	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	3	Tak85	18a	pg299, fig9	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LD	terminal field of area 18a injns in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis is organized wrt to the med.lat axis of area 18a. all injns produced label that extended from posterior to anterior pole of ldlv.all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	LD	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ...the ventrolateral subdivision of the laterodorsal nucleus	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	LD	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ...the ventrolateral subdivision of the laterodorsal nucleus	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISL	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISL	LD	1	1	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	VISL	A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	VISL	A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex. <From diagram in fig3>	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	3	Tak85	18a	pg299, fig9	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LD	terminal field of area 18a injs in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis is organized wrt to the med.lat axis of area 18a. all injs produced label that extended from posterior to anterior pole of ldlv.all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	LD	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ...the ventrolateral subdivision of the laterodorsal nucleus	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	LD	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ...the ventrolateral subdivision of the laterodorsal nucleus	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISL	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISL	LGd	3	3	1	Turl93	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	VISL	principal afferents to DLG originate in (i) small pyramidal cells of {6} of ipsilateral primary visual cortex (area 17) and parts of ipsilateral cytoarchitectonic areas 18a and 18b (Fig1A).	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			1	2	Ser81	b	pg5-6	H	1	VISL	a few cells were usually found in {6} of ipsilateral area 18a	LGd	2 HRP injections were confined to LGNd without any involvement of LGNv	r
					Mas81	a	pg108, fig1	F	1	VISL	a large population of retrogradely labelled small diameter pyramidal cells located in {6} of 17 and fewer large pyramidal cells in {5} of 17 and 18a	LGd/LGd/LP	a microiontophoretic EB injection in LGNd which encroaches into the lateral-ventral aspect of the LTP	r
			c	3	Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	LGd	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN) <LGv described separately so LGN must be LGd>	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	LGd	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN) <LGv described separately so LGN must be LGd>	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LGd	an injection confined to area 18a labeled ... lgd. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
VISL	LP	3	3	1	Harv90	c	pg286-7, fig4	W	3	VISL	WGA-HRP inj	LPI	dense retrograde and anterograde label was seen in the LPL	a
			2	2	Harv90	d	pg287, fig4	W	2	VISFL	The (WGA-HRP) injection was placed slightly more laterally in 18a, probably in area LI, or LL	LPI	label in LPL was seen	a
					Solo&Nomo 84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	2	VISL	Largest descending inputs to the ventrocaudal part of the the nucleus arose from the dentate fascia of the hippocampus & {5} of area 18A	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	1	Solo&Nomo 84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	1	VISL	... whereas from structures in neocortex there were only very weak projections (1 or 2 cells /section), in areas 18a and 36, in the caudal regions of {6}	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r
			c	6	Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	LP	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ...different subdivisions of the lateral posterior nucleus (LPMR, LPLR, LPLC)	a
					Tak85	18a	pg299, fig9	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LPm	the label produced in lprm by area 17 and area 18a injections were identical: labelfields were roughly columnar and emanated anteriorly and slightly medially from the lateral surface of lprm, topography unclear. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Tak85	18a	pg297, fig9	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LPi	the labeling pattern observed in lpl of rats receiving injections involving area 18a: two separate fields, the posterior field extends from caudal pole of lplc to overlap area, while anterior field extends out from overlap area into lpr. Ipsi	a
					Tak85	18a	pg297, fig9	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LPi	the labeling pattern observed in lpl of rats receiving injections involving area 18a: two separate fields, the posterior field extends from caudal pole of lplc to overlap area, while anterior field extends out from overlap area into lpr. Ipsi	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	LP	9 targets were shared <by AL and LM>. These included ...different subdivisions of the lateral posterior nucleus (LPMR, LPLR, LPLC). Inputs to the mediocaudal subdivision of the lateral posterior nucleus came from LM only.	a
					John&Burk 92		pg28, fig9	D	-1	VISL	In six cases larger injections of D-Asp were made into middle layers of area 17 or into area 18a and the survival time increased to allow for labelling of longer pathways. Following injection of D-Asp into the extrastriate visual area 18a (n=2)	LP	labeled neurons (In LP) were lying in a field of increased grain density, indicating labeling of cortico-thalamic projections	a
VISL	PO		1	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	VISL	a very tiny projection could be demonstrated from area 18 (3-4cells per animal in {2,3} and from area 18a (1-2 cells {5}))	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
VISL	LGv		c	2	Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	LGv	Targets that were labelled after AL injections and were not labelled after LM injections included ... the ventral geniculate nucleus (VLG)	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	LGvl	an injection confined to area 18a labeled ... lgv pars externa. all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
			0	1	Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	0	VISL	a projection of the parastriate visual cortex (area18a) to the vLGN could not be observed	LGv	After injecting HRP into the vLGN	r
VISL	RT		2	1	Sef81	d	pg6-8	H	2	VISL	pyramidal or pyramidal-type cells in {6} of ipsilateral cortical areas 17, 18& 18a contained HRP reaction product.	RT	Small (HRP) injections were made into visually responsive RNT.	r
			c	3	Coog&Burk 93	f9a	pg3763, fig9a	P	-1	VISlm	PHA-L injection into LM, injection site was identified in posteromedial part of acallosal oval	RT	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... the reticular thalamic nucleus	a
					Tak85	18a	pg305	A	-1	VISL	as shown in fig4B, 1 injection ([3H]leucine) was confined to area 18a	RT	an injection confined to area 18a labeled ... trn. (pg283: thalamic reticular nucleus). all structs labeled by 18a inj ipsi.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	RT	Connections were found from both areas <LM and AL> to a total of 14 targets of the thalamus. Of these 9 targets were shared. These included ... the reticular thalamic nucleus	a
VISL	ZI		c	1	Coog&Burk 93	f9b	pg3763, fig9b	P	-1	VISal	PHA-L injection into AL, injection site was identified in anterior part of acallosal oval	ZI	Targets that were labelled after AL injections and were not labelled after LM injections included the zona incerta (ZI)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
VISM	PG	2	2	2	Wies82a	f6	pg221, fig6	H	2	VISM	Numerous labeled cells, most of them arranged in clusters of 0.5-1mm diameter. They were found in visual cortex (occipital areas Oc1, Oc2)... In decreasing order, density of labeled corticopontine cells was 1) Sml, 2) Motor Ctx, 3) SMII, 4) Visual areas ...	PG	case 79-196, 81-2: areas of HRP uptake relatively large in these cases & enzyme spread over ventral & lateral surface of nucleus. Fig6 illustrates case 79-196	r
					Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	PG	Labeled fibres ... appeared to end in the anterior pons within the laterodorsal portion of the pontine nuclear complex	a
			c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	PG	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the lateral pontine grey	a
VISM	PRT	3	3	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISM	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cells were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			2	2	Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	NOT	projections ended in the ... lateral and medial nuclei of the optic tract	a
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	PRT	fibres swept dorsally from the area of the reticular nucleus and from the medial lamina of the zona incerta across the ventral nucleus to end in the lateral posterior, posterior and pretectal nuclei	a
			1	1	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	VISM	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	Following a tracer deposit in area 18, there was sparse anterograde label across the whole rostro-caudal extent of APc	a
			c	3	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	APN	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... npa pars compacta, (pg283: anterior pretectal nucleus)	a
					Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	OP	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... nop, (pg283: olivary pretectal nucleus)	a
					Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	PPT/PPT/???	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... npp, (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
VISM	APN	3	3	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISM	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cells were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			1	1	Caduss91	control	pg93	W	1	VISM	WGA-HRP injections were performed in the visual cortex in 5 animals.	APN	Following a tracer deposit in area 18, there was sparse anterograde label across the whole rostro-caudal extent of APc	a
			c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	APN	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... npa pars compacta, (pg283: anterior pretectal nucleus)	a
VISM	NOT	2	2	1	Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	NOT	projections ended in the ... lateral and medial nuclei of the optic tract	a
VISM	OP	c	c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	OP	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... nop, (pg283: olivary pretectal nucleus)	a
VISM	PPT	c	c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	PPT/PPT/???	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... npp, (pg283: no mention in abbreviations)	a
VISM	SC	3	3	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	3	VISM	In all three cases the visual cortical areas were labelled, but to varying degrees: area 17 most densely, area 18a less so and area 18 least of all	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGL, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
					Olav82	f2	pg335, fig2	H	3	VISam	clusters of labeled pyramidal cells are observed in {5} of ... several regions of the cortex adjoining the lateral and anteromedial borders of V1. one or two fields located anteromedial to V1	SC	The SC of nine adult gray rats was injected stereotaxically with 0.01-0.02µl of 30% HRP in saline	r
			2	5	Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	SCd	Only laminae III, IV, V, VI and VIII of the superior colliculus were labelled and a part of the label here was continuous with that in a small laterodorsal portion of the central grey	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Harv90	a	pg283, fig4,5	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	SCd	In general (SC) labelling was lighter than that seen after area 17 injections and was less focal in its distribution. Two horizontal tiers of label ..., one in the middle of the SGI and a second at the border btwn SAI and SGP... bridges btwn tiers.	a
					Harv90	a	pg283, fig4,5	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	SCi	In general (SC) labelling was lighter than that seen after area 17 injections and was less focal in its distribution. Two horizontal tiers of label ..., one in the middle of the SGI and a second at the border btwn SAI and SGP... bridges btwn tiers.	a
					Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	SCi	Only laminae III, IV, V, VI and VIII of the superior colliculus were labelled and a part of the label here was continuous with that in a small laterodorsal portion of the central grey	a
					Sef81	a	pg5, fig1G	H	2	VISM	There were smaller numbers (than in area17) in area 18 and fewer still in area 18a. In all 4 cases labelled cells in areas 17, 18 and 18a were confined to {5}	SC	injection of HRP into SC	r
			c	2	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	SCd	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... intermediate and deep layers of the superior colliculus	a
					Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	SCi	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... intermediate and deep layers of the superior colliculus	a
VISM	SCi	2	2	2	Harv90	a	pg283, fig4,5	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	SCi	In general (SC) labelling was lighter than that seen after area 17 injections and was less focal in its distribution. Two horizontal tiers of label ..., one in the middle of the SGI and a second at the border btwn SAI and SGP... bridges btwn tiers.	a
					Benz83	a	pg5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	SCi	Only laminae III, IV, V, VI and VIII of the superior colliculus were labelled and a part of the label here was continuous with that in a small laterodorsal portion of the central grey	a
			c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	SCi	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... intermediate and deep layers of the superior colliculus	a
VISM	VISL	3	3	1	Mi84	f12	pg196, fig12	A	3	VISM/VISM/VISp/RS Pd	an injection of [3H] amino acids into area 18b, the injection site extends into medial area 17 and to a lesser degree into area 29d... involvements of 17 and 29d seem to be minor	VISL	silver grains are present over {1,2,3,5} of ... the central strip of area 18a	a
			2	2	Mi84 Co90	f7 C	pg189, fig7 C	W	2	VISM VISam/VISpm	in area 18b, HRP-positive neurons are located mainly in {2,3,5} PHA-L	VISL VISL	An injection of WGA-HRP in area 18a {1,2/3,4,5}	r
			1	5	Sa91 Coog&Burk 93	f3b f11	fig3,% pg3763, fig11	W P	1 1	VISam VISpm	%6% labelling in ISO(ips), rostral VISM; presumed area AM In a single case in which PHA-L was injected 1.5mm lateral to the lamda point, the injection site was recovered at the medial border of area 17, <injection into VISpm>	VISL-r VISal	4 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into rostral area 18a Inputs to LM, AL, and PX were remarkably sparse and convincing terminal branching was seen only in LM	r a
					Coog&Burk 93	f11	pg3763, fig11	P	1	VISpm	In a single case in which PHA-L was injected 1.5mm lateral to the lamda point, the injection site was recovered at the medial border of area 17, <injection into VISpm>	VISPX	Inputs to LM, AL, and PX were remarkably sparse and convincing terminal branching was seen only in LM	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f11	pg3763, fig11	P	1	VISpm	In a single case in which PHA-L was injected 1.5mm lateral to the lamda point, the injection site was recovered at the medial border of area 17, <injection into VISpm>	VISlm	Inputs to LM, AL, and PX were remarkably sparse and convincing terminal branching was seen only in LM	a
					Sa91	f3b	fig3,%	W	1	VISpm	caudal VISM, %7% labelling in ISO(ips)	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into rostral area 18a	r
			c	5	Coog90	18b	pg50, fig 1	P	-1	VISM	return projection (from area 18b to 18a) studied in 3 animals (using PHA-L)	VISL	In area 18a, projectin from area 18b stratified and terminated in layers 1,5,6 & avoided middle layers	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f12	pg3765, fig12L9	P	-1	VISam	In a single case the PHA-L injection was recovered rostromedially to area 17 within MX, at a site that presumably corresponds to area AM mapped by Epsinoza and Thomas (1983)	VISlm	Inputs to lateral cortex appeared more robust than after posterior MX injections and distinct projections were identified to LM	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Coog&Burk 93	f12	pg3765, fig12L9	P	-1	VISam	In a single case the PHA-L injection was recovered rostromedially to area 17 within MX, at a site that presumably corresponds to area AM mapped by Epsinoza and Thomas (1983)	VISal	Inputs to lateral cortex appeared more robust than after posterior MX injections and distinct projections were identified to ... AL	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f12	pg3765, fig12L9	P	-1	VISam	In a single case the PHA-L injection was recovered rostromedially to area 17 within MX, at a site that presumably corresponds to area AM mapped by Epsinoza and Thomas (1983)	VISFL	Inputs to lateral cortex appeared more robust than after posterior MX injections and distinct projections were identified to ... multiple sites within FLX	a
					To84	EM10/5	pg544, fig1AB	L	-1	VISam	small lesion in area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections. Conical lesion, no damage to white matter	VISL	terminal labelling (darkly stained granules) densest in (2,3) less in (1). AM projects to ... five fields arranged anterioposteriorly in area 18a, (fields 6,5,3,2,1)	a
			0	2	Sa91	f3a	fig3	W	0	VISpm	connx not mentioned	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into caudal 18a	r
					Sa91	f3a	fig3	W	0	VISam	connx not mentioned	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into caudal 18a	r
			x	1	John&Burk 94		abstract		-1	VISM	MX	VISlm	D-[3H]-aspartate	r
VISM	VISp	3	3	2	Coog&Burk 93	f11	pg3763, fig11	P	3	VISpm	In a single case in which PHA-L was injected 1.5mm lateral to the lamda point, the injection site was recovered at the medial border of area 17, <injection into VISpm>	VISp	Labelling in striate cortex was seen in a swath of terminations that extended from AM to PL, corresponding to a large segment of the upper nasal and upper temporal visual field representation	a
					Mi84	f2	pg186, fig2	W	3	VISM	most afferent projections arose from parts of primary and secondary visual cortices, afferents from 18b predominantly involve medial area 17. Both injections into 17 label neurons in {2,3,5} in a8b	VISp	Two WGA-HRP injections placed in area 17.	r
			2	4	Sa91	V1	pg326,329	W	2	VISpm	one of two clusters of labelling in VISM (AM & PM)	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into V1	r
					Sa91	V1	pg326	W	2	VISam	one of two clusters of labelling in VISM (AM & PM)	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into V1	r
					Mi84	f12	pg196, fig12	A	2	VISM/VIS M/VISp/RS Pd	an injection of [3H] amino acids into area 18b, the injection site extends into medial area 17 and to a lesser degree into area 29d... involvements of 17 and 29d seem to be minor	VISp	silver grains are present over {1,2,3,5} of medial area 17	a
					Mo93	R38b	R38, fig 3A, blue	F	2	VISpm/VIS am/VISa	continuous blob rostralateral VISpm / caudolateral VISam / caudal VISa	VISp	FB at ver=-50, hor=-40	r
			1	1	Sa91	f3e	fig3,%	W	1	VISpm	%8-10% labelling in ISO(ips), majority of cells in {1,2,3}	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into V1	r
			c	8	Coog90	18b	pg50, fig 1	P	-1	VISM	studied in 3 animals, <but not mentioned in text, fig1F>	VISp	Projection from 18b to area 17, showing feedback pattern	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f12	pg3765, fig12L9	P	-1	VISam	In a single case the PHA-L injection was recovered rostromedially to area 17 within MX, at a site that presumably corresponds to area AM mapped by Epsinoza and Thomas (1983)	VISp	projection to area 17 were spread over a wide region that extended from the posterior edge to the anterior tip of striate cortex. ... the projections were non uniform along the rostrocaudal axis, indicating that the input to striate ctx was clustered	a
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISam	upper nasal RB projection caudal parts of AM	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg7, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISam	distributed in wide apart regions of areas A, AM and PM	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISpm	distributed in wide apart regions of areas A, AM and PM	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21r	pg7, fig3B(red)	F	-1	VISpm	upper nasal RB projection caudomedial parts of PM	VISp	RB injection in upper nasal quadrant of V1	r
					Mo93	R38y	pg7, fig3A(yellow)	F	-1	VISpm	distributed in wide apart regions of areas A, AM and PM	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
					Mo93	R21y	pg7, fig3B(yellow)	F	-1	VISam	distributed in wide apart regions of areas A, AM and PM	VISp	FG injection was in upper temporal quadrant	r
			0	1	Sa91	f3e	fig3,%	W	0	VISam	%0.5% labelling in ISO(ips)	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injs into V1	r
			x	1	John&Burk 94		abstract		-1	VISM	MX	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate	r
VISM	ATN	2	2	3	Harv90	e	pg283, fig4	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	LD	Retrograde and anterograde label was seen in LDVL	a
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	AM	... two tracts terminated in a roughly circular area that included the anteromedial nucleus, very light labelling in contralateral AM	a
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LD	The dorsal pathway entering the reticular nucleus was very heavy, but thinned out as entered the lateral and lateral posterior nucleus where most of the fibres terminated, <lateral nucleus=LD, see fig2B>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	VISM	A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	VISM	A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	1	Tak85	18	pg299, fig7	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	LD	terminal field (in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis) for area 18 injs produced was a thick band of silver grains spanning the entire med.lat and ant.pos dimensions of ldvl at a particular horizontal level, only ant.pos axis of 18 repr in ldvl	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISM	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISM	LD	2	2	2	Harv90	e	pg283, fig4	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	LD	Retrograde and anterograde label was seen in LDVL	a
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LD	The dorsal pathway entering the reticular nucleus was very heavy, but thinned out as entered the lateral and lateral posterior nucleus where most of the fibres terminated, <lateral nucleus=LD, see fig2B>	a
			1	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	VISM	A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	VISM	A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	1	Tak85	18	pg299, fig7	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	LD	terminal field (in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis) for area 18 injs produced was a thick band of silver grains spanning the entire med.lat and ant.pos dimensions of ldvl at a particular horizontal level, only ant.pos axis of 18 repr in ldvl	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISM	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISM	LGd	3	3	1	Tur193	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	VISM	principal afferents to DLG originate in (i) small pyramidal cells of {6} of ipsilateral primary visual cortex (area 17) and parts of ipsilateral cytoarchitectonic areas 18a and 18b (Fig1A).	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			1	1	Sef81	b	pg5-6	H	1	VISM	a few cells were usually found in {6} of ipsilateral area 18	LGd	2 HRP injections were confined to LGNd without any involvement of LGNv	r
			c	1	Dori92		pg194, fig1	W	-1	VISM	analysis restricted to {6} since ... afferents to vLGN arise from layer V [Sefton et al '81, BR215:1] WGA-HRP granules were localized in neurons throughout {6} of ipsilateral areas 17 and 18. 60% of labelled cells Glu-immunoreactive, 62% contained Asp.	LGd	WGA-HRP injections into the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, either resulted in restricted labelling within the boundaries of the nucleus <LGd> or in labelling of the dLGN and the ventral geniculate nucleus as well	r
			0	1	Benz83	a	pg3-5, fig2	A	0	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LGd	there were no fibres or terminations within the dorsal and ventral geniculate nucleus (except with brain 18TL5 where inj site encroached into area 17)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
VISM	CL	c	c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	CL	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... centrolateral nucleus	a
VISM	LP	2	2	3	Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LP	The dorsal pathway entering the reticular nucleus was very heavy, but thinned out as entered the lateral and lateral posterior nucleus where most of the fibres terminated	a
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LP	fibres swept dorsally from the area of the reticular nucleus and from the medial lamina of the zona incerta across the ventral nucleus to end in the lateral posterior, posterior and pretectal nuclei. Posterior projections ended in posterior LP	a
					Harv90	f	pg283, fig4	W	2	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	LPrm	an anterograde projection to LPRM was also present	r
					Solo&Nomo84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	1	VISM	Less marked projections <than inputs from DN and VISL>, in addition to areas 18 and 17, were observed from areas 19c, 20 and 7	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
					Solo&Nomo84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	1	VISM	... whereas from structures in neocortex there were only very weak projections (1 or 2 cells /section), in area 18 tagged neurons were found in {5}	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r
VISM	PO	2	2	1	Tak85	18	pg297-9, fig7	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	LPrm	injections of area 18 generally produced a blanket of silver grains (in lprm) a characterized by regions of high grain density and spots of background level activity. No topographic organization	a
					Tak85	18	pg295-7, fig7	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	LPir	the rostral portion of lpl plus the rostral 20% of lplc contains a terminal field arising from ... area 18, diffusely dispersed throughout the nucleus, but was heaviest at rostral levels	a
VISM	PO	2	1	1	Benz83	a	pg3,5-6, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	PO	fibres swept dorsally from the area of the reticular nucleus and from the medial lamina of the zona incerta across the ventral nucleus to end in the lateral posterior, posterior and pretectal nuclei. Posterior projections ended in posterior PO	a
					Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	1	VISM	a very tiny projection could be demonstrated from area 18 (3-4cells per animal in {2,3} and from area 18a (1-2 cells {5}))	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
VISM	MD	2	2	1	Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	MDI	... a few fibres continued to the lateral division of the medial thalamic nucleus <MD from fig2B>	a
VISM	LGv	1	1	1	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368	H	1	VISM	Visual Cortex: labeled neurons are present in visual cortex in {5}. Most of the labeled cells are in area 17 with some in area18	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
					Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	LGv	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... lgv pars interna	a
					Benz83	a	pg3-5, fig2	A	0	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	LGv	there were no fibres or terminations within the dorsal and ventral geniculate nucleus (except with brain 18TLS where inj site encroached into area 17)	a
VISM	RT	2	2	1	Sef81	d	pg6-8	H	2	VISM	pyramidal or pyramidal-type cells in {6} of ipsilateral cortical areas 17, 18& 18a contained HRP reaction product.	RT	Small (HRP) injections were made into visually responsive RNT.	r
					Benz83	a	pg3, fig2	A	1	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	RT	Anterior Projections: fibres ... entered the dorsal aspect of the reticular nucleus where some of them seemed to terminate in a diffuse pattern.	a
VISM	ZI	2	2	1	Benz83	a	pg3,5, fig2	A	2	VISM	Injection sites (of [3H]leucine) in four brains labelled in area 18 are shown in fig.1	ZI	labelled fibres which had appeared to come partly from the reticular nucleus and partly from the cerebral crus formed two lamina in the zona incerta, one on its medial and one on its lateral border. There were undoubtedly some terminations in these layers	a

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			c	1	Tak85	18	pg305	A	-1	VISM	as shown in fig4B, 4 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 18	ZI	Injections confined to area 18 labeled the ... zona incerta	a
VISp	PG	2	2	1	Wies82a	f6	pg221, fig6	H	2	VISp	Numerous labeled cells, most of them arranged in clusters of 0.5-1mm diameter. They were found in visual cortex (occipital areas Oc1, Oc2)... In decreasing order, density of labeled corticopontine cells was 1) SmL, 2) Motor Ctx, 3) SMIL, 4) Visual areas ...	PG	case 79-196, 81-2: areas of HRP uptake relatively large in these cases & enzyme spread over ventral & lateral surface of nucleus. Fig6 illustrates case 79-196	r
			1	1	Benz83	b	pg6	A	1	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	PG	Only the most heavily labelled brain showed a small projection through the cerebral crus to the lateral part of the pontine nuclear complex ... similar to that from area 18	a
			c	2	Dori92		pg195, fig3	W	-1	VISp	The WGA-HRP was retrogradely transported into cell bodies in area 17 ipsilateral to the injection. cells filled with WGA-HRP were located in [5] almost exclusively in its deeper portion. dble labelled cells proportions: WGA-HRP/Glu=42%, WGA-HRP/Asp=51%	PG/PG/TRN	WGA-HRP injections into the pons (P) resulted in complete and intense labelling throughout the rostrocaudal extent of the pontine nuclei, with minor diffusion into the reticular formation or into the contralateral side	r
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	PG	injections confined to area 17 labeled the lateral pontine gray, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	AOS	2	2	1	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	DT	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... pretectum, distributed throughout the NOT-DTN	a
VISp	DT	2	2	1	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	DT	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... pretectum, distributed throughout the NOT-DTN	a
VISp	PRT	3	3	2	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	3	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	APN	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in the pretectum, strongest label in pretectum appeared ven and lat to the NOT where a dense fibre plexus and numerous terminal boutons were found. This area corresponds to the anterior pretectal nucleus	a
					Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISp	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cels were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			2	2	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	NOT	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... pretectum, distributed throughout the NOT-DTN	a
					Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	PRT	the lateral posterior nucleus was filled with silver grains, as was the pretectal nucelus	a
			1	1	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	1	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	OP	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in the pretectum, a few labeled terminals were also found in the olivary pretectal nucleus, their number considerably smaller than those found in NOT-DTN	a
			c	4	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	PPT/PPT/?? ?	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... npp, (pg283: no mention in abbreviations), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	OP	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... nop, (pg283: olivary pretectal nucleus), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	NOT	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... a region of nto adjacent to its retinal terminal zone, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	APN	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... npa pars compacta, (pg283: anterior pretectal nucleus), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
VISp	APN	3	3	2	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	3	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	APN	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in the pretectum, strongest label in pretectum appeared ven and lat to the NOT where a dense fibre plexus and numerous terminal boutons were found. This area corresponds to the anterior pretectal nucleus	a
					Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	3	VISp	densest cortical labelling occurred in the visual cortex, where numerous positive cels were observed in each case. Numerous labelled cells were scattered all over areas 17 and 18 but the densest labelling was in area 18a.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP inj. In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			c	1	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	APN	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... npa pars compacta, (pg283: anterior pretectal nucleus), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	NOT	2	2	1	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	NOT	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... pretectum, distributed throughout the NOT-DTN	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	NOT	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... a region of nto adjacent to its retinal terminal zone, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	OP	1	1	1	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	1	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	OP	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in the pretectum, a few labeled terminals were also found in the olivary pretectal nucleus, their number considerably smaller than those found in NOT-DTN	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	OP	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... nop, (pg283: olivary pretectal nucleus), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	PPT	c	c	1	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	PPT/PPT?? ?	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... npp, (pg283: no mention in abbreviations), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	SC	3	3	2	Olav82	f2	pg335, fig2	H	3	VISp	clusters of labeled pyramidal cells are observed in {5} of striate cortex and several regions of the cortex adjoining the lateral and anteromedial borders of VI	SC	The SC of nine adult gray rats was injected stereotaxically with 0.01-0.02µl of 30% HRP in saline	r
					Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	3	VISp	In all three cases the visual cortical areas were labelled, but to varying degrees: area 17 most densely, area 18a less so and area 18 least of all	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO. HRP injections	r
					Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	SC	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... superior colliculus	a
					Sef81	a	pg5, fig1G	H	2	VISp	there were pyramidal cells in {5} of area 17	SC	injection of HRP into SC	r
					Harv90	a	pg283, fig3	W	2	VISp	ten area 17 (WGA-HRP) injections	SCs	label in the ipsilateral SC. focal patch in upper SO and lower half of SGS. Lighter labelup to the SZ. projection to superficial layers has high degree of visuotopic organization. The labelling density in the SC after A17 injections was greatest of VIS-SC	a
					Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	SCs	the labelled pathway to the superior colliculus ended in the lateral half of that structure where label appeared only in lamina I, II and III	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCzo	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCsg	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCop	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Dori92		pg195, fig2	W	-1	VISp	retrogradely labelled cells were located primarily in the upper half of {5} of area 17 as well as the borders of area 17 with area 18 and18a ipsilateral to the injected hemisphere. double labelled cells proportions: WGA-HRP/Glu=46%, WGA-HRP/Asp=66%	SCs	WGA-HRP injections in the superior colliculus resulted in intense labelling of its superficial layers	r

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VISp	SCs	2	2	2	Harv90	a	pg283, fig3	W	2	VISp	ten area 17 (WGA-HRP) injections	SCs	label in the ipsilateral SC. focal patch in upper SO and lower half of SGS. Lighter label up to the SZ. projection to superficial layers has high degree of visuotopic organization. The labelling density in the SC after A17 injections was greatest of VIS-SC	a
					Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	SCs	the labelled pathway to the superior colliculus ended in the lateral half of that structure where label appeared only in lamina I, II and III	a
		c	4	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCzo	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a	
				Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCsg	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a	
				Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCop	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a	
Dori92		pg195, fig2	W	-1	VISp	retrogradely labelled cells were located primarily in the upper half of {5} of area 17 as well as the borders of area 17 with area 18 and 18a ipsilateral to the injected hemisphere. double labelled cells proportions: WGA-HRP/Glu=46%, WGA-HRP/Asp=66%	SCs	WGA-HRP injections in the superior colliculus resulted in intense labelling of its superficial layers	r					
VISp	SCop	c	c	1	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCop	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	SCsg	c	c	1	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	SCsg	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... sz, sgs and so of the superior colliculus, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	VISL	3	3	8	Sa91	f3a	fig3,%	W	3	VISp	%63-67% labelling in ISO(ips), 65% of cells in {5,6}	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into caudal 18a	r
					Coog&Burk	f4	pg3755, fig4	P	3	VISp	Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.	VISPX	the most anterior projection in lateral cortex corresponds to RL, posterior to that is AL, followed by LM & PX. at core of proj, fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a
					Coog&Burk	f4	pg3755, fig4	P	3	VISp	Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.	VISFL	Proj to FLX is seen lateral to LM & AL. at core of proj, fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a
					Coog&Burk	f4	pg3755, fig4	P	3	VISp	Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.	VISal	the most anterior projection in lateral cortex corresponds to RL, posterior to that is AL, followed by LM & PX. at core of proj, fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a
					Coog&Burk	f4	pg3755, fig4	P	3	VISp	Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.	VISlm	the most anterior projection in lateral cortex corresponds to RL, posterior to that is AL, followed by LM & PX. at core of proj, fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a
					Sa91	f5B	pg326, fig5B	W	3	VISp	main associational input from 17, commissural input from lateral 17	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into caudal 18a	r
		Coog&Burk	f4	pg3755, fig4	P	3	VISp	Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.	VISrl	the most anterior projection in lateral cortex corresponds to RL, posterior to that is AL, followed by LM & PX. at core of proj, fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a			
Mi84	f4	pg188, fig4	A	3	VISp	Autoradiographic injections placed in area 17. [3H]proline/[3H]leucine/[3H]lysine/[3H]A.A. mixture	VISL	In secondary visual cortex, autoradiographic label is in loci within the central strip of area 18a	a					
2	1	Mi84	f7	pg189, fig7	W	2	VISp	retrogradely labelled neurons in area 17 are located in {2,3,5}, {4}.	VISL	An injection of WGA-HRP in area 18a	r			
1	2	Sa91	f3b	fig3,%	W	1	VISp	%8-14% labelling in ISO(ips)	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18a	r			
		Sa91	f5A	pg329, fig5A	W	1	VISp	some commissural input from V1 <ipsilateral input not mentioned in text but present on fig4>	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18a	r			

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
c	18				Coog&Burk 93	f3	pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP	-1	VISp	In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3)	VISrl	Consistent projs were seen to region anterior to striate ctx seemed closely associated with anterior callosal ring. Considerable uncertainty about borders & topography (RL). 2 cases showed input from upper/lower fields, 2 others showed input from either.	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f3	pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP	-1	VISp	In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3)	VISFL	A clear vis plan not apparent in FLX. Temporal injns => more labeled fields than nasal injns but number of projs vble. All cases showed a nasal proj to lateral edge of acallosal oval, temp proj tended to be lateral to nasal proj & contained in callosal zone	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f3	pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP	-1	VISp	In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3)	VISlm	Within acallosal oval lateral to area 17, each inj marked 2 complete sites. PHA-L close to medial border at ant & posterior tip. RD labels more central & lateral	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f3	pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP	-1	VISp	In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3)	VISal	Within acallosal oval lateral to area 17, each inj marked 2 complete sites. PHA-L close to medial border at ant & posterior tip. RD labels more central & lateral	a
					Coog90	17	pg50, fig 1	P	-1	VISp	5 cases (PHA-L) inj sites identified in area 17 which extended throughout thickness of cortex.	VISL	each inj resulted in 5-7 distinct projections lateral to area 17 within cytoarchitectonic area 18a, each proj has similar lamination. Solid column from layer 1 to 6 with terminals most heavily concentrated in layers 2/3,4	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f3	pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP	-1	VISp	In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3)	VISPX	Upper field injections label anterior sites within PX, whereas lower field injns marked posterior portions of PX. Each case also shows nasal representation s at the lateral border of the posterior acallosal zone. suggests additional visual area in PX ???	a
					Mo93	R59r	pg2,3, fig2A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1	VISpl	the lower temporal RD projection is lateral and more rostral	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISpos	nasotemporal axis given by FB/RD axis orientated mediolaterally	a
					Mo93	R59r	pg2,3, fig2A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1	VISal	connections from the RD project laterally	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISal	RD into periphery of the inferotemporal quadrant projects extensively laterally	a
					Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISal	in AL, lower temporal RD labelling is lateral	a
					Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISlm	in LM, temporal visual field is lateral	a
					Mo93	R59r	pg2,3, fig2A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1	VISlm	RD is lateral and caudal	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISll	Nasotemporal axis given by RD-FB is orientated mediolaterally	a
					Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISli	in LI, temporal visual field (RD) is medial	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISli	labels LM and LI as a single field	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISlm	labels LM and LI as a single field	a
					Mo93	R59r	pg2,3, fig2A(red)	F	-1	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1	VISli	RD projection medial	a
0	4				Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	0	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISll	no projection to LL was found	a
					Mo93	R76r	pg5, fig2B(red)	F	0	VISp	RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r	VISpl	no projections found in PL	a
					Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	0	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISpl	no peripheral temporal visual field in area PL	a
					Mo93	R38r	pg5, fig3A(red)	F	0	VISp	RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant	VISpos	no peripheral temporal visual field in area P	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			x	6	John&Burk 94	abstract		-1	VISp			VISlm	D-[3H]-aspartate	r
					John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISlm		a
					John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISrl		a
					John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISpos	PX	a
					John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISal		a
					John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISFL		a
VISp	VISM	3	3	2	Coog&Burk 93	f4 pg3755, fig4	P 3	VISp		Inj was places in lateral striate cortex, near midpoint of ant/pos extent.		VISM	Medial projection is part of the MX. at core of proj. fibers extended in solid column from upper layer 6 to deep parts of layer 1. Degree of involvement o layer 1 vble.	a
					Mi84	f4 pg188, fig4	A 3	VISp		Autoradiographic injections placed in area 17.		VISM	In secondary visual cortex, autoradiographic label is in loci ... over patches throughout area 18b	a
			2	2	Mi84	f10 pg190, fig10	W 2	VISp		HRP positive neurons are in {2,3,5} medial area 17		VISM	A small injection of WGA-HRP into area 18b.	r
					Sa91	f4B pg326,329, fig4B	W 2	VISp		substantial associational inputs from 17		VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
			1	4	Sa91	f3c fig3,%	W 1	VISp		%5% labelling in ISO(ips), 3H leucine injections		VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18b	r
					Sa91	f4A pg329, fig4A	W 1	VISp		only commissural connection mentioned in text		VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18b	r
					Sa91	f3d fig3,%	W 1	VISp		%10-11% labelling in ISO(ips), substantial associational input, majority of cells in {1,2,3}		VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
					To84	EM2 pg544,546, fig2	H 1	VISp		HRP labelled fields: ... few labelled cells scattered in area 17		VISam	HRP injection into area AM. placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r
			c	4	Coog90	17 pg50, fig 1	P -1	VISp		5 cases (PHA-L) inj sites identified in area 17 which extended throughout thickness of cortex.		VISM	each inj resulted in 1-2 distinct projections medial to area 17 within cytoarchitectonic area 18b	a
					Coog&Burk 93	f3 pg3753-5, fig1,2,3	FP -1	VISp		In fig2 expt, RD injected at medial margin of striate cortex, near ant/post midpoint, PHA-L injected in posteromedial striate cortex. (+ 3 additional dble label expts in fig3		VISM	Medial extrastriate cortex showe substantial variability in number & position of projs labeled by different injns. Little correspondence with published visuotopic org. In all 4 cases nasal upper field injns consistently labeled most pos proj in MX	a
					Mo93	R38r pg7, fig3A(red)	F -1	VISp		RD injection was placed in periphery of the lower temporal quadrant		VISam	lower temporal quadrant is distributed at the extreme rostral region of A and AM	a
					Mo93	R76r pg7, fig2B(red)	F -1	VISp		RD injection was placed in lower temporal quadrant of V1, more temporal than R59r		VISam	lower temporal quadrant is distributed at the extreme rostral region of A and AM	a
			x	1	John&Burk 94	abstract		-2	VISp	D-[3H]-aspartate		VISM	MX	a
VISp	ATN	2	2	1	Benz83	b pg6	A 2	VISp		[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals		LD	The dorsal pathway led to two concentrations of label, one in the lateral and one in the medial part of the lateral nucleus, <lateral nucelus=LD, see fig2B>	a
			1	2	Thomp87	f5 pg194, fig5	H 1	VISp		A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex		LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3 pg193, fig3	H 1	VISp		A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex		LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	Tak85	17	pg299, fig6,10	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LD	terminal field of area 17 injs in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis is organized wrt to the med.lat axis of area 17. all injs produced label that extended from posterior to anterior pole of ldlvl., all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISp	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISp	LD	2	2	1	Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	LD	The dorsal pathway led to two concentrations of label, one in the lateral and one in the medial part of the lateral nucleus, <lateral nucleus=LD, see fig2B>	a
			1	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	VISp	A few retrogradely labeled pyramidal cells were found in the occipital cortex. These were in {5} & to a lesser extent in {6} of both striate and peristriate cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	VISp	A few labeled neurons were found in ... {5,6} of areas 17 and 18 of occipital cortex	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	1	Tak85	17	pg299, fig6,10	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LD	terminal field of area 17 injs in nucleus lateralis dorsale pars ventrolateralis is organized wrt to the med.lat axis of area 17. all injs produced label that extended from posterior to anterior pole of ldlvl., all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	VISp	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
VISp	LGd	3	3	1	Turl93	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	VISp	principal afferents to DLG originate in (i) small pyramidal cells of {6} of ipsilateral primary visual cortex (area 17) and parts of ipsilateral cytoarchitectonic areas 18a and 18b (Fig1A).	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			2	6	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	LGd	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	a
					Rees84	b	pg165-6	A	2	VISp	One rat in which the primary visual cortex had been injected ([3H]proline)	LGd	displayed label in the dLGN traversing the length of a typical projection line	a
					Sef81	b	pg5-6	H	2	VISp	some cells always found in {6} of ipsilateral area 17	LGd	2 HRP injections were confined to LGNd without any involvement of LGNv	r
					Harv90	g	pg283, fig3	W	2	VISp	ten area 17 (WGA-HRP) injections	LGd	resulted in label in the ipsilateral ... dLGN. Retrograde label and anterograde label was found in the dorsomedial aspect of the dLGN, corresponding to the upper nasal field representation	a
					Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	LGd	labelled fibres also lead to the dorsal and ventral lateral geniculate nuclei, where some terminated and others continues to the superior colliculus.	a
					Mas81	a	pg108, fig1	F	2	VISp	a large population of retrogradely labelled small diameter pyramidal cells located in {6} of 17 and fewer large pyramidal cells in {5} of 17 and 18a	LGd/LGd/LP	a microiontophoretic EB injection in LGNd which encroaches into the lateral-ventral aspect of the LTP	r
			c	3	John&Burk92		pg27, fig8	D	-1	VISp	In six cases larger injections of D-Asp were made into middle layers of area 17 or into area 18a and the survival time increased to allow for labelling of longer pathways. Following injection confined to the gray matter of area 17 (n=4)	LGd	In addition, silver grains were distributed more diffusely in the immediate vicinity of the labelled cells, indicating anterograde labelling of cortico geniculate fibre endings	a
					Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LGd	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... lgd, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Dori92		pg194, fig1	W	-1	VISp	analysis restricted to {6} since ... afferents to vLGN arise from layer V [Sefton et al '81, BR215:1] WGA-HRP granules were localized in neurons throughout {6} of ipsilateral areas 17 and 18. 60% of labelled cells Glu-immunoreactive, 62% contained Asp.	LGd	WGA-HRP injections into the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus, either resulted in restricted labelling within the boundaries of the nucleus <LGd> or in labelling of the dLGN and the ventral geniculate nucleus as well	r
VISp	LP	2	2	2	Schmidt93	b	pg152, fig9	P	2	VISp	multiple PHA-L injections into area 17	LP	anterogradely labelled fibres ... were observed in all cortico fugal targets checked, particularly in the ... lateral posterior thalamic nucleus	a
					Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	LP	the lateral posterior nucleus was filled with silver grains, as was the pretectal nucleus	a
			1	2	Solo&Nomo84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	1	VISp	Less marked projections <than inputs from DN and VISL>, in addition to areas 18 and 17, were observed from areas 19c, 20 and 7. Large Golgi like neurons {5}	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
					Solo&Nomo84	a	pg140, fig1,2	H	1	VISp	... whereas from structures in neocortex there were only very weak projections (1 or 2 cells /section), in area 17 only in the caudal parts f {5,6}	LP	HRP inj into dorsomedial zones <of LP>	r
			c	2	Tak85	17	pg295-7, fig6,10	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LPPr	the rostral portion of lpl plus the rostral 20% of lplc contains a terminal field arising from all parts of area 17. Roughly columnar labeling. VISp(ant.lat/post.lat./ant.med/post.med)->LPPr(ven.post/dor.post/ven.ant/dor.ant). Ipsi	a
					Tak85	17	pg299, fig6,10	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LPPrm	the label produced in lprm by area 17 and area 18a injections were identical: labelfields were roughly columnar and emanated anteriorly and slightly medially from the lateral surface of lprm, topography unclear, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
VISp	PO	0	0	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2	H	0	VISp	no projection from visual cortical area 17 could be detected	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction produced detected in neighbouring structures	r
VISp	LGv	2	2	1	Cosen&Mor84	a	pg368, fig2B	H	2	VISp	Visual Cortex: labeled neurons are present in visual cortex in {5}. Most of the labeled cells are in area 17 with some in area18	LGv	Of the 24 animals used in this study, injections of HRP, as shown by the benzidine dihydrochloride method, are completely confined to the VLGN in 6 (Fig1).	r
			1	1	Benz83	b	pg6	A	1	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	LGv	labelled fibres also lead to the dorsal and ventral lateral geniculate nuclei, where some terminated ... terminations were seen in the dorsal portion of the LGv in only a few sections midways between its rostral and caudal limits	a
			c	3	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	LGvl	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... lgv pars externa, all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	-1	VISp	Lesions?	LGvl	The vLGN does not project to the visual cortex but receives afferent fibres from area 17. The medial subnucleus of the vLGN is nearly free from terminal degeneration	a
					Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	-1	VISp	we could demonstrate that cells of {5} and few of {6} of area 17 are labeled	LGv	After injecting HRP into the vLGN	r
			0	2	Swa74	b	pg148	A	0	VISp	2 injections of [3H]proline were made into the visual cortex (including both areas 17 & 18 of Krieg)	LGvm	It seems unlikely that the medial division <of LGv> receives an input from the striate cortex	a
					Brau84b	a	pg213, fig4	L	0	VISp	Lesions?	LGvm	The vLGN does not project to the visual cortex but receives afferent fibres from area 17. The medial subnucleus of the vLGN is nearly free from terminal degeneration	a
VISp	RT	2	2	2	Sef81	d	pg6-8	H	2	VISp	pyramidal or pyramidal-type cells in {6} of ipsilateral cortical areas 17, 18& 18a contained HRP reaction product.	RT	Small (HRP) injections were made into visually responsive RNT.	r
					Rees&Cow83	c	pg1244, fig5	H	2	VISp/VISp/VISM/VISL	implants of HRP or its iontophoretic application into the primary visual area of the cortex	RT	Note also the cortical terminals present in the reticular nucleus(RN) of the thalamus just rostral to the dLGN	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			c	2	Tak85	17	pg305	A	-1	VISp	as shown in fig4B, 12 injections ([3H]leucine) were confined to area 17	RT	injections confined to area 17 labeled ... tm, (pg283: thalamic reticular nucleus), all structures labeled were ipsi to inj.	a
					Ohar85		pg387, table2		-1	VISp	ablation of ipsilateral primary visual cortex	RT	...By 2 days after operation, neuropil contained large numbers of small, degenerating axon terminal... Table2: fall in average density of normal appearing terminals, change in relative densities of L & D type terminals	a
VISp	ZI	2	2	1	Benz83	b	pg6	A	2	VISp	[3H]leucine injections into 5 animals	ZI	label also appeared in the dorsolateral zona incerta, some of which seemed to be fibre terminations	a
R	TUA	0	0	1	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	30 animals used for autoradiography study. Each received 1 injection of either L-leucine-3H or L-proline-3H into the posterior chamber of one eye	VMH	The autoradiographic material provided substantial evidence for a retinohypothalamic tract. The hypothalamic nuclei themselves were free of labelling save for the suprachiasmatic nucleus, both ipsi & contra, especially in ventral 1/2	a
R	ATN	1	1	2	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	AD	HRP labeled retinal fibres and terminals were found in the ... contralateral anterodorsal thalamic nucleus. <dots in fig2: lightest labelling>	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	14 adult sprague dawley rats were injected with 1-10µl of 33% HRP in 0.9% saline	AV	HRP labeled retinal fibres and terminals were found in the ... contralateral anteroventral thalamic nucleus. <dots in fig2: lightest labelling>	a
			c	5	Levine91	a	pg353-4	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AV	fibres can be seen in stria terminalis coursing rostrally from these more caudal levels. This pathway gives rise to the thalamic label reported earlier (anterior dorsal, anterior ventral thalamic nuc. & bed nuc. of the stria terminalis.)	a
					Reperant87		pg602, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	AD	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent succesivement sur les noyaux ... antérodorsal (AD)	a
					Reperant87		pg602, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	AV	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent succesivement sur les noyaux ... antéro ventral (AV)	a
					Reperant87		pg601-2, fig1	A	-1	R	L'analyse des projections rétiennes chez le rat blanc ... le transport axonal orthograde de divers traceurs ([3H]proline, HRP, Rhodamine β isothiocyanate) depuis la rétine.	LD	D'autres axones longent, la surface du thalamus et se projettent succesivement sur les noyaux latéral antérieur(LA) ...	a
					Levine91	a	pg353-4	C	-1	R	36 female Sprague-Dawley rats weighing 200-350g. 10µl of CT-HRP(.20%-40%) were injected into one eye ... behind the lens into the vitreous chamber of the eye. pressure injection over 1 min	AD	fibres can be seen in stria terminalis coursing rostrally from these more caudal levels. This pathway gives rise to the thalamic label reported earlier (anterior dorsal, anterior ventral thalamic nuc. & bed nuc. of the stria terminalis.)	a
R	RT	0	0	2	MS83	B	pg27,29, fig2FH,3	W	0	R	No labelled cells were found in retina	RT	In three animals injections of WGA-HRP were made into visual RNT	r
					Ohar85	r	pg390	L	0	R	... Unilateral eye enucleation...	RT	Systematic scannin by EM of visual TTRN contralateral to enucleated eye failed to disclose degenerating axon terminals	a
ATN	SC	2	2	1	Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	2	LD	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... lateral thalamic nucleus, <obs from fig2a> A small number of labelled cells was seen concentrated in ... the dorsal part of the lateral nucleus of the thalamus	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of teh midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
ATN	LHA	0	0	2	Petro83		pg292, fig9,10		0	AD		VTA/LHA/ PH/???	HRP inj, VTA with a small extension into the posterior parts of the lateral hypothalamus	r
					Petro83		pg292, fig9,10		0	AV		VTA/LHA/ PH/???	HRP inj, VTA with a small extension into the posterior parts of the lateral hypothalamus	r
ATN	VISL	1	1	1	Cole80	b	pg207, fig1ABC	H	1	LD	result was labelling of ... the lateral <=LD from fig1C> and mediodorsal nuclei	VISL	The largest HRP injection illustrated (Fig1A)	r
			x	2	Shibita93c		abstract		-1	IAM		VISL		
					Shibita93c		abstract		-1	AM		VISL		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>																		
ATN	VISM	3	3	3	To84	EM2	pg544,548	H	3	LD	subcortically, areas of dense retrograde and anterograde label were observed in anterior posterior portions of the lateroposterior nucleus and adjacent regions of the lateral nucleus	VISam	HRP injection into area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r																		
					vGr92b	PL111	pg433, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ...area 18b. Most labeled axons formed a dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4} of dorsal Rdg & in {1,3,4} of adjacent visual cortex	a																		
					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	3	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	VISM	... labeled terminals primarily in ... area 18b. A number of labeled axons extended into the rostral & lateral parts of area 18b where they formed a dense terminal field in {1,3,4}	a																		
		2	5	Sri&Wys86	CF288	pg159, fig14	b	F	2	LD	The injection in area 18b resulted in neuronal labelling in LD, the LD labelled neurons were present throughout the rostrocaudal extent of the nucleus and tended to be in a position similar to that of the neurons projecting to caudal Rag	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r																		
														Sri&Wys86	CF288	pg159, fig14	b	F	2	AM	The injection in area 18b resulted in neuronal labelling in ... AM	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r								
																								Harv90	h	pg283, fig4	W	2	LD	Retrograde and anterograde label was seen in LDVL	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.
														vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	VISM	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... visual cortex. Labeled axons extended (from Rdg) to the adjacent visual cortex (i.e. area 18b) where they terminated in {1,3,4}	a									
																							vGr92b									
		1	2	vGr92b	PL140	pg432, fig10	P	1	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediodorsal part of caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ... area 18b. A small number of axons extended further laterally to terminate in {1,3,4} of the rostral part of area 18b	a																			
													vGr92b	PL117	pg436, fig13	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ... area 18b. A few labeled axons extended into the caudal part of Rgb and the caudal part of area 18b.	a										
		0	2	Sri&Wys86	CF288	pg159, fig14	b	F	0	AD	The injection in area 18b did not result in neuronal labelling in ... AD	VISM										In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r									
													Sri&Wys86	CF288	pg159, fig14	b	F	0	AV	The injection in area 18b did not result in neuronal labelling in ... AV	VISM		In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r								
ATN	VISp	1	1	3	vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	1	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	VISp										This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... visual cortex. A few axons extended into area 17, predominantly ending in {1,4}		a								
													Hug77a	c	pg320, fig7	H	1	LD	... revealed a very sparse projection from NLT ... to the striate cortex	VISp/VISp/ VISL	Placement of HRP into area 17		r									
																							Rees&Cow8	3	b	pg1244, fig5	H	1	LD	Usually a few labelled cells were found in adjacent lateral ... nucleus of the thalamus; they were very rare when compared with labelled cells in the dLGN.	VISp/VISp/ VISM/VISL	implants of HRP or its iontophoretic application into the primary visual area of the cortex
x	2	Shibita93c	abstract	-1	AM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-																			
														Shibita93c	abstract	-1	IAM	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-						
LD	VISL	1	1	1	Cole80	b	pg207, fig1ABC	H	1	LD	result was labelling of ... the lateral <=LD from fig1C> and mediodorsal nuclei	VISL	The largest HRP injection illustrated (Fig1A)														r					
LD	VISM	3	3	3	To84	EM2	pg544,548	H	3	LD	subcortically, areas of dense retrograde and anterograde label were observed in anterior posterior portions of the lateroposterior nucleus and adjacent regions of the lateral nucleus	VISam	HRP injection into area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r																		

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					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	3	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	VISM	... labeled terminals primarily in ... area 18b. A number of labeled axons extended into the rostral & lateral parts of area 18b where they formed a dense terminal field in {1,3,4}	a
					vGr92b	PL111	pg433, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ... area 18b. Most labeled axons formed a dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4} of dorsal Rdg & in {1,3,4} of adjacent visual cortex	a
		2	4		Sri&Wys86	CF288 b	pg159, fig14	F	2	LD	The injection in area 18b resulted in neuronal labelling in LD, the LD labelled neurons were present throughout the rostrocaudal extent of the nucleus and tended to be in a position similar to that of the neurons projecting to caudal Rag	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r
					Harv90	h	pg283, fig4	W	2	LD	Retrograde and anterograde label was seen in LDVL	VISM	Five (WGA-HRP) injections were made into area 18 and resulted in tectal label. In fig4 example, injection was probably made into area AM.	r
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	VISM	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... visual cortex. Labeled axons extended (from Rdg) to the adjacent visual cortex (i.e. area 18b) where they terminated in {1,3,4}	a
					vGr92b	CFR22 3	pg431, fig8	F	2	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	VISM	... labeled axons in ... area 18b. A number of axons extended into the rostral part of area 18b where they terminated in {1,3,4}.	a
		1	2		vGr92b	PL117	pg436, fig13	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ... area 18b. A few labeled axons extended into the caudal part of Rgb and the caudal part of area 18b.	a
					vGr92b	PL140	pg432, fig10	P	1	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediodorsal part of caudal LD	VISM	... axons were labeled in ... area 18b. A small number of axons extended further laterally to terminate in {1,3,4} of the rostral part of area 18b	a
LD	VISp	1	1	3	vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	1	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	VISp	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... visual cortex. A few axons extended into area 17, predominantly ending in {1,4}	a
					Rees&Cow8 3	b	pg1244, fig5	H	1	LD	Usually a few labelled cells were found in adjacent lateral ... nucleus of the thalamus; they were very rare when compared with labelled cells in the dLGN.	VISp/VISp/ VISM/VISL	implants of HRP or its iontophoretic application into the primary visual area of the cortex	r
					Hug77a	c	pg320, fig7	H	1	LD	... revealed a very sparse projection from NLT ... to the striate cortex	VISp/VISp/ VISL	Placement of HRP into area 17	r
LGd	PBG	0	0	1	Sef84	f	pg147	H	0	LGd/LGv	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5).	PBG	No anterograde transport was ever observed from LG to PBg	a
LGd	VISL	2	2	1	Hug77a	d	pg320,322, fig8	H	2	LGd	extensive cell labelling in LGNd. Venmed and dorlat aspect labelled neurons in all but most ros portions. Suggestion of lamina pattern of the LGNd that project to 18A. Through venmed aspect of LGNd. cells in NLP more densely labelled than cells in LGNd.	VISL	HRP inj into 18a	r
		1	5		Sa91	f2c	pg326, fig2, %	W	1	LGd	%4-5% labelled cells in TH	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into rostral area 18a	r
					Sa91	f2b	pg326, fig2, %	W	1	LGd	%2-3% labelled cells in TH	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj into caudal 18a	r
					Hug77a	e	pg322, fig11	A	1	LGd	injections of [3H]leucine into the LGNd. In three cases these injections did not involve NLP. ...case LGN2: inj site clearly confined to the dorsal division of the lateral geniculate.	VISL	The major geniculate projection is confined to area 17 in all but its most posterior extent, where label extends into 18A. In addition ... the LGNd provides afferents to the lateral portion of the lateral aspect of area 18A	a
					Cole80		pg207, fig1ABC	H	1	LGd	the position of labeled neurons on two thalamic structures: the lateral posterior nucleus and GL <LGd>.	VISL	The largest HRP injection illustrated (Fig1A)	r
					Rib75	rat56	pg347-351, fig2	A	1	LGd/LGd/L Gv	No injections ([3H]proline) were strictly confined to the neurons in this subdivision, i.e. dLGN inj	VISL	there was some extension of label toward the adjacent and cytoarchitecturally defined areas 18 and 18a. This extension was slight but indicated that the geniculocortical terminals extend into the zone of transition between areas 17,18, &18a.	a
		0	5		Harv90	i	pg287, fig4	W	0	LGd	No retrograde label was seen in the dLGN	VISL	WGA-HRP inj	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Olav79	a	pg139	H	0	LGd	failed to label cells in dLGN	VISal	The injection of HRP in anterolateral, lateromedial, and laterolateral areas, previously identified physiologically and marked electrolytically	r
					Olav79	b	pg139	H	0	LGd	failed to label cells in dLGN	VISFL	The injection of HRP in anterolateral, lateromedial, and laterolateral areas, previously identified physiologically and marked electrolytically	r
					Perr80	18a	pg923, fig7	H	0	LGd	no evidence of was found of a projection from the dLGN to area 18a	VISL	Injections of HRP into area 18a	r
					Olav79	c	pg139	H	0	LGd	failed to label cells in dLGN	VISlm	The injection of HRP in anterolateral, lateromedial, and laterolateral areas, previously identified physiologically and marked electrolytically	r
LGd	VISM	1	1	3	Sa91	f2a	pg326, fig2, %	W	1	LGd	%2-3% labelled cells in TH	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18b	r
					To84	EM2	pg544,548	H	1	LGd	only few cells were found in the dorsal lateral geniculate nucleus	VISam	HRP injection into area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r
					Rib75	rat56	pg347-351, fig2	A	1	LGd/LGd/LGv	No injections ([3H]proline) were strictly confined to the neurons in this subdivision, i.e. dLGN injns	VISM	there was some extension of label toward the adjacent and cytoarchitecturally defined areas 18 and 18a. This extension was slight but indicated that the geniculocortical terminals extend into the zone of transition between areas 17,18, &18a.	a
			0	1	Sa91	f2e	fig2, %	W	0	LGd	%0% labelled cells in TH	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
LGd	VISp	3	3	6	Perr80	l7	pg923	H	3	LGd	... produce a denselyb labelled group of cells in the dLGN	VISp	Injections of HRP into area 17	r
					Sef81	e	pg8	H	3	LGd	many cells labelled in LGNd	VISp	single of multiple injections into cortical area 17	r
					Sa91	f2d	pg326, fig2, %	W	3	LGd	%96-8% labelled cells in TH	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into V1	r
					Hug77a	c	pg320,322, fig7	H	3	LGd	... marked uptake by cells in LGNd	VISp/VISp/VISL	Placement of HRP into area 17	r
					Rees&Cow83	b	pg1244, fig5	H	3	LGd	retrogradely labelled cells along a column which traversed the dLGN obliquely, in a predominantly rostro-caudal direction.	VISp/VISp/VISM/VISL	implants of HRP or its iontophoretic application into the primary visual area of the cortex. Sites were not verified histologically in these series of brains	r
					Rib75	rat56	pg347-351, fig2	A	3	LGd/LGd/LGv	No injections ([3H]proline) were strictly confined to the neurons in this subdivision, i.e. dLGN injns	VISp	the visual cortex, the site of axons' termination. label was heavily concentrated in {4} of cytoarchiectural area 17	a
			2	3	Dreh90		pg322, fig3AB	F	2	LGd	labelled thalamic cells found exclusively in DLG, LP, and ILN	VISp	restricted fluorescent dye injns into 17	r
					Harv90	j	pg283, fig3	W	2	LGd	resulted in label in the ipsilateral ... dLGN. Retrograde label and anterograde label was found in the dorsomedial aspect of the dLGN, corresponding to the upper nasal field representation	VISp	ten area 17 (WGA-HRP) injections	r
					Hug77a	e	pg322, fig11	A	2	LGd	injections of [3H]leucine into the LGNd. In three cases these injections did not involve NLP. ...case LGN2: inj site clearly confined to the dorsal division of the lateral geniculate.	VISp	axons ... leave the thalamus through the rostral pole of LGd. They terminate within two spatially distinct cortical target areas. The major geniculate projection is confined to area 17 in all but its most posterior extent... {4,3} {1,6}	a
			1	1	Hug77a	z	pg320-22, fig9,10	L	1	LGd	Normal appearing nerve cells were observed in the LGNd along the medial wall and in a dorsolateral lamina subjacent to the optic tract. ...the transition between the degenerated portions of the nucleus and the lateral lamina is fairly abrupt.	VISp	Lesions, destriate rats... in most cases some involvement of the subcortical white matter was noted	r
			c	1	John&Burk92		pg27, fig8	D	-1	LGd	A cluster of labeled neurons was found in the lateral geniculate nucleus (LGN)	VISp	In six cases larger injections of D-Asp were made into middle layers of area 17 or into area 18a and the survival time increased to allow for labelling of longer pathways. Following injection confined to the gray matter of area 17 (n=4)	r
			x	1	Brau84		abstract		-1	LGd	Caudal part, neurons responding to light with long latencies (W cells)	VISp	FG, dble labelling expt, flattened ctx prep,	

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T															
LGd	RT	2	2	1	Sef81	d	pg6	H	2	LGd	When the HRP was restricted to visual RNT cells only in LGNd were labelled and not in any other thalamic relay nuclei.	RT	Small (HRP) injections were made into visually responsive RNT.	r															
			c	1	Ohar85		pg387		-1	LGd	lesion	RT																	
CL	VISM	1	1	1	Sri&Wys86	CF288b	pg159, fig14	F	1	CL	Like Rag, area 18b receives a small projection from the centrolateral nucleus	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r															
CL	VISp	0	0	1	Ullan85		pg336, fig3B,4	H	0	CL	Nucleus centralis lateralis: This intralaminar nucleus contains the greatest number of HRP marked neurons after the injection into different zones of the cerebral cortex.	VISp	The HRP injections in area 17 did not label any neuron in Cl	r															
PF	MRN	2	2	1	Steinin92		pg527, fig8		2	PF		MRN	WGA-HRP inj, fig3, MEA	r															
PF	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	PF		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r															
LP	APN	1	1	1	Caduss91	HP26	pg88, fig2	W	1	LP	In two cases (HP25 and HP26) a very small number of positive cells was observed in the caudal pole of the lateral posterior thalamic nucleus	APN/APN/PO	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrates the overall afferent input to the APc.	r															
LP	VISL	3	3	3	Harv90 Perr80 Hug77a	1 18a a	pg286-7, fig4 pg923, fig7 pg318, fig4	W H A	3 3 3	LPI LP LP/LP/LD/P RT/LGd	dense retrograde and anterograde label was seen in the LPL dense labelling throughout the lateral posterior nucleus. Hydraulic injections of [3H]leucine were made in the NLP. Injection site in case LP2. included virtually the entire rostrocaudal extent of the nucleus. (inj site) extended ...into N lateralis thalami, ... N. pretectalis, ... LGNd, ... hippocampus (v. slight)	VISL VISL VISL	WGA-HRP inj Injections of HRP into area 18a The majority of the labelled axons course dorsally and posteriorly... the superior limb continues within the and immediately superficial to the medullary substance to terminate in areas 7, 18A, and 18. heaviest thalamic input in {4,3}	r r a															
															2	7	Cole80		pg207, fig1ABC	H	2	LP	the position of labeled neurons on two thalamic structures: the lateral posterior nucleus and GL <L.Gd>	VISL	The largest HRP injection illustrated (Fig1A)	r			
																	Sa91 Olav79	f2b a	pg326, fig2, % pg139	W H	2 2	LP LP	%57-65% labelled cells in TH labelled cells in a portion of LP different from the portions labelled after injections in the other areas. Arranged in a longitudinal column through rost.caud. ext. Inj into anterolateral: label was restricted to the most lateral and ventral parts of LP.	VISL-c VISal	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj, into caudal 18a After the injection of HRP into the anterolateral area	r r			
																	Olav79	c	pg139	H	2	LP	labelled cells in a portion of LP different from the portions labelled after injections in the other areas. Arranged in a longitudinal column through rost.caud. ext. Inj into lateromedial: label along central anteroposterior axis of nuc.	VISlm	After the injection of HRP into the lateromedial area	r			
																	Olav79	b	pg139	H	2	LP	labelled cells in a portion of LP different from the portions labelled after injections in the other areas. Arranged in a longitudinal column through rost.caud. ext. Inj into laterolateral: medial aspect of LP	VISFL	After the injection of HRP into the laterolateral area	r			
																	Harv90 Hug77a	k d	pg287, fig4,5 pg320, fig8	W H	2 2	LPI LP	In the LPL, retrograde WGA-HRP label was situated ventrally in the nucleus, a region shown previously to project to AL The projection of NLP to the lateral portion of area 18A ... a group of cells containing the reaction product extended laterally from the central portions of NLP through the ventromedial aspect of the LGNd	VISal VISL	(WGA-HRP) injection placed more rostrally in area 18a, probably in the AL region HRP inj into 18a	r r			
																	Sa91 Sa91	f2c f1a	pg326, fig2, % pg326, fig1	W W	1 1	LP LP	%9-10% labelled cells in TH minor input from LP to rostral 18a	VISL-r VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP inj, into rostral area 18a 4 WGA-HRP/HRP inj, into rostral area 18a, <fig shows inclusion of 17 in inj site>	r r			
																	John&Burk92		pg27-8, fig9	D	-1	LP	a cluster of cells was found in the lateral posterior nucleus	VISL	In six cases larger injections of D-Asp were made into middle layers of area 17 or into area 18a and the survival time increased to allow for labelling of longer pathways. Following injection of D-Asp into the extrastriate visual area 18a (n=2)	r			
															LP	VISM	3	3	4	Sa91	f2e	pg326, fig2, %	W	3	LP	%88% labelled cells in TH	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP inj, into caudal 18b	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					Sa91	f1b	pg326, fig1	W	3	LP	major input to caudal 18b from LP	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
					To84	EM2	pg544,548	H	3	LP	subcortically, areas of dense retrograde and anterograde label were observed in anterior posterior portions of the lateroposterior nucleus and adjacent regions of the lateral nucleus	VISam	HRP injection into area AM, placed by 1) stereotaxic measurements from physiological experiments, 2) borders of AM identified in Nissl stained sections, 3) distribution of thalamic labelling compared to previous data from the rodent.	r
					Hug77a	a	pg318, fig4	A	3	LP/LP/LD/P RT/LGd	Hydraulic injections of [3H]leucine were made in the NLP. Injection site in case LP2, includedd virtually the entire rostrocaudal extent of the nucleus. (inj site) extended ...into N lateralis thalami, ... N. pretectalis, ... LGNd, ... hippocampus (v. slight)	VISM	The majority of the labelled axons course dorsally and posteriorly... the superior limb continues within the and immediately superficial to the medullary substance to terminate in areas 7, 18A, and 18. heaviest thalamic input in {4,3}	a
			2	2	Sri&Wys86	CF288 b	pg159, fig14	F	2	LP	The injection in area 18b resulted in neuronal labelling in ... LP	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB; <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r
					Perr80	z	pg924	H	2	LP	labelled cells were found in the dLGN, the lateral thalamus and the lateral posterior nucleus	VISM	(HRP) injections into area 18b	r
			1	1	Sa91	f2a	pg326, fig2, %	W	1	LP	%12-13% labelled cells in TH	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18b	r
LP	VISp	2	2	1	Dreh90		pg322, fig3AB	F	2	LP	labelled thalamic cells found exclusively in DLG, LP, and ILN	VISp	restricted fluorescent dye injns into 17	r
			1	3	Perr80	17	pg923	H	1	LP	a few scattered cells are found in the lateral thalamus and lateral posterior nucleus	VISp	Injections of HRP into area 17	r
					Hug77a	c	pg320, fig7	H	1	LP	... revealed a very sparse projection from ... NLP to the striate cortex. Retrograde cell labelling was observed throughout the rostro-caudal extent fo NLP and tended to be found in the more centrally located portions of the nucleus.	VISp/VISp/ VISL	Placement of HRP into area 17. Some indication that the medial portion of area 18A was involved in the injection site, the pattern of thalamic labelling in case HRP5 was obviously different than that in HRP2	r
					Rees&Cow8 3	b	pg1244, fig5	H	1	LP	Usually a few labelled cells were found in adjacent ... lateral posterior nucleus of the thalamus; they were very rare when compared with labelled cells in the dLGN.	VISp/VISp/ VISM/VISL	implants of HRP or its iontophoretic application into the primary visual area of the cortex	r
			0	1	Sa91	f2d	fig2(n=3), %	W	0	LP	%1% labelled cells in TH	VISp	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into VI	r
PO	PG	x	x	1	Cad&Rog90		abstract		3	PO		PG		
PO	MRN	x	x	1	Cad&Rog90		abstract		-1	PO		MRN		
PO	PRT	x	x	1	Cad&Rog90		abstract		3	PO		PRT		
PO	SC	1	1	1	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	1	PO	positive cells were occasionally seen in the following thalamic nuclei: ...posterior	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r
			x	1	Cad&Rog90		abstract		3	PO		SC	intermediate & deep layers	
PO	VISL	3	3	2	Sa91	f2c	pg326, fig2, %	W	3	PO	%82-85% labelled cells in TH	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18a	r
					Sa91	f1a	pg326, fig1	W	3	PO	major thalamic input to rostral 18a comes from PO	VISL-r	4 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18a, <fig shows inclusion of 17 in inj site>	r
			2	1	Sa91	f2b	pg326, fig2, %	W	2	PO	%15%-20% labelled cells in TH	VISL-c	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18a	r
PO	VISM	3	3	1	Sa91	f2a	pg326, fig2, %	W	3	PO	%85-90% labelled cells in TH	VISam	3 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into rostral area 18b	r
			2	1	Sa91	f2e	pg326, fig2, %	W	2	PO	%12% labelled cells in TH	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
			1	1	Sa91	f1b	pg326, fig1	W	1	PO	minor input to caudal 18b from PO	VISpm	2 WGA-HRP/HRP injns into caudal 18b	r
PO	LGd	2	2	1	Pas82c	D	pg413, fig3	H	2	PO	It is consistently demonstrated that the posterior thalamic nucleus projects to both LGB	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
PO	LP	c	c	1	Solo&Nomo 84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	-1	PO	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA)	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
			x	1	Cad&Rog90		abstract		-1	PO		LP		
PO	LGv	2	2	1	Pas82c	V	pg413, fig4	H	2	PO	It is consistently demonstrated that the posterior thalamic nucleus projects to both LGB	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
PO	ZI	x	x	2	Rog&Cad85	abstract		3	PO			ZI		
					Cad&Rog90	abstract		3	PO			ZI		
MD	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22 table1		W	0	MD		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
MD	VISL	1	1	1	Cole80	d pg207, fig1ABC		H	1	MD	result was labelling of ... the lateral <=LD from fig1C> and mediodorsal nuclei	VISL	The largest HRP injection illustrated (Fig1A)	r
MD	VISM	1	1	1	Sri&Wys86	CF288 pg159, fig14b		F	1	MD	Unlike Rag, area 18b receives a small projection from the dorsolateral part of the mediodorsal nucleus.	VISM	In CF288 ... area 18b was injected with 20nl of FB: <Caption in fig14 does not agree with text>	r
MD	RT	1	1	1	Cesaro85	pg31, fig2			1	MD		RT	rostral, [3H]WGA inj	r
					Corn90b	abstract			-1	MD	lateral & central	RT		
PVT	MRN	1	1	1	Steinin92	pg527, fig8			1	PVT		MRN	WGA-HRP inj, fig3, MEA	r
PVT	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22 table1		W	0	PVT		MPO/PV/SCH	WGA-HRP inj	r
PVT	MD	x	x	1	Corn&Phil88	abstract			-1	PVT		MDI		
IGL	APN	2	2	1	Mikk92	a pg958		P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	APN	2 routes from inj site: 1) medial: largest output proj to con hemisphere, projected under caudal op through LD & APN into pc. Presumably, many fibres terminate in the LD and the APN of ips hemisphere. No. of fibres much lower on con side.	a
IGL	ATN	2	2	1	Mikk92	a pg958		P	2	IGL/IGL/LGv/LGd	only PHA-L injections which involved the IGL resulted in labeling of fibres in the contralateral LGN. Injections centred in, or involving the IGL resulted in all cases in additional labeling of cells in the DLG or VLG, or both	LD	2 routes from inj site: 1) medial: largest output proj to con hemisphere, projected under caudal op through LD & APN into pc. Presumably, many fibres terminate in the LD and the APN of ips hemisphere. No. of fibres much lower on con side.	a
IGL	ZI	x	x	1	Mikk92	abstract			3	IGL	PHA-L inj	ZI		a
LGv	PG	2	2	1	Tori86	A pg94, table1, fig1,5		H	2	LGv	In zona incerta, fields of forel and the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, label bilat. heaviest ipsi. Labeled neurons are distributed through the extent of the ZI & is continuous with the LGv & FF d(ZI)>d(H1)>d(LGv)>d(H2). 4-10 cells/section.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
			1	1	Mihail89	pg632, fig14CD			1	LGv		PG	WGA-HRP inj	r
			c	3	Brau84b	a pg214, fig5		L	-1	LGv	Lesions of LGv only in contralaterally enucleated animals	PG	the rostral part of the nucleus medialis pontis is the main termination area in the pons region. Some fibres extend to lateral part of the pons and terminate in the nucleus lateralis pontis	a
					Gray74	F1 pg303, fig1A		A	-1	LGv	In 30 rats ... [3H]proline or a mixture of [3H]proline/[3H]leucine was injected into the LGv hydraulically or iontophoretically.	PG	a second terminal field appears in the lateral pontine gray.	a
					Rib75	rat100 pg353, fig5		A	-1	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	PG	A caudally directed ventromedial projection passed through the lateral terminal nucleus of the accessory optic tract and continued in its caudal trajectory to terminate in the dor.med. & dor.lat. parts of the pontine gray.	a
LGv	TRN	2	2	1	Tori86	A pg94, table1, fig1,5		H	2	LGv	In zona incerta, fields of forel and the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus, label bilat. heaviest ipsi. Labeled neurons are distributed through the extent of the ZI & is continuous with the LGv & FF d(ZI)>d(H1)>d(LGv)>d(H2). 4-10 cells/section.	TRN	HRP injected into the NRTP using either pressure or iontophoresis. Results obtained from 14 pigmented rats. 7 cases had deliberately small injections so that the injection could be localized within NRTP.	r
LGv	PBG	0	0	1	Sef84	f pg147		H	0	LGd/LGv	HRP was injected into sites identified electrophysiologically: SC(n=9), restricted to DLG(n=12), restricted to VLG(3), DLG & VLG(n=5), pretectal nuclei (n=5).	PBG	No anterograde transport was ever observed from LG to PBg	a
LGv	APN	3	3	3	Caduss91	control 4a pg93		W	3	LGv	bilateral applications of WGA-HRP in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus	APN	a dense pattern of both retrograde and anterograde labeling occur in the APc	a
					Foster89	f3 pg689, fig3		F	3	LGv	a very dense population of cells projecting to the APTA was found in the ipsilateral ventrolateral geniculate nucleus, (fewer number of neurons on contralateral side)	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	LGv	The labelled cells were distributed essentially between two structures: the ventral lateral geniculate body and the zona incerta. In all cases, neurons were located laterally in the magnocellular part of the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP injns, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			2	2	Legg79 Rib75	rat100	pg350 pg353, fig5CD		2	LGv	3H A.A, injections 5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	APN APN	LGv->OP projection spills into APN Ips: ... terminal labeling was primarily located in the olivary pretectal nucleus, with some additional label in the anterior pretectal nucleus and the nucleus of the optic tract.	a a
LGv	VISp	0	0	1	Sef81	e	pg8	H	0	LGv	there were no labelled cells in LGNv	VISp	single of multiple injections into cortical area 17	r
LGv	ATN	2	2	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	LGv	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	LGv	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ventral lateral geniculate nucleus,	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	LGv	No labeled cells were found in the vLG, ZI or mammillary bodies	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
			x	2	Sikes&Vogt 87		abstract	-1		LGv		ATN		
					Sik&Vog87		abstract	-1		LGv		ATN		
LGv	ZI	2	2	2	Rib75	rat100	pg353, fig5DEF	A	2	LGv	5 major projections were found to emanate from the vLGN. Rat 100 will be used to illustrate the basic results although these projections were also apparent in other animals. Rats numbered ... 100 (Fig1D) had injections confined to the vLGN	ZI	The shortest of the ventromedial projections was to the ipsilateral zona incerta. While a projection was clearly directed towards the entire anterior extent of this subthalamic structure, it was difficult to assess ... because of proximity to inj site	a
					Swa74	c	pg150	A	2	LGv/LGv/L Gd/CA3	Of 16 injns in and around the LGB only those in which the isotope has spread to involve, or was confined to, the LGNv gave rise to the pattern of projections ... described below. Expt R49 example (cells in LGNd, dor 1/3 LGv & CA3). Same label in 3 more expts	ZI	Ventral pathway ... proceeds through the zona incerta (grain density high enough to suggest term field)	a
			1	1	Rog&Cad85	a	pg482, table1	H	1	LGv	Occasional cell labeling was also observed in the medial and the ventral lateral geniculate nuclei & the ventrobasal complex	ZI	Horseradish peroxidase was introduced in various sectors of the left zona incerta in 7 subjects. All application areas (dense core as well as halo zone) were restricted to the ZI.	r
			c	1	Brau84b	a	pg213-4, fig5	L	-1	LGv	Lesions of LGv only in contralaterally enucleated animals	ZI	the fibres of the vLGN running in ventromedial and caudal direction terminate partly in the zona incerta	a
RT	MRN	0	0	1	Ohar85	c	pg392	H	0	RT	labeled cells not found	MRN	... after injection into cerebral cortex, superior colliculus, midbrain tegmentum, brain stem reticular formation	r
RT	SC	0	0	1	Ohar85	b	pg392	H	0	RT	labeled cells not found	SC	... after injection into cerebral cortex, superior colliculus, midbrain tegmentum, brain stem reticular formation	r
RT	VISp	0	0	1	Sef81	e	pg8	H	0	RT	there were no labelled cells in visual RNT	VISp	single of multiple injections into cortical area 17	r
RT	ATN	2	2	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	RT	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	RT	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ... portion of the thalamic reticular nucleus situated close to LD	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79	pg250, fig5,11	H	1	RT	HRP labeled cells found in uppermost area of reticular nucleus of thalamus.	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
			c	2	Ohar85	k	pg392	H	-1	RT	... labeled cells in dorsal part of TRN rostral to visual sector	LD	HRP injections into laterodorsal nucleus ...	r
					Ohar85	l	pg392	H	-1	RT	Cells rostral to this sector were labeled	ATN	HRP injections into anterior nuclei	r
			x	6	Sik&Vog87		abstract			-1	RT	ATN	WGA-HRP injections	r
					Shib92		abstract			-1	RT	IAM	WGA-HRP injections	r
					Sikes&Vogt		abstract			-1	RT	ATN	WGA-HRP injections	r
					87									
					Shib92		abstract			-1	RT	AD	WGA-HRP injections	r
					Shib92		abstract			-1	RT	AV	WGA-HRP injections	r
					Shib92		abstract			-1	RT	AM	WGA-HRP injections	r
RT	LD	2	2	2	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	RT	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	RT	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ... portion of the thalamic reticular nucleus situated close to LD	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			c	1	Ohar85	k	pg392	H	-1	RT	... labeled cells in dorsal part of TRN rostral to visual sector	LD	HRP injections into laterodorsal nucleus ...	r
RT	LGd	3	3	1	Turl93	A	pg226, fig1,2	F	3	RT	principal afferents to DLG originate in ... (ii) the ipsilateral reticular thalamic nucleus	LGd	Fast Blue/Fluoro Gold (FB/FG) injections into DLGs with no spread into VLGs or LPs	r
			2	1	Sef81	b	pg5	H	2	RT	HRP positive cells were identified in visual RNT	LGd	2 HRP injections were confined to LGNd without any involvement of LGNv	r
			c	1	Ohar85	f	pg392	H	-1	RT	... labeled cells in dorso-caudal TRN.	LGd	(HRP) Injections into LGd ...	r
RT	CL	x	x	1	Raos&Bent		abstract			-1	RT	CL		r
RT	PF	3	3	1	Corn&Phil8	f3	pg142, fig3	W	3	RT	Nucleus reticularis thalami heavily labeled following PF injection. Stained cells found mainly in rostral to mid sections of nucleus, although very anterior tip of Rt largely free of label.	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
RT	PO	c	c	1	Ohar85	m	pg392	H	-1	RT	labeled cells in region of TRN rostral to geniculate projection sectors & caudal to VB & LD projection sectors	PO	HRP injections into posterior thalamic nuclei	r
RT	MD	3	3	2	Groene88	lat-r	pg399, fig16,17	W	3	RT	reticular nucleus of thalamus contains a large number of positive neurons in its rostral part.	MDl	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	r
					Groene88	rh8168	pg398, fig12,13	W	3	RT	strong bilateral labeling ... in reticular thalamic nucleus.	MDm/MDm /EPI/PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8168: inj site includes rostral MDm, PVT, slightly stria medullaris	r
			2	3	Corn&Phil8	8	pg1037,1040, fig4	W	2	RT	Reticular thalamic nucleus provided dense well organized projection to MD. Number of cells less than in cortex. Those cells projecting to central MD (case11) further medial & ventral in centre of nuc, no overlap with cells projecting to MDl.	MDc	injected WGA labeled centre of MD. although light track label seen in stria medullaris & hippocampus. Centre of inj occupied approximately same posn rostrocaudally as MDl case	r
					Corn&Phil8	8	pg1037,1040, fig4	W	2	RT	Reticular thalamic nucleus provided dense well organized projection to MD. Number of cells less than in cortex. Lateral MD (case13) recieved input from group of heavily labelled cells in lateral part of rostral Rt just dorsal to internal capsule.	MDl	Injected WGA labeled lateral MD towards ros end. Darkly staining inj site completely confined to lateral MD, larger halo of less densely stained cells involved very small part of adj centrolateral nucleus & central MD.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Gerf82	md	pg295	W	2	RT	In excess of 80 labeled perikarya were observed in each of the following brain areas: ... (5) the ipsilateral reticular thalamic nucleus;	MD	Iontophoretic injections of WGA-HRP were made into the mediodorsal thalamic nucleus and included the central lateral intralaminar nucleus. There was little detectable spread of the tracer into the intralaminar nuclei.	r
			1	1	Groene88	rh8159	pg392-3, fig8,9	W	1	RT	Neurons in reticular nucleus of thalamus are heavily labeled in rostromedial sector where this nucleus penetrated by labeled fibres of inferior thalamic peduncle. Also some cells in contralateral reticular nucleus labeled.	MD/MD/M H/PVT/PT	relatively large WGA-HRP injections ... RH-8159, inj located centrally in rostral MD & includes all segments, only little spread into stria medullaris, medial habenula paraventricular nucleus & caudal aspect of parataeniaal nuc.	r
			x	1	Corn&Phil88		abstract		-1	RT		MD		
RT	IGL	c	c	1	Moore&Card94	b	pg404, 407	F	-1	RT	following injections of Fluoro-Gold into IGL, there are labeled neurons in contralateral IGL, caudal thalamic reticular nucleus, SCN, & adjacent anterior hypothalamic area & retrochiasmatic area where relatively large numbers of neurons are present...	IGL/IGL/LG d/LGv	Injecting fluorescent tracer into either SCN (bilaterally) or IGL. 50-100nl of fluoro-gold injected stereotaxically (n=10)	r
ZI	IO	2	2	1	Swe&Cas83a		pg335, fig3C		2	ZI		IO	large HRP inj	r
			c	1	Swe&Cas83b		pg262, fig3, see also Swe&Cas83a		-1	ZI		IO	HRP inj	r
ZI	PG	3	3	1	Tori86		pg94, table1, gi1L-O		3	ZI		TRN	HRP injection	r
			2	1	Tori86		pg94, table1, gi1L-O		2	FF		TRN	HRP injection	r
			x	1	Mihail89		abstract		-1	ZI		PG	basilar pontine nuclei	
ZI	TRN	3	3	1	Tori86		pg94, table1, gi1L-O		3	ZI		TRN	HRP injection	r
			2	1	Tori86		pg94, table1, gi1L-O		2	FF		TRN	HRP injection	r
ZI	MRN	1	1	1	Steinin92		pg527, fig8		1	ZI		MRN	WGA-HRP inj, fig3, MEA	r
			x	2	Sh-Lag83		abstract		-1	ZI		MRN		
					Sh-Lag83		abstract		-1	FF		MRN		
ZI	PRT	3	3	2	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	ZI	the cells in the ipsilateral zona incerta made up one of the largest and densest collections of cells in the diencephalon innervating the APTA	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	ZI	The labelled cells were distributed essentially between two structures: the ventral lateral geniculate body and the zona incerta. Labelling particularly dense in the pars caudalis and ventralis.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			1	1	Caduss91	control 5a	pg93	W	1	ZI	a tracer (WGA?) deposit restricted to the zona incerta	APN	induced sparse cellular and terminal labeling in the lateral part of the caudal APc	a
			x	1	Nicollelis92		abstract		-1	ZI	dorsal parts	PRT		
ZI	APN	3	3	2	Foster89	f3	pg689, fig3	F	3	ZI	the cells in the ipsilateral zona incerta made up one of the largest and densest collections of cells in the diencephalon innervating the APTA	APN	Injections of FB into the APTN	r
					Caduss91	HP26	pg86, fig2	W	3	ZI	The labelled cells were distributed essentially between two structures: the ventral lateral geniculate body and the zona incerta. Labelling particularly dense in the pars caudalis and ventralis.	APN/APN/P O	HRP/WGA-HRP inj, In cases HP25 & HP26 the uptake area was larger and spread beyond the limits of the APc, reaching the dorsal border of the pars reticulata and the posterior thalamic nucleus. Case HP26 illustrateS the overall afferent input to the APc.	r
			1	1	Caduss91	control 5a	pg93	W	1	ZI	a tracer (WGA?) deposit restricted to the zona incerta	APN	induced sparse cellular and terminal labeling in the lateral part of the caudal APc	a
ZI	SC	3	3	2	Cad85	Lrge	pg669, fig3, table1	H	3	ZI	The majority of cells (in the diencephalon) were located in the zona incerta (fig3A). Their cell bodies were usually packed together and densely labelled... evenly distributed along the rostrocaudal axis of the zona incerta.	SC	In three cases (Rc14, RC15, RC30), diffusion areas of the enzyme covered much of the dorsoventral extent of the SC. Dark core of the reaction product involved SGI, SAI, SGP and in one case SO, HRP injections	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	3	ZI	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... the zona incerta. Greatest numbers of labelled cells seen ipsilaterally in dorsal and ventral subdivisions of the parabrachial nucleus and the zona incerta.	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of the midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
			2	1	Araki84	a	pg438, fig3	H	2	ZI	distinct neurons labelled by retrograde transport were seen in the ... zona incerta. Labelled cells in the ZI were located in the ventrolateral portion along the cerebral peduncle.	SC	HRP injections were restricted to the SC and did not involve adjacent cell groups such as the pretectal nuclei or the dorsolateral part of the central grey. They occupied all layers of the SC.	r
			1	2	Drug&Syk84	a	pg251	H	1	ZI	HRP +ve cells	SC	HRP inj in deep and med layers	r
					Taylor86	A	pg134, fig2	H	1	FF	labelled cells were seen only ipsilaterally to the injected SC in the ... forebrain field H, contained only a very few labelled cells	SC/SC/PAG /MRN	p134: in 12 animals injected with HRP into superficial layers and in most cases deep layers, in some animals small spread into the dorsal portion of the midbrain reticular formation and the periaqueductal gray ipsilaterally.	r
			x	3	Roman85	abstract		-1	ZI			SC		
					Kim92	abstract		-1	ZI			SC		
					Nicolleis92	abstract		-1	ZI	ventral subregion		SC		
ZI	SCH	0	0	1	Chib&Mura85	22	table1	W	0	ZI		MPO/PV/S CH	WGA-HRP inj	r
ZI	VISL	2	2	1	Car&Rie87	R129	pg207, fig2	x	2	ZI	neurons scattered in zona incerta	VISL	21 WGA-HRP inj into 18a, lack of labelling in LGd, extensive labelling in LP	r
ZI	VISM	2	2	1	Car&Rie87	R126	pg209, fig4	x	2	ZI	neurons scattered within the zona incerta	VISM	19 WGA-HRP inj into 18b	r
ZI	ATN	2	2	3	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	ZI	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	x	2	ZI	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the ... zona incerta ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralamina complex	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	ZI	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ... zona incerta	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	ZI	No labeled cells were found in the vLG, ZI or mammillary bodies	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
ZI	LD	2	2	3	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	ZI	The vLG and ZI both contained a few labeled cells, as did the dorsal portion of R rostrally adjacent to the injection site.	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Gerf82	ld_inj_r	pg296	x	2	ZI	Additionally, labelled perikarya were observed bilaterally in the ... zona incerta ...	LD	WGA-HRP was applied iontophoretically into the laterodorsal thalamic nucleus. The injection site appeared to be confined to this nucleus with minimal spread to the adjacent intralamina complex	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	ZI	Within the thalamus, labeled neurons were seen in the ... zona incerta	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	ZI	No labeled cells were found in the vLG, ZI or mammillary bodies	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
ZI	LGd	0	0	1	Pas82c	D	pg412, fig3	H	0	ZI	No labelling was found in the ZI after LGBd cases	LGd	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
ZI	PF	2	2	1	Corn&Phil88b	f3	pg142, fig3	W	2	ZI	Towards caudal limit of label in Rt, cells found in ventral & medial regions where they became continuous with cells in zona incerta. Labeled cells in ZI fewer & much less heavily stained than those in reticularis.	PF	In those five brains for which retrograde labelling is described in detail, the injection (WGA injections) sites were confined almost exclusively to PF.	r
			x	1	Roman85		abstract		-1	ZI		PF		
ZI	LP	c	c	1	Solo&Nomo84	b	pg141, fig1,2	H	-1	ZI	Ascending projections were represented not only by neurons of PT, SC the dorsal part of LGB, & VP, but also by cells of the ventrolateral and posterior thalamic nuclei, the ventral part of LGB, zona incerta & anterior hypothalamus (ventral AHA)	LP	HRP inj into ventrocaudal zones, <of LP>	r
ZI	PO	3	3	1	Rog&Cad84	RC28	pg478, fig2,3	H	3	ZI	positive cells were located in the entire rostrocaudal extent of the zi, numerous labelled neurons were in the central and lateral part of this region, few in the most medial part, some also found in forel's field H	PO	HRP injection into pt, no reaction product detected in neighbouring structures	r
			2	1	Rog&Cad84	d	pg479, fig5	H	2	ZI	following HRP deposits into ... zi	PO	anterograde transport of the enzyme resulted in axon-terminal labeling within tp	a
ZI	LGv	2	2	2	Sugita89	a	pg201-2, fig3	W	2	ZI	Some neurons in other subcortical structures was also labeled (contralaterally): ... zona incerta	LGv	With unilateral injections of WGA-HRP into the normal LGv ...	r
					Pas82c	V	pg412, fig4	H	2	ZI	Typical large polygonal neurons of the ipsilateral zona incerta ... were consistently labelled in all LGBv cases	LGv	HRP deposits in the LGBd	r
ZI	RT	x	x	1	Berry86		abstract		-1	ZI		RT		

Limbic System Matrix.

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>			
CA1	DG	c	c	1	vGr90a	PHA19	pg518, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	DG	Near injection site. 1 or 2 labeled axons extended into strata moleculare & granulosum of dentate gyrus	a			
CA1	ENT	3	3	1	Swa.et.al81	e	pg553	F	3	CA1	In most successful experiments, at least 90% of the pyramidal cells in CA1 were doubly labeled. It was also apparent in many of these brains that virtually all cells could be labeled even when injected dye did not spread to subiculum	ENT	true blue injected into entorhinal cortex of 1 side & bisbenzamide was injected into septum of the same side.	r			
					Be78	EC4	pg254, fig4, table1	H	1	CA1	Ipsi: Field CA1 & subiculum contained labeled neurons after medial EC injection, <Table1: (Medial EC, CA1): 2; 10-20 cells.>	ENTm	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC4... HRP deposit in medial subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r			
					Be78	EC16	pg254, fig3, table1	H	1	CA1	Ipsi: After injection of lateral EC, HRP +ve cells were found mostly in stratum pyramidale of ventral 2/3 of ammonic field CA1 <Table1: (Lateral EC, CA1): 2; 10-20 cells.>	ENTI	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC16: HRP deposit in lateral subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r			
					Be78	EC14	pg254, fig2, table1	H	1	CA1	Labeled cells appeared ipsilaterally in hippocampal & subicular cortices in all cases of EC injection. <Table1: (Anterior EC, CA1): 2; 10-20 cells.>	ENT	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC14... HRP deposit in anteroventral part of entorhinal cortex.	r			
					c	5	Swa78	R106	pg704, fig21	A	-1	CA1	More temporal parts of field CA1 ...	ENTm	...however project massively & widely to both medial & lateral divisions of entorhinal area (area 28). Highest grain density is over layer IV, but scattered grains are found over most of the other levels	a	
							Swa78	R106	pg704, fig21	A	-1	CA1	More temporal parts of field CA1 ...	ENTI	...however project massively & widely to both medial & lateral divisions of entorhinal area (area 28). Highest grain density is over layer IV, but scattered grains are found over most of the other levels	a	
					vGr90a	PHA19	pg518-9, fig2	Sw81	d	pg152	F	-1	CA1	In CA1 ~90% of true blue labeled neurons contained both TB & bisbenzamide .	ENT	3 rats received TB into infralimbic area (& adjacent cortical fields) & bisbenzamide injection into entorhinal area	r
								vGr90a	PHA19	pg518-9, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	ENT	Most of labeled axons in alveus continued caudally & ventrally to form a dense terminal plexus in deep layer (VI) of caudovernal part of perirhinal cortex & layer VI of adjoining entorhinal cortex... A few labeled axons extended to superficial layers of ENT	a
								vGr90a	PL54	pg521-2, fig7	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L injections into temporal pole of CA1 (PL54) resulted in different labeling pattern to that from other CA1 injns	ENT	Near inj site fibres extended into deep layers of medial & intermediate entorhinal cortex where they appeared to terminate, predominantly in layers V-VI	a
					x	1	Swa.et.al81	abstract		-1	CA1		ENT				
CA1	PAR	2	2	1	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	CA1	Largest single projection to PAR originated in temporal 1/3 of hippocampus. The majority of labeled hippocampal pyramidal cells were in temporal 1/3 of area CA1 near border with subiculum... Few non-pyr cells in str rad & mol labeled	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r			
c	3	vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	CA1	... labeled neurons in ... Area CA1...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r						
		vGr90c	calgen	pg238	F	-1	CA1	Injs in CA1...	PAR	... labeled axons & terminal in deep layer I & layer II & III of PAR	r						
		vGr90a	PL54	pg521-2, fig7	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L injections into temporal pole of CA1 (PL54) resulted in different labeling pattern to that from other CA1 injns	PAR	Many labeled axons extended caudally through alveus to form terminal plexus in layers II-III of parasubiculum.	a						

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
CA1	POST	2	2	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	CA1	ipsilateral cortical label present in CA1... POST inj also labeled pyramidal layer neurons and a few non-pyramidal neurons in septal 1/3 of area CA1 & there were few contralaterally (compared to ipsi) labeled cells. <Fig5: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
			c	3	vGr90b	PHA18	pg173, fig8	P	-1	CA1	Injs into septal 1/3 of CA1 (PHA18)...	POST	... labeled small number of fibres in layers II-V of postsubiculum. Most fibres were found near border between POST & SUB.	a
					vGr90a	PHA19	pg518, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	POST	Major group of labeled axons extended caudally from septal CA1 inj site to subicular cortices. Dense plexus of labeled axons & terminals ... extended into neighbouring postsubiculum. Small number of contra axonal terms.	a
					vGr90a	PL46	pg520-1, fig6	P	-1	CA1	An (PHA-L) injection into splenial (occipital) 1/3 of CA1 (PL46) ...	POST	... labeled fibres & axons in ipsi ... postsubiculum ... no contra. Small number of labeled fibres extended dorsally through SUB to POST where they ended in deep layers (L. IV-VI)	a
CA1	PRE	c	c	1	Sw77	R102	pg73-4, fig9	A	-1	CA1	8 expts with injs involving septal portion of field CA1. Fig9 taken from one of those cases (R102).	PRE	caudally directed fibres which are labeled after this injection pass through & possibly terminate within subiculum & presubiculum en route to the perirhinal cortex	a
CA1	SUB	3	3	1	Swa.et.al81	PS193	pg553	F	3	CA1	more than 90% of the pyramidal cells in the rostral part of field CA1 were found to be doubly labeled.	SUBd	true blue injected into dorsal part of lateral septum & bisbenzimidazole was injected into dorsal subiculum into dorsal subiculum of same side (PS193, injs reversed: PS203)	r
			l	1	Be78	sub	pg255, table1	H	1	CA1	Control injections in subiculum labeled cells only in ammonic field CA1 & SUB presubiculum <Table1: (Subiculum, CA1); 2; 10-20 cells.>	SUB	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectroretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Subiculum...	r
			c	7	Sw77	R102	pg73-4, fig9	A	-1	CA1	8 expts with injs involving septal portion of field CA1. Fig9 taken from one of those cases (R102).	SUB	caudally directed fibres which are labeled after this injection pass through & possibly terminate within subiculum & presubiculum en route to the perirhinal cortex	a
					Swa78	R106	pg703, fig21	A	-1	CA1	More temporally placed injection, labeled fibres course more-or-less transversely to subiculum (expts R106 & R178)	SUB	CA1->SUB ... labeled fibres course more-or-less transversely to subiculum (R106).	a
					Swa78	R172	pg703, fig21	A	-1	CA1	Injections into septal 1/3 of field CA1 (R172)...	SUB	CA1->SUB resembles mossy fibre system... label a projection (~ the width of the injection site) that courses ventrally for some considerable distance after reaching subiculum.	a
					Sw77	R102	pg73-4, fig9	A	-1	CA1	We have several expts with injs involving only temporal half of field CA1 (R171 & R178).	SUB	In these cases a caudally-directed projection to a limited part of subiculum is clearly labeled. Unlike septally placed injections, subicular proj from temporal CA1 does not continue past SUB. Most of labeling in deeper stratum moleculare, some in pyr	a
					vGr90a	PL46	pg520-1, fig6	P	-1	CA1	An (PHA-L) injection into splenial (occipital) 1/3 of CA1 (PL46) ...	SUB	... labeled fibres & axons in ipsi subiculum ... no contra. Most labeled axons extended ... to form dense term plexus in splenial part of SUB Extended through all layers of splenial SUB except supficial L. I. Limited in sep-temp extent	a
					vGr90a	PHA19	pg518, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	SUB	Major group of labeled axons extended ... to subicular cortices. Dense plexus of labeled axons & terminals present in septal pole of subiculum ... very circumscribed in sep-temp extent. Radially... filled entire SUB (except L. Ia), bilat.	a
					vGr90a	PL54	pg521-2, fig7	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L injections into temporal pole of CA1 (PL54) resulted in different labeling pattern to that from other CA1 injs	SUB	No commissural axons labeled. Locally injs in temporal pole of CA1 labeled large plexus of axons & terminals in temporal pole of subiculum, sep-temp extent equalled that of inj site.	a
			x	1	Amaral91	abstract				CA1		SUB		
CA1	ACA	0	0	1	Ja91	CA1	pg577	P	0	CA1	PHA-L Injections in dorsal part of CA1... <No descriptions of inj site, rely on fig3>	PL/ORBm/1 LA/ACA	... did not result in any labeling in prefrontal cortex.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>		
CA1	ILA	c	c	4	Ja91	CA5	pg578-80, fig4	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L Injection labeled pyramidal cells, their dendrites with profuse branching in strata radiatum & lacunosum-moleculare & their axons in stratum oriens.	ILA	<No mention in text, probably because IL 'not part of prefrontal cortex'. Label shown on fig4>	a		
					Sw81	c	pg151-2, fig2	A	-1	CA1	Each small amino acid injection (n=8) which involved temporal parts of CA1, but not subiculum,...	ILA	... gave rise to terminal labeling in infralimbic area & that silver grains were found predominantly over layers I & V.	a		
					vGr90a	PHA19	pg518-20, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	ILA	A small number of labeled axons extended to taenia tecta & caudoventral part of infraradiata cortex (IRa-alpha) <ILA???	a		
					vGr90a	PL54	pg521-2, fig7	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L injections into temporal pole of CA1 (PL54) resulted in different labeling pattern to that from other CA1 injns	ILA	Large number of labeled fibres ... split into 3 groups: 2nd group extended rostrally to terminate in taenia tecta & infraradiata cortex, where labeled terminals were present in all layers of IRa-alpha cortex & in deep layers of IRb-alpha cortex	a		
					0	1	Ja91	CA1	pg577	P	0	CA1	PHA-L Injections in dorsal part of CA1... <No descriptions of inj site, rely on fig3>	PL/ORBm/IA/ACA	... did not result in any labeling in prefrontal cortex.	a
CA1	PL	3	3	2	Ja91	CA5	pg578-80, fig4	P	3	CA1	PHA-L Injection labeled pyramidal cells, their dendrites with profuse branching in strata radiatum & lacunosum-moleculare & their axons in stratum oriens.	PL	most of fibre & terminal labeling present in prelimbic & medial orbital cortices. In prelimbic cortex, labeling observed throughout its entire rostrocaudal extent. In deep V & VI many labeled varicose fibres labeled... Ventral: layer II, Dorsal: deep layers	a		
					Ja89	FG3	pg337-8, fig1,2	F	3	CA1	... labeled cells found in temp part of CA1 field of Ammon's Horn & many of these distributed in pyramidal layer of CA1. Number of cells found depends on roscav lvl off inj site: Ros PL inj > sparse label, Cau PL inj > large no in CA1 & prosub	PL	In all rats with FG injected into prelimbic cortex (fig1B) ...	r		
					2	1	Zen91	f5	pg293,5, fig5,6B	W	2	CA1	Some labeled cells were also present in dysgranular insular cortex, agranular insular cortex & perirhinal cortex, predominantly ipsilaterally. <Fig5: moderate>	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	r
					1	1	Ja91	CA4	pg578	P	1	CA1	Following a slightly more caudal & ventral PHA-L injection (case CA4)... <No descriptions of inj site, rely on fig3>	PL	... weak label was present in medial orbital & prelimbic cortex.	a
					c	1	vGr90a	PL54	pg521-2, fig7	P	-1	CA1	PHA-L injections into temporal pole of CA1 (PL54) resulted in different labeling pattern to that from other CA1 injns	PL	Large number of labeled fibres ... split into 3 groups: 2nd group extended rostrally to terminate in taenia tecta & infraradiata cortex, where labeled terminals were present in all layers of IRa-alpha cortex & in deep layers of IRb-alpha cortex	a
					0	1	Ja91	CA1	pg577	P	0	CA1	PHA-L Injections in dorsal part of CA1... <No descriptions of inj site, rely on fig3>	PL/ORBm/IA/ACA	... did not result in any labeling in prefrontal cortex.	a
CA1	PRh	1	1	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	1	CA1	A few scattered cells area found in the ... hippocampal field CA1	PRh/PRhT/Ev/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERL>	r		
					c	3	Sw478	R172	pg704, fig21	A	-1	CA1	Injections into the septal 1/3 of CA1 ...	PRh	...label projection to perirhinal area rather than to entorhinal area itself. Most of labeled terminals found over layer I & deep half of field	a
							Sw77	R102	pg73-4, fig9	A	-1	CA1	8 expts with injns involving septal portion of field CA1. Fig9 taken from one of those cases (R102).	PRh	caudally directed fibres which are labeled after this injection pass through & possibly terminate within subiculum & presubiculum en route to the perirhinal cortex	a
							vGr90a	PHA19	pg518-9, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	PRh	Most of labeled axons in valvues continued caudally & ventrally to form dense terminal plexus in deep layer (VI) of caudoventral part of perirhinal cortex ... (terminal plexus approx 20 times larger than plex in ENT) V small contra term	a
					0	1	Be78	prh	table1	H	0	CA1	<Table1: (Perirhinal Ctx, CA1): 0; no labelled cells>	PRh	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Perirhinal ctx...	r
CA1	RSP	1	1	1	vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig7, obs	F	1	CA1	In dorsal hippocampus a small number of pyramidal and nonpyramidal neurons were labeled in field CA1. <density taken from fig7>	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	vGr90a	PHA19	pg518-9, fig2	P	-1	CA1	Following an injection of PHA-L into septal pole of CA1 (PHA19) ...	RSPv	... few fibres left bundle ... to retrosplenial granular b cortex where they terminated in layer II.	a
			x	2	Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract		1	CA1	septal parts	RSPd	dysgranular	
					Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract		3	CA1		RSPv	granular b	
CA3	CA1	3	3	1	Swa.et.al81	PS105	pg551, fig2	F	3	CA3	In these brains more than 2/3 of pyramidal cells in restricted parts of regio inferior were triple labeled	CA1	In some cases (PS105, PS115) dye injections into septal nuclei combined with 3rd injection (with a different dye such as Evans Blue) into either CA1 or field CA3...	r
			c	2	Swa78	DGR15	pg698, fig14	A	-1	CA3	A small injection in septal pole of field CA3 (DGR15)...	CA1	... gives rise to extensive labeling bilaterally in fields CA3 & CA1, & in proximal part of subiculum	a
					Swa78	DGR49	pg698-9, 14B	A	-1	CA3	We have 2 injections confined to field CA3 at mid-septo-temporal extent; although one of these involved CA3c & CA3b (DGR49) while other centred in subfield CA3b (DGR37)...	CA1	Label reached septal pole of Ammon's horn on both sides, but extended about 1mm further temporally on side of injection.	a
			x	1	Finn&Jeff93		abstract, stim-Xcorrel study		-1	CA3		CA1		
CA3	DG	c	c	1	Swa78	DGR15	pg698, fig14	A	-1	CA3	A small injection in septal pole of field CA3 (DGR15)...	DGpo	On ipsilateral side there is an additional projection to septal half of field CA4 & to presubiculum	a
			0	1	Swa78	DGR15	pg698, fig14	A	0	CA3	Injs confined to field CA3 were obtained in 5 expts; in 5 additional cases injected isotope had spread to involve CA1...	DGpr	CA3 does not project to the dentate gyrus. True of hilar region of CA3 (CA3c) as well as more distal subfields outside hilus of DG... No label was seen over dentate gyrus in DGR15	a
CA3	ENT	1	1	2	Swa.et.al81	a	pg552	F	1	CA3	... we have seen occasional retrogradely labeled cells within field CA3. These cells are widely scattered & even in the best case, no more than about 2% of the pyramidal cells were labeled.	ENT	After fairly large injections of either true blue or nuclear yellow into entorhinal area ...	r
					Be78	EC16	pg254, fig3, table1	H	1	CA3	Ipsi: After injection of lateral EC, HRP +ve cells were found in lesser numbers (than CA1) in stratum pyramidale of field CA3 <Table1: (Lateral EC, CA3): 1; less than 10 cells;>	ENTI	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC16: HRP deposit in lateral subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
			c	3	Sw77	RH38	pg54,71, fig5	A	-1	CA3	Findings in one brain (RH38) in which inj strictly confined to septal portion of field CA3	ENT	field CA3 appears to give a rise to a more (than -> SUB) limited projection ... to deeper layers of entorhinal cortex ...	a
					Sw77	R104/R 141	pg73	A	-1	CA3	Injections involving field CA3, middle of its septo-temporal extent (R104 & R141) ...	ENT	... there is clear evidence for a projection ... & an equally marked projection to layer IV of entorhinal cortex	a
					Swa78	R105	pg699, fig14C	A	-1	CA3	Subfield CA3a was more or less exclusively labeled by injection in experiment R105...	ENT	Injections involving intermediate part of subfield CA3a clearly label a projection to entorhinal area & parasubiculum. This is the only part of field CA3 from which this projection can be demonstrated autoradiographically.	a
			0	2	Be78	EC14	fig2, table1	H	0	CA3	<Table1: (Anterior EC, CA3): 0; no labelled cells>	ENT	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC14... HRP deposit in anteroventral part of entorhinal cortex.	r
					Be78	EC4	pg254, fig4, table1	H	0	CA3	HRP injectons of medial EC led to no cell labeling in field CA3... <Table1: (Medial EC, CA3): 0; no labelled cells>	ENTm	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC4... HRP deposit in medial subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
CA3	PAR	1	1	1	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	1	CA3	Largest single projection to PAR originated in temporal 1/3 of hippocampus... in CA2 & CA3 a few pyramidal cells were labeled also. Few non-pyr cells in str rad & mol labeled	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
			c	4	Sw77	R104/R 141	pg73	A	-1	CA3	Injections involving field CA3, middle of its septo-temporal extent (R104 & R141) ...	PAR	... there is clear evidence for a projection to a localized part of parasubiculum (ending in layers I & II)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sw77	RH38	pg54,71, fig5	A	-1	CA3	Findings in one brain (RH38) in which inj strictly confined to septal portion of field CA3	PAR	field CA3 appears to give a rise to a more (than -> SUB) limited projection ... to parasubiculum...	a
					Swa78	R105	pg699, fig14C	A	-1	CA3	Subfield CA3a was more or less exclusively labeled by injection in experiment R105...	PAR	Injections involving intermediate part of subfield CA3a clearly label a projection to entorhinal area & parasubiculum. This is the only part of field CA3 from which this projection can be demonstrated autoradiographically.	a
					vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	CA3	... labeled neurons in ... Area CA3...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
CA3	PRE	c	c	2	Sw77	RH38	pg54,71, fig5	A	-1	CA3	Findings in one brain (RH38) in which inj strictly confined to septal portion of field CA3	PRE	field CA3 appears to give a rise to a more (than -> SUB) limited projection to presubiculum... In PRE transported label heaviest over layers I & III ...	a
					Swa78	DGR15	pg698, fig14	A	-1	CA3	A small injection in septal pole of field CA3 (DGR15)...	PRE	On ipsilateral side there is an additional projection to septal half of field CA4 & to presubiculum	a
			0	1	Swa78	DGR49	pg698-9, 14B	A	0	CA3	We have 2 injections confined to field CA3 at mid-septo-temporal extent; although one of these involved CA3c & CA3b (DGR49) while other centred in subfield CA3b (DGR37)...	PRE	No projection to the presubiculum was identified	a
CA3	SUB	c	c	4	Swa78	R105	pg699, fig14C	A	-1	CA3	Injections in the dorsal part of the temporal part of CA3 (R105, R171, THR2)	SUBv	terminal fields do not include septal pole of hippocampus but for the most part are confined to temporal half of Ammon's horn & ventral subiculum	a
					Sw77	RH38	pg54,71, fig5	A	-1	CA3	Findings in one brain (RH38) in which inj strictly confined to septal portion of field CA3	SUB	Large numbers of silver grains can be seen over deep half of stratum moleculare of subiculum & to a lesser extent among pyramidal cell somata themselves. Projection essentially uncrossed.	a
					Swa78	DGR15	pg698, fig14	A	-1	CA3	A small injection in septal pole of field CA3 (DGR15)...	SUB	... gives rise to extensive labeling bilaterally in fields CA3 & CA1, & in proximal part of subiculum	a
					Swa78	DGR49	pg698-9, 14B	A	-1	CA3	We have 2 injections confined to field CA3 at mid-septo-temporal extent; although one of these involved CA3c & CA3b (DGR49) while other centred in subfield CA3b (DGR37)...	SUB	Mid-septo-temporal part of subiculum also labeled	a
			0	1	Be78	sub	table1	H	0	CA3	<Table1: (Subiculum, CA3): 0; no labelled cells>	SUB	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Subiculum...	r
CA3	ACA	0	0	1	Fe87	a	pg422, fig1,2	W	0	CA3	No labeled cells were found in other parts of ipsilateral hippocampal formation (eg: DG, CA4, CA3)	ACA/MOs/ PL	following unilateral inj of WGA-HRP into medial prefrontal cortex, enzyme spread over medial precentral, anterior cingulate & prelimbic areas but bot into infralimbic area.	r
CA3	PL	0	0	1	Fe87	a	pg422, fig1,2	W	0	CA3	No labeled cells were found in other parts of ipsilateral hippocampal formation (eg: DG, CA4, CA3)	ACA/MOs/ PL	following unilateral inj of WGA-HRP into medial prefrontal cortex, enzyme spread over medial precentral, anterior cingulate & prelimbic areas but bot into infralimbic area.	r
CA3	PRh	0	0	1	Be78	prh	table1	H	0	CA3	<Table1: (Perirhinal Ctx, CA3): 0; no labelled cells>	PRh	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Perirhinal ctx...	r
CA3	RSP	x	x	1	Pakhomova & Akopian85	abstract		-1	CA3		RSP			
DG	CA1	c	c	1	Swa78	DGR22	pg693-4, fig9,10,11	A	-1	DGpo	series of 8 expts: heavily labeled cells at different lvls along sep-tem extent of CA4, no apparent involvement of pyramidal cells in CA3c; granule & molecular layers of DG also labeled, some cases with SUB & CA1 (used ctrls in DGgr, DGmol, SUB, CA1)	CA1	Contra: to inj site in DGR22 (fig11) silver grains distributed over septal 1/2 of both blades of dentate gyrus, over fields CA4, through CA1 & over a restricted portion of the subiculum. Ipsi: label over same regions but extended ~1mm more temp in each	a
DG	CA3	c	c	4	Swa78	ext	pg684-6, fig2	T	-1	DG	Timm's sulfide silver stain labeled characteristic endings of mossy fibres upon large, thorn-like spines on proximal dendrites of pyramids in CA3 & CA4.	CA3	It is evident that suprapyramidal bundle extends across entire medio-lateral extent of field CA3 with exception of narrow transition zone (~100-120 μm wide, CA2)	s

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Swa78	RH23	pg686-92, fig5,6,7	A	-1	DGlb-sg	33 experiments in which 3H-amino acid injs, covered virtually every part of DG <Fig7: Injections into CA1 as well as DG but only labeling mossy fibre system>. Most temporal segment of inner blade (RH23)...	CA3	... fibres appear to be relatively short (no more than 0.5mm in length) & transversely orientated, to a first approx.	a
					Swa78	R107	pg686-92, fig5,6,7	A	-1	DGpr	33 experiments in which 3H-amino acid injs, covered virtually every part of DG <Fig7: Injections into CA1 as well as DG but only labeling mossy fibre system>. Over most of temp 1/3 of HIP (R107)	CA3	... mossy fibres that arise from inner blade follow a gentle arching course with a slight temporal inclination	a
					Swa78	DGR10	pg686-92, fig5,6,7	A	-1	DGlb-sg	33 experiments in which 3H-amino acid injs, covered virtually every part of DG <Fig7: Injections into CA1 as well as DG but only labeling mossy fibre system>. Injections confined to septal 1/4 of inner blade (eg. DGR10)...	CA3	Initially, mossy fibres course transversely (slight rostral inclination) through CA3. As field CA1 approached fibres turn abruptly toward temp pole of HIP & course ~2mm in plane le to lat border of CA1, separated from it by narrow region (CA2).	a
DG	POST	c	c	2	Swa78	DGR57	pg694, fig9,10	A	-1	DGpo	CA4: 8 expts. Injections into middle part of field CA4, about 5mm from septal pole of hippocampus (DGR57)...	POST	...result in labeling of fibres throughout septal 1/3 of dentate gyrus & Ammon's Horn on side contra to inj. Ipsi to inj;all but temporal pole of DG & CA labeled together with subiculum & adjoining POST & dorsal PRE.	a
					Swa78	DGR22	pg693-4, fig9,10,11	A	-1	DGpo	series of 8 expts: heavily labeled cells at different lvls along sep-tem extent of CA4, no apparent involvement of pyramidal cells in CA3c; granule & molecular layers of DG also labeled, some cases with SUB & CA1 (used cntrls in DGgr, DGmol, SUB, CA1)	POST	Ipsi: some labeled fibres extended caudally into postsubiculum & adjoining dorsal part of presubiculum	a
DG	PRE	c	c	3	Swa78	DGR22	pg693-4, fig9,10,11	A	-1	DGpo	series of 8 expts: heavily labeled cells at different lvls along sep-tem extent of CA4, no apparent involvement of pyramidal cells in CA3c; granule & molecular layers of DG also labeled, some cases with SUB & CA1 (used cntrls in DGgr, DGmol, SUB, CA1)	PRE	Ipsi: some labeled fibres extended caudally into postsubiculum & adjoining dorsal part of presubiculum	a
					Swa78	DGR57	pg694, fig9,10	A	-1	DGpo	CA4: 8 expts. Injections into middle part of field CA4, about 5mm from septal pole of hippocampus (DGR57)...	PRE	...result in labeling of fibres throughout septal 1/3 of dentate gyrus & Ammon's Horn on side contra to inj. Ipsi to inj;all but temporal pole of DG & CA labeled together with subiculum & adjoining POST & dorsal PRE.	a
					Swa78	RH10	pg695, fig10E	A	-1	DGpo	Extreme temporal pole of field CA4 (together with adjoining parts of DG) injected in expts RH10, 19 & 23.	PRE	In each of these brains transported label restricted to temporal side of blade of dentate & extreme temporal portion of Ammon's horn, or subiculum & of presubiculum of both sides	a
DG	SUB	c	c	3	Swa78	DGR22	pg693-4, fig9,10,11	A	-1	DGpo	series of 8 expts: heavily labeled cells at different lvls along sep-tem extent of CA4, no apparent involvement of pyramidal cells in CA3c; granule & molecular layers of DG also labeled, some cases with SUB & CA1 (used cntrls in DGgr, DGmol, SUB, CA1)	SUB	Contra: to inj site in DGR22 (fig11) silver grains distributed over septal 1/2 of both blades of dentate gyrus, over fields CA4, through CA1 & over a restricted portion of the subiculum. Ipsi: label over same regions but extended ~1mm more temp in each	a
					Swa78	DGR57	pg694, fig9,10	A	-1	DGpo	CA4: 8 expts. Injections into middle part of field CA4, about 5mm from septal pole of hippocampus (DGR57)...	SUB	...result in labeling of fibres throughout septal 1/3 of dentate gyrus & Ammon's Horn on side contra to inj. Ipsi to inj;all but temporal pole of DG & CA labeled together with subiculum & adjoining POST & dorsal PRE.	a
					Swa78	RH10	pg695, fig10E	A	-1	DGpo	Extreme temporal pole of field CA4 (together with adjoining parts of DG) injected in expts RH10, 19 & 23.	SUB	In each of these brains transported label restricted to temporal side of blade of dentate & extreme temporal portion of Ammon's horn, or subiculum & of presubiculum of both sides	a
DG	ACA	0	0	1	Fe87	a	pg422, fig1,2	W	0	DG	No labeled cells were found in other parts of ipsilateral hippocampal formation (eg: DG, CA4, CA3)	ACA/MOs/PL	following unilateral inj of WGA-HRP into medial prefrontal cortex, enzyme spread over medial precentral, anterior cingulate & prelimbic areas but bot into infralimbic area.	r
DG	PL	0	0	1	Fe87	a	pg422, fig1,2	W	0	DG	No labeled cells were found in other parts of ipsilateral hippocampal formation (eg: DG, CA4, CA3)	ACA/MOs/PL	following unilateral inj of WGA-HRP into medial prefrontal cortex, enzyme spread over medial precentral, anterior cingulate & prelimbic areas but bot into infralimbic area.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
ENT	CA1	3	3	1	Wi88	c1	pg194, fig1,2A	P	3	ENTl	In case 1, inj site involves rostral & most lateral part of LEA, close to rhinal sulcus (Fig1). Majority of immunoreactive neurons are found in layers II & III & a small number are labeled in layer IV. <no figs of inj sites>	CA1	In hippocampus, terminal labeling is restricted to CA1 & subiculum & is predominantly present in the inner 1/2 of the molecular layer. <Fig2A: mod/dense>	a
			2	1	Wi88	c4	pg194-5, fig1,2B	P	2	ENTl	In a 4th rat, inj placed approx 1mm caudal to case1, in similar medlat posn. Immunoreactive neurons are found in layers II & III of LEA. <no figs of inj sites>	CA1	A labeled terminal field is further present in molecular layer of CA1, predominantly in its inner 1/2, but labeling weaker than that in FD <Fig2B: moderate>	a
			c	4	Wi88	c3	pg194, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	Inj site centred in layers II & III of LEA, slightly caudal to that of case2 (fig1) <no figs of inj sites>	CA1	Terminal labeling is prominent in the inner half of molecular layers of CA1 & adjacent part of subiculum.	a
					Wi88	c5-7	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	CA1	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a
					Ste&Sco76	H1	pg355, fig7	H	-1	ENT	HRP reaction product found exclusively in cells of layer III, particularly in lateral entorhinal area & these were labeled bilaterally.	CA1	In 2 cases (H1, 24 hrs survival) inj centered in CA1 region of regio superior, relatively distant from CA1/CA2 transition (in both cases, no evidence of spread of HRP into strat mole of fascia dentata.	r
	Wi88	c8	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTm	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	CA1	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a				
ENT	DG	3	3	1	Wi88	c4	pg194-5, fig1,2B	P	3	ENTl	In a 4th rat, inj placed approx 1mm caudal to case1, in similar medlat posn. Immunoreactive neurons are found in layers II & III of LEA. <no figs of inj sites>	DG	this inj results in heavy labeling in outer 1/3 of molecular layer of FD. <Fig2B: dense>	a
			2	1	Ru88	VPI	pg509, fig5	H	2	ENTl	Cells within area vl were always labeled, whereas no cells were labeled on lateral cortical surface.	DG	Ventral pole injections. <HRP inj into DG>	r
			1	1	Ru88	VPI	pg509, fig5	H	1	ENTm	In addition a sparse labeling of area vm neurons was obtained but only within its caudal half	DG	Ventral pole injections. <HRP inj into DG>	r
			c	9	Ru88	5exp	pg509	L	-1	ENT	In remaining five experiments all three subdivisions (dl+vl+vm) sustained damage.	DG	simultaneous lesion of areas dl, vl & vm... Terminal degeneration occurred throughout dentate ST axis & was confined to outer 1/3 of molecular layer. Debris heaviest over suprapyramidal limb, lighter in infrapyramidal, sp-nonexistent wher 2 limbs unite	a
					Ru88	DPI	pg509, fig5	H	-1	ENT	... entorhinal neurons were labeled in dorsal 1/3 of area dl. In any given coronal section 1-8 labeled cells observed. Nearly every section contained labeled cells, indicative of projs originating throughout roscou axis of dl. No cells in ventral 1/2	DG	Following HRP deposits in the dorsal 1/3 of dentate gyrus...	r
					Ru88	3exp	pg509	L	-1	ENTl	in 11 cases only 3 lesions were so confined (to 1 cytoarchitectonic subdiv); all of them were within area dl. Ventral 2/3s of area dl excised leaving small region of intact tissue just ventral to rhinal fissure.	DG	Entire dorsal 1/2 of dentate gyrus displayed a degeneration pattern characteristic for area 28-1, while ventral 1/2 of DG was free of degeneration. Also clear in other 2 cases	a
					Ru88	MST	pg509, fig5	H	-1	ENTl	All 5 inj labeled neurons within area vl. Labeled cells confined to caulat quad of vl. In 3 of 5 cases additional labeled seen in dl. dl cells found at all roscou levels.	DG	Mid-ST injections <HRP inj into DG>	r
					Ru88	2exp	pg509	L	-1	ENTl/ENTm	In two cases lesions simultaneously involved areas vl & vm, with little damage to area dl.	DG	Silver grains were dense within the ventral 1/3 of dentate gyrus. density declined markedly at mid-ST levels & could not be found in dorsal 1/3.	a
	Wi88	c3	pg194, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	Inj site centred in layers II & III of LEA, slightly caudal to that of case2 (fig1) <no figs of inj sites>	DG	In addition a few labeled fibres are present in the outer 1/3 of the molecular layer of the FD	a				
	Wi88	c5-7	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	DG	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a				

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Ste&Sco76	D1	pg355, fig10	H	-1	ENT	In these cases HRP reaction product found almost exclusively in callos of layer II & these cells labeled exclusively ipsilaterally. Careful searching revealed a few lightly labeled cells in layer II of contra ENT	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centred in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into strat lac-mol of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than injns of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
					Wi88	c8	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTm	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	DG	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a
			0	1	Wi88	c1	pg194, fig1,2A	P	0	ENTl	In case 1, inj site involves rostral & most lateral part of LEA, close to rhinal sulcus (Fig1). Majority of immunoreactive neurons are found in layers II & III & a small number are labeled in layer IV. <no figs of inj sites>	DG	No label is present in the FD.	a
			x	4	Wys81	abstract			-1	ENTl		DG		
					Wys81	abstract			-1	ENTm		DG		
					Thomas84	abstract, orthdrom stim			-2	ENT		DG		
					Kohler85b	abstract			-1	ENT	{5,6}	DG	molecular layer	
ENT	PAR	2	2	2	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	ENTm	... entorhinal cortex a number of labeled cell bodies, mainly in layer III, with a few cells in layer VI f the MEA & LEA. Contralateral entorhinal cortex displayed labeled cells only in layer III.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
					vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	ENTl	... entorhinal cortex a number of labeled cell bodies, mainly in layer III, with a few cells in layer VI f the MEA & LEA. Contralateral entorhinal cortex displayed labeled cells only in layer III.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
			c	3	vGr90c	CIR96	pg238	A	-1	ENT	Injs into entorhinal cortex (CIR96)...	PAR	... resulted in a label in layer I of PAR.	a
					vGr90c	PL61	pg238	P	-1	ENT	Injs into ENT, A PHA-L inj (P-L61)...	PAR	... resulted in a dense plexus of labeled axons & terminals in superficial layer I	r
					vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	ENT	... labeled neurons in entorhinal...projection was bilateral.	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
			x	1	Koh86	abstract			-1	ENTm		PAR		
ENT	POST	1	1	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	1	ENT	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... entorhinal... cortices... In caudal ENT, neuronal cells bodies labeled in layers II & III <Fig5: sparse>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
			c	1	vGr90b	CIR105	pg174, fig8	A	-1	ENT	Injs of the entorhinal cortex (CIR105)...	POST	...resulted in label mainly in layer I of postsubiculum	a
ENT	PRE	c	c	2	vGr90c	CIR96	pg233	A	-1	ENT	Injs in entorhinal cortex (CIR96)...	PRE	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in layer I of presubiculum.	a
					vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	ENT	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in ... entorhinal ctx... In caudal ENT, labeled cells restricted to layer IV with a few cells also in layer VI but more rostrally some cells also labeled in layers III & V. <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
			x	2	Koh86	abstract			-1	ENTm		PRE		
					Kohler88	abstract			-1	ENTl	{2a&2b}, {3}	PRE		
ENT	SUB	c	c	7	Ru88	5exp	pg509	L	-1	ENT	In remaining five experiments all three subdivisions (dl+vl+vm) sustained damage.	SUB	Degeneration also apparent within plexiform of subiculum.	a
					Ru88	2exp	pg509	L	-1	ENTl/ENTm	In two cases lesions simultaneously involved areas vl & vm, with little damage to area dl.	SUBv	Degeneration was also evident in plexiform layer of ventral subiculum.	a
					Ru88	Vsub	pg509	H	-1	ENTl	... labeled both layer II & layer III neurons throughout area vl.	SUBv	Ventral subicular injections <HRP>	r
					Wi88	c1	pg194, fig1,2A	P	-1	ENTl	In case 1, inj site involves rostral & most lateral part of LEA, close to rhinal sulcus (Fig1). Majority of immunoreactive neurons are found in layers II & III & a small number are labeled in layer IV. <no figs of inj sites>	SUB	In hippocampus, terminal labeling is restricted to CA1 & subiculum & is predominantly present in the inner 1/2 of the molecular layer. <Fig2A: not clear>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Wi88	c3	pg194, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	Inj site centred in layers II & III of LEA, slightly caudal to that of case2 (fig1) <no figs of inj sites>	SUB	Terminal labeling is prominent in the inner half of molecular layers of CA1 & adjacent part of subiculum.	a
					Wi88	c5-7	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTl	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	SUB	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a
					Wi88	c8	pg195, fig1	P	-1	ENTm	More caudally placed injections in LEA & MEA (cases5-8) ... <no figs of inj sites>	SUB	... all result in labeling in FD, CA1 & subiculum. With exception of case 6 in which density of labeling in FD = that in CA1, the labeling in FD is more dense than in other hippocampal subfields	a
			0	1	Kos83	b	pg348-9	A	0	ENTH	Injections in areas 28, 36 or the prepiriform cortex ...	SUB	... did not produce a pattern of terminal labeling in subiculum similar to that observed following area 35 injections <This does not necessarily mean that there was no labeling???	a
			x	2	Koh86 Kohler88	abstract abstract		-1	1	ENTm ENTl	{individual layers}	SUB SUB		
ENT	LM	0	0	1	Shib88	lm	pg8	H	0	ENT	No labeled cells appeared after injections confined to median region of pars posterior of MM or lateral mammillary nucleus	LM	... injections confined to median region of pars posterior of MM or lateral mammillary nucleus	r
ENT	MM	2	2	2	Shib88	R323	pg8, fig1,2	W	2	ENTm	Injection of WGA-HRP involving layers I-III of medial entorhinal area throughout its rostrocaudal extent...	MMl	... anterogradely labeled fibres seen to travel through fimbria hippocampi & postcommissural fornix & to terminate ipsilaterally within ventrolateral region of pars lateralis of MM. 2 spots. Faintly labeled terminals also found contra	r
					Shib88	R233	pg7, fig1,2	H	2	ENTm	Many retrogradely labeled cells were seen ipsilaterally in layer III of medial 1/2 of entorhinal cortex. A small number were seen contralaterally in corresponding part	MM	In case R233 (HRP) injection covered unilaterally almost all parts of rostral 1/2 of medial mammillary nucleus.	r
			1	2	Shib88	R233	pg7-8	H	1	ENTl	Few labeled cells seen in other regions of entorhinal cortex	MM	In case R233 (HRP) injection covered unilaterally almost all parts of rostral 1/2 of medial mammillary nucleus.	r
					Shib89	R309	pg438-9	W	1	ENTm	A small number of labeled cells were noted ipsilaterally in layer III of medial entorhinals area.	MMl/MMl/ MMm/SUM	Following an injection into the more lateral region within rostral MM (R309) ...Injection was centred in pars lateralis of rostral MM, spreading to dorsal premammillary nucleus & slightly to supramammillary nucleus parse medialis of MM	r
			c	1	Shib88	mml	pg8	H	-1	ENTm	... labeled cells were seen in layer III of medial 1/2 of ipsilateral entorhinal cortex	MMl	After injections limited to ventrolateral region of pars lateralis of MM...	r
			0	1	Shib88	mmm	pg8	H	0	ENT	No labeled cells appeared after...	MMme	... injections confined to median region of pars posterior of MM or lateral mammillary nucleus	r
ENT	ACA	1	1	2	Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	1	ENT	structures that projected to all areas of cingulate cortex: entorhinal cortex, (1-10 somata in a 40µm thick section)	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
					Fin84	c74	pg477, fig4, table1	W	1	ENT	The entorhinal cortex had labeled cells in three cases of posterior or anterior injections	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
ENT	PL	1	1	1	Ja89	FG3	pg337,339, fig2	F	1	ENT	group of retrogradely labeled neurons overlapping border between perirhinal & entorhinal cortices could be observed in all injected animals.	PL	In all rats with FG injected into prelimbic cortex (fig1B) ...	r
ENT	PRh	2	2	1	De83	RS1	pg178, fig12	H	2	ENTl	labels cortical cells in ... dorsal lateral entorhinal cortex ventral to the injection site	PERI	A small superficially placed injection of HRP centered on the ventral bank of the rostral perirhinal area	r
			x	1	Kohler88	abstract		3	3	ENTl	{individual layers}	PERI		
ENT	RSP	1	1	2	Fin84	c67	pg477, fig2, table1	W	1	ENT	The entorhinal cortex had labeled cells in three cases of posterior or anterior injections	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	1	ENT	structures that projected to all areas of cingulate cortex: entorhinal cortex, (1-10 somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
			x	1	Wysv&vGr9 2a	abstract		1	1	ENT	caudal	RSPd	dysgranular	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
ENT	MD	1	1	1	Groene88	rh8159	pg393,421, fig8,9	W	1	ENTI	Also in the periamygdaloid cortex & lateral entorhinal area, a small but consistent number of retrogradely labeled multipolar neurons is observed... in present study ret-lab cells found in deep layers of lateral entorhinal area. (Lrg Multipolar type)	MD/MD/MH/PVT/PT	relatively large WGA-HRP injections ... RH-8159, inj located centrally in rostral MD & includes all segments, only little spread into stria medullaris, medial habenula paraventricular nucleus & caudal aspect of parataeniaal nuc.	r
			x	1	Price&Slot83	abstract		-1	ENTI		MD			
PAR	CA1	1	1	1	vGr90c	PHA35	pg234, fig4	P	1	PAR	Small injns of PHA-L were made into parasubiculum: small inj in intermediate part of parasubiculum (PHA35)	CA1	3rd group of axons... few fibres left fimbria & ended in stratum moleculare of temporal 1/3 of CA1 ... <Fig4: Not shown>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	ca1_ret	pg235-6	F	-1	PAR	... labeled cells in layers II & III of parasubiculum	CA1	Injs into temporal 1/3 of subiculum & CA1...	r
			vGr90c	CIR18	pg234	A	-1	PAR	Large inj of [3H] amino acids into parasubiculum (CIR18)	CA1	... resulted in label in ipsi: hippocampus (CA1)...	CA1		a
			0	2	Ste&Sco76	D1	pg355,357-9	H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centred in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into strat lac-mol of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than injns of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
				Ste&Sco76	H1	pg355,357-9	H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	CA1	In 2 cases (H1, 24 hrs survival) injns centred in CA1 region of regio superior, relatively distant from CA1/CA2 transition (in both cases, no evidence of spread of HRP into strat mole of fascia dentata.	r	
PAR	CA3	0	0	1	Ste&Sco76	D1	pg355,357-9	H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centred in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into strat lac-mol of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than injns of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
PAR	DG	1	1	1	Koh85	r27	pg511, fig7	P	1	PAR	rat27: centre of PHA-L inj located in subdivision b of parasubiculum. Inj site relatively well restricted & extended approximately 200µm in dorsal/ventral extent. Majority of cells confined within PAR, individual cells in deep layers of MEA & PRE stained	DG	Small rostral projection from parasubiculum can also be followed in molecular layers of both Ammon's horn & area dentata	a
			0	1	Ste&Sco76	D1	pg355,357-9	H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centred in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into strat lac-mol of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than injns of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
PAR	ENT	3	3	2	vGr90c	PHA35	pg234, fig4	P	3	PAR	Small injns of PHA-L were made into parasubiculum: small inj in intermediate part of parasubiculum (PHA35)	ENT	2nd group of fibres coursed ven to form dense fiber plexus in L. II of medial part of ipsi med entorhinal cortex (fig5F). Proj topograph organized. Contra: dense fibre plexus in L. II homotopic to inj. <Fig4: dense>	a
					Koh85	r27	pg511, fig7	P	3	PAR	rat27: centre of PHA-L inj located in subdivision b of parasubiculum. Inj site relatively well restricted & extended approximately 200µm in dorsal/ventral extent. Majority of cells confined within PAR, individual cells in deep layers of MEA & PRE stained	ENTm	large number of PHA-L stained fine varicose axons innervate layer II of medial & to a lesser extent also lateral entorhinal area Within layer II, terminals form mosaic pattern of innervation: dense areas surrounded by less dense areas. <more in paper>	a
			2	1	Donovan&Wyss83	a	pg182-6, fig2,3,4	F	2	PAR	... & resulted in labeling of neurons in all appropriate parts of subicular cortex. <Fig2,3,4: moderate>	ENT/ENT/PRh	Injections into posterior entorhinal cortex consistently labeled medial, intermediate & lateral portions of that cortex ... <Figs2,3,4 inj site seems to spread into PERL>	r
			c	3	Ste&Sco76	E	pg359	H	-1	PAR	cells in both contralateral presubiculum & parasubiculum clearly exhibited retrograde transport of HRP	ENT	2 animals received HRP injections of 0.5-0.7µl if HRP into entorhinal region of one hemisphere	r
					vGr90c	CIR18	pg234	A	-1	PAR	Large inj of [3H] amino acids into parasubiculum (CIR18)	ENT	... resulted in label in ipsi: ... entorhinal cortex. Contra: ... entorhinal cortex	a
vGr90c	CF362	pg235	F	-1	PAR	...labeled neuronal cell bodies in both ipsi & contra parasubiculum in layers II & III & in layer V to the ipsi parasubiculum	ENTm	Injs of retrograde transported tracers ... Inj in medial entorhinal cortex (CF362)	ENTm		r			
x	2	CallBled&	abstract		-1	PAR		ENTm	{2}					

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					Witt93 CallBled& Witt93	abstract		-1	PAR			ENTI	{2}	
PAR	POST	2	2	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	PAR	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... parasubiculum... but in PAR only a few neurons were labeled in external lamina. Labeled neurons confined to caudal segments of PRE & PAR. <Fig5: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
			1	1	vGr90c	PHA35	pg234, fig4	P	1	PAR	Small inj of PHA-L were made into parasubiculum: small inj in intermediate part of parasubiculum (PHA35)	POST	In postsubiculum, few fibres were present in layer V <Fig4: sparse>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	CF314	pg236	F	-1	PAR	... primarily labeled neurons in layer II of parasubiculum, but a few labeled cell bodies were present in layers III & V.	POST	Injections in postsubiculum (CF314)...	r
					vGr90c	CIR18	pg234	A	-1	PAR	Large inj of [3H] amino acids into parasubiculum (CIR18)	POST	... resulted in label in ipsi: ... postsubiculum...	a
PAR	PRE	3	3	1	vGr90c	PHA35	pg234, fig4	P	3	PAR	Small inj of PHA-L were made into parasubiculum: small inj in intermediate part of parasubiculum (PHA35)	PRE	In presubiculum, ipsi: labeled fibres formed a terminal plexus primarily in layers I & III, contra: a labeled fibres plexus was present in layers I & III with few fibres in deeper layers. <Fig4: mod/dense>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	CF330	pg236	F	-1	PAR	... arose from neurons in layer III of parasubiculum	PRE	proj to contra PAR (CF332) & presubiculum (CF330)...	r
					vGr90c	CIR18	pg234	A	-1	PAR	Large inj of [3H] amino acids into parasubiculum (CIR18)	PRE	... resulted in label in ipsi: ... presubiculum... Contra: presubiculum, ...	a
PAR	SUB	1	1	1	vGr90c	PHA35	pg234, fig4	P	1	PAR	Small inj of PHA-L were made into parasubiculum: small inj in intermediate part of parasubiculum (PHA35)	SUBv	3rd group of axons... few fibres left fimbria & ended ... in stratum moleculare of temporal 1/3 of subiculum	a
			c	2	vGr90c	sub_ret	pg235-6	F	-1	PAR	... labeled cells in layers II & III of parasubiculum	SUBv	Injs into temporal 1/3 of subiculum & CA1...	r
					vGr90c	CIR18	pg234	A	-1	PAR	Large inj of [3H] amino acids into parasubiculum (CIR18)	SUB	... resulted in label in ipsi: ... subiculum...	a
PAR	LM	3	3	1	Gonz92	lm	pg286, fig16CD,17A	W	3	PAR	main contingent of descending projections to LMN in these animals originated from ipsilateral & contralateral presubiculum & parasubiculum, particularly from contralateral presubiculum.	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
			2	1	All&Hop89	e	pg313, fig1	W	2	PAR	numerous retrogradely labeled perikarya were found mainly ipsilaterally in presubiculum & parasubiculum.	LM/LM/M M/SUM/L HA	WGA-HRP inj site located mainly in lateral mammillary nucleus with a slight involvement of lateral part of medial nucleus. In addition there was some spread from the inj site dorsally into lateral portion of SUM & lateral hypothalamus	r
PAR	MM	0	0	3	Gonz92	mm	pg279, fig3	W	0	PAR	In all animals, main descending projection to MMMN originated bilaterally from entire subicular cortex. Largest numbers of retro labeled cells found bilaterally in all layers of rosdor region of subiculum ...	MM	single ionto inj of WGA-HRP ... Inj sites depicted in fig3. repr cases into subdivisions of MM & surrounding hypothalamic regions in 8 animals. <few representative cases are wholly in MM>... inj sites that involved mainly pars medialis or pars lateralis of MMN.	r
					All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	0	PAR	no labeled cells were found in presubiculum or parasubiculum	MM/MM/S UM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
					Sw77	R133	pg68-71, fig15	A	0	PRE/PAR	From 1 experiment in which isotope inj confined to area of pre- & parasubiculum (R133) & 6 additional experiments in which these fields were involved together with one or more adjacent cortical areas.	MMme	Unlike subiculum, PRE/PAR input to the mammillary complex terminates bilaterally in both medial & lateral mammillary nuclei... pars medianus of medial mammillary nucleus does not seem to receive input from this source	a
PAR	SUM	0	0	1	All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	0	PAR	no labeled cells were found in presubiculum or parasubiculum	MM/MM/S UM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
PAR	ACA	0	0	1	Vo83	f15	pg199-200,206, fig15	H	0	PAR	HRP positive neurons were not present in areas 32, 48, 49, 29a or 18a & lateral area 17	ACA/MOs	Injs of HRP into anterior cingulate cortex. These injections also involved area 8	r
PAR	PRh	3	3	1	De83	RS9	pg184, fig16	H	3	PAR	Dense labelling of cells exhibited in posterior and ventral parasubiculum	ECT/ECT/? ??	An (HRP) injection placed more posterodorsally in the posthinal area	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
PAR	RSP	3	3	1	Vo83	f2	pg194,206, fig2	W	3	PAR	Subicular cortices contained large numbers of HRP labeled neurons including subiculum, postsubiculum, & parasubiculum. The para- & post-subiculum neurons located in internal pyramidal cell layer	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r
			2	1	Koh85	r27	pg511, fig7	P	2	PAR	rat27: centre of PHA-L inj located in subdivision b of parasubiculum. Inj site relatively well restricted & extended approximately 200µm in dorsal/ventral extent. Majority of cells confined within PAR, individual cells in deep layers of MEA & PRE stained	RSP	In addition to innervation of MEA, ventral parasubiculum & retrosplenial area e receive massive innervations by PHA-L stained fibres (fig7)	a
PAR	AD	3	3	1	vGr90c	PHA36	pg234, fig6	P	3	PAR	Inj which predominantly labeled cells in layers IV-VI of PAR (PHA36) ...	AD	gave rise to labeled terminals in rostral AD. <Fig6: dense>	a
			c	1	vGr90c	CF280	pg236	F	-1	PAR	... labeled neurons in layer VI of parasubiculum	AD	Injections in the AD nucleus (CF280)	r
PAR	AV	1	1	1	vGr90c	PHA36	pg234, fig6	P	1	PAR	Inj which predominantly labeled cells in layers IV-VI of PAR (PHA36) ...	AV	very few labeled fibres present in AV <Fig6: sparse>	a
PAR	LD	0	0	1	vGr90c	PHA36	pg234, fig6	P	0	PAR	Inj which predominantly labeled cells in layers IV-VI of PAR (PHA36) ...	LD	No labeled axons could be detected in LD	a
POST	ENT	2	2	2	vGr90b	PHA28	pg168-70, fig2	P	2	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	ENTl	Many labeled fibres coursed ventrally from POST to ... caudal ENTl & PRh Most ventrally directed fibres extended into caudal PRh/ENTl where they ended in layers IV-VI. Dense (50% of ipsi) terminal field labeled contra <Fig2: ENTl label extn from PRh, mod>	a
					Donovan& Wyss83	a	pg182-6, fig2,3,4	F	2	POST	... & resulted in labeling of neurons in all appropriate parts of subicular cortex. <Fig2,3,4: moderate>	ENT/ENT/P Rh	Injections into posterior entorhinal cortex consistently labeled medial, intermediate & lateral portions of that cortex ... <Figs2,3,4 inj site seems to spread into PERl>	r
			c	3	Sw77	R176	pg75, fig16]	A	-1	POST	After this injection (expt R162) into POST...	ENT	In addition, the postsubiculum projects bilaterally to the entorhinal cortex & to the parasubiculum... predominantly distributed to layer I	a
					vGr90b	CF322	pg171	F	-1	POST	... labeled neurons in layers II, III, & V of ipsilateral & contralateral postsubiculum	ENTl	Injections into lateral entorhinal cortex (CF322)	r
					vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	ENT	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in ipsi ...caudal entorhinal ... cortices. Contralateral label predominantly confined to caudal entorhinal & perirhinal cortex.	a
POST	PAR	2	2	1	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	POST	Similarly in postsubiculum cells were labeled in layer V	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
			c	4	Sw77	R176	pg75, fig16]	A	-1	POST	After this injection (expt R162) into POST...	PAR	In addition, the postsubiculum projects bilaterally to the entorhinal cortex & to the parasubiculum... predominantly distributed to layer I	a
					vGr90b	CF332	pg171	F	-1	POST	...cell bodies were labeled in layers II, V & VI of postsubiculum, majority in layer V.	PAR	Following injections into ... parasubiculum (CF332)	r
					vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	PAR	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in ipsi ... parasubiculum...	a
					vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	POST	... labeled neurons in ... postsubiculum...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
POST	PRE	2	2	1	vGr90b	PHA28	pg168-70, fig2	P	2	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	PRE	Many labeled fibres coursed ventrally from postsubiculum to presubiculum... In caudal PRE, axons arborised extensively in small terminal patch in superficial layers (II & III) & larger terminal field in deeper (V-IV)... <Fig2: mod>	a
			c	3	vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	POST	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in ... postsubiculum ... In POST neurons were labeled in layers V & VI, near inj site, a few labeled cells were found in layer II. <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					vGr90b	CF328	pg171	F	-1	POST	...cell bodies were labeled in layers II, V & VI of postsubiculum, majority in layer V.	PRE	Following injections into presubiculum (CF328)	r
					vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	PRE	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in ipsi ... presubiculum...	a
POST	LM	1	1	2	vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	LM	... lightly labeled lateral mammillary nucleus	a
					vGr90b	PHA28	pg168,71, fig2	P	1	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	LM	...labeled a few axons that passed through fimbria/fornix to innervate mammillary bodies. Labeled axons terminated specifically in lateral mammillary nucleus ipsilateral to injection. <Fig2: sparse>	a
			0	1	All&Hop89	h	pg314, fig4	W	0	SUB/POST	cases in which WGA-HRP injns into subicular complex did not involve PRE & PAR ...	LM	... showed no anterograde labeling in the lateral mammillary nucleus.	a
POST	ACA	0	0	1	Vo83	f15	pg199-200,206, fig15	H	0	POST	HRP positive neurons were not present in areas 32, 48, 49, 29a or 18a & lateral area 17	ACA/MOs	Injs of HRP into anterior cingulate cortex. These injections also involved area 8	r
POST	PRh	3	3	1	vGr90b	PHA28	pg168-70, fig2	P	3	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	PRh	Many labeled fibres coursed ventrally from POST to ... caudal ENTI & PRh. Most ventrally directed fibres extended into caudal PRh/ENTI where they ended in layers IV-VI. Dense (50% of ipsi) terminal field labeled contra <Fig2: dense>	a
			c	1	vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	PRh	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in ipsi ... perirhinal cortices. Contralateral label predominantly confined to caudal entorhinal & perirhinal cortex.	a
POST	RSP	3	3	2	Vo83	f2	pg194,206, fig2	W	3	POST	Subicular cortices contained large numbers of HRP labeled neurons including subiculum, postsubiculum, & parasubiculum. The para- & post-subiculum neurons located in internal pyramidal cell layer	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig7, obs	F	3	POST	labeled neurons ipsilaterally in ... postsubiculum. <density taken from fig7> Discussion: Rga is primarily innervated by the AD, LD, POST, caudal Rgb and contralateral Rga	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
			2	3	Fin84	c67	pg477-81, fig2, table1	W	2	POST	Topographically organized. Injs into pos. part of area 29 label cells in posterior PRE, POST and posteroventral part of SUB proper; Injs into ant area 29 labeled cells in dorsal SUB & PRE more anteriorly. Labeling most extensive after posterior 29 injs	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					vGr90b	PHA28	pg168, fig2	P	2	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	RSPv-a	Labeled axons extended from postsubiculum into retrosplenial granular cortex. In Rga, few fibres could be seen running through layer I, arborizing occasionally, apparently synapsing in layer I ... <Fig2: sp/mod>	a
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	2	POST	caudal to injection, neurons were labelled in {6} of Rdg, areas 18b, 17, Rga and postsubicular cortices	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
			c	7	Sw77	R176	pg75, fig16]	A	-1	POST	After this injection (expt R162) into POST...	RSP	There is distinct labeling of a projection to Rose & Woolsey's retrosplenial & cingulate areas (where it is mainly distributed to the molecular layer). <Fig16: label only present in RSP>	a
					vGr90b	CIR29	pg168	A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	RSPv	... resulted in anterogradely transported label in ipsi Rga, Rgb, ...cortices.	a
					vGr90b	CF274	pg171	F	-1	POST	... labeled neurons in layer V of postsubiculum.	RSPv-bc	Injections of fluorescent tracers into Rga (CF310) or Rgb(CF274)	r
					vGr90b	PHA28	pg168-70, fig2	P	-1	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	RSPv-bc	Labeled axons extended from POST into retrosplenial granular cortex. In Rga, few fibres... extending into Rgb where fibres coursed rostrally in L. I & II, synapsing there. Most fibres for RSP coursed through cingulum to innervate layers I & II <more...>	a
					vGr90d	PHA28	pg600	P	-1	POST	Anterograde injections into postsubiculum (PHA-L?)	RSPv-a	labeled axons could be seen in {1},{3,4,5}	a
					vGr92	PHA28	pg203	P	-1	POST	PHA-L injections into postsubiculum	RSPd	labelled axons seen in {1,3,4,5}	a
					vGr90b	CF310	pg171	F	-1	POST	... labeled neurons in layer V of postsubiculum.	RSPv-a	Injections of fluorescent tracers into Rga (CF310) or Rgb(CF274)	r
x			3		Wyss&vGr9		abstract		3	POST	temporal	RSPv	granular a	

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					2a Wyss&vGr9	abstract		1	POST			RSPd	dysgranular	
					2a Wyss&vGr9	abstract		3	POST	septal		RSPv	granular b	
POST	AD	3	3	1	vGr90b	PHA28 pg168,71, fig2,4		P	3	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	AD	Other labeled axons coursed around stria terminalis to rostral thalamic nuclei & terminated in 2 dense terminal fields in lateral dorsal nucleus, & a dense patch in anterodorsal nucleus <Fig4: mod/dense>	a
				2	1	Sek&Zyo84 H79f11 pg250, fig11		H	2	POST	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
				c	1	vGr90b CIR29 pg168		A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	AD	...labeled anterodorsal & laterodorsal nuclei of thalamus	a
POST	AV	1	1	1	vGr90b	PHA28 pg168,71, fig2,4		P	1	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	AV	Further, in anteroventral nucleus a very small terminal field was present anterior dorsally... <Fig4: sparse>	a
POST	LD	3	3	2	Sw77	R162 pg71, fig16		A	3	POST	Studied in 2 experiments with injections confined to this area (postsubiculum) ... Case R162	LD	The primary descending connections of this field are by way of the posterior thalamic radiation to a terminal field within a restricted region of lateral dorsal & lateral posterior nuclei <fig16: mod/dense>	a
					vGr90b	PHA28 pg168,71, fig2,4		P	3	POST	Injections of PHA-L made into postsubiculum. Following a small injection in middle of postsubiculum (PHA28) ...	LD	Other labeled axons coursed around stria terminalis to rostral thalamic nuclei & terminated in 2 dense terminal fields in lateral dorsal nucleus, & a dense patch in anterodorsal nucleus. <Fig2: dense, Fig4: dense>	a
				c	1	vGr90b CIR29 pg168		A	-1	POST	Injections of [3H] amino acids into postsubiculum of rat (CIR29)...	LD	...labeled anterodorsal & laterodorsal nuclei of thalamus	a
PRE	CA1	0	0	2	Ste&Sco76	H1 pg355,357-9		H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	CA1	In 2 cases (H1, 24 hrs survival) inj centered in CA1 region of regio superior, relatively distant from CA1/CA2 transition (in both cases, no evidence of spread of HRP into stratum mole of fascia dentata.	r
					Ste&Sco76	D1 pg355,357-9		H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centered in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into stratum lac-mole of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than inj of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
PRE	CA3	0	0	1	Ste&Sco76	D1 pg355,357-9		H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centered in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into stratum lac-mole of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than inj of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
PRE	DG	1	1	1	Koh85	r76 pg511, fig4		P	1	PRE	rat76: an PHA-L injection with centre located in deep part of layer III in presubiculum at midtemporal levels. In 2 other rats inj restricted to layer II & superficial part of layer III	DG	2 rostrally directed projections can be followed from PHA-L inj site in PRE. One is ... other is relatively sparse innervation molecular layers of both Ammon's horn & area dentata. Has contralateral component homotopic to ipsi term field.	a
				0	1	Ste&Sco76 D1 pg355,357-9		H	0	PRE/PAR	absence of labeled cells in presubiculum & parasubiculum following injections into hippocampal formation suggests that these regions do not give rise to hippocampal afferents	DG/DG/CA1/CA3	In 2 cases (D1 & D2) injections were centered in stratum moleculare if fascia dentata with minimum spread into stratum lac-mole of regio superior. Inj site more diffuse than inj of fig3 & 9. <fig10: Inj site seems to involve CA3>	r
PRE	ENT	3	3	2	vGr90c	PHA30 pg230-1, fig4		P	3	PRE	Smaller inj of anterograde tracer PHA-L. were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	ENT	Axons ... to PAR & ENT... formed dense term field in deep L. I & L. III. Only Fs-o-P in Layer II. Majority labeled axons in fimbria/fornix -> contra PRE, PAR & ENT. Dense term plexus in deep L. I & III, few in L. II of PRE & PAR. <Fig4: dense>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Koh85	r76	pg511, fig4	P	3	PRE	rat76: an PHA-L injection with centre located in deep part of layer III in presubiculum at midtemporal levels. In 2 other rats injns restricted to layer II & superficial part of layer III	ENT	terminal field of presubicular projection to EA completely restricted to medial part of this cortex. Some PHA-L axons ... reach contralateral MEA... Major target of ipsilateral presubicular projection.	a
			2	2	Be78	EC4	fig4, table1	H	2	PRE	HRP injections of medial EC did result in labeling off cells in ventral part of the presubiculum <Table1: (Medial EC, PRS): 3; 20-50 cells.>	ENTm	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectroretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC4... HRP deposit in medial subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
					Donovan& Wyss83	a	pg182-6, fig2,3,4	F	2	PRE	... & resulted in labeling of neurons in all appropriate parts of subicular cortex. <Fig2,3,4: moderate>	ENT/ENT/P Rh	Injections into posterior entorhinal cortex consistently labeled medial, intermediate & lateral portions of that cortex ... <Figs2,3,4 inj site seems to spread into PERI>	r
			c	3	vGr90c	CF362	pg231	F	-1	PRE	Superficial (II & III) layers of presubiculum projected to ENT ... Contralateral projection mainly originated in layers III	ENT	... Entorhinal corex (CF362)... Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected	r
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	ENT	... projected ipsi to ... entorhinal cortex. Contralaterally label present in ... a entorhinal cortex	a
					Ste&Sco76	E	pg359	H	-1	PRE	cells in both contralateral presubiculum & parasubiculum clearly exhibited retrograde transport of HRP	ENT	2 animals received HRP injections of 0.5-0.7µl if HRP into entorhinal region of one hemisphere	r
			0	2	Be78	EC14	fig2, table1	H	0	PRE	<Table1: (Anterior EC, PRS): 0; no labelled cells>	ENT	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectroretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC14... HRP deposit in anteroventral part of entorhinal cortex.	r
					Be78	EC16	fig3, table1	H	0	PRE	<Table1: (Lateral EC, PRS): 0; no labelled cells>	ENTl	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectroretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC16: HRP deposit in lateral subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
			x	2	CallBled& Witt93 Kohler84		abstract		-1	PRE		ENTm	{1,3}	
							abstract		-1	PRE		ENTm		
PRE	PAR	3	3	1	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230-1, fig4	P	3	PRE	Smaller injns of anterograde tracer PHA-L were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	PAR	Axons ... to PAR & ENT... formed dense term field in deep L. I & L. III. Only Fs-o-P in Layer II. Majority labeled axons in fimbria/fornix -> contra PRE, PAR & ENT. Dense term plexus in deep L. I & III, few in L. II of PRE & PAR. <Fig4: mod; txt:dense ???>	a
			2	1	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	PRE	In presubiculum, near inj site labeled neurons were present in all layers; however in more distal areas neurons were labeled only in layer V.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
			1	1	Koh85	r76	pg511, fig4	P	1	PRE	rat76: an PHA-L injection with centre located in deep part of layer III in presubiculum at midtemporal levels. In 2 other rats injns restricted to layer II & superficial part of layer III	PAR	innervation of parasubiculum sparse from deep layers of presubiculum. However after PHA-L inj into superficial layers of PRE, large number of scattered fibres present throughout PAR, this proj still relatively modest.	a
			c	3	vGr90c	CF332	pg231	F	-1	PRE	Projection to contralateral PRE (CF328) & PAR (CF332) & ipsilateal PAR originated layers III-V of presubiculum	PAR	Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected: bilateral PAR	r
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	PAR	... projected ipsi to ... parasubiculum... Contralaterally label present in ... a parasubiculum ...	a
					vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	PRE	... labeled neurons in ... presubiculum... projection was bilateral.	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorecent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
PRE	POST	2	2	2	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	PRE	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... presubiculum... in PRE ipsi & contra to inj site, neurons labeled in external lamina (ie: layers II & III). Labeled neurons confined to caudal segments of PRE & PAR. <Fig5: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					vGr90c	PHA30	pg230, fig4	P	2	PRE	Smaller injns of anterograde tracer PHA-L. were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	POST	Labeled fibres emanated dorsally from presubiculum & most of these formed a terminal field in postsubiculum... in POST term labeling present in layers II/III & V. <Fig4: ipsi, sp/mod>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	CF314	pg231	F	-1	PRE	... originate mainly in layer II, and to a lesser extent in layers III & V	POST	Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected... postsubiculum (CF314)...	r
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	POST	... projected ipsi to ... postsubiculum...	a
PRE	SUB	2	2	2	Koh85	r76	pg511, fig4	P	2	PRE	rat76: an PHA-L injection with centre located in deep part of layer III in presubiculum at midtemporal levels. In 2 other rats injns restricted to layer II & superficial part of layer III	SUB	2 rostrally directed projections can be followed from PHA-L inj site in PRE. One of these terminates in well-restricted but dense fibre network among pyramidal cells of subiculum. Has contralateral component homotopic to ipsi term field.	a
					Be78	sub	pg254-6, table1	H	2	PRE	Control injections in subiculum labeled cells only in ammonic field CA1 & presubiculum <Table 1: (Subiculum, PRS): 3; 20-50 cells.>	SUB	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectroretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Subiculum...	r
			1	1	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230-1, fig4	P	1	PRE	Smaller injns of anterograde tracer PHA-L. were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	SUBv	A few fibres ... end in stratum radiatum of temporal part of subiculum. <fig4: not shown>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	CF340	pg231	F	-1	PRE	... also labeled a few cells in layers II-V of presubiculum, but labeled cells confined to region of presubiculum bordering temporal 1/3 in of subiculum.	SUB	Inj into temporal 1/3 of subiculum (CF340) ...	r
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	SUB	... projected ipsi to ... subiculum...	a
PRE	LM	3	3	2	Gonz92	lm	pg286, fig16CD,17A	W	3	PRE	main contingent of descending projections to LMN in these animals originated from ipsilateral & contralateral presubiculum & parasubiculum, particularly from contralateral presubiculum.	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
					Shib89	R336	pg445, fig12	W	3	PRE	In case R336, an inj of WGA-HRP involved both external & internal laminae of dorsal presubiculum. Periphery of most rostral portion of inj appeared to reach part of subiculum adjacent to presubiculum. Tracer did not appear to involve neocortical gray mat.	LM	Labeled terminals were seen ipsilaterally in LM. <fig12: V dense>	a
			2	1	All&Hop89	e	pg313, fig1	W	2	PRE	numerous retrogradely labeled perikarya were found mainly ipsilaterally in presubiculum & parasubiculum, few labeled neurons in contralateral presubiculum	LM/LM/M M/SUM/LH A	WGA-HRP inj site located mainly in lateral mammillary nucleus with a slight involvement of lateral part of medial nucleus. In addition there was some spread from the inj site dorsally into lateral portion of SUM & lateral hypothalamus	r
			c	1	Eric91	61	pg56	P	-1	PRE	PHA-L injections into the presubiculum (case 61) ...	LM	... resulted in labeled fibres that followed fornix & terminated in lateral mammillary nucleus.	a
PRE	MM	2	2	2	Shib89	R336	pg445, fig12	W	2	PRE	In case R336, an inj of WGA-HRP involved both external & internal laminae of dorsal presubiculum. Periphery of most rostral portion of inj appeared to reach part of subiculum adjacent to presubiculum. Tracer did not appear to involve neocortical gray mat.	MMI	Labeled terminals were seen ... bilaterally in dorsolateral region of pars lateralis & posterior. <fig12: sp/mod>	a
					Shib89	R336	pg445, fig12	W	2	PRE	In case R336, an inj of WGA-HRP involved both external & internal laminae of dorsal presubiculum. Periphery of most rostral portion of inj appeared to reach part of subiculum adjacent to presubiculum. Tracer did not appear to involve neocortical gray mat.	MMp	Labeled terminals were seen ... bilaterally in dorsolateral region of pars lateralis & posterior. <fig12: mod>	a
			1	1	Shib89	R290	pg 440, fig3	W	1	PRE	Some labeled cells, which appeared to be continuous in distribution with labeled cells in subiculum a, were also seen in portion between external & internal lamina of presubiculum.	MMp	In case R290, WGA-HRP was injected into caudal 2/3 of pars posterior of the MM in a median position with an apparent encroachment upon caudal fibre capsule of mammillary nuclei	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			c	1	Mei77b	Mb26	pg215	H	-1	PRE	... HRP +ve cells were observed in the medial portion of subicular complex (presubiculum), with fewer labeled cells noted in central regions along the entire rostrocaudal extent of dor & pos HPF	MMp	Following injections placed into the lateral portion of the pars posterior (cases Mb26, Mb27 & Mb28)...	r
			0	5	All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	0	PRE	no labeled cells were found in presubiculum or parasubiculum	MM/MM/SUM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
					Shib89	R336	pg445, fig12	W	0	PRE	In case R336, an inj of WGA-HRP involved both external & internal laminae of dorsal presubiculum. Periphery of most rostral portion of inj appeared to reach part of subiculum adjacent to presubiculum. Tracer did not appear to involve neocortical gray mat.	MMm	<fig12: No label in MMm or MMme>	a
					Gonz92	mm	pg279, fig3	W	0	PRE	In all animals, main descending projection to MMMN originated bilaterally from entire subicular cortex. Largest numbers of retro labeled cells found bilaterally in all layers of rosdor region of subiculum ...	MM	single ionto inj of WGA-HRP ... Inj sites depicted in fig3. repr cases into subdivisions of MM & surrounding hypothalamic regions in 8 animals. <few representative cases are wholly in MM>... injns that involved mainly pars medialis or pars lateralis of MMN.	r
					Sw77	R133	pg68-71, fig15	A	0	PRE/PAR	From 1 experiment in which isotope inj confined to area of pre- & parasubiculum (R133) & 6 additional experiments in which these fields were involved together with one or more adjacent cortical areas.	MMme	Unlike subiculum, PRE/PAR input to the mammillary complex terminates bilaterally in both medial & lateral mammillary nuclei... pars medianus of medial mammillary nucleus does not seem to receive input from this source	a
					Shib89	R336	pg445, fig12	W	0	PRE	In case R336, an inj of WGA-HRP involved both external & internal laminae of dorsal presubiculum. Periphery of most rostral portion of inj appeared to reach part of subiculum adjacent to presubiculum. Tracer did not appear to involve neocortical gray mat.	MMme	<fig12: No label in MMm or MMme>	a
PRE	SUM	0	0	1	All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	0	PRE	no labeled cells were found in presubiculum or parasubiculum	MM/MM/SUM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
PRE	TM	0	0	2	Eric91	C5355	pg51, Table1	F	0	PRE	<Table1: Presubiculum: C5355: -, No labeling>	TM/PMv	Implantations of fast blue resulted in well demarcated injection sites <1mm diameter. No inj site restricted solely to TMV (C5354, C5356: PMv/TMv). 3 Cases examined in detail. Controls in LM, PMv.	r
					Eric91	61	pg56	P	0	PRE	PHA-L injections into the presubiculum (case 61) ...	TM/PM	Labeling not observed in other parts of hypothalamus.	a
PRE	PRh	3	3	1	De83	RS9	pg184, fig16	H	3	PRE	Dense labelling of cells exhibited in ... middle and dorsal presubiculum	ECT/ECT/?	An (HRP) injection placed more posterodorsally in the postrhinal area	r
			0	1	Be78	prh	table1	H	0	PRE	<Table1: (Perirhinal Ctx, PRS): 0; no labelled cells>	PRh	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrolytic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Perirhinal ctx...	r
PRE	RSP	2	2	2	vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig7, obs	F	2	PRE	labeled neurons ipsilaterally in ... presubiculum, <density taken from fig7>	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
					Fin84	c67	pg477-81, fig2, table1	W	2	PRE	Topographically organized. Injs into pos. part of area 29 label cells in posterior PRE, POST and posteroventral part of SUB proper; Injs into ant area 29 labeled cells in dorsal SUB & PRE more anteriorly. Labeling most extensive after posterior 29 injs	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
			1	1	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230, fig4	P	1	PRE	Smaller injs of anterograde tracer PHA-L. were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	RSPv-a	Labeled fibres emanated dorsally from presubiculum & most of these formed a terminal field in ... retrosplenial granular a cortex. In caudal Rga relatively sparse terminal plexus present in layers II/III <Fig4: ipsi, sparse>	a
			c	4	vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	RSP	... projected ipsi to ... retrosplenial cortex...	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					Koh85	r76	pg511, fig4	P	-1	PRE	rat76: an PHA-L injection with centre located in deep part of layer III in presubiculum at midtemporal levels. In 2 other rats injs restricted to layer II & superficial part of layer III	RSP	distinct fibre bundle ascends from inj site toward superficial layers in caudal tip of presubiculum & retrosplenial area e.	a	
					vGr90c	CF310	pg231	F	-1	PRE	... originated in layer V of presubiculum	RSPv-a	Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected... Rga (CF310)...	r	
					Horikawa88	h	pg41	F	-1	PRE	... presubiculum	RSP	Structures containing labeled neurons following inj of tracer into area 29 were ...	r	
				x	2	Pakhomova & Akopian85	abstract		-1	PRE		RSP			
					Mei77d		abstract		-1	PRE		RSPv			
PRE	AD	2	2	2	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230-1, fig4	P	2	PRE	Smaller injs of anterograde tracer PHA-L were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	AD	A few labeled terminal present in nucleus reuniens & AD nucleus. <Fig6: sparse/moderate>	a	
					Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	2	PRE	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r	
PRE	AV	2	2	1	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230-1, fig4	P	2	PRE	Smaller injs of anterograde tracer PHA-L were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	AV	Dorsal rostral AV nucleus contained small terminal plexus bilaterally. <Fig6: mod>	a	
				c	5	Mei&Sie77	C19	pg6, table1	A	-1	PRE	Case19: In this case an injection was restricted to presubiculum at lvl of central dorsal hippocampal formation.	AV	Labeled fibres were observed in the dorsal fornix & one portion was traced to the ventral half of anteroventral thalamic nucleus.	a
					Mei&Sie77	C23	pg6, table1	A	-1	PRE	Case23: In this case an injection was placed at the level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation. Inj site localized to the presubiculum and did not spread into adjacent retrosplenial cortex.	AV	Instead, labeled fibers were traced through the postcommisural fornix where one component was observed to terminate in ventral half of anteroventral nucleus	a	
					Mei&Sie77	C27	pg6, table1	A	-1	PRE	Case27: In this case an injection was placed into the presubiculum at level at the level of the hippocampal flexure.	AV	Labeled fibres were traced through the medial portion of the fimbria & postcommisural fornix. Fibres destined for the thalamus again were observed to leave descending column of fornix & terminate in ventral portion of anteroventral nucleus	a	
					vGr90c	CF280	pg231	F	-1	PRE	... projection originated in VI of presubiculum	AV	Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected... AV (CF280)...	r	
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	AV	... projected ipsi to ... anteroventral & laterodorsal nuclei of the thalamus...	a	
PRE	LD	3	3	1	vGr90c	PHA30	pg230-1, fig4	P	3	PRE	Smaller injs of anterograde tracer PHA-L were made into presubiculum to study pattern of projections in more detail. Inj at middle of septotemporal axos of presubiculum (PHA30)...	LD	dorsal part of LD nucleus contained dense terminal plexus, ipsilateral to inj. <Fig4&6: dense>	a	
				2	1	Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	PRE	Retrogradely labeled cells in the cerebral cortex were found in ... the infragranular layers of the presubiculum	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
				1	1	Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	1	PRE	A few labeled cells were seen in the internal granular layer of the presubiculum	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
				c	2	vGr90c	CF289	pg231	F	-1	PRE	... projection originated in VI of presubiculum	LD	Injs of retrogradely transported were made in areas to which presubiculum projected... LD (CF289)...	r
					vGr90c	CIR19	pg230	A	-1	PRE	Large [3H] amino acid injections (CIR19) demonstrated that the presubiculum ...	LD	... projected ipsi to ... anteroventral & laterodorsal nuclei of the thalamus...	a	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
SUB	CA1	2	2	1	Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	2	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	CA1	Rostrally directed projection from subiculum innervates all layers of regio superior <CA3> & molecular layer of regio inferior <CA1>. Numerous PHA-L stained fibres are also present in molecular layer of area dentata.	a
SUB	CA3	2	2	1	Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	2	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	CA3	Rostrally directed projection from subiculum innervates all layers of regio superior <CA3> & molecular layer of regio inferior <CA1>. Numerous PHA-L stained fibres are also present in molecular layer of area dentata.	a
SUB	DG	2	2	1	Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	2	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	DG	Rostrally directed projection from subiculum innervates all layers of regio superior <CA3> & molecular layer of regio inferior <CA1>. Numerous PHA-L stained fibres are also present in molecular layer of area dentata.	a
SUB	ENT	3	3	1	Swa.et.al81	d	pg554	F	3	SUBd	Even in zone of maximal labeling in dorsal part of subiculum, only ~1/3 of cells were doubly labeled. In same zone, many cells were labeled by one or the other but not both dyes	ENT	FB/Bisbenzimid injections into septum & entorhinal cortex	r
					Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	2	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	ENTm	Exclusively ipsi... straight, radial course through VI-V, sparse terms; primary term field in layer IV of medial & lateral EA. Layer IV always contains rel dense terminal plexus of PHA-L stained fibres. <more desc in paper>	a
												ENTI	Exclusively ipsi... straight, radial course through VI-V, sparse terms; primary term field in layer IV of medial & lateral EA. Layer IV always contains rel dense terminal plexus of PHA-L stained fibres. <more desc in paper>	a
												ENTm	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC4... HRP deposit in medial subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
												ENTI	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC16: HRP deposit in lateral subdivision of entorhinal cortex.	r
					Donovan& Wyss83	a	pg182-6, fig2,3,4	F	2	SUB	... & resulted in labeling of neurons in all appropriate parts of subicular cortex. <Fig2: moderate Fig3: sp/mod, Fig4: moderate>	ENT/ENT/P Rh	Injections into posterior entorhinal cortex consistently labeled medial, intermediate & lateral portions of that cortex ... <Figs2,3,4 inj site seems to spread into PERI>	r
					Be78	EC14	pg254, fig2, table1	H	1	SUB	Labeled cells appeared ipsilaterally in hippocampal & subicular cortices in all cases of EC injection. <Table1: (Anterior EC, S); 2; 10-20 cells.>	ENT	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci within entorhinal cortex ... case EC14... HRP deposit in anteroventral part of entorhinal cortex.	r
Groene87	b	pg106	P	-1	SUBv	10/15 cases, PHA-L inj restricted to subiculum... one inj involves ventral intermediate part of SUB, and six the ventral or temporal part of SUB.	ENT	Following ventral subiculum injections most anterogradely labeled fibres found in entorhinal cortex ...	a					
SUB	PAR	2	2	1	Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	2	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	PAR	At level of inj site, PHA-L stained axons deviate from projection destined for presubiculum to form distinct fibre bundle which innervates parasubiculum where moderately dense terminal network restricted to most medial subdiv of PAR	a
					vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	SUB	... labeled neurons in ...subiculum...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
SUB	POST	c	c	2	vGr90b	PHA16	pg173, fig8	P	-1	SUB	Injs in septal 1/3 of subiculum (PHA16)...	POST	...labeled axons & terminals in layers I, II, & V of postsubiculum (but most were in layer V)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
					vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	-1	SUBd	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... subiculum... cell bodies were labeled in dorsal septal 1/3 of subiculum ipsilateral to inj. <Fig5: not shown>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r	
SUB	PRE	3	3	1	Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	3	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	PRE	As fibres ascend in deep layers of presubiculum they give off collaterals which penetrate all it layers. Some form terminal plexuses in deep part of molecular layer.	a	
					c	vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	SUBv	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in subiculum... Labeling in the ventral subiculum was confined to neurons near the inj site (within 1mm). <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
SUB	LM	2	2	1	Shib89	R278	pg445, fig10	W	2	SUBv	Following a WGA-HRP injection into caudoventral subiculum (R278)...	LM	Labeled terminals were also found ipsilaterally in ventral & lateral margins of LM. <fig10: sp/mod>	a	
					l	All&Hop89	e	pg313, fig1	W	1	SUBd	a few labeled neurons also found in ipsilateral dorsal subiculum	LM/LM/M M/SUM/L HA	WGA-HRP inj site located mainly in lateral mammillary nucleus with a slight involvement of lateral part of medial nucleus. In addition there was some spread from the inj site dorsally into lateral portion of SUM & lateral hypothalamus	r
					c	Mei77b	S19	pg205-6	A	-1	SUB	In case S19, S47 & S48 injections were placed into region of prosubiculum (lateral portion).	LM	A few fibres also terminated in the lateral mammillary nucleus	a
					0	All&Hop89	h	pg314, fig4	W	0	SUB/POST	cases in which WGA-HRP inj into subicular complex did not involve PRE & PAR ...	LM	... showed no anterograde labeling in the lateral mammillary nucleus.	a
						Sw77	R176	pg64-5, fig11	A	0	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	LM	In no instance was transported label observed over lateral or supramammillary nuclei	a
SUB	MM	3	3	6	Shib89	R266	pg445, fig9	W	3	SUB	In case R266, WGA-HRP centred predominantly in subiculum at same septotemporal lvl as R285. Some amount of tracer spread to more lateral regions of caudal subiculum	MMp	Labeled terminals seen only in caudal 2/3 of ventral region of MM. In pars lateralis labeled terminals were distributed more massively in ventrolateral region than in ventromedial region of pars posterior <fig9: mod/dense>	a	
						Shib89	R268	pg440,445, fig6	W	3	SUB	In case R268, WGA-HRP was injected into rosdor subiculum. Tracer appeared to involve part of subiculum close to CA1 rostrally & part close to presubiculum caudally.	MMp	Densely labeled terminals were seen bilaterally in intermediate 1/3 along dorsoventral axis of MM in pars posterior. Terminal field presented a flattened M-shape particularly in rostral 1/2 of pars posterior. <fig6: dense>	a
						Shib89	R289	pg437, fig1	W	3	SUB	Many retrogradely labeled cells were seen bilaterally in the septotemporal extent of the subiculum. Most large pyramidal cells throughout depth of the pyr cell layer. <complicated description, see pg437, fig1,2 for more details>	MM	In case R289, WGA-HRP was injected into the rostral median region of the MM, spreading slightly to the supramammillary & dorsal premammillary nuclei.	r
						Gonz92	mm	pg279, fig3	W	3	SUB	In all animals, main descending projection to MMMN originated bilaterally from entire subicular cortex. Largest numbers of retro labeled cells found bilaterally in all layers of rosdor region of subiculum ...	MM	single ionto inj of WGA-HRP ... Inj sites depicted in fig3. repr cases into subdivisions of MM & surrounding hypothalamic regions in 8 animals. <few representative cases are wholly in MM>... injns that involved mainly pars medialis or pars lateralis of MMMN.	r
						All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	3	SUBv	large numbers of retrogradely labeled perikarya were found bilaterally in all layers of dorsal & ventral portions of subiculum	MM/MM/S UM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
						All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	3	SUBd	large numbers of retrogradely labeled perikarya were found bilaterally in all layers of dorsal & ventral portions of subiculum	MM/MM/S UM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
					2	Shib89	R290	pg 440, fig3	W	2	SUB	Many cells seen bilat in dor/cau subiculum; cells more numerous than in cases R289 & R309. Most cells in deepest part of pyr cell layer unlabeled. At more temp lvls most cells confined to proximal part of SUB along PRE-CA1 axis, few in distal parts.	MMp	In case R290, WGA-HRP was injected into caudal 2/3 of pars posterior of the MM in a median position with an apparent encroachment upon caudal fibre capsule of mammillary nuclei	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Shib89	R268	pg440, fig6	W	2	SUB	In case R268, WGA-HRP was injected into rosdor subiculum. Tracer appeared to involve part of subiculum close to CA1 rostrally & part close to presubiculum caudally.	MMm	...whereas only weaker labeling was seen within pars medialis. <fig6: sp/mod>	a
					Shib89	R266	pg445, fig9	W	2	SUB	In case R266, WGA-HRP centred predominantly in subiculum at same semptemporal lvl as R285. Some amount of tracer spread to more lateral regions of caudal subiculum	MMl	Labeled terminals seen only in caudal 2/3 of ventral region of MM. In pars lateralis labeled terminals were distributed more massively in ventrolateral region than in ventromedial region of pars posterior. <fig9: moderate>	a
					Shib89	R268	pg440, fig6	W	2	SUB	In case R268, WGA-HRP was injected into rosdor subiculum. Tracer appeared to involve part of subiculum close to CA1 rostrally & part close to presubiculum caudally.	MMl	In rostral region of MM, dense label found bilaterally just ventral to prin mamm tract within pars lateralis. <fig6: mod/dense>	a
					Shib89	R268	pg440-5, fig6	W	2	SUB	In case R268, WGA-HRP was injected into rosdor subiculum. Tracer appeared to involve part of subiculum close to CA1 rostrally & part close to presubiculum caudally.	MMme	A few labeled terminals were also seen in dorsal region of pars mediana. <fig6: moderate>	a
					Shib89	R278	pg445, fig10	W	2	SUB	Following a WGA-HRP injection into caudoventral subiculum (R278)...	MM	... labeled terminals were distributed along ventral margin of MM in entire mediolateral extent & most densely in ventrolateral region of pars lateralis at lvl of LM. <fig10: overall moderate>	a
					Shib89	R280	pg445, fig11	W	2	SUB	Following an inj into most temporal part of subiculum (R280) ...	MM	... only a few labeled terminals seen in rostroventral region of MM. <fig11: overall sp/mod>	a
					Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,185, fig1,3,5	P	2	SUBv	8 adult male Sprague-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	MM	Labeled fibres from medial corticohypothalamic tract ... provide moderately dense inputs to ... fibre capsule around outside of medial mammillary nucleus... Dense plexus of fibres in cell-free region... contains distal dendrites of MM neurons	a
					Shib89	R278	pg445, fig10	W	1	SUB	Following a WGA-HRP injection into caudoventral subiculum (R278)...	MMme	A few labeled terminals were seen in ventral region of pars mediana <fig10: sparse>	a
					Eric91	604	pg56	P	-1	SUBv	PHA-L injection into ventral subiculum (C604, C606)...	MMme	labeled fibres were present in ... medial division of medial mammillary nucleus.	a
					Shib89	R285	pg445, fig8	W	-1	SUB	An inj of WGA-HRP made into distal part of caudal subiculum along its presubiculo-CA1 axis at level of hippocampal flexure with only a slight encroachment upon subiculum a. (R285)	MMm	Fewer labeled terms seen in pars medialis & pars mediana of MM.	a
					Shib89	R233	pg439-40	W	-1	SUB	...additional labeled cells were seen in part of subiculum close to presubiculum ("subiculum a")	MM	Cases with injections into rostral MM but diffusing into more caudolateral region of pars lateralis (R233)	r
					Shib89	R285	pg445, fig8	W	-1	SUB	An inj of WGA-HRP made into distal part of caudal subiculum along its presubiculo-CA1 axis at level of hippocampal flexure with only a slight encroachment upon subiculum a. (R285)	MM	In ros region of MM, labeled terms dist relatively diffusely in pars lateralis & btwn pars medialis of both sides in intermed region along dorven axis of MM. Densely labeled terminals seen in ventral 1/3 of MM at mid rostrocaudal levels.	a
					Shib89	R247	pg440, fig5	W	-1	SUB	Inj WGA-HRP was made into septal pole of subiculum (case R247). Although some tracer spread to the underlying pretectum & superior colliculus & along the pipette overlying neocortex, did not involve any parts of retrosplenial.	MM	Rostrally, weakly labeled were seen in dor region of MM, particularly lateral to principal mamm tract. At more cau lvls, most labeled terms seen bilat in dor 1/3 of pars post of MM. Dor margin of term fields ~ coextensive with dor boundary of MM	a
					Mei77b	Mb22	pg215	H	-1	SUB	Labeled perikarya were observed principally in the lateral region of the subicular complex (prosubiculum) all along the longitudinal axis of hippocampus.	MMp	Discrete injections were placed in midline region of pars posterior of medial mammillary nucleus in cases Mb22, Mb23, Mb24 & Mb25.	r
					Mei77b	S29	pg211	A	-1	SUB	In 6 cases injections of [3H]leucine placed into subicular cortex at level of posterior ventral hippocampal formation (S29, S30, S31, S33, S34, S59). Inj site in each case restricted to either prosubiculum or subiculum & did not spread to adjacent HIP	MM	In cases in which prosubiculum & subiculum incorporated amino acid, labeled fibres were traced through postcommissural fornix terminating bilaterally in ventromedial portion of pars posterior.	a
					Mei77b	S20	pg206	A	-1	SUB	In cases S20 & S50 injections were placed into a cebtral region within the subicular complex (subiculum proper).	MM	Fibers were also treaced through precommissural fornix & occupied a central position within the pars posterior... fibres of the subiculum projected bilaterally throughout medial 2/3 of the pars posterior.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Mei77b	S19	pg205-6	A	-1	SUB	In case S19, S47 & S48 injections were placed into region of prosubiculum (lateral portion).	MM	In addition, fibres from postcommissural fornix were traced through pars lateralis & terminated in medial 1/3 of paars posterior at a central level within dorsoventral axisof this subnucleus <Fig5: >	a
					Swa&Cow7 5b	c	pg304	A	-1	SUBd	When only the dorsal part of the subiculum was labeled ...	MM	... the transported label was found bilaterally within the medial mammillary nucleus, occupying a more-or-less horizontal band across both nuclei.	a
					Shib89	R285	pg445, fig8	W	-1	SUB	An inj of WGA-HRP made into distal part of caudal subiculum along its presubiculo-CA1 axis at level of hippocampal flexure with only a slight encroachment upon subiculum a. (R285)	MMme	Fewer labeled terms seen in pars medialis & pars mediana of MM.	a
					Shib89	R285	pg445, fig8	W	-1	SUB	An inj of WGA-HRP made into distal part of caudal subiculum along its presubiculo-CA1 axis at level of hippocampal flexure with only a slight encroachment upon subiculum a. (R285)	MMp	In caudal region of pars posterior, few labeled terminals restricted to ventral margin	a
					Sw77	R176	pg64-5, fig11	A	-1	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	MMp	as figure 11 shows dorsal subiculum projects to ... (ii) through descending column of fornix to mammillary complex where its efferents end bilaterally in pars medianus of medial mammillary nucleus & dorsal halves of pars medialis & pars posterior	a
					Sw77	R176	pg64-5, fig11	A	-1	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	MMme	as figure 11 shows dorsal subiculum projects to ... (ii) through descending column of fornix to mammillary complex where its efferents end bilaterally in pars medianus of medial mammillary nucleus & dorsal halves of pars medialis & pars posterior	a
					Sw77	R176	pg64-5, fig11	A	-1	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	MMm	as figure 11 shows dorsal subiculum projects to ... (ii) through descending column of fornix to mammillary complex where its efferents end bilaterally in pars medianus of medial mammillary nucleus & dorsal halves of pars medialis & pars posterior	a
SUB	SUM	1	1	2	Shib89	R280	pg445, fig11	W	1	SUB	Following an inj into most temporal part of subiculum (R280) ...	SUM	Labeled terminals also found bilaterally in supramammillary nucleus <fig11: sparse>	a
					Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,185, fig1,3,5	P	1	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	SUMm	Caudalmost projection of ventral subiculum appears to consist of few axons coursing through post hypo nucleus that continue on to end in ... medial subdivision of supramammillary nucleus, <Fig5: implication is for a sparse connection>	a
			0	1	Sw77	R176	pg64-5, fig11	A	0	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	SUM	In no instance was transported label observed over lateral or supramammillary nuclei	a
SUB	TM	2	2	1	Eric91	604	pg56, Table2	P	2	SUBv	PHA-L injection into ventral subiculum (C604, C606)...	TMv	There was also a projection to TMV, but most labeled fibres lay medial to cell group & only a few entered core of nucleus. <Table2: Innerv Dens C604 ++ (Terminal-like profiles, light labeling) , C606 + (Solitary Fibres) >	a
			1	2	Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,185, fig1,3,5	P	1	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	TMv	We observed at this level a few labeled fibres that appear to end in both dorsal & ventral parts of tuberomammillary nucleus.	a
					Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,185, fig1,3,5	P	1	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	TMd	We observed at this level a few labeled fibres that appear to end in both dorsal & ventral parts of tuberomammillary nucleus.	a
SUB	ACA	1	1	1	Ja89	FG7	pg339	F	1	SUB	... only a few labeled cells were observed in dorsal prosubiculum, ipsilateral to injection. <prosubiculum = subiculum>	ACA	In other animals with FG injected into the anterior cingulate area,...	
			0	2	Fin84	c74	pg477, fig4, table1	W	0	SUB	The subicular region was the only region of the hippocampal formation that was reliably labeled, and then only after injections of the posterior cingulate cortex.	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	0	SUB	projections to anterior cingular regions did not derive from the ... subicular cortex	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
			x	1	Roberts84		abstract	-1		SUBd		ACA		
SUB	ILA	1	1	1	Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,183, fig1,5	P	1	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	ILA	... other fibres innervate ... prelimbic, infralimbic & medial orbital areas of cortex <Fig5: thin line representing sparse connection>	a
			c	3	Sw77	R135/R H9	pg66-8, fig13	A	-1	SUBv/SUB v/???	Have no inj wholly confined to ventral subiculum. In expt R135 pre- & parasubiculum were also labeled by the inj & in RH9 parts of fields CA3 & CA4 were implicated...	ILA	Other fibres continue ... to the deeper layers of the infralimbic cortex	a
					Swa&Cow7 5b	d	pg304	A	-1	SUBv	When injection involved the ventral portion of subiculum ...	ILA	Some fibers from ventral subiculum extend into precommissural fornix to ... adjoining cortical areas (taenia tecta, anterior olfactory nucleus, & infralimbic area)	a
					Ja91	SUB4	pg581, fig7,8,9	P	-1	SUB	Most caudally placed PHA-L injections in intermediate subiculum (case SUB-4). Inj labeled cell bodies as well as their dendrites & axons.	ILA	<No mention in text, probably because IL 'not part of prefrontal cortex'. Label shown on fig8>	a
SUB	PL	3	3	3	Ja89	FG3	pg337-9, fig1,2	F	3	SUBv	Additional labeled cells were also seen in dorsal & ventral prosubiculum, the transition zone btwn CA1 & subiculum. At more caudal lvl, PL-projecting neurons seen in prosubiculum & subiculum. Most cells ipsilateral to inj site, few contra.	PL	In all rats with FG injected into prelimbic cortex (fig1B) ...	r
					Ja89	FG3	pg337-9, fig1,2	F	3	SUBd	Additional labeled cells were also seen in dorsal & ventral prosubiculum, the transition zone btwn CA1 & subiculum. At more caudal lvl, PL-projecting neurons seen in prosubiculum & subiculum. Most cells ipsilateral to inj site, few contra.	PL	In all rats with FG injected into prelimbic cortex (fig1B) ...	r
					Ja91	SUB4	pg581, fig7,8,9	P	3	SUB	Most caudally placed PHA-L injections in intermediate subiculum (case SUB-4). Inj labeled cell bodies as well as their dendrites & axons.	PL	dense anterograde labeling in entire rostrocaudal extent of prelimbic cortex ... Prelimbic cortex displayed varicose fibres & terminal plexuses in all layers.	a
			2	1	Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,183, fig1,5	P	2	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	PL	... other fibres innervate ... prelimbic, infralimbic & medial orbital areas of cortex <Fig5: thicker line representing moderate connection>	a
SUB	PRh	1	1	3	Be78	prh	pg256, table1	H	1	SUB	A few labeled cells could be found in subiculum after injection of perirhinal ctx <Table1: (Perirhinal Ctx, S): 1; less than 10 cells.>	PRh	Each of 18 adult, female albino rats received a single microelectrophoretic injection of HRP in various loci in control cases in cortical areas adjacent to EC... Perirhinal ctx...	r
					Cant&Swa9 2b	SUB16	pg181,183-4, fig1,5	P	1	SUBv	8 adult male Sprage-Dawley rats received inj of PHA-L into ventral parts of subiculum... discrete inj sites typically with hundreds of clearly labeled neurons. In 5 expts inj was virtually confined to temporal pole of subiculum. SUB16: repr case	PRh	... Some labeled fibres also appear in ... deep layers of ... perirhinal areas <Fig5: thin line representing sparse connection>	a
					De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	1	SUB	A few scattered cells area found in the subiculum	PRh/PRh/T Ev/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEV/ECT/ENT as well as PERL>	r
			c	1	Sw77	R176	pg64,75, fig11	A	-1	SUBd	In expt R176 heavily labeled cells were strictly confined to dorsal subiculum	PRh	The only cortical area caudal to subiculum which appears to receive a projection from this area is the perirhinal area. The projection to perirhinal area only seen after injections into dorsal dorsal part of SUB	a
SUB	RSP	3	3	1	Vo83	f2	pg194, fig2	W	3	SUB	Subicular cortices contained large numbers of HRP labeled neurons including subiculum, postsubiculum, & parasubiculum. The para- & post-subiculum neurons located in internal pyramidal cell layer	RSP	Injections of lectin-confugated HRP <WGA-HRP> into areas 29c-d ...	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	2	Fin84	c67	pg477-81, fig2, table1	W	2	SUB	Topographically organized. Injs into pos. part of area 29 label cells in posterior PRE, POST and posteroventral part of SUB proper; Injs into ant area 29 labeled cells in dorsal SUB & PRE more anteriorly. Labeling most extensive after posterior 29 injs	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig7.8D, obs	F	2	SUB	labeled neurons ipsilaterally in ... rostroventral subiculum. Injections into rostral Rga labeled cell bodies in the intermediate third of the subiculum, in contrast to more caudal injections that labeled neurons in the temporal third of the subiculum.	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
			1	1	Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	1	SUB	projections to posterior cingular regions derived from the ... subicular cortex, (1-10 somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
			c	3	Groene87	a	pg106	P	-1	SUBd	10/15 cases, PHA-L inj restricted to subiculum, seven injs involve dorsal or septal part of subiculum, one the dorsal intermediate part ...	RSPd	Areas outside striatum that contain heaviest labeling after injs in dorsal subiculum are ... agranular retrosplenial cortex ...	a
					Koh85	r65	pg507, fig2	P	-1	SUB	rat 65: PHA-L injection labeled pyramidal cells in caudal 1/3 of subiculum proper at midtemporal levels of structure. Small number of nonpyramidal cells situated adjacent to angular bundle also labeled by this inj.	RSP	PHA-L stained axons from subicular injs reach retrosplenial area... Other axons <than collaterals to presubiculum> continue further dorsal to form a dense terminal field in layers I & II of retrosplenial cortex.	a
					vGr90d	PHA43	pg600	P	-1	SUBv	Anterograde injections into ventral subiculum (PHA-L?)	RSPv-a	labeled axons in {2}, {1,3} of Rga	a
			x	3	Wyss&vGr9	2a	abstract		3	SUB	septal	RSPv	granular b	
					Wyss&vGr9	2a	abstract		3	SUB	temporal	RSPv	granular a	
					Mei77d		abstract		-1	SUBd		RSP		
SUB	AM	2	2	1	Cullin93	21,32.0	pg6, fig4A 5	P	2	SUBv	PHA-L injs made at several different roscav lvls in proximal or lateral-most portion of ventral subiculum, in region previously termed prosubiculum. In cases 32 & 05, a few neurons in DG also labeled	AM	labeling seen within thalamic paraventricular, parataenia and anteromedial nuclei, & to a lesser extent within the interanteromedial, reunions nuclei	a
			c	4	Mei&Sie77	C40	pg7, table1	A	-1	SUB	Case40: In this animal and extremely small punctate injection was placed into the subiculum at the level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation. There was little diffusion to adjacent pro- & presubiculum.	AM	Labeled fibres traced through internal capsule & descending column of fornix to terminate in anterior thalamus (fig3). Terminal distribution was localized to lateral portion of anteromedial nucleus & to adjacent ventral poriton of anteroventral nucleus	a
					Mei&Sie77	C9	pg2.4, table1	A	-1	SUB	Case 9: In this case & in 4 related animals [3H]leucine injections were confined to the prosubiculum level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation.	AM	Labeled fibres were again traced through the internal capsule to terminate bilaterally throughout the anteromedial thalamic nucleus	a
					Mei&Sie77	C5	pg2.4, table1	A	-1	SUB	In 4 cases [3H]leucine injs placed into prosubiculum caudal to the inj site in case 1 (at central lvls of dorsal hippocampal formation) all yielded similar results. In case 5 inj localized to subicular cortex & no spread into adj hippocampus.	AM	Labeled fibres entered internal capsule & were distributed bilaterally throughout anteromedial thalamic nucleus	a
					Mei&Sie77	C1	pg2.4, fig1a, table1	A	-1	SUB	In 4 cases [3H]leucine injs placed into ant prosubiculum at a posn where subicular cortex emerges adjacent to field CA1 of the anterior dorsal hippocampus. In case 1 small inj limited to prosubiculum, did not involve HIP pyr cells. <prosub = SUB>	AM	Axons distributed bilaterally throughout the anteromedial nucleus... Some fornix fibres could have terminated in anteromedial nucleus.	a
SUB	AV	c	c	2	Groene87	a	pg106	P	-1	SUBd	10/15 cases, PHA-L inj restricted to subiculum, seven injs involve dorsal or septal part of subiculum, one the dorsal intermediate part ...	AV	Areas outside striatum that contain heaviest labeling after injs in dorsal subiculum are ... anteroventral thalamic nucleus	a
					Mei&Sie77	C40	pg7, table1	A	-1	SUB	Case40: In this animal and extremely small punctate injection was placed into the subiculum at the level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation. There was little diffusion to adjacent pro- & presubiculum.	AV	Labeled fibres traced through internal capsule & descending column of fornix to terminate in anterior thalamus (fig3). Terminal distribution was localized to lateral portion of anteromedial nucleus & to adjacent ventral poriton of anteroventral nucleus	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>												
SUB	IAM	1	1	1	Cullin93	21,32.0 5	pg6, fig4A	P	1	SUBv	PHA-L injns made at several different roscaw lvls in proximal or lateral-most portion of ventral subiculum, in region previously termed prosubiculum. In cases 32 & 05, a few neurons in DG also labeled	IAM	labeling seen within thalamic paraventricular, parataenia and anteromedial nuclei, & to a lesser extent within the interanteromedial, reunions nuclei	a												
LM	AD	3	3	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f5	pg250, fig5,11	H	3	LM	HRP was found bilaterally in most cells of the lateral mammillary nucleus, but cells in dorsomedial 2/3s of pars medialis dorsalis at caudal lvl were labeled weakly. <Fig5: Label fills LM, appears dense>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r												
LM	AM	0	0	1	Sek&Zyo84	H159f9 eb	pg251-2, fig9,11	H	0	LM	<Fig9: No labeling in LM>	AM/PT/RE	H-159: Double labeling: Bb in Av (staining extended to lateral 1/2 of both Avm & Avp at a moderately caudal lvl & in Ad) Eb in Am (strongly labeled centre of Am) <Fig9 shows inclusion of PT & RE in inj site>	r												
MM	PRh	c	c	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	-1	MM	Subcortical cells are found in the ... medial mammillary nucleus	PRh/PRh/T Ev/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERL>	r												
MM	AD	2	2	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f5	pg250, fig5,11	H	2	MM	HRP was found bilaterally in most cells of the lateral mammillary nucleus, but cells in dorsomedial 2/3s of pars medialis dorsalis at caudal lvl were labeled weakly. <Fig5: patch of label in MMd, moderate>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r												
															1	1	Shib92	R221	pg121, fig3DEF	W	1	MMI/LHA/ PMd/MMm/ SUM	In case 221, WGA-HRP inj involved dolat region of pars lateralis of MM, adjoining caudal parts of lateral hypothalamus, and dorsal premmammillary nucleus. Small amount of tracer diffused into pars medialis of MM & SUM. Cau: dormed LM	AD	A few terminals were also seen bilaterally in AD <fig3D-F: sparse>	a
															0	1	Shib92	R372	pg121, fig1RT	W	MMp	... & a small number in ros-ven-lat region of pars posterior just dorsal to pia mater.	AD/ILM/M D	Case R372 had injection involving medial part of AD & diffusion into adjoining parts of intralaminar nuclei and mediodorsal thalamic nucleus, but not into AV	r	
MM	AM	3	3	3	Shib92	R261	pg121, fig3ABC,4AB	W	3	MMm	In case R261, WGA_HRP inj centered in ventral 1/2 of pars medialis of MM with diffusion beyond its ventral border.	AM	Labeled terminals were densely distributed in dorsomedial 2/3 of AM & medial part of AV <fig3A-C: dense>	a												
															Shib92	R353	pg120, fig1EF	W	3	MMm	... many labeled cells were observed in dorsal region of rostral 1/2 of pars lateralis & ventral region of pars medialis. <fig1D-F: mod/dense>	AM/AM/A V/RT	Following injection into rostral 1/2 of AM with diffusion into adjoining parts of AV & nucleus reticularis thalami (R353)...	r		
															Shib92	R353	pg120, fig1EF	W	3	MMI	... many labeled cells were observed in dorsal region of rostral 1/2 of pars lateralis & ventral region of pars medialis. <fig1D-F: mod/dense>	AM/AM/A V/RT	Following injection into rostral 1/2 of AM with diffusion into adjoining parts of AV & nucleus reticularis thalami (R353)...	r		
															2	2	Shib92	R472	pg120, fig1HI	W	2	MMm	Labeled cells were seen mainly in dorsal region of pars medialis of MM <fig1G-I: moderate>	AM/AM/M D	In case R472, injection was localized into caudal 1/3 of AM, although tracer spread along pipette track into dorsal part of mediodorsal thalamic nucleus.	r
															Shib92	R221	pg121, fig3DEF	W	2	MMI/LHA/ PMd/MMm/ SUM	In case 221, WGA-HRP inj involved dolat region of pars lateralis of MM, adjoining caudal parts of lateral hypothalamus, and dorsal premmammillary nucleus. Small amount of tracer diffused into pars medialis of MM & SUM. Cau: dormed LM	AM	Labeled terminals were seen in ventral part of AM & AV in its rostral 1/2 <fig3D-F: moderate>	a		
															1	2	Shib92	R353	pg120, fig1EF	W	1	MMme	A few labeled cells were predominantly ipsilaterally in ventrolateral region of pars mediana <fig1D-F: sparse>	AM/AM/A V/RT	Following injection into rostral 1/2 of AM with diffusion into adjoining parts of AV & nucleus reticularis thalami (R353)...	r
															Shib92	R472	pg120-1, fig1HI	W	1	MMI	Weakly labeled cells were scattered within pars lateralis of MM, <figG-I: sparse>	AM/AM/M D	In case R472, injection was localized into caudal 1/3 of AM, although tracer spread along pipette track into dorsal part of mediodorsal thalamic nucleus.	r		
MM	AV	3	3	2	Shib92	R290	pg121, fig3KL,4D	W	3	MMp	In a case (R290) with WGA-HRP injection confined to caudal 2/3 of pars posterior of MM without involving pars basalis of MM, ...	AV	... labeled terminals were observed predominantly caudally in dorsomedial part (= pars magnocellularis) of bilateral AV <fig3J-K: mod-dense>	a												
															Shib92	R444	pg121, fig	W	3	MMp	... many labeled cells appeared predominantly ipsilaterally in lateral region of pars posterior of MM. <fig1N-Q: mod/dense>	AV	Following injection involving dorsolateral part of caudal 1/3 of AV (R444) ...	r		

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			2	2	Shib92	R261	pg121, fig3,4	W	2	MMm	In case R261, WGA_HRP inj centered in ventral 1/2 of pars medialis of MM with diffusion beyond its ventral border.	AV	Labeled terminals were densely distributed in dorsomedial 2/3 of AM & medial part of AV <fig3A-C: moderate>	a
					Shib92	R221	pg121, fig3DEF	W	2	MMI/LHA/PMd/MMm/SUM	In case 221, WGA-HRP inj involved dolat region of pars lateralis of MM, adjoining caudal parts of lateral hypothalamus, and dorsal premammillary nucleus. Small amount of tracer diffused into pars medialis of MM & SUM. Cau: dormed LM	AV	Labeled terminals were seen in ventral part of AM & AV in its rostral 1/2 <fig3D-F: moderate>	a
			1	2	Gonz92	R12a	pg283, fig2C	W	1	MM	Very small injection centred in caudal 1/3 of pars posterior of left MMN	AV	well localized inj of WGA-HRP in caudal part of MP correlated with small & well localized terminal projections in ipsilateral anteroventral thalamic nucleus	a
					Shib92	R444	pg121, fig	W	1	MMI	A few labeled cells were seen ipsilaterally in most lateral region of pars lateralis <fig1N-Q: sparse>	AV	Following injection involving dorsolateral part of caudal 1/3 of AV (R444) ...	r
			c	3	Shib92	R443	pg121, fig1JKLM	W	-1	MMp	labeled cells seen in pars basalis, ventrolateral region of pars lateralis & rostroventral region of pars posterior of MM <fig1J-M: not sure>	AV	Following injection into dorsal part of AV at midrostrocaudal level (R443) ...	r
					Shib92	R443	pg121, fig1JKLM	W	-1	MMb	labeled cells seen in pars basalis, ventrolateral region of pars lateralis & rostroventral region of pars posterior of MM <fig1J-M: not sure>	AV	Following injection into dorsal part of AV at midrostrocaudal level (R443) ...	r
					Shib92	R443	pg121, fig1JKLM	W	-1	MMI	labeled cells seen in pars basalis, ventrolateral region of pars lateralis & rostroventral region of pars posterior of MM <fig1J-M: not sure>	AV	Following injection into dorsal part of AV at midrostrocaudal level (R443) ...	r
MM	IAM	3	3	1	Shib92	R384	pg120, fig1BC,2B	W	3	MMme	Retrogradely labeled cells were concentrated in dorsal region of pars mediana of MM <fig1A-C: mod/dense>	IAM/IAM/ILM/MD/PV/TRH	In case R384, injection was made into interanteromedial nucleus. Tracer diffused into adjoining parts of intralaminar, mediadorsal periventricular & rhomboid thalamic nuclei.	r
MM	MD	0	0	1	Shib92	R372	pg121, fig1RT	W		MMp	... & a small number in ros-ven-lat region of pars posterior just dorsal to pia mater.	AD/ILM/MD	Case R372 had injection involving medial part of AD & diffusion into adjoining parts of intralaminar nuclei and mediadorsal thalamic nucleus, but not into AV	r
SUM	CA1	2	2	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,174, fig4	P	2	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	CA1	Occasional fibres found in fields CA1 & CA2	a
SUM	CA3	3	3	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,174, fig4	P	3	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	CA3	majority of labeled fibres in Ammon's horn is centered in the region of subfield CA3a, where terminal plexuses evident in pyramidal layer & stratum oriens... molecular layer of CA3 also contains moderately dense plexus of term fib (+ boutons)	a
SUM	DG	3	3	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173-4, fig4	P	3	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	DG	labeled fibres in inner & outer blades of dentate gyrus. Patches of label in both blades, esp contralaterally. Ips: all but temporal pole. Con: only septal 1/3. Many fibres were varicose, branched profusely & displayed terminal boutons	a
SUM	ENT	3	3	1	Swa82	VTA129	pg330-3, fig13, table2	F	3	SUMI	Over 2/3 of labeled cells in expts involving ENT found in MBO. Vast majority of these, (all non dopaminergic) located in lateral part of supramammillary region (ips). <Table2: 59% of all cells labeled found in SUMI>	ENT1	TB & bizbenzimid inj, see fig6F, spread into PIR & other parts of cortex none of which receive input from VTA	r
			1	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,175, fig4	P	1	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	ENT	At least some labeled fibres found in all layers of entorhinal area, although plexuses of varicose fibres were clearly most frequent in deeper layers (III-VI)	a
SUM	PAR	1	1	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,175, fig4	P	1	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	PAR	In presubiculum & parasubiculum, occasional plexuses of labeled fibres found in layer VI	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	SUM	... labeled neurons in ... supramammillary nucleus...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
SUM	POST	c	c	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3	F	-1	SUM	Subcortically, neurons were labeled in ... supramammillary region...	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
SUM	PRE	1	1	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,175, fig4	P	1	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	PRE	In presubiculum & parasubiculum, occasional plexuses of labeled fibres found in layer VI.	a
			c	1	vGr90c	f8	pg232	F	-1	SUM	Subcortically, cells labeled in ... supramammillary region ...	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
SUM	SUB	2	2	1	Haglund84	MAE20	pg173,175, fig4	P	2	SUMI	injection of PHA-L (MAE-20) labeled neurons in rostral 2/3s of lateral part of supermammillary nucleus, as well as a few neurons in adjacent parts of posterior & lateral hypothalamic areas adj to rostral tip of nucleus.	SUB	labeled fibres mostly found in superficial part of molecular layer & in deeper parts of pyramidal layer of subiculum itself	a
SUM	LM	2	2	1	Gonz92	lm	pg283,286-8, fig14,15	W	2	SUM	In all expts, retrogradely labeled cells found ... particularly in SuM. Rostral: few labeled cells scattered in medial part of ipsilateral SuM. At caudal levels, moderate retrograde labeling present in lateral caudal SuM.	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
SUM	MM	1	1	2	Gonz92	mm	pg279,283	W	1	SUM	There were a few labeled cells in supramammillary nucleus. Most obvious projection from SuM found towards pars posterior of MMN (R-12, R-24)	MM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... Inj sites depicted in fig3. representative cases into different subdivisions of medial mammillary nucleus & surrounding hypothalamic regions in 8 animals. <few representative cases are wholly in MM>	r
					Gonz92	R12r	pg283, fig8	W	1	SUM	In particular, retrogradely labeled cells were seen in SuM. Rostral lvls: scattered in medial part of SuM. Middle lvls: labeled cells seen in lateral parts of SuM. Caudal lvls: large numbers of cells seen in lateral part of SuM: Semilunar shaped region...	MM	Very small injection centred in caudal 1/3 of pars posterior of left MMN	r
SUM	PL	1	1	1	Zen91	f5a	pg293,5, fig5,6B	F	1	SUM	hypothalamus contained a few, lightly labeled cells in supramammillary nucleus & a few labeled cells in lateral hypothalamic area	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	r
SUM	PRh	1	1	1	Sw82	VTA129	pg330-3, fig13, table2	F	1	SUMm	<Fig13: only few cells in SUMm, Table2: 2% of all cells labeled found in SUMm>	ENTI/PRh/ECT/PIR	lateral part of entorhinal area injected in 5 animals, true blue(4), bisbenzimid(1). In each expt inj spread dorsally into overlying regions of neocortex & in some expts into piriform cortex. None spread to other parts of HPF	r
SUM	AD	1	1	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f5	pg250, fig5,11	H	1	SUM	Some neurons were observed bilaterally in supramammillary nucleus. <Fig5: Small number of cells on 1 diagram out of 4>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
TM	LM	1	1	1	Gonz92	lm	pg283,288, fig14,15	W	1	TM	Very few labeled cells (2/3 per section) were also seen in all subdivisions of the contralateral tuberomammillary nucleus	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
TM	MM	1	1	1	Gonz92	mm	pg279,283	W	1	TM	all injns focussed on pars medianus & medialis of MMN, as in animal R6, resulted in retrograde bilateral labeling of a few neurons... appeared to be situated in lateral subdivision of tuberomammillary nucleus	MM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... Inj sites depicted in fig3. representative cases into different subdivisions of medial mammillary nucleus & surrounding hypothalamic regions in 8 animals. <few representative cases are wholly in MM>	r
TM	PRh	2	2	1	Sw82	VTA129	pg330-3, table2	F	2	TM	In addition, some cells were found on both sides of the brain ... in tuberomammillary nucleus <Table2: 10% of all labeled cells are found in TM: moderate>	ENTI/PRh/ECT/PIR	lateral part of entorhinal area injected in 5 animals, true blue(4), bisbenzimid(1). In each expt inj spread dorsally into overlying regions of neocortex & in some expts into piriform cortex. None spread to other parts of HPF	r
ACA	ENT	1	1	1	Be79	FC20	pg47,49, fig5	A	1	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MD1). Deposit in cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	ENTI	few labelled axons are present in lateral entorhinal area but none are detected in perirhinal cortex	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			0	1	Be79	FC37	pg46, fig4	A	0	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	ENT	No label above background level was detectable in perirhinal, entorhinal cortices or the presubiculum.	a
ACA	PAR	0	0	1	Vo83	f16a	pg206, fig16A	A	0	ACAv	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	PAR	no labelling in area 49	a
ACA	POST	2	2	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	ACA	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... infraradiata cortices. Further rostral, neurons were labeled in layer V of caudal part of area infraradiata (IRbB & IRcB), <Fig5: moderate>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
			0	1	Vo83	f16a	pg206, fig16A	A	0	ACAv	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	POST	no labelling in area 48	a
ACA	PRE	2	2	1	Be79	FC20	pg49, fig5	A	2	ACA	3H A.A. inj. into posterior ACA	PRE	labeling in dorsal presubiculum is quite dense & is continuous across stratum lacunosum into at least the dorsal margin of the ventral presubiculum.	a
			0	2	Vo83	f16a	pg206, fig16A	A	0	ACAv	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	PRE/???	no labelling in area 27	a
					Be79	FC37	pg46, fig4	A	0	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	PRE	No label above background level was detectable in perirhinal, entorhinal cortices or the presubiculum.	a
ACA	LM	2	2	1	Gonz92	lm	pg283,286, fig14,15	W	2	ACA	retrograde cortical labeling also present ipsilaterally in prefrontal cortex, principally in infralimbic cortex and in cingulate gyrus	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
ACA	MM	2	2	1	All&Hop89	a	pg317, fig10	W	2	ACA	Most of retrogradely labeled neurons located in deep layers of infralimbic area while fewer labeled neurons were found rostrally & dorsally in or near layer V of prelimbic and anterior cingulate areas.	MM	injs of WGA-HRP into medial mammillary nucleus. Inj centred in medial part of medial mammillary nucleus, with spread into lateral parts of medial mammillary nucleus.	r
ACA	ILA	c	c	1	Vo83	f16a	pg201-4, fig16A	A	-1	ACAv	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	ILA	...labeled projections to anterior cingulate cortex confined to area 24b, caudal area 32, dorsal area 25	a
ACA	PL	c	c	1	Vo83	f16a	pg201-4, fig16A	A	-1	ACAv	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	PL	...labeled projections to anterior cingulate cortex confined to area 24b, caudal area 32, dorsal area 25	a
ACA	PRh	2	2	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	2	ACAd	labels cells in ... dorsal anterior cingulate cortex, cells found contralaterally	PRh/PRh/T Ev/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERI>	r
			0	2	Be79	FC37	pg46, fig4	A	0	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	PERI	No label above background level was detectable in perirhinal, entorhinal cortices or the presubiculum.	a
					Be79	FC20	pg47,49, fig5	A	0	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	PERI	few labelled axons are present in lateral entorhinal area but none are detected in perirhinal cortex	a
ACA	RSP	3	3	1	Be79	FC20	pg48, fig5	A	3	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	RSP	more caudal injection of area 34 results in extensive fiber-labeling throughout rostrocaudal extent of retrosplenial cortex. <fig5: mod/dense>	a
			2	7	Fin84	c67	pg477, fig2, table1	W	2	ACA	Labeling was also seen in the ipsilateral cingulate cortex rostral and caudal to the injection site and cells quite distant could be labeled. This indicates a cingulocingulate associational pathway. {2,3,4,5}	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Vo83	f2	pg194,204, fig2	W	2	ACAd	Within cingulate cortex ... limited neuronal filling in layers V & VI of rostral areas 24a & 24b... posterior area 24 had extensive neuronal labeling throughout all cellular layers	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202	F	2	ACA	labelled more cells in ventral IRB <more than rostral inj: CFR163>	RSPd	FG injection into caudal Rdg	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	2	ACA	A few labelled cell bodies were present in IRb, mostly in rostral third. In rostral IRb6 and IRcB, <rostrorodorsal IR> relatively large number of neurons labelled in {3,4,5}. few contra. neurons in {5}	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202	F	2	ACA	labelled more cells in dorsal IRb <more than caudal inj: CFR164>	RSPd	FG injection into rostral Rdg	r
					Vo83	f2	pg194,204, fig2	W	2	ACA _v	Within cingulate cortex ... limited neuronal filling in layers V & VI of rostral areas 24a & 24b... posterior area 24 had extensive neuronal labeling throughout all cellular layers	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig7, obs	F	2	ACA	labeled neurons ipsilaterally in ... area infraradiata, a significant number of labeled neurons were seen in {5}. More neurons seen in caudal IR with rostral Rga injections, and caudal Rga injections label rostral IR. <density taken from fig7>	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
			1	3	Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	1	ACA	projections to posterior cingulate regions derived from the anterior and middle cingulate cortex, (10-25 somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
					Vo83	f16a	pg203-4, fig16A	A	1	ACA _v	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	RSPv	terminal labelling within posterior cingulate cortex was light and restricted to rostral parts of 29a and b	a
					Be79	FC37	pg46, fig4	A	1	ACA	3H A.A. inj. into anterior ACA _d /ACA _v	RSP	Labeled fibres course caudalward in cingulum bundle & distribute lightly within retrosplenial cortex	a
			c	3	Horikawa88	h	pg41	F	-1	ACA	... area A24	RSP	Structures containing labeled neurons following inj of tracer into area 29 were ...	r
					vGr92	PL63	pg203, fig5B	P	-1	ACA	PHA-L injection into IRb	RSPd	labelled axons and terminals in {1,5,6}	a
					Vo83	f16C	pg204, fig16C	A	-1	ACA _d /ACA _v /MOs	large inj into area 24b that also partially involved areas 24a & 8 ...	RSP	... labeled terminals in all subdivisions are 29 and areas 18a & 18b.	a
			0	2	Vo83	f16a	pg203-4, fig16A	A	0	ACA _v	3H A.A. injection confined to area 24a	RSPd	labelling restricted to 29a,c	a
					Vo83	f16B	pg204, fig16B	A	0	PL/PL/ACA _v /ILA	Large [3H]-amino acid injection into area 32 that also involved parts of areas 24a & 25...	RSP	Labeling (in area 29) was absent following injection predominantly involving area 32	a
ACA	AD	0	0	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	0	ACA	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
ACA	AM	3	3	2	Be79	FC37	pg46,53, fig4	A	3	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Pre) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	AM	... results in labeling of fibres, traversing & terminating within both ventral & dorsal parts of reticular nuc, & distributing sparsely to PT, LD, RE & medial part of LH & more densely to MD, AM & VM. <Label appears dense in fig4>	a
					Be79	FC20	pg47,53, fig5	A	3	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	AM	In case FC20, labeled fibres enter over superior thalamic peduncle ... terminate primarily in caudal part of MD & densely throughout anteromedial nucleus.	a
			x	1	Dome69	abstract, fig8		-1	ACA		AM			
ACA	AV	1	1	1	Be79	FC20	pg47,53, fig5	A	1	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	AV	In case FC20, labeled fibres enter over superior thalamic peduncle ... course medially through nucleus lateralis dorsalis & anteroventral nucleus.	a
			0	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	0	ACA	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
ACA	LD	2	2	1	Be79	FC20	pg47,53, fig5	A	2	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	LD	In case FC20, labeled fibres enter over superior thalamic peduncle ... course medially through nucleus lateralis dorsalis & anteroventral nucleus.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	4	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	1	ACAv	Retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in retrosplenial area 29c (pyramidal in {5,6}), & to a lesser extent in anterior cingulate areas 24a, & 24b	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Be79	FC37	pg46,54, fig4	A	1	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	LD	... results in labeling of fibres, traversing & terminating within both ventral & dorsal parts of reticular nuc, & distributing sparsely to PT, LD, RE & medial part of LH & more densely to MD, AM & VM.	a
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	1	ACAd	Retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in retrosplenial area 29c (pyramidal in {5,6}), & to a lesser extent in anterior cingulate areas 24a, & 24b	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	1	ACA	A few labeled neurons were found in {5,6} of cortical area 24	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
ACA	MD	3	3	2	Groene88	lat-r	pg399, fig16,17	W	3	ACAd	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present in dense pattern in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate & in medial part of medial precentral cortex.	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	r
					Groene88	lat-r	pg399, fig16,17	W	3	ACAv	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present in dense pattern in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate & in medial part of medial precentral cortex.	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	r
			2	4	Corn&Phil88	1	pg1037,1038, fig2	W	2	ACA	retrograde label found in anterior cingulate 'shoulder' cortex (Area24) throughtout its rostrocaudal extent. Label present in deep layers (mainly lamina VI with some labeling of lamina V) of cortex at all levels; most dense immediately rostral to head of CP.	MDI	Injected WGA labeled lateral MD towards ros end. Darkly staining inj site completely confined to lateral MD, larger halo of less densely stained cells involved very small part of adj centrolateral nucleus & central MD.	r
					Be79	FC20	fig5, obs	A	2	ACA	3H A.A. inj. into posterior ACA	IMD		a
					Be79	FC20	pg47,53,55, fig5	A	2	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	MDI	In case FC20 ... labeled fibres present only in dorsal and caudal parts of the lateral subnucleus of MD.	a
					Be79	FC37	pg46,54, fig4	A	2	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	MDI	... results in labeling of fibres, ... more densely to MD, AM & VM. label present mainly in lateral subnuc, but is less dense in ventral parts of that segment of MD	a
			1	1	Be79	FC37	pg46,54, fig4	A	1	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	MDC	... results in labeling of fibres, traversing & terminating within both ventral & dorsal parts of reticular nuc, & distributing sparsely to PT, LD, RE & medial part of LH & more densely to MD, AM & VM.	a
			c	2	Hu91	R478	pg266, fig10	W	-1	ACA	In both cases, an unbroken band of retro labeled neurons in layer VI throught from dorsal peduncular cortex, through ILC & prelimbic cortex & into anterior cingulate cortex.	MD/MD/PV T	In experiments R478 & R579, injections of WGA-HRP placed in meiodorsal nucleus including border zone with paraventricular nucleus of thalamus	r
					Thier83	a	pg277, fig1	E	-1	ACA	Recorded cells were mainly found in caudal part of medial prefrontal cortex. In all cases neurons mainly located in layers V & VI, none found in superficial cortical layers. <Fig1(MD): neurons appear located in PL, ACA & MOs, cannot estimate density>	MD	Neruons from mPFC antidromically driven by electrical stimulation of either MD, VMT, SN or SC.	r
			0	3	Be79	FC20	pg47,53,55, fig5	A	0	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	MDC	In case FC20 ... labeled fibres present only in dorsal and caudal parts of the lateral subnucleus of MD.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>I</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Be79	FC37	pg46,54, fig4	A	0	ACA	In case FC37, small deposit of label centred in ventral part of anterior cingulate area (A24) at level of genu corporis callosi. Inj appears to involve both dorsal & ventral divisions (Kret&Prc) in ACA both of which receive affs from MDI.	MDm	no labeled fibres are present in medial subnucleus in case FC37	a
					Be79	FC20	pg47,53,55, fig5	A	0	ACA	In case FC20, small dep in ven part of area 24, but more posterior than FC37 (area characterised by input from MDI). Deposit inv cortex of same cytoarch app as supragenual area, does not encroach of caudally contiguous retrosplenial cortex.	MDm	In case FC20 ... labeled fibres present only in dorsal and caudal parts of the lateral subnucleus of MD.	a
			x	2	Dome69 Quim91	abstract abstract	fig8	-1	-1	ACA ACA	{6}	MDI MD		
ILA	CA1	1	1	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,258, fig3	P	1	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	CA1slm	Hippocampus proper contained only a few PHA-L labeled fibres, mainly in a molecular layer of CA1 cell field. These fibres were of a relatively thin caliber & generally smooth with occ branches that demonstrated clusters of boutons.	a
ILA	ENT	2	2	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,258, fig3	P	2	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	ENTl	Lateral entorhinal cortex received a projection of medium caliber fibres with boutons which were primarily distributed to deeper cortical layers. A few labeled fibres were observed in ayers I & III... Contra entorhinal cortex did not contain any fibres.	a
			0	1	De83	RS3	pg178, fig14,16	H	0	ILA	Except for labelling a few cells in prelimbic cortex, labeled cells in frontal cortex are almost completely absent	ENT/ECT/T Ev/SUB/???	HRP injection into the postrhinal area which covers both banks of the rhinal sulcus and possibly extends partially into ectorhinal cortex on the one side and ENTm on the other <Massive inj into ENT/ECT/TEv/SUB and underlying white matter>	r
ILA	PRE	1	1	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,258, fig3	P	1	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	PRE	dorsal & ventral presubiculum innervated by fibres with comparatively fewer varicosities...	a
ILA	SUB	0	0	1	De83	RS3	pg178, fig14,16	H	0	ILA	Except for labelling a few cells in prelimbic cortex, labeled cells in frontal cortex are almost completely absent	ENT/ECT/T Ev/SUB/???	HRP injection into the postrhinal area which covers both banks of the rhinal sulcus and possibly extends partially into ectorhinal cortex on the one side and ENTm on the other <Massive inj into ENT/ECT/TEv/SUB and underlying white matter>	r
ILA	LM	2	2	1	Gonz92	lm	pg283,286, fig14,15	W	2	ILA	retrograde cortical labeling also present ipsilaterally in prefrontal cortex, principally in infralimbic cortex and in cingulate gyrus	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r
ILA	MM	3	3	2	All&Hop89	a	pg317, fig10	W	3	ILA	Most of retrogradely labeled neurons located in deep layers of infralimbic area while fewer labeled neurons were found rostrally & dorsally in or near layer V of prelimbic and anterior cingulate areas.	MM	injs of WGA-HRP into medial mammillary nucleus. Inj centred in medial part of medial mammillary nucleus, with spread into lateral parts of medial mammillary nucleus.	r
					Hu91	R674	pg261	P	3	DPC/DPC/I LC	PHA-L inj site included few neurons in ventral ILC but principally involved dorsal peduncular cortex.	MM	Only dense band of labelled fibres along dorsal border of medial mammillary nucleus demonstrated PHA-L labeled fibres	a
			2	3	Shib89	R306	pg445, fig13	W	2	ILA	Following an injection involving all layers of infralimbic area (R306) ...	MM	Labeled terminals observed bilaterally in rostral 1/2 of MM. At rostral levels terminals were located in dorsal 1/3 of MM, whereas more caudally, they were seen only along dorsal margin of MM. <fig13: overall moderate>	a
					Shib89	R289	pg437, fig1	W	2	ILA	There were many labeled cells mainly in layer V of bilateral infralimbic area & a small number in layer V of prelimbic area	MM	In case R289, WGA-HRP was injected into the rostral median region of the MM, spreading slghtly to the supramammillary & dorsal premammillary nuclei.	r
					Haya93	S44	pg142, fig4	P	2	ILC/DPC	In case S44, PHA-L injected into ventral part of infralimbic cortex & rostradorsal part of dorsal peduncular cortex	MM	fibers produced horzntl band of terminal field including ventral surface of SUM & dorsal surface of medial mammillary nucleus. Many labeled terminals seen bilaterally in this area. Only few labeled fibres in dorsal part of SUM	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			1	1	Ta91	R102	pg28, fig2K-N	P	1	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invading adjacent PL or TT.	MM	A few lightly labeled & terminals were seen in ... medial mammillary & supramammillary nuclei. <Fig2 ???>	a
			c	2	Hu91 Shib89	R674s R309	pg263 pg438-9	P W	-1	DPC ILA	In one series of control experiments (R674, R812, & R862) injections were centred in dorsal peduncular cortex. ... labeled cells were seen in similar areas to those in case R289, ... within cortical regions, number of labeled cells in retrosplenial cortex, induseum griseum and infralimbic area was smaller in this case.	MM MMI/MMI/ MMm/SUM	Following an injection into the more lateral region within rostral MM (R309) ...Injection was centred in pars lateralis of rostral MM, spreading to dorsal premammillary nucleus & slightly to supramammillary nucleus parse medialis of MM	a r
			0	1	Haya93	S46	pg142, fig4	P	0	ILC	PHA-L injected into dorsal part of infralimbic cortex in case S46, ...	MM	a few labeled fibres present in SUM, although there were none in medial mammillary nucleus.	a
ILA	SUM	3	3	2	Haya93 Hu91	S73 R651	pg140, fig2, Table1 pg251-3,261, fig3	W P	3	DPC ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	Many retrogradely labeled cells found bilaterally in dorsal peduncular cortex... labeled neurons of dorsal peduncular cortex were in lamina III to V. <Table1: Inj site SUM: Dorsal Peduncular cortex: +++, more than 6 cells per section> 9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	SUM SUM	In case S73, centre of WGA-inj site was in ventral part of SUM, & just medial to mammillothalamic tract. Halo of WGA deposit extended to median & lateral subnuclei of SUM, but not to medial mammillary nucleus. In expt R651, numerous medium & fine caliber labeled fibres with terminal processes were found throughout the supramammillary nucleus.	r a
			2	3	Haya93	S73	pg140, fig2, Table1	W	2	ILC	several labeled cells were in infralimbic cortex. Labeled neurons of infralimbic cortex located mainly in lamina V. <Table1: Inj site SUM: Infralimbic cortex: ++, 2-5 cells per section>	SUM	In case S73, centre of WGA-inj site was in ventral part of SUM, & just medial to mammillothalamic tract. Halo of WGA deposit extended to median & lateral subnuclei of SUM, but not to medial mammillary nucleus.	r
					Haya93	S31	pg140-1, Table1	W	2	DPC	Similar distribution of cells to that of case S73... <Table1: Inj site SUM: Dorsal Peduncular cortex: ++, 2-5 cells per section>	SUM	In case S31, inj site of WGA-HRP extended to dorsal & ventral parts of SUM.	r
					Haya93	S31	pg140-1, Table1	W	2	ILC	Similar distribution of cells to that of case S73... <Table1: Inj site SUM: Infralimbic cortex: ++, 2-5 cells per section>	SUM	In case S31, inj site of WGA-HRP extended to dorsal & ventral parts of SUM.	r
			1	3	Haya93 Ta91 Haya93	S46 R102 S44	pg142, fig4 pg28, fig2K-N pg142, fig4	P P P	1 1 1	ILC ILA ILC/DPC	PHA-L injected into dorsal part of infralimbic cortex in case S46, ... Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invading adjacent PL or TT. In case S44, PHA-L injected into ventral part of infralimbic cortex & rostradorsal part of dorsal peduncular cortex	SUM SUM SUM	a few labeled fibres present in SUM, although there were none in medial mammillary nucleus. A few lightly labeled & terminals were seen in ... medial mammillary & supramammillary nuclei. <Fig2 ???> fibers produced horzntl band of terminal field including ventral surface of SUM & dorsal surface of medial mammillary nucleus. Many labeled terminals seen bilaterally in this area. Only few labeled fibres in dorsal part of SUM	a a a
			0	1	Hu91	R674	pg261	P	0	DPC/DPC/I LC	PHA-L inj site included few neurons in ventral ILC but principally involved dorsal peduncular cortex.	SUM	Only dense band of labelled fibres along dorsal border of medial mammillary nucleus demonstrated PHA-L labeled fibres	a
ILA	TM	3	3	2	Eric91 Hu91	DB14 R651	pg53, fig6A, Table2 pg251-3,260, fig3	P P	3	ILA ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	PHA-L experiments showed heavy projections from infralimbic cortex... 9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	TMv TM	Major part of labeled fibres innervated are just medial to TMV where some entered into the interior of the nucleus. <Table2: Region injected: Infralimbic cortex, Density of innervation: +++ (Terminal-like profiles, heavy labeling)>	a a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T		
ILA	ACA	2	2	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,257, fig3	P	2	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	ACA	dorsal efferent pathway from ILC innervaed mainly layers I, V, & VI of prelimbic and anterior cingulate cortex.	a		
					1	2	Ta91	R102	pg27, fig2	P	1	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	ACAv	In midline cortical structures lying caudal to inj site, a few labeled fibres & terminals observed in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate cortices. <Fig2: sparse>	a
							Ta91	R102	pg27, fig2	P	1	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	ACAd	In midline cortical structures lying caudal to inj site, a few labeled fibres & terminals observed in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate cortices. <Fig2: sparse>	a
					c	1	Hu91	R38	pg264	W	-1	ILC	... which resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in layer III & superficial portion of layer V of ILC	ACA	Inj of WGA-HRP made into anterior cingulate cortex in R38...	r
ILA	PL	2	2	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,257, fig3	P	2	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	PL	dorsal efferent pathway from ILC innervaed mainly layers I, V, & VI of prelimbic and anterior cingulate cortex.	a		
					c	2	Hu91	R720	pg264	W	-1	ILC	... retrogradely labelled neurons in ILC which formed a band in layer II, were loosely scattered throughout layer III & formed another band in deep portion of layer V.	PL	Injections of WGA-HRP made into prelimbic cortex (R720 & R721) ...	r
							Hu91	R674s	pg263	P	-1	DPC	In one series of control experiments (R674, R812, & R862) injections were centred in dorsal peduncular cortex.	PL	In sections through the frontal pole an occasional labelled fibre was observed in layer II or II of either the ILC or the prelimbic cortex	a
ILA	PRh	2	2	1	Ta91	R102	pg28, fig2N	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	PRh	More caudally, labeled axons appeared in perirhinal cortex <Fig2N: mod/dense but cannot be sufficiently sure>	a		
					0	1	De83	RS3	pg178, fig14,16	H	0	ILA	Except for labelling a few cells in prelimbic cortex, labeled cells in frontal cortex are almost completely absent	ENT/ECT/T Ev/SUB/???	HRP injection into the postrhinal area which covers both banks of the rhinal sulcus and possibly extends partially into ectorhinal cortex on the one side and ENTm on the other <Massive inj into ENT/ECT/TEV/SUB and underlying white matter>	r
ILA	RSP	2	2	1	Vo83	f2	pg194, fig2	W	2	ILA	Within cingulate cortex neurons labeled in area 25 below the rostrum of the corpus callosum ...	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r		
					1	1	Ta91	R102	pg27, fig2?, caseR102	P	1	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	RSP	In midline cortical structures lying caudal to inj site, a few labeled fibres & terminals observed in ... retrosplenial cortex <Fig2E: sparse>	a
					0	1	Vo83	f16B	pg204, fig16B	A	0	PL/PL/ACA v/ILA	Large [3H]-amino acid injection into area 32 that also involved limited parts of areas 24a & 25...	RSP	Labeling (in area 29) was absent following injection predominantly involving area 32	a
ILA	AD	0	0	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	0	ILA	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r		
ILA	AM	2	2	1	Ta91	R102	pg29, fig2IJ	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	AM	Labeled fibres & terminals were seen in rostral & medial aspects of anteromedial, anteroventral ... nuclei. Fibres-of-passage predominant in caudal aspects of these structures ...	a		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
ILA	AV	2	2	1	Ta91	R102	pg29, fig2J	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	AV	Labeled fibres & terminals were seen in rostral & medial aspects of anteromedial, anteroventral ... nuclei. Fibres-of-passage predominant in caudal aspects of these structures ...	a
			0	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	0	ILA	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
ILA	IAM	2	2	1	Ta91	R102	pg28, fig2N	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	IAM	Midline thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from IL included ... interanteromedial.	a
ILA	MD	2	2	3	Ta91	R102	pg29, fig2?, caseR102	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	MDm	Midline thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from IL included ... MD... Labeling in MD appeared almost exclusively within medial division	
					Ta91	R102	pg29, fig2?, caseR102	P	2	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	IMD	Midline thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from IL included ... intermediodorsal...	a
					Groene88	rh8168	pg398, fig12,13	W	2	ILA	antero/retrograde labeling consistently present in dense pattern in prelimbic & ventral agranular insular area & less densely in infralimbic area & lateral & medial orbital regions.	MDm/MDm /EPI/PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8168: inj site includes rostral MDm, PVT, slightly strtia medullaris	r
			1	1	Hu91	R651	pg251-3,259, fig3	P	1	ILC/ILC/DP C/PL/ORB m	9 Injs centred in ILC... In expt R651, large inj into ILC ... PHA-L neurons clustered in layer V with few in layers II, III & VI. Inj site extended through roscaw ext of ILC, incl some PL & few neurons in ORBm. Ventral extension into DPC.	MDm	Labeled fibres tended to cluster along medial edge of mediodorsal nucleus where they were orientated in dorsoventral direction.	a
			c	2	Hu91	R478	pg266, fig10	W	-1	ILC	In both cases, an unbroken band of retro labeled neurons in layer VI thought from dorsal peduncular cortex, through ILC & prelimbic cortex & into anterior cingulate cortex.	MD/MD/PV T	In experiments R478 & R579, injections of WGA-HRP placed in meiodorsal nucleus including border zone with paraventricular nucleus of thalamus	r
					Hu91	R478	pg266, fig10	W	-1	DPC	In both cases, an unbroken band of retro labeled neurons in layer VI thought from dorsal peduncular cortex, through ILC & prelimbic cortex & into anterior cingulate cortex.	MD/MD/PV T	In experiments R478 & R579, injections of WGA-HRP placed in meiodorsal nucleus including border zone with paraventricular nucleus of thalamus	r
			0	1	Ta91	R102	pg29, fig2?, caseR102	P	0	ILA	Among 31 expts, 13 involved IL. 10 chosen. Inj sites are depicted in fig1 <R33, R102, R32 & R107 all seem localised to ILA> Inj site in R102 labeled cells in layersIII-VI of caudal & central IL, without invadinf adjacent PL or TT.	MDI/MDc	Midline thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from IL included ... MD... Labeling in MD appeared almost exclusively within medial division	
PL	ENT	2	2	1	Be79	FC3	pg45, fig2	A	2	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	ENTl	Some labeled fibres enter extern & extreme capsules in which they course caudalward to distribute to the perirhinal cortex & the deeper layers of the entorhinal cortex in especiall deeper layers of its lateral division.	a
			1	1	Se89	P364	pg215, fig2,4	P	1	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices.	ENTl	More caudally, labeled axons appeared in perirhinal & lateral entorhinal cortices (Figs 4J-N, 8C). <Fig4: label looks sparse, bilateral in PRh & ENTl>	a
PL	PRE	1	1	1	Be79	FC3	pg46, fig2	A	1	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	PRE	second group of labeled fibres curves around splenium to gain deep layer of dorsal presubiculum	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>		
PL	LM	2	2	1	Gonz92	lm	pg283,286, fig14,15	W	2	PL	retrograde cortical labeling also present ipsilaterally in prefrontal cortex, principally in infralimbic cortex and in cingulate gyrus	LM	single iontophoretic inj of WGA-HRP ... results from 3 representative expts where inj sites well localized in LMN shown in figure 14	r		
PL	MM	2	2	1	All&Hop89	a	pg317, fig10	W	2	PL	Most of retrogradely labeled neurons located in deep layers of infralimbic area while fewer labeled neurons were found rostrally & dorsally in or near layer V of prelimbic and anterior cingulate areas.	MM	injs of WGA-HRP into medial mammillary nucleus. Inj centred in medial part of medial mammillary nucleus, with spread into lateral parts of medial mammillary nucleus.	r		
					Shib89	R289	pg437, fig1	W	1	PL	There were many labeled cells mainly in layer V of bilateral infralimbic area & a small number in layer V of prelimbic area	MM	In case R289, WGA-HRP was injected into the rostral median region of the MM, spreading slightly to the supramammillary & dorsal premammillary nuclei.	r		
					Se89	P364	pg216, fig4	P	1	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices.	MM	Fibres were also visible in premammillary & rostral medial mammillary nuclei.	a		
PL	SUM	1	1	1	Hu91	R767	pg264	P	1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) injs of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	SUM	The supramammillary nucleus contained only a few labeled fibres in case R767.	a		
					c	1	Be79	FC3	pg45,56, fig2DE	A	-1	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price (77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	SUM	lateral fibres continue to distribute from crus cerebri to ... supramammillary area, mainly in its lateral part. <Can't identify structure on fig2>	a
PL	TM	1	1	1	Hu91	R767	pg264	P	1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) injs of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	TM	Labeled fibres were also observed in tuberomammillary nucleus	a		
PL	ACA	3	3	1	Be79	FC3	pg45, fig2	A	3	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price (77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	ACA	Another contingent of lab fibs ... travels caudal in cingulum bundle. This group gives off some fibres to anterior cingulate and retrosplenial areas	a		
					Se89	P364	pg215, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices.	ACAv	Midline cortical structures lying caudal to inj site were innervated by mPFC, including dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate cortices... <Fig4: bilateral (i>c), looks sparse/moderate>	a		
								P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices.	ACAd	dense plexus within & around inj site. These fibres branched & terminated throughout roscaw extent of ACAd. Structures cau to inj site innervated by mPFC, incl ACAd & ACAv... <Fig4: bilateral (i>c), looks sparse/moderate, some extra lab at same lvl as inj>	a		
					Vo83	f16B	pg204, fig16B	A	2	PL/PL/ACA v/ILA	Large [3H]-amino acid injection into area 32 that also involved parts of areas 24a & 25...	limited	ACAv	...labeled terminals mainly in frontal area 11 & anterior cingulate cortices (area 24a with some in area 24b).	a	
					Vo83	f16B	pg204, fig16B	A	1	PL/PL/ACA v/ILA	Large [3H]-amino acid injection into area 32 that also involved parts of areas 24a & 25...	limited	ACAd	...labeled terminals mainly in frontal area 11 & anterior cingulate cortices (area 24a with some in area 24b).	a	
					c	1	Hu91	R767	pg263-4	P	-1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) injs of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	ACA	extensive projections to all area located along medial surface of frontal lobe including layers I, II, III, & V of medial orbital cortex, tenia tecta, dorsal peduncular cortex, ILC & anterior cingulate cortex	a
					Vo83	f15	pg199-200,204, fig15	H	0	PL	HRP positive neurons were not present in areas 32, 48, 49, 29a or 18a & lateral area 17. HRP injs into posterior (fig2) & anterior (fig15) cingulate cortices labeled neurons in areas 25 but failed to label neurons in area 32	ACA/Mos	Injs of HRP into anterior cingulate cortex. These injections also involved area 8	r		
PL	ILA	2	2	1	Se89	P364	pg215, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices.	ILC	A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site. These fibres branched & terminated ... in deep layers ... of infralimbic cortices. <Fig4: bilateral label, moderate>	a		

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	2	Hu91	R767	pg263-4	P	-1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) injs of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	ILC	extensive projections to all area located along medial surface of frontal lobe including layers I, II, III. & V of medial orbital cortex, tenia tecta, dorsal peduncular cortex, ILC & anterior cingulate cortex	a
					Hu91	R767	pg263-4	P	-1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) injs of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	DPC	extensive projections to all area located along medial surface of frontal lobe including layers I, II, III. & V of medial orbital cortex, tenia tecta, dorsal peduncular cortex, ILC & anterior cingulate cortex	a
PL	PRh	2	2	1	Be79	FC3	pg45, fig2	A	2	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	PERI	Some labeled fibres enter extern & extreme capsules in which they course caudalward to distribute to the perirhinal cortex & the deeper layers of the entorhinal cortex in especial deeper layers of its lateral division. <fig2: sp/modmod>	a
			1	1	Se89	P364	pg215, fig4	P	1	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	PRh	More caudally, labeled axons appeared in perirhinal & lateral entorhinal cortices (Figs 4J-N, 8C). <Fig4: label looks sparse, bilateral in PRh & ENTL>	a
PL	RSP	2	2	2	Be79	FC3	pg45, fig2	A	2	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	RSP	Another contingent of lab fibs ... travels caudal in cingulum bundle. This group gives off some fibres to anterior cingulate and retrosplenial areas <fig2: sp/mod>	a
					Se89	P364	pg215, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	RSP	Midline cortical structures lying caudal to inj site were innervated by mPFC including ... retrosplenial cortex... A few fibres were observed in contralateral ... retrosplenial cortex <Fig4: sp/mod>	a
			0	2	Vo83	f2	pg204	W	0	PL	HRP injs into posterior (fig2) & anterior (fig15) cingulate cortices labeled neurons in areas 25 but failed to label neurons in area 32	RSP	WGA-HRP inj into area 29c-d	r
					Vo83	f16B	pg204, fig16B	A	0	PL/PL/ACA v/ILA	Large [3H]-amino acid injection into area 32 that also involved limited parts of areas 24a & 25...	RSP	Labeling (in area 29) was absent following injection predominantly involving area 32	a
PL	AM	2	2	1	Se89	P364	pg218, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	AM	Terminal fibres were apparent in rostral & medial aspects of ... anteromedial & ... thalamic nuclei. Fibres of passage predominantly in caudal aspects of these structures. <Fig4G: bilateral (i>c), sparse/moderate>.	a
			1	1	Be79	FC3	pg45,53, fig2	A	1	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	AM	In case FC3... fibres course, grouped in tiny fascicles, dorsomedially through anteriomedial nuc to parataenial, mediadorsal & lateral habenular nuclei. <Label appears sparse on fig2D>	a
PL	AV	2	2	1	Se89	P364	pg218, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	AV	Terminal fibres were apparent in rostral & medial aspects of ... anteroventral & ... thalamic nuclei. Fibres of passage predominantly in caudal aspects of these structures. <Fig4G: bilateral (i>c), sparse/moderate>	a
PL	IAM	2	2	1	Se89	P364	pg218, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	IAM	Midline & intralaminar thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from mPFC included ... interanteromedial ... nuclei. <Fig4G-I: midline label, sparse/moderate ???>	a
PL	LD	1	1	1	Se89	P364	pg219, fig4	P	1	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	LD	A small number of terminal axons appeared in medial aspects of laterodorsal ... nuclei.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>	
PL	MD	3	3	3	Se89	P364	pg218-219, fig4	P	3	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	MDm	Both medial & lateral divisions of rostral MD contained high density of PHA-L fibres which exhibited ... terminal specializations. At midthal lvls, terminal axons persisted in dorlat MD but appeared sparse in medial & central divisions. Few PHA-L in cau MD.	a	
					Se89	P364	pg218-219, fig4	P	3	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	MDI	Both medial & lateral divisions of rostral MD contained high density of PHA-L fibres which exhibited ... terminal specializations. At midthal lvls, terminal axons persisted in dorlat MD but appeared sparse in medial & central divisions. Few PHA-L in cau MD.	a	
					Groene88	rh8168	pg398, fig12,13	-r	W	3	PL	antero/retrograde labeling consistently present in dense pattern in prelimbic & ventral agranular insular area & less densely in infralimbic area & lateral & medial orbital regions.	MDm/MDm /EPI/PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8168: inj site includes rostral MDm, PVT, slightly stria medullaris	r
2	4				Be79	FC3	pg45,53,54, fig2	A	2	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	MDm	In case FC3... fibres course, grouped in tiny fascicles, dorsomedially through anteriomedial nuc to parataenial, mediodorsal & lateral habenular nuclei... In MD labeled fibres from A32 are densest in lat & med subnuclei surrounding sparsely labeled MDc.	a	
					Be79	FC3	pg45,53,54, fig2	A	2	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	MDI	In case FC3... fibres course, grouped in tiny fascicles, dorsomedially through anteriomedial nuc to parataenial, mediodorsal & lateral habenular nuclei... In MD labeled fibres from A32 are densest in lat & med subnuclei surrounding sparsely labeled MDc.	a	
					Se89	P364	pg218, fig4	P	2	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	IMD	Midline & intralaminar thalamic structures receiving significant terminal projections from mPFC included the ... intermediodorsal ... <fig4H: sp/mod>	a	
					Groene88	rh8196	pg398, fig12,13	-r	W	2	PL	heavy labeling observed in dorsal agranular insular area, whereas label in prelimbic & ventral agranular insular area less heavy than more rostral injections	MDm/MDm /PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8196: inj into caudomedial MD, includes PVT	r
1	4				Groene88	lat-r	pg399, fig16,17	W	1	PL	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present ... sparse labeling marks prelimbic, ventral agranular insular & ventrolateral orbital areas	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	r	
					Com&Phil8	1	pg1037,1038, fig2	8	W	1	PL	In rostral sections, labeling of deep layers (entirely in lamina VI) of prelimbic cortex (area32) continuous with that in area 24	MDI	Injected WGA labeled lateral MD towards ros end. Darkly staining inj site completely confined to lateral MD, larger halo of less densely stained cells involved very small part of adj centrolateral nucleus & central MD.	r
					Se89	P364	pg218-219, fig4	P	1	PL	Inj site in case P364 involved labeled cells in layers III-VI of caudal & central prelimbic area, without invading adjacentdorsal anterior cingulate or infralimbic cortices. A dense plexus of labeled axons visible within & around inj site.	MDc	Both medial & lateral divisions of rostral MD contained high density of PHA-L fibres which exhibited ... terminal specializations. At midthal lvls, terminal axons persisted in dorlat MD but appeared sparse in medial & central divisions. Few PHA-L in cau MD.	a	
					Be79	FC3	pg45,53,54, fig2	A	1	PL	In case FC3, small deposit of radioactive label centred in prelimbic area (a32) & involves cells in all cortical laminae. Inj appears to be confined to area which Krettek & Price ('77b) consider to receive MD-afferents from ant part of med subnucleus.	MDc	In case FC3... fibres course, grouped in tiny fascicles, dorsomedially through anteriomedial nuc to parataenial, mediodorsal & lateral habenular nuclei... In MD labeled fibres from A32 are densest in lat & med subnuclei surrounding sparsely labeled MDc.	a	
c		3			Hu91	R478	pg266, fig10	W	-1	PL	In both cases, an unbroken band of retro labeled neurons in layer VI thought from dorsal peduncular cortex, through ILC & prelimbic cortex & into anterior cingulate cortex.	MD/MD/PV T	In experiments R478 & R579, injections of WGA-HRP placed in meiodorsal nucleus including border zone with paraventricular nucleus of thalamus	r	

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Hu91	R767	pg264	P	-1	PL	In an additional set of control experiments (R767, R852, R855, R858, R859) inj of PHA-L centred in prelimbic cortex. In expt R767 inj confined to prelimbic cortex.	MDm	medial portion of mediodorsal nucleus itself was innervated by prelimbic cortex	a
					Thier83	a	pg277, fig1	E	-1	PL	Recorded cells were mainly found in caudal part of medial prefrontal cortex. In all cases neurons mainly located in layers V & VI, none found in superficial cortical layers. <Fig1(MD): neurons appear located in PL, ACA & MOs, cannot estimate density>	MD	Neurons from mPFC antidromically driven by electrical stimulation of either MD, VMT, SN or SC.	r
PRh	CA1	c	c	1	Kos83	a	pg348	A	-1	PRh H	Following injection of either HRP or tritiated amino acids into perirhinal cortex, ...	CA1	... anterogradely transported labeled was observed either in or over various parts of ipsilateral ... initial part of the hippocampus (CA1a)	a
PRh	CA3	0	0	1	Kos83	a	pg348	A	0	PRh H	Following injection of either HRP or tritiated amino acids into perirhinal cortex, ...	CA3	In no case did injections in area 35 produce evidence of terminal labeling in dentate gyrus or the CA4 & CA3 sectors of the hippocampus	a
PRh	DG	0	0	1	Kos83	a	pg348	A	0	PRh H	Following injection of either HRP or tritiated amino acids into perirhinal cortex, ...	DG	In no case did injections in area 35 produce evidence of terminal labeling in dentate gyrus or the CA4 & CA3 sectors of the hippocampus	a
PRh	PAR	c	c	1	vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	PRh	... labeled neurons in ... perirhinal...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
PRh	POST	2	2	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	PRh	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... perirhinal... cortices. In caudal PRh, layers II, III, and V contained labeled neurons bilaterally. <Fig5: moderate>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
PRh	SUB	c	c	1	Kos83	a	pg348	A	-1	PRh H	Following injection of either HRP or tritiated amino acids into perirhinal cortex, ...	SUB	... anterogradely transported labeled was observed either in or over various parts of ipsilateral subiculum, the transitional area btwn SUB & HIP (prosubiculum)... Most of label confined to deep part of molecular layer, small amount in superfic. molec. layer	a
PRh	PL	2	2	2	Ja89	FG3	pg337,339, fig2	F	2	PERI	group of retrogradely labeled neurons overlapping border between perirhinal & entorhinal cortices could be observed in all injected animals.	PL	In all rats with FG injected into prelimbic cortex (fig1B) ...	r
					Zen91	f5	pg293,5, fig5	W	2	PRh	Some labeled cells were also present in dysgranular insular cortex, agranular insular cortex & perirhinal cortex, predominantly ipsilaterally. <Fig5: moderate>	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	r
PRh	RSP	1	1	1	Pa91	Add11 b	pg443, fig17A	F	1	PRh	Both (Add11) injections produced labelling in ... area 35	RSP	Case Add-11 was injected in ... area 29 (FG/DY)	r
RSP	ENT	2	2	1	vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	2	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	ENT	anterograde labelling in ... entorhinal cortices	a
					vGr92	PL70	pg207	P	1	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	ENTm	a small number of labelled axons extended further ventrally to end in the superficial layers of caudal presubiculum, parasubiculum and medial entorhinal cortex	a
					vGr90d	b	pg600, table1	F	-1	RSPv-a	The projections to entorhinal ... cortex originated in {5} of Rga	ENT	retrograde labeling experiments (FB/FG)	r
					Wysse&vGr9 2a	abstract		-1	RSPd	dysgranular	ENTl	caudal lateral		
					Wysse&vGr9 2a	abstract		-1	RSPv	granular a	ENTm	caudal medial		
RSP	PAR	2	2	3	vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg597	A	2	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	PAR	anterograde labelling in ... the parasubiculum, lighter contralateral labelling	a
					vGr90d	PHA34	pg600, fig2	P	2	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	PAR	Second group of labeled axons gave rise to deeper terminal labeling in POST, PRE and PAR	a
					Vo83	f8	pg197, fig8	A	2	RSPv-bc	An injection that involved area 29c (fig8) <3H a.a.>	PAR	... resulted in labeling of terminals mainly in areas 24b & 29d with less present in 29a, while moderate termination was also evident in areas 49 & 49. Label present mainly in layer I & inner part of ext. pyramidal layer with some grains in inner pyr layer.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	2	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	1	RSPv	Relatively few neurons were labeled in Rga & Rgb cortices. In Rgb cortex they were confined to layer V, but in Rga cortex labeled neurons were in layers II, III & V.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
					vGr92	PL70	pg207	P	1	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	PAR	a small number of labelled axons extended further ventrally to end in the superficial layers of caudal presubiculum, parasubiculum and medial entorhinal cortex	a
			c	1	vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	RSP	... labeled neurons in ... retrosplenial cortices...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
			x	2	Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1	RSPv	granular a		PAR		
					Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1	RSPd	dysgranular		PAR	caudal	
RSP	POST	3	3	1	vGr92	PL70	pg207, fig6	P	3	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	POST	a number of labelled axons extended ventrally to postsubiculum where a dense terminal plexus was labeled in {1,5}	a
			2	6	vGr92	PHA69	pg207	P	2	RSPd	PHA-L injections into rostral Rdg	POST	predominantly labelled axons in dorsal parts of rostral parts of postsubiculum	a
					vGr92	PL159	pg207	P	2	RSPd	PHA-L injections into caudal parts of Rdg	POST	predominantly labelled axons in dorsal parts of caudal parts of postsubiculum	a
					vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5	F	2	RSP	ipsilateral cortical label present in ... retrosplenial ... cortices Injs also bilaterally label neurons in layer V of Rga & Rgb. In midline cortex, rostral to inj site labelled cells were confined to area around border btwn RSPd & RSPv. <Fig5: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
					vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	2	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	POST	anterograde labelling in ... the postsubiculum, lighter contralateral labelling	a
					vGr90d	PHA34	pg597, fig2,4	P	2	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	POST	One group of labeled axons ran through layer I of POST to PRE with the majority of these appearing to terminate in layer I of the the PRE. Second group of labeled axons gave rise to deeper terminal labeling in POST, PRE and PAR. labelled con	a
					Vo83	f8	pg197, fig8	A	2	RSPv-bc	An injection that involved area 29c (fig8) <3H a.a.>	POST	... resulted in labeling of terminals mainly in areas 24b & 29d with less present in 29a, while moderate termination was also evident in areas 49 & 49.	a
			c	2	vGr90b	PHA34	pg173-4, fig8	P	-1	RSPv-a	Injs of Rga cortex (PHA34)...	POST	... labeled axons & terminals in layers I, III & V of postsubiculum.	a
					vGr90b	PHA51	pg174, fig8	P	-1	RSPv-bc	Injs of caudal Rgb (PHA51)...	POST	... labeled a few fibres & terminals in layers I & IV and a large terminal plexus in layers III & V in dorsal part of postsubiculum.	a
			x	3	Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1	RSPd	dysgranular		POST		
					Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1	RSPv	granular a		POST		
					Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1	RSPv	granular b		POST		
RSP	PRE	2	2	2	vGr90d	PHA34	pg597, fig2,4	P	2	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	PRE	One group of labeled axons ran through layer I of POST to PRE with the majority of these appearing to terminate in layer I of the the PRE. Second group of labeled axons gave rise to deeper terminal labeling in POST, PRE and PAR. labelled con.	a
					vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	2	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	PRE	anterograde labelling in ... the presubiculum, lighter contralateral labelling	a
			1	1	vGr92	PL70	pg207	P	1	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	PRE	a small number of labelled axons extended further ventrally to end in the superficial layers of caudal presubiculum, parasubiculum and medial entorhinal cortex	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			c	3	vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	RSPv-a	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in ... retrosplenial cortices. In Rga, Rgb & Rag cortices, labeled cell bodies were found mainly in layer II (5% of total cells). <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
					vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	RSPv-bc	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in ... retrosplenial cortices. In Rga, Rgb & Rag cortices, labeled cell bodies were found mainly in layer II (5% of total cells) <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
					vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	RSPd	... resulted in retrograde labeling of neurons in ... retrosplenial cortices. In Rga, Rgb & Rag cortices, labeled cell bodies were found mainly in layer II (5% of total cells). <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
			0	1	Vo83	f8	fig8	A	0	RSPv-bc	An injection that involved area 29c (fig8) <3H a.a.>	PRE	<NO LABEL ON FIG 8>	a
			x	1	Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract		-1	RSPv	granular a	PRE		
RSP	SUB	0	0	1	Vo83	f8	fig8	A	0	RSPv-bc	An injection that involved area 29c (fig8) <3H a.a.>	SUB	<NO LABEL ON FIG 8>	a
			x	1	Mei77d		abstract		-1	RSP		SUBd		
RSP	MM	2	2	1	Shib89	R289	pg437, fig1	W	2	RSPv	Some large pyramidal cells were also labeled bilaterally in layer V of areas 29a & 29b in retrosplenial cortex at level just above the splenum of cc.	MM	In case R289, WGA-HRP was injected into the rostral median region of the MM, spreading slightly to the supramammillary & dorsal premammillary nuclei.	r
			1	1	All&Hop89	d	pg313, fig1	W	1	RSP	a few retrogradely labeled neurons also found in deep layers of retrosplenial granular cortex.	MM/MM/SUM	case illustrated in figure1, WGA-HRP inj site centred in midline of medial mammillary nucleus & included most of the subnuclei of MM bilaterally. LM spared but some spread into medial SUM	r
			c	1	Shib89	R309	pg438-9	W	-1	RSP	... labeled cells were seen in similar areas to those in case R289, ... within cortical regions, number of labeled cells in retrosplenial cortex, induseum griseum and infralimbic area was smaller in this case.	MMI/MMI/MMn/SUM	Following an injection into the more lateral region within rostral MM (R309) ...Injection was centred in pars lateralis of rostral MM, spreading to dorsal premammillary nucleus & slightly to supramammillary nucleus parse medialis of MM	r
			x	1	Shib89		abstract		-1	RSP		MM	midrostrocaudal & middorsoventral	
RSP	ACA	3	3	2	vGr92	PL70	pg207, fig6	P	3	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	ACA	In IRb cortex a dense plexus of labelled axons and terminals were present , a densest labelling in IRcb <caudal and dorsal>	a
					Vo83	f8	pg197, fig8	A	3	RSPv-bc	An injection that involved area 29c (fig8) <3H a.a.>	ACAd	... resulted in labeling of terminals mainly in areas 24b & 29d with less present in 29a, while moderate termination was also evident in areas 49 & 49. Most terminals in layers I ^ & II of 24b, rest represented fibres of passage.	a
			2	6	vGr92	PHA69	pg207	P	2	RSPd	PHA-L injections into rostral Rdg	ACA	predominantly labelled axons in dorsal parts of IRb	a
					vGr92	PL159	pg207	P	2	RSPd	PHA-L injections into caudal parts of Rdg	ACA	predominantly labelled axons in ventral parts of IRb	a
					Fin84	c74	pg477, fig4, table1	W	2	RSP	Labeling was also seen in the ipsilateral cingulate cortex rostral and caudal to the injection site and cells quite distant could be labeled. This indicates a cingulocingulate associational pathway. {2,3,4,5}	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
					Re90	AC48	pg269, fig5	F	2	RSPd	Labeling is seen in ...the ipsilateral retrosplenial cortex. Label is concentrated in {2,5,6} in both the granular and agranular retrosplenial areas	ACA	The injection site (FG) is located in the anterior cingulate cortex medial to AGm at the level of the anterior commissure	r
					Re90	AC48	pg269, fig5	F	2	RSPv	Labeling is seen in ...the ipsilateral retrosplenial cortex. Label is concentrated in {2,5,6} in both the granular and agranular retrosplenial areas	ACA	The injection site (FG) is located in the anterior cingulate cortex medial to AGm at the level of the anterior commissure	r
					vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	2	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	ACA	anterograde labelling in ... IR	a
			1	2	vGr90d	PHA34	pg597, fig2,4	P	1	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	ACA	In the IRbb and IRb-a cortices only a few fibres were labeled in {2,3}	a
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	1	RSP	anterior cingulate area received afferent fibres originating in somata in the middle and posterior cingulate areas. (10-25 somata in a 40µm thick section)	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	4	Zen91	f4	pg292, fig3,4	W	-1	RSPd	Labeled fibres & cells were also seen in ipsilateral retrosplenial granular cortex and retrosplenial agranular cortex. cells predominantly in layers 3 & 5	ACA	Collectively, WGA-HRP injections covered entire extent of Cg1/Cg2 area.	r
					Horikawa88	g	pg41	F	-1	RSP	Labeled neurons were found in ... area 29 ...	ACA	... only following injection of tracer <FB or RH> into area 24	r
					Zen91	f4	pg292, fig3,4	W	-1	RSPv	Labeled fibres & cells were also seen in ipsilateral retrosplenial granular cortex and retrosplenial agranular cortex. cells predominantly in layers 3 & 5	ACA	Collectively, WGA-HRP injections covered entire extent of Cg1/Cg2 area.	r
					vGr90d	a	pg600, table1	F	-1	RSPv-a	{5,6} neurons providing input to IR cortex	ACA	retrograde labeling experiments (FB/FG)	r
RSP	ILA	0	0	1	Vo83	f5	pg194-6, fig5	A	0	VISM/VIS M/VISp/RS P	A large injection of 3H-amino acids was made into area 18b... inj site may have extended into area 29b & medial area 17.	ILA	Terminal fields in cingulate cortex present mainly in As 24b, 29d, & 29b, a fewer labeled terminals in areas 29a & 29c, least in 24a & none in areas 32 or 25.	a
RSP	PL	0	0	1	Vo83	f5	pg194-6, fig5	A	0	VISM/VIS M/VISp/RS P	A large injection of 3H-amino acids was made into area 18b... inj site may have extended into area 29b & medial area 17.	PL	Terminal fields in cingulate cortex present mainly in As 24b, 29d, & 29b, a fewer labeled terminals in areas 29a & 29c, least in 24a & none in areas 32 or 25.	a
RSP	PRh	x	x	1	Wyss&vGr9 2a		abstract	-1		RSPd	dysgranular		PERI	
RSP	AD	2	2	1	Sek&Zyo84	H79f11	pg250, fig11	H	2	RSP	Distribution of labeled cells in limbic cortex restricted to ipsilateral retrosplenial, postsubicular & presubicular region. <Nom. nonstandard: see fig11>	AD/AD/AV	H-79: inj into the At confined to middle of Adm & halo extended both rostrally & caudally throughout caudal 3/4s of Ad as well as to a very small portion of dorsal limb of Avm at most caudal level.	r
			1	1	vGr90d	PHA34	pg600, fig5AB	P	1	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	AD	Ipsilaterally, a small number of fibres were labelled in the rostral tip of the AD nucleus, and contralaterally only a small number of fibres were labelled.	a
RSP	AM	3	3	1	vGr92	PL70	pg207, fig6	P	3	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	AM	labelled axons arborized extensively and terminated primarily in AM and LD, some labelling homotopic	a
			0	1	Mei&Sie77	C46	pg9, fig1,2	A	0	RSP	In 4 cases injections were placed into the retrosplenial cortex at the level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation. In case 46 inj site restricted to superior portion of retrosplenial cortex adjacent to presubiculum	AM	<Fig1/table1: no label>	a
RSP	AV	3	3	1	vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	3	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	AV	anterograde labelling in ... the AV nucleus of the thalamus, lighter contralateral labelling. Discussion: major efferent projections of Rga are to the AV and LD thalamic nuclei, the caudal Rga, and the contralateral Rga	a
			2	2	vGr90d	PHA34	pg600, fig3C,5B-D	P	2	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	AV	In the thalamus, axons arborized extensively and terminated in ... the rostral half of the AV nucleus. (both magno and parvocellular segments)	a
					vGr92	PL70	pg207, fig6	P	2	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	AV	formed terminal plexuses in reticular, AV, AM, ventrobasal, LD, LP, centrolateral, and reuniens nuclei	a
			c	2	Mei&Sie77	C46	pg9, fig1,2	A	-1	RSP	In 4 cases injections were placed into the retrosplenial cortex at the level of the posterior dorsal hippocampal formation. In case 46 inj site restricted to superior portion of retrosplenial cortex adjacent to presubiculum	AV	Labeled fibres were followed around lateral ventricle & into internal capsule. These fibres then left this bundle to terminate in dorsal 1/2 of anteroventral nucleus	a
					Sri87	c	pg262	F	-1	RSPv	Labeled many neurons in layer V1b & no neurons in layer V... Other injns confirmed that nearly all Rgb projections to anterior thalamus originate in layer VIa of Rgb.	AV	In CF272 a small (10nl) injection of fast blue was confined to the anterior ventral nucleus of the thalamus + several larger injections	
			x	1	Dome69		abstract, fig8	-1		RSPd			AV	
RSP	LD	3	3	2	vGr90d	CIR10 9	pg596	A	3	RSPv-a	Large injections of [3H]A.A. into Rga	LD	anterograde labelling in ... the LD nucleus of the thalamus. Discussion: major efferent projections of Rga are to the AV and AD thalamic nuclei, the caudal Rga, and the contralateral Rga	a
					vGr92	PL70	pg207, fig6	P	3	RSPd	a large injection of PHA-L into middle (rostrocaudal) part of Rdg	LD	labelled axons arborized extensively and terminated primarily in AM and LD, no contralateral labelling	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			2	6	vGr90d	PHA34	pg600, fig3D,5B-D	P	2	RSPv-a	PHA-L injection involving all layers {2,3,4,5,6} in the middle part of Rga	LD	In the thalamus, axons arborized extensively and terminated in the dorsal LD nucleus; rostral in LD in one patchmore caudal in LD in two patches (1 lat, 1 med), no label in con LD	a
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	RSPv	Labeled cells were also found in {5,6} of the ventral retrosplenial cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	2	RSPv-bc	Retrogradely labeled cells were found prominently in retrosplenial area 29c (pyramidal in {5,6}), & to a lesser extent in anterior cingulate areas 24a, & 24b	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f5	pg194, fig5	H	2	RSPd	The most commonly labeled cortical neurons were the pyramidal cells in {6} and to a lesser extent in {5} of dorsal retrosplenial cortex	LD	In fig5, a small HRP injection was placed in the dorsal part of LD just rostral to the anterior pole of the lateral geniculate body. This injection did not involve the ventral medial sector of LD or the anterior nuclei	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	RSPd	Retrogradely labeled cells in the cerebral cortex were found in{5,6} of areas 29b, 29c, 29d	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
					Thomp87	f3	pg193, fig3	H	2	RSPv-bc	Retrogradely labeled cells in the cerebral cortex were found in{5,6} of areas 29b, 29c, 29d	LD/LD/LP	Fig 3: a relatively large injection of LD. The injection was centred in LD, and did not spread to adjacent anterior or central lateral nuclei, very minor spread to ventral and lateral posterior thalamic nuclei. Inj involved dor.lat. and ven.med. LD	r
			0	1	Thomp87	f6	pg195, fig6	H	0	RSPd	No labeled cells were seen in the dorsal retrosplenial area 29d or in the occipital cortex in this case	LD	In fig6, a small injection of HRP was placed in the ventral medial part of LD just lateral to the central dorsal and central lateral nuclei. The injection avoided the intralaminar and anterior nuclei	r
			x	1	Dome69	abstract, fig8		-1	RSPv			LD		
AD	CA1	c	c	1	Reperant87	pg602, fig2		H	-1	AD	... entraîne un marquage neuronal dans ... quatre noyaux du thalamus limbique: ... antérodorsal	CA1	L'injection iontophoretique d'HRP dans CA1	r
AD	CA3	c	c	1	Pak&Akop8 6	a	pg338-9	H	-1	AD	In anterior thalamus labeled neurons discovered in : anterodorsal, anteroventral, anterolateral <LD???, & anteromedial. Ipsilateral only.	CA3	5 animals injected with HP in rostral CA3 according to stereotaxic coordinates. HP inj site was extremely ocnfined & occupied no more than 1/4 of structure under study. <No mention of spread into neighbouring structures>	r
AD	ENT	2	2	2	Shibita93c	R588	pg434, fig12	P	2	AD	In case R588 with inj involving dorsomedial AD ...	ENTl	2 groups of fibres ... reached rostralateral aspect of entorhinal area. Labeled terminals ... moderate in number in ... layers V & VI of entire entorhinal area besides its rostralateral part. <Fig12: sp/mod>	a
					Shibita93c	R588	pg434, fig12	P	2	AD	In case R588 with inj involving dorsomedial AD ...	ENTm	2 groups of fibres ... reached roslat aspect of entorhinal area. Labeled terminals ... moderate in number in ... layers V & VI of entire entorhinal area besides its rostralateral part. A few labeled terminals were found in layer I of the MENT. <Fig12: sp/mod>	a
AD	PAR	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R588	pg434, fig12	P	2	AD	In case R588 with inj involving dorsomedial AD ...	PAR	Labeled terminals ... moderate in number in ... layers I & IV-VI of parasubiculum <Fig12: moderate>	a
			1	1	vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	1	AD	In rostral thalamus a few labeled cells were present in rostral AD nucleus & a relatively large number of cells were labeled in rostradorsal LD nucleus.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r
			c	1	vGr90c	pargen	pg236	F	-1	AD	... labeled neurons in ... anterodorsal...	PAR	Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r
AD	POST	3	3	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5,7	F	3	AD	Subcortically, neurons were labeled ... in AD ... in anterior thalamic nuclei; labeled cells were present predominantly in rostral part of AD... <Figs5&7: dense>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	vGr90b	CIR14	pg174, fig8	A	-1	AD	Injs in AD nucleus (CIR14)...	POST	... labeled axons in postsubicular layers I & III-V	a
AD	PRE	3	3	2	Thomp&Robert87b	pre	pg181-2, fig8	H	3	AD	Within anterior group, labeled cells were found predominantly in AD & AV. <Fig8: dense>	PRE	Injs of HRP placed at various locations within presubiculum in 8 cases. Fig8 presents results from 2 cases with HRP injs in rostromedial & caudal lateral regions.	r
					Shibita93c	R588	pg434, fig12	P	3	AD	In case R588 with inj involving dorsomedial AD ...	PRE	Labeled terminals were numerous in layers I & III of presubiculum & moderate in number in layers IV-VI of presubiculum. <Fig12: dense>	a
			c	1	vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	AD	Subcortically, cells labeled in ... anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus... In rostral thalamus... a few cells in rostral AD, no topography. <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
AD	SUM	c	c	1	Petro83	a	pg292, fig7,8	H	-1	AD	retrogradely labeled cells at borderline between ncl anteroventralis & anterodorsalis (most cells lie in ncl anteroventralis)	SUM	Identical distribution of labeled cells were found in animals with HRP inj into ... anterior part of ncl supramammillaris.	r
AD	ACA	3	3	1	Horikawa88	d	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AD,P24): FB (n=9): 54.5±11.4, RH (n=8): 30.9±4.6	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
			1	3	Fin84	c74	pg471, fig4, table1	W	1	AD	With one exception the anterior dorsal thalamic nucleus was also labeled exclusively after injections into posterior cingulate cortex	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	24b	pg180, fig5	H	1	AD	Within anterior thalamic nuclei, labeled cells concentrated in AM although a very few were found in AD & AV as well. <Fig5: V sparse>	ACAd	4 injections of HRP were placed in cingulate cortical area 24b. In case illustrated in fig5, inj placed in posterior part of area 24b at lvl of rostral pole of thalamus	r
					Horikawa88	a	pg37, fig1,3	F	1	AD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AD,A24): FB (n=9): 8.8±3.6, RH (n=8): 3.0±2.4	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
			0	5	Conde90	c42	pg345	F	0	AD	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were anterodorsal ... nuclei ...	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
					Conde90	c44	pg345	F	0	AD	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were anterodorsal ... nuclei ...	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF288a	pg159, fig14	F	0	AD	No anterior cingulate projecting neurons were observed in AV, AD or LD	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	24a	pg180, fig3,4	H	0	AD	No labeled cells were seen in anterior ventral or anterior dorsal nuclei	ACAv	Injections of HRP were confined to area 24a in 5 cases. In the case illustrated in figs 3 & 4, small inj of HRP restricted to superficial layers of area 24a of left hemisphere. In inj of similar size placed in deeper layers in RHS avoiding I-III	r
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	0	AD	projections to anterior cingulate regions did not derive from the ... the anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
AD	ILA	0	0	1	Conde90	c43	pg345	F	0	AD	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were anterodorsal ... nuclei ...	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
AD	PL	0	0	2	Conde90	c43	pg345	F	0	AD	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were anterodorsal ... nuclei ...	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345	F	0	AD	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were anterodorsal ... nuclei ...	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
AD	PRh	2	2	1	De83	RS9	pg184, fig16	H	2	AD	In the thalamus labeled cells are found in the ... nucleus anterior dorsalis	ECT/ECT/??	An (HRP) injection placed more posterodorsally in the postrhinal area	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			c	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	-1	AD	Subcortical cells are found in the thalamus in ... the nucleus anterior dorsalis	PRh/PRh/T Ev/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERI>	r
AD	RSP	3	3	8	vGr90d	CIR56	pg600-602	A	3	AD	Anterograde injections into AD nucleus	RSPv-a	provided a major projection to layers {1,3,4} of Rga	a
					Horikawa88	b	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AD,A29): FB (n=9): 65.5±6.1, RH (n=8): 39.7±5.8	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29c	pg181, fig7	H	3	AD	Within the anterior thalamus, HRP labeled cells were concentrated primarily in AV & AD, although AM also contained a few labeled cells <Fig7: dense>	RSPv-bc	9 injections of HRP were confined to various locations within the ventral granular retrosplenial cortex	r
					Fin84	c67	pg471, fig2, table1	W	3	AD	With one exception the anterior dorsal thalamic nucleus was also labeled exclusively after injections into posterior cingulate cortex. Nucleus was heavily labeled with a hundred or more cells spearing a single section	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF213	pg148, fig5	F	3	AD	The AD neurons labeled by the ant agran RSP inj were also brightly fluorescent. Most of these neurons were confined to the ventral 2/3 of the nucleus & were most numerous in the middle 1/3 of ros.cau. extentof AD	RSPv	a 50nl inj of FB was placed into the ant. retrosplenial granular a & b cortex. The inj. extended up to but did not appear encroach on the corpus callosum or the deep white matter. extends approx 0.5-2.0mm cau to ant border of Rgb. No spill into agran RSP	r
					Ch92	PPC17	pg239, fig3	F	3	AD	produced concentrated labelling in anterodorsal thalamic nucleus	RSP	medial FG injection was entirely confined to retrosplenial cortex	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF214	pg148, fig6	F	3	AD	As in CF213 ... the greatest number of labelled cells was in the AD & AV. A larger percentage of labeled neurons were located in the ant 1/2 of AD & AV, although some cells over all roscaw extent. Cells more dorsally situated	RSPv-bc	In case CF214 a 40nl FB inj was placed in the Rgb cortex just posterior to the splenium of the corpus callosum and was confined to {1,2,3,4,5} of Rgb	r
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig9,8C, obs	F	3	AD	subcortically, cell bodies were labeled in ... AD nucleus of the thalamus, <density taken from figs 7 & 9>. Discussion: Rga is primarily innervated by the AD, LD, POST, caudal Rgb and contralateral Rga	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
			2	6	Ch92	PPC14	pg240, fig4	F	2	AD	produced labelled neurons in the anterior thalamic nuclei	RSP	a medial FG injection involved the retrosplenial cortex	r
					Shibita93b	R509	pg536, fig8	P	2	AD	In case R509 with injections confined to dorsal part of AD...	RSPv	...labeled terminals seen in layers I, III & IV of RSG <fig8: sp/mod>	a
					Shibita93b	R481	pg536, fig7	P	2	AD	In a case with injection confined to ventral part of AD (R481)...	RSPv	Labeled terminals seen in layers I, III & IV of rostral part of RSG. In layer I labeled terminals were distributed in patches & were denser in superficial part than deep part. <fig7: sp/mod>	a
					Horikawa88	c	pg37, fig1,3	F	2	AD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AD,P29): FB (n=9): 38.4±4.0, RH (n=8): 19.7±13.4	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29d	pg181, fig6	H	2	AD	In both of these cases labeled cells within the anterior thalamic nuclei were concentrated primarily in the AV and were found to a lesser extent in AD & AM <Fig6: moderate>	RSPd	Injections of HRP were placed at various rostrocaudal levels within the dorsal dysgranular subdivision of retrosplenial cortex (area 29d) in 10 cases. fig6 presents results of 2 cases with injections in anterior and posterior portions of 29d	r
					Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	2	AD	projections to posterior cingular regions derived from the ... the anterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus (50+ somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
			1	3	Sri&Wys86	CF270	pg155, fig11	F	1	AD	Within the AV & AD, the relatively few FB labeled neurons were dimly fluorescent and they were situated in the rostral and dorsal portions of each nucleus	RSPd	The results in rat CF270 demonstrate the pattern of thalamic projections to the caudal Rag cortex. The 20nl injection of FB was confined to Rag approx 1mm caudal to the splenium of the corpus callosum	r
					vGr92	PL97	pg204	P	1	AD	Injections into AD	RSPd	very small number of axons and terminals in {1,3,4}	a
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	1	AD	a few neurons were labelled in the anterior nuclei. (eg: AV and AD)	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
			0	2	Shibita93b	R509	pg536, fig8	P	0	AD	In case R509 with injections confined to dorsal part of AD...	RSPd	<fig7: no label>	a
					Shibita93b	R481	fig7	P	0	AD	In a case with injection confined to ventral part of AD (R481)...	RSPd	<fig7: no label>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
AM	CA3	c	c	1	Pak&Akop86	a	pg338-9	H	-1	AM	In anterior thalamus labeled neurons discovered in : anterodorsal, anteroventral, anterolateral <LD???, & anteromedial. Ipsilateral only.	CA3	5 animals injected with HP in rostral CA3 according to stereotaxic coordinates. HP inj site was extremely occluded & occupied no more than 1/4 of structure under study. <No mention of spread into neighbouring structures.>	r
AM	ENT	3	3	1	Shibita93c	R533	pg433, fig1	P	3	AM	(6 cases in total) Case (R533) with PHA-L inj into rostral part of AM.	ENTl	At caudal 2/3 lvls of entorhinal area, numerous labeled terminals found in layers IV-VL of lateral part of ENTl, & layer IV of cau-med part of LENT... Moderate number of labeled terminals found in ... cau-med part of LENT. <Fig1: mod>	a
			2	1	Shibita93c	R533	pg433, fig1	P	2	AM	(6 cases in total) Case (R533) with PHA-L inj into rostral part of AM.	ENTm	At caudal 2/3 lvls of entorhinal area, numerous labeled terminals found in ... caudal part of medial entorhinal area. Moderate number of labeled terminals found in layers I, V, & VI of MENT ... <Fig1: mod>	a
AM	PAR	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R533	pg433, fig1	P	2	AM	(6 cases in total) Case (R533) with PHA-L inj into rostral part of AM.	PAR	Some labeled terminals were seen mainly in lamina interna of parasubiculum. <Fig1: mod.>	a
AM	PRE	1	1	1	Thomp&Robert87b	pre	pg181-2, fig8	H	1	AM	A very few labeled cells were also observed in AM. <Fig8: sparse>	PRE	Injs of HRP placed at various locations within presubiculum in 8 cases. Fig8 presents results from 2 cases with HRP injs in rostromedial & caudal lateral regions.	r
AM	SUB	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R533	pg433, fig1	P	2	AM	(6 cases in total) Case (R533) with PHA-L inj into rostral part of AM.	SUBv	In medial part of temporal subiculum labeled terminals were numerous in deep part of pyramidal cell layer, whereas they were few in molecular layer. <Fig1B: sp/mod>	a
AM	ACA	3	3	7	Shibita93b	R533	pg534-6, fig1	P	3	AM	In case R533 PHA-L labeled cells confined to rostral part of AM. (fig1A,3AB)	ACAd	At rostral lvl of ACA many intensely labeled terminals found in layers I, V & VI especially in their superficial parts of both Cg1 & Cg2. In layers V & VI at caudal lvl, distributed uniformly. <Fig1: dense ipsilateral label.>	a
					Shibita93b	R533	pg534-6, fig1	P	3	AM	In case R533 PHA-L labeled cells confined to rostral part of AM. (fig1A,3AB)	ACAv	At rostral lvl of ACA many intensely labeled terminals found in layers I, V & VI especially in their superficial parts of both Cg1 & Cg2. In layers V & VI at caudal lvl, distributed uniformly. <Fig1: dense ipsilateral label.>	a
					Shibita93b	R613	pg536, fig2	P	3	AM	Following PHA-L injection restricted to caudal part of AM (case 613)...	ACAd	Fewer labeled terminals found in ... layer I and caudal layer V of Cg1 & Cg2. <Fig2: moderate/dense label in Cg1/2>	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	24a	pg180, fig3,4	H	3	AM	Most labeled cells in this case seen in anteromedial nucleus & occurred as a clump in dorsal medial part of AM. <Fig4: mod/dense>	ACAv	Injections of HRP were confined to area 24a in 5 cases. In the case illustrated in figs 3 & 4, small inj of HRP restricted to superficial layers of area 24a of left hemisphere. In inj of similar size placed in deeper layers in RHS avoiding I-III	r
					Shibita93b	R613	pg536, fig2	P	3	AM	Following PHA-L injection restricted to caudal part of AM (case 613)...	ACAv	Fewer labeled terminals found in ... layer I and caudal layer V of Cg1 & Cg2. <Fig2: moderate/dense label in Cg1/2>	a
					Horikawa88	a	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AM	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AM,A24): FB (n=12): 57.3±6.3, RH (n=5): 56.0±13	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj.>	r
					Horikawa88	d	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AM	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AM,P24): FB (n=12): 38.1±5.0, RH (n=5): 30.2±9.9	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj.>	r
			2	4	Fin84	c74	pg473, fig4, table1	W	2	AM	Several thalamic nuclei were labeled after injections into either the posterior or the anterior cingulate cortex. These included most notably the ... anterior medial nucleus	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	2	AM	anterior cingulate area received afferent fibres originating in somata in ... anteromedial nucleus of the thalamus, (50+ somata in a 40µm thick section)	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Thomp&Robert87b	24b	pg180, fig5	H	2	AM	Within anterior thalamic nuclei, labeled cells concentrated in AM although a very few were found in AD & AV as well. <Fig5: moderate>	ACAd	4 injections of HRP were placed in cingulate cortical area 24b. In case illustrated in fig5, inj placed in posterior part of area 24b at lvl of rostral pole of thalamus	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF288a	pg159, fig14	F	2	AM	A smaller number of NY-labeled neurons were in AM & IAM.	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
AM	ILA	2	2	1	Freed91	f4	pg961, fig4	F	2	AM	LHS of thalamus had fewer cells in periventricular & anteromedial nuclei & very few cells in parataenial nucleus	ILA/ILA/ACA	In one IL injection, site on right side limited to layers 1 & 2 of IL, while left side also included deeper layers of IL as well as a small part of anterior cingulate cortex.	r
AM	PL	2	2	1	Zen91	f5a	pg293,5, fig5,6B	W	2	AM	centromedial & anteromedial thalamus nuclei were reciprocally connected to the Cg3 area but not as heavily labeled as MD & PT	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	r
			c	1	Zen91	f5a	pg293,5, fig5,6B	W	-1	AM	centromedial & anteromedial thalamus nuclei were reciprocally connected to the Cg3 area but not as heavily labeled as MD & PT	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	a
AM	PRh	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R533	pg433, fig1	P	2	AM	(6 cases in total) Case (R533) with PHA-L inj into rostral part of AM.	PRh	In perirhinal area numerous labeled terminals seen in layer V & few in superficial part of layer I. <Fig1: mod>	a
			c	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	-1	AM	Subcortical cells are found in the thalamus in ... the nucleus anterior	PRh/PRh/TEv/ECT/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERI>	r
AM	RSP	3	3	9	Shibita93b	R533	pg534-6, fig1	P	3	AM	In case R533 PHA-L labeled cells confined to rostral part of AM. (fig1A,3AB)	RSPd	In RSP, few labeled terminals in most rostral part. More caudally, fibres gave a massive terms to superficial layers I, V & VI of area 29D. Remaining labeled fibres to terminate ... in superficial layer I of cau part of RSP agranular area <fig1: mod/den>	a
					Sri&Wys86	CF213	pg148, fig5	F	3	AM	AM contained less densely packed and more faintly labeled neurons.	RSPv	a 50nl inj of FB was placed into the ant. retrosplenial granular a & b cortex. The inj. extended up to but did not appear encroach on the corpus callosum or the deep white matter. extends approx 0.5-2.0mm cau to ant border of Rgb. No spill into agran RSP	r
					vGr92	PL124	pg204	P	3	AM	PHA-L inj into AM	RSPd	AM provided a major projection to {1,4,5,6}	a
					Ch92	PPC177a	pg239, fig3	F	3	AM	produced concentrated labelling in ... anteromedial thalamic nucleus	RSP	medial FG injection was entirely confined to retrosplenial cortex	r
					Horikawa88	b	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AM	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AM,A29): FB (n=12): 54.7±13.0, RH (n=5): 25.9±9.7	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
					Shibita93b	R613	pg536, fig2	P	3	AM	Following PHA-L injection restricted to caudal part of AM (case 613)...	RSPv	In retrosplenial cortex, labeled terminals were abundant in layers I & V of rostral parts of RSG & RSA, but they were fewer in caudal parts. A few labeled terminals were also found in layer I of area 29D <fig2: mod/den>	a
					Shibita93b	R533	pg534-6, fig1	P	3	AM	In case R533 PHA-L labeled cells confined to rostral part of AM. (fig1A,3AB)	RSPv	In RSP, few labeled terminals in most rostral part. More caudally, fibres gave massive terms to superficial layers I, V & VI of area 29D. Remaining labeled fibres to terminate in layer I of caudal part of RSG close to PRE & in layer V <fig1: mod/den>	a
					Shibita93b	R613	pg536, fig2	P	3	AM	Following PHA-L injection restricted to caudal part of AM (case 613)...	RSPd	In retrosplenial cortex, labeled terminals were abundant in layers I & V of rostral parts of RSG & RSA, but they were fewer in caudal parts. A few labeled terminals were also found in layer I of area 29D <fig2: mod/den>	a
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	3	AM	many neurons were labelled in the anteromedial nucleus (AM)	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
			2	8	Horikawa88	c	pg37, fig1,3	F	2	AM	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AM,P29): FB (n=12): 21.0±14.8, RH (n=5): 21.7±9.2	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Fin84	c67	pg473, fig2, table1	W	2	AM	Several thalamic nuclei were labeled after injections into either the posterior or the anterior cingulate cortex. These included most notably the ... anterior medial nucleus	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29d	pg181, fig6	H	2	AM	In both of these cases labeled cells within the anterior thalamic nuclei were concentrated primarily in the AV and were found to a lesser extent in AD & AM <Fig6: moderate>	RSPd	Injections of HRP were placed at various rostrocaudal levels within the dorsal dysgranular subdivision of retrosplenial cortex (area 29d) in 10 cases. fig6 presents results of 2 cases with injections in anterior and posterior portions of 29d	r
					Ch92	PPC14	pg240, fig4	F	2	AM	produced labelled neurons in the anterior thalamic nuclei	RSP	a medial FG injection involved the retrosplenial cortex	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202, fig4	F	2	AM	labelled greater number of neurons in dorsal and anterior AM, <more than rostral inj: CFR163>	RSPd	FG injection into caudal Rdg	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF270	pg155, fig11	F	2	AM	within AM brightly labeled neurons were situated rostrally. In the most rostral segments, these labeled neurons occupied the ventrolateral portion of the nucleus, but at the level of the mammillothalamic tract invasion of the AM, cells were dor med	RSPd	The results in rat CF270 demonstrate the pattern of thalamic projections to the caudal Rag cortex. The 20nl injection of FB was confined to Rag approx 1mm caudal to the splenium of the corpus callosum	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202, fig4	F	2	AM	labelled greater number of neurons in ventral and caudal AM, <more than caudal inj: CFR164>	RSPd	FG injection into rostral Rdg	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF214	pg148, fig6	F	2	AM	AM contained rather faintly labeled neurons, which tended to be in the lateral half of the rostral AM	RSPv-bc	In case CF214 a 40nl FB inj was placed in the Rgb cortex just posterior to the splenium of the corpus collosum and was confined to {1,2,3,4,5} of Rgb	r
			1	2	Sri&Wys86	CF275	pg155, fig10	F	1	AM	A small number of brightly labelled cells also were labelled in AM & in the dorsal section of the ventral basal complex	RSPd	In rat CF275 a 20nl FB injection was placed into Rag at the same rostrocaudal position as the Rgb injection in CF213.	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29c	pg181, fig7	H	1	AM	Within the anterior thalamus, HRP labeled cells were concentrated primarily in AV & AD, although AM also contained a few labeled cells <Fig7: sparse>	RSPv-bc	9 injections of HRP were confined to various locations within the ventral granular retrosplenial cortex	r
			0	1	Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	0	AM	anteromedial nucleus of the thalamus... these regions could not be demonstrated to project to posterior cingulate cortex	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
AV	CA1	c	c	1	Reperant87		pg602, fig2	H	-1	AV	... entraîne un marquage neuronal dans ... quatre noyaux du thalamus limbique: ... antéroventral	CA1	L'injection iontophoretique d'HRP dans CA1	r
AV	CA3	c	c	1	Pak&Akop86	a	pg338-9	H	-1	AV	In anterior thalamus labeled neurons discovered in : anterodorsal, anteroventral, anterolateral <LD???, & anteromedial. Ipsilateral only.	CA3	5 animals injected with HP in rostral CA3 according to stereotaxic coordinates. HP inj site was extremely ocnfined & occupied no more than 1/4 of structure under study. <No mention of spread into neighbouring structures.>	r
AV	ENT	1	1	2	Shibita93c	R506	p433, fig8	P	1	AV	A case with inj into ventral part of AV (R506)...	ENT	A few labeled fibres reached layers IV-VI of entorhinal area. <Fig8: sparse>	a
					Shibita93c	R680	pg433, fig4	P	1	AV/AV/RT	In 11 cases, injections made into various parts of AV. In case (R680) with inj involving central part of AV at its rostral third level ...	ENTI	A few fibres reached layers V & VI of LENT. <Fig4: sparse>	a
AV	PAR	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R680	pg433, fig4	P	2	AV/AV/RT	In 11 cases, injections made into various parts of AV. In case (R680) with inj involving central part of AV at its rostral third level ...	PAR	Some labeled fibres also terminated in lamina interna of parasubiculum & layers V & VI of MENT. <Fig4: Restricted dense label. moderate>	a
			1	1	Shibita93c	R534	pg433, fig7	P	1	AV	In a case (R534) with inj restricted to dorsal AV; distribution labeled	PAR	distribution of labeled terminals similar to that seen in R532, <Fig7: Moderate but only close to PRE border: sparse>	a
AV	POST	2	2	1	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5,7	F	2	AV	Subcortically, neurons were labeled ... in AV ... with a small number of labeled neurons in rostralateral part of AV. <Fig5: moderate, Fig7: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
			c	1	vGr90b	PHA22	pg174, fig8	P	-1	AV	Ins in AV nucleus (PHA22)...	POST	... labeled a few axons ending in layer I with a few labeled fibres in layer V (these seemed to be fibres of passage)	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
AV	PRE	3	3	5	Shibita93c	R532	pg433, fig6	P	3	AV	At midrostrocaudal level of AV, inj. were confined to dorsal & lateral, dorsal, ventral & medial part. In case R532, an injection involved dorsal & lateral parts of AV.	PRE	Labeled terminals were distributed predominantly in layers I & III of ventral presubiculum. <Fig6: dense>	a
					Shibita93c	R534	pg433, fig7	P	3	AV	In a case (R534) with inj restricted to dorsal AV; distribution labeled	PRE	distribution of labeled terminals similar to that seen in R532, except that labeled terminals were seen in layers I & IV-VI of ventral presubiculum <Fig7: moderate/dense>	a
					Shibita93c	R506	p433, fig8	P	3	AV	A case with inj into ventral part of AV (R506)...	PRE	Many labeled terminals seen mainly in layers I & III of dorsal presubiculum. <Fig8: dense>	a
					Shibita93c	R514	pg433-4, fig10	P	3	AV	2 cases available for injections of AV at its caudal 1/3 level. In a case with injection restricted to dorsolateral part of AV (R514)...	PRE	... only a few labeled terminals seen in layer III at rostral levels of presubiculum, whereas at caudal levels many labeled neurons found in layer I & superficial part of layer III (esp above/below cell islands in layer II) <Fig10: mod/dense>	a
					Shibita93c	R680	pg433, fig4	P	3	AV/AV/RT	In 11 cases, injections made into various parts of AV. In case (R680) with inj involving central part of AV at its rostral third level ...	PRE	many labeled terminals seen in layers I & III of ventral part presubiculum. <Fig4: dense>	a
			2	2	Shibita93c	R557	p433, fig9	P	2	AV	Following inj restricted to medial part of AV (case R557)...	PRE	labeled terminals found predominantly in layers I & IV-VI of dorsal presubiculum. Labeling sparser than that seen in case R506. <Fig9: moderate>	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	pre	pg181-2, fig8	H	2	AV	Within anterior group, labeled cells were found predominantly in AD & AV. <Fig8: moderate>	PRE	Injs of HRP placed at various locations within presubiculum in 8 cases. Fig8 presents results from 2 cases with HRP inj. in rostromedial & caudal lateral regions.	r
			1	1	Shibita93c	R572	pg434, fig11	P	1	AV	Following injection into central part of AV (R572) ...	PRE	... a small number of labeled terminals seen in deep pyramidal cell layer of ...layers I & IV-VI of dorsal presubiculum ... <Fig11: sparse>	a
			c	2	vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	AV	Subcortically, cells labeled in ... anteroventral ... nucleus of the thalamus... In rostral thalamus, labeled cells were present in rostradorsal AV... no topography. <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
					vGr90c	CIR56	pg233	A	-1	AV	Injs in AV (CIR56) nucleus ...	PRE	... resulted in bands of heavy label in layers I & III of the presubiculum	a
AV	SUB	2	2	5	Shibita93c	R506	p433, fig8	P	2	AV	A case with inj into ventral part of AV (R506)...	SUB	In medial part of septal & midsep-temp subiculum, labeled terminals were also numerous in deep part of pyramidal cell layer. <Fig8: moderate>	a
					Shibita93c	R514	pg433-4, fig10	P	2	AV	2 cases available for injections of AV at its caudal 1/3 level. In a case with injection restricted to dorsolateral part of AV (R514)...	SUB	In medialmost part of midsep-temp subiculum, labeled fibres terminated in pyramidal cell layer. <Fig10: sp/mod>	a
					Shibita93c	R557	p433, fig9	P	2	AV	Following inj restricted to medial part of AV (case R557)...	SUBd	In medial part of septal subiculum, labeled terminals seen in deep part of pyramidal cell layer. <Fig9: sp/mod>	a
					Shibita93c	R532	pg433, fig6	P	2	AV	At midrostrocaudal level of AV, inj. were confined to dorsal & lateral, dorsal, ventral & medial part. In case R532, an injection involved dorsal & lateral parts of AV.	SUB	Terminals ...whereas in medialmost part of midseptotemporal subiculum seen in deep part of pyramidal cell layer, they were seen in deep part of pyramidal cell layer. <Fig6: mod>	a
					Shibita93c	R680	pg433, fig4	P	2	AV/AV/RT	In 11 cases, injections made into various parts of AV. In case (R680) with inj involving central part of AV at its rostral third level ...	SUBv	In medial part of midseptotemporal & temporal subiculum labeled fibres terminated in deep part of pyramidal cell layer. <Fig4: mod>	a
			1	2	Shibita93c	R534	pg433, fig7	P	1	AV	In a case (R534) with inj restricted to dorsal AV; distribution labeled	SUB	distribution of labeled terminals similar to that seen in R532, <Fig7: Almost no label shown in SUB, (at level shown)>	a
					Shibita93c	R572	pg434, fig11	P	1	AV	Following injection into central part of AV (R572) ...	SUB	... a small number of labeled terminals seen in deep pyramidal cell layer of medial septal subiculum... <Fig11: sparse>	a
AV	SUM	c	c	1	Petro83	a	pg292, fig7,8	H	-1	AV	retrogradely labeled cells at borderline between ncl anteroventralis & anterodorsalis (most cells lie in ncl anteroventralis)	SUM	Identical distribution of labeled cells were found in animals with HRP inj into ... anterior part of ncl supramammillaris.	r
AV	ACA	3	3	1	Horikawa88	d	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AV	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AV,P24): FB (n=8): 55.0±3.3, RH (n=7): 36.0±5.0	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			1	2	Thomp&Robert87b	24b	pg180, fig5	H	1	AV	Within anterior thalamic nuclei, labeled cells concentrated in AM although a very few were found in AD & AV as well. <Fig5: sparse>	ACAd	4 injections of HRP were placed in cingulate cortical area 24b. In case illustrated in fig5, inj placed in posterior part of area 24b at lvl of rostral pole of thalamus	r
					Horikawa88	a	pg37, fig1,3	F	1	AV	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AV,A24): FB (n=8): 10.8±5.6, RH (n=7): 0.0±0.0	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
			0	6	Thomp&Robert87b	24a	pg180, fig3,4	H	0	AV	No labeled cells were seen in anterior ventral or anterior dorsal nuclei	ACAv	Injections of HRP were confined to area 24a in 5 cases. In the case illustrated in figs 3 & 4, small inj of HRP restricted to superficial layers of area 24a of left hemisphere. In inj of similar size placed in deeper layers in RHS avoiding I-III	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF288a	pg159, fig14	F	0	AV	No anterior cingulate projecting neurons were observed in AV, AD or LD	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	0	AV	projections to anterior cingulate regions did not derive from ... the anteroverntal nucleus of the thalamus	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
					Conde90	c44	pg345	F	0	AV	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were ... anteroverntal nuclei ...	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
					Fin84	c74	pg471, fig4, table1	W	0	AV	The anterior ventral thalamic nucleus was labeled exclusively into the posterior cingulate cortex	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345	F	0	AV	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were ... anteroverntal nuclei ...	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
AV	ILA	0	0	1	Conde90	c43	pg345	F	0	AV	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were ... anteroverntal nuclei ...	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
AV	PL	0	0	2	Conde90	c43	pg345	F	0	AV	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were ... anteroverntal nuclei ...	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345	F	0	AV	in some thalamic nuclei, no labeled neurons were ever found wherever the localization of the injection. These nuclei were ... anteroverntal nuclei ...	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
AV	PRh	1	1	1	Shibita93c	R572	pg434, fig11	P	1	AV	Following injection into central part of AV (R572) ...	PRh	... a small number of labeled terminals seen in deep pyramidal cell layer of ... layers V & VI of perirhinal area. <Fig11: V, sparse>	a
			c	1	De83	RS2	pg178, fig13,16	H	-1	AV	Subcortical cells are found in the thalamus in ... the nucleus anterior ventralis	PRh/PRh/TEv/ECT/ENT	Injection into the caudal perirhinal area <Fig 13: Injection site includes TEv/ECT/ENT as well as PERI>	r
AV	RSP	3	3	9	Shibita93b	R532	pg536, fig6	P	3	AV	After an injection into dorsolateral part of AV at midrostrocaudal level (R532)...	RSPv	... labeled terminals were found in caudal part of RSG with a laminar distribution similar to that seen in case R506. However, in layer I no patchy pattern was recognized . <fig6: dense>	a
					Ch92	PPC177a	pg239, fig3	F	3	AV	produced concentrated labelling in ... anteroverntal thalamic nucleus	RSP	medial FG injection was entirely confined to retrosplenial cortex	r
					Fin84	c67	pg471, fig2, table1	W	3	AV	The anterior ventral thalamic nucleus was labeled exclusively into the posterior cingulate cortex. Nucleus was heavily labeled with a hundred or more cells appearing a single section	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Horikawa88	b	pg37, fig1,3	F	3	AV	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AV,A29): FB (n=8): 72.3±2.4, RH (n=7): 48.7±10.4	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Shibita93b	R506	pg536, fig5	P	3	AV	In cases R506 with an injection into the ventromedial part of AV with midrostrocaudal level...	RSPv	In retrosplenial cortex, many labeled terminals were seen in layers I & V of a rostral part of RSG. Labeled fibres & terminals in layer I distributed in patches. Labeling denser in deeper 3/4 of layer I (less patchy). <fig5: dense>	a
					Shibita93c	R534	pg433, fig7	P	3	AV	In a case (R534) with inj restricted to dorsal AV; distribution labeled	RSP	distribution of labeled terminals similar to that seen in R532, <Fig7: moderate/dense>	a
					Sri&Wys86	CF214	pg148, fig6	F	3	AV	As in CF213 ... the greatest number of labelled cells was in the AD & AV. A larger percentage of labeled neurons were located in the ant 1/2 of AD & AV, although some cells over all roscaw extent. Cells more dorsally situated	RSPv-bc	In case CF214 a 40nl FB inj was placed in the Rgb cortex just posterior to the splenium of the corpus collosum and was confined to {1,2,3,4,5} of Rgb	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF213	pg148, fig5	F	3	AV	In AV most labelled neurons were confined to the ventral 1/3 & were present in both parvo- and magnocellular subnuclei. There was a slight ros to cau preference shift, ros: more cells in parv. cau: more cells in magn.	RSPv	a 50nl inj of FB was placed into the ant. retrosplenial granular a & b cortex. The inj. extended up to but did not appear encroach on the corpus callosum or the deep white matter. extends approx 0.5-2.0mm cau to ant border of Rgb. No spill into agran RSP	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29d	pg181, fig6	H	3	AV	In both of these cases labeled cells within the anterior thalamic nuclei were concentrated primarily in the AV and were found to a lesser extent in AD & AM <Fig6: Projection does not look much larger than AM/AD but take desc into account: mod/dense>	RSPd	Injections of HRP were placed at various rostrocaudal levels within the dorsal dysgranular subdivision of retrosplenial cortex (area 29d) in 10 cases. fig6 presents results of 2 cases with injections in anterior and posterior portions of 29d	r
		2	8		Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	2	AV	projections to posterior cingular regions derived from ... the anteroventral nucleus of the thalamus (50+ somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig9, obs	F	2	AV	subcortically, cell bodies were labeled in ... AV nucleus of the thalamus, <density taken from fig7>	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
					Ch92	PPC14	pg240, fig4	F	2	AV	produced labelled neurons in the anterior thalamic nuclei	RSP	a medial FG injection involved the retrosplenial cortex	r
					Horikawa88	9a	pg37, fig1,3	F	2	AV	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (AV,P29): FB (n=8): 25.5±9.0, RH (n=7): 21.6±12.9	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>	r
					Shibita93b	R532	pg536, fig6	P	2	AV	After an injection into dorsolateral part of AV at midrostrocaudal level (R532)...	RSPd	A few labeled terminals were also found in layers I & V of caudal part of RSA. <fig6: mod>	a
					Sri&Wys86	CF275	pg155, fig10	F	2	AV	In contrast to the labeling pattern in CF213, labeled neurons in AV were confined to a small portion of the caudal, ventrolateral AVpc. These neurons were relatively faintly labeled.	RSPd	In rat CF275 a 20nl FB injection was placed into Rag at the same rostrocaudal position as the Rgb injection in CF213.	r
					Shibita93b	R506	pg536, fig5	P	2	AV	In cases R506 with an injection into the ventromedial part of AV with midrostrocaudal level...	RSPd	Some labeled fibres reached layer IV of adjoining RSG & area 29D, <fig5: sp/mod>	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	29c	pg181, fig7	H	2	AV	Within the anterior thalamus, HRP labeled cells were concentrated primarily in AV & AD, although AM also contained a few labeled cells <Fig7: moderate>	RSPv-bc	9 injections of HRP were confined to various locations within the ventral granular retrosplenial cortex	r
		1	4		vGr90d	CIR14	pg602	A	1	AV	Anterograde injections into AV nucleus	RSPv-a	only light labeling, primarily in {1}	a
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	1	AV	a few neurons were labelled in the anterior nuclei. (eg: AV and AD)	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF270	pg155, fig11	F	1	AV	Within the AV & AD, the relatively few FB labeled neurons were dimly fluorescent and they were situated in the rostral and dorsal portions of each nucleus	RSPd	The results in rat CF270 demonstrate the pattern of thalamic projections to the caudal Rag cortex. The 20nl injection of FB was confined to Rag approx 1mm caudal to the splenium of the corpus callosum	r
					vGr92	PHA49	pg204	P	1	AV	Injections into AV	RSPd	very small number of axons and terminals in {1,3,4}	a
IAM	ENT	2	2	1	Shibita93c	R508	pg433, fig3	P	2	IAM	In one case with PHA-L injection into IAM (R508) ... <Fig3: Inj site close to AM>	ENTl	In caudolateral part of LENT, labeled terminals numerous in layer IV & less numerous in layers V & VI. At more caudal levels a small number of labeled terminals seen in layers I of both MENT & LENT <Fig3: restricted focus spread from PERI, mod/sparse>	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	1	Shibita93c	R508	pg433, fig3	P	1	IAM	In one case with PHA-L injection into IAM (R508) ... <Fig3: Inj site close to AM>	ENTm	At more caudal levels a small number of labeled terminals seen in layers I of both MENT & LENT. <Fig3: sparse>	a
IAM	ACA	2	2	1	Sri&Wys86	CF288a	pg159, fig14	F	2	IAM	A smaller number of NY-labeled neurons were in AM & IAM.	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
IAM	PRh	3	3	1	Shibita93c	R508	pg433, fig3	P	3	IAM	In one case with PHA-L injection into IAM (R508) ... <Fig3: Inj site close to AM>	PRh	Fibres ran further caudally to reach rostrolateral aspect of ... perirhinal areas. Many labeled terminals also seen in layer V of perirhinal area. <Fig3: mod/den>	a
IAM	RSP	2	2	2	Shibita93b	R508	pg536, fig4	P	2	IAM/IAM/A M/RH/RE	In case R508, most of labeled cells were located in IAM throughout its rostrocaudal extent, a few labeled cells were also seen in parts of AM & nucleus rhomboideus & reuniens adjoining the IAM at levels rostral to & caudal to figure 4a	RSPv	A small number of labeled terminals were also present in layers I, V & VI of the RSG & RSA. <fig4: mod>	a
					Shibita93b	R508	pg536, fig4	P	2	IAM/IAM/A M/RH/RE	In case R508, most of labeled cells were located in IAM throughout its rostrocaudal extent, a few labeled cells were also seen in parts of AM & nucleus rhomboideus & reuniens adjoining the IAM at levels rostral to & caudal to figure 4a	RSPd	A small number of labeled terminals were also present in layers I, V & VI of the RSG & RSA. <fig4: mod>	a
LD	CA1	c	c	1	Reperant87		pg602, fig2	H	-1	LD	... entraîne un marquage neuronal dans ... quatre noyaux du thalamus limbique: latéral antérieur	CA1	L'injection iontophoretique d'HRP dans CA1	r
LD	CA3	c	c	1	Pak&Akop86	a	pg338-9	H	-1	LD	In anterior thalamus labeled neurons discovered in : anterodorsal, anteroventral, anterolateral <LD???, & anteromedial. Ipsilateral only.	CA3	5 animals injected with HP in rostral CA3 according to stereotaxic coordinates. HP inj site was extremely occluded & occupied no more than 1/4 of structure under study. <No mention of spread into neighbouring structures.>	r
LD	ENT	1	1	3	vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	1	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	ENTm	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... entorhinal cortex. A small number of labeled axons extended into {4,5,6} of the adjacent caudal, medial entorhinal cortex	a
					vGr92b	PL140	pg433, fig10	P	1	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediodorsal part of caudal LD	ENTm	... axons were labeled in ... medial entorhinal cortex. A few labeled axons extended into the deep layers of the caudal medial entorhinal cortex	a
					vGr92b	PHA41	pg431, fig7	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	ENT	... axons were labeled in ... entorhinal cortex. A few labeled fibres extended to the deep layers {4,5,6} of the caudal, medial & intermediate entorhinal cortex	a
LD	PAR	3	3	1	vGr92b	PHA41	pg431, fig7	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	PAR	... axons were labeled in ... parasubiculum. Other labeled axons ... to form a dense plexus of axons & terminals in the deep layers of the middle part of presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
			2	4	vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	PAR	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... subicular cortex. Some labeled axons coursed further ventrally to form a terminal plexus in {4,5,6} of the ventral part of presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
					vGr92b	PL111	pg434, fig12	P	2	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	PAR	... axons were labeled in ... parasubicular cortex. Many labeled axons extended further caudally to the rostral part of postsubiculum & intermediate (ros.cau) parts of the presubiculum & parasubiculum. Labeled axons in PRE{4,5,6} extended into PAR	a
					vGr92b	CFR223	pg432, fig8	F	2	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	PAR	... labeled axons in ... parasubiculum. The labeled fibres in the deep layers of postsubiculum extended into the deep layers {4,5,6} of the adjacent presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
					vGr90c	CF332	pg237-8, fig9	F	2	LD	In rostral thalamus a few labeled cells were present in rostral AD nucleus & a relatively large number of cells were labeled in rostradorsal LD nucleus.	PAR	Following injections of intermediate part of parasubiculum (CF332)...	r

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	1	vGr92b	PL140	pg433, fig10	P	1	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediadorsal part of caudal LD	PAR	... axons were labeled in ... parasubiculum. A small number of labeled axons in the deep POST extended into the deep layers of the adjacent presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
			c	2	vGr90c vGr90c	PHA41 pargen	pg238 pg236	P F	-1 -1	LD LD	Injs into LD (PHA41) ... labeled neurons in ... laterodorsal...	PAR PAR	... labeled to a dense terminal plexus in layers IV & V Injections of retrograde fluorescent tracing FB or FG in parasubiculum (fig7) ...	r r
LD	POST	3	3	5	vGr92b	PL111	pg434, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	POST	... axons were labeled in ... postsubicular cortex. Many labeled axons extended to the rostral part of postsubiculum & intermediate (ros.cau) parts of the presubiculum & parasubiculum. In POST: dense terminal fields in {1,3,4,5} few axons in {6}	a
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	3	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	POST	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... subicular cortex. Labeled axons formed a dense terminal field in postsubiculum, predominantly in {1,3,4} extending into {5}	a
					vGr92b	CFR22	pg431-2, fig8 3	F	3	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	POST	... labeled axons in ... postsubiculum. More caudally (from 18b terminals), labeled axons formed a ... dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4,5} in the caudal postsubiculum	a
					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	3	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	POST	... labeled terminals primarily in ... postsubicular cortex. Labeled axons ... formed a dense terminal plexus in the middle (ros.cau) part of postsubiculum in {1,3,4} with a few fibres in {5}	a
					vGr92b	PL117	pg436, fig13	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	POST	... axons were labeled in ... postsubicular cortex. Caudally, labeled axons ... a dense terminal field in {1,3,4,5} of the caudal part of postsubiculum	a
			2	2	vGr90b	CF385	pg171,3, fig5,7	F	2	LD	Subcortically, neurons were labeled ... in LD ... LD nucleus contained dimly labeled neurons in dorsal anterior part of nucleus, suggests that these neurons have extensive collaterals terminating in other parts of cortex. <Fig7: sp/mod>	POST	Injections of retrogradely transported tracers in the postsubiculum (CF385)...	r
					vGr92b	PL140	pg433, fig10	P	2	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediadorsal part of caudal LD	POST	... axons were labeled in ... postsubiculum. Labeled terminals were also in ... {1,3,4,5} of the rostral part of postsubiculum	a
			c	2	vGr90b vGr92b	PHA41 PHA41	pg174, fig8 pg429, fig7	P P	-1 -1	LD LD	Injs of LD nucleus (PHA41)... Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	POST POST	... resulted in terminal fields in layers I & III of postsubiculum ... axons were labeled in ... rostral postsubiculum.	a a
LD	PRE	3	3	1	vGr92b	PHA41	pg431, fig7	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	PRE	... axons were labeled in ... middle presubiculum. Other labeled axons ... to form a dense plexus of axons & terminals in the deep layers of the middle part of presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
			2	4	Thomp&Robert87b	pre	pg181-2, fig8	H	2	LD	Labeled cells in LD were located in broad horizontal band that included most of dorsal region of nucleus. Topographic organization was apparent. LD(med) -> PRE(rosmed); LD(lat) -> PRE(caulat) <Fig8: Labeling dense but in restricted part of nucleus: mod>	PRE	Injs of HRP placed at various locations within presubiculum in 8 cases. Fig8 presents results from 2 cases with HRP injs in rostromedial & caudal lateral regions.	r
					vGr92b	CFR22	pg432, fig8 3	F	2	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	PRE	... labeled axons in ... presubiculum. The labeled fibres in the deep layers of postsubiculum extended into the deep layers {4,5,6} of the adjacent presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	PRE	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... subicular cortex. Some labeled axons coursed further ventrally to form a terminal plexus in {4,5,6} of the ventral part of presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
					vGr92b	PL111	pg434, fig12	P	2	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	PRE	Many labeled axons extended further caudally to the ... intermediate (ros.cau) parts of the presubiculum & parasubiculum. In presubiculum a dense terminal field of labeled axons and terminals was in {4,5} with only a few labeled fibres in {1}	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			1	2	vGr92b	PL117	pg436, fig13	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	PRE	... axons were labeled in ... presubicular cortex. Only a few labeled fibres extended into the deep layers {4,5,6} of caudal presubiculum	a
					vGr92b	PL140	pg433, fig10	P	1	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediodorsal part of caudal LD	PRE	... axons were labeled in ... presubiculum. A small number of labeled axons in the deep POST extended into the deep layers of the adjacent presubiculum and parasubiculum	a
			c	2	vGr90c	PHA41	pg233	P	-1	LD	Injs in LD nucleus (PHA41)	PRE	... resulted in relatively light labeled in layers I & III with heavier labeling in layer IV. Most label in PRE/POST border region	r
					vGr90c	f8	pg232, fig8	F	-1	LD	Subcortically, cells labeled in ... laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus... In rostral thalamus, labeled cells were present in ... rosdor LD ... no topography. <Fig8: ???>	PRE	Injections of retrograde tracers FB or FG in presubiculum of rat ...	r
LD	ACA	3	3	3	vGr92b	PHA41	pg429, fig7	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	ACAv	... axons were labeled in rostral infradiata aβ cortex. At the rostral tip of area infradiata β, labeled axons formed a dense terminal plexus in {1} of the rostral part of IRaβ	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	24b	pg180, fig5	H	3	LD	Labeled cells in LD were located predominantly in its ventral sector. <Fig5: mod/dense>	ACAd	4 injections of HRP were placed in cingulate cortical area 24b. In case illustrated in fig5, inj placed in posterior part of area 24b at lvl of rostral pole of thalamus	r
					vGr92b	PL140	pg432, fig10	P	3	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediodorsal part of caudal LD	ACAv	... axons were labeled in infradiata aβ. Axons ... formed dense labeled terminal plexus in {1} of IRaβ.	a
			2	5	Conde90	c44	pg346, fig9	F	2	LD	Lateroposterior, laterodorsal & posterior nuclear group displayed a large number of labeled neurons, only in their medial part, adjacent to external border of CL, wherever location of inj site was in MFC	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
					Fin84	c74	pg473, fig4, table1	W	2	LD	Several thalamic nuclei were labeled after injections into either the posterior or the anterior cingulate cortex. These included most notably the lateral nucleus of the thalamus also called the lateral dorsal nucleus)	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	24a	pg180, fig3,4	H	2	LD	Labeled cells were also prominent in central part of anterior portion of lateral dorsal nucleus. <Fig3: sp/mod>	ACAv	Injections of HRP were confined to area 24a in 5 cases. In the case illustrated in figs 3 & 4, small inj of HRP restricted to superficial layers of area 24a of left hemisphere. In inj of similar size placed in deeper layers in RHS avoiding I-III	r
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	ACAv	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the infradiata cortex. In area infradiata aβ the labeled terminals were predominantly in {1} with a few axons terminating in {4,5,6}.	a
					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	2	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	ACA	... labeled terminals primarily in infradiata bβ. Labeled axons formed a thin terminal plexus in {1,2,3,4} of the intermediate (ros.cau) part of the area IRbβ.	a
			1	3	Woolf84	t7a	table7	F	1	LD	laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus, (10-25 somata in a 40µm thick section)	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
					vGr92b	PL117	pg435, fig13	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	ACAv	... axons were labeled in ... infradiata cβ. A few labeled axons terminated in {1,2,3,4} of the intermediate part of area infradiata cβ.	a
					vGr92b	CFR223	pg431, fig8	F	1	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	ACAd	... labeled axons in infradiata cβ. Small numbers of axons turned rostrally to terminate in {1,4,5} of IRcβ	a
			c	1	vGr92b	PL111	pg433, fig12	P	-1	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	ACA	... axons were labeled in infradiata β. A few labeled axons ran rostrally to form a thin terminal plexus in {1,5,6} <layers 5,6 described as the 'deeper layers'> of the caudal parts of IRbβ, & a denser terminal field in caudal IRaβ	a

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
			0	3	Sri&Wys86	CF288 a	pg159, fig14	F	0	LD	No anterior cingulate projecting neurons were observed in AV, AD or LD	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
					Horikawa88	a	pg37, fig1,3	F	0	LD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (LD,A24): FB (n=6): 0.0±0, RH (n=5): 0.0±0	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
					Horikawa88	d	pg37, fig1,3	F	0	LD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (LD,P24): FB (n=6): 0.0±0, RH (n=5): 0.0±0	ACA	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 24. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
LD	PL	2	2	2	Conde90	c43	pg346, fig9	F	2	LD	Lateroposterior, laterodorsal & posterior nuclear group displayed a large number of labeled neurons, only in their medial part, adjacent to external border of CL, wherever location of inj site was in MFC	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c42	pg346, fig9	F	2	LD	Lateroposterior, laterodorsal & posterior nuclear group displayed a large number of labeled neurons, only in their medial part, adjacent to external border of CL, wherever location of inj site was in MFC	PL/PL/ACA d	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
LD	RSP	3	3	20	vGr92b	PL111	pg433-4, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	RSPv-a	... axons were labeled in ... Rga. Labeled axons extended ventrally from {1} of Rgb & formed a small dense terminal field in {1} of rostral Rga	a
					vGr92	CFR30	pg202, fig2G,3A	F	3	LD	many neurons were labeled in the laterodorsal nucleus	RSPd	FB injection into mid rostrocaudal levels of Rdg	r
					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	3	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	RSPd	... labeled terminals primarily in ... Rdg. Most labeled axons ... formed a dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4} of rostral Rdg	a
					vGr92b	PL117	pg435-6, fig13	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	RSPd	... axons were labeled in ... Rdg. Most labeled axons... form a dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4} of the ventral half of caudal Rdg	a
					vGr92b	PL111	pg433, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	RSPd	... axons were labeled in ... Rdg. Most labeled axons formed a dense terminal plexus in {1,3,4} of dorsal Rdg & in {1,3,4} of adjacent visual cortex	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	29d	pg181, fig6	H	3	LD	Substantial numbers of labeled cells were found in LD, primarily within caudal 3/4 of nucleus in transition region between its dor.lat. and vent.med. sectors... Loose topographic pattern: LD(med&cau)->29d(ant), LD(>lat)->29d(pos) <Fig6: mod/den/den>	RSPd	Injections of HRP were placed at various rostrocaudal levels within the dorsal dysgranular subdivision of retrosplenial cortex (area 29d) in 10 cases. fig6 presents results of 2 cases with injections in anterior and posterior portions of 29d	r
					vGr92b	CFR22 3	pg431, fig8	F	3	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	RSPd	... labeled axons in ... Rdg. Most axons continued caudally (from IRcB) to terminate in ... Rdg where they formed a dense terminal field in {1,3,4}	a
					Thomp&Robert87b	29c	pg181, fig7	H	3	LD	After each injection of area 29c, labeled cells were found concentrated in the medial part of the nucleus. Loose topographic order LD(most ventral part of medial)->29c(rostral), LD(dorsal parts of medial)->29c(caudal) <Fig7: mod/dense>	RSPv-bc	9 injections of HRP were confined to various locations within the ventral granular retrosplenial cortex	r
					vGr92b	CFR22 3	pg431, fig8	F	3	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	RSPv-a	... labeled axons in ... Rga. More caudally (from 18b terminals), labeled axons formed a dense terminal field in {1} of the middle (ros.cau) part of Rga	a
					vGr90d	CF310	pg600, fig9, obs	F	3	LD	The rostral injection labeled neurons in the lateral and caudal part of the LD nucleus, but the caudal injection labeled a smaller number of neurons in the ant med region of LD. Discussion: Rga is primarily innervated by the AD & LD	RSPv-a	Injections of the retrograde tracers (FB/FG) into Rga	r
					vGr90d	PHA41	pg602	P	3	LD	Anterograde injections into LD nucleus (PHA-L?)	RSPv-a	labeled a dense terminal field in {1}	a
					vGr92	PL84	pg204	P	3	LD	injections into the LD nucleus	RSPd	dense terminal field in {1,3,4,5}	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					Sri&Wys86	CF270	pg155, fig11	F	3	LD	Most thalamic neurons that were brightly labeled in experiment CF270 were in the lateral dorsal nucleus, although they were slightly more numerous in the rostral 1/2	RSPd	The results in rat CF270 demonstrate the pattern of thalamic projections to the caudal Rgb cortex. The 20nl injection of FB was confined to Rgb approx 1mm caudal to the splenium of the corpus callosum	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF275	pg155, fig10	F	3	LD	The majority of brightly labeled thalamic neurons were located ventromedially in the caudal 2/3 of LD.	RSPd	In rat CF275 a 20nl FB injection was placed into Rgb at the same rostrocaudal position as the Rgb injection in CF213.	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF213	pg148, fig5	F	3	LD	Similarly <to AM> the labeled cells in LD were less heavily labeled than those in AD or AV, but a large number of labeled neurons were present in the caudal 2/3 of the nucleus. (nearly all in medial 1/2)	RSPv	a 50nl inj of FB was placed into the ant. retroplenial granular a & b cortex. The inj. extended up to but did not appear encroach on the corpus callosum or the deep white matter. extends approx 0.5-2.0mm cau to ant border of Rgb. No spill into agran RSP	r
					vGr92b	CFR22	pg431, fig8	F	3	LD	An injection of Fluoro-Ruby into the intermediate (rostrocaudal) part of LD	RSPv-bc	... labeled axons in ... Rgb. Most axons continued caudally (from IRcb) to terminate in the dorsal part of Rgb where they formed a dense terminal plexus in {1}.	a
					vGr92b	PHA41	pg430, fig7	P	3	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	RSPv	... axons were labeled in ... rostral Rga. A second group of labeled axons ran around the splenium of the cc to form a dense terminal field in {1} of the rostral half of Rga	a
					vGr92b	PL140	pg432, fig10	P	3	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediadorsal part of caudal LD	RSPv-bc	... axons were labeled in ... Rgb. Most axons continued caudally to the ventral part of Rgb, where they formed a dense terminal plexus in {1} & a smaller terminal field in {3,4}. Only a few axons & terminals were labeled in {1}, {3,4} of cau. Rgb	a
					vGr92b	PL111	pg433, fig12	P	3	LD	Following a small PHA-L injection into the dorsal part of caudal LD	RSPv-bc	... axons were labeled in ... Rgb. More caudally labeled axons formed a dense terminal field in the intermediate part of caudal Rgb, predominantly in {1} with a few axons terminating in {4}	a
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	3	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	RSPv	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... retrosplenial cortex. At the ros. end of Rgb labeled fibres left cingulum & terminated in Rgb & Rdg. In Rgb these axons ... terminated predominantly through {1} with few terms in {4}. Few terms in Rga	a
		2		10	Ch92	PPC17	pg239, fig3	F	2	LD	produced moderate labelling in LD	RSP	medial FG injection was entirely confined to retrosplenial cortex	r
					Ch92	PPC14	pg240, fig4	F	2	LD	produced labelled neurons in ... LD	RSP	a medial FG injection involved the retrosplenial cortex	r
					Fin84	c67	pg473, fig2, table1	W	2	LD	Several thalamic nuclei were labeled after injections into either the posterior or the anterior cingulate cortex. These included most notably the lateral nucleus of the thalamus also called the lateral dorsal nucleus)	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202, fig4	F	2	LD	labelled greater number of neurons in lateral and dorsal LD, <more than rostral inj: CFR163>	RSPd	FG injection into caudal Rdg	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF214	pg148, fig6	F	2	LD	LD likewise contained some faintly labeled neurons in CF214. These tended to be in the mediolateral center of the nucleus	RSPv-bc	In case CF214 a 40nl FB inj was placed in the Rgb cortex just posterior to the splenium of the corpus callosum and was confined to {1,2,3,4,5} of Rgb	r
					vGr92	CFR16	pg202, fig4	F	2	LD	labelled greater number of neurons in ventral and medial LD, <more than caudal inj: CFR164>	RSPd	FG injection into rostral Rdg	r
					vGr92b	PL127	pg433, fig11	P	2	LD	A small injection of PHA-L into the medioventral part of the caudal LD	RSPv	... labeled terminals primarily in ... Rgb, in the dorsalmost part of rostral Rgb, axons & terminals were labeled predominantly in {1} with a few labeled terminals in {4}	a
					vGr92b	PL140	pg433, fig10	P	2	LD	Following a small (PHA-L) injection into the most mediadorsal part of caudal LD	RSPv-a	... axons were labeled in ... Rga. Labeled terminals were also in {1,3,4} of the rostralmost part of Rga	a
					vGr92b	PL84	pg429, fig3,4	P	2	LD	The overall pattern of cortical projections from LD is best shown following a large PHA-L injection into the middle (ros.cau) part of LD.	RSPd	This injection resulted in terminal labeling in the ... retrosplenial cortex. At the ros. end of Rgb labeled fibres left cingulum & terminated in Rgb & Rdg. In Rdg, the axons terminated in layers in {1,3,4}	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
					vGr92b	PHA41	pg429, fig7	P	2	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the rostral tip of LD...	RSPd	... axons were labeled in ... caudal Rdg. The axons formed a terminal plexus in {1,3,4} in Rdg near the border of Rdg with area 18b	a
			1	3	vGr92b	PL117	pg436, fig13	P	1	LD	Following a small injection of PHA-L into the ventrolateral part of the caudal LD	RSPv-a	... axons were labeled in ... Rga. Caudally, labeled axons formed a sparse terminal plexus in the caudal part of Rga.	a
					Woolf84	t7b	table7	F	1	LD	laterodorsal nucleus of the thalamus, (10-25 somata in a 40µm thick section)	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r
					Horikawa88	c	pg37, fig1,3	F	1	LD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (LD,P29): FB (n=6): 7.4±5.2, RH (n=5): 0.0±0	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into posterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
			0	1	Horikawa88	b	pg37, fig1,3	F	0	LD	Table1, N{labeled in nuc}/N{total} as % : (LD,A29): FB (n=6): 66.7±13.1, RH (n=5): 10.5±3.9	RSP	Injs of FB or RH into cingulate gyrus... Injs into anterior 29. Inj foci of FB (d=1mm) were larger than those of RH (d=0.5mm). <Fig1 illustrates posns of inj sites but does not show size of typical inj>.	r
MD	ENT	3	3	1	Beren&Groen91	RP89358	pg82, fig6	P	3	IMD/IMD/MD	PHA-L was injected in the ... intermediodorsal nuc... bilaterally. <See fig 1 for examples of inj sites, but not for every case>. The diameter of the inj sites varies from 150 to 600µm. An inj of PHA-L in the IMD with minimal involvement of the MD.	ENTl	Dense labelling is found throughout {5} of the lateral entorhinal cortex.	a
MD	SUB	0	0	1	Beren&Groen91	RP86445	pg79	P	0	PVT/PVT/MD	An injection more caudally in the paraventricular nucleus which may involve the mediodorsal thalamic nucleus	SUB	Contrary to case RP86189 the subiculum remains free of labelling	a
MD	ACA	3	3	3	Groene88	lat-a	pg399, fig16,17	W	3	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	ACAd	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present in dense pattern in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate & in medial part of medial precentral cortex.	r
					Groene88	lat-a	pg399, fig16,17	W	3	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	ACA v	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present in dense pattern in dorsal & ventral anterior cingulate & in medial part of medial precentral cortex.	r
					Sri&Wys86	CF288a	pg159, fig14	F	3	MD	anterior cingulate injection labeled neurons primarily in mediodorsal nucleus.	ACA	Text: In CF288 anterior cingulate cortex & area 18b were injected with injected with 20nl of NY & 20nl of FB respectively. Fig14: 50nl NY inj into anterior cingulate cortex. <Inconsistency between fig14 & text>	r
			2	3	Ray92	R2755r	pg175,183, fig13	P	2	MDI	In 2755, injs ... indicate that cells projecting to ACd are restricted to dorsolateral segment & are dorsal to those that project to PrCm.	ACA	Data will be presented from R2755 which received, which received 3 cortical injections (... rhodamine labeled latex beads into ACd)	r
					Woolf84	t7a	pg767, table7	F	2	MD	anterior cingulate area received afferent fibres originating in somata in ... mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus, (50+ somata in a 40µm thick section)	ACA	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into anterior cingulate area	r
					Fin84	c74	pg471, fig4, table1	W	2	MD	the mediodorsal nucleus of the thalamus ... were labeled only after injections of the anterior cingulate cortex	ACA	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 24a,b amongst many other examples	r
			1	1	Conde90	c44	pg345, fig5-9	F	1	MDI	retrogradely labeled neurons found in lateral part of MD in all experiments. However, different gradients were found in distribution of these cells along rostro-caudal axis of the MDL	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
			0	5	Conde90	c44	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDm	medial part of MD exhibited retrogradely labeled neurons only when inj site centred on prelimbic area	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDc	central part of MD always devoid of retrogradely labeled neurons	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
					Conde90	c44	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDc	central part of MD always devoid of retrogradely labeled neurons	ACAd	In cases 47, & 44, zone 0 of inj centered in PrCm area & ACd area respectively.	r
					Ray92	R2755r	pg175,183, fig13	P	0	MDc/MDm	In 2755, injs ... indicate that cells projecting to ACd are restricted to dorsolateral segment & are dorsal to those that project to PrCm.	ACA	Data will be presented from R2755 which received, which received 3 cortical injections (... rhodamine labeled latex beads into ACd)	r

S	T	d	C	Nc	Reference	l	Case	M	A	Soma	Soma Notes	Terminals	Terminal Notes	T
					Sar84	m	pg447, fig1,2-4	F	0	MDc	MD shows inner (central) segment neurons labeled by inj into insular prefrontal cortex, whereas medial & lateral segments project to areas of medial prefrontal cortex. No cmediodorsal neurons at all were found	ACA/PL/IL/ORBm	All (NY/FB) injections into anterior medial cortex situated anterior to corpus callosum. Predominantly covered anterior 1/3 of dorsal division of anterior cingulate area, & prelimbic, the infralimbic & medial orbital area	r
				z 2	Vo81 Leo69	abstract abstract				MD MD		ACA ACA		
MD	ILA	3	3	1	Freed91	f4	pg961, fig4	F	3	MD	RHS of thalamus had many cells in Re & MDm & very few cells in parataenia, centromedial & rhomboid nuc. LHS had many cells in paracentral, centromedial, Re, rhomboid nuc. & throughout medlat extent of MD	ILA/ILA/ACA	In one IL injection, site on right side limited to layers 1 & 2 of IL, while left side also included deeper layers of IL as well as a small part of anterior cingulate cortex.	r
			2	1	Groene88	rh8168 -a	pg398, fig12,13	W	2	MDm/MDm /EPI/PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8168: inj site includes rostral MDm, PVT, slightly strtia medullaris	ILA	antero/retrograde labeling consistently present in dense pattern in prelimbic & ventral agranular insular area & less densely in infralimbic area & lateral & medial orbital regions.	a
			c	3	Freed91	f2A	pg960, fig2A	F	-1	MDm	Injections rarely limited to IL (5 cases) strongly labeled cells in reuniens, rhomboid, paraventricular, medial MD nuclei & sometimes labeled cells in parataenia nucleus	ILA	All IL inj (FB) included the dorsal peduncular cortex to varying degrees. Some also included nearby subcortical structures. Injs largely limited to IL (n=5)	r
					Sar84	1	pg447-8, fig1,2-4	F	-1	MDm	This injection resulted in a dense labeling of MD neurons, similar to that following injections which involved both the anterior cingulate and prelimbic areas... <ie: MDm & MDI >	ILA/ILA/ORBm	(FB) Injection R1 principally restricted to infralimbic area (but in addition slightly invaded medial orbital area).	r
					Sar84	1	pg447-8, fig1,2-4	F	-1	MDI	This injection resulted in a dense labeling of MD neurons, similar to that following injections which involved both the anterior cingulate and prelimbic areas... <ie: MDm & MDI >	ILA/ILA/ORBm	(FB) Injection R1 principally restricted to infralimbic area (but in addition slightly invaded medial orbital area).	r
			0	2	Conde90	c43	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDc	central part of MD always devoid of retrogradely labeled neurons	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Sar84	m	pg447, fig1,2-4	F	0	MDc	MD shows inner (central) segment neurons labeled by inj into insular prefrontal cortex, whereas medial & lateral segments project to areas of medial prefrontal cortex. No cmediodorsal neurons at all were found	ACA/PL/IL/ORBm	All (NY/FB) injections into anterior medial cortex situated anterior to corpus callosum. Predominantly covered anterior 1/3 of dorsal division of anterior cingulate area, & prelimbic, the infralimbic & medial orbital area	r
			x	1	Sar83	abstract				-1 MD		ILA		
MD	PL	3	3	7	Zen91	f5	pg293,5, fig5,6B	W	3	MDm	injs into Cg3 yielded dense fibres labeling and many cells in medial part of the mediodorsal thalamic nucleus & parataenia nucleus	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	r
					Ray92	R2431	pg175,180, fig9	P	3	MDm	Thalamic cells ... conc at med edge of MD throughout its length, they extend into other parts of nucleus ros & cau greatest conc of cells is in rostral 1/3 of MD, where they occupy antven as well as med parts. Cau: many of cells found in pos-dor part of MDm	PL	... cases also had injections of different retrograde tracers into areas that receive direct amygdalocortical projections, namely PL (R2431)...	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345, fig5-9	F	3	MDI	retrogradely labeled neurons found in lateral part of MD in all experiments. However, different gradients were found in distribution of these cells along rostro-caudal axis of the MDL	PL/PL/ACA d	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
					Conde90	c43	pg345, fig5-9	F	3	MDI	retrogradely labeled neurons found in lateral part of MD in all experiments. However, different gradients were found in distribution of these cells along rostro-caudal axis of the MDL	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c43	pg345, fig5-9	F	3	MDm	medial part of MD exhibited retrogradely labeled neurons only when inj site centred on prelimbic area	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345, fig5-9	F	3	MDm	medial part of MD exhibited retrogradely labeled neurons only when inj site centred on prelimbic area	PL/PL/ACA d	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
					Groene88	rh8168 -a	pg398, fig12,13	W	3	MDm/MDm /EPI/PVT	5 WGA-HRP injections in MD restricted to medial part & variably include habenula, stria medullaris & paraventricular nucleus. RH8168: inj site includes rostral MDm, PVT, slightly strtia medullaris	PL	antero/retrograde labeling consistently present in dense pattern in prelimbic & ventral agranular insular area & less densely in infralimbic area & lateral & medial orbital regions.	a

<i>S</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>d</i>	<i>C</i>	<i>Nc</i>	<i>Reference</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>A</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Soma Notes</i>	<i>Terminals</i>	<i>Terminal Notes</i>	<i>T</i>
			2	3	Ray92	R2431	pg175,180, fig9	P	2	MDc	Thalamic cells ... conc at med edge of MD throughout its length, they extend into other parts of nucleus ros & cau greatest conc of cells is in rostral 1/3 of MD, where they occupy antven as well as med parts. Cau: many of cells found in pos-dor part of MDm	PL	... cases also had injections of different retrograde tracers into areas that receive direct amygdalocortical projections, namely PL (R2431)...	r
					Ray92	R2431	pg175,180, fig9	P	2	MDI	Thalamic cells ... conc at med edge of MD throughout its length, they extend into other parts of nucleus ros & cau greatest conc of cells is in rostral 1/3 of MD, where they occupy antven as well as med parts. Cau: many of cells found in pos-dor part of MDm	PL	... cases also had injections of different retrograde tracers into areas that receive direct amygdalocortical projections, namely PL (R2431)...	r
					Beren&Groen91	RP893 58	pg82, fig6	P	2	IMD/IMD/MD	PHA-L was injected in the ... intermediodorsal nuc...bilaterally. <See fig 1 for examples of inj sites, but not for every case>. The diameter of the inj sites varies from 150 to 600µm. An inj of PHA-L in the IMD with minimal involvement of the MD.	PL	In the medial prefrontal cortex, labelled fibres are limited to the rostroventral part of the prelimbic cortex involving {1,3,5}	a
			1	1	Groene88	lat-a	pg399, fig16,17	W	1	MDI	3 injections of HRP or WGA-HRP mainly involve the lateral part of MD and variably include the lateral habenula & the central lateral nucleus.	PL	In all 3 cases anter/retrograde label in prefrontal cortex consistently present ... sparse labeling marks prelimbic, ventral agranular insular & ventrolateral orbital areas	r
			c	1	Zen91	f5	pg293,5, fig5,6B	W	-1	MDm	injs into Cg3 yielded dense fibres labeling and many cells in medial part of the mediiodorsal thalamic nucleus & paranaenial nucis	PL	Each of Cg3 area WGA-HRP injections covered entire Cg3 area & spread to dorsal edge of infralimbic area.	a
			0	3	Conde90	c43	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDc	central part of MD always devoid of retrogradely labeled neurons	PL/PL/ILA	In case 43, TB inj centered in rostral & ventral part of PL area but might have involved dorsal part of infralimbic area	r
					Conde90	c42	pg345, fig5-9	F	0	MDc	central part of MD always devoid of retrogradely labeled neurons	PL/PL/ACAd	In case 42, zone 0 of DY inj centered in PL area but might extend to ventral part of ACd area	r
					Sar84	m	pg447, fig1,2-4	F	0	MDc	MD shows inner (central) segment neuronslabeled by injs into insular prefrontal cortex, whereas medial & lateral segments project to areas of medial prefrontal cortex. No cmediodorsal neurons at all were found	ACAAd/PL/ILA/ORBm	All (NY/FB) injections into anterior medial cortex situated anterior to corpus callosum. Predominantly covered anterior 1/3 of dorsal division of anterior cingulate area, & prelimbic, the infralimbic & medial orbital area	r
			x	1	Sar83	abstract			-1	MD		PL		
			z	1	Leo69	abstract				MD		PL		
MD	PRh	1	1	1	Beren&Groen91	RP893 58	pg82, fig6	P	1	IMD/IMD/MD	PHA-L was injected in the ... intermediodorsal nuc...bilaterally. <See fig 1 for examples of inj sites, but not for every case>. The diameter of the inj sites varies from 150 to 600µm. An inj of PHA-L in the IMD with minimal involvement of the MD.	PRh	A few labelled fibres terminate in layers {1,5} of the ventral part of the PRh	a
MD	RSP	1	1	1	Sri&Wys86	CF213	pg148, fig5	F	1	MDI	Labeled cells were also present in the midline, dorsal ventro-anterolateral and intralaminar nuclei as shown in fig5 <fig5d,e,f,g,h: very light labeling restricted to MDI>	RSPv	a 50nl inj of FB was placed into the ant. retroplenial granular a & b cortex. The inj. extended up to but did not appear encroach on the corpus callosum or the deep white matter. extends approx 0.5-2.0mm cau to ant border of Rgb. No spill into agran RSP	r
			0	3	Fin84	c67	pg471, fig2, table1	W	0	MD	the mediiodorsal nucleus of the thalamus ... were labeled only after injections of the anterior cingulate cortex	RSP	From Table1: WGA-HRP inj site: 29cd, amongst many other examples	r
					Thomp&Robert87b	29d	pg181, fig6	H	0	MD	No labeled cells were seen in MD	RSPd	Injections of HRP were placed at various rostrocaudal levels within the dorsal dysgranular subdivision of retrosplenial cortex (area 29d) in 10 cases. fig6 presents results of 2 cases with injections in anterior and posterior portions of 29d	r
					Woolf84	t7b	pg767, table7	F	0	MD	mediiodorsal nucleus of the thalamus... these regions could not be demonstrated to project to posterior cingulate cortex	RSP	fluorescent tracer injections (30% solution of Evans Blue, 20% solution of Propidium iodide.) into posterior cingulate area	r

Appendix D : A Comparison Table For Retinal Efferents.

This table shows the comparisons that act as constraints in the connection weight estimation analysis in Section 4.6.1 for first stage retinal efferents. The left-hand side of the table describes the comparison and the right-hand side shows the data that supports it.

S_1	T_1	CODE	S_2	T_2	Paper	l	Case	M	λ	Soma	Terminal	Type
R	MT	>	R	DT	Kos71	a	pg202,4, fig4	L	3	R	MT	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	DT	a
R	MT	>	R	LT	Kos71	a	pg202,4, fig4	L	3	R	MT	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	LT	a
R	PRT	>?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	0	R	ICc	a
R	PRT	>=?	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	NOT	=?s	R	AOS	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	NOT	>=?	R	MT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	OP	=?s	R	AOS	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	OP	>=?	R	MT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	PPT	<?	R	DT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	PPT	<?	R	LT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	PPT	<?	R	MT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	PPT	<	R	NOT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	PPT	<	R	OP	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	SC	>?	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SC	>s	R	AOS	Quantitative	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3.03	R	SCs	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	SC	>	R	MT	Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	3	R	SC	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	SC	>	R	PRT	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	SCi	>=?	R	ICe	Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	SCi	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCi	<?s	R	AOS	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	SCi	<?	R	DT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	SCi	<?	R	LT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	SCi	<?	R	MT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	SCi	<s	R	PRT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	SCi	<	R	NOT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	SCi	<	R	OP	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	SCi	<	R	PPT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
R	SCs	>?s	R	IC	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCs	>?	R	ICe	Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	SCs	a
					Ita82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCs	>s	R	AOS	Quantitative	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3.03	R	SCs	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	SCs	>	R	MT	Quantitative	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3.03	R	SCs	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	SCs	>	R	PPT	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a

<i>S₁</i>	<i>T₁</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>S₂</i>	<i>T₂</i>	<i>Paper</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Terminal</i>	<i>Type</i>
R	SCs	>	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	SCs	>s	R	SCig	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	SCop	>?s	R	IC	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCop	>?	R	ICe	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCop	>=?	R	PRT	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	SCop	>s	R	SCi	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	SCop	>	R	SCig	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	SCsg	>?s	R	IC	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCsg	>?	R	ICe	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	SCsg	>=?	R	PRT	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	SCsg	>s	R	SCi	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	SCsg	>	R	SCig	Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	MEA	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	MEA	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	CSTR	<?	R	PRT	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	CSTR	<?	R	SC	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	CSTR	<=?	R	MEA	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	AOS	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	DT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	LT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	MT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LZ	<s	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	NOT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	OP	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	PPT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	LZ	<s	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	LZ	=?s	R	SCi	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LZ	<?s	R	SCs	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	LZ	=s	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	LZ	>s	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	LHA	<?s	R	AOS	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LHA	<?	R	DT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	LHA	<?	R	LT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	LHA	<?	R	MT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LHA	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	LHA	<?	R	NOT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	LHA	<?	R	OP	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	LHA	<?	R	PPT	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	LHA	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	LHA	<?	R	SCs	Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	LHA	>	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	AHA	<?s	R	AOS	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	AHA	<?	R	DT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	AHA	<?	R	LT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	AHA	<?	R	MT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	AHA	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a

<i>S₁</i>	<i>T₁</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>S₂</i>	<i>T₂</i>	<i>Paper</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Terminal</i>	<i>Type</i>
R	AHA	<?	R	NOT	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	AHA	<?	R	OP	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	AHA	<?	R	PPT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	AHA	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	AHA	<?	R	SCs	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	AHA	>=	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	AHA	>	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	AHA	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	AHA	=s	R	LZ	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	AHA	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
R	AHA	>=	R	LHA	Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	AHNa	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	AHNa	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	AHNa	>=?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	AHNa	=s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	MPO	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	MPO	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	MPO	>=?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	MPO	=s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	MPO	<=	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	MPN	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	MPN	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	MPN	>=?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	MPN	=s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	MPN	<=	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	RCH	<?s	R	AOS	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	RCH	<?	R	DT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	RCH	<?	R	LT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	RCH	<?	R	MT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	RCH	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	RCH	<?	R	NOT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	RCH	<?	R	OP	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	RCH	<?	R	PPT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	RCH	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	RCH	<?	R	SCs	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	RCH	>	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	RCH	>	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	RCH	C	R	LZ	Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
R	RCH	>	R	LHA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	RCH	>=	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	RCH	>	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	RCH	>	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	RCH	>	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	SBPV	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	SBPV	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	SBPV	>	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	SBPV	<	R	AHA	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	SBPV	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	AHA	a

S_1	T_1	CODE	S_2	T_2	Paper	l	Case	M	λ	Soma	Terminal	Type
R	SBPV	>	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	SBPV	>	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	SBPV	>	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	SBPV	<	R	RCH	Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	SBPV	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	SCH	=?s	R	AOS	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	DT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	LT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	MT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	SCH	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	NOT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	OP	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	SCH	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	SCH	>?	R	SCi	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	SCH	<=?	R	SCs	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	SCH	>	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	SCH	>	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	SCH	>s	R	LZ	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
R	SCH	>	R	LHA	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
R	SCH	>	R	AHA	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	AHA	a
R	SCH	>	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	SCH	>	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	SCH	>	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	SCH	>	R	RCH	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	SCH	>	R	SBPV	Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	SBPV	a
R	PV	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	PV	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	PV	>=?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	PV	=s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	PV	<=	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	PV	<	R	RCH	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	PV	<	R	SBPV	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
R	PV	<	R	SCH	Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	PVH	<?s	R	AOS	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	PVH	<?	R	DT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	PVH	<?	R	LT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	PVH	<?	R	MT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	PVH	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	PVH	<?	R	NOT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	PVH	<?	R	OP	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	PVH	<?	R	PPT	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	PVH	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	PVH	<?	R	SCs	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	PVH	>=	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	PVH	>?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	PVH	=s	R	LZ	Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	PVH	>=	R	LHA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a

<i>S₁</i>	<i>T₁</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>S₂</i>	<i>T₂</i>	<i>Paper</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Terminal</i>	<i>Type</i>
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	PVH	≥	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	PVH	≥	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	PVH	≥	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	PVH	≤	R	RCH	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	PVH	≤	R	SBPV	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
R	PVH	<	R	SCH	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	PVH	≥	R	PV	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
					Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
R	SO	↔s	R	AOS	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Fall84	a	pg355, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	SO	<?	R	DT	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	SO	<?	R	LT	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	SO	<?	R	MT	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Fall84	a	pg355, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	SO	<	R	PRT	Levine91	a	pg351, fig6b	C	1	R	SO	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	PRT	a
R	SO	<?	R	NOT	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	SO	<?	R	OP	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	SO	<?	R	PPT	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Scal&Aran79	a	pg276-77, fig1,2,3	A	3	R	PPT	a
R	SO	<	R	SC	Levine91	a	pg351, fig6b	C	1	R	SO	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	SC	a
R	SO	<?	R	SCs	Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	SO	>	R	CSTR	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	SO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	SO	<	R	LHA	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	SO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig16	C	2	R	LHA	a
R	SO	<	R	AHA	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	SO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	AHA	a
R	SO	<	R	RCH	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	SO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308, fig12,15	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	SO	<	R	SCH	Johnson88	a	pg307, fig12	C	1	R	SO	a
					Johnson88	a	pg307-308, fig12	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	BST	=?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	BST	<	R	PRT	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	BST	<	R	SC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
R	BST	<=?	R	SCi	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	SCi	a
R	BST	<?	R	SCs	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	SCs	a
R	BST	<?	R	SCop	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
R	BST	<?	R	SCsg	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
R	BST	>=?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	BST	=s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	BST	≤	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	BST	<	R	RCH	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	BST	<	R	SBPV	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
R	BST	<	R	SCH	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fi3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	BST	≤	R	PVH	Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1	R	BST	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
R	AD	=?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	AD	<	R	PRT	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	AD	<	R	SC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
R	AD	<=?	R	SCi	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	SCi	a
R	AD	<?	R	SCs	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	SCs	a
R	AD	<?	R	SCop	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
R	AD	<?	R	SCsg	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
R	AV	=?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	AV	<	R	PRT	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a

<i>S₁</i>	<i>T₁</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>S₂</i>	<i>T₂</i>	<i>Paper</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	λ	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Terminal</i>	<i>Type</i>
R	AV	<	R	SC	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
R	AV	<=?	R	SCi	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	SCi	a
R	AV	<?	R	SCs	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Serf&Lind91	a	pg11, fig3,4A	H	3	R	SCs	a
R	AV	<?	R	SCop	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
R	AV	<?	R	SCsg	Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
R	LG	>?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LG	>?s	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LG	>s	R	AOS	Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	LG	>	R	MT	Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	3	R	LG	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	LG	>s	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGd	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LG	>?s	R	SCig	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	LG	=?s	R	SCop	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
R	LG	=?s	R	SCsg	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
R	LG	>s	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	LG	>?s	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	LG	>s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	LG	>s	R	LHA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	LG	>s	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	LG	>s	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	LG	>s	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	LG	>s	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	LG	>s	R	RCH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	LG	>s	R	SBPV	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
R	LG	>s	R	SCH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fig3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	LG	>s	R	PV	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
R	LG	>s	R	PVH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
R	LG	>s	R	SO	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351, fig6b	C	1	R	SO	a
R	LG	>s	R	BST	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
R	LG	>s	R	AD	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
R	LG	>s	R	AV	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
R	LGd	>?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LGd	>?	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LGd	>s	R	AOS	Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	LGd	>	R	MT	Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	LGd	>	R	PRT	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	LGd	>	R	PPT	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGd	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
R	LGd	<	R	SC	Dre85	a	pg30, fig9D	H	3.01	R	LGd	r
					Dre85	a	pg30, fig9C	H	3.02	R	SC	r
R	LGd	>	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGd	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LGd	>?	R	SCig	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	LGd	<	R	SCs	Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
					Quantitative	a	qv: Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3.03	R	SCs	r
R	LGd	>	R	MEA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352-3, fig7	C	1	R	MEA	a
R	LGd	>?	R	CSTR	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Johnson88	a	pg308	C	0	R	CSTR	a
R	LGd	>s	R	LZ	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a
R	LGd	>	R	LHA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351,352	C	1	R	LHA	a

<i>S₁</i>	<i>T₁</i>	<i>CODE</i>	<i>S₂</i>	<i>T₂</i>	<i>Paper</i>	<i>l</i>	<i>Case</i>	<i>M</i>	<i>λ</i>	<i>Soma</i>	<i>Terminal</i>	<i>Type</i>
R	LGd	>	R	AHA	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,350, fig3k-p	C	1.5	R	AHA	a
R	LGd	>	R	AHNa	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg352	C	1	R	AHNa	a
R	LGd	>	R	MPO	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5d-f	C	1	R	MPO	a
R	LGd	>	R	MPN	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349, fig5a-f	C	1	R	MPN	a
R	LGd	>	R	RCH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig3k	C	2	R	RCH	a
R	LGd	>	R	SBPV	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	2	R	SBPV	a
R	LGd	>	R	SCH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348,349-50, fig3,6	C	3	R	SCH	a
R	LGd	>	R	PV	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg350, fig3e	C	1	R	PV	a
R	LGd	>	R	PVH	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg348, fig2	C	1.5	R	PVH	a
R	LGd	>	R	SO	Levine91	a	pg352	C	3.01	R	LGd	a
					Levine91	a	pg351, fig6b	C	1	R	SO	a
R	LGd	>	R	BST	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
R	LGd	>	R	AD	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
R	LGd	>	R	AV	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGd	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
R	LP	C	R	IC	Perr82	a	pg587, fig2	H	1	R	LP	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LP	>=?	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LP	<s	R	AOS	Quantitative	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	LP	a
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	LP	<?	R	DT	Hay62	a	text	L	0	R	LP	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	DT	a
R	LP	<?	R	LT	Hay62	a	text	L	0	R	LP	a
					Kos71	a	pg202,6, fig4	L	2	R	LT	a
R	LP	<	R	MT	Quantitative	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	LP	a
					Quantitative	a	qv: Dann87, pg145, fig3,4	x	3.01	R	MT	r
R	LP	<	R	SC	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	SC	a
R	LP	<=?	R	SCi	Perr82	a	pg587, fig2	H	1	R	LP	a
					Be83	b	pg264, fig4	H	2	R	SCi	a
R	LP	<	R	SCs	Quantitative	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	LP	a
					Quantitative	a	qv Lind83a, pg146-7	x	3.03	R	SCs	r
R	LP	<?	R	SCop	Perr82	a	pg587, fig2	H	1	R	LP	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCop	a
R	LP	<?	R	SCsg	Perr82	a	pg587, fig2	H	1	R	LP	a
					Be83	a	fig4	H	3	R	SCsg	a
R	LP	>	R	BST	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
R	LP	>	R	AD	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
R	LP	>	R	AV	Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
R	LP	<s	R	LG	Quantitative	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	LP	a
					Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
R	LP	<	R	LGd	Quantitative	a	qv: Perr82, fig2	x	1	R	LP	a
					Quantitative	a	qv: Mart86, DLG1	x	3.02	R	LGd	r
R	LGv	>?s	R	IC	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LGv	>?	R	ICe	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					It82a	a	pg45-8, fig1,2	H	1	R	ICe	a
R	LGv	>	R	PRT	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	PRT	a
R	LGv	>s	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LGv	>?	R	SCig	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Be83	a	pg264, fig4	H	1.5	R	SCig	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	LZ	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	LHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	AHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	RCH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	PVH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
R	LGv	>?s	R	SO	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
R	LGv	>	R	BST	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	BST	a
R	LGv	>	R	AD	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AD	a
R	LGv	>	R	AV	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Ita81	a	pg35, fig3	H	1	R	AV	a
R	LGv	>	R	LP	Ita81	a	fig2	H	3	R	LGv	a
					Ita81	a	fig2	H	2	R	LP	a
R	LGvl	=?s	R	AOS	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a

S_1	T_1	CODE	S_2	T_2	Paper	l	Case	M	λ	Soma	Terminal	Type
R	LGvl	>=?	R	MT	Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	b	pg4, table1	A	2	R	MT	a
R	LGvl	>	R	PPT	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	1	R	PPT	a
R	LGvl	>	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LGvl	>?s	R	LZ	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGvl	>?	R	LHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGvl	>?	R	AHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
R	LGvl	>?	R	RCH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
R	LGvl	>=?	R	SCH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
R	LGvl	>?	R	PVH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
R	LGvl	>?	R	SO	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a
					Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
R	LGvm	<?s	R	AOS	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LGvm	<?	R	DT	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig3b	A	3	R	DT	a
R	LGvm	<?	R	LT	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Wree83	a	pg23, fig2b	A	3	R	LT	a
R	LGvm	<?	R	MT	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Fall84	a	pg335, fig3GH	A	3	R	MT	a
R	LGvm	<	R	NOT	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	NOT	a
R	LGvm	<	R	OP	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	OP	a
R	LGvm	>	R	SCi	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	0	R	SCi	a
R	LGvm	<	R	SCs	Perr79	a	pg98, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Perr79	a	pg100, fig1	A	3	R	SCs	a
R	LGvm	>=?s	R	LZ	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGvm	>=?	R	LHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Mai79b	a	pg373-4	A	0	R	LHA	a
R	LGvm	>=?	R	AHA	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	AHA	a
R	LGvm	>=?	R	RCH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	RCH	a
R	LGvm	<=?	R	SCH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	2	R	SCH	a
R	LGvm	>=?	R	PVH	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Moo72	a	pg3, fig1	A	0	R	PVH	a
R	LGvm	>=?	R	SO	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Moo72	a	pg4, fig5	A	0	R	SO	a
R	LGvm	<	R	LGd	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGd	a
R	LGvm	<	R	IGL	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Hick76	a	pg527-8, fig1,2	A	3	R	IGL	a
R	LGvm	<	R	LGvl	Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	1	R	LGvm	a
					Hick76	a	pg524, fig1	A	3	R	LGvl	a

Appendix E : Stress Values

The following table contains the cost function scores for the main NMDS analyses contained in the thesis. The abbreviations ‘N₁’, ‘P₁’, ‘T₁’, ‘W₁’, ‘N₂’, ‘P₂’, ‘T₂’, ‘W₂’, ‘N₃’, ‘P₃’, ‘T₃’ and ‘W₃’ refer to the matrices described in the text of the thesis in Section 4.3.2, Section 4.8.2, and Section 5.2.1.

Connection Matrix	Cost Function	Tied or Untied ?	Cost Function for 2 dimensional configuration	Cost Function for 5 dimensional configuration
N ₁	S ^(0.5)	t	0.21	0.1
N ₁	S ^(0.5)	u	0.06	0.02
N ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.36	0.19
N ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.08	0.03
N ₁	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.52	0.33
N ₁	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.07	0.04
P ₁	S ^(0.5)	t	0.17	0.09
P ₁	S ^(0.5)	u	0.11	0.07
P ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.29	0.17
P ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.11	0.1
P ₁	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.41	0.27
P ₁	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.07	0.07
T ₁	S ^(0.5)	t	0.19	0.08
T ₁	S ^(0.5)	u	0.07	0.02
T ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.34	0.16
T ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.09	0.03
T ₁	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.49	0.29
T ₁	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.09	0.04
W ₁	S ^(0.5)	t	0.11	0.04
W ₁	S ^(0.5)	u	0.11	0.04
W ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.17	0.08
W ₁	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.17	0.08
W ₁	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.21	0.12
W ₁	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.21	0.11
N ₂	S ^(0.5)	t	0.2	0.09
N ₂	S ^(0.5)	u	0.08	0.03
N ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.35	0.17
N ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.12	0.05
N ₂	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.51	0.31
N ₂	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.11	0.05
P ₂	S ^(0.5)	t	0.19	0.09
P ₂	S ^(0.5)	u	0.17	0.08
P ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.34	0.18
P ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.31	0.16
P ₂	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.5	0.3
P ₂	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.46	0.27
T ₂	S ^(0.5)	t	0.17	0.07
T ₂	S ^(0.5)	u	0.09	0.02
T ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.31	0.14
T ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.14	0.04
T ₂	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.45	0.24
T ₂	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.12	0.05
W ₂	S ^(0.5)	t	0.11	0.04
W ₂	S ^(0.5)	u	0.11	0.04
W ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.2	0.07
W ₂	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.2	0.07
W ₂	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.28	0.11
W ₂	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.27	0.11
N ₃	S ^(0.5)	t	0.18	0.08
N ₃	S ^(0.5)	u	0.1	0.04
N ₃	S ⁽¹⁾	t	0.33	0.16
N ₃	S ⁽¹⁾	u	0.16	0.06
N ₃	S ⁽²⁾	t	0.49	0.29
N ₃	S ⁽²⁾	u	0.15	0.09

P_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	t	0.18	0.08
P_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	u	0.16	0.07
P_3	$S^{(1)}$	t	0.32	0.16
P_3	$S^{(1)}$	u	0.28	0.13
P_3	$S^{(2)}$	t	0.48	0.29
P_3	$S^{(2)}$	u	0.42	0.24
T_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	t	0.16	0.06
T_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	u	0.11	0.02
T_3	$S^{(1)}$	t	0.28	0.12
T_3	$S^{(1)}$	u	0.15	0.05
T_3	$S^{(2)}$	t	0.43	0.21
T_3	$S^{(2)}$	u	0.16	0.07
W_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	t	0.08	0.02
W_3	$S^{(0.5)}$	u	0.08	0.02
W_3	$S^{(1)}$	t	0.14	0.05
W_3	$S^{(1)}$	u	0.14	0.05
W_3	$S^{(2)}$	t	0.17	0.07
W_3	$S^{(2)}$	u	0.17	0.07
